

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

**“THE SELF-REVIEW STORIES OF SEVEN FIRST-TAKER BOARD PASSERS IN THE
PHILIPPINE NURSING LICENSURE EXAMINATION (P.N.L.E.):
A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY”**

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the Faculty of Graduate School of
ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA

In Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Arts in Nursing
(M.A.N.)

Major in **Academic Management**

NERISON M. OCAMPO, R.N.

MAY 2015

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
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APPROVAL SHEET

The thesis entitled **“THE SELF-REVIEW STORIES OF SEVEN FIRST-TAKER BOARD PASSERS IN THE PHILIPPINE NURSING LICENSURE EXAMINATION (P.N.L.E.): A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY”** prepared and submitted by **Nerison M. Ocampo, R.N.** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Master of Arts in Nursing major in Academic Management**, has been examined and recommended for acceptance and approval for oral examination.

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CERTIFICATE OF ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that this research paper is my work and does not contain any material previously published or written by another person or material which to a substantial extent has been accepted for any award of any degree or diploma in *St. Paul University-Manila*, and other educational institution, except where due acknowledgment is made in the thesis. Any contribution made to the research by others, with whom I have worked at *St. Paul University-Manila* or elsewhere, is explicitly acknowledged in the thesis.

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Date: March 25, 2015

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ENGLISH EDITING CERTIFICATION FORM

This is to certify that I have edited the final draft of this Thesis entitled

**"THE SELF-REVIEW STORIES OF SEVEN FIRST-TAKER BOARD PASSERS IN THE
PHILIPPINE NURSING LICENSURE EXAMINATION (P.N.L.E.):
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Prepared by:

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Master of Arts in Nursing (M.A.N) major in Academic Management

and have found it complete and satisfactory with respect to grammar,
organization, and APA format and style as prescribed by the
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"To the generous mind the heaviest debt is that of gratitude, when it is not in our power to repay it."

~Benjamin Franklin

Today I celebrate...my shared victory with the people who helped shape this thesis. All those countless and sleepless nights and days that I have spent in my room, in coffee shops, at various parks, under the trees, and in all those shades of places, I say they now have served their full purpose. As my masteral days draw to a close, I would like to set the stage by expressing my immense gratitude to all those people who have given their invaluable support, inspiration, encouragement, and assistance.

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not finish this thesis, I would have been a ‘total disappointment’. Indeed, to get to meet fellow self-reviewees who did what I once did—was a rare privilege. Unfortunately, to maintain anonymity, I am not able to mention you by name. Let it be known, however, that this thesis in the end was about You.

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Last and certainly not the least, to Almighty God – the owner of everything.

Although this study is now complete, I hope that this has opened even just a small window, if cannot be a door, for others to continue my work and gain a better understanding of the personal backgrounds, experiences, review strategies, and traits of self-reviewees!

Notwithstanding all the help received, and my good intentions lodged, any errors and/or shortcomings that may be found in this piece of work are ‘solely’-mine.

~N.M.O. (May 2015)

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Dedication

This humble piece is passionately dedicated to the memory of our grandfather and
my first teacher:

Mr. Florencio Belleza Malquisto

In the absence of a father, you were my foundation.

ABSTRACT

This research presents for the first time, the untold review stories of seven self-reviewees who passed the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.) on their first take. Despite the low passing percentage in the P.N.L.E. in the past decade, the study sought to answer possible reasons why some nurses conduct self-review, what did they do to pass, and most importantly, how did they do it. A multiple explanatory and exploratory case study was used to reveal the answers of the participants to those questions. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following: 1.) What review strategies and techniques, if any, helped them pass the P.N.L.E.? 2.) What personal traits did these self-reviewees possess which helped them pass the P.N.L.E.? and 3.) What could be the marks of a P.N.L.E. self-reviewee board passer? The self-review stories of these seven board passers (and four additional who answered an email survey questionnaire for triangulation) were analyzed through within and cross case analyses. Fourteen self-review strategies emerged and seven self-review flow charts were culled from the analyses of the responses. As to the self-reported traits, self-confidence, self-discipline and determination to pass and finish the review were present in most of the participants.

A discussion of the implications to the nursing licensure, their pedagogical implications to nursing education, and areas for further study are then presented. The study closes with a document titled "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer",

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

developed out of the case participants' stories, highlighting their review strategies, practical tips, and lessons learned to guide future self-reviewees in the P.N.L.E.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

<u>Topic</u>	<u>Page</u>
TITLE PAGE	i
APPROVAL SHEET	ii
CERTIFICATE OF ORIGINALITY	iii
ENGLISH EDITING CERTIFICATION FORM	iv
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	v
DEDICATION	vii
ABSTRACT	ix
TABLE OF CONTENTS	xi
LIST OF TABLES	xv
LIST OF FIGURES AND ILLUSTRATIONS	xvi
1. THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND	
Introduction	1
Purpose of the Study	3
Statement of the Problem	5
Framework of the Study	5
Assumptions of the Study	8
Scope and Delimitation of the Study	9
Significance of the Study	10
Review of Related Literature	13
• The Nursing Licensure Examination	14
• A Look at the Recent Years	17
• Predictors of Nursing Licensure Success	22
• Study/Review Strategies	26
• Learning & Learning Styles	35
• Personality and Learning	39
Synthesis	44
Operational Definition of Terms	46
2. CASE STUDY PROTOCOL	
Research Design	49
Research Approach	50
Research Locale	51
Case Participants	52
• Selection of Case Participants	52
• The Search for Case Participants	56

• The Seven Case Participants	58
○ Mr. NurseR	60
○ Mr. NurseN	63
○ Ms. NurseG	65
○ Ms. NurseE	67
○ Mr. NurseJ	71
○ Mr. NurseB	75
○ Mr. NurseO	77
Sources of Evidence	81
• Sources of Evidence in a Case Study Design	82
• Justification of Sources of Evidence Used	82
• Access to Participants and Availability of Archival Documents: A situationer	83
• Source #01: Interviews	85
• Source #02: Email as a Research Tool	89
• Survey-Questionnaire informants	92
○ Ms. NurseL	92
○ Mr. NurseMJ	93
○ Mr. NurseMM	93
○ Ms. NurseK	94
• Source #03: Documents/Archives	96
• Source #04: Participant Observation	97
Data Collection Procedure	99
Ethical Consideration	105
Data Analysis Procedure	106
• On the Issue of Validity and Reliability	109
3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	120
The Participants' Tailor Fit Self-review Strategies	120
• Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach	120
• Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach	125
• Ms. NurseG's "The Combo Approach" a.k.a. "The Vacant Room"	128
• Ms. NurseE's "Textbook Approach	131
• Mr. NurseJ's "Recalling Approach"	134
• Mr. NurseB's "Traditional Q & A Approach"	136
• Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach	138
Case Study Findings, Interpretations, and Discussion	142
Fourteen Self-review Strategies	142

• 1.a - Conduct a Self-Analysis.	142
• 1.b - Pick a strategy that best fits your learning style and study needs	143
• 1.c - Prioritize and manage your weak areas first	145
• 1.d - Organize your topics to review.	146
• 1.e - Tailor the review duration and frequency based On individual review needs	148
• 1.f - Find your right venue	153
• 1.h -Maximize help from other people and exhaust available resources	155
• 1.i - Watch out for FAQs and emerging health issues.	157
• 1.J - Be Inclusive, comprehensive, and integrate other topics when reviewing	159
• 1.k - Execute the strategy precisely, but be flexible to contain shortcomings	161
• 1.l - Incorporate test-taking and review strategies	163
• 1.m - Implement quality control measures	168
• 1. n – Ward off your worries.	171
Participants' Self-reported traits	173
• 2.a - Self-confidence	175
• 2. b - Self-discipline.	177
• 2.c - Determination	179
• 2.d – Other traits noted	181
Discussion	183
4. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Summary	208
Conclusions	218
Recommendations	220
Implications	225
REFERENCES	232
APPENDICES	
A –Data Matrices/Verbatim Responses as Used in the Findings of the Study	264
1. Participants' Self-Review Strategies	264

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

2. Case Participant's Self-Reported Traits	291
B - Other Findings	298
1. Self-Review Reasons	298
2. Common Themes among Participants' Personal and Educational Background	311
3. Common Themes among Participants' Self-Review Experience	316
C - Letter of Request to the Institutional Head	322
D - The Survey Questionnaire/Interview Guide	324
E - Sample Informed Consent	329
F - Interview Transcripts and Survey Questionnaires' Answers	334
• Mr. NurseR's	334
• Mr. NurseN	369
• Ms. NurseE	402
• Mr. NurseB	458
• Ms. NurseG	492
• Mr. NurseJ	524
• Mr. NurseO	562
• Ms. NurseK	590
• Ms. NurseL	601
• Mr. NurseMM	609
• Mr. NurseMJ	615
G - Practical Output: "Marks of a Successful Self-reviewee"	617
CURRICULUM VITAE	651

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Foreign Studies on Academic Predictors	25
Table 2: Filipino Studies on Academic Predictors	26
Table 3: Participant Demographics	59
Table 4: Participant Reference Codes	105
Table 4: List of case participants who had circumstantial self-review reasons	144
Table 5: Self-review strategies as tailor-fit to reviewees' learning Style and study needs	
Table 6: List of case participants who had circumstantial Self-review reasons	299
Table 7: List of case participants who had preferential self-review reasons	304

LIST OF FIGURES AND ILLUSTRATIONS

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework	7
Figure 2: Comparison between the Number of Examinees vs. N.L.E. passers	18
Figure 3: Passing Percentage from the year 2003-2013	19
Figure 4: Total Number of N.L.E. Passers vs. Total No. of N.L.E. Examinees (2003-2013)	19
Figure 5: Comparison between No. of Examinees vs. No. of Passers per Month/Batch of the Year (2003-2013)	20
Figure 6: School Distribution of Scouted Participants/Informants	60
Figure 7: Data Collection Procedure Diagram	101
Figure 8: Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach	124
Figure 9: Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach	128
Figure 10: Ms. NurseG's Vacant Space: the Combo Approach	129
Figure 11: Ms. NurseE's Textbook Approach	132
Figure 12: Mr. NurseJ's Recalling Approach	135
Figure 13: Mr. NurseB's "Traditional Q & A Approach"	137
Figure 14: Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach	140
Figure 15: The participants self-reported traits	174
Figure 16: Circumstantial Self-review Reasons	299
Figure 17: Preferential Self-review Reasons	304

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Arguably, the culmination of all the exams that an aspirant nurse has to take here in the Philippines is the Nursing Licensure Examination (N.L.E.). For the many of them who took the board exam, and may even for those who have not taken it yet—it is the end-point examination which determines whether or not an aspirant nurse is entitled to practice as a registered nurse here in the Philippines and like any major examination, no one surely holds the outcome.

No matter how they ignore it, there is always that big question of uncertainty and nerve regarding the possibility that, “what if I fail?”. At any rate, in the words of one of the participants in this study, the message to him was clear: “...board exam is do or die” (J191). While currently there is no limit on how many times an aspirant nurse can take the N.L.E., Taylor, Loftin and Reyes (2014) note that the first-time passing rate is still considered by many to be the primary, if not the sole, indicator of the quality of pre-licensure nursing education programs. Many of those who failed shifted careers and left the nursing profession thinking that nursing is not really for them (Botti & Iyengar, 2004; see also Gilbert & Ebert, 2002), doubting their past accomplishments, and carrying failure as a daily burden (Poorman & Webb, 2000). In essence, passing the licensure exam is a big deal. It could be the make or break event for an aspirant nurse.

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Under the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002 a.k.a. R.A. 9173, in order to pass this important examination and become a full-pledged Registered Nurse (R.N.), the nurse-candidate has to get at least 75% with a rating of not less than 60% in any subject of the 500-item multiple type examination given by the Professional Regulation Commission (P.R.C.) through the Board of Nursing (B.O.N.). Looking at the number of examinees and average passing percentage in the last five years of the P.N.L.E., there has been an average of 111,945 examinees per year, and 40.40% average passing percentage with an all-time low of 30.94% last December 2013 (P.R.C.), thus far. These declines in the numbers bring the public a closer view of the likelihood of passing the board exam in the recent times.

Accordingly, while the vast majority of these N.L.E. reviewees enroll in review centers or extended in-house/independent reviews after graduation, there are some who reportedly take an uncommon path in preparation for the licensure examination; a path that is regarded by many as full of risks and uncertainties. In the midst of the low passing percentage trend in the N.L.E., the time-pressure, the uncertainties and the perceived complexity of conducting a review for a major examination such as the licensure exam, the researcher found previous N.L.E. licensure examinees who tried a review method that is rarely tried by many, if at all; less understood by some, and hardly mastered by the public. In this thesis, readers will find stories of some nurses who accepted the challenge to review on their own and still passed the licensure exam. While it is a common knowledge that

some pass through self-review in licensure exams, the researcher found no documented literature that offers why these board passers reviewed on their own, what it is like in those particular situations, and most importantly, what review strategies worked for them. The researcher contends that if an N.L.E. examinee, under unfavorable conditions, passed the licensure on his/her own, it is only proper that the nursing community understands the process and context by which he/she was able to pass. Thus, bringing the whole nursing community, the N.L.E. reviewees, and its readers an understanding why these nurses chose self-review, what is it like to conduct self-review, gives the public an insight of the perceived defining traits that may have contributed to what they were able to accomplish, know about the issues and/or challenges that these self-reviewee board passers encountered, and most importantly, their stories on how they overcame them.

+ Purpose of the Study

This thesis began with two simple questions in mind: (1) given the low passing rate in the Nurses' Licensure Examination, why do examinees conduct self-review?; and (2) Could self-review be good enough to make an N.L.E. reviewee pass the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.)?. The researcher, being a self-reviewee board passer himself, personally knew his answer. But to the many minds, an equally compelling subsidiary question remains: 'how did they pass?'. Another interesting question could be, "Given that these nurses conducted their review on their own, will different patterns of study strategies emerge?". Further,

other interesting questions such as, “Will self-review work for everyone?” “Why, or why not?”. These and some few more, remain concretely unanswered in the extant literature. In other words, these preliminary questions sprang towards a conception of a document that embodies what could be the marks of a self-reviewee board passer which may be used by future N.L.E reviewees who, like the researcher himself, will dare to take the solitary route. As there can be multiple ways of approaching reviews, however, this study was not conceived to appraise or promote self-review method and the desired output of this study was not intended to trump any other existing method of review. Rather, the study was conceived to identify and thus describe the review strategies that have worked, and what might not have worked, for the case participants, and identify self-reported traits that may have been instrumental for the proper execution of their review strategy. The researcher strongly contends, and thus assume, that whether or not self-review is appraised, self-review has already been utilized and will still be utilized by licensure examinees. Therefore, the main purpose of the study was to come up with a document that would describe the “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer” based on the background, experiences, strategies and perceived significant traits of individuals who were able to take advantage of the solitary route—a document capable of giving a rather valid and transferable insights; some ideas, tips, and a sort of prescription to help the N.L.E. reviewees throughout the course of their self-review regimen.

+ Statement of the Problem

This thesis revolves on the belief that self-review could make a P.N.L.E. reviewee pass the licensure exam and thus dealt with the following questions:

- 1.) What review strategies and techniques, if any, helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?
- 2.) What personal traits did these self-reviewees possess which helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?
- 3.) What could be the marks of a P.N.L.E. self-reviewee board passer?

+ Framework of the Study

In this thesis, the *Unit of Analysis* in this Multiple Exploratory and Explanatory Case Study will center on “self-reviewee board passers”. Overall, the study delved on these four constructs:

- *Personal and educational background.* In social research, Yin (1984) claimed that it is often impossible to separate a phenomenon’s variables from their context. In the same manner, the researcher argues that it will be impossible to understand the underlying variables of a self-reviewee board passer without taking a look at his/her personal background. Thus, this variable would describe his/her personality, learning circles (i.e. style, strategy/philosophy, preference) as well as his/her early academic and college life which will present who and what the case participants are.

- *Self-review Strategies.* A review, if it is to be carried with an aim of passing the licensure, inevitably requires a strategy that works. In this thesis, this may be considered as the “bread and butter”. As in any type of endeavor, however, there can be setbacks or failures. There are indeed N.L.E. reviewees who utilized self-review, but not all self-reviewees (as we can see in reviewees who use other review methods, too) succeed. Considering that the “Units of Analysis” of this study are the board passers, then, they are assumed to hold epistemological status that their strategies worked, therefore, may be replicated by others. These strategies, taken as a whole, shaped the most part of the document about the “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer”.
- *Traits.* This thesis dealt with some technical aspects of the review experience to help prospective N.L.E. reviewees who may utilize self-review for their licensure exam. The researcher believes that this framework will not be complete without touching on the “human factor” of the participants. Studies have shown that traits/attitudes are important towards the success of any endeavor (Costa & McCrae, 1992; Judge, Jackson, Shaw, Scott, & Rich, 2007). In maintaining the focus of this study (which was to produce a document as to the “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer”), it only briefly touched on traits as a variable of this framework just to give an insight on the kind of personality, the attitudinal aspect, and the perspectives as perceived by the participants themselves. Identification of these traits from these participants

is believed to help prospective self-reviewees in approaching the review course effectively.

Figure 1: *The Conceptual Framework*

The diagram above outlines their relationship. The participants' personal and educational background hone the review strategies that were used in self-review. In other words, the review strategies take their root from the reviewee's personal (i.e. learning style, approaches, and preference) and educational background whereas the self-reported traits, as part of their personal attributes, act as a traction that keep

the review strategies on track until the completion of self-review. The resultant component is a document that embodies the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" which is the final part of this framework. This document is a module of tips, or an information of what could be the marks of a self-reviewee who passed the board exam to be able to reach out to everyone who may be considering self-review or simply provide some transferable insights to those who are considering their options.

As there can be many factors that may affect the result of a review, the output of the study does not, and will not, provide any guarantee. However, the researcher feels that if self-reviewees view them as suggestions and/or rules of thumb from individuals who have proven to have passed on their own and if reviewees take them in the right perspective, can serve as a starting point in coming up with their own review strategy that is responsive to their needs, learning style, and review preference.

✚ Assumptions of the Study

In view of the study undertaken, the following assumptions were conceived and are hereby posed:

- I. The case participants have their unique personal and educational background as well as review experiences with self-review.

- II. The case participants had their own review strategies that made them pass the licensure exam. In turn, such strategies presented in this thesis may be replicated by other self-reviewees to help them pass the licensure exam.
- III. The case participants have personal traits that helped them carry out their strategies efficiently.
- IV. The desired output of the study, which is a document regarding the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" based on the traits, and review strategies of these self-reviewee board passers can be replicated and utilized by those who, regardless of reason, will utilize the self-review method.

✚ Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The main objective of this study was to offer insights on how to utilize self-review in the Nursing Licensure Exam by coming up with a document as regards the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer". Hence, this study revolved on seven self-reviewee board passers and four online survey informants who also passed through self-review in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.) covering the years 2007 up to the present. Such timeframe was chosen to maintain recent memory of the experience and preservation of critical details (Bradburn, as cited in Hassan, 2006) and still gave some flexibility for the researcher to acquire a decent number of participants. Since the main interest was about self-review strategies that worked, only those self-reviewees who never enrolled in a review center and passed

the licensure exam during their initial take were included in this study. Also, the interview questions did not extensively cover information included in other more detailed questionnaires such as Study Process Questionnaire (Biggs, Kember & Leung, 2001); the Approaches and Study Skills Inventory for Students (Tait, Entwistle, & McCune, 1998) and the Learning and Study Strategies Inventory (Weinstein, Schulte & Palmer, 2010) as available in existing literatures for two main reasons: First, because the participants were interviewed/surveyed from end to end. That is, from their personal and educational background, their review strategies which were the highlight of the study, as well as their self-reported traits. The researcher believed that longer surveys or questionnaire would be too burdensome for the working participants and may have only resulted in their decline to participate or may have caused a loss of interest. Second, the researcher sought to include other questions he found pertinent to his topic that are not included in those other standard survey questionnaires. In addition, due to geographical accessibility, time-table of research, financial considerations and the capacity of the lone researcher, the study was delimited to participants who were graduates of universities/colleges within Metro Manila where the researcher resides in.

✚ Significance of the Study

This study is deemed significant for several reasons:

To the **N.L.E. reviewees**: Whether it is because of a need, or because of personal choice to self-review, or whatever reason or circumstance they might be in, this study would give them an appreciation, will set an expectation and a clearer picture of what it is like to do self-review; provide them with some clues and ideas, direct from those who have used such method and passed on their own; for them to adopt those worth adopting for and, from them, possibly innovate something better which suits their learning style, review needs, and preferences by coming up with a practical output entitled "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer". The document was hoped to give them with practical and research-based review insights that they could use in their review. Surely, however, the findings of this study do not seek to advance a "one best way" of reviewing and the recommendations/guidelines or strategies it presents do not carry any sort of "satisfaction guarantee". The researcher believes that more than likely, licensure reviews in general will evolve over time and so the study does not provide absolute self-review strategies. Rather, it would present, as is, the review strategies of a select self-reviewee board passers. Hence, the practical output must be judged in its context. Indeed, review for a major examination such as the licensure exam is too complex to accommodate itself to simple prescriptions. However, the researcher hopes that the N.L.E. reviewees or its readers will acquire new

ideas and review insights in bringing a meaningful and a wonderful twist on how they will conduct licensure reviews.

To Nurse Educators: The appreciation of the experiences and perceived challenges of these self-reviewee board passers could give nurse educators including professors, clinical instructors, and school administrators a clearer picture of what self-review is, how it might be introduced and sustained, and what barriers will have to be surmounted to reap its benefits in order to assist their students who may utilize self-review. An understanding of their graduate's needs and challenges with self-review can give them an insight for possible review of curriculum, instructional practice, and examination preparation within nursing programs which will be responsive to the needs and review preferences of their students who may utilize self-review.

To Parents and Significant Others: Support system has been shown to be very significant in the success of any endeavor (Caselman, 2007). Thus, the results of this study can help the parents and significant others of those N.L.E. reviewees who may subscribe to self-review method to appreciate, and understand what these N.L.E. reviewees will be going through so they can give emotional, technical, moral and/or financial support.

To the **Nursing Profession**: The ultimate goal of this study is to provide the public, especially the aspirant nurses, insights on how to utilize self-review in the P.N.L.E. An effective way of conducting self-review has been, and still is, hardly understood. Through this study, more reviewees who cannot and who do not want to use other review methods will be empowered and have a better chance to pass on their own. The nursing academes produce thousands of nurses yearly, and while the role of commercial review centers and other review methods in preparing N.L.E. reviewees for their licensure has to be recognized and cannot be overlooked, passing on their own could accentuate and highlight the quality of education they have acquired during the four years of their nursing education.

To **Future Researchers**: This study can be of use to researchers in two ways: (1) towards the appraisal and use of case study as a method of research to have an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon and; (2) use of the results of this study to come up with a related and useful studies about self-review and nursing reviews, in general.

The Review of Related Literature

Introduction:

Aquino (1971, p. 38) reasons that "if a researcher shall come to know what is already known and what is still unknown about a problem, it is likely that he will

know where to start and what to do". In the same manner, this section reviews the published and unpublished works of scholars and researchers on topics that are closely related to the present study. As of this writing, however, it must be mentioned at the outset that no literature regarding self-review in nursing licensure has been found, and so this survey will start with an introduction, history, and status of Nursing Licensure Exam which will be followed by its known predictors. A touch on the present understanding of general review strategies, learning styles, personality traits and their relationships were explored to substantiate and offer some contexts on the present study. Finally, this review of the literature will be concluded with a synthesis at the end.

1. The Nursing Licensure Examination

The Nursing Licensure Examination (N.L.E.) was established to measure the minimal competence required for a nurse graduate to practice the profession safely and competently (McDowell, 2008; Washburn, 2006).

In 1901, the first conference of the International Council of Nurses (I.C.N.) met in New York, U.S.A. and passed a resolution stating that all nurses should be licensed by examination (Kalisch & Kalisch, 1978). From then on, examinations were regularly given and today, the National Council Licensure Examinations (N.C.L.E.X.) examination is given online in the United States and in some other countries to enter the nursing practice. The National Council Licensure Examination for Registered Nurses (NCLEX-RN®) was instituted in 1984, moved to

computerized testing (CAT) in 1994, increased in difficulty in 1998, in 2004 (Mosser, Williams & Wood, 2006), and again in 2010 (Cortes & Pan, 2012). The test is administered by the National Council of State Boards of Nursing and is a computer-adaptive, multiple-choice test organized into four "client needs" sections namely (1):Physiological Integrity, (2)Health Promotion and Maintenance, (3) Safe, Effective Care Environment, and (4)Psychosocial Integrity (NCSBN, 2012).

In the mid-1980s, six percent of nurses taking the licensure examination (NCLEX®) were foreign-educated and this proportion increased to close to twenty percent in the mid-2000s (Cortes & Pan, 2012).

The U.S. has recently become the world's largest importer of nurses and the Philippines has emerged as the single largest source of foreign nurses to the US accounting for over half of all nurses imported in the last two decades (Aiken, 2007). Prior to February 2007, NCLEX examinations were taken in other countries other than the Philippines. Thus, Filipino nurses had to spend for airline tickets and accommodation in another country just to take the exam. Fortunately, on February 8, 2007, the National Council of State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN) added Manila, to be one of NCLEX testing centers administered by Pearson Vue (NCSBN, 2007).

❖ **The Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination**

Different countries have their own licensure exams for nurses. Here in the Philippines, the first local board examination for nurses was given in the year 1919 and was conducted by the Board of Examiners. Ninety-three candidates took the exam. Sixty-eight of them passed with the highest rating of 93.5% which was given

to Anna Dahlgren. The theoretical exam was held at the University of the Philippines (U.P.) Amphitheater of the College of Medicine and Surgery while the Practical exam was held at the Philippine General Hospital (P.G.H.) Library (Nursingcrib, 2007).

The Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.) is a legal requirement for safe practice of the nursing profession as mandated by Section 12, Article IV of the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002 or the Republic Act 9173 which covers the following test sections: (1)*PNLE Nursing Practice I- Basic Foundation of Nursing and Professional Nursing Practice*- a 100 item exam that measures the knowledge, skills and attitude of an entry-level nurse on fundamentals of Nursing including Professional Adjustment; (2)*PNLE Nursing Practice II: Community Health Nursing and Care of the Mother and Child*- a 100 item exam that measures the knowledge, skills and attitude of an entry-level nurse in the field of Maternal and Child Health Nursing; (3)*PNLE Nursing Practice III: Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations, Part A*- a 100 item exam that measures the knowledge, skills and attitude of an entry-level nurse in the field of Community Health and Communicable Disease Nursing; (4)*PNLE Nursing Practice IV: Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations, Part B* -a 100 item exam that measures the knowledge, skills and attitude of an entry-level nurse in the field of Nursing of Adolescents, Adults and Aged, and (5)*PNLE Nursing Practice V: Care of Clients with Physiologic and Psychosocial Alterations, Part C* - a 100 item exam that measures the

knowledge, skills and attitude of an entry-level nurse in the field of Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing.

According to former Professional Regulation Commission (P.R.C.) Commissioner Hermogenes Pobre (as cited in Neri, 2008), the licensure examination by design is a measure to determine one's adequacy before one can practice a particular profession. Thus, the nursing licensure exam establishes the newly graduate nurse's readiness to render safe and competent service to health consumers. Such test, according to Blankas (2003), intends to measure certain domains in the training that the graduate has completed. If the test adequately assessed the particular domain that it intends to measure, its scores should be significantly related with other indices of the individual's past training.

A data from the P.R.C., as cited by Dr. Galvez Tan in his article in Manila Times (2006) revealed that in the '80s and '90s, the passing rate was 80-85% of all test takers. There were even years that the passing rate was 90%. High passing rate is the aim of all schools offering board exam courses like nursing. It serves as a basis of the quality of the effectiveness of the program and a reinforced market value for people who want to enter the nursing course (Asumen, 2008).

2. A Look at the Recent Years

Guirra (1998) contends that the very purpose of the educational system is to develop and mold the minds of the young individuals to become responsible and rational adults who are well-prepared for life. Such educational experiences guide

and strengthen the foundation of one's development towards achieving one's goal in life, which is success. To the very least, for students to attain this vision in life, they should attain the level of academic preparation to be able to pass a licensure examination (Blankas, 2003). To show how the examinees fared recently, the researcher compiled the N.L.E. results for the past 10 years as shown on the Philippine Professional Regulation Commission's (P.R.C.) website and presented them on graphical representations:

Figure 2: Comparison between the Number of Examinees vs. N.L.E. passers from the years 2004-2014

Figure 3: Passing Percentage from the year 2004-2014

Figure 4: Total Number of N.L.E. Passers vs. Total No. of N.L.E. reviewees (2004-2014)

Figure 5: Comparison between No. of Examinees vs. No. of Passers per Month/Batch of the Year (2004-2014)

From the data shown above, the following observations were drawn:

- 1.) In 10 year period (Jun 2004 – Nov 2014), there were more than a million (1,176,442) nursing licensure examinees in the Philippines.
- 2.) Out of 1,176,442 nursing licensure examinees, 42.48% (average) passed or equivalent to 499,735 R.Ns in the last ten years as compared to 40.40% (226,107 passers out of 559,726 examinees) within the last five years (2010-2014).
- 3.) The year 2010 (combined in a year) marked the highest number of examinees or equivalent to 175,295 examinees.

- 4.) To date, the November 2009 N.L.E. had the biggest number of examinees (94,462) in one batch.
- 5.) The November 2008 N.L.E. had the highest number of passers (39,455 R.Ns.) in one batch.
- 6.) The lowest passing rate was the recent exam in December 2013 (30.94 %), the lowest so far in nursing history.
- 7.) The June 2004 N.L.E. marked the highest rating (55.74%) in the past 10 years.
- 8.) There was an upward trend in terms of number of examinees from 2004 up to 2009 followed by downward trend starting from the years 2010 until 2014.
- 9.) For the past 10 years, there were three times (Jun 2004, Dec 2005, Nov 2014) that the rating reached 50% and up.
- 10.) For the past 10 years, there were five times (Nov 2009, Dec 2010, Dec 2011, Dec 2012, and Dec 2013) that the passing percentages were within 30-40% range.
- 11.) For the past 10 years, taken as a whole, the second half of the year (Nov or Dec) has a lower passing percentage as compared to the first half (May, Jun or Jul). Out of 589,986 examinees, only 239,584 (or 40.41%) passed during Nov or Dec examinations whereas 44.36% passed during the May, Jun or Jul exams (260,151 passed out of 586,456 examinees).

12.) More than fifty percent of nursing board examinees (57.52% or 676,707 examinees) in a 10-year period (Jun 2004-Nov 2014) failed in the Philippine Nurses' Licensure examinations. In the last five years, 59.60% failed (333,619 failed out of 559,726 examinees).

3. Predictors of Nurses' Licensure Success

Predicting student success by investigating both academic and non-academic variables of NCLEX-RN® success has been looked at extensively in the literature in the past 25 years (Haas, Nugent, & Rule, 2004; Schmidt & MacWilliams, 2011). Research, however, has been unable to identify one uniform variable predictive of (in his research pertaining to NCLEX-RN®) success or failure across all programs (Truman, 2012), but several studies have made it possible to determine efficient pathways (Almaraz, Bassett, & Sawyer, 2010; Bresó, Schaufeli, & Salanova, 2010; Hwang, Kessler, & Francesco, 2004; Ning & Downing, 2010). These studies have demonstrated that academic intervention and communication, general self-efficacy, academic motivation, social activity, and predictors of success can be considered antecedents for students' academic success (Jenner, 2012).

Breckenridge, Wolf, and Roszkowski (2012) say that the most productive application of variables related to NCLEX-RN® performance may be in a model that considers a multiple set of predictors. The applicability of any single variable may be questionable, but generally the value is enhanced when aggregated.

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Success predictors vary from nursing program to nursing program, due in part to the pedagogical variations among the programs. As the (NCLEX-RN®) licensure examination changes, based upon the test plan, the predictors of success and failure also change (Beeman & Waterhouse, 2001).

For the purposes of brevity and presentation, the researcher compiled some foreign & Filipino studies on licensure predictors presented here in tabular form.

Year	Author(s)	Statistically Significant Predictors of Nursing Licensure Exam
2013	Romeo	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		Overall standardized assessment examination score
2013	Simon, McGinniss, and Krauss	First nursing course
		Grade in Adult health nursing (Medical-Surgical) subject
		Grade in Maternal-Child health nursing subject
2012	Truman	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA) (p=.000)
		Pre-admission GPAs (p=.011)
		Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) verbal scores (p=.009)
		Had significantly fewer Cs in nursing courses (p=.000)
2011	Grossbach and Kuncel	Nursing course GPA (grades earned during the second year being the strongest predictor)
		Standardized admissions tests (SAT and ACT)
		Pre-nursing grade point average (GPA)
2011	Paraszczuk	Beginning level nursing course as the best predictor of pretest and post-test performance (R square = .450, .440, respectively).
		Significant relationship was found between the posttest scores and NCLEX-RN outcomes (r =.334, p=.009).
2011	DeLima, London, and Manieri	Females had a higher pass rate (54%) as compared to males (42%)
		White students had higher pass rates than did minority (Black, Hispanic, and Asian) students
		Grade in Maternal-Child health nursing subject (p < .01)
		NLN assessment (PAX-RN) score (p < .05)
		Grade in Psychiatric nursing (p < .02):

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		NLN scores in the fundamentals ($p < .01$), MCN ($p < .00$), and PSY ($p < .00$) courses
		Score on the HESI exit exam ($p < .00$)
2010	McGahee, Gramling, and Reid	RN Assessment Test scores (given in the last semester)
		Passing grades (C or better) in Theoretical Foundations (N202)
		Passing grades in Pathophysiology
2004	Seldomridge and DiBartolo	Combination of test average in advanced medical/surgical nursing and percentile score on the National League for Nursing Comprehensive Achievement Test for Baccalaureate Students (NLNCATBS) predicted 94.7 percent of NCLEX-RN® passes and 33.3 percent of failures
		The combination of NLNCATBS score and Pathophysiology grade predicted 93.3 percent of NCLEX-RN® passes and 50 percent of failures.
2004	Crow, Handley, Morrison, and Shelton	Use of standardized entrance exams and Scholastic Aptitude Test (SAT) scores for admission criteria
		National League for Nursing (NLN) content at-risk scores for mental health and community health nursing for progression
		Clinical proficiency and use of exit examinations as graduation requirements
		Commercial reviews as an intervention
		Percent White as a demographic variable
2004	Sutton	Performance in Pre-board examination
2000	Roncoli, Lisanti, and Falcone	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA) in nursing & science courses
		Clinical nursing grades
		Standardized test scores
1998	Arathuzi and Aber	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		English as the primary language spoken at home
		Lack of family responsibilities or demands
		Lack of emotional distress
		Sense of competency in critical thinking
1997& 1998	Swenty (1998) and Wescott (1997)	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		Success in nursing courses
		Above average scores on standardized tests
1997	Alexander and Brophy	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		SAT (Student Achievement Test) verbal scores

National League for Nursing (N.L.N.) Comprehensive Achievement Test scores

Table 1: *Foreign Studies on Academic Predictors*

Year	Author(s)	Statistically Significant Predictors of Nursing Licensure Exam
2012	Ong, Palompon, and Banico	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		Performance in Pre-board examination
2010	Tolentino	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
		Performance in Nursing Aptitude Test (NAT)
		Dominance and perfectionism as components of personality test
2010	Palaganas, Divinagracia, and Rosales	Negative correlation with examinee variable (number of times examinee took the examination)
		Weak correlation with institutional variable (number of examinees)
		Lowest passing percentage observed in Nursing Practice IV
		Testing centers influence the performance of the examinee.
2010	Del Rosario and Estrada	A corresponding 0.946 level increase in PNLE score for every one level increase in NCM grade when Entrance examination held constant.
		For every one level increase in the entrance examination result, a 0.046 level increase will be incurred in the PNLE score when effect of average NCM grade is held constant
		Accreditation status: examinees from schools with level 3 accreditation status obtained high passing percentage and average rating in all the NLEs.
2008	Neri	NLE passers were usually performers in 3 areas: (1) in the classroom, (2) during clinical duties, (3) in-house review after graduation
		Non-passers are typically students who were performing poorly in those 3 areas
2000	Hilario	Admission tests given to college aspirants
		Retention policies in an institution

1995	Robles , cited in Bajet (2001)	Nursing course Grade Point Average (GPA)
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Table 2: *Filipino Studies on Academic Predictors*

4. Study/Review Strategies

As mentioned in the introduction, no study was found as regards self-review in nursing. At this juncture, the researcher presents what has been learned about the study/review strategies in general, and the discussion will be started by going back to the definition of learning.

Over the years, scholars came up with definitions of learning. Learning, according to Driscoll (2005) and Ormrod (2004) are often characterized by two components: (1) a change in behavior or mental representation, and (2) an experience that facilitates that change. Such skills and strategies that facilitate that change have been the subject of numerous investigations (Amin, Tani, Eng, Samarasekara, & Huak, 2009; Barker & Olson, 1997; Karpicke, Butler, & Roediger, 2009; McConnell, Regehr, Wood, & Eva, 2011; Pandey & Zimitat, 2007; West & Sadoski, 2011, to name a few). Cognitive theories of learning include activities or methods used by an individual to encode information into long-term memory in the category of experiences that produce changes in mental representations and thereby constitute learning (Anderson, 1995). With such in mind, there is little

debate on the notion that academic achievement is associated with study strategies (Onwuegbuzie, Slate, & Schwartz, 2001).

○ Individual Study Strategy Differences Exist

Not all students report using the same strategies—like learning styles, individual differences also exist between students with regard to their study habits (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012). Theories of Self-regulated Learning (SRL) claim that learners use a variety of strategies to achieve their learning goals, and that the quality of strategy use should be related to performance (e.g., Winne & Hadwin, 1998; Dunlosky & Metcalfe, 2009). To support that notion, studies have shown unique differences between high- and low-achieving students in the specific strategies they engage in to achieve academically (Zimmerman & Martinez-Pons, 1990).

○ Processes Involved in Study Strategies

Learning or study strategies are characterized by two main processes: Rehearsal and Constructive (Ormrod, 2004).

- Rehearsal processes (a.k.a. rote learning): include strategies for encoding information through repetition, rehearsal, mnemonic associations, or repeated practice. These strategies are often referred to as “rote” learning, as they tend to foster the encoding of the information in its original form as separate components isolated from existing knowledge structures. This includes mnemonics, flashcards, practice tests, and memorization.

- Constructive processes: imply that the learner transforms the information from its original form and constructs a new representation of the information in long-term memory, which includes linking the information into existing knowledge structures. Constructive processes include strategies for encoding information through the elaboration of prior knowledge, structuring or organizing information, personalizing information to make it meaningful, and creating visual representations of information (Driscoll, 2005; Ormrod, 2004). Examples include concept maps, life examples, continuous review, and own words.

Cognitive sciences view that rote learning is an ineffective and inefficient method for learning declarative knowledge (Anderson, 1995). The negative association between “surface” learning strategies and medical student performance on examinations was reported by Pandey and Zimitat (2007) in their investigation of study strategies in anatomy.

Ormrod (2004) advocated that students utilize constructive study strategies. To quote, “To learn a classroom subject matter effectively, students should instead develop study strategies that involve meaningful learning, internal organization, and elaboration...they can be encouraged to state ideas in their own words, generate their own examples of an idea, make connections between new concepts and their past experiences, and draw logical inferences from data they

receive” (p. 227). The expectation is that students who utilize constructive strategies when studying learn more effectively and perform better on assessments. Ironically, however, while evidences support the value of using constructive practices, students often resist using constructive strategies, assuming that rote learning strategies are more effective (Ormrod, 2004).

o Study Strategy: Self-Testing

One particular study strategy that has been investigated extensively is self-testing, or practice retrieval, which has been shown as an effective method for learning (Belluck, 2011; Karpicke *et al*, 2009; Larsen, Butler, & Roediger, 2008; Roediger & Butler, 2011; Rohrer & Pashler, 2010; Wenger, Hobbs, Williams, Hays, & Ducatman, 2009). Self-testing has been demonstrated to be quite effective and abundance of research has shown can boost student learning (Roediger & Butler, 2011). Ormrod (2004) indicated that the processes or strategies employed by a learner while studying influences how the information is stored and later retrieved, and she proposed that some study processes promoted better learning.

o Self-Testing and Re-Reading

Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012) surveyed 324 undergraduates about their study habits as well as their college grade point average (GPA). Their findings showed that the use of self-testing and rereading were both positively associated with GPA. Karpicke *et al.* (2009) revealed that self-testing and other retrieval type activities (e.g., using flashcards) were commonly reported by their respondents

(N=177), but the strategy most frequently reported (by 83.6% of students) was rereading notes or textbooks. Students' explanations revealed that most students self-test for the feedback about what they do or do not know rather than as a means to enhance learning. These results were consistent with the general conclusions of Kornell and Bjork (2007), as well as with the recent conclusions of McCabe (2011), who found that students often fail to understand that certain activities—such as testing (vs. restudying) or spacing study (vs. massing study)—are likely to enhance learning.

- Self-Testing and Multiple Choice Item Questions

Current evidence suggests that self-testing has widespread benefits across different kinds of tests, materials, and student abilities. For instance, self-testing by recalling the target information boosts performance on subsequent recall and multiple choice tests of the target information, and it also boosts performance on tests of comprehension (Roediger & Butler, 2011; Roediger & Karpicke, 2006; Rawson & Dunlosky, 2011).

- Time Management and Self-Testing

Multiple regression analyses were done by West and Sadoski (2011) to investigate significant factors of performance. The predictor variables in each regression were: MCAT score; UGPA; and sub-scores on the 10 LASSI subscales for Anxiety, Attitude, Motivation, Concentration, Information Processing, Self-Testing, Selecting Main Idea, Study Aids, Time Management and Test-Taking Strategies. The

results of three regressions indicated that two study skills, time management and self-testing, were generally stronger predictors of first-semester academic performance than aptitude.

○ Caution about Self-Testing

Self-testing (which was related to GPA) can be used ineffectively, such as when students test themselves by evaluating their familiarity with a concept without trying to recall it from memory (Dunlosky, Rawson, & Middleton, 2005). Second, any strategy could be used well or poorly. This variability in how well strategies are used would obscure how valuable they might be if used ideally (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).

○ Re-reading

Reported use of rereading was also related to GPA, which might be viewed as surprising, given that rereading does not always improve performance in the laboratory (e.g., Callender & McDaniel, 2009). When used correctly, however, it can boost retention and performance (e.g., Rawson & Kintsch, 2005), and the present rereading-GPA relationship may in part arise from students who read (a lot) versus those who do not read.

○ Re-Reading, Cramming

Some study strategies—such as rereading text materials and cramming for tests—are commonly endorsed by students (e.g., Karpicke, Butler, & Roediger, 2009;

Taraban, Maki, & Rynearson, 1999), even though they may not always yield durable learning.

One survey was administered by Kornell and Bjork (2007), who sought to describe what students do to manage their real-world study. Their results indicated that majority of students (59%) prioritize for study whatever is due soonest, and that the majority of students use quizzes to evaluate how well they have learned course content (68%).

o Outlines, Collaborative Learning, Use of Diagrams & Highlighting Texts

The reported use of outlines and collaborative learning demonstrated slightly negative relationships, and the use of diagrams and highlighting were not significantly related to GPA (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012). These outcomes are provocative, because many students believe that these strategies are beneficial when in fact they will not always boost learning. For instance, although studying with friends highlighting by a textbook publisher or instructor can improve performance, but students' use of highlighting has been shown to yield mixed results, depending on the skill of the user (e.g., Bell & Limber, 2010; Fowler & Barker, 1974).

o Time of Day

Regarding time of day, they showed similar rates of beliefs about effective study times for students at all GPAs, but somewhat different patterns of actual

studying in which the lowest performers are most likely to engage in late-night studying. Afternoon and evening studying would better match college students' peak diurnal rhythms (May, Hasher, & Stoltzfus, 1993), and hence might be related to GPA.

o Time Management: Cramming

Although this outcome is surprising, cramming the night (and immediately) before an exam might support relatively good exam performance, even though students who use this strategy might remember little of the content even a short time after the exam, as reported by Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012). Furthermore, scheduling study sessions in a spaced manner may afford the use of other strategies, which themselves improve student success. Although these ideas are speculative, post-hoc analyses indicated that the reported use of spacing (vs. cramming) was significantly related to the use of more study strategies overall ($r = .15, p < .009$; combined Question 12 reports) and, in particular, was related to the use of self-testing ($r = .11, p = .05$) and rereading ($r = .15, p = .007$). These relationships are small, but they do suggest that spacing may support the use of more effective strategies.

o Time Management & Scheduling

Differences in scheduling did arise between the highest and lowest achievers, with the lower achievers focusing (a) more on impending deadlines, (b) more on studying late at night, and (c) almost never on planning their study time. Reports of spacing study (vs. cramming) were not significantly related to GPA, even

though spaced (vs. massed) practice is known to have a major impact on retention (Cepeda, Pashler, Vul, Wixted, & Rohrer, 2006). Relevant to scheduling, Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012) examined the responses from the question “How do you decide what to study next? (time-of-day schedules and pattern of spacing vs. massing study), as well as the checklist strategy pertaining to cramming. They found that although many students are heavily influenced by impending deadlines (what’s due soonest/overdue) when deciding what to study next, this scheduling practice is especially true for low performers. By contrast, although relatively few students overall (13%) schedule their study ahead of time, high performers are more likely to do so. It has been shown however in the studies of Kornell and Bjork (2007) and Karpicke, *et al.* (2009) that students who report scheduling practice across sessions (which should be the more effective strategy) did not appear to reap a clear benefit in terms of GPA.

○ No Study Strategy is the Best: The Factor of Chance

According to Hartwig and Dunlosky’s (2012) arguments, even if recommended strategies are an effective means of improving GPA, it is possible that successful students achieve their success in spite of (1) using the same pattern of strategies as low performers or (2) using even poorer strategy options. In the former case, perhaps high and low performers choose the same strategies, but high performers use them more adeptly. In the latter case, perhaps other factors—such

as intelligence, prior experience, or degree of motivation— overpower the differential use of study strategies in determining GPA.

5. Learning & Learning Styles

Keefe's (1987) classic definition of learning is that "learning is an internal process; we know that it has taken place only when we observe a change of learner behavior of a more or less permanent nature resulting from what has been experienced." Schunk (2012) says it endures over time.

○ Pedagogical and Andragogical Learners:

Knowles (1975, 1990) described two opposite poles of a continuum of learning, with teacher- or other-directed (pedagogical) learning at one end and self-directed (andragogical) at the other.

The pedagogical learner prefers to learn in highly structured situations such as lectures and tutorials. According to Knowles (1990), the pedagogical learner is dependent on the teacher to identify learning needs, formulate objectives, plan and implement learning activities and evaluate learning. Conversely, the andragogical learner prefers to take responsibility for meeting his or her own learning needs.

Learning Styles

Learning style is regarded as a way of learning (Busato, Prins, Elshout, & Hamaker, 1998). It refers to the concept that we, as individuals, process and

perceive information in different ways (Shannon, 2008), and it is an attribute or quality of an individual which reflects a pattern of information-processing behaviors used to acquire knowledge or skills and prepare for an anticipated test of memory (Kelly, 1997). There are many different factors that can lead to the differences that arise within learning styles. These factors include, but are not limited to, personality, ability to process information, self-efficacy, sensory intake processes or some complex combination of these and other differences (Institute for Learning Styles Research, 2003). One of many instruments for determining learning style is the VARK questionnaire, developed by Neil Fleming. The VARK system categorizes learners into four styles: (1) Visual (See / imagine / pictures); (2) Auditory (Hear / listen / sounds); (3) Read & write (Tactile); and (4) Kinesthetic (Touch /move/experience). Each preferred style has several specific characteristics that contribute to learning. An individual prefers to use these characteristics when they learn (Mohamed & Helal, 2012). People with a visual style tend to learn mostly through 'sight' they often think in pictures and learn best from visual displays. Those with an auditory learning style will benefit most from listening to lectures, speeches and oral sessions. They prefer to hear an explanation of something rather than read about it. People with Read &write learning style converting visual information like diagrams into descriptions that use words). Finally, People with a kinesthetic learning style prefer to carry out a physical activity rather than listening to a lecture or merely watching a demonstration

(DiCarlo, 2008; Murphy, Gray, Straja, & Bogert, 2004). It is assumed, however, that learning through several inputs is most effective (Mohamed & Helal, 2012).

Knowles (1980) suggests that, older adult learners prefer instructional situation that, emphasize practical, experience-related learning opportunities and assists them to be actively involved in increasing their competence to perform the developmental tasks of various social roles; and allows them to be self-directing and independent in pursuing their individual learning needs. Studies of Merritt's (1983) and Mohamed and Helal (2012) revealed that baccalaureate nursing students expressed a higher preference for tactile (read & write). However, Osman (2004) found that the visual and the tactile (read -write) were the most preferred learning styles. Moreover, research teams found nursing students' learning styles profiles can change between two measurement points (Fleming, McKee, & Huntley-Moore, 2011), tends to change the longer students remain in school, and continues to change as they grow older (Dunn & Griggs, 1995).

Another assessment tool that can be used in establishing a person's learning style is the Perceptual Modality Preference Survey (PMPS). This survey focuses on seven perceptual sensory intake methods that help shape how, we as individuals, view the world around us. There are seven perceptual styles: print, aural, visual, interactive, haptic, kinesthetic, and olfactory (Institute for Learning Styles Research, 2003).

- Print learning refers to seeing printed or written words. This type of learner often take notes, remember things easily that are read, recall information more readily after seeing or writing something, and often times, grasp important concepts on a first reading of material.
- Aural learning refers to listening. These learners excel within a lecture setting, are usually excellent listeners, can learn concepts by listening to a visual medium, such as pod casts or audio recordings, can reproduce symbols, letters or words by hearing them, and can repeat or fulfill verbal instructions with relative ease.
- Interactive learning refers to verbalization. These learners prefer group discussions, enjoy question and answer sessions, and like to use other people as a sounding board.
- Visual learning refers to seeing visual depictions. These learners function well by seeing and by watching demonstrations, often have a vivid imagination, prefer to gain knowledge through visual media, and prefer visual stimuli such as pictures, slides and graphs.
- These learners prefer a "hands on" approach to learning, tend to doodle on notebooks, and succeed with tasks requiring "hands on" manipulation.
- Kinesthetic learning refers to whole body movement. These learners focus with direct involvement in things. They often fidget or find a reason to move, often find success in physical response activities, use movement to help concentrate, are

usually poor listeners, and are not particularly attentive to visual or auditory presentations.

- Olfactory learning refers to sense of smell and taste. These learners use smell to enhance learning, are frequently able to identify smells, and can associate a particular smell with specific past memories (Shannon, 2008).

6. Personality and Learning

The close relationship between personality and learning is generally accepted. It is a common sense that mere effort may not be enough for effective learning (Ibrahimoglu *et al*, 2013).

Personality is defined as an inborn temperament and features arising in different situations and a combination of the characteristics of a person which separate him/her from other people (Phares, 1991). Traits are relatively unconditional behavioral tendencies that attest to individual's potentials in broad domain of functioning (McCrae & Costa, 1999).

Personality traits, then, serve as preparation in achieving specific objectives or certain situations (Caligiuri, 2000). In other words, personality traits facilitate learning behavior and motivate the person, and these traits are decisive for the person in insisting or giving up (Blickle, 1998). Martin, Montgomery, and Saphian (2006) found that individual differences in personality played a unique role in undergraduate performance across 4 years of coursework over and above the

effects due to high-school performance and cognitive ability (i.e., achievement test scores). Personality traits were found to account for an additional 10–17% of unique variance in academic performance (Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2003).

○ The Five Factor Model of Personality

During the last years, conformity about the basic personality traits has emerged. It has been stated that they are extraversion, neuroticism, agreeableness, conscientiousness and openness to experience (Heinström, 2000). These dimensions have been found to be stable across the lifespan and directly related to behavior. They also seem to have a physiological base (Revelle & Loftus, 1992).

The five factors are the following;

A. Extraversion

The “extraverts” tend to be more physically and verbally active whereas the “introverts” are independent, reserved, steady and like being alone. The person in the middle of the dimension likes a mix between social situations and solitude (Howard & Howard, 1998). Extraverts are adventurous, assertive, frank, sociable and talkative. Introverts are quiet, reserved, shy and unsociable (Boeree, nd). Introverted students are expected to outperform extraverts (Entwistle & McCune, 2004); however, research findings are inconsistent so far.

B. Agreeableness

The agreeableness scale is linked to altruism, nurturance, caring and emotional support versus hostility, indifference, self-centeredness and jealousy. Agreeable people are altruistic, gentle, kind, sympathetic and warm (Boeree, n.d.).

C. Neuroticism

The persons with a tendency towards neuroticism are more worried, temperamental and prone to sadness (Howard & Howard, 1998). Emotional stability is related to calm, stable and relaxed persons, whereas neuroticism is linked to anger, anxiousness and depression (Boeree, n.d.). The name neuroticism does not refer to any psychiatric defect. A more proper term could be negative affectivity or nervousness (McCrae & John, 1992). Neuroticism and Agreeableness are generally not associated with academic success (Diseth, Pallesen, Hovland, & Larsen, 2006).

D. Openness

People with a high openness have broader interests, are liberal and like novelty. This factor relates to intellect, openness to new ideas, cultural interests, educational aptitude and creativity (Howard & Howard, 1998). These individuals are cultured, esthetic, and intellectual and open (Boeree, n.d.). The openness to experience can be connected to activities like writing, science and art (Wallach & Wing, 1969).

E. Conscientiousness

The conscientious, focused person is concentrating on only a couple of goals and strives hard to perceive them. He is career oriented, while the flexible person is more impulsive and easier to persuade from one task to another.

Conscientiousness has been linked to educational achievement and particularly to the will to achieve (Howard & Howard, 1998). The more conscientious a person is the more competent, dutiful, orderly, responsible and thorough he is. Conscientious individuals are characterized as organized, purposeful, and strong-willed (Zhang, 2003).

o Relationship among Personality Traits, Learning Style, Learning Strategies, and the Learning Outcome

According to De Raad and Schouwenburg (1996), personality traits are expressed in learning styles, which are in turn reflected in learning strategies, which eventually produce a certain learning outcome. Personality traits serve as directors or blocks for motivation and learning strategies (Mumford & Gustafson, 1988 in Blickle, 1996). Blickle (1996) has compared the Five Factor Model personality traits with learning strategies and learning outcome. He found that, particularly, conscientiousness and openness were related to learning style. The student's personality was related to learning outcome mediated by learning strategies. Conscientiousness is related to work discipline, interest in subject matter, concentration and considering studying as quite easy (Schouwenburg,

1995). Conscientiousness is the trait most consistently positively correlated with academic performance (Diseth, 2003; Nguyen, Allen, & Fraccastoro, 2005).

Openness is linked with questioning and analyzing arguments (Schouwenburg, 1995). It is further related to critical evaluation, searching literature and making relationships (deep approach) (Blickle, 1996). The students with a deep approach want to find out the deeper meaning in the text. They are critical, logical and relate what they learn to their previous knowledge (Entwistle & Tait, 1996). Their motivation is intrinsic and they look for a personal comprehension independent of the syllabus (Entwistle, 1988). Neuroticism is linked to lack of concentration, fear of failure and experiencing studying as stressful. Moreover, neuroticism is linked with a lack of critical ability and problems in understanding how things relate to each other (Schouwenburg, 1995). This can be linked to the surface learning style (Entwistle, 1988). The student with a surface approach concentrates on memorizing without any concern of finding a deeper meaning or understanding of the material. They are most concerned about getting through the exams and are not really interested in the material itself (Entwistle & Tait, 1996). Their motivation is extrinsic and they take on a strategic, syllabus-bound approach to studying (Entwistle, 1988).

Synthesis

The presentation of the survey of the literature showed how a person can become a nurse. In order to become a nurse, a licensure exam is set in place to be the standard of the minimum level of competency that an aspirant nurse must possess in order to practice the profession safely and competently. Upon meeting the eligibility criteria, a graduate nurse can then take the licensure exam in order to become a Registered Nurse (R.N.). In that regard, the academic literature, both from local as well as foreign authors offer the present understanding of the predictors of the Nursing Licensure Exam. Accordingly, the Commission on Higher Education (C.H.E.D.) is tasked by the government to regulate the operation of tertiary schools and courses here in the Philippines, and that includes nursing. True enough, a school in order to continue its existence must show that its graduates are performing well in the licensure exam. Unfortunately, statistics from the Professional Regulation Commission's website suggest a deepening and worsening concern about the passing rate of N.L.E. examinees nowadays. Last December 2013, for example, only about 31% of the examinees passed--- the lowest passing rate in the P.N.L.E. history, thus far. Arguably, these figures reflect the status of the nursing education in the country in the recent and contemporary days. Various strategies are being carried out by N.L.E. reviewees, together with their respective academes, to prepare for the licensure exam. Some enroll in review centers; some try, like the researcher himself, to self-review. No published document has been found,

however, as to the ratio of how many examinees reviewed in the review centers as compared to those who embark on self-review. While the researcher did not find a literature on the experiences of students in review centers, the motivation of this thesis, however, is to present the more overlooked and unstudied review method -- the self-review. To date, nothing has been found regarding self-review, the self-review experience of reviewees, in general, more so regarding those who passed through self-review. The literature documents individual differences in terms of study strategies, learning styles, personality traits, etc., however, it cannot be said that they are the same reasons why some N.L.E. reviewees take a different path of review. Despite the concerning low passing rate in the N.L.E, it is interesting to know why did these reviewees review on their own. If it is because of economic reason, was it purely because of it? What were their experiences? Were there any challenges? If so, how were they able to deal with them? Out of those undocumented self-reviewees, did all pass? If not, why did some fail? More importantly, what made the others pass? The above mentioned questions, their answers, and some more, are not documented in the literature. In trying to understand the context of the experiences of these reviewees and ultimately help the N.L.E. reviewees pass the licensure exam, this thesis attempted to answer part of those questions. In general, this study described the personal background, review experiences, review strategies, and self-reported traits of a select number of self-reviewee board passers. Specifically, the appreciation, insights and

understanding on the marks of a self-reviewee board passer direct from those who did it will be the highlight of this study.

✚ Operational Definition of Terms

In the interest of common understanding among the readers, nine terms were operationally defined in the context of this thesis:

- 1.) **Aspirant Nurse.** A nurse-graduate who is about to take the Nursing Licensure Examination.
- 2.) **In-house review (Pre-review).** An in-house review, or at times called “Pre-review” is a review strategy of nursing institutions given to their students in preparation for the forthcoming Philippine Nurses Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.). Nowadays, schools either choose to have review lecturers selected from their institution or commission a private/commercial review center to conduct the review for them with a fee.
- 3.) **Learning Circles:** This term was used in this study as a collective term for learning style, preferences, and learning strategies of the participants.
- 4.) **Pre-Board Examination or Mock Board Exam.** It refers to the examination usually conducted by the nursing institution and/or review center to test for the “preparedness” of a graduate nurse to take the P.N.L.E. In practice, the nursing institution may withhold approval to take the licensure exam should

- the graduate nurse fail to meet a certain level of test criteria set by the institution.
- 5.) **Review Center.** A review center is an independent/commercial review company that conducts a review course to various candidate professionals, including graduate nurses, “intended to refresh and enhance the knowledge or competencies and skills of reviewees (GR No. 180046, Review Center Association of the Philippines v. Ermita, April 2, 2009)”.
- 6.) **Self-reviewee.** A self-reviewee in the P.N.L.E. is an aspirant nurse/N.L.E. reviewee who may have taken an in-house review at his/her respective institution but has not enrolled nor completed review with the help of a private and/or commercial review center. In this study, they will be divided into two: (1) N.L.E. reviewees who reviewed on his/her own, and (2) N.L.E. reviewees who participated in a peer/group review (vs. alone or in a review center). In plain context of this term, it includes those self-reviewees who are currently reviewing; those who successfully passed the licensure examination, and those who failed.
- 7.) **Self-reviewee Board Passer.** A self-reviewee **board passer** in the P.N.L.E. is a Registered Nurse who passed the nurse’s licensure exam who may have taken an in-house review at his/her respective institution but has not enrolled nor completed nursing review with the help of a private and/or commercial review center. In the context of this study, the R.N. participant must not have (1)

continued to review at their institution (in-house) after graduation, and (2) must have the chance to review on his/her own before the licensure exam was taken, yet still chose to review individually, or with a group.

- 8.) **Self-Review Strategies.** A review, if it is to be carried successfully, inevitably requires an effective strategy. In this thesis, it refers to the techniques or plan of action that the successful self-reviewees used in passing the licensure examination. These strategies will form the major part of a document entitled "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" that this study produced.
- 9.) **Traits.** Traits is a variable that pertains to the component/s of a person's behavior that is assumed to serve as an explanation of his or her enduring personal characteristics (businessdictionary.com). In this thesis, defining traits are assumed to help the reviewee to consistently carry out the strategies in order to pass the licensure exam.

Chapter 2

CASE STUDY PROTOCOL

This chapter describes the rationale and justification of the design of this research. Very briefly, the research was guided and has taken a qualitative research approach, and was a multiple case study. The chapter begins with the researcher's choice of the research approach and design followed by a presentation of his research locale, the introduction of case participants and their review experience, the sources of evidence applied and a discussion on how the data were collected. Following them is a touch on ethical considerations. Finally, the researcher will present how the data were analyzed along with how validity and reliability criteria such as objectivity/intersubjectivity, construct validity, internal validity, external validity, and reliability were addressed in this study.

+ Research Design

The goal of the study was not only to present a document regarding the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer", equally important was to understand the experiences of embarking a self-review itself, and the self-reported traits they bring. Hence, the researcher adopted the qualitative design in order to understand the viewpoints of his participants (Hassard, 1993) coming from their own experiences (Smith & Heshusius, 1986). Further, qualitative research can be used with a relatively small number of cases examined and is recommended when

information obtained from each subject is expected to differ in complex ways and each of their stories was a story in its own right (Ticehurst & Veal 2000).

✚ Research Approach

This study examined current self-review practices, and while in this study, the participants' self-reviews happened in the past, the researcher strongly argues that while they may be undocumented, self-reviews still happen at present and have happened in the past not just in nursing licensures, but in licensure exams in general. Using Yin's (2003) three conditions for determining research strategies, it was determined that based on the purpose of the study and the main problem statement, the most appropriate study methodology was a Case Study since the researcher had no control over when or who will conduct a self-review. Further, Case Study was chosen because of (1) the limited number of case participants, and (2) case study research is considered particularly useful when "research and theory are at their early, formative stages' (Benbasat, Goldstein, & Mead., 1987, p.369). Further, Merriam (1988) stated that a case study is "selected for its uniqueness, for what it can reveal about a phenomenon, knowledge we would not otherwise have access to" (p. 33).

Specifically, this study utilized a mix of "explanatory" and "exploratory" type of "Multiple (holistic) Case Study" approaches. According to Yin (2003), this is an "explanatory" research because it tries to answer a 'how & why' question. However,

because existing literature about self-review is very scarce, if at all; this research can be classified as “exploratory” as well.

✚ Research Locale

In the interest of this thesis, Metro Manila, otherwise known as the National Capital Region (NCR) was chosen as its research locale and there were two reasons for this: First, in terms of educational institutions, there are around 81 colleges and universities in Metro Manila, and is considered as the educational center of the country. Many students from all parts of the Philippines head to Metro Manila to study (philippine-islands.ph, 2012). Of over 400 nursing schools in the Philippines, Metro Manila houses at least 60 of them (Alojado Publishing International, n.d.). In terms of ratio, most of the topnotchers in the Philippine Nurses’ Licensure Exam (P.N.L.E.) so far come from schools located in Metro Manila (P.R.C). Having said so, the number of available schools in Metro Manila gave variability and perceived diversity among prospective participants---a factor perceived as favorable in accomplishing the purpose of the study. The second reason was rather practical: it is in Metro Manila where the researcher resides and so it was logical that he started to scout for participants within his geographic area. Metro Manila covers a total land area of 638.55 km² (Wikipedia, n.d.) and is the center of Luzon and the capital region of the Philippines (philippine-islands.ph, 2012). While the smallest of the country's administrative regions, it is the most populous and the most densely populated, having a population of 11,855,975 (2010 census) and is composed of 16

cities and one municipality (Wikipedia, n.d.). In view of those, graduates of colleges/universities in Metro Manila were scouted for possible participants because that satisfied research considerations such as accessibility, financial resources, and constraints with time in terms of his capacity as a lone researcher while taking into account the likelihood of scouting a decent number of participants. Also, it was part of the strategy not to focus on a specific city or place as the locale was dependent on the availability, willingness, and participant's fitness to the set criteria and, of course, accessibility.

✚ The Case Participants

This section is focused on Case Participants. The first portion of this section discusses the extant literature of case study participants and how the researcher was able to come up with the participants of this thesis; the second portion will detail the search for participants, and the last will introduce their background and review experience.

❖ Selection of Case Participants:

Like what is already known, the study used multiple-case participants that show different perspectives on the problem, process, or event (Creswell, 1998) and the process by which the participants were selected was guided by these three major considerations:

1.) Purpose of the study. Based on the review of literature, there are multiple personalities, learning styles and study strategies. Given that an aim of the study

was to create a document regarding the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" for future reviewees, catering only to one participant may limit the applicability of the output to other reviewees. Also, the perspectives coming from multiple self-reviewees allowed comparison and contrast between the cases to "discover new meanings" and "confirm what is known" (Merriam & Simpson, 2000, p. 109) whether different or the same from his.

2.) Replication Logic. Yin (2003, p.47) argued strongly that multiple cases should be considered as multiple experiments and not multiple respondents in a survey and cases must be selected based on "replication logic" and not based on "sampling logic". As a result, each case either predicts similar results (literal replication) or predicts opposite results for predictable reasons (theoretical replication). To meet these, the researcher took note if there were new answers coming out as he interviewed one participant after another, or if he needed to look for another prospective participant to fill in saturation within the timeframe he allotted for data collection. As Glaser (1978) remarked about theoretical sampling, "It is never clear cut for what and to where discovery will lead. It is ongoing (p. 37)". Lincoln and Guba (1985) however stated, "In purposeful sampling the size of the sample is determined by informational considerations. If the purpose is to maximize information, the sampling is terminated when no new information is forthcoming from new sampled units" (p. 202). As the researcher met and found more participants, there was a struggle when to stop looking. In looking for an answer,

he found comfort in Wolff's (2002) wisdom when he wrote that it "lies not in some externally sanctioned number, but inside the one who embodies the research process. If there was an ideal number, knowing when to stop would be easy" and that the researcher will "recognize" when that moment arrives rather than "decide" (p. 117). Being (1) a lone researcher who will transcribe and analyze a rather lengthy interviews (an hour and 10 minutes in average), and (2) finding some repetitions in responses being elaborated on by different participants --- he understood that the "moment" to stop has "arrived".

3. Availability and Willingness of Case Participants. Selection of case participants were subject to some personal, geographic and theoretical limitations. "Personal" because this was a single person research and, of course, as mentioned in the preceding sections, there were limited self-reviewees found within the researcher's geographic area; and "theoretical" because it had to comply with "theoretical" and not with "sampling logic". Also, in search of the participants, the researcher considered accessibility, or in Stake's (2006) words, "opportunity to learn." Further, given that the potential population was small and that the participation was completely voluntary, the researcher did not have much control over their variability. It was in line with Yin (2009, p. 91) when he said that "an extensive screening procedure" should be avoided when choosing a case. In hindsight, it turned out to be a good decision because every case revealed different perspectives of self-review.

The aim of this study, the anticipated scarce available number of participants, and the nature and types of questions posed dictated that the researcher had to use a sampling technique that covered all of these conditions. Sampling involves decisions about which people to observe or interview and there were various sampling principles that the researcher may have chosen from such as maximum variation sampling, critical case sampling, snowball sampling, purposive sampling or convenience sampling (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Berg, 2004). And so, the researcher used “Purposive Sampling”. Patton (1990, p. 169) introduced the concept of Purposeful or “Purposive Sampling” suggesting that case studies should be selected from among potential cases which are information-rich and provide the researcher with deep knowledge and understanding about the research issue. He identified sixteen different strategies of purposeful sampling for case selection of which four strategies were utilized in the current research. For this study, the researcher used a “criteria” based sampling strategy where he selected participants belonging to a pre-defined group or criteria (Trochim, 2007) as composed of the following (also partly cited in “Scope and Delimitation”):

- 1.) Self-reviewees who did not participate nor enrolled in a review center
- 2.) Self-reviewees who passed the P.N.L.E during his/her first take
- 3.) Has taken his/her exam within the last 7 years to increase the validity and preservation of critical details (Bradburn, 1987 as cited in Hassan, 2006) of their responses.

❖ The Search for Case Participants

Scouting for possible participants that would qualify with the set criteria of this study was relatively an arduous task. The main challenge in searching for possible participants was that there is no identified pool where to find the participants. It is a common knowledge that majority enroll in review centers, or extended in-house reviews. One school administrator, for example, said that they do not allow their graduates to take the licensure without a review center. Another said they knew one student who did self-review, but have not heard of the student anymore after graduation. The researcher was given the contact number and it turned out the number was no longer valid. Another dean said they do not have control over their students once they graduate. Another asked the researcher to leave a letter, which he did, and was instructed to “wait for feedback” but no feedback was received. One other school secretary said their student council might have had the needed list, and said “we will contact you” and then after a number of tries said they could not accommodate it at the time as they were busy with some regulatory certification. With this, the researcher found himself asking his friends and acquaintances for any possible participant, checking online nursing forums, posting invites to nursing groups in Facebook, which is a popular social networking site, went to most of the nursing schools here in Metro Manila to inquire if there was any of their graduate/s that did self-study, and even went to the P.R.C. to ask permission to get possible participants since on the day of the licensure exam, the

examinee is required to fill out a form that asks if he/she enrolled in a review center, with the corresponding name, or did self-review. After all those efforts and a number of correspondences, he was lucky to have found two possible participants. From there, he was fortunate to find some referrals and so after exhausting all possible sources and means, the researcher was able to find seven of them (and four survey informants), which was already a relatively large size in a span of six months. And so he started making the arrangements one after the other, contacted them and introduced himself, sent an invitation with an explanation of what will be expected, with the consent form. The decision to include all eleven of them (including the survey informants) was not because of merely getting more number of participants, but because during the initial interviews, there were still differences on their answers, thus concluded that saturation has not been reached yet. During those courses of “search-propose-get-consent” phase, it soon became clear that taking time to create an atmosphere of trust with a “stranger” researcher was more important than following a pre-arranged schedule. This meant, for example, that with “Ms. NurseK” the researcher was unable to get consent until a month after. Not only that there were trust issues, the participants’ availability was one of the major concerns because all them were working at the time and have their private lives. It was understandable, however, as even in the literature research observers can be perceived as “intrusive” (Angrosino, 2005, p. 729). Understandably, it took a while for the researcher to get a nod and secure an

interview. In fact, the researcher had to send a survey-questionnaire (modified form of the interview guide) to some of them in advance via email.

✚ The Seven Case Participants

The seven nurses who participated in the semi-structured interviews comprised five male and two female. They are the main case participants of the study. In addition, four nurse informants (two male and two female) also contributed by answering an online survey questionnaire. The informants' responses, while self-reviewee board passers themselves, were only treated as an additional source of evidence. The justification as to why they were included in the study is outlined below. Some of them are already located outside of the country and some are in the province, but all of them were graduates of nursing colleges/universities in Metro Manila both from public and private institutions. The participants ranged in age from 22 to 26 at the time of the interview/survey. None of the participants were married at the time. Pseudonyms were used to conform to anonymity. The researcher just used random letters of their names for easy designation. As there could be gender differences in terms of review approaches, the pseudonyms start with a "Mr." or "Ms." to help guide the reader with their gender. Below is a general survey of participant demographics and licensure information:

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

No.	Participant Alias	Age	Gender	School Type	BSN Graduation Date	Date of PNLE	Self-reported Licensure Rating	Present Occupation	Previous Occupation
1	Mr. NurseR	25	M	Public	2008 Mar	2008 Jun	80 & above	Subject Matter Expert/Healthcare Associate	Billing and collections agent/, technical support, and Senior Care Assistant
2	Mr. NurseB	26	M	Private	2007 Mar	2007 Jun	80 & above	Healthcare Associate	Nurse Volunteer
3	Mr. NurseN	24	M	Private	2010 Apr	2010 Jul	80 & above	Supervisor/Healthcare Associate	Customer Care Representative
4	Mr. NurseO	22	M	Private	2010 Apr	2010 Jul	75-79	Supervisor - BPO	Supervisor
5	Mr. NurseJ	26	M	Public	2008 Apr	2009 Jun	75-79	Company Nurse	Financial/Sales Supervisor
6	Mr. NurseE	26	F	Private	2009 Oct	2009 Nov	80 & above	Management Trainee	Nurse Volunteer
7	Ms. NurseG	26	F	Private	2007 Apr	2007 Jun	75-79	Staff Nurse	Staff Nurse
8	Ms. NurseL	26	F	Private	2007 Apr	2007 Dec	N/A*	Healthcare Associate	Medical Student
9	Ms. NurseK	25	F	Private	2009 Apr	2009 Jun	75-79	Senior Software Engineer	Online English Teacher / Content/Software Manager
10	Mr. NurseMM	26	M	Public	2010 Apr	2009 Nov	80 & above	Staff Nurse	Businessman
11	Mr. NurseMJ	24	M	Private	2010 Apr	2010 Jul	75-79	Staff Nurse	Staff Nurse

* The participant expressed that she has not gotten her licensure rating yet.

For presentation purposes, the stars on the map below show the school distribution of the seven scouted participants including the four survey informants.

Figure 6: School Distribution of Scouted Participants/Informants

“Mr. NurseR”

Mr. NurseR is 26 years old who exhibits characteristics of an introvert personality (see Howard & Howard, 1998; Boeree, nd). He says he is “like a nerd (R18)” who wants to accomplish tasks alone, does not like multi-tasking (R149), and avoids being pressured. He says that when he feels being pressured, the more that he would not be able to understand (R60). When asked if he went out to relax with friends in between his reviews, he replied “I did not have many friends (247)”. He claims, however, that he can be a team player, although he said he is more

efficient when allowed to work alone (R22). Upon further questioning, his preference can be rooted from his experience working with a group. He recounts that whenever there is a group task, nothing happens, and that he would end up doing more tasks for everyone just for them to finish the assigned task (R104, R105). He said he can work with a group if everyone is doing his/her part, yet he argues that no one would know who would be the member of the group and that if tasks were distributed individually, results were better (R106).

Interestingly, Mr. NurseR claims to be fond of reading. He says he is interested in Science and World History particularly in Astronomy, Geography, and war stories, and that habit continued even until college. He shares, "I am fond of reading. Before, the library was already about to close, and I would still be there. The librarian was already about to leave, and I would still be there (R24)." Such trait must have earned him an academic advantage, though. He says that since grade one until second year in high school, he was first honor (R42). Conversely, like some of the participants, Nursing was not his first choice. He wanted to take up Journalism (R34) as he used to write for his high school publication as a Feature Editor (R39).

Upon passing the licensure, Mr. NurseR worked as a Senior Care Assistant (Geriatric Care) in London, U.K. for two and a half years and on his return in the Philippines, he worked in a couple of call centers (R10, R11). Right now, he is

working in a health insurance company as a Clinical Review Associate and acts as a Subject Matter Expert (SME).

What made Mr. NurseR do self-review were threefold: one was of perception, second was the circumstances at the time, and third was his learning preference. He says that he has cousins who enrolled in review centers yet only passed the licensure after their fourth take. Also, during that time, he wanted to prove he can make his own money, stay within his budget, and set a low expectation from his parents so in case he fails, they would not be surprised. Moreover, he has more to say about his reasons why he chose to self-review:

(R193) I hold my own pace of learning, the way I learn, I can follow it as compared when I'll be in a review center. When afternoon comes, I can no longer understand when I study in a classroom setting..." and that (R195) "we have different learning styles. If I attend a review center, what may happen, what I think may happen, it's a classroom setting, right? I might be forced to learn how they learn in a class. Not all will learn well

Despite experiencing some challenges in self-review, Mr. NurseR was one of those fortunate examinees who got more than 80% rating in the licensure. He asserts that he does not know why but said maybe because he was able to retain what was studied as he was not being pressured. He was able to retain his style, how he answers a question, and became comfortable answering multiple-choice questions (R200). And the moment he found out from his neighbor that he passed,

he remarked "I slipped from the stairs!" (R212), and he started laughing. While he received a high rating, he did not expect it. He said "I was not 100% hopeful that I will pass. I left a room for doubt; a small 20% room for doubt" (R330).

Another interesting comment he made was:

(R228) If I fail, then there's a reason. You can't tell why, nobody knows maybe you failed because you have to learn how to deal with failure. You can't tell what happened. For me, you can't act like you're close-minded that, "I will pass, I will pass" --what if you don't? Then it will be hard to deal with.

"Mr. NurseN"

What could possibly happen if someone was just forced to accept a challenge he was not prepared to do? The story of Mr. NurseN's review unfolds this way:

Here's what happened: isn't it that when you'll take the board exam you'll attend a review center? In my case I was dared by my brother. Since he will be the one to pay for my review, he challenged me that he'll give me the money if I'll self-review (N48)" ...and I was bigheaded, so I said 'sure!' (N49), of course that's cash (N74)" ... Eventually I even realized, during the time that I still haven't taken the board exam; that I might have made a wrong judgment (N52)..., but I could no longer back off (N53).

Mr. NurseN states he is not the kind of person who will read when he arrives home; not someone who will go home early just to read. Although he says he likes the subject Anatomy and Physiology, particularly the cardiovascular system, and is amazed how the body works and is perfectly designed (N36). He claims to be part of the music ministry playing the keyboard for their church (N265, N266). He says he is the youngest of four and the only one who was still studying at the time. Initially, he started to study E.C.E. (Electronic and Communication Engineering) for a year, but claims to have been forced to shift to Nursing, or else he will not be able to continue his studies (N18).

So what he did to avoid embarrassment in case he fails, he decided not to tell his friends that he would take the board exam. Only selected few, about three of them, knew (N77). He describes self-review as “challenging (N80)”. He narrates that there were times when he just started that he would overhear his friends mention topics and then he would tell himself “Oh, I don’t know them yet! (N81)”

Incidentally, when he graduated from college he had classmates who were not able to graduate because of a review subject ‘Nursing Audit’. They were five of his close friends. Since he already started reviewing then, he was asked to give a ‘lecture’ on some (N114). According to him, “So, I took it as an opportunity to help myself, too. Actually, that was the biggest help that was endowed to me. It was the one that pushed me to review more because I was forced to study” (N170). He did that until May (N116) concurrent with his personal review. He did the teach-back

either in coffee shops, or at the house of one of them. When he was not with them, he would review on his own.

“Ms. NurseG”

(G80)...And so it was our first day, Monday. All papers were still blank and then it was my turn, Monday, because we were five and I was assigned on Monday. ‘Oh, this is what I’ll teach you, Pharmacology!’ I remarked. On every wall, there was someone assigned to write.

Such was the atmosphere in the room where Ms. NurseG and her four friends reviewed. To her, it was “challenging...it was challenging because for me I like it if I’m being challenged. There’s a thrill, and I like it when I’m thrilled (G136)”. The context of their story sprung from the structure of their curriculum. According to her, their university’s academic structure was divided into three: (1) pilot group, or students who were at the brink of being removed from the course because of poor performance; (2) regular students -expected to reach until 4th year; and (3) second coursers and transferees. She said she belonged to the regular class (G31). According to her, about $\frac{3}{4}$ of her class belonged to the Dean’s listers.

One day when they were about to graduate, they were challenged by their professors to self-review since taking the board exam nowadays is already unlimited, she said. There are no more refresher courses if you fail. It was a test on who will really pass, and who will not. Some of her classmates attended review

centers, and they did not. They even had a bet on who will pass or who will not, she said (G43).

(G72) A vacant space in the room. The books, the pencils, and papers were at the center. Around the room were manila papers posted... (G76) When you enter the room, you'll see everything. The posts had big characters... the laboratory values... (G77) Every now and then, topics on the wall were replaced. (G78)...Then there was a white board with a marker. The whiteboard had the list of the scheduled presenters. We were five. Each subject had someone who acted as a professor. (G74) The place served as our study room.

She agreed to conduct a group review with her close friends. They have been together since first year, anyway. "We were 'bffs' ("best friends forever"), and we were only separated by sleep (G264)", she affirmed. Not so long time ago, however, she says she was not like that. "Before, I was a loner. I liked it when I was alone, because I had nothing to worry about. Just myself. The time management was just with myself. I have no one to wait for (G37)", she remarked. Then she started to join her classmates. The change of preference happened when she was on her 3rd year, when they brainstormed; she was able to retain the topics better. And so, they reviewed together.

The advantages, you're only few in the group. If there's something that you can't understand, there will be someone who will teach you, because you'll be like buddy system. Then the time is flexible, the time depends on you. For example, if the consensus is not to review on Wednesday, then you can switch it to Saturday. Unlike in a review center, it's fixed. If you're absent on this day, in a review center the topic is only good for a day, they won't repeat it for you. With us, we can repeat; we repeat (G118). It was better when we did it ourselves, because it was fun" (G236). "We were like playing! (G79), she grinned.

And she has something to say about her preference:

In a review center, you have competitors and you'll be ashamed to ask if you have questions since there are many of you there. You can't say, 'Ma'am, I don't understand', you'll feel ashamed" (G237). The feeling that others might think you're an idiot when you ask something that everybody might already know, that's one of the reasons why we decided to review on our own" (G238).

The five of us passed (G134).

"Ms. NurseE"

Ms. NurseE's story is about distance, competency, and care. Here's her story.

When I was young, I was raised by my parents' teachings. That's what I am sure of, because I am a 'mamma's girl'. She guided me. She's not a nurse, but for me my values came from her. Because my father, he didn't stay that long here in the Philippines because he's a seafarer. So more on I was raised by my mommy. As an eldest child, I must be responsible. That's what I feel that until now I still have. Being the eldest, I must be a good example to my siblings. You must be responsible, you'll lead their way. So when I was still young it was like I didn't become a hassle to my mom... (E23).

Throughout the course of her academic life, she became a writer of their school publication, and then became a Core Ex-O (second to Core Commander in C.A.T. [Citizen's Army Training]) when she was in 4th year high school (E26).

Here's her description on how she fared in her studies:

In academics, I am not really part of the top students most of the time, but what I can say, what my mom told me, I am a hardworking child. I am not intelligent, but hardworking. So if there's something that I can be proud of, that's me being hardworking in my studies (E28).

According to her, her first love was H.R.M. (Hotel and Restaurant Management), but was unable to pass the entrance exams for HRM, and so she took Caregiving because the courses left for her at the time were Caregiving and Computer Programming. She chose Caregiving as her aunt is abroad and might be

able to help her work there. It was her professor, however, who encouraged her to take the ladderized curriculum from the two years Caregiving to Nursing as she was praised having a 'good performance' (E36) in Caregiving. Meanwhile, her decision to self-review was influenced by at least three factors:

- ✓ Her mom was sick at the time:

During that time, my mom was also sick. She had a kidney problem, then there's high blood pressure and chills. That's why I preferred to stay at home so I can watch over her while reviewing. At least, it wouldn't be like my family will still call me if something happened to her. So it occurred to me to just self-review instead, because I already had an idea in the pre-review at school (E86).

- ✓ She claims she already had a good foundation from their in-house (pre-review – see E104, E105)
- ✓ While her school offered a free review, it takes her two hours to get there (see E81-E84)

For Ms. NurseE, passing the board exam was something personal:

I felt that my uncle's family, who are well off, looked down at us. That's what challenged me, they looking down at my father. It was like they were on a look out if what will his children can do. They were my pressure, of my father's, because I felt that they were belittling us. That's what challenged me. They belittling my father, which I did not like. We were not close to my father side. And so when I saw our situation, I thought that it was the time that I needed to strive harder and hoped that I will be able to pass the board exam. That we will have something to be proud of, too, plus I am the eldest. It was like this is already my second course, and I still haven't started working yet. I am not getting any younger and so I needed to prove something with my studies (E120).

To make the story short, here's the outcome, "When I passed, I was the proudest of them all!"(E303). (E155) "People asked me what review center I went to. And then I said, "I didn't", and so they were surprised and asked what I did to pass. And here's the treat.

Like what I was telling you earlier...I felt my uncle became proud of me too because he attended my 'thanks giving party'. It's like, of all the graduations that I had, that was the only time that I asked for a celebration. He attended my party, and I saw him proud of me. I'm proud that I was able to do it. When I passed, if there's someone who can be a bigheaded, I can, because I was not someone who just passed, I got a good rating. I became proud (E163).

Here's her view about self-review:

It is because you studied on your own, you savor what you're reviewing because you're on your own. No one aided your review...you can explain what you studied because you reviewed every details...it's because you imagined them by yourself, and not others asking you to imagine them. You imagined them by yourself (E346).

“Mr. Nursej”

The story of Mr. NurseR can be subsumed to his learning preference – he preferred studying and reading alone which was the main reason why he preferred to self-review. What would happen, however, if someone is not used to that learning style? Below is a story of necessity, resourcefulness, and making a difference.

When I was young, I was used to imagining, to rationalize. It's like I can rationalize something that is too small. Let's say, I am a person that would look at things from different perspectives. I would have a lot of explanations (J106).

And here is the factor, however, that may have spelled out the succeeding events:

My father is a driver, and my mother is a BHW (Barangay Health Worker)... I am the fourth in the family. My older brother, he's an undergraduate in college. My elder sister, she's a graduate. My other sister is also an undergraduate, then I'm next" (J21)...“we're about 30 at home... (J192)

In trying to cope with their financial situation, he seemed to have developed and, in the long run, accustomed to a learning style:

(J34) Actually, I just don't like to read. I just listen. Whatever you teach me, I'll retain it in my mind." (J125) I will use you. You are my book." (J128) I'll use you for me to learn. You are a book that speaks.

In fact, he says:

Actually, ever since high school, I was already like that. I am not the kind of guy...isn't it normally guys would have huge bags complete with books? I am the kind of guy who would have one notebook, and everything will be there..." (J35)...I guess that my record in college...I only went to the library thrice (J47).

He doesn't simply accept what he listens to, though. Here's what he says how he does it:

(J44)...I would evaluate him if he's right or wrong."..."I'm like that. I want to oppose all the time, as much as I can stand firm with what I'm saying. When I oppose, it doesn't mean that he/she is right or wrong, I just want to know up to what extent he can support his/her word. That's regardless whether he/she is my classmate, my professor...it's just the way it is...even though I know he/she is right (J45).

And he further clarifies his learning strategy:

I don't know, but for me...they just pop-up in my mind that I'll be able to recall the scenario. I remember them because I am listening. When I listen, I really listen thoroughly. I am a fault finder in all things. That's what I was tagged. I look for errors. When I find a flaw in you, I'll target that flaw. That's my style. It's not that I would like to embarrass you, or whatsoever, but I would like you to defend yourself why you were able to say such. That was my style (J155).

In the end, he said "...me asking questions, I would listen to you...there I am able to gain more knowledge..." (J169).

In college he says his favorite subject was "Psychology" (J118). Mr. Nurse] was able to successfully develop his own learning style that would fit his economic resources. He claims "as I didn't have a book" (J116, J13), just relied on photocopy (J13), and so he "maximized whatever he has" (J117). Despite of those, he elaborated that during that time his name was one of the top of his batch. He says he was "top three, or top five" (J65). Accordingly, he narrates the main reason why he was not able to attend review:

...Actually, the reason why I was unable to attend a review center was financial. During our time, it costs P15, 000. For us, P15, 000 was already a big amount, so it wasn't like I really liked to self-review. In our school, their priority was those who went to a review center. I wasn't able to take the licensure exam as we were required to review before we take the licensure...so they can guarantee the result (J1).

And so with self-review, here's what he says happened:

It was difficult...difficult..."(J147) as "...it's like it was only then that I experienced reviewing on my own. Because my strategy was to listen, ask, then retain" (J169)...I was in a room. That was the only time in my life that I was in a room (studying)... I talked to my family not to disturb me, give me food when it's already time to eat. That's how they helped me. They did not disturb me. They gave everything, silence... (J188).

At the height of his narration, he described his experience as "...more than ICU (Intensive Care Unit), dude" (J189).

To make the long story short, he passed. He said, "People looked up on me, because not only that I did not attend a review center, I passed with two days of review..."

(J234). Yes, he claimed to have done it in two days! Nonetheless, the story of Mr. Nurse] is a story of a person with big self-confidence, and he had some recollection to share, (J218) "I looked for my name from the top...it was from the top! (smiles)... my name wasn't there...(J219) I started from the top ten. From the top ten...it wasn't there." But then he said, "But it was okay, the fact that I passed, just with that, is already an achievement. In the cream of the crop... I wasn't there. It's okay" (Silence) (J219).

“Mr.NurseB”

The very first impression that one may perceive of ‘Mr. NurseB’ is that he is a silent type. Mr. NurseB admits “There, I was the silent type. I was not the person who asked a lot” (B63).

He further shares more about him:

I grew up in a family that...how will I say it...actually, within my siblings three of us took nursing. My aunt is also a nurse. She was the one who influenced us to take up nursing. She's in the U.S., so we see her goes here she has presents for us, all those, so she once mentioned if we like to take up nursing so we can go there, too. She'll help us go there (B17).

In terms of learning style, ‘Mr. NurseB’ says he is an audio-visual learner and that he would have to see and hear it (B62) and then he would write it down in his own words (B64). Moreover, he claims that he adopts a learning strategy based on the situation and does not simply stick to one (B69, B71). He is fond of memorization though, (B31) and finds ways to remember topics (B69) such as using mnemonics to help him recall them (B66). He is fond of listening to Japanese soundtracks (B202) and finds them energizing and relaxing (B204). Being the silent type, he prefers to be alone so he can focus (B69, B70, and B71) although he says that he can work with a group if everyone does his/her part (B84). He claims that working with a group can be enjoyable although might accomplish less because of a tendency to just chat with each other (B83).

It appears that doing self-review for 'Mr. NurseB' was not a mere coincidence. What influenced him to self-review were twofold:

One was because of their pre-review (in-house review):

It's because in our school, they have a review program for us graduating students during our last semester. They reviewed us during the weekends and gave us exams afterwards, then they'll discuss the rationale" (B87)... and that a candidate will have to undergo a series of exams before they will allow him/her to take the board exam and I was able to pass (B99).

He claims that only few of them reviewed in a review center because students already felt contented with the school's in-house review (B117).

Another was the influence of her two sisters, "I told myself, it's okay because my two sisters also did self-review. (B91, B92)... "My sisters did not review in a review center" (94). When asked up to what extent his sisters influenced his decision, he responded:

A lot... they influenced a lot. It's like it runs in the family" (B107). "...Both of them passed the NCLEX, too..." (B230). "It's like I was confident that I can make it in the board exam because my sisters also made it. I saw myself to be like them. I told myself that I can do it too I just needed to focus in my review and I can do it, too (B108).

Like his sisters, he also applied his strategy when he took and passed NCLEX-RN® (B230). He affirms that self-review for him was "fulfilling" (B128), and

that made him believe that when faced with difficulties, he can find ways to deal with them on his own (B230). Self-review for him, however, has its downsides:

Perhaps, if there was anything that I would have changed, or added, that must have been to review with my friends. Perhaps, I found my review routine...I found it boring somehow because I was alone. Maybe if I tried it with my friends who are also serious in reviewing, maybe I would have appreciated it more because of course we can share our best practices... (B235).

Although he says that with self-review, “you can manage your time and can review anytime, anywhere” (B152).

“Mr. NurseO”

The story of Mr. NurseO started from his dream:

First off, my dream was to become a doctor. Actually, that drove me to become a nurse, but apparently being a physician or a doctor really needs brains and guts, and I don't have much of them, so I just took up a course in line with nursing because I believe even when I was still young that health is really one of the important things in life that you can share, or you can do for others.... (O14).

With regard to his family background, he narrates:

My mom's dream was to become a doctor as well, so I adopted that dream to become a physician, but she decided to take up another course, or another profession which is teaching, but she's still pursuing to become a PhD..." (O15). My mom is working at UniversityL. We're three children and I'm the middle child. My brother is taking up Law at UniversityE, but I'm very lucky and blessed that my little sister is now taking up B.S. Biology at UniversityA. She is going to pursue my failed dream of becoming a doctor" (O16).

Mr. NurseO says that he is not a people person and would rather be praised in private than in public (O39), and that he says that he is the "type of person that would prefer to memorize" and is "not good with analytical situations" (O22). When he started college, he claims that he was a typical student that would sleep in class, studies a little, hang out with friends and had difficulties when he was in first and second year as he had vices back then like smoking and drinking (O18), although that changed when he was in 3rd and 4th year as he was blended with, and influenced by, his bright and competitive classmates (O32). He further explains:

...during the course of my stay at UniversityC since it's a Born Again Christian institution, I stopped those vices. My life started to go well...no more smoking and drinking. I tried to become a more responsible person though I am not really into leadership that's why I was surprised that I became a supervisor, but definitely what I have learned in that university was that, of course, you shouldn't settle for something less. You should always look up and beyond. You must always have a goal, but definitely it must be feasible... They trained us to become future leaders that's why...although I was not that competitive when I was in college, maybe I was able to adopt the environment that we were born to become a leader (O18).

In understanding the reason why he had to self-review, the participant offers some context: The late payment –

Taking up B.S.N. is really costly and I was not the only child who was studying at tertiary level (at the time). I have my brother and my younger sister. After graduation, we were really on a tight budget. My dad was expecting income, but it didn't materialize. My dad is a C.P.A (Certified Public Accountant), he has clients that don't pay him timely (O49). I wanted to attend a review center, but I couldn't. I tried to ask assistance from our relatives abroad, but during that time I think there was recession in the U.S. and so we were on a tight budget... I had low morale. My classmates already started their review, and I was not with them. I wanted to have a job even just in a bake shop to earn. Then after three weeks there came an opportunity in a call center. I applied and then after three attempts, I passed (O50).

When Mr. Nurse0 was reviewing, he was working at the same time. He aired, "I didn't have a choice but to self-review" (048). Being new at his work, he claims there were some pressures, and challenges:

(055) I was already decided to take the board exam. Before I started to work, we had an in house review for about a week to give us updates, share information, and so I attended that. After that, I was on my own...Then I told myself that as long as I haven't passed the board exam, I won't have a right to communicate or go to our school because, of course, I was ashamed. I felt that I would be the only one who did not attend a review center, and so I was the only one who had a chance not to pass. I was the only one who did not enroll in a review center, and knowing that my school is one of the top schools in Manila in the lower bracket. I had low self-esteem back then because I felt that I will be their only failing student. So I did not go to school, I was alone. No communication with anyone else even with my classmates. I was really on my own.

As expected, Mr.Nurse0 says that he didn't have syllabus or pattern of what will appear in the exam (033) and there was pressure as his workmates started to tease him that he might be the only one who may not pass because he was with them and his classmates were reviewing (039).

(091) Actually, the most challenging was that I just came from my shift at work back then. I was at closing 3-12 midnight so I asked my previous supervisor if I can be transferred to the opening shift from 8 to 5 so I can make it on time in the exam so I had 8-5 AM for two days and I was working alone because my team mates had a different shift which was 3-12. So what I only brought for that 8-5 shift was an energy drink and Paracetamol so my head won't ache. I just came from shift then.

And so after those tales and stories, in short--he passed. Here's some blissful treat:

(064) I cried on the bus. (065) My name was in the list! Our school got a 100% rating". (0112) I was proud. My self-confidence was boosted. I could now enter the school premises with pride... I saw my parents very proud of me (0114). My parents hang a big tarpaulin bearing my name at our house and the high school where I studied at (0117). During that time, our finances were already okay. There was just really a late payment with my dad's client at the time (0118).

For him, with self-review:

(081) Hard work beats talent when talent does not work hard. Hard work beats Talent." "...I proved to my parents that they had the right decision to have trusted me...maybe that's also the reason of what I am right now, I mean I'm confident. I became courageous (0193).

✚ Sources of Evidence

This section describes the sources of evidence recommended by the literature which the researcher subscribed to meet the aims of this thesis. The first portion will be a discussion on the extant literature on sources of evidence for Case Study approach, followed by the sources of evidence that were used in this study.

❖ Sources of Evidence in a Case Study Design

There are several sources of information that can be used in a case study (Yin, 2009). According to Yin (1989), case study approach typically combines data collection methods such as archives, interviews, questionnaires, and observations (either direct observation and participant observation). The literature mentions the importance of using several data sources in a case study in order to limit the effects of one interpretation of one single data source. If the same conclusion can be drawn from several sources of information, i.e. triangulation, this conclusion is stronger than a conclusion based on a single source (Runeson & Host, 2008, p. 13). Combinations of interviewing, observation, and document analysis are expected in much social science fieldwork. Studies that use only one method are more vulnerable to errors linked to that particular method" (Patton, 1990, p. 187-188). In this study, the sources of evidence that were used were survey questionnaire through email, face to face interviews, archival documents in the form of review materials, and participant observation. Their justification of use will be discussed shortly.

❖ Justification of Sources of Evidence Used

In this research, there were decisions that had to be made and steps that had to be taken for each source of evidence as regards what to utilize and up to what extent to utilize such source given the time and the capacity of the researcher. The reader will notice shortly that the sections of the 'Sources of Evidence' and 'Data Gathering Procedure' are intertwined because the use of those sources will be justified in the context of the circumstances in data gathering procedures. Very briefly, it would have been preferable, and even ideal, to have acquired and utilized all recommended sources of evidence, however, as what Runeson & Host (2008, p. 14) say, in many cases the researcher must, to some extent, base the details of the data collection on what data is available.

❖ **Access to Participants and Availability of Archival Documents: A Situationer**

Meyer (2001) says that the choice of data collection procedures should be guided by the research question and the choice of design. However, she also admitted that the choice of data collection methods is also subject to constraints in time, financial resources, and access. Indeed, one of the major issues during data collection phase was the accessibility of participants, as has been mentioned, and of the documents. There were two main reasons for this: First, during the initial search, finding one prospective participant was a rare-find. By the time the researcher found one, looking for a possible addition to the list of participants was a real challenge. Self-reviewees who passed the licensure were not usual, atleast, in

his area and during the time of scouting. All of the prospective participants that the researcher found were working at the time. This meant that the researcher had to act instinctively and strategically. In the researcher's mind, he opted to send an online survey-questionnaire (out of the interview guide) first so as to get an initial data while he was still establishing rapport for him to secure an interview. This way, he would have already gathered some data should there was a need to change the research design. Establishing of validity and reliability would have come afterwards. That was part of the strategy, although with those who allowed an interview, the researcher found that most of the interviewees did not browse the interview guide prior to the interview. Nonetheless, the Interview Guide was found useful for those who preferred an online survey instead of a personal interview.

Second, with regard to documents---the initial experience in scouting of participants in majority of the nursing schools unfortunately found that majority didn't have a record of those who and who did not enroll in review centers. With an exemption of two schools, the researcher could not rely on school records when it comes to establishing self-reviewee's records. In addition, while the researcher showed a formal letter from his graduate school to seek assistance, there was some reluctance to give out such data. In fact, in P.R.C., the researcher was asked to secure a letter from the Board of Nursing, approved by the Commissioner of the P.R.C., before the researcher could have gotten (this course was not pursued consequently) some data with a fee by the page.

Source #01: Interviews

“Much of what we cannot observe for ourselves has been or is being observed by others...Qualitative researchers take pride in discovering and portraying the multiple views of the case. The interview is the main road to multiple realities”

~ Stake, 1995, p. 64

Much of the data in this research relied on interviews as the primary data collection method. All of the seven case participants were interviewed. It provided a way of collecting information on and finding out about things that the researcher was not able to directly observe (Patton, 1990) to “understand the participants’ experiences and reconstruct events in which the researcher did not participate in” (Rubin& Rubin, 1995, p. 1). According to Anisimova and Thomson (2012), in-depth interviews are also valuable for researching people with busy lifestyles who would be unlikely to attend a focus group (p. 99) such as these participants.

For this study, the interviews served several of the purposes listed by Lincoln and Guba (1985, p. 268):

- Obtaining here -and-now constructions of a phenomenon
- Reconstructions of previous events
- Projections of the future
- Verification and corroboration of data from other sources (triangulation)

Given that the majority of the interviewees have not met the researcher before, the issue then of building trust between the researcher and the interviewees became

apparent and very important. Like that of Meyer (2001), the researcher addressed this issue by several means:

1. He established a procedure of how to approach the interviewees. In most cases, the social networking site Facebook was useful and convenient. As majority of young professionals, which the participants belong to, have Facebook accounts, the researcher proactively giving out his Facebook account helped confirm and verify his identity and alleviated, possibly, some safety concerns. The researcher communicated his research goals, the need for the research, the interview process (parts of the interview, and how the transcripts will be stored and used, etc.). See "Ethical Consideration".
2. In almost of all them, referencing the person who referred them to the researcher was helpful because those referrers served as a bridge bypassing some of the trust and possible security concerns of the participants. The referrers were composed of (a.) the secretary of the dean's office of the participant, (b) co-workers of the researcher whom the participants personally know of, (3) friends and/or acquaintances of the researcher.
3. In most cases, the person who knew the participant would introduce the researcher first to the participant. The researcher then manifested his intentions, explained the topic, the role of the participant, and entertained

initial questions and then an exchange of contact information normally commenced afterwards. From there, negotiation took place as to the details of the interview.

4. The researcher made sure that the participants were made aware that he/she can choose the place and time of interview and that the researcher was willing to follow his/her preference. That was done proactively and at the outset of the invitation. The intention was to make the interviewees aware that the researcher acknowledged feelings of hesitations thus make them feel comfortable, safe, and in control. Places of interview ranged from the participant's house, office, and most of them were in coffee shops and/or fast food and restaurants.

5. Lastly, from the start, the researcher built trust by making the participants aware of how he intended to use and store the information as an assurance of anonymity. To establish 'belongingness', he also proactively mentioned that he also passed the licensure through self-review and discussed the intention of sharing their experiences and strategies for other N.L.E. reviewees' use. Somehow, it was important to connect that the study will not only be done to satisfy a degree requirement, but make them feel that whatever they would share may be of use by other N.L.E. reviewees' review. That helped set the stage, started a conversation, until the researcher was able to negotiate an interview.

The central purpose of interviews is to engage in dialogue with participants to elicit their descriptions and perceptions of themselves and their experiences according to the research questions (Merriam, 2002). More importantly, interviews reveal how case study participants construct reality and think about situations, not just to provide the answers to the researcher's specific questions and own implicit construction of reality (Patton, 2002, p. 12). It would have helped establish credibility on the output. To accomplish this, Cohen (1984, p. 225) recommended open-ended questions because if "were we simply to pursue a schedule [of interview questions] of our own devising, we would then be displaying the contrivances of our own minds, rather than discovering the minds of those we want to study". Hall (1999) even goes on by recommending on keeping the questions unrestricted, those that require paragraph answers stating that if the informant goes off on a tangent...this often leads to very useful information that we didn't know was needed. Moreover, King (1994, p. 15) recommends that one has "a low degree of structure imposed on the interviewer, a preponderance of open questions, a focus on specific situations and action sequences in the world of the interviewee rather than abstractions and general opinions." In this research, however, Semi-structured type of interview was used because some questions were predetermined yet it left space for probing beyond given answers (Berg, 2004). With the use of semi-structured interview, the researcher, being a newbie in this field, was able to focus on the questions that he found relevant to his goal—

that is, making a document regarding the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer". Questions that were asked were "open", i.e. allowing and inviting a broad range of answers and issues from the interviewed subject, and "closed" offering a limited set of alternative answers (Patton, 1990). Even when the researcher prepared a set of questions, he built his next question from the response of the participant and skipped some questions when it was already answered in other sections within the interview. The interview questions were not fixed, it evolved as one interview progressed towards the next considering the emerging understanding of self-review. In the words of Erlandson *et al.* (1993, p. 113) "...data analysis does not occur in a vacuum". For each interview that was conducted, relevant topics and concerns emerged: not only about concepts within self-review, but also about the interview guide as well (Folkestad, 2008). As the aim of the interview was to identify and describe the background, experiences, strategies, and traits, collection of data from other participants was extended when the variation was felt to be under represented and then cut short when the researcher felt that no new material was forth coming (Cope, 2002). After all, qualitative inquiry is based on "informational, not statistical, considerations...Its purpose is to maximize information, not facilitate generalization" (Lincoln & Guba, 1985, p. 202).

○ **Source #02: Email as a Research Tool**

Merriam (1988) concurs stating, "A case study can also include data gathered by a survey instrument... [The survey] responses would form part of the database

for the case study” (p. 8). Here, what helped resolve the first problem was the use of email. Email, as a way of data collection through a survey-questionnaire (modified Interview Guide), was found very useful as:

(1) It solved the initial barriers of trust, possible security concerns and accessibility on some of the participant-informants. While majority were cooperative even at the outset, the prospective participants were composed of guys and girls and some could be understandably reluctant to allow a personal interview until they knew the researcher better and felt he could be trusted. And so the researcher had to be dependent on starting the data collection through other means before having built sufficient trust and time.

(2) These informants/participants were working at the time and have their own private lives. Also, one of the informant/participant was already based in the province, while another flew abroad at the time of research and so while they studied here in Metro Manila, were not accessible at the time of research. While they have their own self-review stories, for the purpose of presentation, the email survey informants were not regarded as case study participants, but rather part of the additional sources of evidence to help triangulate and add some more perspectives to the statements of the seven interview case participants.

Email as a Research Tool: more justification

Over the years, researchers have identified challenges associated with the observation and in-depth interview methods, including cost, time, and limited

access to research participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005; Gubrium & Holstein, 2002; Kvale, 1996; Miles & Huberman, 1994; Patton, 2002; Strauss & Corbin, 1998; Taylor & Bogdan, 1998). The researcher, in this case study, was not an exemption. While the common method was to utilize interview as much as possible, the researcher found email in the form of online survey-questionnaire, which was tailored from the interview guide, an invaluable tool in data collection. Meho (2013) posits that with an estimated 800 million Internet users worldwide (Internet World Stats, 2005) and thousands of scholars utilizing the ease of access to many of these users, online research has become a field in its own right, boasting a number of peer-reviewed journals. It was found that e-mail interviewing offers unprecedented opportunities for qualitative research, providing access to millions of potential research participants who are otherwise inaccessible. The method can be employed quickly, conveniently, and inexpensively and can generate high-quality data when handled carefully. Semi-structured e-mail interviewing can be a viable alternative to the face-to-face and telephone interviews, especially when time, financial constraints, or geographical boundaries are barriers to an investigation. Using e-mail as a research tool potentially offers researchers many advantages such as easy access to world-wide samples, low administration costs (both financially and temporally) and its unobtrusiveness and 'friendliness' to respondents (Selwyn & Robson, 2004). Researchers who utilized email as a collection method include Kennedy (2000); Karchmer (2001); Meho and Tibbo

(2003); Kim, Brenner, Liang and Asay (2003); Hodgson, (2004) and Lehu (2004). To help establish authenticity, email headers (see Al-Zarouni, 2004 about tracing email headers) were kept and Facebook conversation/s were saved.

Survey-Questionnaire informants:

At this juncture, the researcher will introduce to the readers those informants who were sent an online survey-questionnaire. The use and justification of their inclusion were already presented in the preceding sections.

Note: Complete verbatim responses can be found in **Appendix E**.

“Ms. NurseL”

Ms. NurseL is a jolly and a good looking woman who always wears a smile whom the researcher met at work. Originally, the plan was to have an interview which she already agreed upon, however, during the day of the actual interview, something happened at the site and so she said that a survey-questionnaire would be preferable instead. An attempt was made to secure another interview schedule, however, it has been agreed that since she already answered the questionnaire in detail, another interview of the same set of questions and nature will just be redundant.

According to her narrative, the reason why she had to self-review was because at the time, she already started taking Medicine units. She expressed that “Choosing self review for me was a necessity since I can't afford to go to a review center because I was a 1st year medical student back then” (L7) and so she opted to

self-review instead as she “didn’t have a choice” and “there was no time” to apply in a review center (L15). She described her experience this way: “Self-review: Epic! One of those things that you thought you can never do, but when you finally did it it feels like you’re Superman and kryptonite can't hold you back” (L12).

“Mr. NurseMJ”

In the middle of this research, the researcher changed job, and one of his new co-workers mentioned about Mr. NurseMJ. She said they were classmates and she knew Mr. NurseMJ did self-review. The co-worker introduced the researcher via a phone call and then correspondence was made via SMS, email, and social networking site. Due to distance and accessibility, the informant could only agree to a survey-questionnaire. The way Mr. NurseMJ described himself was that he is inquisitive, nature-lover (MJ1) and even branded himself as “weird” (MJ3). According to Mr. NurseMJ he self-reviewed with the opinion that fours years of studying is already good enough (MJ5). He said self-review allowed him to study anytime, read books as much as he can, need not wake up early to go to a review center, and can focus on subjects (MJ13). He termed what he did as a “great achievement” (MJ17).

At the moment, Mr. NurseMJ already finished his master’s degree and is already based abroad working as a nurse.

“Mr. NurseMM”

Mr. NurseMM was introduced to the researcher by a co-worker from his previous company. The co-worker said Mr. NurseMM graduated from a top university and is very good in his studies. During the month-long time of negotiation via SMS, email, and social networking site to secure an interview, Mr. NurseMM flew abroad for a family business trip and he had to stay there for another month so he preferred a questionnaire due to his hectic schedule.

In the case of Mr. NurseMM, he said he worked immediately after graduation and didn't want to spend money for a review center (MM5) stating it was very challenging in terms of time management and resources (MM10). He narrated that no one knew he was already reviewing and he never informed anyone about his decision and/or even taking NLE because he wanted to surprise them (MM8). He openly stated though that he personally believed that he came from an institution with strong educational foundation (MM32). Mr. NurseMM graduated from a premier university. As to his review experience, he said, "It was priceless!!" (MM18).

"Ms. NurseK"

During the initial phase of scouting, Ms. NurseK was one of the possible participants he found in one of the licensure forums in the internet. In the forum, an N.L.E. examinee posted a question seeking for ideas and tips on how to self-review in the N.L.E. Ms. NurseK eloquently answered the question stating she reviewed on her own and explained what she did in the forum. Fortunately, the

forum had a way to contact its members so the researcher created an account, sent an email with his intentions, and left a contact number. After some waiting, Ms. NurseK left a note and confirmed she did self-review and then agreed for a survey-questionnaire. The researcher did make attempts to secure an interview via SMS, email, and social networking, however, due to the nature of her work, among her other personal reasons; she could only allow a survey questionnaire.

The way Ms. NurseK described herself, she used to consider herself a loner but has outgrown it during the course of time (K3). She had a remarkable educational background graduating as a valedictorian in high school, a semestral dean's lister, and was part of the school publication as editor-in-chief (K2). She self-reviewed because of her study habit, for financial reasons, and convenience (K5) and stated that self-review allows a reviewee to have the "flexibility to focus more on your weak areas" (K17). Although she admitted to have doubts in passing the licensure through self-review (K22), in her words her experience with self-review "...was a truly enriching experience where the impossible became possible through confidence in one's knowledge and capabilities" (K20).

Note: These informants may have given other valuable, rich insights and/or clarifying and more probing questions may have been asked should an interview with them was secured. In hindsight, however, being restricted by time and his own capacity as a researcher, the survey helped boost the attainability of the analysis of

the already bulky data while, at the same time, still including their valuable insights and experiences in the study. It is important to note that the study used the responses shared by the survey informants as an additional source of evidence. They helped triangulate and/or negate the responses of the seven case study participants. As Glick, Huber, Miller, Doty and Sutcliffe (1990, p. 423) brilliantly put it --- “an important advantage of using multiple informants is that the validity of information provided by one informant can be checked against that provided by other informants”. It is in that thought and purpose why they were included.

○ **Source #03: Documents/Archives**

Examining the review materials was part of the research strategy, although here the available documents were found limited. They were, however, deemed helpful in a number of ways. First, and most important, the exposition of chosen review materials and why they chose those materials were important for the practical output regarding the “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer”. Second, they were used as inputs to guide the interview. Third, the documents were helpful in counteracting the biases of the interviews (Meyer, 2001). The researcher, however, did not get to see all materials. Some of the participants could no longer provide their review materials. An explanation could be partly due to the fact that in reality, review materials are often passed down from one reviewee to another. Some of the participants already shared their review materials with someone else; some just borrowed them so they had to return them; others were no longer to be

found. Runeson and Host (2008) cautions that it is important to keep in mind that these documents were not originally developed with the intention to provide data to research in a case study. As some materials were missing, Flynn, Sakakibara, Schroeder, Bates, and Flynn (1990) say that whatever there is must be combined with other data collection techniques in order to obtain missing historical factual data. Indeed, these documents gained meaning and utility when they were corroborated with other sources of evidence.

○ **Source #04: Participant Observation**

Guba and Lincoln (1981) advocated the central use of observation in qualitative research to maximize “the inquirer’s ability to grasp motives, beliefs, concerns, interests, unconscious behaviors and the like. Observation allows the inquirer to see the world as his subjects see it, to live their time frames, to capture the phenomenon in and on its own terms, and to grasp the culture in its natural, ongoing environment” (p. 193). Also, the major strength of direct observation, according to Adler and Adler (1994), is that it is unobtrusive and does not require direct interaction with participants. Observation produces rigor when it is combined with other methods. When the researcher has access to group processes, direct observation can illuminate the discrepancies between what people said in the interviews and casual conversations and what they actually do (Pettigrew, 1990). According to Waddington (1994), there are four ways in which an observer may gather data:

- (1) The complete participant who operates covertly, concealing any intention to observe the setting;
- (2) The participant-as observer, who forms relationships and participates in activities, but makes no secret of his or her intentions to observe events;
- (3) The observer-as-participant, who maintains only superficial contact with the people being studied; and
- (4) The complete observer, who merely stands back and eavesdrops on the proceedings.

In this study, the researcher used the second and third ways of observing, and they were only partially used-- partial because they happened after the fact of the review itself. The use of the participant-as-observer mode was limited in the study. There were two reasons for this. First, and most significant, the interviews happened after the fact. The review already happened by the time the interview was conducted. Three of the participants, however, were his workmates. During training, the researcher and those three were in the same room. He was able to observe their personalities and how they interact with others.

Also, during the time of analysis, the researcher talked with them from time to time. For the most part, however, the researcher had limited time available for collecting data in this manner, and that was partly can be attributed to the number of participants and timeframe of this study. Interviews made more effective use of

this limited time than extensive participant observation. As observer-as-participant, he observed the participants during interviews, their non-verbal cues, the way they answer, and their choices of words, to the least. Of primary importance, Bogdan and Biklen (1982) add, is learning to understand human behavior from the subject's own frame of reference. This can only come about through what Clegg (2003) terms as an 'ethical relationship' which involves accepting that the other person has a point of view which, whether you agree with it or not, is valid to that person and worth listening to. It can also be said that the researcher consciously asked problem-oriented questions in order to expose those cues. All these observations gave him an opportunity to help validate, although not conclusively, the data from the interviews.

✚ Data Collection Procedure

When conducting a case study, Yin (2003) identified "Three Principles of Data Collection" that can maximize the benefits of the aforementioned six sources of evidence. The first is to use multiple sources of evidence, which, if done properly, enables data triangulation (Bourgeois & Eisenhardt, 1988; Rowley, 2002; Yin, 2003). By using multiple sources of evidence, the researcher was able to gather data which can add credibility to the study and helps to avoid "tunnel vision" (Verschuren, 2003) and gave him more confidence about concluding what had transpired than had he relied on a single source alone. The second principle is to create a case study database. Yin (2003) recommends keeping the data or evidence

and reports separated. The third or the last principle is to maintain a chain of evidence, which increases the reliability of the information. This way, the data will make sense as a whole.

Below is a diagram that shows the data collection procedures in this study:

Figure 7: *Data Collection Procedure Diagram*

As a whole, the following steps were employed in data collection:

- 1.) Scouting of prospective participants was started upon approval of the research topic by the thesis panel.
- 2.) By the time the researcher found the initial set of participants, approval was sought either from the school administrator/dean's office for those scouted from the academe, or from the individual participants themselves (those who were scouted either from referral, personal acquaintance, or via online). By that time, negotiation took place to secure an interview which, as it turned out eventually, 4 out of 11 of them chose an email survey questionnaire instead.
- 3.) Consent forms were secured (initially forwarded via email, and then face to face).
- 4.) Initial interview was done, review materials were viewed and examined, and participant observation was conducted. Survey questionnaire were sent out via email which helped triangulate data gathered from interviews.
- 5.) Interviews were recorded via a generic digital recorder. They were eventually transcribed and stored in a secure database (saved in a secure email, and stored in a laptop hard drive with password, and in a USB with Bitlocker drive encryption as a back-up). Survey questionnaires were retrieved via email and the review materials' photographs were stored the same way too.

6.) Preliminary data analysis was started every after interview because of two reasons: First, the type of this case study was both explanatory and exploratory. The preliminary analysis was carried out to identify some topics that may not be found in the Interview Guide, but were brought up in the conversation by the participants. If new topics were found, new questions derived from them were added in order to explore and/or confirm the answers to these topics with later participants. The interview process was then in a continuous refinement for some time. Second, preliminary analysis served as a checkpoint if an additional participant will still need to be scouted to satisfy data saturation. As needed, the researcher went back to scouting of another participant until saturation was reached.

7.) When saturation was reached, the researcher then went back to the database. All identifying information such as participants' names and their respective schools were edited out and replaced with pseudonyms.

❖ **Handling the Bulk of Collated Data**

Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2011) say that while researchers who adopt an objectivist/positivist approach to the social world, and who consequently adopt 'structured approaches' to data collection, drawing upon methods such as surveys and questionnaires, may produce data that while being perhaps 'weak in reality', it is nonetheless data that may be 'susceptible to ready organization'. Qualitative researchers, on the other hand, while being free to be more creative in their choice

of methods, often end up with an enormous amount of data, while being 'strong in reality', may be notoriously difficult to organize' and that the researcher can "expect to be overwhelmed with the sheer volume" (Glesne & Peshkin, 1992, p. 131). Such was the same reality the researcher immediately faced (and perhaps by all researchers who adopt a qualitative approach). The collated transcripts were just enormous. As Patton (2002) warns, qualitative research is "time consuming, intimate, and intense" (p. 35). At the outset, the collected transcripts were easily comparable with the collated survey-questionnaire answer sheet from the four survey informants. There was a big difference in data. Being a newbie in research, looking at the transcripts, to be honest, were just too many to handle aside from the answers were from shifting angles and points of view of diverse participants. Worries such as "how will they be treated and presented?" were part of the initial considerations. As the interviews progressed and more data came in, the researcher had to find a strategy on how to handle them. The following strategies were used:

- As suggested in the literature, a database was established. The interview recordings were transcribed in Taglish (Tagalog-English) in full.
- What greatly helped were the preset research constructs, or initial set of subjects of interests, developed from the review of academic literature and out of the researcher's experience in self-review. At that point, there were reservations on other possible constructs that may emerge. Transcripts that

seemed not fit to the preset codes were set aside and grouped together and were assigned another code. The transcripts were transferred to M.S. Excel file where sorting, filtering and data validations were done. They were organized by case participant, by attribute, by category, and sub-category in the master file. The transcripts were reduced (Miles & Huberman, 1994) and translated in English afterwards and reference numbers were assigned per statement. As new categories emerged, then adjustments/additions were done.

- Out of the master file, two further strategies were done to segregate the data and the researcher termed them as “Vertical” and “Horizontal” banks. The chosen terms were just personal. “Vertical” was a “reduced data (Miles & Huberman, 1994)” of translated statements (with references) per participant per M.S. Excel sheet which was in anticipation for the “within case” analysis afterwards; whereas, “Horizontal” bank pertains to a collection of all responses grouped together for a specific topic across all participants in anticipation for the “across-case” analysis. For instance, the topic on “Dealing with the Bulk of Topics to Cover”, all responses for that particular subject per participant were grouped together in one M.S. Excel sheet (Horizontal). Hyperlinks were embedded and a main sheet with the main topics (with hyperlinks on them) was created for convenience in toggling back and forth to the main page.

As a guide, reference codes were tagged as shown below:

Participant Alias	Reference Code	Sample
Mr. NurseR	Starts with R	R1
Mr. NurseN	Starts with N	N1
Mr. NurseJ	Starts with J	J1
Mr. NurseB	Starts with B	B1
Mr. NurseO	Starts with O	O1
Ms. NurseE	Starts with E	E1
Ms. NurseG	Starts with G	G1
Ms. NurseL	Starts with L	L1
Mr. NurseMJ	Starts with MJ	MJ1
Mr. NurseMM	Starts with MM	MM1
Ms. NurseK	Starts with K	K1

Table 4: *Participant reference codes*

These responses have been grouped together according to the message they convey to enable data comparison, discussion and interpretation of the studied phenomenon (Patton, 1990; Seale, 1999).

✚ Ethical Considerations

Silverman (2000, p. 201) reminds that researchers should always remember that while they are doing their research, they are in actual fact entering the private spaces of their participants. Moreover, even though a research study is built on trust between the researcher and the case (Amschler, Andrews & Pradhan, 2001), Creswell (2003) cautions that the researcher has an obligation to respect the rights, needs, values and desires of the participants. In this study, observing

Ethics was not only important in terms of principle, but was also of practical and strategic importance. That means that in a study where participants are hard to find such as this, the researcher had to be extra cautious in terms of presenting the invitation to participate in the research and had to be careful in his timing and choices of words, else take the consequence of losing a prospective participant. The participants who participated in this study had their names withheld for confidential reason and were enjoined to do so based on their willingness to participate. Information on the extent of their participation, the research objectives, need for the research, the interview process and their anticipated role were explained. A copy of the semi-structured interview guide was also sent in advance for their review. They were fully informed that their participation was completely voluntary and had the right to withdraw anytime without consequence. On the survey questionnaire, and even on face to face interviews, the informants/participants were reassured that they had every right to refuse or skip a question. In addition, the data that were collected throughout this study were separated with any document that might reveal the identity of the participants. Consent agreements were handled through a form or contract between the researcher and the individual participants (see e.g. Robson, 2002; Runeson and Host, 2008).

+ Data Analysis Procedure

Glesne (2011) says that “Data analysis involves organizing what you have seen, heard, and read so that you can make sense of what you have learned. Working with data, you describe, create explanations, pose hypotheses, develop theories, and link your story to other stories” (p. 109). Being new to case study research, the researcher read myriads of available case studies or, as Zucker (2009, p. 17) advised reading, “good case studies” to help him prepare do this task. An observant spectator would agree that case study researchers adopt multiple ways of analyzing their case study data depending on the author they chose, or a combination thereof. As Yin (2009, p. 162) acknowledged, a technique that “can be applied mechanically, following any simple cookbook procedure” does not exist. In making sense of those differences, a logical explanation, perhaps, is that case studies can be applicable to any field and, in that process, may yield different kinds of data depending on the problem statement and/or the availability of the sources of evidence. As such, the collected data might be treated differently. As explained in the preceding sections, the bulk of the mined data in this particular study came from interviews and online survey questionnaire derived from the Interview Guide. Due to same limitations, as explained previously, only few archival documents were retrieved, and the participant observations were confined to three participants. Those being considered, the researcher used these two main techniques in his data analysis:

I.) Within-Case Analysis

Out of the master data, data reduction and data displays (Miles & Huberman, 1994) were done. The resultant outputs were the “Vertical” and “Horizontal” banks of collated data. From the “Vertical”, within case analysis was done for each case participant as follows:

I.) Within Case analysis: composed of four main topics of interest

A. Academic and demographic background of the participants and their review experiences

B. Self-review experience

C. Self-review strategies (Please see complete list of topics covered under this construct in Appendix.)

D. Defined traits

II.) Cross-Case Analysis

Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian (1978) theory on “Cognitive Theory of Meaningful Learning” emphasizes that people learn meaningfully by developing cross-connections between related concepts. In making sense of the responses of the case participants as a whole, cross case analysis was done. With the help of the categories collated in the “Horizontal bank” (see “Data Collection Procedure”), cross-case analysis facilitated comparison among/between cases toward exploring properties of each category (Douglas, 2003), understanding the key issues, as well

as creation and discovery of emerging themes. Taken as a whole, they formed the bulk part of the resultant output --- "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer".

On the Issue of Validity and Reliability

While the researcher, in his mind, was sure he tried his level best to follow the scientific processes of research, he very well understood that it was his responsibility to prove the validity and reliability of this research to be acceptable to the community of scholars. As in every researcher, the burden of proof was on his shoulders. For him, this quote from Miles (1979, p. 591) clearly embodies such responsibility:

"The most serious and central difficulty in the use of qualitative data is that methods of analysis are not well formulated. For quantitative data, there are clear conventions the researcher can use. But the analyst, faced with a bank of qualitative data, has very few guidelines for protection against self-delusion, let alone the presentation of unreliable or invalid conclusion to scientific or policy-making audiences. How can we be sure that an "earthy," "undeniable," "serendipitous" finding is not, in fact, *wrong*?"

Miles and Huberman (1994) argue that the problems of validity in qualitative studies are related to the fact that most qualitative researchers work alone in the field, they focus on the findings rather than describe how the results were reached, and they are limited in processing information. Researchers writing about qualitative methods have questioned whether the same criteria can be used

for qualitative and quantitative studies (Kirk & Miller, 1986; Sykes, 1990; Maxwell, 1992). As they are different from analytical and controlled empirical studies, case studies have been criticized for being of less value, impossible to generalize from, being biased by researchers etc. According to Runeson and Host (2009), this critique can be met by applying proper research methodology practices as well as reconsidering that knowledge is more than statistical significance (Flyvbjerg, 2007; Lee, 1989). One approach in examining validity and reliability is to apply the criteria used in quantitative research (Meyer, 2001). With due acknowledgement, the researcher adopted the same strategy here. Similarly, the criteria of the underlying philosophical assumptions that were examined here were objectivity/intersubjectivity, construct validity, internal validity, external validity, and reliability.

And so here they are:

- Objectivity/Intersubjectivity (Confirmability)

When Watt (2007) was conducting her research, she entered on her journal, "I cannot shake off my biases, but I can make them known (Journal entry, November 7, 2003)." Leonard-Barton (1990) claims that in qualitative research one may be perceived as, and may even become an advocate rather than an observer. As mentioned all throughout this thesis a number of times, the researcher was a self-reviewee board passer himself and, as such, he may be construed being biased. When listening to the interviews again and recollecting his feelings and insights,

the researcher found himself that there were times, although minimal, that he was leaning towards self-review appraisal. For a person who had first-hand experience, he couldn't help it. It turned out, however, that such stance is, in fact, supported by the literature. King (1994, p. 30) stated that "...with qualitative research, in seeking to describe and make sense of the world does not require researchers to strive for objectivity and distance themselves from research participants. Indeed, to do so would make good qualitative research impossible, as the interviewer's sensitivity to subjective aspects of his or her relationship with the interviewee is an essential part of the research process". Glesne (1999) says "You learn that your subjectivity is the basis for the story that you are able to tell. It is the strength on which you build...Seen as virtuous, subjectivity is something to capitalize on rather than to exorcise (p. 109). This does not imply, (and the researcher agrees), that the issue of possible research bias can be ignored. It is just as important as in a structured quantitative interview that the findings are not simply the product of the researcher's prejudices and prior experience (Meyer, 2001). Chinn (1985) states that "qualitative methods allow exploration of humans in ways that acknowledge the value of all evidence, the inevitability and worth of subjectivity, the value of holistic view and the integration of all patterns of knowing"(p. 171). One way to guard against this bias, however, is for the researcher to explicitly recognize his or her presuppositions and to make a conscious effort to set these aside in the analysis (Gummesson, 1988) and raise it to consciousness and use it as part of the

inquiry process (Reason, as cited in Maxwell, 1996, p.12). Furthermore, rival conclusions should be considered (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The researcher tried to achieve this through the following:

First, and for instance, one of the participants said that if he had resources, he would have chosen to enroll in a review center, came as a complete surprise. It was unexpected and the researcher consciously searched for similar negative evidences (Miles & Huberman, 1994) in later participants. Throughout all of the interviews, the researcher was aware from the start that the issue about review centers maybe touched on the interview, and he made it a point not to make comments about it. He focused on what the participant said and built the follow up question from them. The observant reader would notice that the follow up questions that were posed to any participant were tuned to each specific interview situation. Transcripts would show that while the interviews were structured, there were some differences in the topics discussed. Thus, the questions that were raised as actually verbalized in the interviews derived from the line of inquiry (e.g., mental framework) and did not come from a verbatim script (Patton, 2002, p.14). Most of the comments coming from the researcher were just to bridge the gap from one question to another. It was part of the strategy. After all, the researcher was aware that the interview was not about him, but of the participants. Lastly, the researcher was curious how the participants did their review and so he allowed them to just talk freely.

Another important issue when assessing objectivity is whether other researchers can trace the interpretations made in the case studies, or what is called intersubjectivity (Meyer, 2001). To deal with this issue, Miles and Huberman (1994) suggest that: (1) the study's general methods and procedures should be described in detail, (2) one should be able to follow the process of analysis, (3) conclusions should be explicitly linked with exhibits of displayed data, and (4) the data from the study should be made available for reanalysis by others. As the reader may have already noticed, the researcher described the study's data collection procedures as detailed as he could. Then, the primary data were displayed in the written report in the form of quotations and extracts from documents to support and illustrate the interpretations of the data. The transcripts (in Taglish [Tagalog-English]) are made available in the Appendices.

- Construct Validity

Construct validity refers to whether there is substantial evidence that the theoretical paradigm correctly corresponds to observation (Kirk & Miller, 1986). Similarly, Hakim (1987) says that the great strength of qualitative research is the validity of data obtained because individuals are interviewed in sufficient detail for the results to be taken as true, correct, and believable reports of their views and experiences. Thus, meaning can be probed, topics covered easily from a number of angles, and questions made clear for respondents. Construct validity is strengthened by the use of multiple sources of evidence which include multiple

viewpoints within and across the data sources. By using multiple-case studies (7 interviews and 4 surveys in this case), one can validate stability of constructs used in this research across situations given in the questions (Leonard-Barton, 1990).

- Internal Validity (Credibility)

Internal validity concerns the validity of the postulated relationships among the concepts. In other literatures, internal validity is called “credibility” (e.g. Shenton, 2004; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). The main problem of internal validity as a criterion in qualitative research is that it is often not open to scrutiny (Meyer, 2001). For instance, the question about the perception of the participants on their school was generally positive. Nobody mentioned any negative aspect. While that could very well be the case on these participants, others may have said differently. Patton (2002) advised to exercise caution “as they all may be echoing the same institutional “mantra,” developed over time for speaking with outsiders (such as researchers or media representatives), and the collective “mantra” may not necessarily coincide with the organization’s actual practices”, (p.13). In this study, internal validity was addressed by within-case analysis and searching for patterns across cases. According to Eisenhardt (1989), this is crucial to the establishment of internal validity (p. 542). The self-review participants were selected through theoretical sampling, not randomly. As shown on the research locale, the participants scouted in this study came from different schools (both from public and private) dispersed within Metro Manila and were unrelated from each other.

Details of previous interviews were deliberately not disclosed to the next interviewee in an effort to yield independent answers. That step was an attempt to qualify to what Shenton (2004) termed as "site triangulation" to reduce the effect on the study of particular local factors peculiar to one participant and Dervin's (1983) concept of "circling reality", which she defines as "the necessity of obtaining a variety of perspectives in order to get a better, more stable view of 'reality' based on a wide spectrum of observations from a wide base of points in time-space". Where similar results emerge at different participant, findings may have greater credibility in the eyes of the reader. In addition, the transcripts of the interview would show that there was also a conscious and deliberate effort for iterative questioning by the researcher in which the researcher returns to matters previously raised by the participant to extract related data through rephrased questions in order to identify any discrepancies with their answers (Shenton, 2004, p. 67).

Another consideration was that due diligence was done to meet theoretical sampling in this study, however, self-reviewees were not individuals whom the researcher could find in all places, and while there were preset criteria (i.e. purposive sampling frame) in recruiting the case participants, to some extent this study exercised random sampling. Once the prospective participant met the preset criteria, there was no pre-screening of whether or not a participant may yield rich data. Being content with the assumption that an individual who passed a board on

his/her own had a story worth listening to, the researcher intentionally avoided asking questions prior to the interview. For the most part with the end output in mind, which was the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer", needed to be applicable to most situations, and so discoveries and formal discussions happened within the interview as they unfolded before the researcher. That being said, the researcher maintained an open mind no matter what the outcome would have been. There was an anticipation, although with some guarded optimism, as Sofaer stated (cited in Kohn, 1997, p. 6), "As case study researchers, we have to be willing to be proven wrong; that means you're a scientist." For instance, there was even an element of surprise when a participant mentioned "I also thought that I should have reviewed in a review center instead" (Mr. NurseN, ref#N93]. Such strategy in data collection was found consistent with what the academic literature says. According to Lincoln and Guba (1985) random approach may negate charges of researcher bias in the selection of participants. Also, Preece notes that random sampling helps to ensure that any "unknown influences" are distributed evenly within the sample and what Stake (cited in Shenton, 2004, p. 65) describes as 'multiple voices, exhibiting characteristics of similarity, dissimilarity, redundancy and variety, are sought in order to gain greater knowledge of a wider group'. All being said, such was the handling of credibility.

- Reliability (dependability)

Reliability focuses on whether the process of the study is consistent and reasonably stable over time and across researchers and methods (Miles &

Huberman, 1994). In the qualitative parlance, it is termed as "dependability" (Shenton, 2004; Guba, 1981). In the context of qualitative research, reliability is concerned with two questions (Sykes, 1990): 'Could the same study carried out by two researchers produce the same findings?' and 'Could a study be repeated using the same researcher and to yield the participants same findings?' The problem of reliability in qualitative research is that differences between replicated studies using different researchers are to be expected. However, while it may not be surprising that different researchers generate different findings and reach different conclusions, controlling for reliability may still be relevant. The curious public deserves to know how the qualitative researcher prepares him or herself for the endeavor, and how the data is collected and analyzed (Kirk & Miller, 1986, p. 311). The study addressed these requirements by discussing and making public the researcher's experience, attention and description of the processes within the study were reported in detail, thereby enabling a future researchers to repeat the work, if not necessarily to gain the same results (Shenton, 2012). The researcher also used audio recording to ensure the recording were available for subsequent analysis by the panel. A coding frame was developed to characterize each utterance in relation the relevant topics concerning the phenomenon under study (e.g. Krippendorff, 1980).

- Generalizability (Transferability)

Mitchell (1983) posits that case studies are not based on statistical inference. The validity of the extrapolation depends not on the typicality or

representativeness of the case but on the cogency of the theoretical reasoning (Meyer, 2001). One way to increase the generalizability is to apply a multiple case approach (Leonard-Barton 1990). The advantage of this approach is that one can replicate the findings from one case study to another. This replication logic is similar to that used on multiple experiments (Yin, 1993). This research was composed of four survey-questionnaire informants and seven case participant interviews. Those numbers tried to achieve that requirement. Notwithstanding the numbers, Walsham (1995, p. 79) considers convincing the reader of the validity of a case study research is "as much a matter of rhetorical style and flair as it is of accuracy and care in matters of theory and methods". Despite the lack of a detailed step-by-step data analysis of case studies data (Miles & Huberman, 1994), and the problem of not being able to provide generalizability in a statistical sense, Denzin and Lincoln (2000, p.193) argue that case studies can be generalized, arguing that "looking at multiple actors in multiple settings enhances generalizability". Buttriss and Wilkinson (2006) maintain that generalization does not have to be universal or have wide applicability that researchers can acknowledge tendencies and patterns but these do not have to work for them to be present. Stake (1995) proposes the approach-centered on a more intuitive, empirically-grounded generalization, which he termed 'naturalistic' generalization. The researcher conceived this research to relay the message he tried to convey to his readers about self-review, however, it has to be said that the burden to demonstrate the applicability and the

transferability of the findings to another setting lies on the reader (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). While there was a conscious effort to provide a detailed and rich description of the setting of the study to provide the reader with sufficient information to be able to judge the applicability of the findings to other settings that they know (Seale, 1999, p. 45), it was not the intention to produce 'generalizable' findings in relation to self-review. Same assertion is being supported by Anisimova and Thomson (2012) when they said, "One important difference of case study from other methods is that it is not sampling research" (p. 98). Most importantly, this study contends that while the studied case participants maybe unique or may have different learning styles and personalities as compared with others, the study aspires towards producing 'transferable' insights to some N.L.E. reviewees who would like to try to self-review, or finds him/herself self-reviewing. In the end, it will still be the Candidate Nurse who may find the output as beneficial or not. As there is no easy formula, he/she would have to remember what has been said before, which bears repeating: "You will get out of it, what you put into it." And so those were how the issues of validity and reliability were treated in this study.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

“When we have to tell what we have seen and found, it is our business to give a true account, disguising nothing and keeping nothing back. But let us be careful not to speak as if our little plummets had sounded the depth of the universe.”

~ Professor L.C. Miall

(In Prins, 1994, p. 27 as cited in Boberg, 2006)

The Participants’ Tailor Fit Self-review Strategies

This section narrates the untold self-review strategies of the case participants. Seven flow charts with narrative to depict their respective strategies will be featured at the outset. They will shortly be followed by fourteen review strategies culled from the cross-case analysis of the seven participants integrating the responses of the four online survey informants.

Note: In the interest of space, only the direct English translations were used in this section, verbatim interview transcripts can be found in **Appendix E**.

✓ 1. Mr. NurseR’s “Diagram Approach”

For the reader to better appreciate Mr. NurseR’s review strategy, it would be worthy to consider knowing his learning style and line of thought first:

(R148) I am not fond of writing notes. I would just create a summary that is easy to understand. I would underline the term and write at the side of the notes for easy reference. I don't like writing while listening. I prefer to do it one at a time, else I will be stuck.

He claims he has to understand the 'whys' (R178), the mechanism why things happen, and prefers to analyze than memorize (R195). He says "If one material is hard to understand, I will look for other resources that are simpler and easier to understand" (R98) and that he has to see that mental image in his mind (R280) so he can analyze.

Mr. NurseR designed his review without a timeline (R235). He says what was important was that he understood the topic (R236). He asserts that timelines are what he hates most, and the reason why he did not enroll in a review center as he did not want any constraints. If he has a space for him to finish the review, then he would as he has focus on what he is doing (R238). His reasoning was that if he will not be able to cover all of the topics, at least those that he did cover, he is sure that he was able to study them thoroughly (R239). Mr. NurseR's review ran from April to June (two months) (R189, R190). He says he usually started his review with an exercise in the morning (R240), and reviews from either seven or eight up to eleven in the morning (R241) and that is with breaks in between (R242). He did those in their store as he was asked to watch over their store at the time. After lunch, he would continue reviewing until 3 PM, would take a break, then would resume before he slept at night (R243). He says he did that every day except on Sundays. On Sundays, he only reviewed from 1-4 PM. Meanwhile, he says that if he could not understand a topic, he would stop as nothing will enter into his brain. His view was that a reviewer should not review when he no longer understands as it

will not be effective. He has to stop, do something else and may have to go back onto it at a later time (R218). Considering those factors, here is a representation of what Mr. NurseR did. For easy recall, the researcher will call this as “*Mr. NurseR’s Diagram Approach*”.

- State the answer
- END

Figure 8: *Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach*

Depending on what Mr. NurseR was studying, he says he would create a diagram out of it, something simpler. If there was a diagram in the book, he would still make it simpler than what the book has and would try to re-write a summary or the essence out of the diagram on a piece of paper, although he says not all of the topics—only those topics that he was confused of. He would get the essence and re-write at the back of the paper without looking (R218) the way he understood the topic (R219).

The way he strategized his review was in line with his learning style. He says he practiced “situational” questions (R257), and that he needed to see the concept from the context of a situation (R258). To illustrate, he says if one would tell him the difference between the definitions of “malpractice” and “negligence” he will not be able to easily tell the difference. Give him a situation and he would easily be able to differentiate them (R260). Similarly, with Medical-Surgical, Pediatric, Psychiatric Nursing subjects, he liked to study them with cases, and with situational problems so that he could analyze what is happening (R266) and then he would integrate the others (R271). He would start his review with situational questions and if he gets confused, then he will read the definition (R268). As he writes his own diagram, he

would imagine the diagram and relate the figures as applied on the situation (R283). The way he described it, he says “it’s like connect the dots” (R284). As he went on studying, he would observe some labels or keywords, although he says that even if he sees those keywords, he would still double check with the question (R289). He would not answer right away, unless he is really sure that it is the right answer (R290).

✓ 2. Mr. NurseN’s “Blank Paper Approach”

Mr. NurseN’s Review Tenets

- ✓ “I answered by logic (N220)”
- ✓ “Get the answer from the basics (N228, N271)”
- ✓ “Don't review by memorization. Do your review by explaining it to yourself. Don't use your memory, use your reasoning (N269).”
- ✓ “Maybe if you'll be taking the exam, you can do what I did, too. It is taxing to review from a text book, but it will be well spent. It's like it will have a better outcome, as compared to you reviewing using reviewers. Those materials, they're already summarized, they will be easier, but if you will compare them with the book, it can be overwhelming, but it will have a greater outcome, you'll learn more from it.”

Mr. NurseN started sharing his review strategy by saying that the moment he graduated, he already planned to create his own reviewer (N163). He bought a

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notebook and he would read his books in college and make a summary in his notebook (N164). He claims he already had like 20% of preparation even if he was not yet sure he would take the exam (N167). He says he collated licensure reviewers, although was not able to use them as he preferred using his textbooks in college (N164). He reasons that while studying from textbooks will be a lot of work, it yields better results and you will learn more from them instead of using standard reviewers (N271). The way he designed his personal reviewer was like commercial review materials (N193, N194), though. He wrote them by system, and by topic (N195). When Mr. Nurse N was already doing the teachback to his classmates, he would take what he will discuss from his notebook, and then there is a blank paper and while explaining he would draw and illustrate them on the blank paper. He says he intentionally did it on a blank paper so he will be forced to recall what he wrote on his notebook-reviewer (N197). He designed his notebook-reviewer patterned on how he wanted to explain the topics to his classmates (N206).

Below is a depiction of what he did:

Figure 9: *Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach*

Mr. NurseN's recounts, "That was my strategy, I guess that was the core strategy that I was able to make. I had a lesson plan, I explained it to myself, I knew how to explain this and that...and when I was already in front of my classmates..." (N198). He would explain the topics while he writes on a blank paper, do the illustrations and would give the paper with his write ups to his classmates afterwards (N200, N204). He emphasized going back to the basics (N215), using logic (N220). During the interview, he gave some examples on how he defines "basics". He says "In general, you know the basic concept...for example, in Medical Surgical, you should know the blood flow, the anatomy" (N216) and then he would analyze a disease based on the basic concepts and then integrate the others (N230). When asked how he filtered a semester long of topic into a notebook reviewer, he says "...somehow you already know what's written there... you would just put them back to your brain (N273)." When he was not reviewing his classmates, he would read on his own at home (N210); most of the time on their rooftop (N211).

✓ 3. Ms. NurseG's "Vacant Space: the Combo Approach"

Ms. NurseG's review strategy was a combination of group review and self-review. As what has been presented earlier, the highlight was the group review. With group review, they had some safeguards. She says they would not start when someone is missing (G104), and the facilitator (presenter) must be knowledgeable on the topic (G94). Initially, they used fish bowl to choose whoever will be the

presenter, but said they had a problem with it as sometimes the presenter may not be well versed on the topic (G96, G93). As a presenter, the intention was to tinker each and everyone’s stock knowledge. For example, she narrates, if she gives a drug she would ask the group of the indications, etc. and so prior reading of the topic was important (G140). Once again, for the purpose of easy recall, this time the researcher will call this as “Ms. NurseG’s Vacant Space: the Combo Approach:

Figure 10: Ms. NurseG’s Vacant Space: the Combo Approach

Ms. NurseG says “...you should have read, as you will be asked...you’re all like reciting.” What happened was that it became a brainstorming (G93). Once the presenter asks the group, the presenter will be responsible to expound on the topic (G140) and then will integrate other topics related to the topic at hand (G146) until they reach the point wherein they would tackle the associated disease condition of that topic (G148).

The review itself was done from 8-5 PM (G101) and they did it from the first week of April until June (G100). Concurrent with group review was self-review at home. As she already had a study habit while in college, she did her self-review from 2-5 AM (G175). She did it as she already estimated what will be covered in group review and what other topics that she had to focus on (G172). She had a calendar of review activities at home (G179) and once done would tick ‘yes’ (G178). She studied in her room (G180) and the way she designed her room was like their review venue with the group. She says there were paraphernalia posted around even in their restroom (G187). When it comes to review materials, what they used were their college textbooks (G212) plus they would photocopy some other reviewers which they thought can be useful (G213). As a measure of effectiveness, they bought a compilation of board exam questions and they would answer them at home (G214, G215). The following day, they would discuss them together towards the end of the day (G217). She mentioned that it had to be done towards the end of the day so as not to cause information overload at the start. She reasons that atleast

even when their brains get stretched toward the end of the day, they would have learned the topics discussed prior to that (G219). When asked if they had a standard on their readiness to take the exam, she said that they compared themselves with their bright classmate. See said "...if she knows this, we should know it, too. It shouldn't be that she knows it and we don't" (G115).

✓ 4. *"Ms. NurseE's "Textbook Approach"*

Ms. NurseE claims that even before she graduated, she already had a study habit of reviewing at midnight. Once she arrives home from school, she would sleep until midnight, wake up around 12 and then study until 4 AM and would sleep again until 6 AM before going to school (E110). That became her study habit (E124). She already started reviewing on her own at the time (E112, E119) concurrent to their in-house review at school (E113, E114). By the time that Ms.NurseE graduated, as mentioned on the precipitating circumstance earlier, she was already decided to self-review (E116). So she created a calendar of review activities for the day, for the week, and prioritized her most difficult subjects (E145) to the least difficult ones (E184). She says she focused on the most difficult subjects as she felt that they are the areas that she still had to study more (E146, E227, and E314). Here's the depiction of what she did:

Figure 11: Ms. NurseE's "Textbook Approach"

Ms. NurseE says that with her review, she used a textbook like of reviewer (E205) and just used other reviewers for references or if there were techniques that she can use such as mnemonics (E204). She would look at them, but she claimed she did not read them (E203). She says that when she writes and summarizes the topics, she will just put the root-words highlighted, but when reviewing she prefers detailed reviewers so she can understand them (E210, E218). Once done reviewing on a topic, she would take the end-of-chapter assessment (E251). The questions and answers on her reviewer were separate, and

so she stressed that she could not cheat (E247). She would not read the answers and rationale as of yet and would mimic the actual board exam (E247). Whenever she gets a wrong answer, she would just remember the answer and rationale and would not go back to it later as it might just confuse her more as she already started reviewing other topics (E250). Whenever there were some delays, she would make it up to meet her target review activities (E316). If she had to take a nap that day, she would skip the nap so she can catch up on that subject (E317).

In between her review was their pre-board exam and she said she failed on the exam. In her words, "...my review was not effective" (E91) and calls it as her assessment. But that did not discourage her, though as she said, she thought that she just had to study more as she noted the questions on their pre-board exam (E91). Ms. NurseE was receptive to the common questions on their exams. She said she would notice that those topics would appear more often, and so she studied them including their nursing management, signs and symptoms, etc. and those topics that she was not sure of (E141). She said "...there I failed, and so there I focused" (E140). In addition, she says that her school made them sensitive to the board of examiners that would craft the board exam that time and so she focused on them, too (E150). Moreover, there were the trending health conditions at the time that she had to particularly be attentive to (E190, E191, and E192). She says "...it was AH1N1 back then...and the gas mask" (E191).

✓ 5. Mr. NurseJ's "Recalling Approach"

It was two days of review (J88). **Mr. NurseJ** says he reviewed in two out of three days of his leave and on the third day, he used it to rest at home (J89). As he was working at the time, he took the exam a year after he graduated and remarked "it was still fresh" (J99). Prior to his review, he says that he gathered all his notes as he is more of an OC (Obsessive-Compulsive) (J171). Acknowledging the difficulty of what he was facing, he stated that even in those two days, he had a timeline (J147). He reasons that in his four years of college, in the results of his exams, he knew his weaknesses and so he focused on them (J148, J205). To illustrate, he asserts that in Fundamentals of Nursing, in a count of ten, ten being the highest, he would rate himself as eight or nine, so he did not review it any longer (J149). On Maternal & Child and Medical Surgical Nursing, however, there he struggled and so he gave more focus on them (J150, J151). He focused on the basics and nursing actions. Mr. NurseJ reasons that 'nursing is caring' (J152). He would still remember his topics and accounts them more on his learning style and says that they would just pop up in his mind (J155). His notes helped as they were summarized the way he would be able to easily recall them (G180). It was in line with his learning style that he would ask questions as he reminded the researcher that he had memories as "...every day is meaningful to me" (J160) and that "if it's meaningful, you would remember it" (J182), and since something meaningful happened, and he also wrote

it down, same thing happened when he was studying his notes (J186). He says it was more on “recalling” (J181), and that post tests after review helps (J227) the recalling process. Here’s his chart:

Figure 12: Mr. Nurse's Recalling Approach

During the actual exam, he says that he used the test taking strategy of “elimination” and that he would always leave two possible correct answers for that particular question and that there he would start to rationalize with his stock knowledge and experience before picking an answer (J245). While he was only partly able to do it due to time constraints, he outlined what, in his view, is an ideal

self-review: “...one must identify his weaknesses first, after such is to come up with a timeframe. Of course, you know where you’re weak at. You know your personal abilities, how fast you’re able to absorb a subject matter. After identifying your weaknesses, only then you’d be able to come up with a time line” (J225).

✓ 6. Mr. NurseB’s “Traditional Q & A Approach”

Mr. NurseB said that what he did in his review was that he used a book-reviewer where he would read the topic first and then there would be 10-15 questions after every topic (B158). He stated that he prioritized the subjects that he was having most difficulty with (B199). The other reviewer he had (same author) was a pure Q & A questions (B168). If the topics were not in his primary reviewer, then he would use the hand-outs and materials he acquired from his school (B169, B170). He would usually start his review at home at their dining table, which the family was using as their study table (B180) from 8-9 AM until 12 noon, then, he would start again at 2 PM until the afternoon (B173). At night, he would stay from 7-8 PM until 12 midnight; 1 AM being the latest (B177, B173). That ran from Monday to Sunday (B178), although sometimes he said that there were some interruptions (B176). At home, only his mother and father were around so he was able to read alone (B185). He would read a topic in his book-reviewer, take sample questions, and then check the answers and the rationale afterwards. In other words, from the book, he applied what he read on the test questions (B165).

He says he also used that strategy when he passed his NCLEX-RN® (B165). When reviewing, he claimed he would not eat at the same time. When felt hungry, he would just go to the kitchen to eat (B205).

Figure 13: *Mr. NurseB's "Traditional Q & A Approach"*

Mr. NurseB says he used to listen to Japanese music to relax and re-energize (B204). He used testing strategies such as elimination, the longest word, etc. that he learned in school although he cautioned that one should still read the questions to be sure (B168). He advised to get the latest (B219), and reliable (B220) review materials complete with topics (B219) and then read the topics first then do the Q

& A and the rationale. He expressed that his review consisted of test taking strategies and his prior knowledge (B224). He also said that when he answered a question, that served as his final answer. He would not go back to check to save time and prevent any confusion as too much brooding may just lead to an incorrect answer (B245).

✓ 7. Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach

Mr. NurseO's review strategy was an espousal of his study style when he was still in college. He said he believes in the power of writing (O131) and takes time to write down questions and answers on a yellow pad or bond paper [normally about 5 pages per subject (O136) and that he would memorize as he writes them down to aid recall (O135). Once his self-made reviewer was done, he would run the Q & A again and check how he fared (O132). When Mr.NurseO makes his reviewer, the questions would come from his notes in college which consists of, for example, definition of terms (O133) and then he would brainstorm whatever he would remember about that topic. When asked how he compressed a topic of one semester into a 5 page reviewer, he says that as a student he knows what important details to include and that his college notes had special marks, extra notations (O139), highlights and so those were what he would write down (O138). Afterwards, he used a standard Q & A reviewer (a pocketbook-like of reviewer) to check for his understanding (O134). The bulk of his review was spent on Q & A using his Q & A reviewer. After he answers a question, he would check the answer

and rationale at the back of the reviewer (O176). If he answered wrong, he would dig deeper why his answer was wrong as against the answer of the reviewer (O177, O179).

Figure 14: *Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach*

He recounts that he would recheck his answer most especially if he was confident that he answered the right one, but got it wrong. He would assume that the answer of the reviewer is wrong, would critique the answer, and check other references (O180) to investigate (O181). When at work, he reviewed during breaks and/or lunches after he ate, and when he arrived home he would spend an hour or two reviewing. When he was not at work, he says he would review on a study table at home, in a quiet place, with good ventilation, where his brain can function well (O160, O161). He says he starts his review upon waking up while the brain is still 'absorbent' (O152). He reviewed from the basics (O125) although he focused on 3rd and 4th year subjects (O124, O126). His review ran from April after he graduated until a couple of days before the board exam (O86, O90) and that 60% of it was spent on Medical Surgical Nursing (O167). The rest were spent on

other subjects and those that he thought will appear in the board exam (O171). As he was working at the same time, his way of relaxation was to sleep (O150) and that whenever he had an idle time, he would sit and review (O151). In his words, "...instead of going out and having fun, me I was reviewing" (O54). A week before the exam, he extended his review hours and reviewed during his breaks, lunches, once he arrived home, and even said that he would even review while eating his breakfast and on his way to work (O95, O96).

Despite his efforts, Mr. NurseO did not escape from fear of failure. He says the very crucial part was after he took the exam and airs that "it is the waiting that kills" (O104) as he was clueless. There were some recollections as to why he answered this and that (O105). To help him cope with that feeling, he says he prayed every day and made himself busy with work so as not to entertain thoughts about the result of the exam (O104).

✚ Case Study Findings, Interpretations, and Discussion

"Now...bring me that horizon." -

Last line of Capt. Jack Sparrow (Johnny Depp),
Curse of the Black Pearl

The principal findings of this case study will center on 575 minutes and 17 seconds of interview, or equivalent to 361 single-spaced pages of interview transcripts, and 30 single-spaced pages of the retrieved email survey responses, the collated review material samples, the researcher's observations, and nothing more.

Question #01: What review strategies and techniques, if any, helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?

Note: In the interest of space, only the direct English translations were used in this section, data matrix of verbatim responses can be found in **Appendix A**.

A closer analysis of the eleven successful self-reviewees' responses provides fourteen answers:

✓ *Finding #1.a- Conduct a Self-Analysis.*

With the exception of Mr. Nurse0, one thing conspicuous in the self-reported review strategies of the case participants was being perceptive about their learning style, strengths and weaknesses, and areas that needed further enhancements before and even during the review proper. The result of such self-analysis led to and

became part of their main review strategy. Mr. NurseR tried to make his point by issuing this statement:

First, what the reviewee must do is to know how he studies, how he learns best, his learning style and depending on his learning style, then that's what he must follow. For instance, in my case I am not fond of studying for a longer period of time, but for some others they're really focused studying that they are not to do anything the whole day but to review. It's fine that way... But for me I don't like to be in a big group...Whatever they're comfortable with then they would be able to focus more on their review

When asked how long would be an ideal review, Mr. NurseJ suggested half a month per subject assuming the reviewee already identified his strengths and weaknesses (J226). For Ms. NurseE, she started reviewing random topics then took their mock board and it was from there that she found out what areas she still had difficulty with (E177). By precisely pinpointing her weak areas, she created her calendar-planner accordingly. Ms. NurseL, in another point, understood her time limitations because of her studies and coped with it by "...reading a lot and making time to really understand (my) weak points during the course of the review (L22).

✓ *Finding #1.b- Pick a strategy that best fits your learning style and study needs*

Some responses of the participants indicated that they espoused their study strategy and learning philosophy in college when self-reviewing. For instance, Mr.

NurseO mentioned that he was able to carry over his review strategy when he was still a student. He explained that he creates his own reviewer and takes the time to write down questions then their answers for about five pages of yellow pad or bond papers and while he writes, he would memorize the answer and so when he does the rundown one more time, then he would better recall the answer (O132).

Moreover, he emphasized, "Ahh I create my own (reviewer)...because I believe in the power of writing...I would write the questions and then the answers" (O131). For Mr. NurseR, the talk was about self-analysis, listening to one-self and following his learning style. He advised that it will still depend on the learning style of the person. For him, if he could not understand a topic, then he would pause. He reasoned that nothing will be absorbed by the brain if he continued. If he is reviewing a topic and he can no longer understand then he would pause, would skip that topic and just go back to it at a later time. Once he is already freshened up, then that is the time he will take it again. He counsels that the reviewee must not force himself to study a topic that he no longer understands. Continuing on reading without understanding will be a waste. He said the reviewee must rest, stop, and do something else first... (R218). Depending on what he was studying, he would create a diagram out of the topic. If it is being explained in a particular way, then he would create a diagram out of it, something simpler, he said. If there is a diagram in the book, he would still create a simpler version then he would rewrite it. He would do that to that topics that he is having a hard time with. He would summarize, get the

essence and rewrite it the way he understood it at the back of the paper without looking (R218b). For Ms. NurseE, she picked a detailed reviewer because she learns best when there is a detailed explanation and when she jots down notes she would just indicate the root words and sometimes would highlight them, but when she is reviewing, she needs to review from a detailed reviewer so she would be able to understand it. She mentioned that she would not get it if there are only labels or signs on what she is reviewing (E210).

Meanwhile, Mr. NurseN was fluid and took advantage of the situation of his classmates to review them and at the same time review himself. For example, if his classmates were about to take an exam in Anatomy, then that is what he will review them with. He used it to review his classmates at the same time review himself (N114). He later conceded by saying, “Actually it was the most significant help that was extended to me as it forced me to study...” (N170).

✓ *Finding #1.c - Prioritize and manage your weak areas.*

Eight out of eleven participants prioritized their weakest subjects first. For Ms. NurseE, self-analysis paved the way towards her focusing more on her most difficult subjects and those subjects she is not comfortable yet (E108, E146, E178). She felt that she needed more time to tackle those compared to the easier ones (E314). For Ms. NurseK, here is what she asserted, “I gave a timeframe for every topic and I would try as much as possible to squeeze in as much knowledge as I can.

However, for my weak subjects, I would allot more review time for it” (K35). Doing so reflected on her increased confidence after the review: “Before the review, I rate my confidence level as 6 and after finishing the review it was an 8 since I managed to cover as much subjects as I can especially on my weak areas” (K39). Meanwhile, Ms. NurseL said, "I concentrated on my weak points...I coped by reading allot and making time to really understand my weak points during the course of the review" (L22). She further said, "I studied test 1 and 5 first because they are my weakness then every weekends it would be test 3 and 4, the test 2 was the last one that I studied" (L26). She cited, it is an advantage of self-review as "you get to concentrate on the topics that is harder for you to understand" (L19). Mr. NurseB likewise noted and said there were some topics that he needed to place special attention to, those that he was still weak at (B199). When asked what advice he would give to future self-reviewees, the same view was reflected in the advice of Mr. NurseMM, “Manage your topic to be reviewed and make sure to focus more on a topic that you think is complicated for you” (MM37). For Mr. NurseB, if there was a nagging topic, he would prioritize it (B221). Even Mr. NurseJ, in the interest of time trimmed his review in order of priority and so with Fundamentals in Nursing wherein if he will be asked to rate himself from one to ten, ten being the highest, he would give it an eight or nine so, he no longer reviewed it (J149).

✓ *Finding #1.d - Organize your topics to review.*

Along with prioritizing and managing their weakest subjects, the participants reportedly had their own ways to organize their topics to review and it was done in two ways: First, by plotting a review timeline complete with a review calendar or a list of topics to cover in their review, and second was to create a review calendar without a timeline. The participants had their own take on each of them.

Having an advantage of starting her review prior to graduation, Ms. NurseE created her own review-calendar on what and when to review (E177, E184). According to her, she prioritized the most difficult subjects down to the easier ones. She plotted them on her calendar planner (E145). Likewise, while doing their group review, Ms. NurseG reportedly conducted self-review on topics that she thought will not be covered in their review and she created a planner and would tick "yes" once a topic was completed (G178). She mentioned that aside from their review, she also reviewed at home wherein she also followed a calendar planner for the topics that she needed to study more on (G177). Ms. NurseK, for her part, understood that the time that she had after graduation and the licensure exam was just right for her review, and so what she did was this: "...Right before the self-review, I made a schedule complete with deadlines so that I can cover as much subjects as I can before the exam" (K25). Same thing was done by Mr. NurseMM and Mr. NurseMJ. In his words, Mr. NurseMJ said, "I made a time plan and setting a goal is so important" (MJ23). For Mr. NurseMM, creating a timetable served in

balancing his work and review: “Since I was working at night and would prefer to sleep during the day, I made my own time table when to scan my review materials” (MM12). In the contrary, while both had a review calendar that guided their review, the importance of setting a timetable was directly challenged by Mr. NurseR and Ms. NurseG and they both have their own personal reasons of saying such. For Mr. NurseR, he had to really understand the topic, and timeline must be at the sideline. He underscored that he did not plan his review (R235) and did not have a timeline as long as he understood the topic (R237). He did so as it was the reason why he did not enroll in a review center to avoid any constraints. He said that if he had an ample time then he would be able to finish them in breeze as he was so focused (R238). What occurred to him was that if in case he will not be able to finish his review, what was important was that there was a greater percentage of the topics that he was able to thoroughly review (R239). And for Ms. NurseG, all members of the group review must be on the same page so everyone has to wait for each other. She argued that they did not give a timeframe for each topic. For them, what was important was that they are on the same page even if they needed to repeat the topics all over as they have different paces of picking up a topic and they needed to consider their review mates (G170).

✓ *Finding #1.e - Tailor the review duration and frequency based on individual review needs.*

The findings revealed a downside of self-review – that is, balancing between quantity and quality side of the review itself.

On the negative side, those that did not set a timetable without a bargain of a longer review duration seemed to have crammed. While pushed by circumstances, evident in the words of Mr. NurseJ was that, two days of review was not enough. In hindsight, he noted that he should have set a longer timeframe for his review and he must have gotten a higher rating. He aired that he was not satisfied with his board rating.

Ms. NurseL suggested that reviewees must stop two days before the exam although even she herself was not able to do it:

Actual board exam: deep breaths, pray and leave it to God and two days before the exam (don't review anymore). The last two days, I was not able to do (it) because...at that point...I think I still had a lot to go so I still read during the two days (L37).

Knowing the uncertainty and risk of what he had started undertaking, Mr. NurseN had to hide what he has been doing to most of his classmates and friends which, in turn, compromised his review schedule. He narrated that the fact that his classmates did not know about what he was doing was a disadvantage because understandably those that were not reviewing would go out and knowing his personality, he also wanted to go out with them and he did not want them to notice

that he was reviewing, and so he said most of the time he was with his classmates (N88).

Understanding, therefore, the context and situation of Mr. NurseN at the time, he encountered the same problem as Ms. NurseL, wherein he thought that a day before the exam he still have not read Orthopedic nursing (N181).

Having a calendar-planner based on individual review needs, scheduling the duration, time and frequency of participants review also varied. Mr. NurseR reviewed for two months from Monday to Sunday starting from 8-11 AM then resumed about 1-3 PM then would start again during nighttime except for Sundays wherein he would only review from 1-4 PM (R240-46). Mr. NurseN, as established earlier, did not have a definite time of review (N186) and would review as long as he was in the mood (N187), but he reviewed mostly after midnight until dawn (N237) and that was aside from his 2-3 hours teach-back session with his classmates (N202). Ms. NurseE's review lasted for about three months and she started her review a month prior to graduation. She studied from midnight until 4 AM prior to graduation (E111) whereas after she graduated, she studied every day from 7 AM- 8 PM with breaks in between (E125). Ms. NurseG also did their group review for 2 months (G100) usually from 8 AM-5 PM (G101) and would do her personal review from 2-5 AM (G175). For circumstantial reasons, as laid down previously, Mr. NurseJ reportedly reviewed for two days (J100), and in those two days he would review in two hours interval, and he had this notion about his

justification of what he did. According to Mr. NurseJ, he read a book that reviewing must only last for two hours interval. The max must only up until two hours otherwise it will adversely affect retention of the topic. And so every after two hours he would rest for about 30 or 15 minutes then would continue to review for another two hours. He added:

I don't review for three hours straight and why is that? It's because someone told me, I have heard him say that the brain's threshold to retain a particular (subject) matter is two hours. And so because I have heard of it, I took note of it and that's what I did (J194).

Although he commented that if he would be asked what the ideal review time is, it is two and a half months, half month per test item (J226). In the case of Mr. NurseO, he also reviewed for two months and he had this belief in studying upon waking up as doing so, according to him, the brain is still "absorbent" (O152). At work, he used his breaks and spent the remaining of his lunch time reviewing and would read about an hour or two before sleeping (O157). The same was true to Mr. NurseMM who was also already working at that time; he also studied whenever he had free time (MM27). As the exam neared, Mr. NurseO reportedly intensified his review that even when he was on his way to work, or while eating during breakfast, he would maximize his time reading (O95).

Mr. NurseB also started his review after graduation and he did it every day from Monday to Sunday starting from 8-9 AM until lunch break (B173) then would

resume around 2 PM to 4 PM (B175). He would then commence around 8 PM to 12 midnight (B173). For Ms. NurseK, she said she usually studied around afternoon to evening since she is not a morning person (K26). Mr. NurseMJ would start reviewing in the morning after breakfast (MJ24) and Ms. NurseL who was studying Medicine at the time reviewed during her available time, too:

I sucked at time management. So what I did was when I got home I (would) sleep for about three hours then I studied until 2 AM (which gave me five hours of review time) My study habit during school days was from 9 PM until 2 AM (although I wasn't able to strictly follow this all the time) over the weekends I usually get up at 10 AM, but my review started at 2 PM onwards. I usually ended up sleeping at around 4 AM during the weekends (L22).

✚ #1.e.1 – *Take time to Pause*

In the interim, in some way or the other, the participants did not engage all of their time reviewing. Saying such, they also had their own relaxation techniques. Relaxation pauses ranged from listening to Japanese music, taking a nap, going out with friends, watching amusing TV shows, reading their favorite books, eating allot mostly to relax and re-energize. Most, however, did not eat while reviewing so as not to lose focus.

On the positive side, like in the case of Ms. NurseE, having started her review early before graduation (E107, E115), she had the luxury of completing her review agenda just right on time that she stopped reviewing two days before the exam, "...when I was answering the practice exam of Saunders, I saw myself get the correct answers.

At that time, I stopped reviewing. Two days before the licensure I was already prepared” (E244). At that, she knew she already had enough.

✓ *Finding #1.f - Find your right venue.*

The physical place where the participants conducted their review varied. Interestingly, except for those who were working at the time like Mr. NurseMM and Mr. NurseO, majority reviewed at home. Themes such as “secluded, quiet, no disturbance, personally and ergonomically comfortable, well ventilated, and private’ emanated from their choices of venue.

Mr. NurseB reviewed at an area of their house which was well lighted (B179, B181); Mr. NurseMJ stated he usually stayed at one place at their reading area where it is quiet and there is no disturbance (MJ25). Ms. NurseE, who also reviewed at home was mindful of the ergonomics. She said she had to sit properly. At the time, her family was busy taking care of their store so she would be left alone reviewing. Her family members did not disturb her, she said. They would only go there to eat (E129). Whereas Mr. NurseJ also studied in his room and requested his extended family to give him privacy for the whole two days he reviewed (J192). Comparatively, Mr. NurseN reviewed on their rooftop, if not at the houses of their friends or in coffee shops, as he found it “conducive” (N212). For Mr. NurseR, he just stayed at their store during the morning while looking over their store then would transfer to their study table at night (R249), although he says if he needed

silence, he would go to their vacant house to review (R253). The group of Ms. NurseG, on the other hand, rented a small vacant room near their school where they conducted their group review (G71-78), and finally for Ms. NurseL, she at the time reviewed at their terrace and at coffee shops at night together with her friends (L22).

While the participants got their review materials from various sources and means, some of them gave their views on the characteristics of a good review material. Mr. NurseN, for example, was very vocal in saying reviewees must review using textbooks for being detailed:

Maybe if you'll be taking an exam, do the same thing. You may have to take an extra effort to review using a book, but it will be worth it. It will have a better outcome...then review using a (standard) reviewer that is already summarized. It might be easier to do, but reviewing through a book would yield better results. You'll learn a lot more (N271).

He did that since he had to “retell” what he reviewed to his classmates, he needed to get the core concepts from a textbook (N164). Conversely, Ms. NurseE did not use her books, but she favored a review material that is detailed and explanations that are clear and complete with practice sessions. Ms. NurseE said that she was able to compare them and she was able to grasp the topics better when she used a book (E194). The topics were clearer; were explained one by one

(E194, E207, E208) and the practice sessions were already included (E106). If she needed to consult other references or if she needed to get some tips or mnemonics, she would then open other reviewers, although she said she did not fully read them (E203). Incidentally, Mr. NurseB used the same reviewer that Ms. NurseE used and he underscored the importance of getting a reviewer that is “latest” and “complete” (B219) and “reliable” with practice sessions (B220). For those topics that were not in his primary reviewer, he similarly used his notes and other materials given by their school (B169).

Conversely, in the opinion of Mr. NurseR, reviewers must trickle to simple explanations (R77, R79 & R97) and such preference was expected of him knowing that he learns through association, linking the concepts and through seeing them from context of a situation. So if what he is reading is vague, he would borrow other materials with simpler explanations or look it up in the internet (R79), he said.

✓ *Finding #1.h - Maximize help from other people and exhaust available resources.*

One characteristic of the review strategies of the participants was the need to be resourceful. Resourcefulness, in this context, was embedded both as a trait of the participants as well as an invaluable tool in crafting their review.

There was, for instance, a deficiency of review materials in the case of Ms. NurseL. While Ms. NurseG did a group review with her friends, Ms. NurseL also relied on her friends. She shared, “I guess the big challenge for me (was) that I

(didn't) have that much test papers to answer on. So I had no idea how the questions were gonna be raised. That time, I relied allot from my friends since they shared their papers with me as well the answers" (L13). Further, she narrated:

My friends helped a lot! We used to have a Starbucks session where we stayed there and compared notes on how we reviewed this and that (because back then they were all enrolled in a review center) so my time with them usually started after my classes. I asked from friends for their test papers and some test taking strategies...usually we're in a group of three people... (L22).

Accordingly, Mr. NurseB and Mr. NurseMM incorporated technology into their review by using computer assisted Question and Answer type of exams (B231) and online questionnaires (MM11). In addition, both Mr. NurseR and Ms. NurseK used the internet to search for more study materials (K46, R143). Ms. NurseK said, "I sought advice usually from internet forums like 'Do's & Don'ts of test taking plus subjects where I need to focus on" (K24). Mr. NurseR got most of his review materials from his uncle who was then reviewing for the NCLEX-RN® (R254). Similarly, Mr. NurseMM borrowed review materials from his friend who attended a review center and passed the N.L.E. and consolidated everything (MM11). Aside from asking review tips and materials from her friends, Ms. NurseL also mentioned, "I sometimes go to Morayta to buy the very cheap test papers of the boards from 2000 to 2005, there I answered and tried to learn the test taking strategy that my friend taught me" (L28). In the same manner, Ms. NurseG had

their friends gave them pointers in the board exam (G121). Scarce with review materials and books, Mr. NurseJ nevertheless knew he might need his notes someday so he collated all of his notes in college and used them in his review. Acknowledging his limitations in terms of resources, Mr. NurseJ said he focused on whatever he had (J115) and maximized whatever he could use (J117). And he tried to make some more points by saying he already envisioned that he may need his notes someday (J172, J174) and that he needed to take care of his notes for future use which, true enough, he was able to use (J187).

✓ *Finding #1.i - Watch out for FAQs and emerging health issues*

Ms. NurseE talked about the value of being receptive as part of her review strategy. First, she talked about what she learned from her friend, and second was what she noticed, and later applied, from their in-house review.

First, she mentioned that her friend advised her to be aware of health related current events. She asked her friend what appeared in the exam and what area she needed to focus more on. According to her friend, as she narrated, say for communicable diseases, if there is anything to review with communicable disease they are to be the ones related to the current events. In communicable disease, what appears are the diseases for that year. During the time of Ms. NurseE, it was AH1N1. During her friend's time, it was dengue fever which was prevalent at the time (E137). And yes indeed, her friend purportedly did not fail her as the health issues at the time appeared in Ms. NurseE's licensure exam. The AH1N1 and even

the gas mask (i.e. N95). She said all of them came out (E192) including IMCI (Integrated Management of Childhood Illness) (E193). Another lesson she shared was about being receptive with the usual type and topics of the exams given in their in-house review. As she had stated, during their pre-review and on their major exams, she noticed that some topics frequently appear on the exams and so she focused on them until the time that she would review their nursing management including their symptoms. She said she took note of them and it was from there that she thought that it could be possible that they will also appear in the actual board exam. And so she reviewed them and those areas that she was not sure of yet. She also noted that some topics appeared on their mock board exam at school that she was not able to include on her self-review and so she also focused on them (E141). Ms. NurseE then underscored the competence of their lecturers in school and explained why she had to do what she did. She said the the reviewee must be receptive and mindful of what is being taught during the in-house review at school. She noted:

I believe that those in-house lecturers in our school are updated with those that will most likely appear in the actual board exam. Also, be mindful of the specialties of the clinical or board of directors that will pen the exam (E150). In those often appear in your major exams. In other words, get the bits or pieces of knowledge that often appear in your exams. I took note of them. I remembered them even if I didn't know the answer yet. Notice all of your exams, be observant as they might come out in the exam (E134).

✓ *Finding #1.J - Be Inclusive, comprehensive, and integrate other topics when reviewing.*

Another finding that showed up was inclusivity and it was manifested by participants in different ways. In hindsight, one lesson learned by some participants after they took the board exam was that they should have covered as much topics as they can. Even Mr. NurseMM when asked of his level of confidence to pass the exam, and who considered himself a competitive student and personally thinks that he came from an institution that has a strong educational background, admitted and said, “Before the review- 10- I thought I covered everything. After the review- 8- after the exam there were questions that were very tricky...” (MM36).

Same was the encounter of Mr. NurseMJ and he just then said, “I just prayed that I would pass the exam (MJ20). For Mr. NurseO, he recollected that he saw questions on Community Health Nursing that he was not able to touch on his review (O185) and so he received a lower rating in CHN. In hindsight, he said, he should have focused more on it.

Other participants indicated inclusivity by brainstorming or ensuring collective understanding such as what Ms. NurseG did with her friends in their group review (G222), considering all possible factors of a disease process like what Mr. NurseJ did when asking questions (J110-112). Similarly, at some point Mr. NurseO, when he was doing brainstorming when creating his self-reviewer notes

(O134), he acknowledged that putting one semester of topics in few pages of reviewer can be risky (O137), however, he said he was guided by his experience. He explained that as a student, he already knew the important details that he had to write down. His notebook contained special notes or highlighted texts that needed special attention (J138). Another portrayal of inclusivity was memorizing some laboratory values even though it is contrary to his learning style such as what Mr. NurseR did. For Mr. NurseR, for those laboratory values, for example, then he would be forced to memorize although he noted that they are a few of them anyways (R274). Lastly, Ms. NurseG showed it by creating notes all over her place in her room and even in their comfort room (G184). In addition, in order to cover her individual needs, she concurrently did self-review to compensate for the topics that she anticipated that would not be covered in their group review due to time constraints and review limitations (G172).

Another strategy Ms. NurseG found to be effective was topic integration. She purportedly said that whoever was assigned to facilitate the group review for the day would ask questions and would expound the topic on hand. She then explained the dynamics of it by saying:

Yes, until it came to a point wherein we would tackle the disease itself. The topics were in sequence and so we would not have to report all because they were already discussed and we already knew. It was amusing as sometimes they would speak simultaneously and so I would say “Hey, one at a time” (G148).

✓ *Finding #1.K - Execute the strategy precisely, but be flexible to contain shortcomings.*

Like all successful strategies, participants shared how they executed their review. It was evident in the words of Ms. NurseE. For her, there was a definite time of study and she had to stick to her plan. She deprived herself of texting, watching TV, etc (E234, E129) and had maintained a calendar planner which, according to her, she followed religiously. If she assigned a particular topic, say, on Monday, then she would not jump to another topic or take it on another day (E143).

Unlike Mr. NurseN who became worried when he overheard his classmates who were enrolled in review centers talking about topics he did not know yet, Ms. NurseE refrained from consulting her friends. According to her, she refrained from glancing at her classmates' practice test papers from the review centers to avoid being discouraged (E262). Moreover, if she misses on her target for the day, she would compensate (E317). In the case of Ms. NurseG, they experimented on what will serve them best in terms of who will facilitate a certain topic. She stated that at first they had some challenges with fishbowl sampling (G96). So she said they decided to just assign the topics according to the forte of who will facilitate or whoever was comfortable discussing the topic (G95). The facilitator would present the topic and was responsible in throwing questions at the group and expounding the topic by integrating other topics (G141-143). For Mr. NurseN, he said he has to be in the mood for him to study well, however, doing the teach-back to his

classmates indirectly helped him as he said he was forced to be in the mood because they needed to finish the topics assigned for the day (N188). Anticipating that group review may not be able to cover all topics, Ms. NurseG also did self-review at home to compensate (G93). Besides, as part of managing his topics, Mr. NurseMJ said, "I made a time plan and setting a goal is so important" (MJ23) and it conformed to what Ms. NurseE did. According to Ms. NurseE, she started her self-review prior to graduation and created a calendar planner. She started from her weakest subjects (E107).

For that same mindset, Ms. NurseK explained that in self-review there are no instructors to serve as guides, only yourself. You create your own schedules and so she studied seriously because she was determined to pass on her first take (K46). Ms. NurseG, on the other hand, just followed through her schedule in spite of detractors. She explained that in reality, when you call it off at 5 PM it is not like you would be able to arrive home at 5 PM. There would be times wherein they would still stroll around with friends to unwind. Nonetheless, she pointed out that regardless of what they did that night, they would still attend review the following morning even if they are all sleepy (G138). Moreover, in order for Ms. NurseG's group to be interactive, imperative for them was to come prepared. Say she would give a medication, she would call one of the remaining four for, say, the drug indications. Before everyone came in, all should have read because everyone will be asked and and were expected to recite (G140). And if somebody came unprepared,

they would simply tease the person for coming unprepared and advise the person to come prepared next time. Even the timing of when to discuss the take home exam was also intentional. She said they would answer the assessments toward the end of the day so as not to induce information overload at the outset. She reasoned that just in case their brains will not function well toward the end of the day, atleast they would have been able to get the bulk of topics discussed on the first part of the day (G219).

For Mr. NurseJ, he admitted his pride was at stake and he expressed that he simply did not just rely on his stock knowledge, he did exert an effort to pass (J188). Lastly, Mr. NurseO fueled his motivation to finish his review so as not to be left behind. He mentioned that at the outset he was already decided not to be left behind by his batch. They belong to the same batch, graduated simultaneously, and so in his mind they would become nurses at the same time as well (O102) and so when it was already a week prior to the exam, he increased his load of topics for review and whenever he had a free time, even just his review schedule at work, he really devoted most of his idle moments reading or reviewing (O151).

✓ *Finding #1.L - Incorporate test-taking and review strategies.*

Apparent in the review strategies of the participants was the use of test-taking techniques. They used them in various ways that were ingrained with the way they approached their review and how they approached questions.

Mr. NurseB remembered to have used the classic “elimination”, “select all that apply” and “the longest option being the right answer (or the umbrella technique)” strategies (B188a). In answering questions, he was also mindful in balancing time as well as the number of test questions. He had to use his time wisely than spend all his time on a particular question only to find out he answered it wrong (B245) although he said caution must be done in doing so as one still has to scrutinize the question and options to be on a safer side (B188b). Like Mr. NurseB, Ms. NurseL also learned “...the very popular, if you don't know it choose the longest answer as well as the letter C” (L22). As introduced in other parts of this manuscript, Mr. NurseR, on the other hand, claimed that he already got used to multiple-choice type of questions and would get few mistakes, about 95 in a 100 item exam, if there are choices to choose from. He was comfortable in the elimination technique (R165). Mr. NurseR argued that while other people would reason out that three of the four choices in a multiple-type question are “almost correct”, him being a wide-reader in reality knows that the choices are really different from each other. He said, “If they're in anyway specific, they're not specific to the same subject matter. For example, all of the options there are specific, but if you'll scrutinize them, the other options are not intended for the question on hand, but for others (R181). He then seconded, “They're really intended for others” (R182). Mr. NurseN disagrees and says, “That is, they have a little difference from each other. Whatever would suit best to the situation is what I would choose.

That's how I look at it..." (N170), but both agreed that having prior knowledge is important. Same was true with Mr. NurseO wherein he would analyze the question and eliminate (O128). Mr. NurseMM's suggestion accordingly was to "read the question thoroughly and do not overanalyze" (MM25). For Ms. NurseL (LA24), Mr. NurseB (B66) and Ms. NurseE (E203), the three of them found self-created mnemonics as well as those in reviewers helpful. Meanwhile, Ms. NurseG expressed that she associated scenarios that happened during their review in recalling the topic within a question. She would remember a topic as she would be able to relate it with something that happened while they were reviewing (G156). Mr. NurseJ agrees as he claims to be a "fault finder" (J155) and the "meaningful experience" (J159) created from him asking a lot of questions help aid recall and that he would be able to better recall the topic (J157). Moreover, he has another concept of "recalling". The mere practice tests (pre and post-tests self-testing), for him, create an imprint in the mind that aid in recalling the next time the question is encountered and all of them serve to aid recall of topics (J227, J228). In the same regard, Ms. NurseE stressed understanding the chain of connection in between topics to aid in answering questions. She also mentioned the use of "pick-up lines" or statements in the texts that could be associated with a particular topic. As she has stated, the questions in the board exam are situational. One has to be mindful of the integration and sequence of the topics and notice some keywords or pick up lines when answering situational questions (E212). The effect of such strategy, as

previously cited, was an improved retention. As she reasoned, “It’s because you have studied them one by one, each detail you have imagined them all on your own when you were studying alone, and not others asking you to imagine them...”(E346). Mr. NurseN explained the way of doing so by rooting the connection between the topics by starting from the fundamentals:

I would start from the basics... (N215). In general, you know the basic concept. For example, in MS (Medical-Surgical Nursing), you should know, for example, the blood flow...the Anatomy. Let’s go with Anatomy first and then Physiology and then I would analyze it, say, Myocardial Infarction or MI... the blood flow is hindered...it’s like I would disrupt the normal Anatomy and then I would take it from there.... (N216). It’s by logic (N220). You would not memorize that for this question, this is the answer ... (N222) There I would factor in the medications, the procedures, the Nursing Care Plan... You would get it from the basics... (N217).

In doing so Mr. NurseJ, for his part, says he would integrate other concepts by asking all other related perspectives (J124). This view is in consonance with Mr. NurseN’s thought process. Mr. NurseN underscores the importance of starting from the “basics” and integrating logic and linking connections in between topics when approaching his review and answering questions. Before he teaches the topic back to his classmates, he already wrote the topic on his notebook. The way he taught was that there was a blank notebook then he would illustrate the anatomy and integrate the other topics through illustrations. Again, he emphasized, on a blank paper so he

would be forced to recall the topic (N197) incorporating logic and the fundamentals (N219, N2630).

Likewise, Ms. NurseG shared how her group did the same. She stated that they would start with a certain topic until the time that they would tackle the disease mechanism itself and the related topics. They needed not report all as they already knew what's next (G145, G148).

Ms. NurseL, herself, indirectly benefited from this strategy as well:

As I learned from my friends the mnemonics of the drugs (a really great help!!!) the delusion of grandeur, bipolar, schizo; a lot of terms to learn but with the help of my friends it was fun because we would make fun of each other and relate the terms to ourselves (ex. Histrionic) (L27).

Lastly, Mr. NurseR and Mr. NurseO stressed taking the answer from the context of the situation and relating that context to their prior knowledge. Mr. NurseO noted that in the examinations that they have taken in school, they are analytical in nature than definition of terms (O126). Mr. NurseR, further, emphasized that he views the answers in the context of the situation. He said, "I would relate it with the exam. Isn't it that it's how the questions are being asked in the exams? The symptoms of Patient X is indicative of what type of ..., it's like that" (R271), and for those topics with values that need memorization, he says he would create a picture in his mind of the structure and relationship of the values then apply them to the situation:

I would relate it with the table. And when I did so in the exam I would think of the table in my mind (R279). For example, Alkalosis, I would imagine how they're being arranged and compared in the table and then there I would be able to get it (R283).

✓ *Finding #1.M - Implement quality control measures.*

The responses from five participants suggest that they found a way to espouse quality control in their review both in the structure as well as in the content of the review itself and they did it in four ways:

First, through *self-testing*:

Like what was expected, participants did self-testing. Mr. NurseO did self-testing through his handbook (O175) and those that he got from his notes (O133). Ms. NurseE answered pretest questions before she reviews on a subject and posttest on her last day for that subject (E251). She stated that she feigned as if she was already taking the board exam (E246). As she started reviewing early, she used their mock board to gauge what she had learned in self-review. When she initially failed, she was mindful of the topics she missed. She noticed that there were common questions in the exams and so she tried to remember them (E140). She used the mock board result as a way of measuring her level of competence. And so

she failed, but she took note of the questions in the mock board. She thought that she had to exert more efforts. She intensified her review even more (E191).

For those who did group review like Ms. NurseG, she said they bought a compilation of all the board exam questions that they concurrently used to test what they knew at the time (G215-216) together with their review proper and it was like a bring-home assessment. She said that it was up to each one of them if they would like to cheat. They would answer a set, say first five compilations, and then on the following day they would scrutinize piece by piece (G217). In addition, there was an emphasis on maintaining quality through collective understanding. She stressed that they did not allot a timeframe. For them, everyone has to get the topic regardless whether they have to repeat it over and over. It should not be that they would allot a timeframe as each has different pace of picking up a topic. They needed to consider their review mates (G170).

Second, by *following through on missed target*:

During the times that Ms. NurseE was unable to follow her schedule because, for example, she overslept which was not part of her schedule, she noted that she had to make it up to meet her target (E316). If she had to sleep during that day, then she would skip sleeping so as to catch up. With a smile on her face, she said it was like she was penalizing herself for missing a topic (E317).

Third, by *double checking answers*:

Mr. NurseR, for his part, had a safeguard in answering test questions. When he spots a keyword on an answer, he mentioned that he didn't hastily pick that option as his answer.

He shared that when he notices keywords, and he reads the options, he would double check and revert back to the question first (R289). He said he is not the kind of person who will read and then answer the question right away without giving a second thought unless he really knows the answer (R290). In the same way, Mr. NurseO had to dig deeper by putting the right answer of his handbook on trial. If he got the answer wrong, he would dig deeper why the answer was correct (O177) most especially if he got it wrong as according to him, at the time that he was answering the question he had a feeling that what he answered was correct. And so, he would judge the book and would look for the explanation why the answer was correct (O180).

Finally, *by having a standard of reference:*

Ms. NurseG further stated that they measured what they knew against their classmate whom they consider being intelligent. She said if their classmate knew something, they should also know it (G115). For Ms. NurseE, two days before the exam she knew she already had enough. Two days prior to the exam, she said she already stopped reviewing. When she answered post test assessments, she saw herself get the correct answer. At that time, she knew she already had enough.

✓ *Finding #1.N –Ward off your worries.*

In the words of Mr. NurseJ himself, "...Board exam, is like do or die..." (J191), and so it is in the same context and understanding that the case participants themselves experienced feelings of anxiety, even fear of failure prior, during, and even after review and the licensure exam itself, and they dealt with them in a variety of ways.

Ms. NurseE acknowledged the existence of fears as well as employed positive diversion to reassess and brace herself up. She focused more on her weak areas; intensified her review to tackle subjects she was weak at (E149). She just thought that even though there is that fear, she needed to divert such fear. She opined that she needed to be optimistic on what she did as she reasoned that she did study well, took her review seriously, refrained from overanalyzing, and so she had the gut-feel that she would make it (E159).

In addition, Ms. NurseE, Mr. NurseN and Mr. NurseR reported having low expectations in the results to cope with untoward feelings. Ms. NurseE further emphasized that she was not expecting a higher rating anyway (E344). She further stated to have feigned to just treat the licensure like a major exam to diffuse tension and anxiety (E102). Similarly, Mr. NurseR reported giving a 20% room for doubt that he may fail (R157) aside from he did not want his parents to expect he will pass (R108), and so in effect, the lowered expectation simmered his anxiety. He

acknowledged there was some anxiety, but he was able to control it (R220). Mr. NurseN just stated that it was just okay as even if he fails, then we would simply enroll in a review center the next time around (N105).

Same was true to Ms. NurseG. She said it was okay as she did not expect a high rating anyway. The five of them did not have high expectations. For them, what was important was that they pass and show that everyone was able to do it and passed (G247). During the times of uneasiness, they just acknowledged the feelings and tried to comfort each other. According to her, there was really a mild anxiety – if they answered them right, if they studied them right, if they were already knowledgeable enough, those stuff. They would just see each other and bid good luck. In the same manner, Ms. NurseK and Mr. NurseO both expressed notably how they were worried about the results. Mr. NurseO acknowledged that, "...it's the waiting that kills..." (O104), and Ms. NurseK said, "I admit I had doubts that I would pass..." (K22) and so both of them used diversion by being busy with work and, like Mr. NurseMM (MJ20), just prayed that they will pass. For Mr. NurseJ and Mr. NurseO, their high degree of self-confidence and self-appraisal helped. Mr. NurseJ said that there was pressure, indeed. Two days of review and then on the third day he used it to rest and while he admitted that there was pressure, he nonetheless said that he was able to handle it (J200). Moreover, he lifted it up to God:

Actually, I did not think that I would fail as I am not a pessimistic person. I didn't have a slightest idea that I would fail. My idea was to keep focused; I knew my capabilities; I could do it. Of course with the help of God. I prayed that whatever the outcome will be, it's His will. At the end of it all, all of my decisions, all that I do, I pray. Whatever the outcome will be, good or bad, failure or success, I would think that it's the will of God, so I won't have any regrets. That's the way I viewed it (J203).

For Mr. NurseO, he reassured himself by believing that if others passed through self-review, he would also pass as he started convincing himself that they came from the same school anyway and whatever they have, he would also have (O75).

Question #02: What personal traits did these self-reviewees possess which helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?

Data findings have gone over the participants' backgrounds, what binds them together personally to somehow contribute to the success that they have achieved in passing the licensure without having to enroll in a review center. Their perception of self-review and what it entails have also been covered. Most recently, the combined common strategies found among them have also been delved into in order to determine the likelihood of a key formula to passing the nurses licensure without having to resort to attending a review center.

Question # 2 focuses on the most significant variable to consider: self-reported traits. What trait should a self-reviewee possess in order to succeed by his or her own perseverance? Among the participants in this study who have successfully obtained their licenses by reviewing on their own—and passing upon their first attempt—, what traits do they share that could have made their success possible?

Figure 15: *The Participants Self-reported Traits*

Note: In the interest of space, only the direct English translations were used in this section, data matrix of verbatim responses can be found in **Appendix A**.

The top three self-reported traits possessed by the participants involved **self-confidence**, **self-discipline**, and **determination**. They are the ones that stood out to most of the participants. Equally significant were other traits such as **spirituality**, **curiosity**, **diligence**, **patience**, and **resourcefulness**. Participants expressed these traits played key roles in their review. Below is an enumeration and description of each.

✓ *Finding #2.a:Self-confidence*

There was an agreement among six case participants about the value of self-confidence in self-review, and what was interesting to find was that self-confidence, as a trait, was perceived to be helpful to self-review itself as well as an outcome of successfully conducting self-review.

For one, belief in oneself and personal abilities amid uncertainties of self-review and the application of it in the licensure exam were the themes of Mr. NurseN's statements when he said, "Trust, trust in yourself, and trust in God" (N276). He then said, "I didn't have anyone to trust anyway. I will still be the one to do it, so I just had to trust what I did" (N277). That was how viewed what he was doing. Accordingly, Mr. NurseB seemed to have bolstered his self-confidence by his

realization that he was equally equipped as his two sisters who also passed the local and U.S. NCLEX-RN® through self-review:

I became confident that I would be able to pass the board exam through self-review because my siblings passed through self-review, too. My siblings also made it, and based on how I gauged myself, I could also compare myself to be like them. So I told myself that it was okay to self-review. I just needed to focus on reviewing and I'll make it (B108).

Moreover, both Mr. NurseB and Mr. NurseMJ believed that for a person to pass the licensure exam, he/she has to be self-confident (B250, B253; MJ43). Such self-confidence was best portrayed by Mr. NurseJ in dealing with the risk of failure. He asserted, "It's because I have a strong sense of self-confidence" (J201). In a statement that he further made, Mr. NurseJ acknowledged that there was pressure, indeed. Two days of review and then on the third day he used it to rest and while he admitted that there was pressure, he nonetheless said that he was able to handle it (J200) and then, he once again shared and affirmed his trait, "...I can do it, I trusted myself, I can" (J235).

In the case of Mr. NurseO, his confidence was deeply rooted from what he learned from his school. He stated, "...definitely what I have learned in that university was that, of course, you shouldn't settle for something less. You should always look up and beyond. You must always have a goal, but definitely it must be

feasible...” (O18). As a result of what they did, both he and Ms. NurseK claimed that self-review boosted their confidence. For Ms. NurseK, she indicated that “In the end, I became confident in my own knowledge and capabilities which truly helped on the day of the exam where exam jitters is your enemy” (K46).

✓ *Finding #2.b: Self-discipline*

Closely related to self-confidence is self-discipline, and the responses revealed self-discipline as a reported cause of success of the self-review as well as an acquired trait as a result of that success.

Evident in the words of Ms. NurseK was the role of self-discipline: “For me, it’s all about discipline. If you don’t instill discipline in yourself and just slack off then self-review would not be effective” (K41), and this trait was tested when Mr. NurseN learned his lesson when he was not able to complete his review schedule:

Discipline. It's difficult especially if you'll self-review, it's difficult to control yourself, it's difficult to have self-control not to go out with (friends) just like what I mentioned (N274). It's not even part of your schedule to go out, but you would do it anyway which is the reason why I wasn't able to finish my review, so you have to have discipline (N275).

Accordingly, Ms. NurseG and Ms. NurseE both said to have portrayed and exhibited self-discipline in their review. In Ms. NurseG’s case, she claims she had

self-discipline in tandem with dedication by attending her review despite distractions:

I had self-discipline. It was self-discipline. I would attend the review even if I was sleepy. When we had the group review, it's not that you left for home at 5 PM you'll arrive home right away, sometimes you would go out. Sometimes, you still have other friends that will ask you out and of course you can't say no. So it's like you'll go to the dorm like that, that you're intoxicated (G138).

Similarly, Ms. NurseE deprived herself of cell phones, television and just focused studying (E129). Knowing the seriousness of the licensure exam, she was able to develop a study habit by purportedly studying starting midnight until dawn during school days a month before her graduation and that was apart from their in-house review (E111). In the long run, her body got used to it, "It was really a sacrifice. Actually, my body got used to the less sleep, more on long review. Because I prayed (E321).

What's more fascinating were the claims that self-review brought about self-discipline. Ms. NurseK indicated, "Self-review made me not only gain knowledge but taught me the art of discipline as well. It also boosted my self-esteem which is good for my health as I became more confident in myself" (K49). Likewise, Mr. NurseMM felt ecstatic and said, "Gained discipline and got more confidence! Very Proud!" (MM15).

Finally, Ms. NurseK summed it all up with an encompassing statement, “Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline” (K45).

✓ *Finding #2.c:Determination*

Appearing third is the trait for determination, and this key trait liaised other positive traits such as diligence, spirituality, and focus to drive the case participants to finish their review program and ultimately pass the licensure exam.

As previously referenced, despite Ms. NurseE’s failure during the mock board exam, she did not take it against herself and instead used that feeling to push herself to study further (E130). Ms. NurseK displayed the same trait when she was adamant that she claimed to have pushed herself harder to pass the board exams on her first take (K21). For Ms. NurseL, she said she was stubborn, “Stubbornness - they told me to stop but I still went forward :)” (L40). Ms. NurseL also added that the determination and dedication to prioritize her review above all else are a must (L41). Another participant, showed his determination to pass by exerting effort:

...I was in a room. That was the only time in my life that I was in a room (studying)... I talked to my family not to disturb me, give me food when it's already time to eat. ...Even if I initially thought that I only wanted to know how the board exam works, my pride was still there that I will pass. Two days of review, you still have that pride that "I can do this!" So I still really exerted an effort. I am not even saying that I only passed because I relied on my memory. I really exerted an effort... (J188).

Like Mr. NurseJ, as cited above, Mr. NurseR portrayed determination by studying intently:

Yes, because when I was studying, even if I didn't have to study for long hours, a short time of two hours that I allot in the morning, or two hours for example, my focus was really there. I really absorbed what I was studying. When I was taking the exam, during the day of exam, I was really focused. There was nothing in my mind but to take the exam (R315).

For Ms. NurseE, she was simply giving all she got, “It's because I already poured all I have got, focus everything. I was already reviewing, I already gave all of me” (E310). Ms. NurseE shared that she knew she was no genius or no braniac— but she was patient, diligent (E337). The same message was conveyed by Mr. NurseO, “It's because there are braniacs out there too bigheaded that they just cling to their intelligence. Of course you should not only be reliant on your own wisdom, you also have to persevere (O83).

Both of these participants emphasized that having these traits are definite plus factors in order to pass the exam all on their own review efforts. And determination was not only shown in determination to pass, but also determination to finish her self-review and ultimately become a Registered Nurse, “Yes because when I started with nursing I really had a hard time. But I thought that I'm already into this, I needed to finish it whatever happens” (E335).

True enough, in few weeks' time, she got what she wanted.

Some other self-reported traits of the case participants that were identified were curiosity, resourcefulness, creativity, hard work, perseverance, stubbornness, optimism, patience and resilience.

✓ *Finding #2.d: Other traits noted*

Apart from the three traits that surfaced in the responses of the participants, positive traits such as spirituality, curiosity, diligence, patience, and resourcefulness were also mentioned both directly and indirectly.

In the case of Mr.NurseN, he claimed to be a church musician (N267) and the main trait that he claimed to have was trust in God. He said, "Perhaps number one is your trust in the Lord (N263) and that you can do it because God trusts you... "(N264) and while he was already reviewing at the time, he said he did not take his church duties for granted (N267). By the time that his churchmates found out that he will take the board exam, Mr.NurseN said they included him on their prayer meetings. For Mr.NurseJ, he repeatedly mentioned about his trust in God and his mindset that whatever happens, it will be the will of God (J263). He said:

Actually, I did not think that I would fail as I am not a pessimistic person. I didn't have a slightest idea that I would fail. My idea was to keep focused; I knew my capabilities; I could do it. Of course with the help of God. I prayed that whatever the outcome will be, it's His will. At the end of it all, all of my decisions, all that I do, I pray. Whatever the outcome will be, good or bad, failure or success, I would think that it's the will of God, so I won't have any regrets. That's the way I viewed it (J203).

Mr.NurseB also prayed to God to grant him wisdom to answer the question (B250, B252) and for Ms.NurseE, she engaged in prayer fasting that she reviewed at dawn then would attend the morning devotion from 4:30 in the morning until 6 and considered it as a sacrifice (E320, E321). Meanwhile, Ms.NurseG mentioned a long held trait of being curious eversince when she was still student she was known to be asking alot of question (G260-263).If there was something nagging Ms.NurseL when they were having a Q & A session with her friends and she did not know the answer, she would immediately search for the answer (L40). For Mr.NurseE, it was not because of being intelligent at school that she attributed her licensure results, but because of diligence. According to her, even her teachers in college noticed such trait in her that she might not be a brainiac at school that she would be on top, but was able to achieve something (E336). She shared, “Me being diligent, I guess that's the significant factor. It's because I am not intelligent, but I am a diligent person (E332). For Ms. NurseK, she narrated that she was not content with her own materials and searched the internet for more study materials (K46b). Lastly, there was stubbornness in Ms.NurseL, as she calls it, her friends told her to stop already, but she still went forward (L40).

3.) What could be the marks of a P.N.L.E. self-reviewee board passer?

As expressed in the “Purpose of the Study”, the answer to this question is a document entitled “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer” in Appendix F.

Discussion

"Everyone believes the results of an experiment except the person who ran it, but no one believes a theory except the person who proposed it".

~ (Source unknown)

The present study was designed to examine if self-review could make an N.L.E. reviewee pass the Nursing Licensure Examination by looking at the personal backgrounds, review experiences, strategies, and self-reported traits of eleven nurses who passed the licensure through self-review on their first take. While, apparently, these nurses already passed the licensure, the major questions concern how did they pass, and why did they take self-review in the first place amid the high risk of failure and the absence of a clear guide. At any rate, as the findings revealed, the researcher was successful in looking for answers to these fundamental questions about self-review as discussed below.

1.) What review strategies and techniques, if any, helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?

At this point, the discussion will focus on the “technical aspect” of the self-reported review strategies of the participants. Below shows the findings of the analysis of the data and this time with some degree of assertion, although definitely without making a conclusion, that there could be (at least) “Fourteen marks of a self-reviewee board passer” in terms of their review strategies which were collectively present at various paces of the participants’ review. All of them start with a handle phrase, “A successful self-reviewee...

✓ *Assertion #1.a- Conducts self-analysis.*

It was surprising to find that there was a convergence of answers of case participants to self-reflect so as to know their strengths and weaknesses first, before planning and executing their review. And analyzing what they did, the activity they did could be helpful for the self-reviewee in at least three ways: (1) self-analysis underscores time element in dealing with priority subjects; (2) it brings a structure to the review, and (3) it helps to maximize and target resources toward the completion of review. If the prospective self-reviewee is able to understand his/her own personal characteristics and the consequences of possible different experience when conducting self-review, then proper planning and adjustments could be done ahead of time. A possible alternative explanation is at this stage, the prospective self-reviewee could weigh in if he/she is able to bear self-review, or would have to choose a different method suited to his/her review needs. This means that the prospective self-reviewee has to have an informed decision in self-reviewing. As what was shown in the case of Mr. NurseJ, he had a hard time at first (J189), and Mr. NurseN had distractions and hesitations (N92) that he eventually fell short of his review schedule (N181). On the positive, however, it served to an advantage to Ms. NurseE as from the start she was already decided and, in fact, she already started self-reviewing prior to graduation (E107).

✓ *Assertion #1.b- Picks a strategy that best fits his/her learning style and study needs.*

Not all students report using the same strategies—like learning styles, individual differences also exist between students with regard to their study habits (Hartwig & Dunlosky’s, 2012). Obviously, for a short window period between the date of graduation and the day of examination, strategic is to use an existing review strategy tailored on the learning style and study needs of the reviewee. Looking back at the case stories starting from “Mr. NurseR” up until the seventh featured case story which is for “Mr. NurseO”, the reader may already have noticed that each review strategy that they have used, as shown and depicted in the self-review flow charts created, are tailored with the way they learn best as bounded by their circumstantial and preferential self-review reasons. Below is a table that shows how the data could be interpreted with a short justification:

Self-review Reason	Self-review Strategy
Preferential	Mr. NurseR’s Diagram Approach
	Ms. NurseE’s Textbook Approach
	Mr. NurseJ’s Recalling Approach
	Mr. NurseB’s Traditional Q & A Approach
	Mr. NurseO’s “Self-made Q & A Reviewer” Approach
Circumstantial	Mr. NurseN’s Blank Paper Approach
	Ms. NurseG’s Vacant Space: the Combo Approach

Table 6: *Self-review strategies as tailor-fit to reviewees’*

Learning style and study needs

Pushed by varied preferential and/or circumstantial self-review reasons, the experience of self-review itself, being “unaided”, sprang different self-review approaches. The circumstances, through self-review reasons, which these self-

reviewees were in born creative and tailor-fit strategies based on their learning beliefs, style, and approaches and the way they thought they would learn best at the time. For instance, Mr. NurseR learns best when concepts are made “simpler” and put into diagram (R218-219) and when he sees the concepts in the context of situations (e.g. R257), and so that is how he reviewed. Similarly, Ms. NurseE learns best when there are detailed explanations (e.g. E210, E218) so she used textbooks when self-reviewing. Same was true with Mr. NurseJ, Mr. NurseB, and Mr. NurseO. They have their respective stories and justifications. Conversely, Mr. NurseN and Ms. NurseG’s review strategies can be considered incidental, or mixed type. Mr. NurseN took advantage of his classmate’s situation and did his review with them. It does not mean, however, that he did not incorporate his learning approaches. In the contrary, his “Blank Paper Approach” suited the way he learns through “logic” (N220) and rooting from the basics (e.g. N228, N271). Further, Ms. NurseG, who was also challenged like Mr. NurseN, maximized the situation they were in when they reviewed in a vacant space (room) while reviewing at home. The fact that all of them used different review strategies mean that self-review accommodates, regardless of the declared reason, individual differences and review needs of the reviewees. And, since they were successful and eventually passed, the experience translated to increase in self-efficacy.

Once again, this concept is not new. Weinstein, Acee, and Jung (2011) suggest that students need to develop a repertoire of strategies that help them

“mindfully determine their preferences and to access alternative strategies when their preferences do not work” (p. 49). It would, hence, preferable to use an existing review strategy that works for the person just like what Mr. NurseO did when he carried over his review style during college (O132). The term is “preferable” because if existing review strategy may not have worked for the reviewee, then, the reviewee may have to consider other strategies that would work while, as much as possible, still tailor on the reviewees’ learning approaches. The strategy could be a technique or a learning approach to go over review materials and maximize learning and test taking. This means, for example, using a book instead of the classic reviewers like what Mr. NurseN did (N114), or a reviewer with detailed explanation (E210) in the case of Ms. NurseE. It is said that individuals tend to develop learning strategies in order to deal with learning materials and therefore learning strategies can be regarded as cognitive tools, which enable learners to complete tasks and solve problems... what they value in the learning experience (e.g., Biggs, 1987; Entwistle & Ramsden, 1983).

✓ *Assertion #1.c - Prioritizes and manages his/her weak areas.*

In consideration with the time element, and as a result of self-analysis, findings suggest that prioritization is important. Findings revealed that eight out of eleven participants openly mentioned that they prioritized their weakest subjects/ areas first. This finding could imply that for self-review to be effective, the reviewee must, through self-analysis, prioritize subjects or topics that he/she is still weak at.

This does not mean, however, that the reviewee will overlook other topics as the participants still took care of them. The idea seemed to be to even out mastery of topics across all subjects. Appearing antagonistic, Ms. NurseK appraised self-review with her point:

Yes, I recommend self-review as it is very budget-friendly and convenient. Besides, reviewing is just a culmination of our four years in school. No review center can pack in four years of knowledge in a few weeks so the main advantage of self-review is that you can have the flexibility to focus more on your weak areas (K17).

✓ *Assertion #1.d - Organizes his/her topics to review.*

The findings revealed that participants made a way to organize their topics by creating review timelines, planners, etc. They brought their own framework to the task. What information is attended to, how the information is organized and what personal knowledge is combined with the information all revolves around... (Honebein, Duffy, & Fishman, 1993, p. 93). Circling back to the literature, Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012) noted that differences in scheduling did arise between the highest and lowest achievers, with the lower achievers focusing (a) more on impending deadlines, (b) more on studying late at night, and (c) almost never on planning their study time. And the findings of this study, although not conclusive because, again, there could be other intervening factors, show that the more

articulate the self-review was on their study strategy in terms of organizing their topics, the higher the rating they got.

✓ *Assertion #1.e - Tailors his/her review duration and frequency based on his/her review needs.*

Likewise, the reviewees planned their timelines based on their self-analysis, and such strategy is supported by empirical studies. Multiple regression analyses were done by West and Sadoski (2011) to investigate significant factors of performance. The results of three regressions indicated that two study skills--time management and self-testing, were generally stronger predictors of first-semester academic performance than aptitude. Cramming, like what Mr. NurseJ did, interestingly yield good results as reported by Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012), but is not preferable, and the possible reasoning behind that is there is just voluminous of topics to cover in reviewing that they could not fit in a couple of days, else the reviewee may just have to rely on stock knowledge which may not always work. It could work for some, but the researcher argues it should not be done in a major examination as the licensure if the aim is to pass. In a related topic, scheduling study sessions in a spaced manner may afford the use of other strategies, which themselves improve student success, and such strategy was done by Mr. NurseR (R315). In this case, Mr. NurseJ did pass, although he reported a lower rating (J252). What is interesting is that reports of spacing study (vs. cramming) are not

significantly related to GPA, even though spaced (vs. massed) practice is known to have a major impact on retention (Cepeda, Pashler, Vul, Wixted, & Rohrer, 2006).

✓ *Assertion #1.f - Finds his/her right venue.*

As stated by Abdullah (2001), self-directed learners are “responsible owners and managers of their own learning process” (p. 1). Self-directed learning integrates self-management (management of the context, including social setting, resources, and actions) with self-monitoring (the process whereby learners monitor, evaluate, and regulate their cognitive learning strategies) (Bolhuis, 1996; Garrison, 1997).

The common reasons behind such looking for the right venue as confirmed by the findings is to be in an environment that is conducive to learning and facilitate better memory. Experimental evidence confirms that human episodic memory can be influenced by changes in context (Smith & Vela, 2001, cited in Lohre, 2011). If some material is learned in one context and then tested in another context, it is less well remembered than if learning and testing occurs in the same context. For instance, scuba divers who learnt lists of words either underwater or on land, remembered fewer words when they were tested in the other environment as compared to the same environment (Godden & Baddeley, 1975). The forgetting that occurs due to a change in context is often referred to as context-dependent forgetting. The other side of the coin is that context can act as a cue that improves memory. For instance, when environmental context is changed between learning and testing, it has been shown that a mental reinstatement of context will lead to

better performance on a memory test (Smith, 1984, also cited in Lohre, 2011). According to Smith (2007, p. 111): "Context, most generally defined, is that which surrounds." According to this broad definition, a wide range of sensory stimuli as well as internal states can act as contexts during cognitive processing, and many different types of contexts have been studied by psychologists at different times. A lot of studies support the effect of physical surroundings on memory (Smith & Vela, 2001), although the effects are greater when the context manipulation is quite strong, such as in Godden and Baddeley's (1975) classic experiment with scuba divers underwater or on land. With weaker manipulations of environmental context (changing rooms between learning and testing) the effects of context on memory are sometimes not found at all (Fernandez & Glenberg, 1985; Saufley, Otaka, & Bavaresco, 1985). So having said all those, the participants, as what was expected, find their comfortable places to better focus on their review.

✓ *Assertion #1.g - Gets a good review material.*

Review approaches help emphasize encoding process of reexamining or reviewing course resources (Omrod, as cited in McNulty *et al.*, 2012). In inferring the case participants' choice of review materials, there seems to be two lessons: First, the choice of review material must be in line with the review strategy and learning approach of the reviewee. So in the case of Ms. NurseE and Mr. NurseN, for example, they were more comfortable with studying using a textbook (N271, E194) and so that is what they used. For others, they used a combination of college

textbooks, and traditional reviewers. Second, a good review material must be complete, reliable, latest and drills down to a simpler explanation of the topic (E203, B219-20, R77 onwards, for example). Being part of the review strategy, having good review materials eases the effectiveness of re-reading. Hartwig and Dunlosky (2012) surveyed 324 undergraduates about their study habits as well as their college grade point average (GPA). Their findings showed that the use of self-testing and rereading were both positively associated with GPA. Karpicke *et al.* (2009) revealed that self-testing and other retrieval type activities (e.g., using flashcards) were commonly reported by their respondents (N=177), but the strategy most frequently reported (by 83.6% of students) was rereading notes or textbooks. When used correctly, however, it can boost retention and performance (e.g., Rawson & Kintsch, 2005), and the present rereading–GPA relationship may in part arise from students who read (a lot) versus those who do not read.

✓ *Assertion #1.h - Maximizes help from other people and exhausts available resources.*

This strategy seems to be more of a need for self-review than a preference, and this could be possibly tied to the finding that self-review is “unaided”, and so inevitably, at any rate, the self-reviewee must know when, and how to use other resources to his/her advantage. Interesting was the use of the internet, or the use of technology to aid review like what Ms. NurseK (K24), Mr. NurseB (B231), Mr. NurseMM (MM11) did. Langlois (in Collis, 1999, p. 374) makes the following statement: “New information technologies, and particularly the

Internet, is dramatically transforming access to information, are changing the learning and research process, how we search, discover, teach and learn..." Another interesting result came from the study of Saeed, Yang and Sinnappan (2009) in which they concluded that, "...today's learners are flexible in stretching their learning styles and are able to accommodate varying instructional strategies, including the use of emerging web technologies" (p. 106). However, Palloff and Pratt (2003) impress caution about its use when they said that, "Although the Internet is cited as being a big equalizer, dealing with learners should be done considering individual differences in learning, gender, culture, and ability" (p.13). On the sideline, peer relationships, and support system have also been linked to performance. Intimate peer support, such as from close friends, is just as beneficial as global peer support, such as from classmates and that peer relationships in children and teens can be seen as the building blocks to intellectual, social, and identity issues (Caselman & Self, 2007; Galbraith, 2005). Perfect example was the case of Ms. NurseG's group review wherein they helped address individual inadequacies by reviewing altogether. An important aspect is the management of who to include in the study environment; being able to seek help and learn from peers are important characteristics of a self-regulated learner (Ryan & Pintrich, 1997). Considering that they have been together for years already, Ms. NurseG and her friends knew each other already (see G264) that they blended with each other's

strengths to counter somebody else's weakness. Overall, the participants were resourceful and creative in dealing with their review.

✓ *Assertion #1.I - Watch out for FAQs and emerging health issues.*

Out of the eleven participants, only Ms. NurseE broached this strategy and she tried to make a point by purportedly claiming that her strategy worked in the licensure and that she did encounter questions about current health issues (and the researcher confirms). It makes sense that the Board of Examiners includes current health issues and/or challenges since those are part of the nursing concerns at the time. And so, therefore, being receptive in accounting those topics that commonly appear in the exams, and/or being sensitive to current health issues are a must in an effective review.

✓ *Assertion #1.J - Is inclusive, comprehensive, and integrates other topics when reviewing.*

If a person has to take a test, and since tests are supposed to be sampled and not all will be asked (see B221) in a test, it is only right that he/she has all the necessary information to cover all possible topics where those "samples" of questions will be taken from. Such was how the participants, in general, reckoned this strategy. In part, it was part of the lessons learned such by Mr. NurseMM (MM36) or those that were encountered by Mr. NurseO wherein he was not able to cover in his review (O185). An effective review, therefore, has to be inclusive, comprehensive as much as possible, integrating all other topics together as part of

the review. In particular, this could be boosted by proper duration planning, time management, and by constructive learning review strategies.

✓ *Assertion #1.K - Executes the strategy precisely, but flexible in containing shortcomings.*

An axiom stating “Plan your work, then work your plan” condenses this review strategy. Chances are, if the reviewee misses to execute the strategy as planned, self-review will not be effective. Without a strategy to work on and failure to “sticking to the plan”, the review could be haphazardly done. Partly and at some points within the course of their review, that reportedly happened to some participants such with Ms. NurseE and Ms. NurseG, although they were quick to do something about it and get back to their review regimen. Another noteworthy comment was made by Mr. NurseN in that he did not plan, but reviewed when he was in the mood (N187), although he remarked being forced to be in the mood because of his classmates. It is not surprising as the literature says that memory is also influenced by affective states, or moods. (Ellis & Moore, 1999). Mood-congruent memory refers to enhanced encoding and/or retrieval of material which is congruent to the current mood. This is for instance demonstrated by the fact that depressed patients retrieve less positive and more negative memories than control participants (Lemogne *et al.*, 2006). Mood-dependent memory refers to mood acting as a contextual cue for memory, such that more material is remembered when the mood at retrieval matches the mood at encoding (Bower, Monteiro, & Gilligan, 1978; Eich & Metcalfe, 1989). This was concerning because self-review is

self-regulated, and when a person has to wait for him/her to be “in the mood”, chances are review will not be completed. This could be regarded as another inherent challenge of self-reviewing, and one of the most probable accounts for the difference between an effective and ineffective self-review. An effective review, therefore, has to have controls to limit the shortcomings of self-review. There has to be some controls, and Fisher, King, and Tague (2001) infer that the degree of control the learner is willing to take over their own learning will depend on their attitude, abilities and personality characteristics. In simple terms, the more internal the level of control, the greater the ability of the individual to deal with changes within their learning environment (Shannon, 2008). For the most part, the review itself is mostly centered on the reviewee him/herself. Ms. NurseE, for example, had to make some “sacrifices” (e.g. E321) to ensure that she adheres to her review program and does her part. Learning is not one way. It can be argued that no review strategy will be good enough and a good review program will be ineffective and futile if the reviewee him/herself does not study.

✓ *Assertion #1.L - Incorporates test-taking and review strategies.*

Aside from the obvious need to incorporate test-taking techniques as what is being taught in (in-house) review, what is remarkable was the emphasis of the participants’ thought process in terms of preference of constructive learning strategies over rote learning as part of their test-taking strategy. While test-taking

strategies could aid recall and serve as a tactic on how and what to answer, analysis, reasoning consideration of all other factors of such topic, and inference of what could be the best answer are mostly imbued in a person's learning style and approaches. Ausubel, Novak, and Hanesian (1978) emphasizes that people learn meaningfully by developing cross-connections between related concepts. This allows them to engage in inferential and analogical reasoning. As such, as evident in the emphasis of Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach', or Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach and even with Mr. NurseJ's Recalling Approach, incorporating these techniques based on the way they process information could be an effective test strategy.

✓ *Assertion #1.M - Implements quality control measures.*

The findings showed that there has to be quality control measures in an effective self-review. Firstly was self-testing which was done by all case participants. Self-testing, as shown in the review of literature, has been demonstrated to be quite effective and abundance of research has shown can boost student learning (Roediger & Butler, 2011). Ormrod (2004) indicated that the processes or strategies employed by a learner while studying influences how the information is stored and later retrieved, and she proposed that some study processes promoted better learning. Self-testing by recalling the target information boosts performance on subsequent recall and multiple choice tests of the target information, and it also boosts performance on tests of comprehension (Roediger &

Butler, 2011; Roediger & Karpicke, 2006; Rawson & Dunlosky, 2011). Apart from self-testing, other measures following through on missed target, by double checking answers before answering, and by having a standard of reference all of which are important in ensuring quality. In a related concept, the Biggs presage-process model of student learning identifies two factors of student learning:

Presage: personal characteristics such as the student's personality, locus of control, ability, background, conceptions of learning, attitudes, and general experience.

Process: Situational factors which include the learning context, nature of task, time pressures, teaching method, assessment, and perception of institutional requirements. Together, presage and process affect the quality of learning through the chosen learning approach (Biggs, Kember, & Leung, 2001; Snelgrove, 2004).

✓ *Assertion #1.N –Wards off his/her worries.*

This deals with the affective part of review. As in all tests, there are no guarantees. There could always be pass-fail scenario. An exploratory study to examine the impact of coping, locus of control, and academic worry on first-attempt passing rates on the Board of Certification (BOC) examination was done by Breitbach, Downey, and Frager (2013) and their data suggest that candidates experiencing psychological factors, such as high academic worry, emotion-focused coping mechanisms, and an external locus of control, have a lower first-attempt pass rate on the examination. It is true even to other exams such as the NCLEX-

RN® in the US. Graduates from nursing programs are also failing the NCLEX-RN® on their first attempt (Carrick, 2011). In an interview with 10 students who passed the NCLEX-RN® on the first attempt and nine students who did not, Eddy and Epeneter (2002) found that students who passed the NCLEX-RN® took responsibility for learning, paced their preparation, and took the exam when they felt prepared and used stress management strategies to cope with the inevitable emotional responses to the examination. In contrast, students who failed the NCLEX-RN® failed to identify a reasonable plan for review, felt confident prior to the test but became quite anxious during the test, perceived pressure by others to take the exam before they were ready, believed that they had not known how to take an NCLEX-RN® exam, which requires critical thinking instead of recall of fact-based knowledge, felt they lacked knowledge in some content areas, and felt that they were not able to manage the anxiety that occurred during the exam. If an examinee fails once, there's that risk of recurrence. And yes, the participantsthemselves were not immune to these feelings of fear of failure, anxiety, worries, among others, but evident in their responses was that they were able to do something about them in a timely manner by acknowledging their feelings, through positive diversion, prayers, good preparation, and self-reassurance. A person could argue that self-testing, or reading all thick past NLE questions is a waste as questions rarely repeat. That argument could be true, however, having an effective review strategy and executing it precisely as planned,

and incorporating the constructive learning strategies, basing the analogy from core concepts like what these participants reported are, of themselves, a way of effectively coping with these worries.

In summary, it can be said that the compiled fourteen self-review strategies of these participants give the structure of their review. Structure refers to the form, the arrangement of elements or parts of anything, the manner of organization; the emphasis on the way those elements are bound together (Pines, 1985). These steps may not be mutually exclusive, but could be inferred as interdependent. As shown in the findings, missing a step could have serious implications to the overall outcome of self-review. Hence, a well-structured and holistic review could be the secret ingredient of self-review that works.

3.) What personal traits did these self-reviewees possess which helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?

Three self-reported traits came on top of the list: self-confidence, self-discipline, and determination.

✓ Finding #2.a: Self-confidence.

Self-confidence could have played a major role in the participants' review, as what the findings revealed. It could be extrapolated that a person who is conducting self-review involves great risk of possibly losing a chance to attain a degree he/she has invested for four years requires a great deal of self-confidence. It can be argued,

further, that self-review which has not been done by so many could be risky considering the small number of examinees who pass the licensure. Poorman and Webb (2000) interviewed 10 nursing graduates who had failed the NCLEX-RN® to gain an understanding of their experience. Several themes emerged including: “carrying failure as a daily burden; losing the identity of being a nurse; doubting past accomplishments; seeing self as damaged goods; wanting support; and daring to hope”. Failure is just one exam away. The fact that these participants reported having self-confidence could possibly have made an impact to their licensure approach. A study in the domains of Mathematics (N=1940) and English (N=1786) that assessed confidence together with scales measuring self-belief – i.e., self-efficacy, different kinds of self-concepts, and anxiety – among the 15-year old students from Singapore was done by Stankova, Lee, Luo, and Hogan (2012). Results showed that confidence is: a) a robust individual differences dimension; b) that can be combined with accuracy information to obtain bias scores that may be useful for group comparisons and for identification of misconceptions about particular topics. These researchers concluded that confidence as studied in work to date has been c) the best predictor of achievement in both Mathematics and English; d) is related to both cognitive and self-belief measures; and e) it captures much of the predictive variance of other self-beliefs that are, in turn, among the best known predictors of achievement. Another study proves self-confidence associated with achievement. Al-Hebaish (2012) investigated the correlation

between general self-confidence and academic achievement in the oral presentation course. The results revealed a positive, significant correlation between general self-confidence and academic achievement. As could be confirmed by experience and empirical studies, self-confidence is built over time. In these participants, it could be because of the aforementioned personal and academic background that have molded them to have some degree of self-confidence, or borrowed confidence in the case of Mr. NurseB from his siblings, but since in hindsight knowing what they did and how they did it suggest that an effective self-reviewee must be self-confident.

✓ *Finding #2.b: Self-discipline*

If self-confidence could be regarded as the gasoline of a car, self-discipline is the steering wheel. Manifested in the participants' responses was self-discipline, which was an expected finding. There was an absence and presence of self-discipline among participants. Present in most of them, but some, like Mr. NurseN admittedly did not have. While he claimed he did not have it, knowing his scenario, it could very well be out of his control and may have been caused by him not disclosing to others that he was already self-reviewing. Nonetheless, he emphasized this trait to be as an important factor (N274). In Self-determination Theory (SDT), self-discipline is one facet of the trait "conscientiousness" among diligence, dependability, prudence, competence, dutifulness, order, and achievement striving which are conducive to performance in academic settings,

attainment of academic honors, and lower disciplinary infractions (MacCann, Duckworth, & Roberts, 2009). In a similar study, Trockel, Barnes, and Egget (2000) used other aspects of physical and mental health criteria as predictors of success. The researchers incorporated a time diary with all of these criteria and suggest that life patterns, clear goals, disciplined personal habits, and health issues greatly influence success and accomplishment. With all distractions and/or inherent shortcomings of self-review, the mere possession of self-discipline alone could greatly influence self-review outcome.

✓ *Finding #2.c: Determination.*

Third in the list was determination, and as evident, relies on other traits to be effective. If self-confidence is the fuel, and self-discipline is the steering wheel, determination on the other hand could serve as the roadmap or the GPS (Global Positioning System) of the review structure towards accomplishing the review plan, and ultimately pass the licensure and such determination was portrayed in various means by the participants as discussed in the findings.

✓ *Finding #2.d: Other traits noted*

Traits such as spirituality, curiosity, diligence, patience, and resourcefulness give breadth to the respective efforts each and every reviewee exerted. They have their respective use and role in the review all of which to attain the desired outcome.

❖ *Tying the knots altogether*

One could safely infer that the findings of this study suggest two focal points in terms of the marks of a self-reviewee board passers in the Nursing Licensure Exam: (1) that the outcome of self-review could be tied to their review strategies, and that (2) there could be specific and observable characteristics and traits of self-reviewee board passers. Addressing by reiterating the last three findings of Eddy and Epeneter (2002) as cited earlier, their findings revealed that those who failed “...believed that they had not known how to take an NCLEX-RN® exam, which requires critical thinking instead of recall of fact-based knowledge, felt they lacked knowledge in some content areas, and felt that they were not able to manage the anxiety that occurred during the exam”. These three, to the least, could have multiple implications in terms of a possible explanation as to why the self-review participants in this study passed the licensure: First, Mr. NurseO, for example, affirmed that the exercises or tests in their school are more of analyses of situations and seldom are definition of terms (see ref#O126). Accordingly, one major finding of the present study is that participants prefer constructive learning strategies over rote learning. Constructive processes, as elaborated, include strategies in encoding information through the elaboration of prior knowledge, structuring or organizing information, personalizing information to make it meaningful, creating visual representations of information (Driscoll, 2005; Ormrod, 2004), make connections between new concepts and their past experiences, and draw logical inferences

from data they receive (Pandey & Zimitat, 2007; Ormrod, 2004). As a result, they learn more effectively and perform better on assessments (*ibid*). It could be surmised, therefore, that at any rate these participants were effective and efficient in dealing with scenario or situational types of tests. In turn, this characteristic could have addressed the deficiency of critical thinking abilities as found by Eddy and Epeneter (2002) in those who failed. Second, at varying rates, findings #3.I and #3.J as part of review strategies talk about inclusiveness and being receptive in terms of efforts to capture every facet of topics or content areas nursing. What these could mean is that these participants differ from those who failed in these aspects underscoring the criticality of incorporating these review strategies into self-review. Last of the concerns in Eddy and Epeneter (2002) study is the issue of managing the anxiety that occurred during the licensure exam. Regarded as a normal phenomenon, the thinking of the researcher is that anxiety could have been controlled by the participants' traits such as self-confidence, discipline in terms of preparation and execution, and determination to pass, and determination to finish their review regimen. These traits can be rooted from and/or could be synergistic with their personal backgrounds. Preference in constructive learning strategies could have helped them acquire a strong academic background and, understandably, made them academic performers which in turn helped them develop self-confidence and efficacy over time. That self-confidence, efficacy, and their personal backgrounds must have been instrumental in crafting tailor-fit

review strategies; rallying local resources amid the lack or even absence of help during self-review. These characteristics, apart from majority preferring solitary activities, possession of traits such as self-discipline and determination, must have helped them bear the inherent challenges of self-review which ultimately translated onto having to manage anxiety and jitters on the day of examination. For instance, while Mr. NurseJ claims that there was pressure, he says he was able to handle it (J200) because of his high degree of self-confidence (J201). Another example is Mr. NurseR wherein while he acknowledged that there was pressure, he said it was not too much (R221) and that whenever he takes an exam, he is really focused. On the day of the licensure exam, he claims that there was nothing in his mind, but the exam (R335). And so in these instances, and some more, it can be inferred that the marks of a successful self-review are best exemplified through their effective and efficient self-review strategies tailored from their personal backgrounds as mediated and/or augmented by their self-reported traits.

To finish, one nagging yet crucial concern that a prospective self-reviewee could ask, which has also been raised earlier in the Purpose of the Study, is that: "Will self-review work for everyone?" or in a personal stance, "Do I have to exhibit all these personal and academic background, demonstrate these self-reported traits, and comply with all the fourteen step self-review strategies for me to pass the licensure through self-review?", "What if I miss one or a couple of them, will self-review still be effective?" Evidently, the findings are specific and ideal based on

the analysis of what were common among these successful participants. They are ideal in the sense that they “could be” the best determinants of a working self-review in the licensure. Potentially, however, it is also possible that a person could pass licensure through self-review without having to possess all of these. For example, it could be possible that one who does not possess a high degree of constructive learning strategies, but may have high degree of motivation, self-discipline, determination and effective review strategies in the absence of desirable personal background pass the exam. In the words of Mr. NurseO, “...it really boils down to hardwork...” (N189), isn’t it? Or to Ms. NurseK’s argument, “Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline” (K45). Circling back to, and borrowing the arguments of, Hartwig and Dunlosky’s (2012, p. 2), “...it is possible that successful students achieve their success in spite of (1) using the same pattern of strategies as low performers or (2) using even poorer strategy options. In the former case, perhaps high and low performers choose the same strategies, but high performers use them *more adeptly* (with emphasis). In the latter case, perhaps other factors—such as intelligence, prior experience, or degree of motivation— overpower the differential...” which very well could be a case. Lastly, the researcher argues that the lessons learned, as well as the review strategies, traits and insights broached by these board passers who have been there and, at any rate, conquered their personal self-review journeys could serve as starting points and/or guides for other self-reviewees.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

“Say not, ‘I have found the truth,’ but rather, ‘I have found a truth.’”

--Kahlil Gibran, *The Prophet*

Summary

This thesis was about the self-reported use of the self-review method in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination. The questions that guided this study explored the academic and personal learning backgrounds of the self-reviewee board passers; their review experiences prior, during, and after their review including the role of support systems, if any, their self-reported review strategies as well as traits that helped them carry out their review strategies. Eleven nurses (seven were interviewed and four were sent a survey questionnaire) who passed the P.N.L.E on their first take and took their licensure examinations from 2007 to 2010, ages 22 through 26 at the time, were scouted as case participants of this study. Also, all of the case participants were scouted in Metro Manila, which happens to have the most number of nursing graduates in the country at present. In addition, due to geographical accessibility, time-table of research, financial considerations and the capacity of the lone researcher, the study was delimited to participants who were graduates of universities/colleges within Metro Manila where the researcher resides in. To determine the self-reported effectiveness of

self-review in preparing them for licensure, to identify review strategies and find out if there was a pattern of personal and academic background, review strategies and traits, and to find out why did they conduct self-review in spite of the low national passing percentage in the P.N.L.E and unpopularity of self-review, an “exploratory” case study was conducted. However, because there was no previous research identified from existing literature about self-review, Yin (2003, 2009) classified this study as “exploratory” as well. The case study (Yin, 2009) research design was the most suitable method in this research because it allowed the researcher to use in-depth interviews as well as have the flexibility to allow an online survey questionnaire for data gathering in order to capture different responses from different participants – flexibility that is not present in most other methods. The methodological approach taken in this study was broadly qualitative, although some elements of quantitative research such as the online survey questionnaire was used for those participants that were unavailable and unreachable in terms of location. The justification as to why they were included was laid down in the section for “Sources of Evidence” in Chapter 2. Within and cross-case analyses (Yin, 2009; Creswell, 2007; Novak, *et al.*, 1978) were completed to analyze the data collected.

After data analysis, findings revealed that participants had two main self-review reasons: (1) Circumstantial and (2) preferential. Circumstantial reasons was operationally defined as reasons to self-review because of the “need to do so”,

whereas preferential reasons describe reasons to self-review because of the 'choice or preference to do so'. Circumstantial reasons reported include short of funds, time constraints (i.e. working while reviewing, started taking another course, need to take care a family member), and lastly was because of being challenged by professors and brother to self-review. As to preferential reasons, participants reported academic preparedness to take the licensure even prior to graduation, study habit and learning style were in line with self-review, set low expectation to peers and family, a belief that no review method can guarantee success and so participant did not want to spend money for review, and lastly, a participant reported self-review because of the influence of siblings who also passed the P.N.L.E. and NCLEX-RN® through self-review.

After presenting the self-review reasons, below were the questions raised in the study as well as what the findings revealed:

Question #01: What could be the effective and efficient strategies that contributed to the success of the P.N.L.E. self-reviewees?

In an effort to identify a common pattern among the review strategies of the participants and help craft the "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" in aid of future reviewees, responses were analyzed and fourteen answers were put together:

✓ *Finding #1.a- Conduct a Self-Analysis.*

Realizing the limited timeframe between graduation and the day of licensure exam, conducting a self-analysis helped participants tailor their review schedule to the subjects that they really needed to pay more attention to. Those that did not do so failed to cover all of the topics even a day prior to the exam.

✓ *Finding #1.b- Pick a strategy that best fits your learning style and study needs.*

Evident in the responses of the seven main participants who were interviewed were differences in review strategies, but all of them shared that their review strategies were tailored on their existing learning style, review strategies during college and review needs and circumstance at the time.

✓ *Finding #1.c - Prioritize and manage your weak areas.*

Findings revealed that ten out of eleven participants prioritized their weakest subjects/ areas first in consideration to the duration of their review as against the date of the licensure and pressed urgency to finish those that needed more time reviewing and those that they still were weak at.

✓ *Finding #1.d - Organize your topics to review.*

Organizing topics coincides with prioritizing and managing the weak areas and there were two variations as to how the participants did it: First, by plotting a review timeline complete with list of topics to cover in their review, and second was to create a review calendar without a timeline. While all had their review calendars, noteworthy were those two participants (Ms. NurseG and Mr.

NurseR) who challenged having a timeline for each subject as they prioritized “understanding” vs. “completing” their topics. Upon further validation, however, while both emphasized quality vs. quantity they nonetheless completed their review calendar as they started right on time to complete all topics listed.

✓ *Finding #1.e - Tailor the review duration and frequency based on individual review Needs.*

On the negative side, those that did not set a timetable without a bargain of a longer review duration seemed to have crammed. Those were the lessons shared by Mr. NurseN, Mr. NurseJ and Ms. NurseL, all of whom had time constraints. Mr. NurseN hid his review from his classmates and acquaintances and to make it believable, he had to go out with them more often than he wanted to, thereby, compromising his review schedule. Ms. NurseL, on the other hand, was studying Medicine at the time and so she just did not have enough time to finish her review schedule right on time, and Mr. NurseJ reportedly took the licensure to “have a feel” and since he was working at the time only reviewed for two days.

Meanwhile, participants took the time to pause, or take a break to “relax” and “re-energize”, as some would say. Their experience, as compared with those who completed their respective review timelines and calendar, point to the need to tailor the review duration and frequency based on individual review needs.

✓ *Finding #1.f - Find your right venue.*

While majority reviewed at home, not all did, and all had their preferred place or area to study at. Common themes, however, were found such as place being “secluded, quiet, no disturbance, personally and ergonomically comfortable, well ventilated, and private” emanated from their choices of venue.

✓ *Finding #1.g - Get a good review material.*

Two participants gave strong opinion on using textbooks in reviewing instead of reviewing through traditional review materials. While participants used different review materials, findings suggest that review materials must be “latest”, “complete”, “reliable”, and must trickle down to “simpler explanations” for better grasp of the topics of the licensure.

✓ *Finding #1.h - Maximize help from other people and exhaust available resources.*

Self-review being “unaided” has to be coupled with maximizing available help and resources. Such was one of the findings that was revealed. From review materials acquisition, boosting each other’s morale, up to getting of pieces of advice and tips in the licensure, participants were found to be resourceful in those aspects.

✓ *Finding #1.i - Watch out for FAQs and emerging health issues*

Participant Ms. NurseE purportedly found this helpful in two ways: First, she mentioned that her friend advised her to be aware of health related current events, which she did. She claimed that current health issues at the time such as

AH1N1 virus did appear in the licensure exam during her time. Second was about being receptive with the usual type and topics of the exams given in their in-house review. She underscored being sensitive to those as a way to be up to date downsizing the self-review being unaided.

✓ *Finding #1.J - Be Inclusive, comprehensive, and integrate other topics when reviewing.*

Mr. NurseMM, mentioned for instance, "Before the review- 10- I thought I covered everything. After the review- 8- after the exam there were questions that were very tricky..." (MM36). Same thing happened to Mr. NurseO as he focused more on Medical-Surgical Nursing, but missed on Community Health Nursing (CHN) and so he got the lowest rating in CHN. In hindsight, he said it could have been better if he studied CHN more intently. Conversely, positive portrayal of inclusivity, for example, was found through Mr. NurseR wherein even if he did not like memorizing topics, he still went ahead and did it only that he pictured out the laboratory values as a table and did a mental image, and then he would relate the questions against the values in the table and how they were arranged in the table.

✓ *Finding #1.K - Execute the strategy precisely, but be flexible to contain shortcomings.*

In order to carry out what was planned, like the review timeline and review calendar, findings showed that correct execution is necessary. Ms. NurseE, for instance, would "stick to the plan" and, if she had shortcomings, would catch up and

penalize herself by extending extra time, or skipping her nap time to cover topics she missed.

✓ *Finding #1.L - Incorporate test-taking and review strategies.*

As in any test, the case participants also had various test-taking strategies, and they reportedly used them when they were still studying as well as on the day of the licensure exam itself. Test strategies such as “elimination”, “select all that apply” and “the longest option being the right answer (or the umbrella technique)” were mentioned to the least. Being analytical, concepts association, rooting it from the basics, finding connections and preferences in constructive learning helped as claimed by the participants. There was emphasis on constructive strategies as found in the actual licensure exam being scenario or situation-based questions.

✓ *Finding #1.M - Implement quality control measures.*

Quality control was achieved in four ways: First, through “self-testing”. Like what was expected, participants did self-testing and self-testing was done through Q & A, pre and posttest after each topic, using the compilation of licensure exam questions and bring home assessment, to name a few. As Mr. NurseJ remarked, they served to “recall” topics when faced with the same in the licensure. Second measure was by following through on missed target like what Ms. NurseE did when she missed a topic because of oversleeping. Third was by double checking answers just like what Mr. NurseR did. When he spots a keyword on an answer, he mentioned

that he did not hastily pick that option as his answer. He would double check to make sure before answering. Mr. NurseO, for his part, put the answer of his handbook on trial by checking against other references especially when “in doubt”. Finally, by having a standard of reference, Ms. NurseG, for example, stated that they measured what they knew against their classmate whom they consider being intelligent. Ms. NurseE, similarly used self-testing as a standard of reference. When the time came when she was already getting correct answers on practice tests, it was then that she felt she already had enough.

✓ *Finding #1.N –Ward off your worries.*

Participants undeniably felt anxiety, pressure, and even fear of failure and while inevitable, the participants shared ways on how they reportedly coped with such strong feelings. Ms. NurseE acknowledged the existence of fears as well as positive diversion to reassess and brace herself up. In addition, Ms. NurseE, Mr. NurseN and Mr. NurseR reported having low expectations in the results to cope with untoward feelings. Most of them just prayed and hoped they will pass, and Mr. NurseO further mentioned constantly reassuring himself that he was prepared well by his school and that whatever those who passed knew, he also knew of them.

2.) What personal traits did these self-reviewees possess which helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?

Three self-reported traits came on top of the list: self-confidence, self-discipline, and determination. Equally significant were other traits such as spirituality, curiosity, diligence, patience, and resourcefulness were also noted.

✓ *Finding #2.a: Self-confidence.*

Responses from six participants revealed that self-confidence is needed in self-review as well as a positive outcome of self-review. Mr. NurseJ, for instance, managed the feeling of the risk of failure with strong self-confidence; a trait that he already developed within him for some time. As a result of what they did, both he and Ms. NurseK claimed that self-review boosted their confidence. Self-review strengthened and boosted their self-confidence and efficacy.

✓ *Finding #2.b: Self-discipline*

Closely related to self-confidence is self-discipline, and the responses revealed self-discipline as a reported cause of success of the self-review as well as an acquired trait as a result of that success. Evident in the words of Ms. NurseK was the role of self-discipline: “For me, it’s all about discipline. If you don’t instill discipline in yourself and just slack off then self-review would not be effective” (K41) and even Mr. NurseN, learning his lesson when he was not able to finish his review schedule due to distractions, affirmed the importance of discipline in self-review. Likewise, both Ms. NurseK and Mr. NurseMM agreed self-review taught them the art of discipline. In the end, Ms. NurseK said, “Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline” (K45).

✓ *Finding #2.c: Determination*

Appearing third is the trait determination, and this key trait liaised other positive traits such as diligence, spirituality, and focus to drive the case participants to finish their review program and ultimately pass the licensure exam. And, determination was not only shown in determination to pass, but also determination to finish self-review and ultimately become a Registered Nurse.

✓ *Finding #2.d: Other traits noted*

Traits such as spirituality, curiosity, diligence, patience, and resourcefulness give breadth to the respective efforts each and every reviewee exerted. They have their respective use and role in the review all of which to attain the desired outcome.

Overall, the personal and academic background of the participants, shown and reflected in the common characteristics above, their strategic review strategies, as well as the strong self-reported traits help petrify the assertion that self-review, indeed, could be an effective and efficient method to make an N.L.E. reviewee pass the P.N.L.E. on his/her own.

✚ **Conclusions**

This thesis brings into the profession of nursing an understanding of the self-review experiences, strategies, and review traits from the voices of eleven self-review board passers who passed on their first take. While study findings cannot

be generalized, this paper offers a significant contribution to the nursing literature by demonstrating that self-review could be used in passing the Nursing' Licensure Examination. Further, the findings revealed that self-review, as a method, is potentially responsive to circumstantial and preferential review needs of a licensure reviewee. Given that majority of the licensure studies focus on licensure predictors, this multiple case study was designed to fill the gap by presenting a baseline understanding and the potential of this review method unique to eleven self-reviewee board passers so that we can then "...draw some new maps that enrich and extend the boundaries of our understandings beyond the margins" (Smith, 2005, p. 102) of review approaches.

The Philippine nursing educational system, if not for the whole nursing education, is continually being threatened by quality of education issues. There is still much collective work to be done, indeed, if we are to achieve and/or maintain excellent educational standards. It is a fact, however, that learning preferences and review needs vary greatly across reviewees. Therefore, trying to fit reviewees into one encompassing review approach, of any kind, would just yield poor results. As to whether those factors affect the present national licensure passing percentage, that was not established and the study did not elicit that assertion. In light of the need and preference to self-review, however, perhaps the comment offered by one of the participants that reviewing is just a culmination of the N.L.E. reviewee's four years in school and that the main advantage of self-review is that the reviewee can

have the flexibility to “focus more on your weak areas in a few weeks before licensure” could be rendered true and reflects the nature of the legitimacy and utility of this method most accurately. If fueled by effective review strategies, driven by commensurate self-review traits, and sufficient support is provided, similar success levels can be achieved in self-review as in traditional or classical review methods such as in review centers and extended in-house reviews. This kind of interpretation does not, in any way, mean that self-review is better or an alternative option to traditional or classical licensure review methods. That interpretation should and must be left with individual licensure reviewees to experience and decide. However, this thesis have argued and found that self-review, together with the resultant “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer” developed out of the participants’ review practices is an alternative solution to the material review needs of those who are interested in or find themselves the need to self-review in the Nursing Licensure Examination.

✚ Recommendations

The findings of this study point to the critical need to implement the following recommendations:

- 1.) First, that the output entitled “Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer” developed in this study, along with the practical tips and lessons learned be considered, expectations be set, or a similar document or guide for self-

reviewees be made available to those who will self-review. As what case participant Mr. NurseO opined, "Maybe if there was a research such as this before that would serve as my guide, maybe I would have gotten a higher rating..."(O186). Such necessity was underscored in the words of participant Mr. NurseR, "If you don't know what you'll cover in your review, you'll lose many things, if you don't know what you're supposed to study" (R208). Review documents such as "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" can be placed in school libraries or departmental shelves, or be made available commercially for reviewees' perusal.

2.) Second, the findings of this study revealed that self-review could be an alternative review solution for those who do not want to and those who cannot enroll in review centers or other review methods. The study therefore recommends that school administrators incorporate the study results to their curriculum. Some of the participants decided to self-review prior to graduation (e.g. ref#s R121, E107, K7, MJ7), which in turn gave them more time to cover as much topics as they can. Therefore, it would be more helpful, and thus the researcher recommends, interjecting a discussion about self-review to a subject or through a forum at least a semester away before graduation or at the outset of the last semester so students would have choices of review methods and could prepare beforehand. Awareness and setting of expectations must be conferred before graduation so as not to leave

their graduates in the dark who are unable to enroll in a review center or even to those who do not want to enroll in review centers. Nurse educators must plan and execute curricular strategies that will meet their graduates' needs regardless of review preference by having a variety of support resources in place.

3.) Third, on the day of the examination, licensure examinees fill out a form to indicate whether he/she completed a review in a review center or just conducted self-review, however, the licensure exam results being published by the Philippine Professional Regulation Commission (P.R.C.) only show the name and ratings of those who passed versus those who failed and do not indicate licensure results of those who purely passed from self-review and those who did not, neither the pass rate of those who have taken self-review. Hence, another recommendation addressed to the Philippine Nurses Association (P.N.A.), which is the primary professional organization established to promote the welfare of nurses, to suggest to the P.R.C. to allot a portion of the licensure results showing such data so that the nursing community and the public would have an accurate picture of review results regardless of review method for curriculum or review planning enhancements. While this can be done at an institutional level, the P.R.C. is tasked, through the Board of Examiners, to administer the licensure exams and is the regulating body that publishes the licensure results. Since such information is presently

being collected on the day of examination, then it may be useful to release them as a baseline data on a national level. To the very least, such data could help licensure examinees make an informed decision based on his/her self-appraisal if self-review is suited or not suited to him/her.

4.) Fourth, despite its added value to licensure reviews, the study has some limitations that are mainly due to the methodological approach chosen and the situations present at the time of research. Notwithstanding, they provide promising avenues for future research that stem from the results of this study. While part of the original plan, due to certain research constraints, the researcher was unable to include nurse educators such as the professors, clinical instructors, school administrators, institutional heads and support systems like the immediate family, close friends or people in this study. It would be interesting to find out the voices and insights of these stakeholders that may have a direct bearing and influence on the self-reviewee for policy and support system enhancements. One recommendation is to begin with a single or fewer case studies and include their significant others and the institutional heads for a more in-depth examination of each case from multiple perspectives. From there, nursing programs can establish a self-reviewees' database and continue to evaluate review outcomes in order to provide a more accurate information in predicting the likelihood of their self-reviewee graduate to pass the board exam.

5.) Fifth, this study, envisioned to help reviewees pass the licensure on their own when there is a need or preference to do so, only focused on self-reviewees who passed on their first take. Another exciting avenue for future research is to examine those who self-reviewed, but failed in the board exam. What distinguishes self-reviewee board passers, if any, from those who failed? Did the self-reviewees who failed also share the review strategies as those who passed? If so, what explains their failure? What factor, variable, or strategy, if any, is missing? Was the difference because of their personal background, review strategies, and/or traits? Comparative analysis can be done between those who failed and those who passed through self-review to identify possible self-review modification and/or enhancement.

6.) Sixth, the review strategies that were used by these nurses were deemed effective. In some ways, however, they are unique to these nurse self-reviewees. Having said that, it would be interesting to find other qualitative researchers in other fields and courses conduct studies such as this not only to identify any similarities and/or differences among self-reviewees belonging to different courses, but also be used to assist their respective reviewees and disciplines. Cross-case analysis can be done to identify common themes among and across disciplines and courses and then share those strategies with other reviewees that could be useful across and regardless of discipline. The present

study can be used as a breaking ground in setting the stage for future licensure self-review research.

7.) Lastly, in this study, one of the participants (Mr. NurseJ) reported that he had to self-review because of necessity, but admitted that he had a very difficult time with self-review as self-review is way different than his learning strategy and personality type. The participant may have been able to bear self-review though as he only did it in two days, and so it would then be interesting to find a study that would investigate self-reviewees who are extraverts and are unable to study alone for a longer period of time and were forced to self-review for circumstantial reasons. Questions such as “were they able to bear the whole time self-reviewing? How? And if so, what step/s did the self-reviewee take to cope with self-review? Also, did they pass? Why, or why not? Answers to those questions would give a better understanding on the potential usability of self-review across different personality types and learning styles.

Implications

Self-review in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.) is an area of licensure and professional nursing research that has been completely under studied, if at all. In fact, as mentioned previously, the researcher has not found, to date, an existing literature that discusses self-review similar to what has been done here. The lack or absence of research on this topic is troubling because all Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates, whether here in the Philippines

or abroad, or whether the N.L.E. reviewee enrolls in a review center, extended in-house reviews, group study or self-review, do require licensing for him/her to be allowed to safely practice the nursing profession. The fact that self-review is one of those few review methods in preparation for the licensure legitimizes the need for attention onto this review method.

Accordingly, the intent of this study was to determine if self-review could be good enough to make an N.L.E. reviewee pass the Philippine Nursing Licensure Exam (P.N.L.E.). A second intent was to have a written document, in the form of "Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer" developed from the generosity of the case participants to help, in some way, future self-reviewees in their quest to pass the licensure and ultimately practice the nursing profession. The third intent of this study was to have a written document that would be available to inform school administrators, curriculum planners, professors, support systems such as parents and peers and all concerned as to the experience of self-reviewees, what worked and what have not worked for them, what areas need more attention to in terms of curriculum planning, possible review enhancements, financial and/or moral assistance, to the least. The fourth and final intent of this study was to provide a baseline understanding for self-reviewees and provide a basis for future self-review research. This exploratory and explanatory case study on the personal and academic backgrounds of self-reviewees, their experiences, review strategies and

self-reported traits was, as to the knowledge of the researcher, first of its kind, breaking-ground, and setting the stage for future self-review research.

The first implication of this study concerns the first intent. While, time and again, there are hearsays that some self-reviewees pass licensure across disciplines, there is no formal documented basis. As to how they passed and as to what they have been, the general public and the nursing community did not know. This study just confirmed that self-review, indeed, could be used in preparation for the licensure exam notwithstanding whether circumstantial or preferential reasons. In other words, for self-review to matter, there has to be some structure in a form of a strategy. This study did not elicit responses from those who failed, so comparison cannot be done. However, there were confluence of answers among these self-reviewee board passers as to how self-review may be carried out and what traits to have for the method to work to their advantage. Perhaps, if Mr. NurseO did have a guide, he would have also focused more on his weak areas like the rest, or paid attention to Community Health Nursing and even would have gotten a higher grade, as he lamented. More to the point, if someone would have known at first that snowball may not work in group review like what Ms. NurseG and her classmates did, he/she would have saved a spare time. It maybe important to realize that in a limited time such as between graduation and the day of the licensure, the challenges and lessons learned of some could be strengths and insights to others when appropriately used and lessons are learned. In hindsight,

these measures are not inconceivable, but in reality lapses, oversights, and miscalculations happen, and one miss could mean someone's failure to become a nurse.

The second implication concerns lack or absence of academic and review assistance and/or advising both from the academe and from support systems post-graduation. The findings from these sampled participants revealed being "unaided" and that they only found a way on their own to make it to the licensure and pass. The experience of the researcher during scouting wherein only two schools among the many schools he went to had a record of their self-reviewees as well as the responses of all the participants that no assistance was extended to them before, during and even after the review post-graduation provide an ample proof. The study, therefore, strongly recommends that nursing programs assess their students' review preference even before graduation, closely monitor, and provide N.L.E. reviewee with academic advising to assist their graduate until he/she passes the licensure exam. Awareness and setting of expectations must be conferred before graduation so as not to leave their graduates in the dark who are unable to enroll in a review center or even to those who do not want to enroll in review centers. It is important that graduates know what to expect and how to conduct self-review properly so they will realize the gravity of their decision and anticipate possible challenges, if any. The scores that self-reviewees get in the Nursing

Licensure Examination not only impact their graduates, but also pose strong implications for the educational institution the student graduated from.

Assuming, that an institution already requires their graduates to enroll in a review center before they are allowed to take the licensure, how many of them are solitary learners such as Mr. NurseR or Ms. NurseK who do not learn best in a crowded area? If they fail because of inability to focus, does that mean they are no longer capable of passing the licensure and ultimately become a nurse? If, granting, that only one in 300 graduates conducts self-review, and that graduate fails in the licensure because he/she was pressed to study using a method that he/she is not comfortable with, will that person try again? As to whether that is another reason why there is a low national nursing licensure passing percentage, it has yet to be established. But how many Mr. NurseJ or Mr. NurseO the nursing community has who pursued self-review because of circumstantial short of funds? Will it happen again to somebody else? The strong assertion is 'yes'. How many graduates work immediately after graduation to support their family and do not have time to accommodate a formal review? Or how many Ms. NurseE who chose to self-review because she needed to take care of her ailing mother? To name a few... they happened to the case participants in this study, and may happen to anyone. If these participants did not pass, how many of them will shift careers and think that nursing is not really for them and/or doubt their past accomplishments such as in the study of Poorman a nd Webb

(2000)? As Shultz (2010, cited in Lee, 2014, p. 8) aired “...the implication goes far beyond the individual...”

The final implication of this study concerns a call for curriculum planners and professors to continually introduce and interject constructive learning processes instead of rehearsal or rote learning into their classes and Related Learning Experience. The findings revealed that these self-reviewees purportedly claim preference in constructive learning strategy over rote learning and had a strong academic background. Regardless of review method, these two could possibly be the ultimate reasons why they passed the licensure. Constructive learning strategies address the abstract, analytical, situational and/or scenario based questions in the licensure exam. Even with the use of self-testing, as an example, if the reviewee does not understand the concept behind the question and only memorizes the question and the answers themselves, chances are that same question, the way it has been written, will not be asked again in the licensure, but that same disease condition, that same topic, will be. There is a need, therefore, for more students to develop “meaningful experience” as what Mr. NurseJ and Ms. NurseG did and associate such experience to topic recollection; root the answers and questions from the basics and study through logic and integrate all other topics starting from the basics like what Mr. NurseN did, or use what Mr. NurseR did wherein he would create a mental image of the laboratory values and picture out in his mind the association between and among the values when answering questions.

Most of the questions in the licensure are situation-based, as the real practice of nursing it depicts to represent are situation or context based. As existing literature support, there is a need for more efforts to instill higher level of learning than mere rote memorization in students. Reviewing or preparing for the licensure only takes a couple of months and it is also possible that these self-reviewees passed the licensure, not because of the review strategy they have used as arguably they could have already been developed and embedded into their faculties beforehand, but a strong chance is that these self-reviewees may have passed the licensure purely because they already possessed that higher level of thinking instilled to them through quality education. As these self-reviewee board passers claim that they had a strong academic background, in the end, the contention is - there is no substitute for acquiring quality education.

✚ REFERENCES

- Abdullah, M. H. (2001). *Self-directed learning* (ERIC digest No. 169). Bloomington, IN: ERIC Clearinghouse on Reading, English, and Communication. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED459458).
- Adler, P. A., & Adler, P. (1994). *Observational techniques*. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research*. (p. 377-392). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Aiken, L. (2007). *U.S. Nurse Labor Market Dynamics Are Key to Global Nurse Sufficiency*. *Health Service Research* 42, Part II, June: 1299-1320.
- Alexander, J., & Brophy, G. (1997). A five-year study of graduates 'performance on NCLEX-RN. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 36, 443-445.
- Almaraz, J., Bassett, J., & Sawyer, O. (2010). Transitioning Into a Major: The Effectiveness of an Academic Intervention Course. *Journal of Education for Business*. 85: 343-348.
- Alojado Publishing International (2012). *National Capital Region*. Retrieved on July 23, 2014 from http://www.philippine-islands.ph/en/national_capital_region-philippines.html
- Al-Hebaish, S.M. (2012). The Correlation between General Self-Confidence and Academic Achievement in the Oral Presentation Course. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, Vol 2, No 1 (2012), 60-65, Jan 2012.
doi:10.4304/tpls.2.1.60-65
- Al-Zarouni, M. (2004). *Tracing E-mail Headers*. We-B Centre & Edith Cowan University, Australia.
- Amin, Z., Tani, M., Eng, K. H., Samarasekara, D. D., & Huak, C. Y. (2009). *Motivation, study habits, and expectations of medical students in Singapore*. *Medical Teacher*, 31(12), e560-569.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/01421590903193554>

- Amschler, Andrews, A., & Pradhan, A.S. (2001) Ethical issues in empirical software engineering: the limits of policy. *Empir Softw Eng* 6(2):105–110 doi: 10.1023/A: 1011442319273
- Anderson, J. R. (1995). *Learning and Memory: An Integrated Approach*. New York: Wiley.
- Angrosino, M. V. (2005). *Recontextualizing observation: Ethnography, pedagogy, and the prospects for a progressive political agenda*. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (3rd ed., pp. 729-745). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Anisimova, T. & Thomson, S.B. (2012). *Using multimethod research methodologies for more informed decision making*. JOAAG, Vol. 7. No.1
- Anyanwu, C N. (1992). Community Development. *The Nigerian Perspective*. Gabesther Educational Publishers, Ibadan.
- Aquino, G. (1971). *Essentials of Research and Thesis Writing*. Phoenix Publishing, Inc.
- Arathuzik, D. & Aber, C. (1998). *Factors associated with national council licensure examination-registered nurse success*. University of Massachusetts Boston, College of Nursing. Elsevier Inc.
<http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S8755722398800409>
- Arp, L. & Woodard, B. S. (2006). Accommodating Diverse Learning Styles in an Online Environment. *Reference & User Services Quarterly*, 2006; 46(2):27-32
- Assor, A., Vansteenkiste, M., & Kaplan, A. (2009). Identified versus introjected approach and introjected avoidance motivations in school and in sports: The limited benefits of self-worth strivings. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 101, 482–497. doi:10.1037/a0014236.
- Asumen, M. (2008). *Aptitude and Academic Achievement Variables as predictors of Nursing Board Exam Performance*. National Library of the Philippines. pg 15-33.
- Ausubel, D., Novak, J., & Hanesian, H. (1978). *Educational psychology: A cognitive view*. New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.

- Bajet, J. A. (2001) *The Integrated Nursing Comprehensive Licensure Examination Performance of the CHS, BSN, graduates of UNP*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
- Bandura, A. (1994). Self-efficacy. In V. S. Ramachaudran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of human behavior* (Vol. 4, pp. 71-81). New York: Academic Press. (Reprinted in H. Friedman [Ed.], *Encyclopedia of mental health*. San Diego: Academic Press, 1998).
- Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy: The exercise of control. U.S.A. : W.H. Freeman and Company.
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: an agentic perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52 (1), 1-26.
- Bandura, A., Barbaranelli, C., Caprara, G. V., & Pastorelli, C. (1996). Multifaceted impact of self-efficacy beliefs on academic functioning. *Child Development*, 67, 1206-1222.
- Barker, J., & Olson, J. (1997). Medical students' learning strategies: evaluation of first year changes. *Journal of the Mississippi Academy of Sciences*, 42(2). Retrieved February 25, 2014 from <http://www.msacad.org/journal/ejour2.html>.
- Beeman, P., & Waterhouse, J. (2001). *NCLEX-RN performance: Predicting success on the computerized examination*. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 17(4), 158-165.
- Bell, K. E., & Limber, J. E. (2010). *Reading skill, textbook marking, and course performance*. *Literacy Research and Instruction*, 49, 56-67.
- Belluck, P. (2011, January 20). *To really learn, quit studying and take a test*. Retrieved March 23, 2013 from: <http://www.nytimes.com/>.
- Benbasat I, Goldstein D.K., & Mead M. (1987). *The case research strategy in studies of information systems*. *MIS Q* 11(3):369-386 doi: 10.2307/248684
- Berg, B. L. (2004). *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. Boston, MA, USA: Pearson Education.

- Berg, B. (2007). *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences* (6th Ed.).
- Berk, L. E. (2003). *Child development*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Betz, N. E., Klein, K. L., & Taylor, K. M. (1996). Evaluation of a short form of the Career Decision-making Self-Efficacy Scale. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 4, 47-57. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/106907279600400103>
- Biggs, J. B. (1987). *Student approaches to learning and studying*. New York: Plenum.
- Biggs, J. B., Kember, D., & Leung, D. Y. P. (2001). *The revised two-factor Study Process Questionnaire: R-SPQ-2F*. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71, 133-149.
- Blankas, R. C. (2003). *The Licensure Examination for Teachers' performance of graduates of Northwestern University, Laoag City*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City
- Blickle, G. (1996). Personality traits, learning strategies, and performance. *European Journal of Personality*, 10, 337-352.
- Blickle, G. (1998). *Personality traits, learning strategies, and performance*. *European Journal of Personality*, 10(5), 337-352.
- Boeree, G. C. (no date). *Personality theories*. Available on: <http://www.ship.edu/~cgboeree/persintro.html>.
- Boberg, A. (2006). *An exploratory case study of the self-reported motivations of students who set school fires*. Dissertation. Northern Arizona University. December 2006. pg. 99
- Bolhuis, S. (1996). *Towards Active and Selfdirected Learning. Preparing for Lifelong Learning, with Reference to Dutch Secondary Education*. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association (New York, NY, April 8-12, 1996).
- Bonis, S., Taft, L., & Wendler, M. (2007). Strategies to promote success on the NCLEX-RN[R]: An evidence-based approach using the ACE Star Model of Knowledge Transformation. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 28(2), 82-87.

- Botti, S., & Iyengar, S.S. (2004). The psychological pleasure and pain of choosing: When people prefer choosing at the cost of subsequent outcome satisfaction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 87(3), 312-326. DOI: 10.1037/0022-3514.87.3.312.
- Bower, G. H., Monteiro, K. P., & Gilligan, S. G. (1978). Emotional mood as a context for learning and recall. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior*, 17, 573-585. doi: 10.1016/s0022-5371(78)90348-1
- Breckenridge, D. M., Wolf, Z. R., & Roszkowski, M. J. (2012). Risk assessment profile and strategies for success instrument: Determining prelicensure nursing students' risk for academic success. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 51(3), 160-6. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.3928/01484834-20120113-03
- Breitbach A., Downey D., & Frager A. (2013). The Relationship Between Candidate Psychological Factors and First-Attempt Pass Rate on the Board of Certification Examination. *Athletic Training Education Journal*: January-June 2013, Vol. 8, No. 1-2, pp. 10-16.
- Breso, E., Schaufeli, W.B., & Salanova, M. (2010). *Can a self-efficacy-based intervention decrease burnout, increase engagement, and enhance performance? A quasi-experimental study*. Published with open access at Springerlink.com. *High Educ* 61: 339-355.
- Bulatao, R.A. (1973). Measures of Happiness among Manila Residents. *Philippine Sociological Review*, 1973, Vol. 21, 229 – 238.
- Busato, V. V., Prins, F. J., Elshout, J. J. & Hamaker, C. (1998). *The relation between learning styles, the Big Five personality traits and achievement motivation in higher education*. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 26(1), 129–140.
- Buttriss, G., & Wilkinson, I. F. (2006). Using narrative sequence methods to advance international entrepreneurship theory. *Journal of international Entrepreneurship*, 4, 157–174.
- Caligiuri, P. M. (2000). The big five personality characteristics as predictors of expatriate's desire to terminate the assignment and supervisor-rated performance. *Personnel Psychology*, 53(1), 67–88.

- Callender, A. A., & McDaniel, M. A. (2009). The limited benefits of rereading educational texts. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 34, 30–41.
- Caprara, G. V., Vecchione, M., & Schwartz, S. H. (2009). The mediational role of values in linking personality traits to political preference. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 12, 82–94.
- Carrick, J. (2011). Student Achievement and NCLEX-RN Success: Problems That Persist. *Nursing Education Perspectives*: April 2011, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp. 78-83.
- Carrier, C., & Melvin, K. (1982, May). *Linking teacher theories to teacher practices*. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the Association for Educational Communications and Technology, Dallas, TX
- Caselman, T., & Self, P. (2007). "Adolescent Perception of Self as a Close Friend: Culture and Gendered Contexts." *Social Psychology of Education* 10 (2007): 353-73. Education Research Complete.
- Cepeda, N. J., Pashler, H., Vul, E., Wixted, J. T., & Rohrer, D. (2006). Distributed practice in verbal recall tasks: A review and quantitative synthesis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132, 354–380.
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T., & Furnham, A. (2003). Personality predicts academic performance: Evidence from two longitudinal university samples. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 37, 319–338.
- Chen, G., Casper, W. J., & Cortina, J. M. (2001). The role of self-efficacy and task complexity in the relationships among cognitive ability, conscientiousness, and work-related performance: A meta-analytic examination. *Human Performance*, 14, 209–230.
- Chinn P. (1985). Debunking Myths in Nursing Theory Research. *Image Journal of Scholarship*. 7:2 pp. 171-179
- Clegg, J. (2003). The ideal proxy informant. *Ethics and Intellectual Disability*, 7, 2, 1-5.
- Coggins, C. C. (1988). Preferred learning styles and their impact on completion of external degree programs. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 2(1), 25-37

- Cohen, A. P. (1984). Informants. In R. F. Ellen, *Ethnographic research: A guide to general conduct*. (pp. 223-229). Orlando, FL: Academic Press, Inc.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2011). *Research Methods in Education* (7th ed.). New York
- Collis, B. (1999). New didactics for university instruction: why and how? *Computers & Education*, 31(4): 373 – 393.
- Confrey, J. (1990). A review of the research on student conceptions in mathematics, science, and programming. *Review of Research in Education*, 16, 3-56.
- Cope, M. (2002). *Feminist epistemology in geography*. In Moss, P. (ed.) *Feminist geography in practice: research methods*. Cambridge, MA: Blackwell Publishers, pp. 43-56
- Cortes, P. & Pan, J. (2012). *Relative Quality of Foreign Nurses in the United States*. Boston University.
- Costa, P. T., Jr., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). *Revised NEO Personality Inventory (NEO-PI-R) and NEO Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI) professional manual*. Odessa, FL: Psychological Assessment Resources.
- Cunningham, D.J. (1991). Assessing Constructions and Constructing Assessments. *Educational Technology*, 31(5):13-17
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crow, C., Handley, M., Morrison, R. & Shelton M. (2004). *Requirements and interventions used by BSN programs to promote and predict NCLEX-RN success: A national study*. Elsevier Inc. 2004
- Curry, L. (1983). *An organization of learning styles theory and constructs*. Retrieved June 26, 2014, from ERIC database, TM 830 554.
- De Raad, B. & Schouwenburg, H. C. (1996). Personality in learning and education: a review. *European Journal of Personality*, 10, 303-336

- Deci, E.L. & Ryan, R.M. (1985). *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. New York: Plenum Press.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11, 227–268. doi:10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01.
- De Vaus, D. (2001). *Research Design in Social Research*. London: Sage.
- Del Rosario, B., & Estrada, R. (2010). Predictors of Success in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (PNLE) Among DDC Nursing Graduates (2004 – 2006). College of Nursing. *Faculty Research Journal*, Vol 1, No 1 (2010). C&E Publishing, Inc.
- DeLima, M., London, L., & Manieri, E. (2011). *Looking at the past to change the future: A retrospective study of associate degree in nursing graduates' National Council Licensure Examination scores*. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 6(3), 119–123.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). *Introduction: Entering the Field of Qualitative Research*. In Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (eds) (2000) *Handbook of Qualitative Research*. London: Sage
- Denzin, N.K., & Lincoln, Y.S. (2005). *Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research*. In N.K. Denzin & Y.S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The sage handbook of qualitative research* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Dervin, B. (1983). *An overview of sense-making: concepts, methods, and results to date*. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the International Communications Association, Dallas, TX
- DiCarlo, S.E. (2008). *Teaching alveolar ventilation with simple, inexpensive models*. *Adv Physiol Educ* 32: 185–191
- Diseth, A. (2003). Personality and approaches to learning as predictors of academic achievement. *European Journal of Personality*, 17, 143-155.
- Diseth, A., Pallesen, S., Hovland, A., & Larsen, S. (2006). *Course experience, approaches to learning and academic achievement*. *Education & Training*, 48, 156-169.

- Douglas, D. (2003). Inductive theory generation: A grounded approach to business inquiry, *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 2(1), <http://www.ejbrm.com>
- Driscoll, M. P. (2005). *Psychology of learning for instruction (3rd ed.)*. Boston: Pearson Allyn and Bacon.
- Duffy, T.M. & Jonassen, D.H. (1991). Constructivism: New Implications for Instructional Technology? *Educational Technology*, 31(5):7-12
- Dunlosky, J., & Metcalfe, J. (2009). *Metacognition*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Dunlosky, J., Rawson, K. A., & Middleton, E. (2005). What constrains the accuracy of metacomprehension judgments? Testing the transfer-appropriate-monitoring and accessibility hypotheses. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 52, 551–565.
- Dunn, R., & Griggs, S. (1995). *Multiculturalism and learning styles: Teaching and counseling adolescents*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Eddy, L. L., & Epeneter, B. J. (2002). The NCLEX-RN experience: Qualitative interviews with graduates of a baccalaureate nursing program. *Journal of Nursing Education* (41)6.
- Eich, E., & Metcalfe, J. (1989). Mood Dependent Memory for Internal Versus External Events. *Journal of Experimental Psychology-Learning Memory and Cognition*, 15(3), 443-455.
- Eisenhardt, K., & Bourgeois, L. J. (1988). Politics of strategic decision making in high-velocity environments: Toward a midrange theory. *Academy of Management Journal*, 31: 737-770.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. (1989). *Building theories from case study research*. *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 14, No. 4, pp. 532-550.
- Ellis, H. C., & Moore, B. A. (1999). Mood and Memory. In T. Dalgleish & M. J. Power (Eds.), *Handbook of cognition and emotion* (pp. 193-210). New York, NY, US: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

- Entwistle, N. J., & Ramsden, P. (1983). *Understanding student learning*. London: Crumb Helm.
- Entwistle, N & Tait, H (1996). *Approaches and Study Skills Inventory for Students*. Centre for Research on Learning and Instruction. University of Edinburgh.
- Entwistle, N. (1988). *Motivational factors in students' approaches to learning*", in: *Learning strategies and learning styles*. Edited by R. R. Schmeck. New York: Plenum Press. pp. 21-49
- Entwistle, N., & McCune, V. (2004). *The conceptual bases of study strategy inventories*. *Educational Psychology Review*, 16, 325-345.
- Erlandson, D. A., Harris, E. L., Skipper, B. L. & Allen, S. D. (1993). *Doing Naturalistic Inquiry: a Guide to Methods*. Newbury Park, Calif., Sage.
- Fernandez, A., & Glenberg, A. M. (1985). Changing environmental context does not reliably affect memory. *Memory and Cognition*, 13(4), 333-345.
- Fisher, M., King, J., & Tague, G. (2001). *Development of a self-directed learning readiness scale for nursing education*. Harcourt Publishers Ltd
- Fleming, S., McKee, G., & Huntley-Moore, S. (2011). *Undergraduate nursing students' learning styles: A longitudinal study*. *Nursing Education Today* 31, 444-449. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2010.08.005>
- Flynn B.B., Sakakibara S., Schroeder R.G., Bates K, & Flynn E.J. (1990). *Empirical research methods in operations management*. *Oper Manage* 9(2):250-284 doi: 10.1016/0272-6963(90)90098-X
- Flyvbjerg B (2007). *Five misunderstandings about case-study research*. In *Qualitative Research Practice: Concise Paperback Edition*. Sage, pp. 390-404
- Folkestad, B (2008). *Analysing Interview Data: Possibilities and challenges*. Eurosphere Working Paper Series. Eurosphere Working Paper Series. Online Working Paper No. 13, 2008. Retrieved on July 02, 2014 from <http://eurosphere.uib.no/knowledgebase/workingpapers.htm>.

- Fowler, R. L., & Barker, A. S. (1974). Effectiveness of highlighting for retention of text material. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59, 358–364.
- Frith, K., Sewell, J., & Clark, D. (2006). Best practices in NCLEX readiness preparation for baccalaureate student success. *Nurse Educator*, 33(5) (Suppl.), 46S-53S.
- Galbraith, A & Alexander, J. (2005). "Literacy, self-esteem and locus of control." Support for Learning 20.1 (2005): 28-34. *Academic Search Complete*. Web 10 Sep. 2011.
- Garrison, D.R. (1997). Self-directed learning: Toward a comprehensive model. *In Adult Education Quarterly*, Fall 97 v 48 n 1, p18, 16 p.
- Gilbert, D., & Ebert, J.E.J. (2002). "Decisions and revisions: The affective forecasting of changeable outcomes." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. 82: 503-514.
- Gibran, K. (n.d.). *Kahlil Gibran quotes*. Retrieved on February 16, 2015 from http://thinkexist.com/quotation/say_not--i_have_found_the_truth-but_rather--i/15687.html
- Glaser, B., 1978. *Theoretical Sensitivity*. Sociology Press, Mill Valley, CA.
- Glesne, C. (2011). *Becoming qualitative researchers: An introduction* (4th ed.). Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Pearson.
- Glesne, C., & Peshkin, A. (1992). *Becoming qualitative researchers: An introduction*. White Plains, NY: Longman.
- Godden, D. R., & Baddeley, A. D. (1975). Context-Dependent Memory in 2 Natural Environments - Land and Underwater. *British Journal of Psychology*, 66(3), 325-331.
- Griggs, S., & Dunn, R. (1996). Learning styles of Asian-American adolescents. *Emergency Librarian*, 24(1), 8-13

Grossbach & Kuncel (2011). *The Predictive Validity of Nursing Admission Measures for Performance on the National Council Licensure Examination: A Meta-Analysis*. University of Minnesota. Elsevier Inc.

Guba, E.G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries, *Educational Communication and Technology Journal*. 29, pp. 75–91.

Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1981). *Effective evaluation: Improving the usefulness of evaluation results through responsive and naturalistic approaches*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

Gubrium, J. & Holstein, J. (2002) *Handbook of interview research: context and method*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Guirra, G.A. (1998). *Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of Northwestern University: An analysis*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Northwestern University, Laoag City

Gummesson, E. (1988). *Qualitative methods in management research*. Lund, Norway: Studentlitteratur, Chartwell-Bratt.

Haas, R. E., Nugent, K. E., & Rule, R.A. (2004). The use of discriminate function analysis to predict student success on the NCLEX-RN. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 43(10), 440-446.

Hakim, C. (1987). *Research design. Strategies and choices in the design of social research*. Boston: Unwin Hyman.

Hall, B. L. (1999). *How to do ethnographic research: A simplified guide [On-line]*. Available: www.sas.upenn.edu/anthro/CPIA/METHODS/

Hartwig, M. & Dunlosky, J. (2012). *Study strategies of college students: Are self-testing and scheduling related to achievement?* *Psychon Bull Rev* (2012) 19:126–134. DOI 10.3758/s13423-011-0181-y

Hassan, E. (2006). Recall Bias can be a Threat to Retrospective and Prospective Research Designs. *The Internet Journal of Epidemiology*. 2006 Volume 3 Number 2. DOI: 10.5580/2732

Hassard, J & Parker, M. (1993) *Postmodernism & Organizations*, London: Sage.

- Hayes, J., & Allinson, C. W. (1997). Learning styles and training and development in work settings: Lessons from educational research. *Educational Psychology*, 17(1-2), 185-193.
- Heinström, J. (2000). *The impact of personality and approaches to learning on information behaviour*. Information Research, Vol. 5 No. 3.
<http://informationr.net/ir/5-3/paper78.html>
- Herriott, R. E., & Firestone, W. A. (1983). *Multisite qualitative policy research: Optimizing description and generalizability*. Educational Researcher, 12(2), 14-19.
- Hilario, I. (2000). *Factors influencing the licensure examination performance of teacher education institutions in the Cordillera Administrative Region*. Unpublished Dissertation. St. Louise University, Baguio City.
- Hodgson, S. (2004). *Cutting through the silence: A sociological construction of self-injury*. Sociological Inquiry, 74(2), 162-179.
- Honebein, P. C., Duffy, T. M., & Fishman, B. J. (1993). Constructivism and the design of learning environments: Context and authentic activities for learning. In T. M. Duffy, J. Lowyck, D. H. Jonassen, & T. M. Welsh (Eds.), *Designing environments for constructive learning* (pp. 87-107). Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- Hopper, K. B. (2003). In defense of the solitary learner: A response to collaborative, constructivist education. *Educational Technology*, 43(2), 24-29
- Howard, P. J. & Howard, J. M. (1998). *An introduction to the five-factor model for personality for human resource professionals*.
- Hwang, A., Kessler, E.H., & Francesco, A.M. (2004). *Student Networking Behavior, Culture, and Grade Performance: An Empirical Study and Pedagogical Recommendations*. Academy of Management Learning and Education. Vol. 3, No. 2, 139-150.

- Ibrahimoglu, N., Unaldi, I., Samancioglu, M., & Baglibel, M. (2013). The relationship between personality traits and learning styles: a cluster analysis. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences and Education*. Issn: 2186-845x issn: 2186-8441 print vol. 2 no. 3, july 2013
- Institute for Learning Styles Research. (2003), in Shannon, S. (2008). *Institute for Learning Styles Research*. Retrieved August 8, 2014 from <<http://www.learningstyles.org>>.
- Internet World Stats. (2005). *Internet World Stats: Usage and population*
- Jenner, C. (2012). *College of Business Students' Predictors of Success and Academic Performance: The Effects of Academic Intervention and Communication, General Self-Efficacy, Academic Motivation, and Social Activity*. Savannah State University
- Jonassen, D. H., & Grabowski, B. L. (1993). *Individual differences: Learning and instruction*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum
- Judge, T. A., Jackson, C. L., Shaw, J. C., Scott, B. A., & Rich, B. L. (2007). Self-Efficacy and Work-Related Performance: The Integral Role of Individual Differences. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92, 107-127.
- Kalisch, P.A. & Kalisch, B.A. (1978). *The advance of American nursing*. Boston: Little, Brown.
- Kanfer, R. (1992). Work motivation: New directions in theory and research. In C. L.Cooper & I. T.Robertson (Eds.). *International review of industrial and organizational psychology* (Vol. 7, pp. 1-53). Chichester, England: Wiley.
- Karchmer, R. A. (2001). *The journey ahead: Thirteen teachers report how the Internet influences literacy and literacy instruction in their K-12 classrooms*. Reading Research Quarterly, 36, 442-466.
- Karpicke, J. D., Butler, A. C., & Roediger, H. L., 3rd. (2009). *Metacognitive strategies in student learning: do students practise retrieval when they study on their*

own? Memory, 17(4), 471-479.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09658210802647009>

- Keefe, J.W. (1987). *Learning style theory and practice*. Reston, VA: National Association of Secondary.
- Kelly, E. (1997). Development of strategies to identify the learning needs of baccalaureate nursing students. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 36(4), 156–162.
- Kennedy, T.L.M. (2000). *An exploratory study of feminist experiences in cyberspace*. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 3(5), 707–719.
- Kim, B.S.K., Brenner, B.R., Liang, C.T.H., & Asay, P.A. (2003). *A qualitative study of adaptation experiences of 1.5-generation Asian Americans*. *Cultural Diversity & Ethnic Minority Psychology*, 9(2), 156–170.
- Kinshuk, Liu, T. & Graf, S. (2009). Coping with mismatched courses: students' behaviour and performance in courses mismatched to their learning styles. *Education Technology Research and Development*, 2009; 57:739-752.
- King, N. (1994). *The qualitative research interview*. In *Qualitative methods in organizational research: A practical guide*. Edited by C. Cassell and G. Symon, 14–36. London: Sage.
- Kirk, J., & Miller, M. L. (1986). *Reliability and validity in qualitative research*. Qualitative Research Methods Series 1. London: Sage.
- Kleih, Riccio, Mattia, Schreuder, Tangermann, Zickler, Neuper, & Kubler (2011). Motivation affects Performance in a P300 Brain Computer Interface. *International Journal of Bioelectromagnetism*. Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 46- 47, 2011
- Knowles M.S. (1975). *Self-Directed Learning: A Guide for Learners and Teachers*. Association Press, New York, NY
- Knowles MS (1980) in Merrit S. *learning style preference of baccalaureate nursing students*. *Journal of nursing education*, 1983; 32(6), 367-72.

- Knowles, M.S. (1990). *The Adult Learner: A Neglected Species, 4th edn.* Gulf Publishing, Houston, TX
- Koestner, R., & Losier, G. F. (2002). Distinguishing three ways of being highly motivated: A closer look at introjection, identification, and intrinsic motivation. In E. L. Deci & R. M. Ryan (Eds.), *The handbook of self-determination theory research* (pp. 101–121). Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press.
- Kohn, L. (1997). *Methods in Case Study Analysis.* The Center for Studying Health System Change Technical Publication No.2.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential Learning: Experience as the source of learning and development.* New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Kolb, D. A. (1999). *The Kolb Learning Style Inventory:* Hay Resources Direct.
- Kornell, N., & Bjork, R. A. (2007). *The promise and perils of self-regulated study.* *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 6, 219-224
- Krippendorff K. (1980). *Content analysis: an introduction to its methodology.* London: Sage
- Kvale, S. (1996). *Inter Views: An introduction to qualitative research interviewing.* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Larsen, D. P., Butler, A. C., & Roediger, H. L. (2008). *Test-enhanced learning in medical education.* *Medical Education*, 3rd. (42(10), 959-966.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2923.2008.03124.x>
- Lee, A.S. (1989) *A scientific methodology for MIS case studies.* *MIS Q* 13(1):33–54
doi: 10.2307/248698
- Lee, K. (2014). *NCLEX-RN test anxiety among Hmong Nursing Students.* Master of Arts/Science in Nursing Scholarly Projects. Paper 72. Retrieved from http://sophia.stkate.edu/ma_nursing/72
- Lehu, J-M. (2004). Back to life! Why brands grow old and sometimes die and what managers then do: An exploratory qualitative research put into the French context. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 10, 133–152.

- Lemogne, C., Piolino, P., Friszer, S., Claret, A., Girault, N., Jouvent, R. . . Fossati, P. (2006). Episodic autobiographical memory in depression: Specificity, auto-nocentric consciousness, and self-perspective. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 15, 258-268. doi: 10.1016/j.concog.2005.07.005
- Leonard-Barton, D. (1990). *Manual methodology for case studies: Synergistic use of a longitudinal single site with replicated multiple sites*. *Organization Science* 1 (3): 248-66.
- Limberg, L. (1999). *Three conceptions of information seeking and use*. In T. D. Wilson & D.K. Allen (Eds.)
- Lincoln Y.S. & Guba E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Beverly Hills: Sage
- Lohre, E. (2011). Context-Dependent Memory. Master of Philosophy in Psychology, *Cognitive Neuroscience*. Universitetet I Oslo. May 2011
- Lopez, E., Nandagopal, K., Shavelson, R., Szu, E., & Penn, J. (2013). Self-regulated learning study strategies and academic performance in undergraduate organic chemistry: An investigation examining ethnically diverse students. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*. Volume 50, Issue 6, pages 660-676, August 2013. DOI: 10.1002/tea.21095
- MacCann, C., Duckworth, A. L., & Roberts, R. (2009). Empirical identification of the major facets of conscientiousness. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 19, 451-458.
- Marczyk, G., DeMatteo, D., & Festinger, D. (2005). *Essentials of research design and methodology*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Martin, J. H., Montgomery, R. L., & Saphian, D. (2006). Personality, achievement test scores, and high school percentile as predictors of academic performance across four years of coursework. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 40, 424-431.

- Martocchio, J. J., & Judge, T. A. (1997). Relationship between conscientiousness and learning in employee training: Mediating influences of self-deception and self-efficacy. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82, 764–773.
- Marton, F. (1986). Phenomenography – a research approach to investigating different understandings of reality. *Journal of thought*, 21, 28-49.
- Marton, F., & Booth, S. (1997). *Learning and awareness*: New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Maxwell, J. (1992). *Understanding and Validity in Qualitative Research*. Harvard Educational Review; Fall (1992). 62, 3; Research Library. Core pg. 279
- Maxwell, J. A. (1996). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- May, C. P., Hasher, L., & Stoltzfus, E. R. (1993). *Optimal time of day and the magnitude of age differences in memory*. *Psychological Science*, 4, 326–330.
- McCabe, J. (2011). *Metacognitive awareness of learning strategies in undergraduates*. *Memory & Cognition*, 39, 462–476. doi:10.3758/s13421-010-0035-2
- McClanaghan, M. D. (2000). A strategy for helping students learn how to learn. *Education*, 120(3), 479-486
- McConnell, M. M., Regehr, G., Wood, T. J., & Eva, K. W. (2011). *Self-monitoring and its relationship to medical knowledge*. *Advances in Health Sciences Education, Theory and Practice*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10459-011-9305-4>
- McCrae, R. & John, O. (1992). An introduction to the Five-Factor Model and its applications. *Journal of Personality*, 2, 174-214.
- McCrae, R. R., & Costa, P. T., Jr. (1999). *A five-factor theory of personality*. In L. A.Pervin & O. P.John (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (2nd ed., pp. 139–153). New York: Guilford Press.

- McDowell, B. (2008). KATTS: A framework for maximizing NCLEX- RN performance. *Journal of Nursing Education* 47(4), 183- 186.
- McGahee, T., Gramling, L., & Reid, T. (2010). NCLEX-RN® Success: Are There Predictors. *Southern Online Journal of Nursing Research*. Vol. 10, No. 4.
- McNulty, J, Ensminger, D., Hoyt, A., Chandrasekhar, A., Gruener, G., & Espiritu, B. (2012). Study Strategies Are Associated with Performance in Basic Science Courses in the Medical Curriculum. *Journal of Education and Learning*; Vol. 1, No. 1; 2012. Canadian Center of Science and Education
- Meho, L. (2013). *E-Mail Interviewing in Qualitative Research: A Methodological Discussion*. School of Library and Information Science, Indiana University. Retrieved on July 22, 2013 from <http://eprints.rclis.org/8377/1/email-interviewing.pdf>
- Meho L. I., & Tibbo, H. R. (2003). Modeling the information seeking behavior of social scientists: Ellis's study revisited. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 54(6), 570-587. Retrieved March 25, 2013, from <http://dlist.sir.arizona.edu/1641/pdf>
- Merriam, S. B. (1998). *Qualitative research and case study applications in education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Merriam, S. B. (2002). *Qualitative Research in Practice: Examples for Discussion and Analysis*. New York: Wiley, John & Sons
- Merriam, S., & Simpson, E. (2000). *A guide to research for educators and trainers of adults*. Malabar, FL: Krieger.
- Merrit, S. (1983). *Learning style preferences of baccalaureate nursing students*. *Journal of nursing education*. 32(6), 367-72.
- Metropolitan Manila Development Authority. (2009). *Metropolitan Manila Land Area and Year of Cityhood by Local Government Units*. Retrieved April 8, 2013, from <http://www.mmda.gov.ph/>
- Meyer, C. B. (2001). *A Case in Case Study Methodology*. *Field Methods*, Vol. 13, No. 4, November 2001 329–352© 2001 Sage Publications.

- Miles, M. B. (1979). *Qualitative Data as an Attractive Nuisance Problem of Analysis*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24, 590-601.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Mitchell, J. C. (1983). *Case and situation analysis*. *Sociology Review* 51 (2): 187–211.
- Mohamed, A.A. & Helal, H.A. (2012). Learning Styles of Community Health Nursing Students' at Faculty of Nursing and Technical Institute of Nursing - In Alexandria. *New York Science Journal*, 2012; 5(4)
- Mosser, N., Williams, J., & Wood, C. (2006). *The use of progression testing throughout nursing education programs: How colleges promote success on the NCLEX-RN*. *Annual Review of Nursing Education*, 4, 305-319.
- Mostyn B. (1985). The Content Analysis of Qualitative Research Data. In Brenner M., Brown J. and Canter D. (Eds) *The Research Interviews. Uses and Approaches*. London: Academic Press.
- Mouton, J. (1996). *Understanding social research* (Pretoria, J. L. van Schaik Publishers).
- Murphy RJ, Gray, S.A, Straja SR, & Bogert M.C. (2004). *Student learning preferences and teaching implications*. *J Dent Educ* 68: 859–866.
- Myers, M., (1997). *Interpretive Research in Information Systems*", in J Mingers and F Stowell (Eds), *Information Systems: An Emerging Discipline?* McGraw-Hill, London, pp 239-266
- NCSBN (2007, February 9). *NCSBN Selects the Philippines as International Testing Site for NCLEX Examinations*. National Council of State Boards of Nursing, Inc. Retrieved June 30, 2013 from <https://www.ncsbn.org/1152.htm>
- Nauta, M. (2004). Self-efficacy as a mediator of the relationships between personality factors and career interests. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 12, 381–394.

- Naveh-Benjamin, M., McKeachie, W.J., & Lin, Y.G. (1987). Two types of test-anxious students: Support for an information processing model. *J. Educ. Psychol.*, 79: 131-136. DOI: 10.1037/0022-0663.79.2.131
- Nelson, S., & Conner, C. (2008). *Developing self-directed learners*.
- Neri, D.L. (2008). Intellective Variables as Predictors to Nursing Licensure Examination Performance. *Liceo Journal of Higher Education Research*. Vol. 6 No. 1 December 2009 ISSN: 2094-1064.
- Nguyen, N. T., Allen, L. C., & Fraccastoro, K. (2005). Personality predicts academic performance: Exploring the moderating role of gender. *Journal of Higher Education Policy & Management*, 27, 105-116.
- Ning, H.K., & Downing, K. (2010). *The impact of supplemental instruction on learning competence and academic performance*. Society of Research into Higher Education. Vol. 35, No. 8, 921-939.
- Nursingcrib (2007, October 8). *History of Nursing in the Philippines*. Retrieved April 8, 2014 from <http://nursingcrib.com/nursing-notes-reviewer/history-of-nursing-in-the-philippines/comment-page-3/>
- O'Brien, R. (2001). *An Overview of the Methodological Approach of Action Research*.
- Oldham, J. M., & Morris, L. B. (1995). *The new personality self-portrait: Why you think, work, love, and act the way you do*. Boston: Bantam Dell
- Ong, M., Palompon, D., & Banico, L. (2012). Predictors of Nurses' Licensure Examination Performance of Graduates in Cebu Normal University, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Health*. Vol. 2 • January 2012. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7828/ajoh.v2i1.122>
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., Slate, J. R., & Schwartz, R. A. (2001). Role of study skills in graduate-level educational research courses. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 94(4), 238-246. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00220670109598757>
- Ormrod, J. E. (2004). *Human learning (4th Ed.)*. Upper Saddle River, N.J.: Merrill.

- Ornek, F. (2008). *An overview of a theoretical framework of phenomenography in qualitative education research: An example from physics education research*. Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching, 9(2).
- Osman, A. (2004). *Comparative study of learning style*. Master's thesis. Faculty of nursing. EL Menia University, Egypt.
- Packer, M. (2011). *The science of qualitative research*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Palaganas, E. C., Rosales, A. B., & Divinagracia, C. D. C (2012). *Nurse Licensure Examination Performance of Graduates of Philippine Colleges of Nursing in the Philippines: Policy Implications*. Podium Presentation, STTI 23rd International Nursing Research Congress, Brisbane, Australia.
- Palloff, R. M. & Pratt K. (2003). *The virtual student: A profile and guide to working with online learner*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Paprock, K., Yumol, B., Atienza, T. (2006). National Human Resource Development in Transitioning Societies in the Developing World: The Philippines. *Human Resource Development International*. 8(1): 46 – 58.
- Pastorelli, C., Caprara, G. V., Barbaranelli, C., Rola, J., Rozsa, S., & Bandura, A. (2001). The structure of children's perceived self-efficacy: A cross-national study. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 17, 87–97.
- Pandey, P., & Zimitat, C. (2007). *Medical students' learning of anatomy: memorisation, understanding and visualisation*. *Medical Education*, 41(1), 7-14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2929.2006.02643.x>
- Paraszczyk, A. M. (2011). *The Effect of Review Classes on Performance on Comprehensive Assessments and the National Council Licensure Examination of Graduating Baccalaureate Nursing Students*. STTI International Nursing Research Congress. <http://hdl.handle.net/10755/155940>

- Parkhe, A. (1993). Strategic alliance structuring, a game theoretic and transaction cost examination of interfirm cooperation'. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36, pp. 794 – 829.
- Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods (2nd ed)*. London: Sage
- Patton, M.Q. (2002). *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Pettigrew, A. M. (1990). *Longitudinal field research on change: Theory and practice*. *Organization Science* 1 (3): 267–92.
- Phares, E. J. (1991). *Introduction to psychology. (3rd. Ed.)* New York: Harper Collins Publishers.
- Pines, A. L. (1985). Toward a taxonomy of conceptual relations and the implications for the evaluation of cognitive structures. In L. H. T. West and A. L. Pines (Eds.). *Cognitive Structure and Conceptual Change*. New York: Academic Press, Inc.
- Poorman, S., & Webb, C. (2000). *Preparing to retake the NCLEX-RN: The experience of graduates who fail*. *Nurse Educator*, 25(4), 175-180.
- Rawson, K. A., & Dunlosky, J. (2011). Optimizing schedules of retrieval practice for durable and efficient learning: How much is enough? *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 140,283–302. doi: 10.1037/a0023956
- Rawson, K. A., & Kintsch, W. (2005). *Rereading effects depend on time of test*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 97, 70–80.
- Revelle, W. & Loftus, D. (1992). *The implications of arousal effects for the study of affect and memory*. Retrieved March 23, 2014 from <http://pmc.psych.nwu.education/revelle/publications/r191/rev-loft-ToC.html>.

- Riding, R., & Grimley, M. (1999). Cognitive style and learning from multimedia materials in 11-year children. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 30(1), 43-59.
- Robson C (2002) *Real World Research*. Blackwell, (2nd edition)
- Rodriguez, S., Romero-Canyasa, R., Downey, G., Mangels, J. & Higgins, E.T. (2013). When School Fits Me: How Fit Between Self-Beliefs and Task Benefits Boosts Math Motivation and Performance. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology* Volume 35, Issue 5, 2013. DOI:10.1080/01973533.2013.823613
- Roediger, H. L., 3rd, & Butler, A. C. (2011). *The critical role of retrieval practice in long-term retention*. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 15(1), 20-27.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2010.09.003>
- Roediger, H. L., III, & Karpicke, J. D. (2006). *Test-enhanced learning*. *Psychological Science*, 17, 249-255.
- Rohrer, D., & Pashler, H. (2010). *Recent research on human learning challenges Conventional Instructional Strategies*. [Reports Evaluative]. *Educational Researcher*, 39(5), 406-412. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3102/0013189X10374770>
- Romeo, E. (2013). *The Predictive Ability of Critical Thinking, Nursing GPA, and SAT Scores on First-Time NCLEX-RN Performance*. *Nursing Education Perspectives*: August 2013, Vol. 34, No. 4, pp. 248-253.
- Roncoli, M., Lisanti, P., & Falcone, A. (2000). Characteristics of baccalaureate graduates and NCLEX-RN performance. *Journal of NY State Nurses Association*, 31(1), 17-19.
- Rowley, J. (2002). *Using case studies in research*. *Management Research News*, 25 (1), 16-27.
- Rubin, H., & Rubin, I. (1995). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Runeson, P. & Host, M. (2008). *Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering*. Empirical Software Engineering.

Runeson, P. & Host, M. (2009). *Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering*. Empir Software Eng. 14:131-164. DOI 10.1007/s10664-008-9102-8

Ryan, A., & Pintrich, P. (1997). "Should I Ask for Help?": The Role of Motivation and Attitudes in Adolescents' Help Seeking in Math Class. *Journal of educational psychology*, 89(2), 329-341.

Saeed, N., Yang, Y., & Sinnappan, S. Emerging Web Technologies in Higher Education: A Case of Incorporating Blogs, Podcasts and Social Bookmarks in a Web Programming Course based on Students' Learning Styles and Technology Preferences. *Educational Technology & Society*, 2009; 12(4):98-109

Saufley, W. H., Otaka, S. R., & Bavaresco, J. L. (1985). Context Effects - Classroom Tests and Context Independence. *Memory & Cognition*, 13(6), 522-528.

Schmidt, B., & MacWilliams, B. (2011). *Admission Criteria for Undergraduate Nursing Programs: Systematic Review*. Nurse Educator. 36(4), 171-174.

Schouwenburg, H. C. (1995). *Personality and academic competence*. Poster presented at the seventh meeting of the International Society for Study of Individual Differences, Warsaw, Poland.

Schunk, D. H. (2012). *Learning theories: An educational perspective*. Boston: Pearson.

Seale, C. (1999). *The quality of qualitative research*. London: Sage.

Seldomridge, L. & DiBartolo, M. (2004). Can success and failure be predicted for baccalaureate graduates on the computerized NCLEX-RN? *Journal of Professional Nursing*. Volume 20, Issue 6, November-December 2004, Pages 361-368

- Selwyn, N., & Robson, K. (2004). *Using e-mail as a research tool. Social Research Update*, 21. Year 1998. Retrieved on July 22, 2013 from <http://www.websm.org/db/12/2888/rec>
- Shannon, S. (2008). Using Metacognitive Strategies and Learning Styles to Create Self-Directed Learners. *Institute for Learning Styles Journal*. Volume 1. Fall 2008, pp 14-28.
- Shenton, A.K. (2004). *Strategies for ensuring trustworthiness in qualitative research projects*. *Education for Information* 22 (2004) 63–75 63. IOS Press
- Siggelkow, N. (2007). *Persuasion with case studies*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1): 20-24.
- Silverman, D. (2000). *Doing qualitative research: A practical handbook*. London: Sage.
- Simon, E. McGinniss, S. & Krauss, B. (2013). *Predictor Variables for NCLEX-RN Readiness Exam Performance*. *Nursing Education Perspectives*: January 2013, Vol. 34, No. 1, pp. 18-24.
- Smith, S. M. (1984). A comparison of two techniques for reducing context-dependent forgetting. *Memory & Cognition*, 12(5), 477-482.
- Smith, S. M. (2007). Context and human memory. In H. L. Roediger, III, Y. Dudai, and S. M. Fitzpatrick (Eds.), *Science of Memory: Concepts* (pp. 111-114). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Smith, J. K. & Heshusius, L. (1986). *Closing down the conversation: The end of the quantitative-qualitative debate among educational inquiries*. *Educational Researcher* 15: 4–12.
- Smith, S. M., & Vela, E. (2001). Environmental context-dependent memory: A review and meta-analysis. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 8(2), 203-220.

- Snelgrove, S.R. (2004). Approaches to learning of student nurses. *Nurse Education Today*, 24, 605-614. doi.10.1016/j.nedt.2004.07.006
- Sonnenwald D. H., & Li B. (2003). Scientific collaboratories in higher education: exploring learning style preferences and perceptions of technology. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 34(4), 419-431.
- Spielberger, C.D. & Gorsuch, R.L. (1983). *Manual for the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory*. 1st Edn. Consulting Psychologists Press, Palo Alto, CA. pp: 36.
- Stake, R. E. (1994). *Case studies, in: Handbook of qualitative research*. N.K. Denzin and Y.S. Lincoln, Eds, Thousand Oaks: Sage, pp. 236–247.
- Stake, R (1995). *The Art of Case Study Research*. Sage Publications, California, United States.
- Stake, R. E. (2006). *Multiple case study analysis*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Stankova,L.,Lee, J., Luo, W. & Hogan, D. (2012).Confidence: A better predictor of academic achievement than self-efficacy, self-concept and anxiety? *Learning and Individual Differences*. Volume 22, Issue 6, December 2012, Pages 747–758. doi:10.1016/j.lindif.2012.05.013
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Sutton, D. H. (2004). *The theory of margin as a predictor of success on the National Council Licensure Examination for registered nurses (Doctoral dissertation)*. Available from ProQuest Dissertations and Theses database. (UMI No. AAT 13165154)
- Swenty, C. F. (1998). *Use of the RNEE, ACT, and grades as predictors of success in associate degree nursing programs*. Dissertation Abstracts International. 36(05), 1333. University Microfilms No. 1389177
- Sykes, W. (1990). Validity and reliability in qualitative market research: A review of the literature. *Journal of the Market Research Society* 32 (3): 289–328.

- Tait, H., Entwistle, N. J., & McCune, V. (1998). *ASSIST: a reconceptualisation of the approaches to studying inventory*. In C. Rust (Ed.), *Improving students as learners* (pp. 262-271). Oxford: Oxford Brookes University, Centre for Staff and Learning Development.
- Taraban, R., Maki, W. S., & Rynearson, K. (1999). *Measuring study time distributions: Implications for designing computer-based courses*. *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, & Computers*, 31, 263-269.
- Taylor, S. J., & Bogdan, R. (1998). *Introduction to qualitative research methods: A guidebook and resources (3rd Ed.)*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Taylor, H., Loftin, C. & Reyes, H. (2014). First-Time NCLEX-RN Pass Rate: Measure of Program Quality or Something Else? *The Journal of nursing education*. 05/2014; 53(x):10.3928/01484834-20140520-02
- Taylor, G., Jungert, T., Mageau, G., Schattke, K., Helena Dedic, H., Rosenfield, S. & Koestner, R. (2014). A self-determination theory approach to predicting school achievement over time: the unique role of intrinsic motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*. 2014 Elsevier Inc. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2014.08.002>
- Thomas, A., Menon, A., Boruff, J., Rodriguez, A., & Ahmed, S. (2014). Applications of social constructivist learning theories in knowledge translation for healthcare professionals: a scoping review. *Implementation Science*, 2014, 9:54
- Ticehurst, G. W. and Veal, A. J. (2000). *Business Research Methods: a managerial approach*. Longman, Pearson Education Pty Limited.
- Tolentino, L. S. (2010). *Factors related to passing the Philippine Nurses Licensure Examination among Graduates of Tarlac State University*. Proceedings of the Luzon Industry & Energy Research and Development Consortium (CLIERDEC) Regional Research and Development Symposium, Baliuag University, December 9, 2010.

- Trochim, W. (2007, June). *Evolutionary Perspectives on Evaluation: Theoretical and Practical Implications*. Invited Presentation, Colorado Evaluation Network, Denver, Colorado, June 26, 2007.
- Trockel MT, Barnes MD, Egget EL. (2000). Health-related variables and academic performance among first year college students: implications for sleep and other behaviors. *Journal American College Health*. 2000; 49:125–132.
- Truman, J. (2012). *Identifying Predictors of National Council Licensure Examination for Registered Nurses (NCLEX-RN) Success in an Associate Degree Nursing Program*. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology* Vol. 2 No. 7; August 2012
- Vansteenkiste, M., Zhou, M., Lens, W., & Soenens, B. (2005). Experiences of autonomy and control among Chinese learners: Vitalizing or immobilizing? *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 97(3), 468–483.
- Verschuren, P.J.M. (2003). Case Study as a Research Strategy: Some Ambiguities and Opportunities. *Int. Journal of Social Research Methodology*, vol. 6, no 2, 121-139.
- Waddington, D. 1994. *Participant observation*. In *Qualitative methods in organizational research*. Edited by C. Cassell and G. Symon, 107–22. London: Sage.
- Wallach, M. A. & Wing, C. W. (1969). *The talented student*. Retrieved March 23, 2014 from <http://home.ku.education.tr/~earik/personality/wallach.html>.
- Walsham, G. (1995). *Interpretive case studies in IS research: nature and method*. *European Journal of Information Systems* 4(2), 74–81.

- Washburn, J. (2006). *The Influence of Participation in Student Nurse Extern Programs on NCLEX-RN Pass Rates for First-Time Candidates*. Master's Theses and Doctoral Dissertations. Paper 98; p. 12
- Watt, D. (2007). *On becoming a qualitative researcher: The value of reflexivity*. The Qualitative Report, 12(1), 82-101. Retrieved August 23, 2014, from <http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR12-1/watt.pdf>
- Weinstein, C. E., Acee, T. W., & Jung, J. (2011). *Self-regulation and learning strategies*. New Directions for Teaching and Learning, 2011(126), 45-53
- Wenger, S., Hobbs, G., Williams, H. J., Hays, M., & Ducatman, B. (2009). Medical Student Study Habits: Practice Questions Help Exam Scores. *Journal of International Association of Medical Science Educators*, 19(4), 170-172.
- Wescott, C. L. (1997). *The effectiveness of admission criteria in predicting academic success for baccalaureate nursing students*. Dissertation Abstracts International. 58(08B), 4151, University Microfilms No. 9805076.
- West, C. & Sadoski, M. (2011). *Do study strategies predict academic performance in medical school?* Medical Education Volume 45, Issue 7, pages 696-703, July 2011
- Wikipedia (n.d.) Metro Manila. Retrieved July 30, 2014, from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metro_Manila
- Winne, P. H., & Hadwin, A. F. (1998). *Studying as self-regulated learning*. In D. J. Hacker, J. Dunlosky, & A. C. Graesser (Eds.), *Metacognition in educational theory and practice* (pp. 277-304). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Witkin, H. A., Moore, C. A., Goodenough, D. R., & Cox, P.W. (1977). Field-dependent and field independent cognitive styles and their educational research. *Review of Educational Research*, 47(1), 1-64.
- Wolff, S. (2002). *Design Features for Project-Based Learning*. Oregon State University.
- Yin, R. K. (1989). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Applied Social Research Series, Vol. 5. London: Sage.

- Yin, R. (1993). *Applications of case study research*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publishing.
- Yin, R. (1994). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods (2nd ed.)*. Sage Publications, London, United Kingdom.
- Yin R. K. (2003). *Case study research. Design and methods (3rd ed.)* London, Sage
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods (4th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Yumol, B. (2009). *A humanist approach to understanding the migration of Filipino nurses to the United States*. Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Texas A & M University.
- Zhang, L. (2003). *Does the big five predict learning approaches? Personality and Individual Differences*, 34, 1431-1446.
- Zimmerman, B.J. (1986). Becoming a self-regulated learner: which are the key subprocesses? *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 11(4), 307-13.
- Zimmerman, B.J. (2001). Theories of self-regulated learning and academic achievement: An overview and analysis. In B.J. Zimmerman & D.H. Schunk (Eds.), *Self-regulated learning and academic achievement: Theoretical perspectives (2nd ed., pp. 1-37)*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Zimmerman B.J. (2002). Becoming a self-regulated learner: an overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(2), 64-72.
- Zimmerman, B. J., & Martinez-Pons, M. (1990). Student differences in self-regulated learning: Relating grade, sex, and giftedness to SE and strategy use. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(1), 51-59. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.82.1.51>
- Zimmerman, B.J., & Schunk, D.H. (Eds.). (2001). *Self-regulated learning and academic achievement: Theoretical perspectives (2nd ed.)*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum

Zucker, D. (2009). *How to Do Case Study Research*. School of Nursing Faculty Publication Series. Paper 2. Retrieved from http://scholarworks.umass.edu/nursing_faculty_pubs/2

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: Data Matrices/Verbatim Responses as Used in the Findings of the Study

A.1 Self-Review Strategies

✓ Finding #1.a - Conduct a Self-Analysis.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseR	☞ <i>Una ang dapat mong gawin ano, alamin niya muna kung paano siya mag-aral. Yung talagang alam niya, kung papano siya mag-aral, yung matututo siya, yung learning style niya talaga. Tapos depende sa learning style niya, yun ang gagawin niya. Kunyari yung tipo ko, ayoko nung tuloy- tuloy na pag-aaral magbabasa, pero yung ibang tao gusto nila, yun ang gagawin nila as in focus na focus talaga sila. Yun talagang wala silang gagawin sa isang buong araw kundi mag-aral. Okay na yun, sabi mo nga, yung iba grupo sila yung may nag di-discussion. Eh ako ayaw ko yung nasa isang malaking grupo, kung ano yung komportable mas mag fo-focus sila yun (R308).</i>
Mr. NurseJ	☞ <i>...Assuming na naidentify mo na yung kahinaan mo, alam mo yung weaknesses mo at strengths. Siguro, yun, two and a half (J226b)</i>
Ms. NurseE	☞ <i>Nung una tapon-tapun lang yun, kung ano yung pinag-aaralan namin sa pre-review. Kung baga wala pang sistema talaga na 'heto yung subject na uunahin ko'. Kung baga dun lang ako nagkakarun ng idea na 'ay hirap ako sa subject na 'to... (E177a)</i>
Ms. NurseL	☞ <i>I concentrated on my weak points which is test 5, and you can include test 1 as well. test 3 and 4 are my strengths. Doubts are normal if we dont have it then how will we strive to do more. I cope up by reading a lot and making time to really understand my weak points during the course of the review (L22a).</i>

✓ Finding #1.b - Pick a strategy that best fits your learning style and study needs

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>Nung nasa school ako then nadala ko na din siya nung nag rereview ako gumagawa ako ng sarili kong reviewer so I'll take time to write down yung mga important things gagawin ko yon questions, answer, questions, answer siguro magkakaroon ako ng mga five pages na yellow pad or five bond papers, siyempre habang nagsusulat ka nagme-memorize mo yung sagot then kapag I rundown mo uli siya almost perfect na yung sagot mo (O132).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ahh I create my own ahh ...kasi I believe in the power of writing so gumagawa ako ng sarili kong reviewer, so nagsusulat ako ng questions then yung answer (O131).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Ang ano kasi sa akin, depende rin sa learning style ng tao, ang sa akin kasi ...pag di mo na maintindihan, tumigil ka na. Kasi wala ng papasok sa... utak mo. Kunyari mag focus ka sa isang topic, pagka hindi mo na maintindihan yon, tigil ka muna. Balikan mo kung gusto mo mamaya, kaya kung mag-skip ka, tapos balikan mo ulit. Pagka medyo fresh yung utak mo basta wag mong pipilitin yung magrereview ka na di mo maintindihan. Basa ka lang ng basa, wala hindi siya magiging effective. Pahinga ka, tumigil ka, maghanap ka ng ibang gagawin... (R218a).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...Tapos yung depende sa, kunyari, ano yung pinag-aaralan ko, yung gagawa ako ng diagram. Kunyari nagpaliwanag siya ng ganito, gagawan ko siya ng diagram, mas simple. Kung may diagram na sa libro mas sisimplehan ko pa lalo yun, tas susubukan ko siyang... susubukan ko siyang isulat ulit, kung papano ko siya papaiikliin pero hindi sa lahat ng process, yung process na medyo nalilito ako i-sa-summarize ko parang i-sa-summarize ko ganun, kukunin ko yung pinaka essence niya tapos susubukan kong ulitin yun, yung di nakatingin sa likod, susubukan kong isulat sa papel yon (R218b).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Oo, sa kanila kasi parang every week may exam sila ganyan. Kunyari ang exam nila is Anatomy, inaral ko na yung Anatomy then iaano ko sa kanila yun i-rereview mo sila or le-lecture ran ko sila kung pano ang style nung review center kung бага ang style ko I'm the reviewer of my classmates (N114).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, so I took it as an opportunity para matulungan din yung sarili ko. Actually yun nga ang pinaka malaking tulong na naano sa akin, yun pa ang pinakamalaking tumulak sa akin na rereviewhin kasi I was forced to study" (N170).</i></p>

Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ Pero kapag sinusulat ko siya, naka-tabs na lang siya. Yung pinakaroot-words, yung nakahighlight na lang siya. Pero gusto ko kapag nagrereview ako, kailangan detailed para mas maintindihan ko. Hindi ko siya makukuha ng parang signs-signs lang (E210).</p>
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✓ Finding #1.c - Prioritize and manage your weak areas.

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ Magself-review? Bago ako grumaduate. Nagself-review na talaga ako nun. Kung baga may mga prereview na, may mga idea na, nagsisimula na ako. Actually, gumawa ako rito (pointing to plotted schedule planner) nung mga sisimulan kong pag-aralan. Nagsimula kasi ako, sa case ko, yung pinakamahirap na subject sa'kin, dun ako nagfocus muna (E107).</p> <p>☞ Pharma (pharmacology), NRes (nursing research), yung hindi madalas daanan sa nursing. Tingin ko kasi ang pharma (pharmacology) sa akin noon naging mabilis lang kasi summer class ko lang siya kinuha. Parang dun ako hirap sa mga gamot (E108).</p> <p>☞ Nagfocused ako sa pinakamahirap, kasi nga feeling ko dun ako maraming dapat pag-aralan (E146).</p> <p>☞ Yun nga, mula sa pinakamahirap... (E178).</p> <p>☞ Ang masasabi ko sa kanya, kung mag-aaral ka, piliin mo muna yung part kung saan ka mas mahihirapan, kumbaga yun ang unahin mong aralin, kasi nga yun ang mga mahirap eh kesa ileft behind mo. Kasi feeling ko dun ka mas maraming dapat itackle compared dun sa mas madali mong subject...(E314a).</p>
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ I gave a timeframe for every topic and I would try as much as possible to squeeze in as much knowledge as I can. However, for my weak subjects, I would allot more review time for it" (K35).</p> <p>☞ Before the review, I rate my confidence level as 6 and after finishing the review it was an 8 since I managed to cover as much subjects as I can especially on my weak areas" (K39).</p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ I concentrated on my weak points...I coped by reading allot and making time to really understand my weak points during the course of the review" (L22).</p> <p>☞ I studied test 1 and 5 first because they are my weakness then every weekends it would be test 3 and 4, the test 2 was the last one that I studied" (L26).</p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	☞ "...you get to concentrate on the topics that is harder for you to understand" (L19).
Mr. NurseB	☞ <i>...kasi may mga bagay akong halimbawa ito kailangan ko yata itong ahm pagtuunan ng pansin ngayon, ganyan-ganyan may mga bagay akong parang mahina pa dito..." (B199).</i> ☞ <i>Actually hindi ko naman na aano na okay tapos ko na lahat ito, ganyan ganyan, na pag may isang bagay na, halimbawa, parang hindi ko yata alam ito, ito muna yung aaralin ko ganon (B221).</i>
Mr. NurseMM	☞ <i>Manage your topic to be reviewed and make sure to focus more on a topic that you think is complicated for you (MM37).</i>
Mr. NurseJ	☞ <i>Sa funda (Fundamentals in Nursing). Kung i-rate man ako ng one to ten, eight or nine ako dito, kaya hindi ko na siya ni-review (J149).</i>
Ms. NurseG	☞ <i>Ang ginawa kasi namin nun, kung saan kami mahina. Kunyari mahina ka sa ganitong subject, siya yung mapupunta sayo. Kunyari mahina ka sa ganito, example, sa renal, mahina ka don sayo mapupunta yon. Hindi pwdeng dapat renal ako kasi ano magaling ako dun hindi sayo ibibigay (G220).</i>
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ <i>I focus on the topic that im not familiar with (MJ32).</i>

✓ *Finding #1.d - Organize your topics to review.*

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseE	☞ <i>Nung first month, pagkagraduate ko, gumagawa na'ko. October 22, gumagawa na ako ng rereviewhin ko. Yung umpisa sa pinakamahirap, sa pinakamadali. Kung mapapansin mo yung mga pinakamadali ko—yung M.S. (Medical Surgical subject), Psyche (Psychiatric Nursing), yun yung mga last ko. Kahit hapyan ko na lang yun, kumbaga kaya ko na siya (E184).</i> ☞ <i>Hindi actually sa schedule eh. Ang style ko nun sarili ko, (inuuna ko) yung pinakamahirap na subject, sa pinakamadali. Kumbaga sinulat ko siya sa isang calendar sa libro na, ito yung pag-aaralan ko per week, saka per day (E145)</i>
Ms. NurseG	☞ <i>Ano, usually books yung talagang ano. Kasi yung sa akin, yung study habit ko, diba iba pa yung nandodon sa dorm, sa bahay din may calendar na itong books na ito dapat mabasa mo siya (G177)</i> ☞ <i>Oo tas tinitick ko yung "yes" (G178).</i> ☞ <i>...iba pa yung nandodon sa dorm, sa bahay din may calendar na itong books na (mga) ito dapat mabasa ko siya" (G177).</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseK	☞ ...Right before the self-review, I made a schedule complete with deadlines so that I can cover as much subjects as I can before the exam” (K25).
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ I made a time plan and setting a goal is so important” (MJ23).
Mr. NurseMM	☞ Since I was working at night and would prefer to sleep during the day, I made my own time table when to scan my review materials” (MM12)

✓ *Finding #1.e - Tailor the review duration and frequency based on individual review Needs.*

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Ahh, yung fact na hindi alam ng mga classmates ko. Siyempre yung iba yung mga hindi magrereview pupunta sa ganito kung бага sa siyempre attach ka pa rin sa kanila kasi kakagraduate niyo lang tapos mapapasama ka, kunyari gigimik sa labas siyempre ikaw gusto mo ring lumabas parang ang inaano ko non parang pagka madalas akong hindi nakikita baka magduda sila na may ginagawa 'to, nagrereview 'to, kaya madalas lumalabas ako nung mga panahon na yon (N88).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo kasi yung feeling ko nun ahh 'bukas na yung board exam' hindi ko pa nababasa yung ano Ortho (Orthopedic nursing) eh...” (N181).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Wala akong definite time (N186).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>As long as I am in the mood (N187).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo I'll do it, pag wala kahit anong gawin ko di ko gagawin yon but I was forced to be on the mood nga kasi yung mga kaklase ko naman, kailangan at this day aralin na namin ito ang ano ha, Maternal (nursing), aralin na natin (N188).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Usually ganon, morning before the lecture o kaya a day before, ganyan dapat prene-prepare ko na ng maigi (N191).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>3 hours siguro, kasi they still have to sleep, mga ganun (N202).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>What I was doing since inaabot ako ng gabi. Usually time kasi ng pag-aaral ko, minsan gabi or inaabot ako ng paumaga, ewan ko (N237).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo or mga tipong mag start ako 1 (morning) ganyan, I find it kasi tahimik eh (N239).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, 1 am and then dun sa roof top pag minsan pag nagugutom ako kumakain ako mag isa (N240).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Ano, ang study habit ko kunyari sa umaga, yung pagkagising sa umaga mag e-exercise muna ako tapos mag exercise mag-aaral ako mula alas-otso hanggang eleven (R240).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>8-11 ganyan (R241)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>May mga breaks in between (R242)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi nga sabi ko sa'yo nasa tindahan ako eh, pero ano yun 8-11 tapos lunch. After nun minsan 1-2 ganyan 1-3 o kaya 3 basta yung ano mga after nun tapos titigil ako, gabi magbabasa uli ako bago matulog (R243).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Araw-araw (R244)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Bukod sa linggo, yung linggo magbabasa ako isang beses lang, parang hapon lang, 1-4 ganon lang (R245)</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Midnight. Sinubukan ko mag-12 midnight. Yung madaling araw na review. Tulog, gising sa umaga, tapos bago ka uli pumasok ng 6 sa umaga. Matutulog uli ako ng 4 (AM), saka uli ako papasok (E111).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ginawa ko na siyang parang normal na habit na ng isang tao. Seven AM (morning), dun ako mag-aaral hanggang 8 PM. Sinunod ko yung nabasa ko dati na kapag mag-aaral ka.. (E125)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi naman straight yun, may nap yun. Kapag alam kong full na yung laman ng utak ko, kapag inaantok talaga, nagpapahinga ako (E126).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Oo 2 months lang (G100).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Usually 8-5 pagdating, pag-ano na ng 5 gagala na kami (G101).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>2-5 ng umaga (G175).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Two days (J100).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi may nabasa akong libro, na in two hours lang dapat magreview tayo, dapat maximum two hours lang, kasi kapag lumagpas na yung two hours, hindi na maretain sa utak mo, kaya kapag nagrereview ako, two hours lang ng two hours. After two hours, pahinga naman ng 30 minutes, 15 minutes then two hours ulit. Hindi ako nagrereview ng straight 3 hours. Kasi nga, bakit kamo, kasi nga may nagsabi sakin, narinig ko sa kanya na yung threshold lang ng utak natin, para maretain yung particular matter na gusto mong aralin is two hours lang. So dahil narinig ko yun, tinandaan ko yun. Ginamit ko yung two hours na yun, ganong strategy (J194).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Pero siguro, kung maging ano tayo...siguro (thinking), half month per subject. Kung five (areas) tayo rito, siguro mga two and a half months---Guaranteed, papasa ka! sa self-review. Assuming na naidentify mo na yung kahinaan mo, alam mo yung weaknesses mo at strengths. Siguro, yun, two and a half (J226).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siguro mas hinabaan ko yung time frame ko sa self-review. Kasi nga I only gave two days sa review ko eh, although I passed. Kasi nga, hindi ako satisfied sa score ko eh. Kumbaga, kung naglaan ako ng more time frame sa review ko, baka mas mataas yung nakuha ko (J252).</i></p>
<p>Mr. NurseO</p>	<p>☞ <i>Ahh sabi daw nila kasi base on statistics on research hindi ko maalala sa Reader's digest ko o nabasa yon sabi nila pagka fresh mag start ka ng pagkagising mo kasi parang sponge pa daw yung brain mo nun eh pagkagising mo sa umaga or basta pagkagising na pagkagising mo ahh very absorbent yung brain mo non so I really started my review my study everytime I wake up in the morning ganon (O152).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo tapos pagka during breaks and lunches yun review uli ako 15 minutes, 30 minutes after kong kumain review then pagka-uwi ahh I spend 1-2 hours bago matulog (O157).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo kasi kailangan ko rin siyempre kasi papasok na naman ako kinabukasan (O158).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi ahh nung malapit na yung exam medyo dinadagdagan ko na yung pagrereview before kasi during sa break, lunches saka uwian pero nung magbo board exam na siya bago ako pumasok habang kumakain ako breakfast during breakfast nagrereview na ako sa biyahe nag rereview ako non (O95).</i></p>
<p>Mr. NurseB</p>	<p>☞ <i>Depende ano, kung halimbawa, walang ginagawa sa bahay usually siguro mga 8 or 9 tapos siyempre may mga lunch break yan ganyan, merienda pag sa gabi siguro pinaka late ko na siguro 12 or 1 (midnight) (B173).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>8 or 9 tapos hanggang 12 tapos ahh siyempre tanghalian yon lunch break (B174).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...co-continue na ako siguro mga 2 (PM) tapos 2 kasi may meryenda pa na alas 4 dun (B175).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Actually Monday to Sunday. Nung actually halos pareho lang siya nung nag board (exam) ako tapos nag NCLEX ako almost everyday (B178).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ I sucked at time management. So what I did was when I got home I (would) sleep for about three hours then I studied until 2 AM (which gave me five hours of review time) My study habit during school days was from 9 PM until 2 AM (pero hindi to nasusunod palagi) over the weekends I usually get up at 10 AM, but my review started at 2 PM onwards. I usually ended up sleeping at around 4 AM during the weekends (L22).</p> <p>☞ Actual board exam: deep breaths, pray and leave it to God and two days before the exam (don't review anymore). The last two days, I was not able to do (it) because...at that point...I think I still had a lot to go so I still read during the two days (L37).</p>
Mr. NurseMM	☞ Nothing in particular during my avail time regardless of time of the day (MM27).
Ms. NurseK	☞ I usually studied around afternoon to evening since I am not a morning person (K26).
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ Every morning after breakfast, 1 hour per day (MJ24).

✓ *Finding #1.f - Find your right venue.*

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Kasi nga yung lang level sa upo ko eh, so dun ako nagreview... Sina mama, kasi may tindahan naman kami, kaya dun siya sa tindahan. Kaya yung bahay na yun, ako lang talaga mag-isa, hindi nila ako ginugulo; kakain lang sila" (E129).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi. Di ba sabi ko extended family kami? So andun yung mga pamangkin ko. Siguro sa bahay namin, 'di ba friend mo siya, siguro mga 30 kami sa isang bahay. Sa amin, kumbaga 24 hours maingay. Pero nirequest ko sa kanila, two days lang bigyan niyo ako ng time magreview (J192).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Normal lang. Kung ano yung normal na kwarto na ilaw, yun yung ginamit ko (J193).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Yung normal lang, fresh air. Kasi may nabasa akong libro, na in two hours nagreview tayo, dapat maximum two hours lang, kasi kapag lumagpas na yung two hours, hindi na maretain sa utak mo, kaya kapag nagrereview ako, two hours lang ng two hours. After two hours, pahinga naman ng 30 minutes, 15 minutes then two hours ulit. Hindi ako nagrereview ng straight 3 hours. Kasi nga, bakit kamo, kasi nga may nagsabi sakín, narinig ko sa kanya na yung threshold lang ng utak natin, para maretain yung particular matter na gusto mong aralin is two hours lang. So dahil narinig ko sayo yun, tinandaan ko yun. Ginamit ko yung two hours na yun, ganong strategy (J194).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Sa roof top namin (N211).</i> ☞ <i>May shade naman yon, ewan ko parang conducive, I find it conducive (N212).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Mag-isa lang ako (N213).</i> ☞ <i>Tindahan (R248).</i> ☞ <i>Pero pagka gabi na, dun ako sa, may study table ako (R249).</i> ☞ <i>Oo dun lang ako (R250).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Pagkakailangan ko talaga maging tahimik, pumupunta ako dun sa kabilang bahay, yung bakante (R253).</i> ☞ <i>5 sets kami nung mga friends ko ang ginawa namin nag rent kami ng house, ay nag rent ng sa dorm, nag rent kami ng room, tapos ano yon 8-5 lahat dapat nandon na kami sa loob basta 8-5 basta yung loob na yun vacant (G71).</i> ☞ <i>Vacant lang siya, books lang yung nasa gitna. Yung ginagawa namin, books lang yung sa gitna tapos lapis at saka papel tapos sa room may mga naka post na manila paper (G72).</i> ☞ <i>Yung lang yung study room namin (G74).</i> ☞ <i>Pag pumasok ka sa room lahat makikita mo, ano yon malalaki yung ano niya, malalaki yung handwriting kasi yung naka unang set ng pinost namin yun may values kasi diba ano... (G76).</i> ☞ <i>Yun yung ginawa namin tapos every now and then nagpapalit kami, nagpapalit kunyari (G77).</i></p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ <i>...Our terrace and Starbucks (araneta branch before it got shut down, West ave and Congressional branch) usually were in a group of 3 people whenever I got to Starbucks (L22)</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Sa bahay lang talaga ako (B179).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p>☞ <i>I usually stay at one place....At home (reading area) the environment is quiet and no disturbances (MJ25).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

✓ Finding #1.g - Get a good review material.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Siguro kung mag e-exam ka rin ganun din gawin mo ahh matrabaho magreview sa libro, sa libro talaga pero sulit naman. Parang mas maganda yung kalalabasan, parang ganon, kesa magrereview ka ng mga reviewer, mga ganyan, summarized na, mas madali yun pero icocompare mo siya dun sa reviewer talaga mas matrabaho pero mas sulit yun, mas malaki yung kalalabasan mas marami kang matutunan (N271).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sa sarili ko, kaya bumili na ako nun ng notebook ko. Eh susulatan ko, ang ginawa ko nun, babasahin ko yung libro. Hindi ako nag reviewer, hindi ako nag reviewer. Actually, nag gather ako ng mga reviewer pero hindi ko rin sila nagamit kasi yung mga ginamit ko talaga is yung, yung mga books talaga yun Funda, MS..Su.. (N164).</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Nakita ko kasi, napagcompare ko na, parang mas madaling intindihin 'to, kesa sa gumamit ka ng iba pang reference. Kasi sa Saunders (book reviewer) nacompile na siya, iba-ibang subjects. Yun yung ginamit ko (E194).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Parang feeling ko mas malinaw. Iniexplain niya kasing isa-isa. Nakalagay dun definition ni Angina, pathophysio (-logy) niya. Kung baga hindi kagaya sa libro natin ng M.S. (Medical-Surgical) na may mga arrow-arrow pa. Sa Saunders iniexplain niya... (E207).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yes. Kasi nga mas naintindihan ko (E208). Kasi may mga practice sessions na rin yun (E196).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Binubuksan ko na lang 'to (referring to Balita's reviewer), kapag, halimbawa, "ano nga ba 'tong sakit na' to?" Sa halip na buksan ko kay Saunders na pagkakapal-kapal...Tiningnan ko na lang yung kay Carl Balita. Kung may technique si Carl Balita na mas madaling tandaan. Yung may mga tinatawag siyang "caricature" ba yun? Yun mga palatandaan. Mas madali mo tandaan. Dito ko siya tiningnan. Pero hindi ko siya binasa (E203).</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Siguro kumuha ka ng latest na material na kung baga lahat nandun na, pero hindi naman siyempre lahat nandon, kung baga kumuha ka ng materials makakatulong sayo (B219).</i></p>

	<p>☞ <i>...na reliable na makakatulong sayo and then kasama non mag practice ka din Q and A ganyan pero before Q & A magbasa ka muna ng diba particular topic kang gustong i-master o magbasa basa ka muna after nun i-apply mo sa Q & A kung baga parang ano lang ahh basa, take ng questions tapos after mo mag take ng question check mo yung ano yung tamang sagot tingnan mo kung rationale ganyan-ganyan (B220).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi, may iba akong review material like syempre sa atin diba mga NRES (Nursing Research) mga ganyan, eh wala namang masyadong dun sa Saunders. Kapag mga ganun hindi Saunders yung ginagamit ko, yung mga bigay na material ng school, galing sa school ganyan (B169).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Yung tipong hindi ko siya, hindi ko siya nahaharap, kasi lalo kung pag aaralan ko, kunyari magulo 'to, kailangan may pagtatanungan ako. Kung di mapagtatanungan, eh noon kasi wala, wala pa kaming internet nun eh, hahanapin ko. Ngayon, kung may hindi ako maintindihan hinahanap ko sa internet kung may mas simpleng explanation (R79).</i></p>

✓ Finding #1.h - Maximize help from other people and exhaust available resources.

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ I guess the big challenge for me (was) that I (didn't) have that much test papers to answer on. So I had no idea on how the questions were gonna be raised. That time, I relied allot from my friends since they shared their papers with me as well the answers" (L13).</p> <p>☞ I sometimes go to Morayta to buy the very cheap test papers of the boards from 2000 to 2005, there I answered and tried to learn the test taking strategy that my friend taught me" (L28).</p> <p>☞ My friends helped a lot! We used to have a Starbucks session where we stayed there and compared notes on how we reviewed this and that (because back then they were all enrolled in a review center) so my time with them usually started after my classes. I asked from friends for their test papers and some test taking strategies...usually we're in a group of three people... (L22).</p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Ganoon talaga parang... mayroon akong goal, gusto ko pumasa ng nursing. Mayroon ako... pero iyong resources ko kulang e para makapasa. So kung anong mayroon ako doon ko lang pino-pokus</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p><i>kung anong mayroon ako. Doon ako gumagawa ng paraan para makapasa ako... (J115)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Mina-maximize ko kung anong mayroon ako. Iyong resources ko para magamit ko in return sa ... sa sarili ko (J117).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ako iyong alam mo iyong tawag sa term na iyong small things na tinatago ko siya kasi alam ko magagamit ko ito (J172). Oo tsaka alam ko na (in) the end wala akong resources. Ito lang iyong resources ko e. Ito iyong kayaman ko itatago ko ito. Iyon (J174).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Okay, magandang tanong yan... (thinking). Siguro inisip ko na magagamit ko 'to kasi alam ko na wala ako eh, wala akong magiging resources eh. Alam ko na, kapag nagreview center, alanganin akong makapagreview center eh. Alam ko na. Kagaya ng sinabi ko, nirarationalize ko na yung mangyayari sa akin sa hinaharap eh. So alam ko na na baka hindi ako makapagreview (center), so kailangan kong makapagtake down notes. Kailangan kong alagaan yung mga notes ko para magamit ko. Yun nga, nagamit ko nga talaga siya (J187).</i></p>
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ 3. Resourcefulness – I was not content with my own materials so I searched the internet for more study materials (K46).</p> <p>☞ I sought advice usually from internet forums like dos & don'ts of test taking plus subjects where I need to focus on (K24).</p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Nasa abroad na sila ngayon. Nung nag-aaral siya nagNCLEX siya, pero NCLEX-PN, Practical Nurse. Eh hinihiram-hiram ko yung libro niya, eh ginagamit din niya parang nag-aantay na muna ako para matapos niya, tapos kung hindi naman, eh wala naman kaming internet nun, nagpupunta ako ng computer shop... (R143).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Kasi nga binibigyan kami ng pointers eh, binibigyan kami kaya parang wala din. Minsan sa resources... (G121).</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Yon nga gawin mo yung ganito, pag-aralan mo yung ganyan, mag practice questions ka kasi di ba dati bukod dun sa book na may Q and A meron din yung sa, sa computer na Q and A ganon, mag ganon ka kasi parang sina-simulate nung yung mismong exam kasi pag sa NCLEX click click mga ganyan -ganyan ,ganon (B231).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMM	<p>☞ Resources/Review materials: read sample questionnaires from a nursing website, used my previous notes when I was in a nursing school, borrowed review materials from a friend who attended from a review center and passed the NLE and consolidated everything (MM11).</p>

✓ Finding #1.i - Watch out for FAQs and emerging health issues.

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseE	<p>Q Tinanong ko sa kanya, kung ano ba yung lumabas sa board (exam), kung saan ba dapat ako magfocus. Pinayuhan niya ako, say communicable disease, na kung meron kang dapat pag-aralan dun, dapat yung related sa panahon. Sa communicable diseases kasi, ang lumalabas daw kasi sa board exam kung anong sakit nitong year. Dati sikat nung panahon ko, AH1N1. Nung sa panahon niya, dengue yata yung sa problem niya (E137).</p> <p>Q Yes, lumabas yun, yung signs and symptoms. Kung anong ginawa ng DOH (Department of Health) nung time na nagkarun ng AH1N1. Naalala ko may ganung lumabas. Pati yung tawag sa gas mask (i.e. N95). Lumabas lahat yun (E192).</p> <p>Q IMCI yung more on lumabas dun sa board exam (E193).</p> <p>Q Sa pre-review tapos sa mga exams sa major (subjects). Napapansin ko na “parang lagi siyang kasali”; kaya binasa ko yung part na yun, hanggang sa naaral ko heto pala yung nursing management, mga signs niya. Tinandaan ko na yun. Dun ako nagkaroon ng idea na, “oh possible pala na ganon lumabas”, kasi lagi naman ganon yung tanong eh. Kaya yun yung mga nirereview ko lagi. Saka yung mga parts na hindi ko sure, so inaaral ko na yun. Kasi may mga parts na lumalabas sa pre-review eh, tapos hindi ko naman siya na-rereview. Tinitingnan ko kung ano yung mga yun. So yun yung mga naging style ko sa reviewing (E141).</p> <p>Q Kasi ang review makikiramdam ka lang, as graduating, kung may pre-review sa school, kung ano yung tinuturo nila. Kasi naniniwala ako yung mga nagtuturo sa amin updated din sila sa mga possible na lalabas, saka kung sino yung mga clinical o board of directors na gagawa ng exam (E150)...</p> <p>Q ...Dun sa mga major exams mo na lagi na lang iniexam san’yo, kumbaga kunin mo na yung mga bits ng knowledge na---“parang lagi ‘tong lumalabas’, tingin ko meron na naman”. Kinukuha ko siya...Parang tinatandaan ko lang, kahit hind ko alam kung tama yung sagot ko dun. Yung question na yun na tungkol sa sakit na yun tinatandaan ko siya. Siguro yun siguro yung isa sa mga ano ko... na parang possible. Bigyang pansin mo lahat ng iniexam mo, ginagawa mo, na pwede pa la ‘to, na lalabas pala. Yun ang masasabi ko (E314).</p>

✓ Finding #1.J - Be Inclusive, comprehensive, and integrate other topics when reviewing.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>Meron nga kasi nung board exam more of community based yung nakita ko so hindi ako masyadong nakapag focus dun nung nakita ko yung board rating ang pinakamababa ko community tas nagkaroon na lang ako ng realization ahh Phiippines setting ang ibibigay nila ahh much as possible Philippines setting then parang nurses kasi is really designated to community, promoting health, ahh preventing further disease so yun di ko na fo-focus maigi yung community kaya mababa sana nag focus ako sa community nurse (O185).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>What is angina ganyan mga ganon, lalagay ko yon tapos kung ano pa mare-recall ng isip ko lalagay ko don then sasabayan ko ng yung sa pocket book ko yung maliit na reviewer isasabay ko siya don (O134).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Isusulat ko din para mabilis kong ma memorize o maalala kung ano yung sagot (O135).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yun yong medyo crucial kasi tama ka dun kasi in 1 sem sobrang dami (O137).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siguro sa akin na lang as a student ahh parang ano na yan eh parang sa experience mo lang as a student na parang you get to know kung ano yung mga important details na kailangan mo isulat isa pa ahh dun sa mga notebook ko may mga special notes dun siguro is either highlighted in red or with other ink so iyon ang isusulat ko (O138).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo college may mga anu don extra notations so yun yung dinadagdag ko (O139).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Yung mga tipong ganun, kunyari yung sa mga laboratory values ganyan, mapipilitang magmemorize. Yun talaga nagmemorize ako dahil kailangan, pero iilan lang naman yun.</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ire-relate ko siya sa table. Mismong pakainirerelate ko siya dun sa exam, iniisip ko yung table sa utak ko (R279).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo kasi yung medyo visual ako pagkaganyan eh. Hindi ko lahat matatandaan yung sa listahan ganun, kailangan makita ko yung table sa utak ko. Yung comparison kung bakit mataas ito, mababa yung base niya, pagkamababa yung base niya, mataas yung ganito parang... (R280).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, kunyari Alkalosis ganon, ma-imagine ko kung ano itsura nung comparison nung ano... mage-gets ko na siya kung bakit nagkaganon (R283).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Sabi ng nanay ko. 'Sabi ko bakit ba, gusto ko mag-aral eh.' Kasi pati yung kapatid ko, kaya naengganyo din maging nurse kasi nakikita niya na natatandaan ko, "inaral niya ito eh, inaral ni ate ito eh", kasi kung saan saan nakadikit pati sa kwarto ko, sa room din, sa C.R. meron nakakabitin(G184).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi nasa loob kami ng kwarto, tapos pagka sa bahay, kagaya ko, ako kunyari gagala may parang naging habit ko na yung mag-aaral ng ano ng madaling araw. Parang yon ikaw na sa sarili mo kung ano, kung mag-aaral ka ba talaga, kung tingin mo, ako ini-estimate ko kung lahat ba makukuha eh. Yung sa amin, sabi ko nga eh puro babae naglalandian din, tapos minsan nagkakaayaan na lumabas siyempre parang na e-echepwera yung review. So parang kino compensate ko na 'dapat dahil hindi tayo nag-aral, dapat mag-aaral ako (G172).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, hanggang dumating na kami na tina tackle na yung sakit na yon, sumasama, para pagka sa susunod pag nag topic siya, di mo kailangan mag report kasi may alam na yung mga yun, mag aano na lang sila 'Oy alam ko yan'. Nakakatawa lang kasi minsan sabay-sabay sila. Sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita. Sabi ko 'isa-isa lang' kasi sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita (G148).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo tinutulungan yon kasi para pag ikaw naman tutulungan ka din nila pero nagkakaano na may times din na nagpapalit palit kami kunyari "Uy may ano magpalit naman tayo pag hindi ko talaga kaya eh, pwede bang yung akin na lang talaga. Depend sa ano kung papayag lahat "sige pagbigyan siya", ganon (G222).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Lahat ng possible questions na related sa pananakit ng tiyan mo including time of sleep mo, anong kinain mo? Anong history mo? (J110).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Family history. Lahat-lahat (J111).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo. Katulad noong atleast mayroon na akong basis ayun mayroon akong assessment sa kanya kung bakit masakit nag tiyan niya (J112).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMM	<p>☞ <i>Before the review- 10- I thought I covered everything. After the review- 8- after the exam there were questions that were very tricky..." (MM36).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p>☞ <i>I just prayed that I would pass the exam (MJ20).</i></p>

✓ Finding #1.K - Execute the strategy precisely, but be flexible to contain shortcomings.

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Yun nga, may oras lang talaga ako ng aral eh. Kumbaga kung anong nakatokang subject ng araw na yun, yun lang yung pag-aaralan ko. From 7 (AM)-8 (PM), may kasama na dun tulog o may kain man. Ganun lang eh, hindi pa'ko nagrerelax nung time na yan. Wala munang TV, walang text-text (E234).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi kasi nakasulat na kung ano yung pag-aaralan ko that day. Kung Pharma (pharmacology), kung MS (Medical-Surgical), yung sa Monday na pag-aaralan ko, yun na yun, so hindi na'ko tatalon sa ibang book (E143).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sa review center? Hindi ako tumingin sa exam nila, kasi nga baka madiscourage ako" (E262)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...naging parusa ko sa sarili ko no cell phones, no TV, aral lang talaga (E129).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kung matutulog ako nung araw na yun, that time wala munang tulog-tulog, kailangan habulin ko yung subject na naiwan ko. Parang pinaparusan ko yung sarili ko... (E317).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>"Oo, nung una kasi nahirapan kami, fish bowl ginawa namin" (G96).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi, ako yung magtatanong sa kanila diba, tatanungin ko sila tas yon palalawakin ko tas kunyari (G141).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Tapos pag may hindi kayo naintindihan, kunyari nagpresent ako nagtanong ako sa kanila, ang sagot nila sabi ko 'Gets mo ba talaga?' hindi may ganito parang isa-sub ka pa nila, sina-sub ka talaga nila, ganon. Kunyari, sa gamot example para sa Clonidine o para saan siya? (G145).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Parang papasok na dun yung nagreview sa MS siya (G146).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, hanggang dumating na kami na tina tackle na yung sakit na yon, sumasama, para pagka sa susunod pag nag topic siya, di mo kailangan mag report kasi may alam na yung mga yun, mag aano na lang sila 'Oy alam ko yan'. Nakakatawa lang kasi minsan sabay-sabay sila. Sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita. Sabi ko 'isa-isa lang' kasi sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita (G148).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ano sa house nag-aaral na ako tas ko yung magre-refill sa kanila, sila din nagbabasa din sila parang magiging brainstorming sa amin (G93).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Kasi nga disiplina pumapasok ako kahit na inaantok ako yung nag self-review kami kasi diba hindi naman ano pag uwi mo ng 5 makakauwi ka, minsan gagala ka. Minsan may iba ka pang siyempre friends na uy tara labas tayo siyempre hindi ka naman makakatanggi kasi. So parang ano ka papasok ka dun sa dorm na ganon, na may tama ka, may ganon yun (G138).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Example magbibigay ako ng gamot, yung gamot tatawag ako ng isa sa apat, 'Oh, ikaw ano yung indications? Bago sila pumasok kasi sa amin nag ano ka nagbasa, dapat nagbasa ka kasi matatanong ka, parang nag re-recite kayo" (G140)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi parang ano, parang ano "hoy hindi ka prepared" parang inaasar lang namin "sana next time ano ganito ha" parang nag sasuggest din..." (G107).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Pag pauwi na, kasi hindi pwedeng before mag-discuss eh sasakit na yung ulo nung bawat isa diba? Fully-loaded agad, hindi kagaya non pag-ano na, parang "Oy bakit ito yung sagot?" atleast don kahit hindi masyadong magfunction yung brain ng (bawat) isa, atleast nakuha na nila yung isang unang subject namin, ayon (G219).</i></p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>Nung una pa lang decided na ako ahh ayoko mahuli, gusto ko sabay sabay kaming nag graduate sabay sabay kaming magiging nurses (O102).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>One week before the review, nagdagdag ako ng (topics)...Basta ako kung may libreng oras as much as possible nakaupo ako nagbabasa ganon I really devoted most of my idle moments reading or reviewing (O151).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>...Kasi although ang una kong naisip ay para malaman lang yung sistema ng board exam, andun pa rin yung pride mo na papasa ka. Two days review, andun pa rin yung pride mo na "kaya ko 'to". So nag-effort pa rin talaga ako. Hindi ko naman sinasabi na (inasa) ko lang sa memory ko yung pagpasa ko ng board (exam). Nag-effort talaga ako, dahil yung review na ginawa ko nun... (J188).</i></p>
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ <i>4. Independence - In self-review, there are no instructors to guide you, only yourself. You create your own schedules (K46).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p>☞ <i>I made a time plan and setting a goal is so important" (MJ23)</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Magself-review? Bago ako grumaduate. Nagself-review na talaga ako nun. Kung бага may mga prereview na, may mga idea na, nagsisimula na ako. Actually, gumawa ako rito (pointing to plotted schedule planner) nung mga sisimulan kong pag-aralan. Nagsimula kasi ako, sa case ko, yung pinakamahirap na subject sa'kin, dun ako nagfocus muna (E107).</i></p>

✓ Finding #1.L - Incorporate test-taking and review strategies.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Ang ano ko dyan...pag nag-exam ako, pagka multiple choice, mas madali sa akin kasi yung nag a-analyze ako kung alin dito, kung ano yung tama, kesa yung sa blanko lang iisipin mo kung ano, kasi hindi ako mahilig magmemorize. Kunyari tanong mo ako anong gamot yung para sa ganitong sakit, blanko lang yung... identification na tanong, di ko masasagot yan on top of my head, pero yung may apat na choices... (R164).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, elimination... Ito hindi pwede dahil para sa ganitong sakit ito, pwede pero di gaanong ginagamit, ito di ako sigurado, ito para sa ibang sakit din yan, tas bigla ko na lang ito pipiliin parang tipong ganon” (R165).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi kasi ano yung naging experience ko naman kasi nung exam, yung mga tanong, hindi siya ganun ka specific (R180).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kung specific man, hindi sila yung specific sa pare-parehong bagay. Kunyari yung lahat ng choices dun specific, pero kung tutuusin mo, hindi sila para sa tanong, para sa iba talaga (R181).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Para sa iba talaga (R182).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kaya malalaman mo hindi na ito, e di isusulat mo na siya (R183).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ire-relate ko siya sa exam, hindi ba parang ganun din yung itatanong sa exam? Yung symptoms ni Patient X is indicative of what type of ..., parang ganyan (R271)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ire-relate ko siya sa table. Mismong pagkainirelate ko siya dun sa exam, iniisip ko yung table sa utak ko (R279).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo kasi yung medyo visual ako pagkaganyan eh. Hindi ko lahat matatandaan yung sa listahan ganun, kailangan makita ko yung table sa utak ko. Yung comparison kung bakit mataas ito, mababa yung base niya, pagkamababa yung base niya, mataas yung ganito parang... (R280).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kunyari Alkalosis ganon, ma-imagine ko kung ano itsura nung comparison nung ano. Mage-gets ko na siya kung bakit nagkaganon (R283).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...parang connect the dots (R284).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kunyari makita ko yung bakit nagkaganito yung alkalosis niya, bakit ganito yung values niya (R285).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Ganon, pero parang pag may nakita akong ganon, tapos binasa ko yung mga ano, yung mga sagot mag do-doble check ako parang titingnan ko uli yung tanong (R289).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, hindi ko sasagutin kagad yun! Hindi ako yung sagot kagad na, unang basa, sagot. Maliban na lang kung talagang kabisado ko yong tanong. Yung alam na alam ko, sigurado talaga ako (R290).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Babalikan ko yung tanong, ia-analyze ko muna, kung eto ba talaga (R291).</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Binubuksan ko na lang 'to (referring to B's reviewer), kapag, halimbawa, "ano nga ba 'tong sakit na' to?" Sa halip na buksan ko kay Saunders na pagkakapal-kapal...Tiningnan ko na lang yung kay B. Kung may technique si Carl Balita na mas madaling tandaan. Yung may mga tinatawag siyang "caricature" ba yun? Yun mga palatandaan. Mas madali mo tandaan. Dito ko siya tiningnan. Pero hindi ko siya binasa (E203).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, mga mnemonics (E204).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, pero more on Saunders ako. Heto (referring to B's reviewer) pang reference ko na lang 'to. Yung madadaling idea lang niya yung kinukuha ko. Para kasing hindi ko siya ganun nagamit. Mas madali ko siyang naintindihan kay Saunders (E205).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi nga ang exam ng board ay situational. So dun ko nagamit yung parang "oo nga 'noh heto yung sakit niya, si Angina, so kailangan alam ko yung intervention niya. Kasi kay Saunders, nakaspecify yung first mong gagawin...what if kung situation mo ganito...nakalagay kay Saunders yun. Kaya nung nag-eexam na'ko sa situational, 'ah heto yun, nabasa ko kay Saunders 'to". Kasi kung minsan may mga pick-up lines na... (E212).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>"...kasi nga naaral mo siya individually, yung bawat details kasi nga iniimagine mo mag-isa nung nag-aaral ka. Hindi pinaiimagine sa'yo ng iba, kundi ikaw yung nag-iimagine mag-isa" (E346).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Makakatulong siya na ma-recall mo. Recalling kasi yung mga ganyan eh, para sa akin eh... (J227).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, so may mga answer dun na, apat 'di ba, ABCD? Isa dun tama. Tapos at the end, sa likod nun 'di 'ba kung ano yung tamang sagot. Normally, sasagutan mo siya. "Tama ba ako?", "Ay mali", iba yung tamang sagot. Let's say letter B yung tamang sagot. Para sa akin ha, recalling lang yun eh, hindi mo alam mismo yung antidote sa gamot na yun, pero tanda mo siya kasi naexperience mo. Pero kapag tinanong ka kung anong antidote sa Amphetamine, hindi mo masasagot not unless nakita mo talaga yung sagot, dun mo marerecall (J228).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Alam mo ba iyong appendicitis sabihin mo sa professor mo ganyan. Ano ba iyong nursing approach doon. Ano ba iyong gamot doon? Sa pagtatanong ko, nakikinig ako sa'yo doon ako nakakakuha ng knowledge (J124).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Tapos may reasoning (J125).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo. Parang ginamit kita para matuto ako. Parang ikaw ay librong nagsasalita (J128).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Tapos pag may hindi kayo naintindihan, kunyari nagpresent ako nagtanong ako sa kanila, ang sagot nila sabi ko 'Gets mo ba talaga?' hindi may ganito parang isa-sub ka pa nila, sina-sub ka talaga nila, ganon. Kunyari, sa gamot example para sa Clonidine o para saan siya? (G145).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Parang papasok na dun yung nagreview sa MS siya (G146).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...Oo, hanggang dumating na kami na tina tackle na yung sakit na yon, sumasama, para pagka sa susunod pag nag topic siya, di mo kailangan mag report kasi may alam na yung mga yun, mag-aano na lang sila 'Oy alam ko yan (G148).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yung hindi ko sigurado naka mark. Naka mark talaga siya tas kasi diba ang kagandahan kasi pag may kasama kang mag-aral kunyari diba. Hindi naman maiwasan yon eh, natatandaan mo siya kasi may comeding nangyari. Pumapalo dun yung 'Ay naalala ko, ganito yung ginawa ni ganito nun ah'. Heto yung sagot non kasi nagpapatawa siya, may sinabi siyang hindi namin naintindihan, pumunta siya ng ganito. Pumapasok talaga yung ganon parang narerecall mo na may ginawa talagang palatandaan, may ginawang palatandaan (G156).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Ayun ganun nga, yung maliliit na diperensya lang, pagka yung... choose the best find answer diba? Kung ano yung best para dun sa situation ganun talaga ako mag-ano... (N170)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>I go from the basics muna... (N215).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>In general ahh alam mo yung basic na concept. Kunyari ahh kunyari MS, MS dapat alam mo...kunyari blood flow...Anatomy ...let's go with Anatomy first and then Physiology and then ia-analyze ko siya kunyari Myocardial Infarction or MI ahh hihina yung parang idi-disrupt ko yung Anatomy parang don ko igagaling sa anatomy na hanggang sa...(N216).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo by logic (N220).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, parang ganon nga hindi mo siya tatandaan na pag ito yung tanong ito yung sagot... (N222).</i></p>

	<p>☞ Parang dun ko na lang din ipapasok yung mga gamot, mga procedures, yung mga Nursing Care Plan parang ganon, huhugutin mo yung sagot from the basic... (N217).</p> <p>☞ ...parang ganon nga hindi mo siya tatandaan na pag ito yung tanong, ito yung sagot (N222).</p> <p>☞ Pagka ito yung tanong ganun ung tanong ito yung sagot "letter B" huhugutin mo siya (N223).</p> <p>☞ Yung aalamin mo yung mga para saan yung neuro transmitters, bakit neuro transmitter na (N226).</p> <p>☞ Oo, sabi ko nga Physiology and then sa mga Nursing Care Plan parang huhugutin mo siya na parang, kunyari, ang prioritization huhugutin mo siya pag may mga tanong diba galing sa Nursing Care Plan for this di huhugutin mo siya sa priority case mo (N227)</p> <p>☞ Oo basta lagi kang may paghuhugutan ng basic. Parang ganon ang concept sa pagsagot lagi kang may paghuhugutan ng basic (N228).</p> <p>☞ Oo, alam mo yung basic (N229).</p> <p>☞ Parang ganon nga in-approach ko siya from basic, kunyari dun sa MS, yung pulmo (pulmonary) patent yung airway tapos ito yung lalabas, ito yung koneksyon ng sakit ganon, ito yung paglumabas na sakit, pagka ganon, dugtong-dugtong na sila, from basic lagi (N230).</p> <p>☞ Oo nung bago ko na tinuturo sa kanila, kasi parang ang siste non, sinulat ko sa ganito, sinulat ko sa notebook ko eh ang pagtuturo ko sa kanila may blankong papel, tapos may blangkong notebook tas habang tinuturo ko heto yung parang ganon eto yong ano oh this is cardio this is ido-drawing ko kunyari yung pulmonary. Again, on the blank paper para mapupwersa ako na maalala ko (N197).</p> <p>☞ Pharma, kunyari anong tawag dito anti-depressant, depressant pampababa...so parang iincorporate mo yung lahat mababa tapos sa gamot na ito na kapag may adverse effects, like ito yong magiging adverse effect yung lahat ng bumababa, mga dizziness; mga ganon (N219).</p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ ...kasi dun sa mga examination namin sa school more of analytical talaga so bihira lang yung definition of terms, it's more of in-analyze mo yung situations (O126).</p> <p>☞ Halimbawa yung mga concept na hindi ako ma...yung parang madali kong matandaan, natatandaan mo pag halimbawa, ahm ano ba yon yung left at tsaka right sinister, dexter (B66).</p> <p>☞ Oo ginagawa ko Sleft, Dright parang sleft diba sinister (O67).</p>

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(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, sinister left, dright diba dexter right yung mga ganun, gumagawa ako ng sarili kong way para matandaan ko yung concept nung isang particular na topic, mga ganun (068).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>50-50 kung baga tinitingnan ko yung kung ano yung way na matututo, hindi ako nag stick sa isang ano sa isang strategy or ganun (069).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ahh, siyempre it will depend naman dun sa question, so talagang i-analyze mo yung question let's say for example ang situation is more of ahh bed side nursing, siyempre I eliminate mo yung bed side nursing kunyari ahh health education kasi post operation na yun eh, or education or teaching the client to ambulate mga ganun stuff, so it will really depend on dun sa topic and dun questions (0128).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siyempre kailangan yung based on facts talaga hindi lang siya puro logic kasi yung logic anu lang yong puro support support lang ng way ng pag a-answer siyempre yung pinakamalaking role dun yung facts, science lahat nung previous knowledge yun yung naging kailangan mo talaga when your taking any exam naman eh kailangan knowledgeable ka (0130).</i></p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ <i>II - Pilliterri/ test paper from P & G</i> <i>I reviewed about the vaccines, used a lot of tips and mnemonics from P & G (sorry Neri hinde ko malagay yung lahat ng tinutukan ko, basta ang naalala ko ay vaccines at yung development ng mga bata. Yung sa panganganak yung about sa eclampsia and pre-eclampsia...mga newborn tests (L24).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>As I learned from my friends the mnemonics of the drugs (a really great help!!!) the delusion of grandeur, bipolar, schizo; a lot of terms to learn but with the help of my friends it was fun because we would make fun of each other and relate the terms to ourselves (ex. Histrionic) (L27).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...I asked from friends for their test papers and some test taking strategies (the very popular, if you don't know it choose the longest answer as well as the letter C...(L22).</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Ahm kasi nga parang in-adapt na din ng local boards natin yung NCLEX diba so parang yun nga yung mga select all that apply, or mga ganyan or halimbawa kung ano yung pinaka mahabang, pinakamahabang option or yun yung sagot, pero not all the time siyempre yun yung sagot talaga, basahin mo din talaga tas yung mga eliminations ganyan ano pa ba, nakalimutan ko na yung mga testing strategies na yon eh, yon (B188).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	☞ <i>Oo minsan kasi pag masyado kong inisip, alam mo yun, masasayang yung oras. Imbis na mag uumpisa ka dun sa ibang answer magtatagal ka lang dun sa isang tanong; tapos yung nagtagal ka ng mag-isip tapos mali pa diba?" (B245)</i>
Mr. NurseMM	☞ Yes, read questions carefully and do not overanalyze (MM25).

✓ *Finding #1.M - Implement quality control measures.*

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>Dun na lang bini-base ko na lang sa handbook (O175).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Tinitingnan ko na lang sa likod kung tama yung sagot (O176).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Pag mali sagot ko I'll dig deeper bakit mali yung sagot ko kung bakit ito yung sagot na tama (O177).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>A, B, C, D ahh anu yung kunyari for emergency anu yung pinaka primary intervention eh breathing or circulation kunyari ang sinagot ko circulation kasi tatanga tanga kasi (O178).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>I di-dig deeper ko bakit airway yung summary ganon (O179).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Lalo't pag mali ako, kasi I have the feeling nung sinasagot ko siya na confident ako tama yung sagot ko na yon eh, ayon so parang gina judge ko yung book mali itong book na ito so kailangan kong hanapin yung reason na mag re-reason out tatama talaga yung book na yon, yun dun ako nagkakamali lagi naman ako mali hindi naman yun yung author ng book (O180).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo sa ibang libro yun nga pag nag i-imbistigate na ako lalo pag mali yung sagot ko (O181).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Some, siyempre nakatulong siya, yung knowledge mo nadadagdagan kasi parang yung type ng questions nung nagrereview ako parang nandun din siya sa board exam yung type din ng questions din nandon its more of multiple choice bibigyan ka nila ng almost the same answer so kailangan ano yung priority mo dun sa answer na yon (O183).</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	☞ <i>Kunwari nag-eexam (board) na ako (E246).</i>

- ☞ *Hindi siya ganun kay Saunders eh. May bukod siyang answer. Kaya hindi ka rin makakapandaya (smiles). Hindi ko tinitingnan yung sagot. Kasi nga yung bukod niyang sagot, meron siyang rationale dun. Kapag nagsasagot ako, sagot lang, pero nag-aanalyze na'ko nun. Parang nagbobo board exam na'ko nun, nung sinasagutan ko yung pre-test ni Saunders (E247).*
- ☞ *(interrupts) pero kailangan sagutan ko muna lahat saka ko tinitingnan yung rationale (E248).*
- ☞ *Hindi na, kasi parang feeling ko kapag binalikan mo ulit yung pag-aaral mo na yun, malilimutan mo ulit eh. Basta tandaan mo na siya, yun na yun. Kasi baka magkaron ka ng confusion eh, kasi tumatalon ka na sa ibang subjects na inaaral, tapos babalikan mo pa ulit yung una mong inaaral, parang waste of time (E250).*
- ☞ *Oo, yung pinakalast day ng review ko sa subject na yun, itake ko yung pinaka-post test ni Saunders. Yung pagkatapos mo yung subject niya, may exam sa dulo (E251).*
- ☞ *Dun ako nagfail, kaya dun ako nagfocus. Yung mga topics na yun, dun ako nag-aral. Yung mga nababasa ko sa exam na 'laging ito na naman' laging may naiinclude na ganung tanong. So tinatandaan ko siya (E140).*
- ☞ *Yun ang assessment ko eh. Kasi yun nga hindi ako lumevel dun sa mock board", kung baga hindi (naging) effective yung review ko nun. Pero that time, ang naisip ko, kahit hindi ako mag-review center okay lang. Ang naisip ko yung mga aaralin ko pa, dadagdagan ko kasi tinandaan ko yung bawat... questions sa mock board (E91).*
- ☞ *Two days, kasi nga wala ng basa-basa yun. Lahat kami ng mga kklase ko, saka nung nagsagot ako nung mga exam ni Saunders, nakita ko na 'ay pumapasok yung mga sagot ko'. That time, tigil na yung review ko, kailangan two days before, okay na ako (E244).*
- ☞ *Oo, gumawa ka ng plano. Planner talaga, saka Calendar Planner talaga ang tawag ko rito eh, yung araw na nireview ko. Saka huwag siyang mag-skip. Kung ano na yung nilagay mo na yun na yung subject na pag-aaralan mo that day, yun lang. Huwag ka munang tatalon sa isa pang subject kasi magkaron ng confusion na hindi ka makakapagfocus sa subject that day kasi nga tumulong ka dun sa isang subject (E315).*
- ☞ *(interrupts) Kailangang habulin ko kung ano yung target ko (E316).*

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, kung matutulog ako nung araw na yun, that time wala munang tulog-tulog, kailangan habulin ko yung subject na naiwan ko. Parang pinaparusan ko yung sarili ko (smiles). Siguro parang super-ego, para dun sa psyche (psychiatric nursing) (Smiles) (E317).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Meron kaming binili na ano, kami tig isa-isa kami, nung ano parang compilation ng board exam result (G215).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Tas yon sinasagutan walang dayaan yung parang o assignment parang ganon (G216).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Bahala ka na kung gusto mag cheat. Nasa sa iyo naman iyon eh. Yung book na yon o ito 1st set kunyari 1st 5 nung compilation mo ganitong page sagutin nyo tas kayo bahala kung gusto ninyo mag cheat tapos kinabukasan ano dalahin ninyo yung sagot dun tayo mag check tapos dun na hihimayin yung bawat tanong (G217).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Pag pauwi na, kasi hindi pwede ng before mag discuss eh sasakit na yung ulo nung bawat isa diba? Fully-loaded agad, hindi kagaya non pag-ano na, parang "Oy bakit ito yung sagot?" atleast don kahit hindi masyadong magfunction yung brain ng isa, atleast nakuha na nila yung isang unang subject namin, ayon (G219).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sa isa naming classmate, matalino talaga siya eh. So kung alam ni ate, dapat alam natin, yun yung sinasabi naming lima, pag alam ni ate dapat alam natin. Hindi pwedeng alam lang ni ate, dapat alam din natin (G115).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ano hindi kami kasi nagbibigay ng oras na 'ito dapat tapos na tayo ha'. Yung sa amin kasi dapat makuha niya kahit na paulit-ulit di pwede na bibigyan mo siya ng oras kasi hindi naman tayo pareparehas ng pick-up eh, kailangan i-consider yung kasama natin (G170).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>...pag may nakita akong ganon, tapos binasa ko yung mga ano, yung mga sagot mag do-doble check ako parang titingnan ko uli yung tanong (R289)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...hindi ko sasagutin kagad yun! Hindi ako yung sagot kagad na, unang basa, sagot. Maliban na lang kung talagang kabisado ko yong tanong. Yung alam na alam ko, sigurado talaga ako (R290).</i></p>

✓ Finding #1.N – Ward off your worries.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	☞ <i>...Board exam, kumbaga, do or die..." (J191)</i>

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(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>May pressure talaga eh. Kumbaga two days, tapos one day pahinga ko after that exam na eh. May pressure ako, pero although andun yung pressure kaya ko namang ihandle” (J200)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Actually, hindi ko inisip na babagsak talaga ako, hindi ako pessimistic eh. Wala akong idea na babagsak ako. Ang idea ko is nagfocus ako, alam ko yung kakayahan ko, kaya ko ‘to. Syempre, sa tulong na rin ni God. Nagpray ako sa kanya na kung anong kakalabasan nito, kagustuhan niya. At the end talaga ng lahat ng bagay sa akin, lahat ng desisyon ko, gagawin ko, nagppray ako. Kung ano mang kakalabasan, pangit o maganda, failure o hindi, iniisip ko yung kagustuhan ng Diyos, para wala akong regrets. Ganun sa’kin (J203).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Anxiety, may mild anxiety talaga, na ano ba yon tama ba lahat ng kinuha ko, tama ba lahat ng napag-aralan ko, ano na ba kami, knowledgeable na ba? Ganon. Yun yung inaano ko, may mild anxiety talaga, tas nagkikita kami... ano “Oy okay ka na? Sa tingin mo makakapasa? Oo, gumaganon lang kami (G113).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Okay naman kasi hindi ko naman ina-achieve eh. Kahit kami, lahat kami hindi nag a-achieve ng mataas. Ang sa amin, ang sa amin lang makapasa ka, tapos ano mapakita mo na kinaya mo (G247).</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Kahit na nagfailed ako sa mock board, hindi ko naisip na ‘uy dapat magreview center na’ko’. Hindi eh. Mas nagfocus ako na ‘ay naging weak ako sa subject na yun, so kailangan aralin ko pa siya. Lalo akong nagkainteres na dapat daanan ko yung subject na yun kasi nga talo ako dun eh (E149).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siyempre natatakot siya na baka nga bumagsak ka, kasi nga meron naman talangang fear na ganun, kaya lang, kailangan kasi idivert ko siya eh, na hindi dapat ganun eh. Kailangan optimistic ka pa rin sa ginagawa mo na “nag-aaral naman akong mabuti eh”, “hindi naman ako nagwawaste ng time eh”, “so why not? Kaya ko tong ipasa!” Nagseseryoso naman akong magreview, hindi ko naman siyang sobrang inaanalyze. So nandun yung guts ko na, pwede kakayanin ko yun (E159).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi, hindi. Kasi hindi naman ako nun nag-eexpect ng mataas eh (E344).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>“...Kasi nga parang pressure kapag sinabi mong board (exam) eh. Estudyante pa rin na nag-aaral lang para sa exam; yung mga major exam lang. Hindi ko siya inisip na board (exam) kasi para sa akin pressure siya (smiles). Parang light review para dun sa exam” (E102)</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, kasi nga sakripisyo talaga. Actually nasanay ang katawan ko dun na less tulog, more on aral. Kasi nga feeling mo na nakapagpray ka (E321).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Eh nasanay nga yung katawan ko nun. Kasi nga nagpray ako ng umaga eh (E328).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>No, kasi alam mo na nagppray ka eh, Kasi nga alam mo na yung bagay na yun pinagkakatiwala mo na kay God (E329).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi that time may prayer, kasi August na nun may pre-review na kami. Yung prayer-fasting sa Church namin, one month yun. So parang super sacrifice yun. Nagreview na nga ako ng madaling araw, tapos meron morning devotion sa church namin na 4:30 hanggang 6 (AM). So after nun magprayer na sa church, saka didiretso ng pasok. So that time nabuo na rin yung deeper faith ko nun kay God na, kasi sinasabayan ko rin ng prayer, one month yun, August yun, parang sacrifice na tinatawag. Nagkarun kasi ng program ang church namin, na parang prayer-fasting month (E320).</i></p>
<p>Mr. NurseR</p>	<p>☞ <i>Ang ano ko, parang 80% papasa ako 20% babagsak ako, parang ganon 80-20 pero ang ano dun, pasa lang as in pasa lang talaga” (R157)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...ayoko rin yung umasa sila na dahil nagreview center ka, papasa ka. Ayokong umasa sila (R108).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, oo pero hindi siya ganun katindi” (R220)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Umuwi kasi ako sa probinsya nung mga isang linggo bago mag-exam, eh ang relaxation ko nun, yung tipong yung maglakad-lakad sa gilid ng dagat, o yung mag-ikot ikot dun sa bayan lumabas ako (R292).</i></p>
<p>Mr. NurseO</p>	<p>☞ <i>Ahh oo, that was the very crucial part, it is the waiting that kills talaga eh hindi ko talaga alam I was clueless ang ginawa ko lang siyempre everyday prayers para lumakas yung loob tapos ginawa kong busyung sarili ko sa pagtrabaho oo kasi I don’t want to think the result of the board exam pa siyempre nandun din yung second thoughts na bakit ko sinagutan ‘to bakit ganun yung sagot ko dito parang nagkakaroon ka ng realization yung parang nag fa-flashback lahat ng sinagot mo dun sa board exam kasi maaalala mo yung ibang questions dun eh (O104).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...may point din yon na ahh yung iba nga pumasa ng hindi nag-aano (nagreview-center) eh, anung meron sila na wala ako siguro yung naging parang kapit sa patalim na lang ako non, sila nga nakapasa eh, we came from the same school naman... (O75).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Siguro 50-50, 50-50 kasi siyempre I was clinging on my basic knowledge na lang kung ano yung natutunan ko dun sa school parang naisip 4 years ako nag-aral oh 4 years na gumasta yung parents ko imposibleng wala naman ako natutunan dyan or imposibleng hindi naman nadaanan ito nung college ako aside from that siyempre yun nga the power of prayer na lang siguro yun na lang din yung nagbigay sa akin ng hope. My own knowledge tsaka coming from above (O144).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Okay lang yon eh kasi ang plano non pag di ka pumasa edi yung 2nd take mag review center ka na, parang ganon” (N105).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Pagtitiis, mahirap yon, pagtitiis. Wala ka ng magagawa eh, siyempre pray ka din sa Diyos na bigyan ka ng tiwala sa sarili, tsaka ng knowledge (N136).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Nagpasalamat ako sa Diyos kasi I believe na hindi talaga yun mangyayari kung hndi sa kanya, isa yun sa pinakamalaking blessing na binigay ng Dios na pumasa ako. I prayed, I prayed (N147).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Na nakapasa ako, kaya nagpapasalamat ako, I believe na hindi yon mangyayari kung hindi ako nag pray or kung hindi will ni God (N149).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ahh wala naman siguro nung before the ahh...Oo nung kasi minsan pag uma-attend ako, kasi yung ibang mga church mates ko, alam nila na may board exam ako. Kapag may prayer meeting ahh sinasali ko na din yung may board exam ako, ganyan (N268).</i></p>
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ <i>I admit I had doubts that I would pass...(K22)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Before the actual exam day, don't cram. Try to relax since you will just have exam jitters on the actual board exam. Pray and just be confident. Don't mind others around you and concentrate on your paper. Don't rush and double check your answer key. Be mindful of erasures and try to count the items you answered with the actual items to see if they match. Bring light snacks and water. Have your pencils ready (K42).</i></p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ <i>Actual boards: deep breaths, pray and leave it to God and 2 days before the exam (don't review anymore) (L37).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p>☞ <i>Pray and have a confidence to pass the exam...think that it's just a quiz in the class.hehhehe (MJ39).</i></p>

A.2 Self-Reported Traits

✓ Finding #2.a: Self-confidence

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Tiwala, tiwala mo sa sarili, sa Diyos (N276).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Wala naman akong ibang pagkakatiwalaan eh, ako rin naman ang gagawa non nasa sa akin din naman yung gawa so pagtiwalaan mo na lang yung gawa mo (N277).</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Siguro isa yun sa mga pinagkakatiwalaan. Hindi, pano ko ba sasabihin? Kung бага confident ako sa sarili ko na makakaya ko yung board exam kasi yung mga kapatid ko nakaya din nila eh kung бага nagigauge ko naman yung sarili ko na kung бага naikukumpara ko naman yung sarili ko dun sa dalawa kong kapatid. Sabi ko, okay kaya ko ito, basta kailangan lang talaga may focus ako dun sa pag-rereview makakaya ko yun (B108).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ahh, siguro kung meron man akong way na ako hindi sumuko, siguro dun sa mga question na yung alam mo yun na parang ahn malapit ka na dun sa answer kung бага tina-trust mo na lang yung sarili mo dun sa, yun dun sa answer na yon ahm tsaka may kasama na ring ano ahm faith, or yun nga (B250).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ang isang tao para pumasa of course be confident and at the same time ahm be open, kailangan mong kung бага huwag mong isarado yung sarili mo sa mga options or mga bagay bagay na maaring makatulong sayo na ma achieve yung goal (B253).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>May pressure talaga eh. Kumbaga two days, tapos one day pahinga ko after that exam na eh. May pressure ako, pero although andun yung pressure kaya ko namang ihandle” (J200)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ano lang, malakas kasi tiwala ko sa sarili ko eh” (J201).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Syempre, umangat yung pride ko, yung self-esteem, umangat pa lalo, lahat yun. Kasi feeling ko, kung nagawa ‘ko to sa sarili ko, sa iba nahihirapan sila, hirap na hirap sila, ako nakaya ko isa lang, tapos limited resources pa ako, limited time...Sa ibang bagay siguro kaya ko ring gawin. Kagaya yun nga, nagtrabaho ako sa bangko, wala akong ka-alam-alam, pero dahil nga sa naging lifestyle ko na ‘kaya ‘ko ‘to’, nagtiwala ako sa sarili ko, kaya ko. Ganun din sa pag-aaral ko, ganun din nung nagtake ako ng review, tiwala lang sa sarili. Pero syempre, meron kang back-up dapat, na knowledge kahit papano (J235).</i></p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>“...definitely ang natutunan ko dun sa college na yon is siyempre you should not settle for something less. You always look up and beyond, laging mag go-goal ka ng mataas but definitely dapat feasible yung mga goals mo (O18).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseK	☞ In the end, I became confident in my own knowledge and capabilities which truly helped on the day of the exam where exam jitters is your enemy” (K46).
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ Confident enough to pass the exam.... (MJ43).

✓ *Finding #2.b: Self-discipline.*

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ For me, it’s all about discipline. If you don’t instill discipline in yourself and just slack off then self-review would not be effective” (K41)</p> <p>☞ Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline” (K45).</p> <p>☞ <i>Self-review made me not only gain knowledge but taught me the art of discipline as well. It also boosted my self-esteem which is good for my health as I became more confident in myself” (K49).</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>...Yun nga lang, naging parusa ko sa sarili kom no cell phones, no TV, aral lang talaga. Yun yung naging focus ko. Sina mama, kasi may tindahan naman kami, kaya dun siya sa tindahan. Kaya yung bahay na yun, ako lang talaga mag-isa, hindi nila ako ginugulo; kakain lang sila (E129).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Midnight. Sinubukan ko mag-12 midnight. Yung madaling araw na review. Tulog, gising sa umaga, tapos bago ka uli pumasok ng 6 sa umaga. Matutulog uli ako ng 4 (AM), saka uli ako papasok (E111).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kasi nga sakripisyo talaga. Actually nasanay ang katawan ko dun na less tulog, more on aral. Kasi nga feeling mo na nakapagpray ka (E321).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Discipline. Kasi mahirap lalo na kung mag self-review ka, mahirap mag-ano sa sarili mo, parang mahirap kontrolin yung sarili na wag lumabas diba sabi ko nga (N274).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Wala naman talaga sa schedule mo yung labas ka ng labas pero nakakalabas ka pa rin that’s why hindi ko nga natapos, so you have to have a discipline also (N275).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Kasi may ano may discipline din ako. Kasi nga disiplina pumapasok ako kahit na inaantok ako yung nag self-review kami kasi diba hindi naman ano pag uwi mo ng 5 makakauwi ka, minsan gagala ka. Minsan may iba ka pang siyempre friends na uy tara labas tayo siyempre hindi ka naman makakatanggi kasi.</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<i>So parang ano ka papasok ka dun sa dorm na ganon, na may tama ka, may ganon yun (G138).</i>
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ Self discipline
Mr. NurseMM	☞ "Gained discipline and got more confidence! Very Proud!" (MM15).

✓ *Finding #2.c: Determination*

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseK	☞ I believe that it became effective through my determination. When I was reviewing, I pushed myself harder by reminding myself that I should pass the board on my first try since I did not want to undergo the grueling PRC exam registration again (K21).
Ms. NurseL	☞ Qualities a person must have: the dedication to put the review above everything else the know how to balance your review with your life the hunger to reach for the stars (L41). ☞ Stubbornness - they told me to stop but I still went forward :) (L40).
Mr. NurseJ	☞ <i>Nasa isang room ako. Nun ko lang ginawa sa buhay ko na nasa isang room ako. Kinausap ko ang family ko, na huwag niyo akong iistorbohin, bigyan niyo ako ng pagkain during, kapag kakainan na.... Kasi although ang una kong naisip ay para malaman lang yung sistema ng board exam, andun pa rin yung pride mo na papasa ka. Two days review, andun pa rin yung pride mo na "kaya ko 'to". So nag-effort pa rin talaga ako. Hindi ko naman sinasabi na (inasa) ko lang sa memory ko yung pagpasa ko ng board (exam). Nag-effort talaga ako... (J188).</i>
Mr. NurseR	☞ <i>Oo kasi nga nung nag-aral ako, kahit na hindi ako mag-aral ng matagal basta yung short time na 3 oras na nag-aral ako sa umaga, kunyari ganon, 2 oras kunyari sa umaga yung focus ko nun andun talaga. Talagang i-a-absorb ko talaga yun, pagka nung nag-exam naman ako, yung araw ng exam, talagang focus din ako, kasi wala talagang ibang laman ang utak ko kundi mag-exam (R315).</i>

Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Hindi nga. Kahit na nung mock board na kahit na feeling ko nag-fail ako, dun ako lalo nag-aralyung mga hindi ko nadaanan (E130).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi alam ko ginawa ko na, focus ng lahat na eh. Nung nagreview na'ko nun, buong sarili ko na nun eh" (E310).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sana matiyaga rin siya. Kasi nga naniniwala ako na hindi langkasi matatalino yung pumapasa ng board exam eh. Kasi may nakikita ako na yung matatalino yun pa yung lumalagapak. Kaya yung taong nagtiyatyagang mag-aral, sila yung nag-eexcel sa board exam (E337).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kasi nga 'di ba, sa nursing parang nung una hirap na hirap ako. Pero naisip ko na, pinasok ko 'to eh, kailangan tapusin ko 'sya kahit na anong mangyari (E335).</i></p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>Kasi may mga matatalino naman dyan e na siguro puro yabang lang nag cling na lang sa katalinuhan nila siyempre you should not only be reliant with your own wisdom eh kasi kailangan mo din yung magpursige (O83).</i></p>

✓ *Finding #2.d- Other Traits Noted:*

Participant	Responses
Spirituality	<p>☞ <i>Born again, so yun hindi ko yun pinabayaan kahit nagreview ako, hindi ko pinabayaan yung ministry (N267).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ahh wala naman siguro nung before the ahh...Oo nung kasi minsan pag uma-attend ako, kasi yung ibang mga church mates ko, alam nila na may board exam ako. Kapag may prayer meeting ahh sinasali ko na din yung may board exam ako, ganyan (N268).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Tiwala, tiwala mo sa sarili, sa Diyos (N276).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siguro number one jan yung tiwala mo sa Diyos (N263).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...na magagawa mo ito dahil, dahil nagbibigay ng tiwala si God, yun ang number 1, number 1 then sumunod na lang din siguro yung sa sarili mo, na ability mo na tiwala sa sarili mo (N264).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Actually, church musician ako (N267).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Inaano ko na lang, para hindi ko maging regrets, parang sublimation na lang na hindi ko matawag na regrets 'to, iniisip ko na lang na yan gusto ni God (J263).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Actually, hindi ko inisip na babagsak talaga ako, hindi ako pessimistic eh. Wala akong idea na babagsak ako. Ang idea ko</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

is nagfocus ako, alam ko yung kakayahan ko, kaya ko 'to. Syempre, sa tulong na rin ni God. Nagpray ako sa kanya na kung anong kakalabasan nito, kagustuhan niya. At the end talaga ng lahat ng bagay sa akin, lahat ng desisyon ko, gagawin ko, nagppray ako. Kung ano mang kakalabasan, pangit o maganda, failure o hindi, iniisip ko yung kagustuhan ng Diyos, para wala akong regrets. Ganun sa'kin (J203).

☞ *Ahh, siguro kung meron man akong way na ako hindi sumuko, siguro dun sa mga question na yung alam mo yun na parang ahn malapit ka na dun sa answer kung бага tina-trust mo na lang yung sarili mo dun sa, yun dun sa answer na yon ahm tsaka may kasama na ring ano ahm faith, or yun nga (B250).*

☞ *Actually hindi ako yung every Sunday nagsisimba. Ano lang kami parang yung with the family tsaka kung бага, hindi naman kami yung basta nagre-rely na lang kay God okay na tulongan ninyo po akong masagot ko ng tama, kung бага nasa sarili din kasi iyon ahm kung бага I do my part basta I guide ninyo lang po ako (B252).*

☞ *Kasi that time may prayer, kasi August na nun may pre-review na kami. Yung prayer-fasting sa Church namin, one month yun. So parang super sacrifice yun. Nagrereview na nga ako ng madaling araw, tapos meron morning devotion sa church namin na 4:32 hanggang 6 (AM). So after nun magprayer na sa church, saka didiretso ng pasok. So that time nabuo na rin yung deeper faith ko nun kay God na, kasi sinasabayan ko rin ng prayer, one month yun, August yun, parang sacrifice na tinatawag. Nagkarun kasi ng program ang church namin, na parang prayer-fasting month (E319).*

☞ *Kasi that time may prayer, kasi August na nun may pre-review na kami. Yung prayer-fasting sa Church namin, one month yun. So parang super sacrifice yun. Nagrereview na nga ako ng madaling araw, tapos meron morning devotion sa church namin na 4:32 hanggang 6 (AM). So after nun magprayer na sa church, saka didiretso ng pasok. So that time nabuo na rin yung deeper faith ko nun kay God na, kasi sinasabayan ko rin ng prayer, one month yun, August yun, parang sacrifice na tinatawag. Nagkarun kasi ng program ang church namin, na parang prayer-fasting month (E320).*

☞ *Oo, kasi nga sakripisyo talaga. Actually nasanay ang katawan ko dun na less tulong, more on aral. Kasi nga feeling mo na nakapagpray ka (E321).*

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Curiosity	<p>☞ <i>Ayon tas ano, gutom sa kaalaman, kahit nung estudyante kami. "Para saan ito?" "Anong pangalan niya?" Yung mga doctor naasar na nga sa akin kakatanong (G258).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Matanong (G259).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, matanong ako kahit sa hanggang ngayon matanong pa rin ako, 'bakit ganon, bakit ganito?' si "bakit" si bakit ako eh (G260).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Bakit, bakit yung tawag sa akin si "Ms. Bakit" talaga ito (G261).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yon bakit nangyayari yung ganyan, curiosity yon (G262).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi diba kung may curiosity ka parang pati yung kasama mo "Ay oo nga ano?", ganon. Kunyari may sinabi ka na ito para sa ganito, ganito, ganito may ano sila parang mas madaling parang natatandaan nila agad-agad pagka ganon ang ginagawa ko "Oy ang sabi ni prof ganito, oy sabi ni doc ganito sabi ni doc" kasi maganda sa amin kasi nga magkaka start kami ng apelyido, classmate kami so since 3rd year kami-kami talaga as in kasi nga sunod sunod kami so during duty hours kami, talagang ang hiwalayan lang namin tulog (G263).</i></p>
Diligence	<p>☞ <i>Yung pagiging matiyaga ko, yung siguro yung pinakamalaking factor. Hind kasi ako matalino, pero matiyaga ako (E332).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kumbaga naalala ko lang yung sinabi ng teacher ko dun sa C.A.T., na kumbaga yung karangalan ko, nakikita niya talaga na solo ko lang siya eh. Mag-isa kong kinukuha yung achievement ko. Kasi nga matiyaga nga daw ako. Para sa ibang tao nakikita rin nila na itong taong 'to, mag-aachieve siya sa sarili niya. Kasi nga, ganon nga siya. Hindi man super-brainy sa school na nasa top siya, kaya nga nagulat din sila na yung batang simple lang, naging ganun siya (E336).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yung sa father ko, sabi niya yung anak ko lang yung kumbaga maipagmamalaki, Kasi siya asensado siya before, bumagsak siya. Hindi siya pinag-igi yung trabaho niya. Parang naging dahilan yun ng parang minamaliit kami ng family eh. Ang sabi niya, itong anak kong 'to, siya yung maipagmamalaki na. Nakapasa siya, kumbaga gumawa siya ng paraan. Hindi nga nila iniexpect kasi nga sa magkakapatid hindi naman ako super talino, matiyaga lang talaga. Hindi niya akalain na papasa ako, kaya thankful siya kasi ng worthy yung hirap niya sa akin (E164).</i></p>

Patience	♀ Qualities: Curiosity? - if something is nagging me whenever we have the q and a with my friend and i dont know the answer. I'd looked for it the answer right away Stubbornness - they told me to stop but I still went forward :) patience - w/out it were all goners :) Never give up mantra (L40).
Resourcefulness	♀ 3. Resourcefulness – I was not content with my own materials so I searched the internet for more study materials (K46b).

✚ APPENDIX B: Other Findings

B.1 – Self-Review Reasons

Apart from the main findings presented in the body of the manuscript, analysis also revealed that self-review could be an alternative solution for those Nurse Candidates who *didn't* want to (preferential reasons) enroll in review centers, and those who *can't* (circumstantial reasons). Except for Mr. NurseN, Ms. NurseG and Ms. NurseL, the rest of the participants gave multiple and compounded reasons. Each of them, however, offered his/her respective reason/s and are summarized below:

- **Circumstantial Reasons**

In this study, there were case participants who did self-review because of the need to do so:

Figure 16: *Circumstantial Self-review Reasons*

Reason	Participant Name
Financial (Short of funds)	Mr. NurseJ, Mr. NurseO & Mr. NurseR
Time Constraints	
Working while reviewing	Mr. NurseO, Mr. NurseJ, & Mr. NurseMM
Family Issue	Ms. NurseE
Advanced Studies	Ms. NurseL
Others	
Challenged	Mr. NurseN & Ms. NurseG

Table 6: *List of case participants who had circumstantial self-review reasons*

✓ Financial (short of funds)

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	☞ <i>Actually yung mga factors kaya hindi ako nakapagreview center nahirapan ako sa financial. Kasi during sa time namin, siguro fifteen thousand (Php15,000) iyon eh. Para sa'min malaking bagay yung fifteen thousand Php15,000 so hindi naman sa ginusto o gusto ko magself-review. Kungbaga yung naging ano sa school namin ang priorities nila, priority nila ay yung mga nag-review center yun</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p><i>lang yung pag-eexamine nila. June yung examination. Sila yung priority. Pero ako naman ahhh yun hindi ako nakapag-review (J1).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Financially... (J50).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kungbaga ano that time walang-wala talaga kami. Parang nahuli iyong padala ng tito ko abroad. Parang ganoon talaga... nagkataon talaga (J61).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi mayroon kasi akong anak. Kungbaga graduating ako nabuntis ko iyong girlfriend ko so kailangan ko mag-trabaho (J71).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kaya kung sabagay pagka-graduate ko magtra-trabaho talaga ako ayun. Naging factor din iyon kaya after ko grumaduate nagtrabaho agad ako dahil may anak ako (J72).</i></p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>After graduation, kasi I was really expecting na kasama ako dun sa review center (O67).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yung buong 1 week na yon, yung after graduation mayron kaming in house, libreng in house review dun within that span of 1 week I heard the news from my dad na di daw niya ako kayang suportahan (O68).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo kasi nung after graduation siyempre kasi taking up BSN is really pricy diba gastos tayo diyan and I'm not the only child who was studying at tertiary level so I have my brother and my younger sister. So after graduation, we were really on a tight budget ahh my daddy was expecting income after my graduation pero di siya lumabas. Kasi my dad was a CPA, may mga clients siya na hindi timely na magbayad (O49).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>So I tried to ask assistance from my relatives abroad pero my recession ata nun sa US they were really in a tight budget so yun lang siyempre parang naawa ako sa sarili ko na...ang sabi ko yung mga classmates ko nag- eexam, ako nakatengga wala akong ginagawa. Sila nagre review, ako wala so parang ang baba ng morale ko non, sabi ko kahit anong trabaho na lang a applyan ko. Ang naisip ko nga kahit sa panaderya na lang nagbebenta ng bread para lang magkaroon ako ng income but then again siyempre another opportunity came after graduation 3 weeks lang ako nawalan ng ginagawa but within that 3 weeks I tried applying to different call centers. Ahh first attempt I failed, second attempt I failed, third attempt sa ibang company Teleperformance I passed so yun, para siyang naging sign sa akin na this is it siguro kung</i></p>

	<p><i>magkakaroon ako ng income and yet I'll have time to think about what I'm going to do dun sa incoming board exam pero after graduation tsaka kahit wala akong wala kaming means for review sabi ko naisip ko kung ano man yung natutunan ko nung 4 years ko siguro sapat na yon or it's really more than done enough kasi sobrang ganda ng training sa amin noon, so yon I started as an agent... (O50).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Actually ano siya eh, those were not really the factors, I didn't have a choice talaga (O48).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>...Yung manghihiram ako ng mga questionnaire ganyan, ako magsasagot mag-isa pero yung tipong review center parang di ko siya gustong gawin kasi magastos (R107b).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...Hindi ayoko mag review center, ayoko talagang gumastos (R122).</i></p>

✓ Time Constraints

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseMM	<p>☞ <i>I worked immediately after graduation and didn't want to spend money for a review center (MM5).</i></p>
Mr. NurseO	<p>☞ <i>...Siyempre another opportunity came after graduation 3 weeks lang ako nawalan ng ginagawa but within that 3 weeks I tried applying to different call centers. Ahh first attempt I failed, second attempt I failed, third attempt sa ibang companyO I passed so yun, para siyang naging sign sa akin na this is it siguro kung magkakaroon ako ng income and yet I'll have time to think about what I'm going to do dun sa incoming board exam pero after graduation tsaka kahit wala akong wala kaming means for review sabi ko naisip ko kung ano man yung natutunan ko nung 4 years ko siguro sapat na yon or it's really more than done enough kasi sobrang ganda ng training sa amin noon, so yon I started as an agent.</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>...Kungbaga yung naging ano sa school namin ang priorities nila, priority nila ay yung mga nag-review center yun lang yung pag-eexamine nila. June yung examination. Sila yung priority. Pero ako naman ahhh yun hindi ako nakapag-review. Hindi ako nakapag-take ng exam after I graduated kasi nga sa'min parang ni-required nila na before mag-take ng exam... parang ma-guarantee nila yung result. So, after akong grumaduate nagtrabaho ako sa CompanyJ for eight (8) months. After that, naging supervisor ako sa CompanyJ2 then yung 2010 na-hired ako as company nurse dito sa CompanyJ3.</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Kasi mayroon kasi akong anak. Kungbaga graduating ako nabuntis ko iyong girlfriend ko so kailangan ko mag-trabaho.</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kaya kung sabagay pagka-graduate ko magtra-trabaho talaga ako ayun. Naging factor din iyon kaya after ko grumaduate nagtrabaho agad ako dahil may anak ako.</i></p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Hmm okay. Kasi nung bata kasi, kung baga ako laki sa pangaral sa magulang. Yun ang pinaka-sure ko, kasi nga maka-“mamma’s girl” kasi ako eh. So siya yung nung bata pa lang, siya yung guide ko eh. Pero hindi naman siya nurse,pero para sa’kin part ng individual ko na values, more on, sa kanya galing. Kasi father ko, hindi naman siya masyado nag-stay sa Philippines, dahil seaman siya. So more on palaki ako ng mommy (E23).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kasi nga that time may sakit pa si mama nun. Nagka-kidney problem siya, tapos nag-high blood pressure, nag-chichills siya. Kaya mas preferred ko nun dapat nasa bahay lang ako para habang nag-aaral, nakikita ko siya, kung may mangyayari. Atleast hindi gaya ng tatawagin pa’ko na “uy si mama may ganito”. That time, sa bahay na lang ako siguro, kasi yung nga nag-occur yun sa akin na self-review na lang, kasi kung baga may idea na’ko nun sa pre-review (E86b).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, kasi kung ibabiyahe ko pa, 2 hours, what if sabahay na lang ako...(E82)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Two hours ang kinuconsume ko sa biyahe... (E83).</i></p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>☞ <i>Choosing self-review for me was a necessity since I couldn't afford to go to a review center because I was a first year medical student back then (L7a).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>I didn't have a choice to opt out to self-review since that was my only choice back then if I wanted to take the board exam. There was no time for me to apply to a center. So when I applied for my boards I already knew that Im gonna work harder during the weekends to study (L16).</i></p>

✓ Challenged

Participant	Responses
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Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Chinallenge kasi kami ng professors namin. Kasi nga nasa regular students kami. Chinallenge kami, total unlimited na naman. Wala ng refresher course. Try nga natin kung sino talaga yung papasa sa inyo. Trip-trip lang. Sabi nung professors namin. Tapos ano, halos half nung class namin sumang-ayon naman. Kaya halos half sa amin, nagreview yung iba, tapos kami nag-selfreview. Yung mga friends ko talaga, pinagpustahan namin yun kung sino yung papasa o hindi. Kaya five kami nun na nagboarding house (G43a).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ilang professors kasi yung nagchallenge sa amin nun eh (G44).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, marami sila. Mga 4 to 5 sila. Sabi nga namin, ' pinag-usapan niyo kami ha'. Pero selected na section lang yung ginaganon (G45).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Five kaming sections na ginanun ng 4-5 na professors namin. Kasi yung section namin, $\frac{3}{4}$ nun halos nasa DL Dean's List) (G54).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Balak ko nun, magreview center sana ako nun, pero sige, chinachallenge niyo kami kaya nagbukod kami, kami-kami na lang. Tapos nung January to March, pumapasok ako kasi nga compulsory na pumasok sa, parang Nursing Audit kung tawagin. Yun pumapasok kami kasi nga "attendance is a must", pero tinutulugan ko lang siya. Nakakaboring eh (G56).</i></p>
Ms. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Actually ganito kasi yon, ahh diba pag mag bo-board ka mag rereview ka, mag review center. Nagkayabangan kami ng kuya ko parang nagkaroon eh kasi siya magbabayad ng review center, parang sige yung pera sayo na lang mag self-review ka na lang parang ganon (N48).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kung di ako papasa di ko din makukuha yon (N142).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Napasubo na lang din ako (N51).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Kaya yun, napa self-review ako, pero it was not really planned, siguro kung hindi nagkaganon nagreview center din ako. Pero mayabang nga, mayabang kuya ko, mayabang din ako napa-oo ako (N50).</i></p>

○ **Preferential Reasons**

Another was they “preferred” or “chose to do” so:

Figure 17: *Preferential Self-review Reasons*

Reason	Case Participant
Readiness to take the licensure exam prior to graduation	Mr. NurseB, Ms. NurseE, Mr. NurseJ, Mr. NurseN, Ms. NurseG, Mr. NurseMJ & Mr. NurseMM
Study Habit and Learning Style	Ms. NurseK, Ms. NurseE, Mr. NurseR & Mr. NurseB
Lower Expectation	Mr. NurseJ, Mr. NurseR, Mr. NurseN & Ms. NurseG
No method can guarantee success	Mr. NurseR & Ms. NurseK
Tradition in the making	Mr. NurseB

Table 7: *List of case participants who had preferential self-review reasons*

✓ Readiness to take the licensure exam prior to graduation

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ ...it's like I've already proven to myself when I passed our exams. In our school, before you're able to take the board exam, you'll have to undergo a series of exams (B99).</p> <p>☞ It's like you'd start it in the finals; it's where it'll start, and so when you've already proven that you've passed the final exam it means that you can already gauge yourself that you can do it in the board exam. Then you'll review for the comprehensive (pre-board) exam. If you passed that exam, then you'd feel ready for the board exam..." (B100).</p> <p>☞ ...and I can tell you we didn't lack review materials... even just for that I already became confident..." (B132).</p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ When I was in my fourth year, I was so focused and I saw myself pass the exams... (and) earned good scores" (E103).</p> <p>☞ Sixty percent was the passing rate, so if the test was 1-100, I was already within the level of the average students. If they're at 80%, I would get 80%. I was no longer failing the tests. If previously I only barely passed, during that time I'd already got 80% (E104).</p> <p>☞ It was not only because of the distance from school, it was also because of our pre-review at school. It was then that I thought to just get an idea from our pre-review and study on my own" (E105).</p> <p>☞ ... in the pre-review, I already had an idea of what may appear in the board exam" (E261).</p> <p>☞ Yes, it was already like a waste of time, because I already had a foundation in the pre-review at school. There I got the idea that it's possible to just review on my own. I got some tips from our professors in the pre-review. So I decided that I'll do it on my own, instead of travelling to school even if the review would be provided for free by our school... (E84).</p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ I was consistent until fourth year...so based on the results of our tests, even though I didn't have a book, I felt I could make it. I felt that I could do it (J65b).</p> <p>☞ Yes, during the pre-review. It might also be because of that reason that I became over confident that I no longer feared taking the board exam (J66).</p>

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(St. Paul University System)

Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ It was a big part, especially the in-house (pre) review (N251).</p> <p>☞ It was from there that I got the style of teaching my classmates.” There I wondered ‘... how do these reviewers prepare themselves before they face us?’ (N252)</p>
Ms. NurseG	☞ It's because most of the topics that were being taught, I already had a good grasp. I felt like I already knew something (G235).
Mr. NurseMJ	☞ Four years of studying was good enough (MJ5).
Mr. NurseMM	<p>☞ I personally believed that I came from an institution with strong educational foundation” (MM34).</p> <p>☞ RATE: from 1-5 as 5 would be the highest, I would rate myself as 4.5 as my class standing. I considered myself as a competitive student (MM2).</p> <p>☞ ...didn't want to spend money for a review center (MM5).</p>

✓ Study Habit and Learning Style:

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseK	<p>☞ Study habit -I believe that I can study harder if I am alone. I get distracted easily and do not find studying in an auditorium full of people conducive to learning (K5a).</p> <p>☞ Convenience – I wanted to study at my own pace so self-review was very convenient for me. If I will get too tired, I can just sleep to refresh my mind for another day of learning. It is unlike review centers where there are times that one can't concentrate because of information overload" (K5c).</p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>☞ <i>Siguro hati, kasi nga may gusto nga ako na palaaral na tao, yung kasabay ko sila na nag-aaral, pero ang ayoko lang kapag groupings na review, yung tanungan. “Anong ganito, ganito?” Yung parang question and answer portion. Dun ako umiiwas (E60).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ayoko lang yung maguguluhan ako na mag-iisip ako ng matagal. Kaya gusto ko sabay-sabay lang tayo mag-aral, at mas gusto ko tahimik lang. Tahimik ako magreview, pero may mga kasama ako (E61).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>Q Oo, kung baga individual; kung magbabasa ka, individual, pero kung magtatanungan kayo, okay kayo-kayo lang, pero huwag niyo ako isali kasi parang naguguluhan ako eh, like “ano nga ba yun?” So nag-iisip ako ng matagal. Tanungin mo’ko after ko sigurong magreview, o kaya after kong mag-ano... (E62).</p> <p>Q Oo, that time kasi nagsisimula na nun. Naisip ko na kaya ko na rin siguro magreview mag-isa, nagsisimula na’ko magbasa-basa nun (E119).</p> <p>Q Nagkarun kasi ako ng study habits di ba? That time kasi, tuloy-tuloy naman ang aral kaya hindi rin ako nahirapan mag-cope (E124).</p> <p>Q Eh nasanay nga yung katawan ko nun... (E328).</p> <p>Q Kasi ikaw nag-aral mag-isa mo, kasi ninanamnam mo yung nirereview mo kasi nga ikaw lang mag-isa. Wala kang naging katulong sa pag-aaral mo na yun. So hanggang ngayon, siguro patanungan na lang, siguro kahit papano makakasagot ka compared dun sa may mga nakita silang mga examples. Ikaw, siguro kakayanin mong iexplain yun kasi nga naaral mo siya individually, yung bawat details kasi nga iniimagine mo mag-isa nung nag-aaral ka. Hindi pinaiimagine sa’yo ng iba, kundi ikaw yung nag-iimagine mag-isa (E346).</p>
Mr. NurseR	<p>Q ...parang ano ahh yung tipong nerd (R18).</p> <p>Q Ahh ano parang gusto ko ako lang gagawa ng trabaho ko mag-isa (R21).</p> <p>Q Mas gusto ko nagtatrabaho ng independent. Yung parang pwede ako maging teamplayer, pero mas madali akong magtrabaho pag hinayaan mo akong mag isa; parang mas focus ako (R22).</p> <p>Q Grade 5 (nag-umpisa) (R23).</p> <p>Q Mag-isa akong nagbabasa, pero yung babasahin ko yung simpleng explanation. Ayoko ng masyadong, yung sobrang detalyado (R97).</p> <p>Q Alone, alone talaga (R99).</p> <p>Q Question: Kung may option kang dalawa, kung may option ka let’s say, pwede kang mag-isa o pwede kang may kasamang tasks yung may kahalubilo sa iba... Answer: Mag-isa (R100).</p> <p>Q Mas makakapag concentrate ako (R102).</p> <p>Q ...Inisip ko, mag-aaral na lang ako mag-isa, ganun din naman yung matutunan ko (R107).</p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo ganun talaga ako eh, kaya nga gusto ko mag-isa kasi kailangan focus talaga ako, hindi ako multi task, kaya kung ano yung ginagawa ko focus lang talaga ako (R149).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Oo, yun kasi nga nakakapagfocus ako nung nag-aaral ako mag-isa (E313).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yun nga parang hindi ko nakikita yung punto ng pumasok ako dun sa review center kahit na ano, kahit na may pera ako, mas matututo ako kung sinundan ko ang sarili kong style ganun (R323).</i></p>
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Ay mag-isa lang ako. Alin yung halimbawa yung magrereview ako ng exam ganun? Mag-isa lang (B79).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Mas more ako dun sa ano work alone, pero I can work in groups din naman. Mas preferred ko lang talaga yung mag-isa (B82).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Actually, I like doing things alone, mag-isa lang ako kasi parang mas nakakapag-concentrate ako eh wala akong napagkokomperahan, or walang nagdidirect sa akin, mas gusto ko ito (N43).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Hayon, before nga soloista ako. Mas gusto ko na mag-isa ako, kasi wala kang iintindihin. Yung "ah sige ako lang". Yung time management nasa sa'yo talaga. Yung wala kang iintayin (G37).</i></p>

✓ Lower Expectation:

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>...Ayokong umasa sila (R108)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Na papasa ako kagad (R109)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Medyo mababa yung expectations (laughs) (R112)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Hindi yung makapasa ako ng mataas na score, as in makapasa ka lang (R158).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ang ano ko, parang 80% papasa ako 20% babagsak ako, parang ganon 80-20 pero ang ano dun, pasa lang as in pasa lang talaga (R157)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>...may dahilan kung bakit nangyari yun. Hindi mo masasabi kung bakit malay mo bumagsak ka dahil kailangan mong matuto ka kung paano ano yung magdeal sa failure, ganun, parang di mo masasabi kung ano yung nangyari. Yung sa akin ha, hindi pwede yung tipong close-minded ka na papasa ako, papasa ako--- eh paano kung hindi? Eh di mas mabigat sa loob mo yun (R228).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	<p>☞ <i>Oo, satisfied ako kasi ang ano naman sa akin niyan, pumasa ako. Pumasa ako o hindi, hindi ko nga ini-expect na makakuha ng lagpas sa 80 eh. Yung parang factors na nag-influence na makapasa ako? ma-satisfy ako? ano yung, yun nga yung parang tipong kahit na nagreview ako, hindi ako yung 100% na umasa na papasa ako, nag-iwan ako ng room for doubt kahit konti if 20% na room for doubt (R309).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>☞ <i>Yung nanay ko ang sagot sa akin 'Bahala ka sa life mo. Kasi ikaw naman yan eh. Kung confident ka na makakapasa ka, okay lang. Hindi naman kami umaasa na with flying colors naman yung bibigay mo sa amin eh. Basta ang sa amin, makapasa ka (G60).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Okay naman kasi hindi ko naman ina-achieve eh. Kahit kami, lahat kami hindi nag a-achieve ng mataas. Ang sa amin, ang sa amin lang makapasa ka tapos ano mapakita mo na kinaya mo (G247).</i></p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>☞ <i>Parang hindi rin sila, hindi rin sila ganon ka nag e-expect parang kung baga kasi ang ano ko ang palabas kasi non parang try lang give it a shot (N106).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Ayun ganon nga rin tipong pag hindi ka papasa edi mag review-center ka na lang basta kung baga ang ano non, tiningting ko lang, testing ko lang (N107).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>☞ <i>Sabi ko nga kanina iyong examination noong 2009, mag-eexam ako para hindi pumasa. Mag-eexam ako para malaman kung paano ba, ano ba iyong ginagawa doon? Iyon lang paano ba ang sistema? (J74)</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Iyon lang, iyon lang ang inano ko yung parang target ko kaya ako nag-exam. Para atleast makita ko iyong grades ko alam ko na kung saan ko titirahin e parang ganoon. Parang gusto... parang iyong 2009 June evaluation ko sa sarili ko lang iyon (J75).</i></p>

✓ No review method can guarantee success:

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseR	<p>☞ <i>Ano parang, yung mga ano, yung mga kamag anak kong iba nagnursing din sila. Nagreview center sila, hindi naman lahat sila pumasa. Eh, magrereview center ako, wala naman akong maraming pera non. Inisip ko, mag-aaral na lang ako mag-isa, ganun din naman yung matutunan ko. Yung materials, hihiramin ko na lang. Yung manghihiram ako ng mga questionnaire ganyan, ako magsasagot mag-isa pero yung tipong review center parang di ko siya gustong gawin kasi magastos (R107).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

	☞ <i>Ang inisip ko naman kasi sa dinami-dami ng nagreview center hindi naman lahat papasa kaya hindi naman ibig sabihin mag review center ka papasa ka (R123).</i>
Ms. NurseK	☞ <i>Enrolling in a review center can be very expensive. Why put my parents the burden of additional expenses when there is no guarantee that I will pass if I enroll in a review center? In the end, it is me who will take the exam so I control my own destiny" (K5b).</i>

✓ Tradition in the making:

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseB	<p>☞ <i>Malaki, as in malaki talaga yong epekto kung baga, it runs in the family (B107).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Siguro isa yun sa mga pinagkakatiwalaan. Hindi, pano ko ba sasabihin? Kung baga confident ako sa sarili ko na makakaya ko yung board exam kasi yung mga kapatid ko nakaya din nila eh kung baga nagigauge ko naman yung sarili ko na kung baga naikukumpara ko naman yung sarili ko dun sa dalawa kong kapatid. Sabi ko, okay kaya ko ito, basta kailangan lang talaga may focus ako dun sa pag-rereview makakaya ko yun (B108).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sabi ko sa sarili ko, "okay din naman kasi yung since may 2 akong sisters kasi diba? (B90).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Sila kasi hindi din nagreview center (B91).</i></p> <p>☞ <i>Yun dun sa hindi ako mag rereview-center? Ano kasi sa kanila din kung baga confident din sila na makakaya kong makapasa sa exam, sa board exam (B109).</i></p>

B.2 Common Themes among Participants' Personal and Educational Background

- ✓ Preference in constructive learning strategy over rote learning:

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	<p>Q Siguro ano. Kasi noong bata ako parang mahilig ako mag-imagine e. Mahilig akong mag-rationalize. Parang kaya kong i-rationalize ang isang bagay na napakaliit. Let's say ano...ako yung tao na isang bagay lang ang dami kong pupuntahan. Ang dami kong explanation (J106).</p> <p>Q Ang dami kong tanong sa kanya para mag-comeup ako sa anong kinasakit ng tiyan niya. Same ng pag-aaral ko, ganoon din ako parang I over rationalize small things na in the end maganda naman" (J108).</p> <p>Q Lahat ng possible question na related sa pananakit ng tiyan mo including time of sleep mo, anong kinain mo? Anong history mo? (J110).</p> <p>Q Oo. In the sense na mas naalala ko siya (J157).</p> <p>Q E ang kaso everyday ay meaningful day sa'kin e (J160).</p> <p>Q ...Biglang nag-po-pop up na lang sa utak na iyon kasi naaalala ko siya kasi nga nag-po-pop-up, naaalala kasi nakikinig ako e. Iyong pakikinig ko, talagang thorough listening talaga iyong ginagawa ko. Fault finder ako. Hindi ako sa tama. Tama na nga siya bakit mo pa iintindihin e. Fault finder ako sa lahat. Iyon yung tag sa'kin sa school. Fault finder, ako yung naghahanap ng mali. Pagnahanapan kita ng butas, doon kita titirahin. Ganoon iyong style ko. Hindi dahil...hindi dahil na...gusto kita ipahiya or whatsoever. Gusto ko i-defend mo iyong sarili mo kung bakit nasabi mo iyon. Ganoon iyong style ko" (J155).</p> <p>Q ...alam ko naman na heto na ako hindi ko na kaya sit down na lang pero before mangyari iyon, before ko malaman na iyon na lang ako ang dami ko ng tanong sa professor ko bakit ganoon. Parang wala akong libro tinatanong ko lang sa teacher ko. Katulad iyong appendicitis... (J121).</p>

<p>Ms. NurseG</p>	<p><i>Q Yung hindi ko sigurado naka mark. Naka mark talaga siya tas kasi diba ang kagandahan kasi pag may kasama kang mag-aral kunyari diba. Hindi naman maiwasan yon eh, natatandaan mo siya kasi may comeding nangyari. Pumapalo dun yung 'Ay naalala ko, ganito yung ginawa ni ganito nun ah'. Heto yung sagot non kasi nagpapatawa siya, may sinabi siyang hindi namin naintindihan, pumunta siya ng ganito. Pumapasok talaga yung ganon parang narerecall mo na may ginawa talagang palatandaan, may ginawang palatandaan (G156).</i></p>
<p>Mr. NurseR</p>	<p><i>Q Hindi ako pala-notes. Ang notes ko nun, kunyari Pathophysiology, yung magiging notes ko dun, diba yung process na mahaba--- paiikliin ko siya, yung mas madaling intindihin, ganon, isa-summarize ko siya, yung kunyari sa gilid ng libro may susulat akong ganito-ganyan. Kunyari may sinabing ganitong sakit I aa-underline ko tapos isusulat ko yung notes kung ano yung parang na search ko, nakikita ko kagad, nasa gilid. Ayoko kasi yung maghahanap pa ako sa notebook. Tsaka, hindi ako yung may babasahin ako magsusulat ako ganyan, o kaya may nag le-lecture nagsusulat ako ganyan then ma-istuck ako" (R148).</i></p> <p><i>Q Mahahirapan akong ipaliwanag yon hanggang sa hindi ko naiintindihan ano yung simpleng paliwanag" (R179).</i></p> <p><i>Q Oo kasi yung medyo visual ako pagkaganyan eh. Hindi ko lahat matatandaan yung sa listahan ganun, kailangan makita ko yung table sa utak ko. Yung comparison kung bakit mataas ito, mababa yung base niya, pagkamababa yung base niya, mataas yung ganito parang... (R280).</i></p> <p><i>Q Hindi ko kakabisaduhin yung pathophysiology niya. Mas gusto kong makita kung ano yung mangyayari, paano siya ginamot, kunyari, paanong treatment and ginawa sa kanya, bakit siya nagamot nung treatment na yon.. Ipapaliwanag sa akin, pero hindi ko kakabisaduhin yung buong pathophysiology pero mas gusto ko pinaliwanag ng mas simpleng paraan (R96).</i></p> <p><i>Q Kunyari kailangang makita ko siya sa context ng isang situation (R258).</i></p>

Mr. NurseN	<p>Q Because yung Anatomy yung... if you study Anatomy, you'll be amazed how your body works. Masasabi mo na rin talaga na may God na gumawa sa katawan ng tao kasi its perfectly designed para gumana, kaya paborito ko siya (N36).</p> <p>Q Oo may notes na ako, and then yun na rin ginawa ko na rin yung ano, yung nino-notes ko ini-style ko siya parang like na lesson plan parang dun sa mga kaklase ko kasi they ask talaga ng tulong (N168).</p> <p>Q Oo, kasi hindi ako matandain eh. Parang by process. Kung panong nagyayari 'to...hindi exactly kung ano nakalagay, I'll explain it to myself (N256).</p>
Ms. NurseL	<p>Q I always wanted to know how this disease works, how we can manage it and the steps we need to cure it" (L3).</p>

✓ Preference in solitary over outgoing activities

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseB	<p>Q Ayan, ako yung silent type malalaman mo naman din dib a yung sa activity natin, hindi ako masyadong matanong (B61).</p> <p>Q Ay mag-isa lang ako. Alin yung halimbawa yung magrereview ako ng exam ganun? Mag-isa lang (B79).</p> <p>Q Nagawa ko na, ano nga ba, actually wala akong iniisip na kung anong strategy basta kung ano yung maisip ako dun ako kung baga, walang particular na strategy akong pinipili or inaano basta just go with the flow, parang ganun (B71).</p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p>Q Kunwari sa pag-aaral, gusto ko ako lang mag-isa. Ayoko nang may kasama ako e. Mas focus ako pag-ako lang mag-isa (J33).</p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p>Q Yes I prefer to do things alone (MJ4).</p> <p>Q I love math coz I enjoyed computing or solving a math problem, I love trigonometry. I love science especially, biology and astronomy. I love to experiment and I love to discover the heavenly bodies.... Im sorry Sir Neri if I'm weird (MJ3).</p>
Mr. NurseN	<p>Q ...I like doing things alone, mag-isa lang ako kasi parang mas nakakapag-concentrate ako eh wala akong napagkokomperahan, or walang nagdidirect sa akin, mas gusto ko ito (N43).</p>
Ms. NurseK	<p>Q Before I would consider myself as a loner but as I grew older, I became more of a people person. I think it's because I have gained confidence in myself and my capabilities as opposed to my shy and meek demeanor in the past (K4).</p>
Ms. NurseE	<p>Q Siguro hati, kasi nga may gusto nga ako na palaaral na tao, yung kasabay ko sila na nag-aaral, pero ang ayoko lang kapag groupings na review, yung tanungan. "Anong ganito, ganito?" Yung parang question and answer portion. Dun ako umiiwas. Oo, kung baga individual; kung magbabasa ka, individual, pero kung magtatanungan kayo, okay kayo-kayo lang, pero huwag niyo ako isali kasi parang naguguluhan ako eh, like "ano nga ba yun?" So nag-iisip ako ng matagal. Tanungin mo'ko after ko sigurong magreview, o kaya after kong mag-ano... (E62).</p>
Ms. NurseG	<p>Q Hanggang sa pagdating ko ng third year, second sem. Parang ginusto ko ng may kajamming (G25).</p> <p>Q Kasi parang ano, nagbbrainstorming kami ng mga friends ko. Mas natatandaan ko (G26).</p>

✓ Strong academic background

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	<p><i>Q Ano naman eh consistent ako hanggang fourth year two point twenty-five (2.25) ako... yung GWA ko. So based sa mga tests namin, results namin although wala akong libro, wala ako mga ganun parang kaya ko parang ganun. Parang kaya ko 'to ganun lagi ako. Ayun (J18).</i></p> <p><i>Q Mayroon naman. Mayroon. Mayroon. Iyon nga during that time nasa top iyong pangalan ko e. Una top three ako, top five. Kungbaga... (J65).</i></p> <p><i>Q Siguro yung school namin kasi, pinasok sa utak namin na yung school ng PamantasanJ is a public school, na gobyerno nagpaparal sa'min, taxes ng tao sa Pasig. Tumatak sa amin na ganun. So kailangan namin pagbutihan. Saka maganda yung turo sa PamantasanJ. Yung strategy nila.</i></p> <p><i>Ah first.. First year ko one point seventy-five (1.75) yung GWA ko. So, dapat Dean's Lister ako 'nun eh. Pero mayroon akong isang as a...subject na tres (3.0) ako eh. Two point seventy-five (2.75) sa Math. I hate Math talaga kaya hindi ako nag-enjoy noon eh (J17).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMM	<p><i>Q I personally believed that I came from an institution with strong educational foundation (MM32).</i></p>
Mr. NurseMJ	<p><i>Q Before and after review: 8... my RLE experiences and studies is a good preparation for the exam (MJ37).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p><i>Tapos nung ah 3rd year na ako, lumipat na ako ng public, pero okay naman kasi di naman sa pagmamayabang, pero mula nung nag naggrade 1 ako hanggang second year high school , 1st honor ako (R42).</i></p> <p><i>Q Yung ano kasi dun sa Pamantasan, kahit na parang petics-petics lang yung pag-aaral, pero ano yun, kasi pagdating na nung talagang nursing proper na, 3rd year, 4th year, talagang ano na. Mag-aaral ka na talaga. Hindi kagaya nung 1st year, 2nd year petics-petics, nung 3rd year, 4th year mag-aaral ka na talaga. Ang ano niya kasi, malaki yung ineexpect sa iyo ng school na papasa ka. Kaya simula pa nung 3rd year, binubomba na kayo ng major-major (R300).</i></p>

Mr. NurseO	<p><i>Q Ahm ang pinaka pinagtuunan ko ng pansin yung mga subjects ng 3rd year and 4th year, yun nga yung mga pharmacology, med surgs, ahh phychiatric nursing kasi dun sa mga examination namin sa school more of analytical talaga so bihira lang yung definition of terms, it's more of in-analyze mo yung situations yon (O126).</i></p> <p><i>Q ...knowing na yung school namin is really one of the top schools in Manila yung bracket na lower bracket... (O55).</i></p> <p><i>Q And some of the same time may practice din sa yung as a whole yun ang pinaka standards of nursing practice, so yun I get to know the 2 faces of nursing field or nursing practice yung siyempre dito sa Pilipinas ahh kulang tayo sa kagamitan kulang tayo sa technologies so tinuturo din sa amin paano ka mag-a-adjust dun papano din kung walang ambubag anong gagamitin mo siyempre pwede ka ng mag paper bag na lang pag nag hyperventilate kapagka walang defibrilator anung pwede mong gawin? Siyempre at the same time kung meron ka nung mga gamit papanong magre-respond dun sa mga gamit na yon</i></p> <p><i>So let's say isang subject MS gaano mo siya katagal na inaral (O166)</i></p>
Ms. NurseK	<p><i>Q I believe that I did fairly well in my studies. During elementary, I was always part of the honor roll and in high school I graduated as valedictorian. In college, I also managed to become a semestral dean's lister. Also, I was active in extracurricular activities as I used to join quiz bees and was part of the school publication as editor-in-chief (K2).</i></p>
Ms. NurseL	<p><i>Q The duties from different hospital helped me be exposed to the real nursing world, I have no regrets choosing SchoolL for my college I think God led me there. For what purpose? I still dont know but im thankful that i went there. Proud to be a tangaraw :) haha as for the review, lahat naman may pros and cons e. Minsan yung teacher hidne marunong magturo, kaya you need to adjust (L32).</i></p>
Ms. NurseG	<p><i>Q Five kaming sections na ginanun ng 4-5 na professors namin. Kasi yung section namin, ¾ nun halos nasa DL (G54).</i></p> <p><i>Q Dean's Listers, kaya kilala kami (G55).</i></p>

B.3 Common Themes among Participants' Self-review Experience

✓ *Self-review is "tailor-fit" to the reviewee*

B.3.1.1 Self-paced: Six of the participants expressed self-review as self-paced.

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseJ	<i>Q ...hawak mo oras mo, hindi ka mappresure, kung ano yung irereview mo, may sarili kang timeline eh. Kung ano yung subject na irereview mo, masusunod, kung ano yung gusto mong ireview. Unlike kapag nagreview center ka, meron kayong particular subject for that day. Ayaw mo, o sa gusto mo kailangan mong matutunan. Unlike kapag nag-selfreview ka, may focus ka. May focus ka kung saan mo gusto magreview; kung saan mo dapat ienhance yung sarili mo. Tapos yun nga, hawak mo oras mo, less pressure ka, siguro, kasi nga mag-isa ka lang (J221).</i>
Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Q You can focus on (the) subject that you are not excelling (in)" (MJ13).</i>
Mr. NurseR	<i>Q Yun nga hawak ko yung sarili ko, na yung pace of learning ko, kung pano ako matuto, nasusunod ko. Kesa mag-review center ako, pagdating ng hapon wala na akong maintindihan niyan pagpasok ko sa classroom (R193).</i>
Ms. NurseE	<i>Q Atleast nakakapagpahinga ako. Ang alam ko gaya ng review center, tuloy-tuloy dun ang class 'di ba? Kung may break man sila, hindi ko alam. Sa self-review, kapag feeling pagod na ako, kapag feel ko overload na yung utak ko, makakapagpahinga ako (E147).</i>
Ms. NurseK	<i>Q I wanted to study at my own pace so self-review was very convenient for me. If I will get too tired, I can just sleep to refresh my mind for another day of learning. It is unlike review centers where there are times that one can't concentrate because of information overload (K5). Q You control your own destiny, creating study schedules and gathering study materials. If you slack off from studying, you have no one to blame but yourself (K10).</i>
Ms. NurseL	<i>Q Self review for me is an interesting experience. It saves time because I get to concentrate on the topics that I don't really know rather than going to a center that goes over all the topics. Plus I can adjust everything to fit my study schedule rather than adjusting to a review center's sched (L10).</i>

B.3.1.2 Accommodates individual differences

Participant	Responses
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Mr. NurseR	<p><i>Q Oo, hindi naman ako... iba-iba naman tayo ng learning style eh. Baka mag review center ako, parang mangyari niyan, palagay ko ha, parang classroom setting diba? Parang mapupuwera kang matuto kung pano sila matuto sa klase. Hindi naman lahat matututo ng maayos ng ganun” (R195).</i></p> <p><i>Q Hindi ko alam. Ang ano ko kasi, siguro dahil mas naretain ko yung pinag-aralan ko, dahil hindi ako na pressure. Mas na retain ko yung style ko, paano ako sumagot, nagging komportable ako kung paano ako sumagot nung multiple answer. Kumportable na akong sumagot talaga yung multiple choice na questions kesa sa identification (R200).</i></p> <p><i>Q Yung sa review center kasi, parang nag-aral ka talaga eh, parang nag-eskuwelahan ka talaga, may curriculum sila diba tapos yung... hindi ko alam, kasi hindi nga ako nag review center eh... yung mga iba pang seminar, ilang araw silang nandito sa etong system. Sa akin di ko masabi kung maiintindihan ko yung ganon kabilis na turo. Lahat ng kailangan kong pag-aralan don sa system na yun. Kunyari mahirap, sabihin mo na Psyche (Psychiatric nursing) sa dalawang araw hindi ko maano lahat yun, tsaka yung buong araw kang nag-aaral, nandun ka sa isang lugar na ano, yung classroom, hindi ko gusto yung parang pagod ka na nag-aaral ka pa, ang gusto ko yung nakakapag unwind ako (R136).</i></p>
Ms. NurseK	<p><i>Q Effective for those with a study habit like mine (K15).</i></p> <p><i>Q I usually studied around afternoon to evening since I am not a morning person” (K26).</i></p>

B.3.1.3 Flexible

Participant	Responses
Ms. NurseG	<p><i>Q Yung advantages, kasi nga ayon konti kayo. Pag meron kang hindi maintindihan may magtuturo sayo tas buddy, nagiging buddy-buddy kayo. Yun yung advantages non tapos flexible yung time, halos parang pwedeng maging flexible yung time depende sa inyo, kunyari kung gusto ninyo wala kayong pasok ng Wednesday papalitan ninyo ng Saturday. Hindi kagaya ng review center, fixed diba hindi pwedeng, ‘hay pag absent ka nito. Pag review center one day lang yung topic, hindi pwedeng magrepeat. Sa amin, may repeat, nire-repeat (G118).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseK	<i>Q Yes, I recommend self-review as it is very budget-friendly and convenient. Besides, reviewing is just a culmination of our four years in school. No review center can pack four years of knowledge in a few weeks so the main advantage of self-review is that you can have the flexibility to focus more on your weak areas (K17).</i>
Mr. NurseN	<i>Q ...pag graduate ko ng March may mga kaklase akong hindi grumaduate may binagsak na test yun yung review, review eh nandun yung basta hindi sila pumasa don so nung nag bo-board exam na ako since nag-aral ako sa sarili ko ang ginagawa ko para matandaan ko ako yung nag le-lecture sa kanila ako yung...(N113)</i>

✓ Self review is “unaided”

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseB	<i>Q ...maaring may mga materials ka na ma miss or mga tips or na pwede mong makuhanan ng strategy or something kung self-review ka lang, kasi pag sa review center marami kang makukuhanan ng tips, mga testing strategies ganyan, pag self review syempre di mo magagaw yon pero nandyan naman yung internet diba, diba now a days diba? (B152).</i>
Mr. NurseN	<i>Q Oo parang kailangan mo pang... parang kulang pa, kulang or hindi ko alam yan, hindi ko alam yan, parang ganon, parang ganon, kaya challenging” (N83).</i>
Mr. NurseO	<i>Q Ahh siyempre challenges ahh wala akong sariling syllabus or pattern kung ano yung lalabas sa exam its really more on feelings ko na lang kung ano yung lalabas na ahh baka ito, baka ito ganon yung challenges kasi hindi ko alam point black talaga siya hindi ko alam kung ano yung I fa-follow kong steps basta ako ang ginawa ko nagsimula ako basics hanggang dun sa so nagsimula ako ng first year kung ano meron sa first year Anatomy, Physiology then Fundamentals (O98). Q Siguro ako satisfied ako in a way na I passed pero siguro naisip ko I can do better kung tama lang yung way ng pagrereview ko kung may mga ganitong research parang maibibigay sa mga nurses or future nurses ng guide para makapag self review siguro kung may ganitong research noon pa may guide ako mas mataas yung nakuha kong grade imbes na 76 siguro mga 80 ganyan kasi yung score ko na 76 is almost failing na din yun diba (O186).</i>
Mr. NurseMM	<i>Q It was very challenging in terms of time management and resources because I had a job (MM10),”</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseK	<p><i>Q Distractions such as TV, internet</i> <i>No tips from review centers</i> <i>Can be boring for some people (K16)</i></p>
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✓ *Self-review helps increase sense of self-efficacy*

Participant	Responses
Mr. NurseB	<p><i>Q ... kung baga parang I can deal ... with anything, siguro 'pag may dumating na isang bagay na mahirap or ano kung baga madali kong... I can find ways na ma accomplish ko yung isang bagay or malampasan ko yung isang bagay na na darating, 'yon (B162)</i> <i>Q Kasi nga since yung local board (exam) kasi in-aadopt na rin nila yung NCLEX, so parang ganun na rin yung ginawa ko, saka yun nga, kung baga kung ano rin yung naging naimpart sa akin nung 2 kong kapatid, kasi parehas din silang pasado ng NCLEX eh, kaya yun na rin ang in-apply ko sa ano nag review ako for NCLEX (B230).</i></p>
Mr. NurseR	<p><i>Q Ayun parang ano ahh naging handa ako parang ano yung prenepare ako para maging independent, pano ako gagawa ng trabaho mo ganun yung pano mo kunyari may isang challenge kunyari sa trabaho may isang project kang kailangang gawin yung sa ginawa ko dun kung paano ako magtrabaho ng maayos, napatunayan ko na kaya kong gawin yung isang bagay kung talagang pag aanohan ko talaga (R319).</i> <i>Q As an individual, parang ano kaya ko pala, ganon yung hindi ko kailangang umasa sa iba na tulongan ako. Sa sarili kong paraan, makakaya ko. Yun ang ano ko, parang yung makakatulong siya sa independence, yung feeling mo na independent ka (R209).</i></p>
Mr. NurseJ	<p><i>Q Syempre, umangat yung pride ko, yung self-esteem, umangat pa lalo, lahat yun. Kasi feeling ko, kung nagawa 'ko to sa sarili ko, sa iba nahihirapan sila, hirap na hirap sila, ako nakaya ko isa lang, tapos limited resources pa ako, limited time...Sa ibang bagay siguro kaya ko ring gawin. Kagaya yun nga, nagtrabaho ako sa bangko, wala akong ka-alam-alam, pero dahil nga sa naging lifestyle ko na 'kaya 'ko 'to', nagtiwala ako sa sarili ko, kaya ko. Ganun din sa pag-aaral ko, ganun din nung nagtake ako ng review, tiwala lang sa sarili. Pero syempre, meron kang back-up dapat, na knowledge kahit papano (J235).</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Ms. NurseO	<i>Q Na boost lahat psychologically kasi I proved them wrong ahh kaya ko kaya ko pala; mentally I prove na kaya din ng utak ko kaya ko as a person, and emotionally siyempre I proved to my parents na tama yung naging decision nila na pagtiwalaan ako lahat talaga siya nag improve na boost talaga siguro that's also the result of what I am right now I mean confident ako, lumakas yung loob tumapang parang ganon (O193).</i>
Ms. NurseL	<i>Q Self review gave me the determination and the confidence to know that anything is possible if you just do the work and believe in God. As a nurse (since I was just a student back then) this review made me realize that we are on the verge of being professionals who are about to take care of people's lives so I know that I had to take it seriously (L21).</i>
Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Q I proved to myself that I can do anything without the help of others" (MJ15).</i>
Ms. NurseK	<i>Q The knowledge gained in my self-review was enriching as I also get to focus on topics that were not taught in school. Also, it gave me the confidence that I can do whatever tasks given to me as long as I put my heart in it" (K18).</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

APPENDIX C

Letter of Request to the Institutional Head

St. Paul University Manila
680 Pedro Gil St, Malate, 1004, Manila, Philippi

Date

Dean's name

Address

Greetings!

I, the undersigned—a candidate for the degree of *Master of Arts in Nursing* (M.A.N.) at *SaintPaul University-Manila Graduate School*, am writing a thesis entitled ***“THE EXPERIENCES, REVIEW STRATEGIES, AND DEFINING TRAITS OF SUCCESSFUL SELF-REVIEWEES IN THE PHILIPPINE NURSES’ LICENSURE EXAMINATION (P.N.L.E.): A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY”*** As part of the pre-survey of respondents, I would like to seek your assistance by providing data of your school’s board passers who utilized *self-review* in hurdling their licensure exam (in the period 2007 to 2012).

Since your school is considered one of the *Top Performing Schools* in nursing education, I believe that your alumni/alumnae can adequately provide vital information in my study, of which you will be given the final output. Rest assured that their participation in this study is voluntary and that all information will be kept *confidential*. As a self-reviewee board-passer myself, I hope that this study can crystallize student nurses’ experiences in pursuing a demanding yet cherished profession.

My sincerest appreciation for your valuable concern.

Truly yours,

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Nerison M. Ocampo, R.N.
M.A.N. Student

Noted by:

Prof. Gerardo L. Guiuan, Ed.D.
Thesis Adviser

APPENDIX C
The Survey Questionnaire/Interview Guide

Dear Case Participant:

The following interview guide/questionnaire was designed to capture the essence of the study. Please answer them as **honest, specific** and **thorough** as you can. The goal of this thesis is to make a "*Marks of a Self-reviewee Board Passer*" which may be used as a guide of prospective self-reviewees---that they may learn from those very few who utilized self-review in passing the licensure exam. Thus, the output of this thesis is only as good as your valuable inputs, and the achievement of its intention is only as useful as your contribution. However, should you find a question to be irrelevant, or inapplicable, feel free to skip.

I appreciate your time.

THANKS FOR ALL YOU DO.

Truly yours,

Neri Ocampo, RN
Researcher

Demographics & Educational Background:

As a primer, the researcher would like to understand the person that is in you. Specifically, the researcher would like to understand your *social* and *educational background* that may have influenced, at any rate, your decision to self-review.

Name/nickname (optional):

Year (month) PNLE was taken:

Age (optional):

Licensure Rating:

Year of BSN graduation:

School:

BSN:

Current Occupation:

Any other previous employment (if any)

How long?

Briefly narrate who you are as a person. If possible, kindly tell us a little more about your upbringing, your main beliefs about life and education, or anything that you value as a person, and the story why you took up nursing.

Overall, how did you fair in your studies? What was your class standing during school years (in elementary, high school and/or in college)? What was your class like?

If there were anything, what were (was) your favorite subject/s back then, & why?

Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone?

As regards your “experiences” with self-review

What were the factors/reasons that influenced you to decide to take self-review? (i.e. possible personal reasons, individuals and/or situations that might have influenced you)

Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school? Or were you required to attend the review center? If there was, how did you go about it? (If yes, please explain what happened)

When did you decide to take self-review (way before graduation? Immediately before graduation, or after graduation?)

How did your parents/family members/friends (or classmates) react to your decision to do self-review? Please specify.

Did you have any family member/close friends who took the same path (method of review) like you? How did it affect you, if any?

What is it like to self-review (overall description of your review experience)?

Can you share your experience on the challenges/issues, if there were any that you faced before your review? What about during the review? How did you cope and deal with those issues/challenges? (Please answer below)

Pre-Review	Intra-Review
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ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

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Were you, at any point during the course of the review, tempted to quit self-review and just wanted to enroll to a review-center instead?

How did you feel about the outcome of your review? Were you dis/satisfied?

What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?

Advantages <i>(Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)</i>	Disadvantages <i>(Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)</i>
-	-

Will you recommend self-review to others? Why, or why not?

What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you as an individual and/or as a nurse?

What was the reception/reaction, if there was any, of the people around you when you passed the licensure examination (family, academe, friends, etc)?

If you can describe your overall experience in a sentence, what would it be? Is there anything else that you would like to add or share about your review experience? Optional.

To unfold the “Strategies” of the Self-reviewees

How did you do it that made it effective for you?

Did you have doubts/ issues in failing the exam? How did you deal with it?

Did someone (or individuals, groups) help you throughout the review? ___ If yes, in what way?

Did you seek advice from others or you just relied solely on your own? ___ If yes, what information/advice did you receive?

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

How did you deal with time constraints (the duration between the Time after graduation until you finally took the exam)/how did you manage your time?

What were your strategies in terms of:

-Study habits (time of the day, and why?)

-Venue where you usually study at (do you stay at one place, or different places? Did you seclude yourself, or you did it with a group, and why did you do it in such way?)___ Why? ___

-What review materials did you acquire? Where did you get those review materials from?

<i>Subject Area</i>	<i>Book/Review Material/s Used</i>	<i>Specific Strategies/Pointers you focused more on (Please list down as much as you can)</i>	<i>Comment/s (if any)</i>
<i>I. Fundamentals of Nursing including Professional Adjustment</i> <i>-Legal</i> <i>-Research</i> <i>-Ethico-Moral</i>			
<i>II. Maternal and Child Health Nursing</i>			
<i>III. Community Health and Communicable Disease Nursing</i>			
<i>IV. Nursing of Adolescents, Adults and Aged</i>			

V. Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing			
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Had there been any issues where to get the review materials from? Did you think what you initially had were sufficient to cover all the topics in nursing? If not, what did you do about it?)

Specifically, how did you organize the review (what did you study first & why did you do it in such way? Was there any specific reason/s, or none?)

-How did you go through with the bulk of topics? Did you study each topic in detail or you just browsed everything?

-Did you have relaxation moments/techniques in between or while reviewing? Please specify.

-Did you receive any help from your school? Please specify.

How well did your educational program(s) had prepared you to pass the Licensure exam, and what, (did you identify strengths or any inadequacies in your education?)

Were you confident that you can make it? (In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what were your subjective take on your confidence level before the review? After finishing the review?) Please explain your answer...

In your perspective, how does one should do self-review to be effective?

If any, what tip/s can you give to licensure exam takers during the actual board exam? Please specify.

Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE? If yes, what factor/s do you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to identify the reasons/factors that might have caused it? If yes, what are they?

Did you learn something from it? Was there anything you could've done that you think must've helped you more in your review? If there were any, what were they?

Is there anything you want to add or say about self-review as a whole?

To unfold the defining "Traits" of the reviewees

If there were any, what do you think were the important quality/-ies you possessed that made you pass the exam? How did it (they) help you pass? (Please specify...)

What do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective?

Did you have any regrets that you chose to do self-study instead of enrolling in a review center? (Please specify...)

How did it affect you psychologically, mentally, and emotionally?

APPENDIX E Sample Informed Consent

This informed Consent form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share the information about the study with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you chose to participate)

Part I: INFORMATION SHEET

Introduction

I am **Nerison M. Ocampo, RN**. I am aware that we're all busy these days but I am hoping that you will give me some minutes of your time. I am currently doing a research on the traits, experiences, and strategies of *successful* self-reviewees in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (PNLE). I am pleased to give you information and invite you to be a part of this research. You do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate in this research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research.

Also, this consent form may contain words that you may not understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask them of me.

Purpose of the Research

This thesis began with a simple question: amid the overwhelming risks of failure in the nursing licensure examination, *could "self-review" be effective enough to make a Graduate Nurse pass the Philippine Nursing Licensure Exam (PNLE)?* The researcher, being a *self-reviewee* board passer himself, believed the answer was 'yes.' But to many minds, a collateral question remains: *how can it be done successfully?* In other words, this preliminary question springs towards a creation of a guide—a *review guide* that can be used by Graduate Nurses who, like the researcher himself, will dare to utilize self-review as a method of conditioning or preparing him/her towards passing the nursing licensure examination.

The creation of a document that embodies the "Marks of a Successful Self-reviewee" from the words and experiences of individuals who successfully did it—a guide capable of giving a valid and valuable insights, some ideas, tips, and a sort of prescription and guide to light the ways of Graduate Nurses throughout the course of the self-review regimen is the solemn purpose of this thesis.

Types of Research Intervention

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA (St. Paul University System)

This research will involve your participation in one-on-one or face to face interview that will take about one and half hour. Additional questions may be completed through other form of communication like email, or follow up visits.

Participant Selection

Taking the licensure examination is full of risks and uncertainties, and these days we can seldom find people who used self-review in preparation for this end-point exam. It is indeed a great chance to know nurses like you who dared to risk failure and did not enroll in a review center. You are being invited to take part in this research because we feel that your experience and the accompanying strategies, if there were any, can contribute much to our understanding and knowledge of self-review as a method of licensure exam preparation. It is hoped that your contribution will give other benefactors some clues, some ideas, for them to adapt those worth adapting and, from them, possibly innovate something better and bring a meaningful and a wonderful twist in the way licensure exam review is being conducted.

Voluntary Participation

Your Participation in this research is entirely **voluntary**. It is your choice whether to participate or not. The choice that you make will in no way be taken against you, or your status as a nurse. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

Procedures

The researcher invites you to help him learn about the traits, experiences, and strategies employed of successful self-reviewees in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (PNLE). He is inviting you to take part in this research project. If you find it acceptable, you will be asked to participate in an interview with myself.

During the interview, I will sit down with you in a comfortable place at your preferred venue. If it is better for you, the interview can take place at your home or a friend's home or any other place you'll find convenient. If you do not wish to answer any of the questions during the interview, you may say so and I will move on to the next question. No one else but me will be present unless you would like someone else to be there. The information recorded is *confidential*, and no one else except me will have access to the information documented during the interview. The entire interview will be taped recorded, but no one will be identified by name on the tape. The tape will be kept in a safe storage area. The tapes/recorded information will be destroyed after more or less 20 weeks.

Duration

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA (St. Paul University System)

The research will take place over two months in total duration. During that time, the researcher may visit you or send an email to follow up or clarify on certain information.

Risks

There is no known risk associated with this research. The researcher, however, may ask you to share some information that you may consider very personal and confidential, and you may feel uncomfortable talking about some of the topics. You do not have to answer any question or take part in the interview if you don't wish to do so, and that is also fine. You do not have to give him any reason for not responding to any question, or for refusing to take part in the interview

Benefits

There will be no direct benefit to you, but your participation is likely to help us, and those that may find this research useful, find out more about the success stories of self-reviews, from the universe of those who successfully did it, so others may learn from them.

Reimbursements

You will not be provided any incentive to take part in the research. However, the researcher will give you a token or simple gift for your valuable time, and/or travel expense.

Confidentiality

The research being done in may draw attention from those who know you and if you participate you may be asked questions by other people in your area. The researcher will not be sharing information about you to anyone outside of the research team/panel/thesis adviser. The information that he will collect from this research project will be kept private. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the researcher will know what number is and he will lock that information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except me and his thesis adviser.

Sharing the Truth

Nothing that you tell will be shared with anybody outside of the research team, and nothing will be attributed to you by name. The knowledge that we get from this research will be shared with you before it is made widely available to the public. Each participant will receive a summary of the results. Following the meetings, he will publish the results so that the other interested people may learn from the research.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so, and choosing to participate will not affect you in any way. You may stop participating in the interview at any time that you wish. I will give you an opportunity at the end of the interview to review your remarks, and you can ask to modify or remove portions of those, if you do not agree with my notes or if I did not understand you correctly.

Who to contact

If you have any questions, you can ask them now or later. If you wish to ask questions later, feel free to contact any of the following: **Nerison "Neri" Ocampo**, 09214024604 and or the_untamed_mind@yahoo.com.

Part II. CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT

I have been invited to participate in research about the traits, experiences, and strategies of *successful* self-reviewees in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (PNLE).

(This section is mandatory)

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent *voluntarily* to be a participant in this study

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: _____

Day/Month/Year

Statement by the researcher/ person taking consent

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands that the following will be done:

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this ICF has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of Researcher: _____

Signature of Researcher/ Person taking the consent: _____

Date: _____

Gerardo L. Guiuan, Ed.D.
Thesis Adviser

APPENDIX F

Interview Transcripts and Survey Questionnaires' Answers

Mr. NurseR

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Good evening. My name is Neri Ocampo from St. Paul Manila. I'm currently researching a topic about self-review. I will be interviewing you about your experiences with self-review. Mainly, there are 4 parts of this interview: first one is about your demographics and your educational background; second is about your experiences during your self-review and then 3rd is about the strategies, kung meron ka man, and lastly about your traits, if there is any, kung may naidentify kang traits that helped you during your review. To start off, my 1st question is if you can tell me your name or nickname...</i>
1	Mr. NurseR	<i>Buong pangalan?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw nickname, kung okay lang, hindi naman yun eh.</i>
2	Mr. NurseR	Mr. NurseR
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How old are you right now? Optional lang naman din</i>
3	Mr. NurseR	25
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you graduate from BSN?</i>
4	Mr. NurseR	2008
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was it your first course or second course?</i>
5	Mr. NurseR	First course.
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What is your current occupation?</i>
6	Mr. NurseR	Health Care Associate.
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any previous employment prior to that?</i>
7	Mr. NurseR	Of course
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What were they? If any.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

8	Mr. NurseR	<i>Billing and collections agent, technical support, and Senior Care Assistant.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Senior Care Assistant, gaano ka katagal don?</i>
9	Mr. NurseR	<i>2 ½ years</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 ½ years for those jobs?</i>
10	Mr. NurseR	<i>2 ½ year as Senior Care Assistant, for 9 months for billing and collections, 4 months as technical support.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Alam ko nagpunta ka rin ng U.K. (United Kingdom) diba?</i>
11	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga Senior Care</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Senior Care</i>
12	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, Senior Care</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Related sa nursing?</i>
13	Mr. NurseR	<i>Geriatric care.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ok, Senior...when did you take your nursing license exam?</i>
14	Mr. NurseR	<i>2008</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2008 ahh</i>
15	Mr. NurseR	<i>June</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>June 2008. Yung licensure rating mo, optional lang. Yung first option 75 to 79 or 80 and above.</i>
16	Mr. NurseR	<i>80 and above</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung school mo private or public?</i>
17	Mr. NurseR	<i>Public</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Second portion of demographics and educational background is about you. Ahh if you can tell me briefly about who you are as person, a little more about your upbringing. Your main beliefs about your life, about education, or anything you value as a person, and yung lastly why did you take nursing... what was the reason?</i>
18	Mr. NurseR	<i>Simpleng lumaki lang sa subdivision, pero di naman kami mayaman, tama lang panggitna lang tapos yung parang ano ahh yung tipong nerd.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nerd?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

19	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, yung laging nasa loob ng bahay, naglalaro ng computer kasi...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Panong nerd? Maliban sa naglalaro ng computer, yung thinking mo paanong ano?</i>
20	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung thinking?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
21	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ahh ano parang gusto ko ako lang gagawa ng trabaho ko mag-isa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mag-isa</i>
22	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mas gusto ko nagtatrabaho ng independent. Yung parang pwede ako maging teamplayer, pero mas madali akong magtrabaho pag hinayaan mo akong mag isa; parang mas focus ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan nag umpisa yun? Mga ilang taon ka? Yung ganong...</i>
23	Mr. NurseR	<i>Grade 5</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Grade 5... palabasa ka?</i>
24	Mr. NurseR	<i>Palabasa talaga ako, ano ako dati, nagsasara na yung library sa school nandun pa ako; naglilipit na yung librarian nandun pa ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano anong mga bagay ang binabasa mo? Anong mga materials?</i>
25	Mr. NurseR	<i>Science, History.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit mo nahiligan yun?</i>
26	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala, ano ko lang, interesante lang kasi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paanong interesante?</i>
27	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun na talaga ang ano ko, kasi kunyari history, parang paborito kong topic dati history.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>History</i>
28	Mr. NurseR	<i>History...world history o kaya science.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong specific sa history yung nagustuhan mo?</i>
29	Mr. NurseR	<i>Gera</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gera, yung mga gera...nung elementary ganon hanggang high school?</i>
30	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, hanggang college.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hanggang college? mahilig ka pa rin sa history?</i>
31	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maski nag nanursing ka na?</i>
32	Mr. NurseR	<i>Maski nag nanursing ako. Siguro kung hindi ako nag ano ang...yung Nursing kasi, parang ano lang yan eh, yung napilitan lang, napilitan lang ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay.</i>
33	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun yung tanong mo, kasi napilitan lang ako yung lola ko lahat ng kapatid niyang babae nurse, tiyahin ko, tiyuhin ko nurse, yung tiyahin ko sa father side ko administrador ng hospital, yung mga kapatid ng lola ko na lalaki lahat doctor. Parang puro medical (field) nandun sila lahat sa Amerika. Sabi sumunod ka dito, so nagnursing ako, eh kaso nung nagnursing ako, di na kumukuha ng nurse sa Amerika.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, pero ano talaga yung gusto mo?</i>
34	Mr. NurseR	<i>Journalism</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Journalism? Bakit mo nagustuhan yung Journalism?</i>
35	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kasi nagsusulat ako dati sa ano, yung ano investigative journalism parang ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan ka nasali nun?</i>
36	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nagsusulat ako dati sa school paper.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh sa School paper.</i>
37	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo pero nung nag college ako di na gaano kasi busy busihan na eh, pero nung high school ako mas active ako sa school paper yun ang extracurricular activity ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Going back to what you like, yung subjects like Science and History</i>
38	Mr. NurseR	<i>Parang yun ang gusto kong sinusulat kasi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun ang gusto mong sinusulat? Maski nung yung journalism na sinasabi mo sa school paper? Ano bang ano mo dun, yung position mo dun?</i>
39	Mr. NurseR	<i>Feature editor</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Feature editor</i>
40	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, pero nung ano kasi, parang pasingit-singit lang nung una, history parang ganito ganyan, yung mga may school occasion,</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>idescribe mo yung... yung simpleng ganun lang. Bakit nangyari ito, ganun mga feature, science feature, ganun. Madali lang naman, pero yun talaga ang hilig ko pagsulat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, when it comes to education, kamusta yung pag-aaral mo nung elementary, high school?</i>
41	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo naman yung elementary at high school hanggang second year high school ako private.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh...</i>
42	Mr. NurseR	<i>Tapos nung ah 3rd year na ako, lumipat na ako ng public, pero okay naman kasi di naman sa pagmamayabang, pero mula nung nag naggrade 1 ako hanggang second year high school, 1st honor ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>
43	Mr. NurseR	<i>Tapos 1st honor, 2nd honor di lumalayo tapos nung nag public ako nasa section 1 parin ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong nangyari nung nagpublic ka at bumaba yung ano mo?</i>
44	Mr. NurseR	<i>Naimpluwensiyahan (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay okay, kapag nasa public ganon talaga...Yung pag aaral mo ng college nung mag-umpisa ka na, kamusta naman? 1st year, 2nd year, lower years...</i>
45	Mr. NurseR	<i>Lower years okay naman, kaso parang ano eh, parang... yung... naninibago ako kasi may mga ibang subjects non siyempre kailangan pag aralan mo, eh yung gawain ko pa naman nung High School, nung nasanay ako nung public papetics, walang aral-aral, walang-aral aral pagka yung tipong periodical exam, dasal-dasal ng unti kunyari, eh nung college ako, tipong Chemistry, Biochemistry sakit sa ulo, Algebra yung first year Algebra ayokong-ayoko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Parang di mo gusto yung Science gusto mo yung Math.</i>
46	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, ayoko nung Math</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ayaw mo ng Math</i>
47	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun talaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gusto mo ng Science</i>
48	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo yung science okay lang mapag aaralan, yung Chemistry, Biochemistry, yung Physics pinagtitiyagaan ko lang yun pag-aralan, yung Physics nga lang talaga maraming Math, pero yung tipong Algebra yun ang di ko maintindihan.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga Trigo (Trigonometry) ganun</i>
49	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala akong Trigo(Trigonometry) nung ano eh..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh wala kang Trigo(Trigonometry).</i>
50	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala akong Trigo, hanggang College Algebra lang kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May block section ba kayo nung college? Oh paano ba set up don?</i>
51	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo block section, section 1, 2, 3</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1, 2, 3.</i>
52	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ako section 1, section 2, tapos section 3 yung mga sabi nila medyo mahina pero maraming matatalino sa section 3, yung nagmagna cum laude nursing, ang alam ko, galing section 3 dati. Section 1 sabi lang nila magaling, pero hindi naman talagang parang section 1 ng high school na lahat nahandon. Halo-halo din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, kamusta na yung class standing mo non?</i>
53	Mr. NurseR	<i>Class standing? Wala ako ranking nun, hindi yung sa mga top, nag top ganun. Nagdean's lister ako, isang sem. Sinuwerte lang (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung college ka paano ba yung klase nyo? Anong set up ng klase nyo?</i>
54	Mr. NurseR	<i>Parang high-school din, yung sa Pamantasan kasi, hindi yung parang ibang college na ikaw yung pipili ng klase mo, parang high school talaga ang itsura niya. Parang punta ka dito, punta ka dito, punta ka ditto. Talagang may schedule talaga kayo; structured masyado yung 1st and 2nd year hindi katulad sa iba na parang pwede kang mamili kung ano ang uunahin mo na subject diba? Kung ano, yung kunyari, yung kukunin mong P.E. kunyari ayaw mo ng (electrical), iba yung kukunin mo, dun sa Pamantasan hindi pwede.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailangan yun talaga.</i>
55	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun talaga kukunin mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Parang yung curriculum nila?</i>
56	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo susundin mo talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero yung mismong klase kamusta may magagaling ba don, pano ba kayo nag-iinteract?</i>
57	Mr. NurseR	<i>Meron, marami. Kami tipong ano, nandun sa likod mga lalaki pagka-ano magugulo, ganyan pero yung mga ibang matatalino,</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>daw, nasa gitna, nasa harap ganyan. Sila yung lagging tinatawag. Pagka natutulog sa klase babatuhin kami sa likod! (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga? (exchanged smiles) ganun yung ano...</i>
58	Mr. NurseR	<i>Parang high school-bukol, pero hindi naman talaga kasi seyempre college eh, pero seryoso kunyari, pero hindi siya yung sobrang ano, yung sobrang aral aral aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, ahh sabi mo from elementary hanggang high school 1st honor ka diba?</i>
59	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hanggang 2nd year. Ano yung naging tingin mo nun nang nasa college ka na petics petics na kayo?</i>
60	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala lang, parang maluwag lang. Nasanay na kasi ako nung nasa high school ako, parang naging ganun din yung ano eh, petics petics din ako eh. Pero di din ako komportable kapag napepressure. Ayoko ng napepressure pag nag-aaral ako. Mas natututo ako pag Masaya yung klase.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, okay</i>
61	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong ano, kasi pag na pe pressure ako, hindi ko naiintindihan, parang magulo yung ano, magulo yung... hindi ko siya, hindi ko naabsorb ng matino.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa lahat ng mga subjects ng nursing, ano yung nagustuhan mo? kung meron man.</i>
62	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nursing subject, nursing major? Kasama ba RLE (Related Learning Experience) dun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, kasama lahat, lahat talaga kasama yung mga nasa curriculum.</i>
63	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ahh sige, management, nursing management. Yung sa 4th year, yung pang head nursing kasi yun talaga feeling ko nagtatrabaho ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Panong...</i>
64	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong ganyan maghead nursing ka diba? Yung pangmanagement na tinuturo, yung leadership styles ganon, yung nakalimutan ko na yung iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Leadership styles?</i>
65	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kunyari.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naging leader ka ba non?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

66	Mr. NurseR	<i>Leader-leaderan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh naging leader-leaderan ka din?</i>
67	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kasi ang ano namin dun, simula 3rd year ako, nung talagang nag ano na kami sa nursing, maraming binibigay sa aking trabaho, yung tipong ume extra extra ako dun sa opisina kaya maraming ina-assign na trabaho sa akin. Parang ako yung leader-leaderan sa amin, yung kaming mga lalaki. Yung may mga pinagmanahan sa section namin (laughs).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Parang ikaw yung nagiging pinuno.</i>
68	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, parang responsable sa kanila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Formal leader o</i>
69	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw yung tumatayong leader lang?</i>
70	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo ako yung tumatayong ano nila, kunyari hindi naman leader talaga. Kunwari, nagcommunity kami, sabi 'Oh ikaw yung responsible yan sa mga yan', parang ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban sa management, meron ka pa bang ibang nagustuhang subject? Kung meron man</i>
71	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung ano, yung med surgs (Medical-Surgical).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Medical-surgical?</i>
72	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, nagustuhan ko siya pero hindi ko siya naintindihan (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo siya naintindihan?</i>
73	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ko siya maintindihan, pero yung gusto ko talaga siyang aralin, naguguluhan lang talaga ako dun sa iba. Gusto ko talaga siyang pagtuunan ng pansin, kasi kung tutuusin interesante. Kasi mahilig ako sa Science e, interesanti yung mga ano niya, kasi yung tipong madugo na yung pinag aaralan parang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like for example, ano yung madugo dun?</i>
74	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong mga system by system na sakit. Kasi diba may nagpaphathophysiology din sa Med-surgs (Medical-Surgical) diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo.</i>
75	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kahit na may hiwalay na subject na patho..</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	Oo
76	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nagpapathophysiology pa rin siya sa Med Surgs. Kunyari tipong ano yung sa heart? yung systemic na circulation, ganon? Tapos, gulong-gulo ako dun pagka lalo na yung ano.. sa new born.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Oo mas komplikado nga yun.
77	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mas magulo yun, madami yun di ba may kung saan pa diba? Yung sa Patent Ductus Arteriosos. Ano yun, ang gulo yung mga tipong ganun kailangan mo talaga siyang pag aralan, yung pinag aralan ko siya parang lalong gumulo, yung mas lalo siyang mahirap intindihin. Hanggang sa may magpapaliwanag sa akin ng mas simpleng paraan, nahirapan akong intindihin siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ka ba mag aral? Papano mo ma eenjoy yung isang ano?</i>
78	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, pag nag aral lang talaga ako basa lang, pero yung mag aaral ako yung talagang focus na focus, makukuha ko siya pero yung tipong yung pag aaral ko nun na tulad ng college, maraming akong pinagkakaabalahan...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Oo
79	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong hindi ko siya, hindi ko siya nahaharap, kasi lalo kung pag aaralan ko, kunyari magulo 'to, kailangan may pagtatanungan ako. Kung di mapagtatanungan, eh noon kasi wala, wala pa kaming internet nun eh, hahanapin ko. Ngayon, kung may hindi ako maintindihan hinahanap ko sa internet kung may mas simpleng explanation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Ahh
80	Mr. NurseR	<i>Eh dati wala naman kaming internet sa bahay, yung libro lang ng med surgs (Medical-Surgical), ayun magulo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, gusto kong maintindihan yung sinasabi mo... Sabi mo mahilig ka sa Science, alin sa Science yung hilig mo?</i>
81	Mr. NurseR	Ano tipong..
Researcher:	Researcher	Anong subject sa Science?
82	Mr. NurseR	<i>Astronomy, ahh Geography ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Ahh mga ganon?
83	Mr. NurseR	Oo
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mga analytical like sa Physics o</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

84	Mr. NurseR	<i>Di gaano, Physics di gaano, kasi may Math yun eh. Pagka may Math ayoko nun eh (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Biology ganon?</i>
85	Mr. NurseR	<i>Biology, pero yung biology as in Biology na hindi yung Human Anatomy & Physiology, yung parteng Botany</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Botany</i>
86	Mr. NurseR	<i>Botany, zoology ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay okay, so kung irerelate mo yun sa mga subjects mo, saan ka mas makakarelate? Yung hilig mo ganung klase like Geography, Physics...</i>
87	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kung sa nursing subjects?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kumbaga, ano yung almost the same na nursing subject na mas nadadalian ka?</i>
88	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kung nursing subject?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In comparison with your basic Sciences, saan ka kung baga nadadalian na subject?</i>
89	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pagka sa nursing, yung nursing na talaga...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Diba yung sabi mo kanina, gusto mo yung management? Yung yung nadadalian ka.</i>
90	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung ano, ahh Pharma (Pharmacology).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pharma...</i>
91	Mr. NurseR	<i>Di ko lang siya gaanong naalala ngayon pero nung nag Pharma ako dati kasi yung Pharma yung parang may mga formula ng drug, hindi siya katulad ng Pathophysiology na maraming pwedeng mangyari. Ang Pharma kasi tuloy-tuloy yung nangyari sa kanyang ano diba? Yung kunyari binigay yung ganitong chemical, ang magiging action niya mag ti trigger siya ng ganitong mechanism. Kunyari pagka antibiotic sisirain niya yung cell wall ng bacteria, simpleng ganon lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh ano yung pinagkaiba ng Pathophysiology?</i>
92	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ang sa Pathophysiology kasi, parang naguguluhan ako pagka... mahaba kasi yung sa Pathophysiology.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung baga integrated?</i>
93	Mr. NurseR	<i>Maraming maaring pwedeng mangyari yun, yung tinitingnan ko. Yung Pharma kasi ganito lang yun eh. Yung Pathophysiology, sa</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>isang sakit marami yung pwedeng mangyari, masyadong maraming variables.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mas gusto mo yung memorization o gusto mo yung analysis?</i>
94	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ah, ayoko nung memorization.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung gusto mo?</i>
95	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mas gusto ko yung analysis. Yung tipong alam ko kung bakit nangyari ito, hindi ko na kailangang i-memorize basta alam ko kung ano yung mangyayari... ahh alam ko kung paano yung mechanism niya, kunyari ganon, ngayon yun ang gusto kong iniintindi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say isang disease, papano mo natatandaan yon?</i>
96	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ko kakabisaduhin yung pathophysiology niya. Mas gusto kong makita kung ano yung mangyayari, paano siya ginamot, kunyari, paanong treatment and ginawa sa kanya, bakit siya nagamot nung treatment na yon.. Ipapaliwanag sa akin, pero hindi ko kakabisaduhin yung buong pathophysiology pero mas gusto ko pinaliwanag ng mas simpleng paraan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gusto mo yung may nagpapaliwanag sayo, o yung mas prefer mo na mag-isa kang nagbabasa?</i>
97	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mag-isa akong nagbabasa, pero yung babasahin ko yung simpleng explanation. Ayoko ng masyadong, yung sobrang detalyado.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like for example, isang topic hindi mo naintindihan, nag research ka... papano</i>
98	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nung nag-aaral ako? Oo, maghahanap ako ng ibang libro. Maghahanap ako kasi isa lang yung Med-Surg na libro ko dati eh. Minsan ang ginagawa ko para maintindihan ko pupunta ako dun sa kaibigan ko, hihiram ko yung sa nursing na iba tapos babasahin ko yun, kunyari tulad sa yung sa yung sa Med-Surgs na burn di ko masyadong naintindihan. Yung hiniram kong libro parang tungkol sa burn unit, binasa ko yung paliwanag parang simple lang, mas naintindihan ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Next question, did you consider yourself as a people person or someone who prefers to do things alone?</i>
99	Mr. NurseR	<i>Alone, alone talaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung may option kang dalawa, kung may option ka let's say, pwede kang mag-isa o pwede kang may kasamang tasks yung may kahalubilo sa iba...</i>
100	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mag-isa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mag-isa</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

101	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo,</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit?</i>
102	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mas makakapag concentrate ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Binigyan ka ngayon ng task, grupo kayo, mas magiging effective ka ba kung mag-isa ka lang, tingin mo?</i>
103	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>In what instance, like situations, or instances that that happened? Ahh... anong nangyari? Kung meron man</i>
104	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kunyari nung college nag te-thesis kami eh yung isang buong grupo kami ganyan, yung walang nangyayari nung ginagawa namin yung thesis ng sabay-sabay. Ay hindi siya thesis, yung ano pangalan nun, yung community diagnosis?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>COPAR?</i>
105	Mr. NurseR	<i>COPAR, isang buong grupo kami, hindi naman sa hindi ko naintindihan magulo yung...walang nangyari dun sa discussion namin. Parang kasi ganito, maghati-hati tayo ng trabaho, ito gawin mo ito, gawin mo ito ganyan, tapos gagawin ko din yung sa akin. Ako yung leader ng grupo namin tapos ganito yung ginawa ko ito gawin mo yung ginawa ko, as in walang nangyari talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh pag may kasama ka walang nangyayari? Pero ano sa tingin mo kung mga okay din naman yung mga kasama mo?</i>
106	Mr. NurseR	<i>Siguro depende kung pare-pareho kami ng ano, way of thinking, madali pero kasi syempre di mo masasabi kung sino kasama mo e. Eh iba-iba talaga kami ng ano... kaya gawin mo ito, gawin mo ito, kaya ang ginawa nmin, dinelegate nalang namin, tapos yung huli kinollate namin, saka kami nag-usap nung kinollate namin, pero yung tipong gagawin mo talaga yung report, nag-isa isa kami mas marami kaming nagawa non, naging ganon kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos na tayo sa 1st part, yung 2nd part is like a fast track of what happened after 4 years of your education. We now go to the part wherein you had your experience, after the graduation na ito, mas ano dito yung mga pananaw mo, ano yung nangyari, hindi talaga yung strategy hindi yung technical. It yung mga opinions mo, yung thoughts about what happened. Ahh una, what were the factors or reasons that have influenced you to decide to take self review? Like personal reasons, individuals, or situations that might have influenced your decision.</i>
107	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano parang, yung mga ano, yung mga kamag anak kong iba nagnursing din sila. Nagreview center sila, hindi naman lahat sila pumasa. Eh, magrereview center ako, wala naman akong maraming</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>pera non. Inisip ko, mag-aaral na lang ako mag-isa, ganun din naman yung matutunan ko. Yung materials, hihiramin ko na lang. Yung manghihiram ako ng mga questionnaire ganyan, ako magsasagot mag-isa pero yung tipong review center parang di ko siya gustong gawin kasi magastos</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Grumaduate ka... anong situation nyo non, nung panahon na yon? Papanong nagdecide kang mag self-review?</i>
108	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi kasi nung grumaduate ako parang gusto ko ng magtrabaho eh. Sabi ng nanay ko mag board (exam) ka muna... Eh gusto kong patunayan na kayang-kaya kong gumawa ng sarili kong pera, yung parang independent, ung ako yung gumagastos. Hindi ako nag review center. Gusto ko yung medyo binabadget ko, pero ayoko rin yung umasa sila na dahil nagreview center ka, papasa ka. Ayokong umasa sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah ayaw mong umasa sa iyo magulang mo?</i>
109	Mr. NurseR	<i>Na papasa ako kagad.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Syempre gagastos ka don diba?</i>
110	Mr. NurseR	<i>Syempre gagastos din ako, magkano yun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, so nagtry ka na lang mag-isa para hindi sila ganon ka ano...</i>
111	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kung sakaling</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala silang expectations?</i>
112	Mr. NurseR	<i>Medyo mababa yung expectations (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay sige. Yung school mo ba was there any review center that was endorsed by your school?</i>
113	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala, wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala</i>
114	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala talaga, kasi ano yun eh public yun eh, hindi sila yung hindi sila pwedeng maglagay pero ayaw nung Dean namin maglagay ng review center dahil alam niya karamihan ng estudyante wala din namang pambabayad. Karamihan kasi talaga dun scholar.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You were not required to attend any review center?</i>
115	Mr. NurseR	<i>in-house</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In house?</i>
116	Mr. NurseR	<i>In-house nung last sem, every Saturday yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ibang review-center yun oh yung mga professors niyo din?</i>
117	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ibang professors dun, nagtatrabaho sa review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
118	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nung tinawag nila yung mga kasama nila pero nagre review-review dun sa mga ano, pero may company yun, nakalimutan ko yung pangalan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, okay lang. So galing yun sa labas, pero yung mga...</i>
119	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung mga professors</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tagadun din. Kasama sa tuition nyo yon oh pro-bono?</i>
120	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pro-bono yata yun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan ka nagdecide na mag self review na lang? After graduation, immediately, or way before graduation?</i>
121	Mr. NurseR	<i>Way before graduation</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano nangyari yun</i>
122	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ayoko mag review center, ayoko talagang gumastos.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay yun ang reason mo, part ng reason mo?</i>
123	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo ayaw ko talagang gumastos. Ang inisip ko naman kasi sa dinami-dami ng nagreview center hindi naman lahat papasa kaya hindi naman ibig sabihin mag review center ka papasa ka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero pakiramdam mo, papasa ka?</i>
124	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi nga eh, kaya nga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay okay, nung mag decide ka na mag self review na lang, papano mo sinabi sa magulang mo, ano yung sabi ng magulang mo?</i>
125	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo nasabi ko, hindi naman nila tinanong kung magreview center ako o hindi. Hinayaan lang nila ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi nila alam, walang pressure?</i>
126	Mr. NurseR	<i>Walang pressure, nag-aral ako sa bahay ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

127	Mr. NurseR	<i>Aral-aral lang ako sa bahay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero alam nilang June ka mag te-take?</i>
128	Mr. NurseR	<i>Alam nila. Tinanong nila ako minsan kaya lang, parang wala lang, di naman nila gaanong pinansin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May kilala ka bang nag self review din? Na pumasa?</i>
129	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hm... hindi...nag review center yun eh, mga pinsan ko nagreview center, hindi pumasa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagreview-center?</i>
130	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nag review-center, dun sa Bicol</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi pumasa?</i>
131	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo kaya nga hindi ibig sabihin nag review center ka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pumasa naman na sila ngayon?</i>
132	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pumasa naman sila, mga apat na take.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If you can describe your experience in one sentence, or one word, yung experience mo na yon buong experience na yon, kung maalala mo.</i>
133	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung yung pag re-review sa bahay?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong description?</i>
134	Mr. NurseR	<i>Two words <u>slow paced</u></i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i><u>Slow paced?</u> Bakit?</i>
135	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ninanamnam ko yung pag-aaral ko eh. Yung sabi ko nga kanina, ayoko yung pressure na aral. Dinahan-dahan ko siya, sabi ko matagal pa naman, atleast may panahon ako para dahan-dahanin ko ito kung may hindi man ako maintindihan pwedeng talunan ko, minsan tinatalunan ko, binabalikan ko para maging fresh na uli, o kaya pag talagang gusto kong... na cu-curious ako na hindi, hindi, hindi ko maintindihan talaga, kailangang malaman ko kung bakit ganito, mag re-research ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, in the end, ano sa tingin mo ang pinagkaiba nun sa review center?</i>
136	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung sa review center kasi, parang nag-aral ka talaga eh, parang nag-eskuwelahan ka talaga, may curriculum sila diba tapos yung... hindi ko alam, kasi hindi nga ako nag review center eh... yung mga iba pang seminar, ilang araw silang nandito sa etong system. Sa</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>akin di ko masabi kung maintindihan ko yung ganon kabilis na turo. Lahat ng kailangan kong pag-aralan don sa system na yun. Kunyari mahirap, sabihin mo na Psyche (Psychiatric nursing) sa dalawang araw hindi ko maano lahat yun, tsaka yung buong araw kang nag-aaral, nandun ka sa isang lugar na ano, yung classroom, hindi ko gusto yung parang pagod ka na nag-aaral ka pa, ang gusto ko yung nakakapag unwind ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero diba ang dami naman daw nag pe-present ng anu dun, yung mga professors nyo...(smiles)</i>
137	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ahh ano bang malay ko? (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay okay, nagkaroon ka ba ng challenges before, before you review, during your review?</i>
138	Mr. NurseR	<i>Before? Before ako nagstart?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, yung challenges mo nun, at anong ginawa mo?</i>
139	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nung...?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan ka kumuha ng mga resources?</i>
140	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung during, yung sa paghahanap ng mga resources...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
141	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung kasi yung tiyuhin ko naghandle ng...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tiyuhin mo nurse diba?</i>
142	Mr. NurseR	<i>Tiyuhin ko nurse.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
143	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nasa abroad na sila ngayon. Nung nag-aaral siya nagNCLEX siya, pero NCLEX-PN, Practical Nurse. Eh hinihiram-hiram ko yung libro niya, eh ginagamit din niya parang nag-aantay na muna ako para matapos niya, tapos kung hindi naman, eh wala naman kaming internet nun, nagpupunta ako ng computer shop. Nasa computer shop na ako... "Bakit nga ba ako ulit nandito? Eh sa iba napupunta (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naglalaro lang?</i>
144	Mr. NurseR	<i>Naglalaro lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, pero ano ah, nagkaroon ka ba ng libro nung college ka?</i>
145	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, pinagtiyagaan kong bumili ng libro. Yung importante talaga, kunwari, Med Surgs, Funda (Fundamentals of nursing), Psyche, pati nga yung chemistryat biochemistry bumili ako eh. Pero yung iba</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>hiniram ko sa tiyuhin ko, yung mga luma as in lumang-luma na. Kunyari nanghiram ako ng Brunner and Sudarths sa kanya na libro yung Med Surgs, naninilaw-nilaw na yung page nun 1980 plus pa yata yun na libro lumang-luma na yung knowledge pero pinagtiyagaan ko (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun yung second edition pa lang? (Smiles)</i>
146	Mr. NurseR	<i>(Smiling) tipong ganun, ngayon pang-ilan na diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo dami na, pero okay may libro ka, notes mahilig ka ba mag-notes?</i>
147	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ay hindi ako pala-notes talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka pala-notes?</i>
148	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ako pala-notes. Ang notes ko nun, kunyari Pathophysiology, yung magiging notes ko dun, diba yung process na mahaba--- paiikliin ko siya, yung mas madaling intindihin, ganon, isa-summarize ko siya, yung kunyari sa gilid ng libro may susulat akong ganito-ganyan. Kunyari may sinabing ganitong sakit I aa-underline ko tapos isusulat ko yung notes kung ano yung parang na search ko, nakikita ko kagad, nasa gilid. Ayoko kasi yung maghahanap pa ako sa notebook. Tsaka, hindi ako yung may babasahin ako magsusulat ako ganyan, o kaya may nag le-lecture nagsusulat ako ganyan then ma-istock ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh kailangan focus ka lang?</i>
149	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo ganun talaga ako eh, kaya nga gusto ko mag-isa kasi kailangan focus talaga ako, hindi ako multi task, kaya kung ano yung ginagawa ko focus lang talaga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Habang nag- re-review ka, maliban dun sa mga resources kung meron pa ano?</i>
150	Mr. NurseR	<i>Challenge?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>O kaya kanina na di-distract ka ganun?</i>
151	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung challenges na natatandaan mo.</i>
152	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nung nagrereview ako nun may tindahan kami sa bahay eh... Habang walang bumibili tsaka ako nagrereview, pagka may nabili parang maraming distraction o kaya may gagawin sa bahay kasi wala kaming katulong non. Yung tumutulong ka sa bahay, habang</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>nagrereview ka, saka syempre di mo naman pwedeng pabayaan yung mga trabaho sa bahay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you at any point during the course of your review, tempted to quit self review and just wanted to enroll at a review center instead?</i>
153	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, never.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit naman?</i>
154	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, ayaw ko talaga mag-review center parang di ko talaga siyang gustong gawin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang mga kilalang nagrereview center nung mga panahon na yon, let's say, ka close mo?</i>
155	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kakilala pero di ko ka close, yung mga kaklase ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala ka bang nababalitaan sa mga ginagawa nila?</i>
156	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala kasi hindi ako nakikihalubilo sa kanila eh, kasi yung girlfriend ko dati hindi din nag review center, nag review din sa bahay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero tingin mo, ano yung confidence level mo nun na papasa ka? Ito inaaral ko ito, yung mga notes ko ganun, may mga notes man ako, ito yung libro ko.</i>
157	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ang ano ko, parang 80% papasa ako 20% babagsak ako, parang ganon 80-20 pero ang ano dun, pasa lang as in pasa lang talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay.</i>
158	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi yung makapasa ako ng mataas na score, as in makapasa ka lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta ba yong mga...going back to your college years, kamusta ba yung mga scores mo sa mga exam nyo?</i>
159	Mr. NurseR	<i>Scores ko sa exam?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
160	Mr. NurseR	<i>Basta multiple choice? Na pe-perfect ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga? Ilang items yon?</i>
161	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mga 300</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Na pe-perfect mo yung 300 questions?!</i>
162	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi kasi ganun ako kapag ano, pagka may pagpipilian ako ang pag-iisip ko...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?! (surprised)</i>
163	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, kung may mali man 2, 3 ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>300 items 2, 3 lang (mali)?</i>
164	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ang ano ko dyan, tatanong mo pag may tanong ka, pag nag-exam ako, pagka multiple choice, mas madali sa akin kasi yung nag a-analyze ako kung alin dito, kung ano yung tama, kesa yung sa blanko lang iisipin mo kung ano kasi hindi ako mahilig magmemorize. Kunyari tanong mo ako anong gamot yung para sa ganitong sakit, blanko lang yung... identification na tanong, di ko masasagot yan out of the top of my head, pero yung may apat na choices dyan parang ipag...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Elimination?</i>
165	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, elimination yan. Ito hindi pwede dahil para sa ganitong sakit ito, pwede pero di gaanong ginagamit, ito di ako sigurado, ito para sa ibang sakit din yan, tas bigla ko na lang ito pipiliin parang tipong ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say na 1 – 100 na exam, ilan ang nakukuha mo?</i>
166	Mr. NurseR	<i>95 ganyan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung revalida ninyo, ilan ang nakukuha mo?</i>
167	Mr. NurseR	<i>Anong...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Diba may exam yun? O kaya pre board exam</i>
168	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pre-board? Di ko na matandaan pero nung yung kukwentahin mo siya parang 89</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>89?</i>
169	Mr. NurseR	<i>Parang 89, 88 ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mga tanong sa, let's say, yung board exam type questions diba halos pare-pareho lang yung sagot eh, konti lang yung deperensya eh. Konting deperensya may 01, 02 diba? Papano mo siya sinasagot?</i>
170	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ayun ganun nga, yung maliliit na diperensya lang, pagka yung... choose the best find answer diba? Kung ano yung best para dun sa situation ganun talaga ako mag-ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kailangan may prior knowledge ka dun?</i>
171	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, sabi mo nung elementary ka mahilig ka magbasa</i>
172	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Parang Journalism gusto mo, nung nag high-school ka, half of your high-school years nag public ka, naging petics ka.</i>
173	Mr. NurseR	<i>Petics pero hindi naman siya bagsak.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay nung college parang petics din, pero hindi naman petics na petics</i>
174	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta yung reading habit mo nun?</i>
175	Mr. NurseR	<i>Reading habit ko nung college ako? Palabasa pa rin ako sa bahay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anu-ano binabasa mo?</i>
176	Mr. NurseR	<i>Iba-iba. Mahilig ako magbasa fiction nung college.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, pero yung nursing subject?</i>
177	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nursing subjects babasahin ko pag di ko ma gets sa libro yun nga maghahanap ako ng libro ng madaling intindihin, so pag titiyagain kong pumunta sa library.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung nape-perfect mo yung exams, almost perfect mo yung exams mo, yung mga topics na yun alam mo?</i>
178	Mr. NurseR	<i>Alam ko pero hindi ko siya ano, kung baga alam mo yun, yung parang alam mo bakit nangyari ito, pero kung iisa-isahin mo pa yung bakit nangyari yun, hindi ko siya masasagot. Yung kunyari yung tipong kunyari alam ko kung bakit siya nagkakaroon ng stroke ganyan, ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
179	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pero yung process kung bakit siya nagka-stroke mahihirapan akong ipaliwanag sayo, ayun alam ko yung pinakadahilan, pero yung as in sunod-sunod talaga na ganito ang nangyari, mahihirapan akong ipaliwanag yon hanggang sa hindi ko naiintindihan ano yung simpleng paliwanag.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, pagdating sa exam papano mo na eeliminate yun?</i>
180	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi kasi ano yung naging experience ko naman kasi nung exam, yung mga tanong, hindi siya ganun ka specific.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

181	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kung specific man, hindi sila yung specific sa pare-parehong bagay. Kunyari yung lahat ng choices dun specific, pero kung tutuusin mo, hindi sila para sa tanong, para sa iba talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung iba hindi para sa tanong?</i>
182	Mr. NurseR	<i>Para sa iba talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah okay</i>
183	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kaya malalaman mo hindi na ito, e di isusulat mo na siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After mo ng review mo, kamusta yung how did you feel about it? Halimbawa, mag te-take ka na ng exam, immediately before taking the exam--- ano yung pakiramdam mo nun? Tingin mo papasa ka ba o sapat na ba napag-aralan mo?</i>
184	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano... bahala na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bahala na?</i>
185	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo bahala na, hindi ang ano ko kasi...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo mapapasa mo ba lahat ng ano...?</i>
186	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung lahat ng ano... ang feeling ko nun nagawa ko na lahat ng kailangan kong gawin, bahala na yung Diyos. Ganun na bahala na, yung tipong ginawa ko na yung parte ko, Diyos na yung bahala kung ano mangyari.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba yung naging parte mo?</i>
187	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun yung ginawa ko na ang lahat, yung sa tingin ko na dapat pag-aralan ko, napag-aralan ko na, 5 yun diba yung parang 5 area na yun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>500 -item questions yun in 5 areas.</i>
188	Mr. NurseR	<i>5 areas diba? Yung 2 parang naulit lang Med-Surgs 1, Med-Surgs 2. Di yung parang apat na yun, dun ako nag focus. Hindi ako yung tipong system by system ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay ahh nung grumaduate ka anong month?</i>
189	Mr. NurseR	<i>April</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>April? June ka nagtake, 2 months?</i>
190	Mr. NurseR	<i>2 months</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo slow paced?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

191	Mr. NurseR	<i>Slow-paced.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Compared to a review-center, ganun din yun diba?</i>
192	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, slow-paced ako kasi pagka yung nagrereview ako, hindi yung tuloy-tuloy, as in yung tuloy tuloy na isang araw wala akong gagawin kundi mag-aral? Hindi. Magbabasa-basa ako sa umaga, may gagawin ako sa tanghali, magbabasa-basa ako ng konti, may gagawin ako sa hapon hanggang sa gabi. Hindi ako yung tuloy-tuloy, binabalik-balikan ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano sa tingin mo yung advantages/ dis-advantages ng kapag sariling review?</i>
193	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga hawak ko yung sarili ko, na yung pace of learning ko, kung pano ako matuto, nasusunod ko. Kesa mag-review center ako, pagdating ng hapon wala na akong maintindihan niyan pagpasok ko sa classroom.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo mahalaga yun sa....</i>
194	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...yung learning mo? Yung style mo</i>
195	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, hindi naman ako... iba-iba naman tayo ng learning style eh. Baka mag review center ako, parang mangyari niyan, palagay ko ha, parang classroom setting diba? Parang mapupuwera kang matuto kung pano sila matuto sa klase. Hindi naman lahat matututo ng maayos ng ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang nakitang dis-advantage/s?</i>
196	Mr. NurseR	<i>Sa pag rereview ng sarili? Oo! Kunyari yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Palagay mo oo? O sige anu-ano?</i>
197	Mr. NurseR	<i>Meron talaga. Kasi yung pag-kausap ko yung nagreview center, meron silang sinasabi na hindi ko naintindihan, yun pala parang mga techniques na kunyari mnemonics ganyan, di ko alam yon, kasi yong tipong exam-taking techniques, binibigay sa kanila diba? Yung techniques mismo. Hindi naman yung mismong subject matter yung binibigay sa kanila, pero papaano ka mag exam. Yun yong wala ako non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo more than 80, more than 80 ka?</i>
198	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero hindi ka naman, wala ka naman exam taking ng techniques.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

199	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala, yun lang talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano ka tumaas yung rating mo?</i>
200	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ko alam. Ang ano ko kasi, siguro dahil mas naretain ko yung pinag-aralan ko, dahil hindi ako na pressure. Mas na retain ko yung style ko, paano ako sumagot, nagging komportable ako kung paano ako sumagot nung multiple answer. Kumportable na akong sumagot talaga yung multiple choice na questions kesa sa identification.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay multiple choice questions. Kelan nag-umpisa yung almost 100 ka, yung almost na peperfect mo yung exam?</i>
201	Mr. NurseR	<i>2nd year, 3rd year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2nd year?</i>
202	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong mga subjects yon?</i>
203	Mr. NurseR	<i>Sa... kunyari tipong Pharma ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pharma? MS (Medical-Surgical) kamusta?</i>
204	Mr. NurseR	<i>M.S. okay lang, pero Psyche (Psychiatric) ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Psyche? Let's say yung mga Funda (Fundamentals of nursing)?</i>
205	Mr. NurseR	<i>Funda, nung nagtest kami sa Funda, hindi multiple choice.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh iba</i>
206	Mr. NurseR	<i>Iba, as in, alam mo yung test na ano... may true or false, may...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay</i>
207	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong halu-halo. Pagka may multiple choice ayun okay ako diyan, eh ilan lang yun 20, so out of 100.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka pa bang advantages/disadvantages, maliban sa mga nabanggit mo?</i>
208	Mr. NurseR	<i>Siguro, kunyari pagkaano, yung disadvantage nya parang kung di alam I co-cover mo marami mawawala sa'yo, kung hindi mo alam ang dapat mong aralin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you? As an individual or as a nurse?</i>
209	Mr. NurseR	<i>As an individual, parang ano kaya ko pala, ganon yung hindi ko kailangang umasa sa iba na tulungan ako. Sa sarili kong paraan, makakaya ko. Yun ang ano ko, parang yung makakatulong siya sa independence, yung feeling mo na independent ka.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa pagkatao mo ngayon, meron bang...</i>
210	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga parang ano, yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...naging epekto? Kung meron man.</i>
211	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung nakakaboost siya ng moral. Saka yung sense of independence.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nalaman mong pumasa ka, anong nangyari?</i>
212	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ay nadulas ako sa hagdanan (Laughs).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hahahahaha anung nangyari?</i>
213	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kasi yung mga kasabay kung nag board sa subdivision namin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
214	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung nanay niya, nauna pang nakabili ng dyaryo eh, kagigising lang namin nun. Pagkalabas-labas ko ng bahay sumigaw yung kapitbahay namin: Hoy! Mr. NurseR, pumasa ka! Nadulas ako kakamadali kong bumaba, nadulas ako sa hagdanan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>hahahaha, anong naging reaction ng pamilya mo o mga kakilala?</i>
215	Mr. NurseR	<i>Natuwa sila, mga kamag-anak ko sa Amerika, 'sige magNCLEX ka na', parang madaliin mo na lahat yan, para maka abroad ka na'. Eh ayun wala, pinipilit na nila ako sa Amerika.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Itong part na'to yung sinabi kong technicalities ng strategies. Not really about yung thoughts, pero kung papano mo siya ginawa, yung details. Papano mo siya ginawa na nagging effective sa'yo?</i>
216	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung strategy ng pagrereview?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, papano yung nagiging strategy mo kung meron ka mang naging strategy?</i>
217	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung una, sa oras</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oras, okay.</i>
218	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ang ano kasi sa akin, depende rin sa learning style ng tao, ang sa akin kasi yung di mo, mag-aaral ka na... pag di mo na maintindihan, tumigil ka na. Kasi wala ng papasok sa ano nun eh, sa utak mo. Kunyari mag focus ka sa isang topic, pagka hindi mo na maintindihan yon, tigil ka muna. Balikan mo kung gusto mo mamaya, kaya kung mag-skip ka, tapos balikan mo ulit. Pagka medyo fresh yung utak mo basta wag mong pipilitin yung pagrereview ka na di mo maintindihan. Basa ka lang ng basa, wala hindi siya magiging effective. Pahinga ka, tumigil ka, maghanap ka ng ibang gagawin. Tapos yung depende sa, kunyari, ano yung pinag-aaralan ko, yung gagawa ako ng diagram. Kunyari nagpaliwanag siya ng ganito, gagawan ko siya ng diagram, mas simple. Kung may</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>diagram na sa libro mas sisimplehan ko pa lalo yun, tas susubukan ko siyang... susubukan ko siyang isulat ulit, kung papano ko siya papaiikliin pero hindi sa lahat ng process, yung process na medyo nalilito ako i-sa-summarize ko parang i-sa-summarize ko ganun, kukunin ko yung pinaka essence niya tapos susubukan kong ulitin yun, yung di nakatingin sa likod, susubukan kong isulat sa papel yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung sarili mong pagkaintindi.</i>
219	Mr. NurseR	<i>Sarili kong pagkaintindi, para malaman ko kung nakuha ko ba o hindi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have doubts in failing the exam?</i>
220	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, oo pero hindi siya ganun katindi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo, diba ang daming bumagsak let's say ratings 30% , o 40% na lang ang daming nagrereview center di pumapasa, ikaw hindi mo naman di sigurado diba?</i>
221	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mong na deal, how did you deal with it?</i>
222	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano ako eh, wala lang, ano parang ano ko eh, yung "fatalist". Alam mo yung "fatalist" na way of thinking?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yun?</i>
223	Mr. NurseR	<i>Bahala na, ganun siya, "fatalist" nga. Yung leave it all to fate.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Fatalist</i>
224	Mr. NurseR	<i>Fatalist, fatal, fatal, fatalist yung leave everything to fate.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay sige, bahala na yung tadhana?</i>
225	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh, papano kung bumagsak ka?</i>
226	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ibig sabihin...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tadhana pa rin yun? (grins)</i>
227	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, may ano yun, kung бага parang may</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Dahilan</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

228	Mr. NurseR	<i>...may dahilan kung bakit nangyari yun. Hindi mo masasabi kung bakit malay mo bumagsak ka dahil kailangan mong matuto ka kung paano ano yung magdeal sa failure, ganun, parang di mo masasabi kung ano yung nangyari. Yung sa akin ha, hindi pwede yung tipong close-minded ka na papasa ako, papasa ako--- eh paano kung hindi? Eh di mas mabigat sa loob mo yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So meron din talagang part sa'yo na hinahanda mo kapag bumagsak ka, ganon?</i>
229	Mr. NurseR	<i>Alam mo yung kasabihan na ano 'hope for the best, prepare for the worst'?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay, did you seek advice from anyone or did someone help you throughout your review?</i>
230	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano? Assist, parang ganon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, assistance</i>
231	Mr. NurseR	<i>Meron akong assistance, humihiram ako ng materials sa tiyuhin ko yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ba siyang binigay na tip sayo at ano, kung meron man?</i>
232	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala naman</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala, nanghiram ka lang?</i>
233	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo nanghiram lang ako, kasi ano eh alam naman niya kung pano ako mag-aral eh, hinahayaan niya ako kasi, ano yun clinical instructor, matagal siyang nagturo, 'kung paano ka mag-aral, ganun lang gawin mo.'</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo, how did you deal with time constraints? Paano mo dinivide yung oras let's say 2 months ka nagreview.</i>
234	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo plinano yung review?</i>
235	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ko plinano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano kung hindi mo natapos?</i>
236	Mr. NurseR	<i>Eh di wala, ang ano ko dun kasi...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala kang timeline?</i>
237	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala akong timeline, hindi ako nag ta-timeline basta naintindihan ko, yun ang importante.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka naglagay ng araw na ito, yung araw na ito,</i>
238	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, yun nga yung ayaw na ayaw ko, kaya nga hindi ako nagreview-center, ayaw kong may constraints. Gusto ko yung may lugar ako, pagkamay lugar ako na tapusin yun, matatapos ko siya ng mas madali, kasi nagfo-focus ako dun sa bagay na yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero beforehand naisip mo ba na baka hindi ko ma-cover lahat?</i>
239	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo pero ano ang pumasok sa akin, kung di ko man ma-cover lahat atleast yung ncover ko siguradong-sigurado ako dun. Ang importante sa akin kung hindi ko man makuha lahat, may malaking percentage nakuha ko, napag-aralan ko maigi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay what were your strategies in terms of study habits, time of day, why?</i>
240	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano, ang study habit ko kunyari sa umaga, yung pagkagising sa umaga mag e-exercise muna ako tapos mag exercise mag-aaral ako mula alas-otso hanggang eleven.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>8-11?</i>
241	Mr. NurseR	<i>8-11 ganyan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tuloy-tuloy yon</i>
242	Mr. NurseR	<i>May mga breaks in between</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
243	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kasi nga sabi ko sa'yo nasa tindahan ako eh, pero ano yun 8-11 tapos lunch. After nun minsan 1-2 ganyan 1-3 o kaya 3 basta yung ano mga after nun tapos titigil ako, gabi magbabasa uli ako bago matulog.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Magbabasa uli, ano yun Monday to Friday o Monday- Sunday pano ba?</i>
244	Mr. NurseR	<i>Araw-araw</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Araw-araw hanggang Sunday?</i>
245	Mr. NurseR	<i>Bukod sa linggo, yung linggo magbabasa ako isang beses lang, parang hapon lang, 1-4 ganon lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1-4 linggo?</i>
246	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Di kayo lumalabas ng mga kaibigan mo?</i>
247	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, wala naman akong gaanong masyadong kaibigan eh.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Venue, saan ka usually nag-aaral?</i>
248	Mr. NurseR	<i>Tindahan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tindahan?</i>
249	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pero pagka gabi na, dun ako sa ,may study table ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May study table ka?</i>
230	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo dun lang ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ilan bang, may kapatid ka ba?</i>
251	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo may kapatid ako, isa lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh kamusta yung ambience sa inyo? Maingay ba o tama lang?</i>
252	Mr. NurseR	<i>Tama lang, sanay na ako dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sanay ka na dun?</i>
253	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pagkakailangan ko talaga maging tahimik, pumupunta ako dun sa kabilang bahay, yung bakante.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh may bahay din kayo</i>
254	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi yung ano, yung tiyuhin ko nga, yung ano siya, nung mag abroad siya iniwan niya yung lahat ng gamit niya sa ami. Mga May na yun, isang buwan bago mag-exam. Iniwan niya lahat ng resources, yun hindi na ako hirap non. Nung maggraduate kami April-May. Ahh first week ng May ganyan, nanghihiram-hiram pa ako eh. Nung nag-abroad na sila, ayun na, nagamit ko na lahat ng libro niya sa bahay pero hindi rin ako pala stay dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, itong mga subjects na ito let's say anong natatandaan mo sa Funda (Fundamentals of Nursing) o Professional Adjustment? Papano mo siya inaral?</i>
255	Mr. NurseR	<i>Anong papano ko siya inaral?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Diba yung Professional Adjustment, yun yung laws, nursing laws?</i>
256	Mr. NurseR	<i>Jurisprudence?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Jurisprudence o kaya sa Funda, sa Funda, papano mo siya natatandaan, tapos papano mo na-apply yung technique mo dun sa multiple choice type?</i>
257	Mr. NurseR	<i>Situational</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Situational?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

258	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kunyari kailangang makita ko siya sa context ng isang situation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Context ng situation?</i>
259	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kunyari Jurisprudence diba, ano yung pinagkaiba ng Negligence sa Malpractice?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh so base don? Kailangan may knowledge ka sa mga terms na yon?</i>
260	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kailangan yon, kapag sinabi mo yung definition ng "negligence" saka "magpractice", parang vague yung difference niya sa akin. Di ko siya maintindihan kagad. Bigyan mo nung situation ng "negligence" at "malpractice", alam ko na kagad kung anong pinagkaiba non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung nag-aaral ka ganun ba maganda?</i>
261	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga, yun nga tipong ganun nga explanation sa libro maghahanap ako ng iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano sa Research</i>
262	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nursing Research?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
263	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung tipong thesis?</i>
Researcher:		<i>Oo, diba may mga questions about Research?</i>
264	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, pero di ako ganung nag focus dun eh. Yung sa school kasi namin, tipong subject sa Research, yung lecture talaga ng Research, kokonti lang. Nagfocus kami sa paggawa ng thesis.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh Maternal and Child Nursing?</i>
265	Mr. NurseR	<i>Parang... okay lang pero yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailangan ng memory?</i>
266	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi naman, kapag ka mga ganyan, kunyari Med-Surgs, Pedia, Psyche, gusto kong pinag-aaralan yung may case, tapos kunyari may case na ganon diba, kunwari multiple choice magtatanong kunyari, magtatanong ganito, ganyan. Gusto ko yung mga tipong ganun, kunyari yung kpag nagbabasa ka sa libro, may mga side problem na parang may situation, tapos may ina-analyze na kung anong nangyari. Yun ang gusto kong basahin kesa yung tipong ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mismong definition?</i>
267	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mas babasahin ko yung application niya.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Application?</i>
268	Mr. NurseR	<i>Dun ako magsisimula tapos kapag medyo naguluhan ako saka ako pupunta dun sa definition.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong nagging epekto nun sa exam?</i>
269	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kasi diba yung exam mas maraming situational, kesa yung tipong purong definition. Ang itatanong niya based on the situation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay kung hilig mo, hilig mo yun, papano mo siya ina-approach yung situation?</i>
270	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga kunyari, parang isang situation, yung pagdating sa baba ang unang itatanong ganun, ano yung complaints ni Patient X ganyan, parang irerelate ko siya...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ire-relate mo siya?</i>
271	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ire-relate ko siya sa exam, hindi ba parang ganun din yung itatanong sa exam? Yung symptoms ni Patient X is indicative of what type of ..., parang ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, so yung mga subjects na walang, kung бага kailangan mo siya ng prior knowledge na specific, ano ba ang sukat ng ganito? Papano yung walang situation?</i>
272	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi siya situational kung бага...</i>
273	Mr. NurseR	<i>Definition?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, matter-of-fact siya.</i>
274	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung mga tipong ganun, kunyari yung sa mga laboratory values ganyan, mapipilitang magmemorize. Yun talaga nagmemorize ako dahil kailangan, pero iilan lang naman yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say yung ABG (Arterial Blood Gases) values ganon,</i>
275	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yan di ko na matandaan yan ngayon, noon siguro.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>3.5, 4.5</i>
276	Mr. NurseR	<i>Diba ano yan? Yung ABG</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May table, ahh Arterial Blood Gases</i>
277	Mr. NurseR	<i>Pagka ano, yung acidic</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Acidic ganon</i>
278	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung PH niya diba? Diba may ano siya, kapagkanaghyperventilate,may parang ano siya, may table.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May table. Irerelate mo ba siya sa ano?</i>
279	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ire-relate ko siya sa table. Mismong pakainirerelate ko siya dun sa exam, iniisip ko yung table sa utak ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh yung pagkakatanda mo nung nagbabasa ka?</i>
280	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo kasi yung medyo visual ako pagkaganyan eh. Hindi ko lahat matatandaan yung sa listahan ganun, kailangan makita ko yung table sa utak ko. Yung comparison kung bakit mataas ito, mababa yung base niya, pagkamababa yung base niya, mataas yung ganito parang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero yung nare-relate mo ba yung sumunod na part ng table na yun, oh kailangan kung ano talaga yung...</i>
281	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi ano ibe-base ko sa table na yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Table talaga</i>
282	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, kunyari ganito yung table na yon...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Alkalosis</i>
283	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kunyari Alkalosis ganon, ma-imagine ko kung ano itsura nung comparison nung ano.. mage-gets ko na siya kung bakit nagkaganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
284	Mr. NurseR	<i>parang connect the dots</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Connect the dots?</i>
285	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kunyari makita ko yung bakit nagkaganito yung alkalosis niya, bakit ganito yung values niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw ba yung tipong mahilig sa queues ganon? Na pag may nakita ka ng ganito eh...</i>
286	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo sa isang question?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, mga label.</i>
287	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung pang label kunyari may nakita akong ganitong nakalagay sa question alam mo na ganito hinahanap?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>O iniintindi mo muna lahat?</i>
288	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi, ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano ba approach mo?</i>
289	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ganon, pero parang pag may nakita akong ganon, tapos binasa ko yung mga ano, yung mga sagot mag do-doble check ako parang titingnan ko uli yung tanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh titingnan mo uli yung tanong?</i>
290	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, hindi ko sasagutin kagad yun! Hindi ako yung sagot kagad na, unang basa, sagot. Maliban na lang kung talagang kabisado ko yong tanong. Yung alam na alam ko, sigurado talaga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Babalikan mo yung tanong?</i>
291	Mr. NurseR	<i>Babalikan ko yung tanong, ia-analyze ko muna, kung eto ba talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have relaxation techniques? Sabi mo nga nagbabantay ka ng tindahan, meron ka pa bang ibang ginagawa, let's say, kumakain ka habang nagrereview, chichicha.</i>
292	Mr. NurseR	<i>Umuwi kasi ako sa probinsya nung mga isang linggo bago mag-exam, eh ang relaxation ko nun, yung tipong yung maglakad-lakad sa gilid ng dagat, o yung mag-ikot ikot dun sa bayan lumabas ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung isang linggo na yun nag-aral ka ba?</i>
293	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nag-aaral ako. Dala ko yung libro ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag-aral ka. Talaga?</i>
294	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, nag-aral ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakibalita ba school mo sayo? Did you receive any help from the school? Di sila nag survey kung sino nag-review center, hindi nag review center?</i>
295	Mr. NurseR	<i>Nagtanong naman sila bago ako magreview tapos pagkatapos na mag-exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bago ka magreview?</i>
296	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi bago maggraduation, "magrereview center ka ba o hindi?"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong sabi sa'yo?</i>
297	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala, wala lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala lang?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

298	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi naman nila ano, ang ano naman nila kasi, eto mukha namang papasa ito eh. Yung mga tipong ganun. Mukha namang papasa ito kung hindi pumasa ito e di patay (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did your educational program prepared you to pass the licensure examination? ano Let's say naging effect ng education mo sa sarili mo, naging effect niya sa pagrereview mo, at naging effect niya dun sa kinalabasan nung exam?</i>
299	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ano yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron man ha</i>
300	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung ano kasi dun sa Pamantasan, kahit na parang petics-petics lang yung pag-aaral, pero ano yun, kasi pagdating na nung talagang nursing proper na, 3rd year, 4th year, talagang ano na. Mag-aaral ka na talaga. Hindi kagaya nung 1st year, 2nd year petics-petics, nung 3rd year, 4th year mag-aaral ka na talaga. Ang ano niya kasi, malaki yung ineexpect sa iyo ng school na papasa ka. Kaya simula pa nung 3rd year, binubomba na kayo ng major-major.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Magagaling ba yung mga teacher niyo?</i>
301	Mr. NurseR	<i>Magagaling.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang nagustuhang teacher na ano...</i>
302	Mr. NurseR	<i>Meron, yung nagustuhan ko yung mga naging Clinical Instructors sa amin, naglelecture din sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag le-lecture sa hospital?</i>
303	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo pagkanaglelecture sila, sila din yung sa school namin, Clinical Instructor. Minsan dun sila sa ospital eh yung Pasig General (a hospital) pagkanaglelecture sila sa klase, situational.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Ahh yun ang practical</i>
304	Mr. NurseR	<i>Practical, oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you confident in a scale 1-10, 10 being the highest, bago ka magreview, ahh ano tingin mo?</i>
305	Mr. NurseR	<i>Na papasa?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Confidence na papasa ka?</i>
306	Mr. NurseR	<i>6</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After ng review mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

307	Mr. NurseR	8. Yun nga 80-20
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay ahh ngayon na pumasa ka na, ano sa tingin mo, how should a person review? I mean ahh how does one should do self-review to be effective?</i>
308	Mr. NurseR	<i>Una ang dapat mong gawin ano, alamin niya muna kung paano siya mag-aral. Yung talagang alam niya, kung papano siya mag-aral, yung matututo siya, yung learning style niya talaga. Tapos depende sa learning style niya, yun ang gagawin niya. Kunyari yung tipo ko, ayoko nung tuloy- tuloy na pag-aaral magbabasa, pero yung ibang tao gusto nila, yun ang gagawin nila as in focus na focus talaga sila. Yun talagang wala silang gagawin sa isang buong araw kundi mag-aral. Okay na yun, sabi mo nga, yung iba grupo sila yung may nag di-discussion. Eh ako ayaw ko yung nasa isang malaking grupo, kung ano yung komportable mas mag fo-focus sila yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you satisfied with the result of your exam? If yes, what factor(s) did you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to identify reasons or factors that might have caused it?</i>
309	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, satisfied ako kasi ang ano naman sa akin niyan, pumasa ako. Pumasa ako o hindi, hindi ko nga ini-expect na makakuha ng lagpas sa 80 eh. Yung parang factors na nag-influence na makapasa ako? ma-satisfy ako? ano yung, yun nga yung parang tipong kahit na nagreview ako, hindi ako yung 100% na umasa na papasa ako, nag-iwan ako ng room for doubt kahit konti if 20% na room for doubt</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was there anything you could have done that you think must have helped you more in your review? Ahh looking back at what you did?</i>
310	Mr. NurseR	<i>Kung may dapat gawin ako?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were any, what were they?</i>
311	Mr. NurseR	<i>Siguro dapat mag ano muna ako, dapat na nag-ipon ako ng information, kasi yung pinagtanungan ko na nag-board ilan lang eh, siguro bago ako nagreview dapat nanghingi muna ako ng maraming advice.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay last itong about traits of success, yung ano mo. If there were any, what do you think were the important qualities or quality you posses that made you pass the exam, and how did it affect you or helped you to pass the exam?</i>
312	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yung focus</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Focus</i>
313	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, yun kasi nga nakakapagfocus ako nung nag-aaral ako mag-isa.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun yung important quality mo, tingin mo?</i>
314	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo, kasi...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Focus ka?</i>
315	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo kasi nga nung nag-aral ako, kahit na hindi ako mag-aral ng matagal basta yung short time na 3 oras na nag-aral ako sa umaga, kunyari ganon, 2 oras kunyari sa umaga yung focus ko nun ayun talaga. Talagang i-a-absorb ko talaga yun, pagka nung nag-exam naman ako, yung araw ng exam, talagang focus din ako, kasi wala talagang ibang laman ang utak ko kundi mag-exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban sa "focus", meron pa bang iba o yun ang tingin mo...</i>
316	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun yong pinaka, kung meron mang iba hindi ko gaanong...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any regrets that you chose self study?</i>
317	Mr. NurseR	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh my last question: how did it affect you, pyschologically, mentally and emotionally yung lahat na lahat...</i>
318	Mr. NurseR	<i>Na...?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Overall, pagiging nurse mo, anything about what you did?</i>
319	Mr. NurseR	<i>Ayun parang ano ahh naging handa ako parang ano yung prenapare ako para maging independent, pano ako gagawa ng trabaho mo ganun yung pano mo kunyari may isang challenge kunyari sa trabaho may isang project kang kailangang gawin yung sa ginawa ko dun kung paano ako magtrabaho ng maayos, napatunayan ko na kaya kong gawin yung isang bagay kung talagang pag aanohan ko talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Follow up ko, I have P15,000 for you, right now</i>
320	Mr. NurseR	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh will you choose to enroll in a review center instead kung may pera ka non, may sapat kang ano...</i>
321	Mr. NurseR	<i>Hindi rin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Or dun ka pa rin</i>
322	Mr. NurseR	<i>Mag self review pa rin ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

323	Mr. NurseR	<i>Yun nga parang hindi ko nakikita yung punto ng pumasok ako dun sa review center kahit na ano, kahit na may pera ako, mas matututo ako kung sinundan ko ang sarili kong style ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Salamat, hanggang dito na lang. Maraming salamat magandang gabi.</i>
		[Time Stamp 01:13:30- END]

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, let's start... Good morning. My name is Neri Ocampo, from St. Paul University Manila. I'll be interviewing you about your experience in self-review. So the interview will be subdivided into four parts: number one is about your 'demographics and background'. The second would be about your 'experiences'; third is about the strategies and fourth is about some traits, if you have, that might have helped you with your review.</i> <i>So for demographics and background, the first question is about your name, or nickname, optional lang. May I have your name, please?</i>
1	Mr. NurseN	<i>Does it have to be in English?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>It's okay, if it's tagalog or ano...</i>
2	Mr. NurseN	<i>Mr. NurseN, my name is Mr. NurseN</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What year did you graduate in BSN?</i>
3	Mr. NurseN	<i>2010.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2010. IS BSN your first course, or second?</i>
4	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, nag-one year ako ng Computer Engineering. Just 1 year tapos I transferred immediately.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nag-nursing ka?</i>
5	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yup. So technically, not my first course, because I was a transferee.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Not your first course. But was it from the same school?</i>
6	Mr. NurseN	<i>Different school.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So you transferred to that school. (Pause). (How about) your current occupation?</i>
7	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ah, supervisor.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Any other previous employment? If you had any.</i>
8	Mr. NurseN	<i>You mean the same..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kahit anong work..</i>
9	Mr. NurseN	<i>I have worked with Teleperformance for one year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung current occupation mo, gano ka na katagal?</i>
10	Mr. NurseN	<i>Just two months.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, year or month your licensure exam was taken?</i>
11	Mr. NurseN	<i>2010. Same year that I graduated.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was that April?</i>
12	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ah I graduated April and I took the board exam in July. Yeah, June or July.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2010. Yung licensure rating, naka-cap siya: 75-79 or 80 and above.</i>
13	Mr. NurseN	<i>It's 80 and above.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was your school private or public?</i>
14	Mr. NurseN	<i>Private. Are there any public school for nursing?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yes, there are a lot. U.P. (University of the Philippines) is a public school. (Pause). Okay, yung next set of questions is about who you are as a person, if you can tell me a little about your upbringing, your views, your main beliefs about life, education, or anything that your value as a person, and the story why your took up nursing, or transferred from engineering to nursing.</i>
15	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ah, apat kaming magkakapatid. Yung isa ay anak sa unang asawa. My brother, who was supporting me, is with (Bureau of) Customs, and my sister right now, she's working with another BPO (business process outsourcing) company, and I'm the youngest.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You're the youngest.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

16	Mr. NurseN	<i>I'm the youngest. And... (thinking)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Your beliefs or anything that you can describe yourself, anything that you value. Papano ba yung Mr. NurseN na ikaw, ano ba yung tingin mo..</i>
17	Mr. NurseN	<i>Papano ba yan? Siguro naniniwala ako na things happen for a reason, and what we are right now is a product of what you did before, what you did in the past. That's what I believe.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the reason why, then, you transferred from engineering to nursing? What was the story?</i>
18	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, iniano lang..hindi naman sa pinilit, pero sinabihan lang ako na magnursing or hindi na'ko mag-aaral. Walang pilitan yun (smiles...)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Walang pilitan yun? (exchanged smiles). Pero ano yung first choice mo talaga?</i>
19	Mr. NurseN	<i>I wanted engineering..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong klaseng engineering yun?</i>
20	Mr. NurseN	<i>Electrical</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Electrical Engineering. Ah, E.E.</i>
21	Mr. NurseN	<i>E.C.E. (Electronic and Communication Engineering).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit mo naman napili yung school mo?</i>
22	Mr. NurseN	<i>Because it's mura, compared to other schools that are offering (nursing). Other schools for first year were offering 23 (thousand pesos), but my school was only eighteen (thousand pesos).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eighteen. Yung layo ng bahay mo sa school nay un, yung proximity, gano kalayo?</i>
23	Mr. NurseN	<i>At first I was travelling, but eventually I rented a place with my classmates. Kaya hindi na rin ako nahirapan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Mula kelan yun nag-umpisa?</i>
24	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, second year.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Second year. So after a year of engineering course, nagging first year ka ulit sa nursing o merong nacredit na subjects?</i>
25	Mr. NurseN	<i>May nacredit pero technically first year ulit ako, kasi may chemistry at meron akong mga subjects na major (like) Anatomy.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Overall, how did you fair in your studies? Nung pagpasok mo ng first year, kamusta yung pag-aaral mo?</i>
26	Mr. NurseN	<i>Umm, I can say I was not failing, but I was not really studious, hindi ako maaral na tao. Hindi ako masyadong nag-aaral, pero I was not failing.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When you say "not failing", mga ilan ba yun? Let's say 1-100, ilan ba yung fail dun?</i>
27	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pano ba 'to, pano ko ba sasabihin 'to, kapag it's major kasi, nag-aaral naman ako, kapag minor, dinadrop ko na yung minor like P.E. (Physical Education), Filipino. Imagine that I was already fourth year and I had P.E. because I dropped those subjects.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, go ahead..</i>
28	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa major subjects, I was not failing, pero hindi talaga ako studious. Hindi ako yung tipo na pagpaunta ng bahay magbabasa. Uwi ng maaga para magbasa ng ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung elementary-high school ganon din?</i>
29	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yeah, ganon din, but during elementary high school I had good grades, my average was 88 (percent</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eighty eight (percent) when you were in elementary?</i>
30	Mr. NurseN	<i>High school.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>High school? Nice. Kung meron ka man, ano yung favorite subject mo nun, nung college ka? Or anything that you found most interesting?</i>
31	Mr. NurseN	<i>Math.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, kasi engineering ka? Anong math sa nursing? Trigo (Trigonometry) o..</i>
32	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa nursing walang Math, Algebra lang sa nursing</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Algebra</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

33	Mr. NurseN	<i>Algebra, Basic Algebra</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung subject mo sa nursing, meron ka bang nagustuhan dun sa mga nursing subjects talaga?</i>
34	Mr. NurseN	<i>Anatomy.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anatomy.</i>
35	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yeah, because it's really interesting.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papanong naging interesting?</i>
36	Mr. NurseN	<i>Because yung Anatomy yung if you study Anatomy, you'll be amazed how your body works. Masasabi mo na rin talaga na may God na gumawa sa katawan ng tao kasi its perfectly designed para gumana, kaya paborito ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So Anatomy and Physiology, ahh how it works?</i>
37	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yeah, Anatomy and Physiology.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban don meron ka bang iba pang nagustuhan?</i>
38	Mr. NurseN	<i>Medical-Surgical, cardio I don't know pero gustong gusto ko yung Cardio (cardiovascular), yung cardio mismo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aling part don?</i>
39	Mr. NurseN	<i>cardio</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero di mo alam kung anong reason?</i>
40	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh basta I like that parang ang dali ko siyang intindihin pag Cardio</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say kung ite-test ka ngayon maaala mo siya?</i>
41	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kasi its like 2 years ago</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 years ago</i>
42	Mr. NurseN	<i>But still I can remember kung ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh Okay, noon ba at hanggang ngayon, do you can consider your self as a people person or someone who would do things alone?</i>
43	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, I like doing things alone, mag-isa lang ako kasi parang mas nakakapag concentrate ako eh wala akong</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>napagkokomperahan, or walang nagdidirect sa akin, mas gusto ko ito.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halimbawa, kung nandun ka sa crowd o dun sa grupo, anong nangyayari?</i>
44	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahm usually okay lang if the group is witty naman or makakasama naman but I'm better if I'm alone.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan pa nag-umpisa yun? Yung ganong preference mo like elementary, high school or ano?</i>
45	Mr. NurseN	<i>I don't know eh, di ko rin maalala eh pero siguro high school kasi ma te-train ka para maging cooperative, siguro college kasi diba high school ite-train ka para maging cooperative para group works, so I guess it's better kapag college because you're on your own pag college.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung layo ng bahay mo dun sa school mo, gaano kalayo? Like how many rides?</i>
46	Mr. NurseN	<i>It's only 2 rides, but the bus is like 1 ½ hour</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh 1 ½ hour pagkabus, so parang naging independent ka hanggang sa nagsarili ka nag rent ka with your classmates?</i>
47	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay itong 2nd part or the interview is about your experiences nung self review na so this is like... yung parang ano ito, your opinions and views about what happened with your review so after graduation, kung baga shi nortern natin yung 4 years mong pag-aaral; nung mag self review ka na.</i>
		<i>The initial question is, kung may identify ka, anung reasons or factors that influenced you to decide to self review?</i>
48	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually ganito kasi yon, ahh diba pag mag bo-board ka mag rereview ka, mag review center . Nagkayabangan kami ng kuya ko parang nagkaroon eh kasi siya magbabayad ng review center, parang sige yung pera sayo na lang mag self review ka na lang parang ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
49	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sayo na lang yung pera, eh ako mayabang, sige kako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talaga</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

50	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kaya yun, napa self-review ako, pero it was not really planned, siguro kung hindi nagkaganon nagreview center din ako. Pero mayabang nga, mayabang kuya ko, mayabang din ako napa-oo ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Chinallenge ka ?</i>
51	Mr. NurseN	<i>Napasubo na lang din ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Napasubo ka na lang din.</i>
52	Mr. NurseN	<i>Eventually narealize ko nga yun eh, parang siyempre nung hindi pa ako nag bo-board exam, parang inaano mo rin ang sarili ko na napasubo ako ah, parang mali ahh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero di ka na makauwi ron?</i>
53	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi na ako maka-atras eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, meron bang in-indorse yung school ninyo na review center?</i>
54	Mr. NurseN	<i>Meron, kasi yung ibang mga profs ko are affiliated sila sa review center, some of the review centers so they recommended this review center -R.U.N. (a review center).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay R.U.N, were you required to attend that review center?</i>
55	Mr. NurseN	<i>In our school?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
56	Mr. NurseN	<i>What do you mean?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay diba nagka in house kayo? Dun sa in-house, sino ba nag review non?</i>
57	Mr. NurseN	<i>Mga prof</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So mga prof ninyo, so after graduation may ni-recommend sila?</i>
58	Mr. NurseN	<i>Na review center?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Recommended lang, hindi naman required?</i>
59	Mr. NurseN	<i>Recommended</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
60	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kasi may mga kaklase ako na nag review sa S.R.G. (a review center)</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, pero kailangan mo mag attend ng review center?</i>
61	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh oo, bago ka mag board exam, its like ahh, nag-ano kasi ako eh... I broke some rules para mag self review ako pero sa school talaga namin before you take board exam, its required.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi naman kailangan dun sa recommended nila basta kailangan mo merong review center?</i>
62	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So anong nangyari? Papano mo na ano yon? Ahh how did you deal with it? How did you go about it?</i>
63	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh taking board exam?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Ah, nung nag self review ka papanong ... papano ka nakapagboard-exam kung wala ka namang review center?</i>
64	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh ganito kasi yan—share ko na rin. Kasi nung college kasi ako, gumagawa ako ng mga pekeng resibo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
65	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pero ano yon para sa mga classmate ko yon, nangingikbak.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
66	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ako yung gumagawa ng resibo nila, ng registration form, let's say na magaling akong pumeke ng mga documents dati.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
67	Mr. NurseN	<i>And yun yung huling huli na penneke kong documents yung resibo ng isang review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
68	Mr. NurseN	<i>So para makapag ano ako, ito po magreview po ako, pero hindi yun totoo talaga. Ginawa ko lang yon, tapos hanggang sa napirmahan na nila yung papers ko, ayon nag live start na ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Napirmahan na nino?</i>
69	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ng school, yung application ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh pinakita mo yung ano don na meron kang...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

70	Mr. NurseN	<i>May pekeng resibo ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, pero mino-monitor nila o hindi?</i>
71	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi hindi, basta titingnan lang nila yon. Okay, anyway ang down payment yata sa review is mga P4,000 or P3,000 alangan namang sayangin mo yung P3,000 para pakita sa kanila, so inisip nila mag-rereview talaga ito but they didn't know peke yung resibo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay kuha ko na. When did you decide? kailan kayo nagkasubukan ni kuya mo? Before graduation, or after graduation?</i>
72	Mr. NurseN	<i>After graduation</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After graduation mga how many days or weeks or months after graduation?</i>
73	Mr. NurseN	<i>I don't know mga weeks after 2 weeks</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 weeks after.</i>
74	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh, hindi ganito kasi yun naalala ko na, meron kasi kakilala kuya ko naggraduate din ng nursing eh nag review center siya, nagreview-center siya na sa ibang review center, tapos parang sige kuya hiram in ko yung mga review papers ni Mutya. "Mutya" yung pangalan. Oh sige. Tapos habang papunta kami dun, dun niya ako inano na kunin mo na lang kaya lahat ng reviewer niya, sayo na lang pera ko, yung pambayad sa review center. Sabi ko sige, pera yun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, okay so nung nag decide ka na, sinabi mo ba yan sa magulang mo?</i>
75	Mr. NurseN	<i>Nino?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did they react?</i>
76	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh wala lang supportive naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi sila nag-alala na baka bumagsak?</i>
77	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, I'm not the first in the family na nag take ng board exam. Wala lang. Sabi galingan mo ganyan, tapik sa balikat, pero wala namang sinabi. Honestly, mga classmate kos hindi nila alam na mag bo-board exam. May mga pili lang akong mga classmates ko, like 3,</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>na nakaalam na magboboard ako, na nakaregister ako for review center na yung the rest di nila alam na magboboard exam ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban dun sa Mutya na yon, ay sorry nag review center siya diba, meron ka bang kakilala na di nagreview maliban nung mga panahon na yon?</i>
78	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually lahat ng mga classmate ko yata nun nag review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay over all, if you describe in one sentence, ano yung madi-describe mo dun sa nangyari sa'yo, yung experience mo?</i>
79	Mr. NurseN	<i>It's challenging</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Challenging?</i>
80	Mr. NurseN	<i>Challenging</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What made you say so?</i>
81	Mr. NurseN	<i>Because before mag exam ka di mo alam yung i-exam mo. Kasi may part din na ano eh, siyempre may kakilala din ako na nag rereview center and they didn't know na mag-eexam ako. Naririnig ko sa kanila na ito yung nirereview namin sa review center, ito yung mga inaral namin and parang pag-ako, hala, hindi ko pa alam yun ah.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah...</i>
82	Mr. NurseN	<i>Parang ganon. Hindi ko pa alam na may ganon pala tapos sinasabi sa mga review center daw, na yun ang lalabas sa exam ganyan ganyan ganito. Di parang siyempre pag naririnig mo na ngayon mo lang narinig yon eh you don't know di parang nakaka-paranoid</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong nakaka-paranoid?</i>
83	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo parang kailangan mo pang... parang kulang pa, kulang or hindi ko alam yan, hindi ko alam yan, parang ganon, parang ganon, kaya challenging.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano yon kadalas nangyayari like nung first part ng review mo o hanggang sa dulo ba may nariririnig ka pa ring ganon na hindi mo alam?</i>
84	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa first part oo, kahit hanggang sa huli may mga ganon pa rin.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero tatlo lang sa kanila yung nakakaalam na mag bo-board exam ka?</i>
85	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kasi yung plano talaga tatlo lang talaga but since yung isa dun madaldal, siguro ang nakaalam dun mga 10 na kasi madaldal yung iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay</i>
86	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hanggang sa sinabi ko na lang na huwag mo na lang sabihin sa iba... kasi ang purpose nun, para pag bumagsak ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
87	Mr. NurseN	<i>Walang tabla, e kapag nakapasa e di mayabang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay. Nagkaroon ka ba ng issues about dun sa mga sinabi mo nga kanina na hindi mo alam na naririnig mong ganon...Maliban dun sa mga issues na yun, let's say before or during your review ahh challenges nung nagreview ka, kung meron man?</i>
88	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh yung fact na hindi alam ng mga classmate ko. Siyempre yung iba yung mga hindi magreview pupunta sa ganito kung baga sa siyempre attach ka pa rin sa kanila kasi kakagraduate niyo lang tapos mapapasama ka, kunyari gigimik sa labas siyempre ikaw gusto mo ring lumabas parang ang inaano ko non parang pagka madalas akong hindi nakikita baka magduda sila na may ginagawa 'to, nagreview 'to, kaya madalas lumalabas ako nung mga panahon na yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So in terms of mga review materials so ano, yung issue sa pamilya o sa school --nagkaroon ka ba ng issue na ganon na?</i>
89	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala naman, yun lang yung parang separation feeling na naiiba ka na?</i>
90	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Di ka makasama dun sa grupo?</i>
91	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, kasi sama-sama sila sa review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, pumasok ba sa isip mo na kahit nandon ka na nagreview ka na, na mag quit? Were you tempted to quit o kaya naisip mo na sana na nag review center na lang ako?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

92	Mr. NurseN	<i>Naisip ko talaga yon, na sana nag review center na lang ako, lalo na yung mga naririnig ko sa labas, lalo pa na nasasabi na magaling daw, magaling, magaling eh ikaw ano bang meron ka, para bang sabi nila magaling yung prof mo, magaling yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagtuturo?</i>
93	Mr. NurseN	<i>Magaling yung nagtuturo, ganyan talagang matututo ka, ganyan-ganyan eh ikaw ano bang meron sayo sarili mo lang, parang ano ba sa tingin mo magaling ba ako kaya nga, kaya nga naisip ko din na sana nagreview center na lang ako. Oo, nasa isip ko rin yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung nangyari sa'yo like after your review, ano naging pakiramdam mo nung immediately after, yung confidence level mo?</i>
94	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa board exam?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka pa nag-eexam, nung magte-take ka pa lang?</i>
95	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ay magte-take pa lang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
96	Mr. NurseN	<i>ahh not confident.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In a scale of 10, 10 is the highest</i>
97	Mr. NurseN	<i>6</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>6. Okay after you took the board exam, hindi mo pa alam yung result.</i>
98	Mr. NurseN	<i>it became 4</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>4?</i>
99	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo bumaba kasi mahirap talaga yon, ahh I mean I'm not sure kung after talaga nun papasa ako. I was not that confident.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
100	Mr. NurseN	<i>Papasa ako, papasa ba yung ginawa ko?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ano naging pakiramdam mo after nung pumasa ka?</i>
101	Mr. NurseN	<i>ahh actually...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo nalaman na pumasa ka?</i>
102	Mr. NurseN	<i>May...may isa akong kaklase... e di alam mo ng dadating yung results ng board exam diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
103	Mr. NurseN	<i>Alam mo na darating yung result tapos siyempre nagtatago parang ayaw kong malaman, gusto ko yung ipatay yung cellphone, pero meron akong isang kaklase, yung bestfriend ko. Alam niya na magbo-board exam ako, tinatawagan niya ako. Tinawagan niya ako pinapatay ko, parang one time nung mga gabi na, sinubukan ko sagutin na. "Oy bagsak ka, bagsak ka parang expected ko. Okay lang, okay lang" pero ano... yun pala joke lang. "Hindi, pasado ka ganyan ganyan siyempre hindi ako naniwala nung una kasi nga kasi nga hindi ako confident eh, naniwala na lang ako nakita ko pumasa ako sa...sa internet tas yon natuwa ako siyempre.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Natuwa ka. Nung naghihintay ka ng result, nababanggit mo ba sa magulang mo na yung pakiramdam mo na baka hindi ka pumasa?</i>
104	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, nasabi ko na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong sabi nila?</i>
105	Mr. NurseN	<i>Okay lang yon eh kasi ang plano non pag di ka pumasa edi yung 2nd take mag review center ka na, parang ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
106	Mr. NurseN	<i>Parang hindi rin sila, hindi rin sila ganon ka nag e-expect parang kung бага kasi ang ano ko ang palabas kasi non parang try lang give it a shot.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Si kuya mo anong sabi sayo, nung naghahantay ka pa lang?</i>
107	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ayun ganon nga rin tipong pag hindi ka papasa edi mag review center ka na lang basta kung бага ang ano non, tinstesting ko lang, testing ko lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung after you graduated, meron ka pa bang kapatid na nag-aaral o ikaw na lang?</i>
108	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ako na lang.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sila tapos. Ano sa tingin mo yung advantages or disadvantages of having self-review?</i>
109	Mr. NurseN	<i>You're on your own yung parang kasi kung iisipin mo nasa disadvantage yon kasi kung titingin ka sa labas ahh parang masasabi mo na wala, kasi tulad nga ng sinasabi nila na magaling yung nagtuturo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
110	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ganyan ganyan kumpleto sa review materials. Ahh masasabi nila na ano may nakuha ka, kung baga you're on you own na hindi mo alam kung anong kalagayan ganyan- ganyan. Advantage din yung you're on your own kasi you manage your time.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Manage your time tapos...</i>
111	Mr. NurseN	<i>Tapos you manage your time, tapos your studying habits mga ganon yung style mo nagagawa mo sa sarili mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang style mo non?</i>
112	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh style ko non, ganito kasi yon, yung pag graduate ko ng college, it's March may mga kaklase akong...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>sige tumigil, okay (the recorder stop)</i>
113	Mr. NurseN	<i>...pag graduate ko ng March may mga kaklase akong hindi grumaduate may binagsak na test yun yung review, review eh nandun yung basta hindi sila pumasa don so nung nag bo-board exam na ako since nag-aral ako sa sarili ko ang ginagawa ko para matandaan ko ako yung nag le-lecture sa kanila ako yung...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw yung nag le-lecture?</i>
114	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, sa kanila sa mga kasi parang every week may exam sila ganyan. Kunyari ang exam nila is Anatomy, inaral ko na yung Anatomy then iaano ko sa kanila yun i-rereview mo sila or le-lecture ran ko sila kung pano ang style nung review center kung baga ang style ko I'm the reviewer of my classmates.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga? So gaano katagal yung ginawa mo non</i>
115	Mr. NurseN	<i>Natapos nila sila ng May ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

116	Mr. NurseN	<i>April-May yung patapos ng May ganon tas yung mga ganon na cover namin yun most of the topics so usually yung natitirang araw na I'm on my own ahh dun ko na lang inaral yung mga katulad ng halimbawa Community nursing mga ganyan ganyan. May mga topics kasi na hindi namin nadaanan eh na sa pag aano rereview ko sa kanila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say, for example, after nila ng buong week na yon nag-attend sila ng review center pagkatapos nun rereviewhin mo pa sila?</i>
117	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi, it was not a review center kasi. Ang ano kasi dun, parang tine-test na lang sila parang may ni le-lecture pero hindi siya sa review center parang tine-test na lang sila, test test ganyan so ako yung sa pag gabi. Mahirap din kasi yung ano, I have to find my time to study then I have to find the time to lecture them, to have a review with them.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sinong tine-test na lang sila nino?</i>
118	Mr. NurseN	<i>Nung school, ng mga profs naming. Parang ayon my lecture sila ganyan and at the end of the day, at the end of the week may test.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Teka, bago ba ito mag graduation or after mag graduation?</i>
119	Mr. NurseN	<i>After graduation</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Even after graduation?</i>
120	Mr. NurseN	<i>Diba bumagsak sila? Bumagsak sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan?</i>
121	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa subject na yon; sa review ang pangalan ng subject Nursing Audit</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, Nursing Audit.</i>
122	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, Nursing audit, so bumagsak sila don then ako yung nag-aano sa kanila tumulong, tinutulungan ko sila para</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>bumagsak sila sa Nursing Audit?</i>
123	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero graduate na kayo nun?</i>
124	Mr. NurseN	<i>Graduate na ako, sila hindi pa.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh iba mong mga kaklase yon?</i>
125	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nag sabay sabay kayo nag take ng exam?</i>
126	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh nahuli sila.</i>
127	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, 2nd batch</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2nd batch sila, okay so after graduation nung school year na yon, let's say nung April, pinatapatuloy pa rin nila yung Nursing Audit?</i>
128	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, tapos nag ne Nursing Audit pa sila ulit.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun yong mga batch nung nag review center ka kaso hindi pa sila graduate?</i>
129	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi pa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, mga kakilala mo yon?</i>
130	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, mga kakilala ko, mga classmate ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Classmate mo din? so yung iba pala sa inyo hindi naka graduate?</i>
131	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka makakagraduate pag di ka pumasa ng Nursing Audit?</i>
132	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay kuha ko na, may nagging effect ba sa'yo yung self review? sa sarili mo?</i>
133	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh oo, tumaas yong confidence ko na magagawa ko rin... yung confidence mo na, na magagawa mo rin sa sarili mo yung mga bagay-bagay mga ganon, tumaas yung confidence ko sa sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tumaas yung confidence mo. Yung sa buhay mo ngayon-- yung confidence mo ba na yon nakakaapekto pa rin sayo o hindi?</i>
134	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, parang masasabi ko rin na makakaya ko din yon kunyari may bagay kang haharapin, masasabi mo sa sarili mo na makakaya ng ability mo yun, parang mga ganon</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kaya mo din</i>
135	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, magagawa ng ability mo yun, parang tiwala lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tiwala ka lang sa sarili. Papanong pagtitiwala ginawa mo non? (hahaha)</i>
136	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pagtitiis, mahirap yon, pagtitiis. Wala ka ng magagawa eh, siyempre pray ka din sa Diyos na bigyan ka ng tiwala sa sarili, tsaka ng knowledge.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung pumasa ka na, anong reaction sayo? Let's say nalaman mo na yung news na yon na akoy pumasa sa internet naconfirm mo na, papano mo sinabi sa magulang mo? Sa pamilya mo?</i>
137	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh nalaman nila ano eh, tinawagan ko sila kasi sabi ko pumasa pala ako ng board exam, nasa probinsya sila nung panahon na yon, ahh ganon natuwa sila tas yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano sabi nila?</i>
138	Mr. NurseN	<i>ahh magaling, magaling tas binigyan nila ako ng pera binigay nila pang review ko dapat</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pang review mo dapat?</i>
139	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, na pera siyempre natuwa na din ako, eh pera yon (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero ahh para sana sa pangalawa?</i>
140	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, yun yong supposedly mag rereview nga ako, eh since hindi nga ako nag review pang-enroll ko sana binigay na nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh hindi nila binigay yon muna</i>
141	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi, binigay lang nila yon nung ano nung pumasa na ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
142	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kung di ako papasa di ko din makukuha yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh talagang kailangan mong peke-in yung resibo kasi wala kang pangbigay don diba?</i>
143	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo wala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, si kuya mo ano sabi?</i>
144	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ayon natuwa din siyempre, siyempre lahat naman natuwa eh.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa school</i>
145	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa school, oo ayon sa school natuwa din sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pagkapasa mo anong ginawa mo?</i>
146	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung malaman mo na pumasa ka, may ginawa ka ba? Tumawag ka ba o ano?</i>
147	Mr. NurseN	<i>Nagpasalamat ako sa Diyos kasi I believe na hindi talaga yun mangyayari kung hindi sa kanya, isa yun sa pinakamalaking blessing na binigay ng Dios na pumasa ako. I prayed, I prayed.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pinakamalaking blessing</i>
148	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Isa sa mga pinakamalaki?</i>
149	Mr. NurseN	<i>Na nakapasa ako, kaya nagpapasalamat ako, I believe na hindi yon mangyayari kung hindi ako nag pray or kung hindi will ni God.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Considering na 80 above yung nakuha mo diba? Tapos sabi pa ng kaklase mo eh hindi ka pumasa.</i>
150	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ha? Hindi ano, joke niya lang yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos ano yung confidence level mo after nung nag take ka board exam?</i>
151	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kasi ganito kasi nangyari non...yung ano yung 1st part ng exam actually ano ba yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Foundation</i>
152	Mr. NurseN	<i>Foundation skill in nursing diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, fundamentals</i>
153	Mr. NurseN	<i>Fundamental, nag e-exam ako tapos parang eh ang dali non, parang 'ito lang ba yon? Hindi naman sa pagmamayabang ito na ba yon board exam? Inaano ko, yung pinapetsics ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh</i>
154	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ayon tas hanggang sa nalaman ko nasa 80 palang pala ako , tama 80 tama 83 ganyan , tapos time na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
155	Mr. NurseN	<i>Time na, di ba may time limit?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 hours yun eh</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

156	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo 2 hours yun oo, yun na yun, basta nung time na edi yung the rest di ko na siya nabasa or na ano so parang kaya..kaya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>minadali mo na lang</i>
157	Mr. NurseN	<i>tas simula nung ano na yon 1st part ko pa lang, parang 11 items or parang 20 items yata yon hindi ko na kagad sigurado and bukod pa yon sa mga hindi mo, hindi mo pinapatalo ganyan. Kaya parang dun pa lang, alanganin na ako, paano ba ito? Gets mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papanong napaniwala mo sarili mo na 80 pala ako, 80 + ako... ang taas ng rating na yon ha.</i>
158	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ha?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Considering na marami kang hindi nasagutan or minadali mo, papanong nangyari yun?</i>
159	Mr. NurseN	<i>Di ko rin alam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Di mo rin alam (exchanged smiles)</i>
160	Mr. NurseN	<i>Di ko rin alam, basta natatandaan ko. Kahit nga nung kumukuha na ako ng license eh baka sabihin 'hoy mali pa ito' parang ganon hanggang sa nakuha ko na nga yung license ko, nakapasa na nga ako parang ganon, pero nung ano hindi pa naman ako naniniwala nung ano, kung baga sa internet baka magbago pa ganyan kasi hindi talaga ako confident baka palitan pa nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero hanggang ngayon hindi ka pa rin naniniwala?</i>
161	Mr. NurseN	<i>Naniniwala ako, siyempre. Anjan na yun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kinaya mo yung, I mean mataas talaga yung nakuha mo dun, I mean looking back to the questions themselves ah yung naisip mo ba na nasagot mo talaga yung tanong o nagkataon lang?</i>
162	Mr. NurseN	<i>Siguro some of them alam ko, some of them siguro parang ganito yata yon, eto nga parang nabasa ko na eh, ito yata yon, yan yata yon, you're not that 100% sure sa lahat ng tanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Thank you. The next set of questions is about your strategies siguro mga more on details na 'to, technicalities about how did you do it, so it's not more of the views na or insights mo, paano mo talaga ginawa review mo. Ahh pwede mo bang ikuwento papano mong ginawa siya nung nagreview ka?</i>
163	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ganito kasi, nung una pagka graduate na pagka graduate ko nag plano ako na gumawa ng reviewer.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
164	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa sarili ko, kaya bumili na ako nun ng notebook ko. Eh susulatan ko, ang ginawa ko nun, babasahin ko yung libro. Hindi ako nag reviewer, hindi ako nag reviewer. Actually, nag gather ako ng mga reviewer pero hindi ko rin sila nagamit kasi yung mga ginamit ko talaga is yung, yung mga books talaga yun Funda, MS..Su..</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Suddarth (author)?</i>
165	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, Suddarth, ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Brunners?</i>
166	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, Brunners, yun talaga yung mga ginamit ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So may mga libro ka, mga libro mo yun?</i>
167	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo mga libro ko. Actually dun ko nga lang sila nagamit talaga eh. Nung nagreview na ako like binasa ko, ang ginagawa ko, sinusulat ko siya in a summary before pa pagka graduate ko mga siguro after 3 weeks ganon grumaduate ako eh ahh ginawa ko yon. Hindi ko pa alam nun na magboboard exam ako, parang ginawa ko lang siya in preparation and yung mga kalagitnaan na dun na nga nangyari yung 'hala mag boboard exam ako, mag board exam ka na nga ganyan ganyan, so parang before ko pa nalaman na mag bo-board exam ako, somehow parang may 20% na preparation na ako na sa sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May notes ka na.</i>
168	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo may notes na ako, and then yun na rin ginawa ko na rin yung ano, yung nino-notes ko ini-style ko siya parang like na lesson plan parang dun sa mga kaklase ko kasi they ask talaga ng tulong</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailangan pumasa sila muna ng Nursing Audit bago sila magboard?</i>
169	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo bago sila mag-</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, dun ka nag leecture ganon?</i>
170	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, so I took it as an opportunity para matulungan din yung sarili ko. Actually yun nga ang pinaka malaking tulong na naano sa akin, yun pa ang pinakamalaking tumulak sa akin na rereviewhin kasi I was forced to study.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...to study</i>
171	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yeah, I was forced to study.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yun, nasabihan ka lang na 'review-hin mo naman kami' ganon, paano ang nangyari?</i>
172	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, parang ganon review-hin mo naman kami eh they're my close friends eh. Mga babae yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan sila?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

173	Mr. NurseN	5
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>5 sila, ano yon saan kayo nag rereview?</i>
174	Mr. NurseN	<i>Minsan sa bahay nung isa, sa bahay naman nung isa ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ganon</i>
175	Mr. NurseN	<i>Minsan sa labas parang ganito, pag-usually gabi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gabi. So gabi, ano yon nag kaklase pa rin ba sila o hindi na?</i>
176	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo nag kaklase pa rin sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Klaseng...</i>
177	Mr. NurseN	<i>I don't know what they were doing pag ano eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
178	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh ang alam ko talaga basta may exam at the end of the week or Friday they had an exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>nagkaroon ka ba ng issue about time constraints?</i>
179	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano yon?</i>
180	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pero what do you mean by constraints yung kulang ka sa oras?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo,oo</i>
181	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo kasi yung feeling ko nun ahh 'bukas na yung board exam' hindi ko pa nababasa yung ano eh Ortho..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung ortho (Orthopedic nursing).</i>
182	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala pa akong alam sa Ortho, wala pa akong alam sa... hindi sa walang alam, I mean hindi ko pa nababasa yung Ortho, hindi ko pa nababasa yung skeletal, ano pa ba neuro..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Psychiatric?</i>
183	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi neuro-skeletal</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga nervous system. neurological disorder</i>
184	Mr. NurseN	<i>Neuro- skeletal , ahh paralysis, mga ganon. Well, na ano talaga kami, na pressure din ako nung bago mag board exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh pero di mo nagawan ng paraan?</i>
185	Mr. NurseN	<i>Di na talaga, ahh ayon nga ang ginawa ko na lang don natulog na lang ako eh kesa antukin ka sa board exam tas ngayon natulog na lang ako ng natulog ng maaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh papano ka ba nag-aaral papanong study habit mo, time of day?</i>
186	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala akong definite time.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala kang definite time</i>
187	Mr. NurseN	<i>As long as I am on the mood.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh kailangan may mood?</i>
188	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo I'll do it, pag wala kahit anong gawin ko di ko gagawin yon but I was forced to be on the mood nga kasi yung mga kaklase ko naman, kailangan at this day aralin na namin ito ang ano ha, Maternal (nursing), aralin na natin ito okay okay edi I was forced to.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Teka ilang beses sa isang linggo niyo ginagawa yon?</i>
189	Mr. NurseN	<i>Like 2</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 beses. So kailan ka nagbabasa ng sarili mo lang?</i>
180	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh panong kelan?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo yung lecture mo sa kanila tsaka yung review mo sa sarili mo</i>
181	Mr. NurseN	<i>Usually ganon, morning before the lecture o kaya a day before, ganyan dapat prene-prepare ko na ng maigi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero papano ka nagbabasa, nasa oras or walang oras?</i>
192	Mr. NurseN	<i>Walang oras.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo nasusunod yung plan mo? Sinabi mo kanina, lesson plan.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

193	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh ano kasi siya, yung style ng pagsusulat ko, kung makikita mo kasi siya, para siyang reviewer style, diba yung mga kina-Carl Balita (reviewer)?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
194	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yung mga reviewer nila gumawa ako ng sarili kong parang ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>By system?</i>
195	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo by system, by topic, gumawa ako non, yun nga lang nasa kaklase ko yon eh, hiniram nila, ginawa nilang reviewer, nung sila na yung magbo-board exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nagamit mo?</i>
196	Mr. NurseN	<i>Okay, nasusunod mo ba yung ano mo nun, yung</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>gusto kong oras?</i>
197	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi, yung lesson plan mo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo nung bago ko na tinuturo sa kanila, kasi parang ang siste non, sinulat ko sa ganito, sinulat ko sa notebook ko eh ang pagtuturo ko sa kanila may blankong papel, tapos may blangkong notebook tas habang tinuturo ko heto yung parang ganon eto yong ano oh this is cardio this is ido-drawing ko kunyari yung pulmonary. Again, on the blank paper para mapupwersa ako na maalala ko.</i>
198	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oh nice.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Edi ganon yung strategy ko, siguro ganon nga talaga yung pinaka strategy na nagawa ko. I have a lesson plan, I explain it to my self, I know how to explain this and then pagkaharap ko na sila parang...</i>
199	Mr. NurseN	<i>parang irereteach mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>oo</i>
200	Mr. NurseN	<i>I have a blank paper tas 5 concepts ganyan, ayon parang habang tinuturo ko parang nandyan sila habang tinuturo ko, tinuturo ko sa blank paper, para yung papel na yon na nasulat namin nung gabi na yon, sa kanila na yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga gano katagal yon? Anong oras nag-uumpisa usually? Anong oras natatapos, mga ilang oras?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

201	Mr. NurseN	<i>Di ko ma sure yung time eh, siguro mga 2 hours.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 hours</i>
202	Mr. NurseN	<i>3 hours siguro, kasi they still have to sleep, mga ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh pano niyo tinuturo yung, let's say, Research o kaya na Professional Adjustment? Di naman na do-drawing yun.</i>
203	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kunyari ano, okay ito yung 2 types of nursing, ahh 2 types of research kunyari ganon, Qualitative-quantitative tas habang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh may dialogue ka</i>
204	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo tapos habang sinusulat ko iexplain ko yun sa kanila, ito yung ibig sabihin nyan, ganyan, tapos susulat kong konti--- tapos sila nakikinig naman sila, yon ganyan yan ganyan tas susulat ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, tanong ko na lang ganito, yung tinuturo mo sa kanila galing din sa libro mo?</i>
205	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa notebook ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, sa notebook mo?</i>
206	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sinulat ko na, ini style ko na sa notebook ko na iniisip ko na itinuturo ko na sa kanila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilang libro yung source mo? O yun lang ba libro mo?</i>
207	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ilang libro?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say one particular topic ahh</i>
208	Mr. NurseN	<i>Kung ano yung libro talaga sa school, yun talaga ginagamit ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah yung sa school? Yung venue, ahh okay venue sa iba ibang lugar diba? Kapag mag-isa ka lang, saang venue?</i>
209	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa sarili ko?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>oo</i>
210	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa bahay lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa bahay, saang sulok ng bahay normally?</i>
211	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa roof top namin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa roof top nag-aano bakit mo napili roof top?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

212	Mr. NurseN	<i>May shade naman yon, ewan ko parang condusive, I find it condusive.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kahit maraming tao katulad nito, o mag-isa ka lang?</i>
213	Mr. NurseN	<i>Mag-isa lang ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maalala mo ba yung mga inaral mo sa, halimbawa, Funda? (Fundamentals of nursing)</i>
214	Mr. NurseN	<i>oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo sinasagot na lang, let's say sa Funda ahh yung mga questions is about ahh procedure, Nursing Fundamentals, nursing theories. Nung habang nag-e-exam ka, papano mo sinasagot yung mga questions, paano ka mag- analyze ng isang tanong?</i>
215	Mr. NurseN	<i>I go from the basics muna, parang ang ano dyan ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Everything in general na lang</i>
216	Mr. NurseN	<i>In general ahh alam mo yung basic na concept. Kunyari ahh kunyari MS, MS dapat alam mo yung, yung kunyari blood flow, blood flow ganyan, Anatomy ganyan ano yun lahat ng anatomy, let's go with Anatomy first and the Psychology and then ia-analyze ko siya kunyari Myocardial Infarction or MI ahh hihina yung parang idi-disrupt ko yung Anatomy parang don ko igagaling sa anatomy na hanggang sa...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung maydidis-rupt yung normal physiology?</i>
217	Mr. NurseN	<i>Parang dun ko na lang din ipapasok yung mga gamot, mga procedures, yung mga Nursing Care Plan parang ganon, huhugutin mo yung sagot from the basic, hindi mo siya tatandaan na ito yung sagot para dito, hindi ito yung sagot para sa tanong na ganito, sa situation ulit huhugutin mo yung sagot from the basic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>from the basic?</i>
218	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yeah.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo incorporate yong,let's say, Pharma (pharmacology and therapeutics)?</i>
219	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pharma, kunyari anong tawag dito anti-depressant, depressant pampababa ng sakit so parang I- corporate mo yung lahat mababa tapos sa gamot na ito na kapag may adverse effects, like ito yong</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>magiging adverse effect yung lahat ng bumababa, mga dizziness; mga ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ano yon parang by logic?</i>
220	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo by logic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh ganon ang approach mo?</i>
221	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>From basic tapos i-corporate mo yung ibang concepts?</i>
222	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, parang ganon nga hindi mo siya tatandaan na pag ito yung tanong ito yung sagot parang ganon nage-gets mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
223	Mr. NurseN	<i>Pagka ito yung tanong ganun ung tanong ito yung sagot "letter B" huhugutin mo siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung ano yung basic, kung ano alam sa concept na yan?</i>
224	Mr. NurseN	<i>Nagegets mo ba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, naintindihan. Sa ano, sa Psyche (psychiatric)?</i>
225	Mr. NurseN	<i>Sa Psyche?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo sinasagot?</i>
226	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yung aalamin mo yung mga para saan yung neuro transmitters, bakit neuro transmitter na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So Anatomy pa din, Physiology?</i>
227	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, sabi ko nga Physiology and then sa mga Nursing Care Plan parang huhugutin mo siya na parang, kunyari, ang prioritization huhugutin mo siya pag may mga tanong diba galing sa nursing care plan for this di huhugutin mo siya sa priority case mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May basic ganon</i>
228	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo basta lagi kang may paghuhugutan ng basic. Parang ganon ang concept sa pagsagot lagi kang may paghuhugutan ng basic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Basic concept. So, kailangan alam mo yung basic?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

229	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, alam mo yung basic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung review mo ba dine sign mo sa basic o papano mo in-approach? Papanong naging approach mo?</i>
230	Mr. NurseN	<i>Parang ganon nga in-approach ko siya from basic, kunyari dun sa MS, yung pulmo (pulmonary) patent yung airway tapos ito yung lalabas, ito yung koneksyon ng sakit ganon, ito yung paglumabas na sakit, pagka ganon, dugtong-dugtong na sila, from basic lagi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halimbawa may question dyan, normally interrelated na, integrated na lahat ng concepts sa board exam diba? Maraming subjects ganon?</i>
231	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pinag sasama-sama mo?</i>
232	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo parang ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay ahh</i>
233	Mr. NurseN	<i>Magulo ba yon? magulo ba yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi nakukuha ko, pareho din kasi ako. Nagkaroon ka ba ng relaxation moments or techniques in between or while you were reviewing?</i>
234	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually ang plano ko nun, wala talagang relaxation pero parang di naman yata talaga maiiwasan yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ka mag relax?</i>
235	Mr. NurseN	<i>Parang nung una yun nga, pag lumalabas yung mga classmates ko napapasama ako. Hindi naman talaga dapat, kung бага kung iaano ko yung schedule ko dapat hindi ako sasama don ahh siguro natural sa akin yung ganon na kahit ayaw ko nagyayari talaga natural na sa akin yung maghanap ng relaxation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Habang nagbabasa ka mayroon ka bang kinakain na chitcha o like junk food or anything, finger foods?</i>
236	Mr. NurseN	<i>Habang nagbabasa, wala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala</i>
237	Mr. NurseN	<i>What I was doing since inaabot ako ng gabi. Usually time kasi ng pag-aaral ko, minsan gabi or inaabot ako ng paumaga, ewan ko.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paumaga?</i>
238	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mula gabi hanggang umaga?</i>
239	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo or mga tipong mag start ako 1 (morning) ganyan, I find it kasi tahimik eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1 am?</i>
240	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, 1 am and then dun sa roof top pag minsan pag nagugutom ako kumakain ako mag isa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Teka, twice a week kayo nag rereview o tumutulong ka para mag lecture, mga ilang beses ka sa isang linggo nakakapag-aral sa sarili mo lang?</i>
241	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi kasi pare-pareho, iba-iba</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung maximum? Kung natatandaan mo, mga 2..3 ganon?</i>
242	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo mga ganon 2..3</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maski malapit na yung exam?</i>
243	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yung malapit na yung board exam namin parang ano nag ano pume-petics petics lang ako nun kahit alam ko na, hindi naman pume petics, parang pinipilit kong i-rush kaso ayaw kong parang nadaan/nabasa ko lang di mo naman naintindihan kung ano lang yung na-absorb ko siguro nung time na yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung mga subject mo na nahhirapan ka, tingin mo?</i>
244	Mr. NurseN	<i>Community</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nahirapan kang pag-aralan, Community...</i>
245	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo kasi Community, yun yung concept na wala akong... diba ang sabi ko nga, ang concept ko, ang style ko ay huhugutin ko siya sa basic eh yung community you have to remember sino si ganyan diba, COPAR diba, COPAR okay lang pero yung community diba iaano mo, kung sino yung mga, may mga rules, sila yung nagpa... basta di ko na maalala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say yung mga R.A. (republic acts) ganon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

246	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo yung mga R.A. ganyan, dyan ako nahirapan kasi you have to remember, you have to remember na ito yung R.A. ito yung kung baga wala kang paghuhugutan ng basic walang concept kaya ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, yung ano, kamusta naman yung result ng exam mo? Ahh saan ka mababa, saan ka mataas? Nakita mo ba yung result? Kung natatandaan mo.</i>
247	Mr. NurseN	<i>Part 1 is okay, Part 3 yata yun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Part 3, yung MS yun</i>
248	Mr. NurseN	<i>Part 2 Community ata yon part 2, part 2</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh Community</i>
249	Mr. NurseN	<i>Community talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like how, mababa ka talaga?</i>
250	Mr. NurseN	<i>Mababa ako sa ibang part.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How well did your educational program prepare you to pass your licensure exam? Anong naging playing factor?</i>
251	Mr. NurseN	<i>It's a big part kasi, lalo na yung in-house review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In house review</i>
252	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, kasi dun ako kumuha ng ano eh ng style ng pagtuturo parang pano ko I she-share yun, dun ko kinuha yung...parang inisip ko, paano kaya nag-aral itong mga nagrereview sa amin bago kami harapin?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ba sila mag-aral? Yung style nila.</i>
253	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yung ano din, nagsusulat din sila ng habang nagsulat sila, o ito yan ganyan ganito</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala silang ano power point?</i>
254	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano yun gagawin?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

255	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala, wala silang powerpoint, all they had they was this projector yon and sinusulatan nila yung projector, yun ang style nila and...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ganon so papano inaano yung information sa utak mo? Yung memory mo, papano mo ino-organize yung information na yon, yung inaaral mo?</i>
256	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh ganon so papano inaano yung information sa utak mo? Yung memory mo, papano mo ino-organize yung information na yon, yung inaaral mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung papano interconnected yung mga concepts?</i>
257	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo, and then I explain it to myself, on my own all over.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung babalikan mo ngayon, meron ka bang bagay na hindi mo nagawa noon ahh, halimbawa, na dapat sana nagawa mo, kung i-improve mo yung ginawa mo kung meron man ha, meron ka bang na identify na bagay na dapat sana nagawa mo na hindi mo nagawa?</i>
258	Mr. NurseN	<i>Siguro time management. Kasi sabi ko nga diba yung program ko na dapat naaral, hindi ko naaral lahat. Hindi ko naaral yung dapat aaralin. So kung may time management pa ako dapat hindi ako lumabas-labas ganyan, kasi nag-aano pa talaga ako eh gumigimik-gimik so kung hindi ko siguro ginawa yon, baka natapos ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung time management na yon, yung ginawa mong lesson plan hanggang saan mo nagawa? Let's say 1-10, kumbaga anong part na yong..?</i>
259	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh percentage?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo yung natapos mo sa lesson plan mo?</i>
240	Mr. NurseN	<i>mga 85</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>85 % natapos mo naman</i>
261	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you satisfied with the result of your exam?</i>
262	Mr. NurseN	<i>Satisfied</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong mga factors that you can attribute to your, ano sabi mo kanina di ka makapaniwala diba, pero nandyan na yan eh, ang taas</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>ng nakuha mo dib a? May na identify ka bang possible reason kaya mo nakuha yun? Although hindi naman natin alam kasi kung alin dun yung tamang sagot diba pero tingin mo lang sa sarili mo... ahh kung may idea ka syempre ikaw yung nakaachieve non ikaw yun eh so meron ka bang na identify na ano na factor or reason why you achieve that?</i>
263	Mr. NurseN	<i>Siguro number one jan yung tiwala mo sa Diyos.</i>
Researcher:		<i>Tiwala ahh</i>
264	Mr. NurseN	<i>...na magagawa mo ito dahil, dahil nagbibigay ng tiwala si God, yun ang number 1, number 1 then sumunod na lang din siguro yung sa sarili mo, na ability mo na tiwala sa sarili mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So habang yung mga panahon ba na yon nagsisimba ka ba o ano may ginagawa ka bang mga...</i>
265	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually, church musician ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Church musician ka? Anong tinutugtog mo?</i>
266	Mr. NurseN	<i>Keyboard</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh keyboard oh nice. Sa Catholic ba o Born Again?</i>
267	Mr. NurseN	<i>Born again, so yun hindi ko yun pinabayaan kahit nagrereview ako, hindi ko pinabayaan yung ministry.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Habang nag-eexam ka or papano meron ba kayong pray over o pano ba ginagawa dun sa inyo?</i>
268	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ahh wala naman siguro nung before the ahh...Oo nung kasi minsan pag uma-attend ako, kasi yung ibang mga church mates ko, alam nila na may board exam ako. Kapag may prayer meeting ahh sinasali ko na din yung may board exam ako, ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I have last 2 questions, ahh I think last 2 or 3 questions ahh sasama ko na yung last part. Kung may ibibigay kang tips sa, halimbawa, ako nga hindi pa ako nag e-exam, kung may maibibigay kang tips ano bang maibibigay mong tips sa akin sa review?</i>
269	Mr. NurseN	<i>Huwag kang nagrereview na tatandaan mo yung ano, huwag kang nagrereview ng by memorization, do you review na explain it to your self---don't use your memory, use your ahh reasoning.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Reasoning</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

250	Mr. NurseN	<i>Intindihin mo siya, huwag mong kabisahin, intindihin mo yun yung pinakamalaking ano, malaking bahagi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Merong pa ba, merong ka pa bang idadagdag?</i>
271	Mr. NurseN	<i>Siguro kung mag e-exam ka rin ganun din gawin mo ah magmatrabaho magreview sa libro, sa libro talaga pero sulit naman. Parang mas maganda yung kalalabasan, parang ganon, kesa magreview ka ng mga reviewer, mga ganyan, summarized na, mas madali yun pero icompare mo siya dun sa reviewer talaga mas matrabaho pero mas sulit yun, mas malaki yung kalalabasan mas marami kang matutunan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Teka, may follow up ako dyan: sabi mo after 3 weeks mo dun ka nagumpisa gumawa ng ano ng reviewer 20 % ng preparation mo ang kapal kapal ng libro ng nursing papano mo kinompresyon sa ginawa mong reviewer?</i>
272	Mr. NurseN	<i>Hindi naman lahat don ano, hindi naman lahat yon eh some part is introduction some part is like a yung somehow alam na rin naman kung ano yung nakasulat dun eh diba so parang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pinag-aralan mo dati.</i>
273	Mr. NurseN	<i>So parang pinapasok mo na lang sa utak mo na..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What did you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a review to be effective?</i>
274	Mr. NurseN	<i>Discipline. Kasi mahirap lalo na kung mag self review ka, mahirap mag-ano sa sarili mo, parang mahirap kontrolin yung sarili na wag lumabas diba sabi ko nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
275	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala naman talaga sa schedule mo yung labas ka ng labas pero nakakalabas ka pa rin that's why hindi ko nga natapos, so you have to have a discipline also.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Merong pa ba tingin mo</i>
276	Mr. NurseN	<i>Tiwala, tiwala mo sa sarili, sa Diyos.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo tinitiwalaan ang sarili mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

277	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala naman akong ibang pagkakatiwalaan eh, ako rin naman ang gagawa non nasa sa akin din naman yung gawa so pagtiwalaan mo na lang yung gawa mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh last na meron ka bang regrets, nung nag self review ka, after nung pumasa ka na, nalaman mo yung rating mo o ano now looking behind, looking from afar, looking back, meron ka bang regrets na nag self review ka?</i>
278	Mr. NurseN	<i>Wala, ako sa sarili ko wala pero yung mga dating classmate ko bestfriend ko ang inaano nila mas mataas pa sana kanila yung nakukuha ko nung nag review-center ako yun ang sinasabi ko so</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mas mataas yung sa kanila?</i>
279	Mr. NurseN	<i>Mas mataas pa sana yung makukuha ko sa sarili ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, pero mas mataas nakuha nila kesa sayo?</i>
280	Mr. NurseN	<i>Actually they passed the subject, the Nursing Audit, but the board exam I don't know, hindi yata sila pumasa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh ba't nila nasabing mas mataas pa makukuha mo?</i>
281	Mr. NurseN	<i>Ako mataas pa yung makukuha ko sana kung nag review center ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nag review center sila?</i>
282	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo kasi nga maganda daw yung turo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mga nagsabi na maganda yung turo, pumasa naman?</i>
283	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo yung mga nag board exam din na kasabayan ko? Oo naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
284	Mr. NurseN	<i>Oo naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>matataas ba yung nakuha nila</i>
285	Mr. NurseN	<i>ahh that's what I don't know</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Last question is how did it affect you psychologically, mentally, emotionally as a nurse as a person? Kung meron lang naman.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

286	Mr. NurseN	<i>It increased my confidence, yung self-confidence na nagawa ko yon. Na magagawa ko yon kung may ganon man uli, magagawa ko uli, kaya kong gawin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anything you like to add or anything you like to say?</i>
287	Mr. NurseN	<i>Tanong ko lang naguluhan ka ba dun sa sinabi ko noon na kailangan galing ka sa basic</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi, kasi I understand it that's how I do things, too.</i>
288	Mr. NurseN	<i>Yun lang kasi parang ako naguluhan ako sa explanation ko eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay hindi, kasi ganon din ako mag-aral eh.</i>
		END OF RECORDING Time Stamp 1:08:38

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ok, good afternoon ulit. I'm from St. Paul University Manila. Iinterbyuhin kita tungkol sa experience mo sa self-review. Just like what have mentioned earlier, ung apat na parts: una, yung demographics, yung tungkol sa'yo. Pangalawa, yung "experiences" mo; yung pangatlo ay yung strategies, kung meron man, na ginamit mo nung nagrereview ka. At yung pang-apat about some traits that might have helped you during your review.</i> <i>So yung unang part, name mo, nickname, or optional lang naman yan. So, nasayo kung gusto mong ibigay. Yung age mo, ah ilang taon ka na ba, sa ngayon?</i>
1	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa ngayon? 26 na'ko ngayon e. 26 years old.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Twenty-six. Nung grumaduate ka, anong year ka grumaduate?</i>
2	Ms. NurseE	<i>Graduate ako sa SchoolE (University) ay October 12, 2011</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2011. Ah bago lang din pala 'noh? First course mo yung ano..</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

3	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Interrupted...) Sorry, October 12, 2009.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah 2009, okay. Ah so 2009 ka grumaduate, okay, so first course mo yung nursing?</i>
4	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, second course ko na siya. First course ko yung (caregiver), sa Pamantasan. Tapos ladderized nga, sabi ko kanina, 2nd year kagad ako nag-start sa (nursing).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah 2nd year...</i>
5	Ms. NurseE	<i>2nd year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung...ano bang work mo ngayon?</i>
6	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ngayon...Service crew ako ngayon sa Yellow-Cab</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, Yellow Cab..</i>
7	Ms. NurseE	<i>Parang part-time company nurse na rin ako nila, kasi kapag may mga kailangan sa field, ako yung pinadadala, kasi wala talagang company nurse dun. Kasi alam na nilang nurse ako, kapag may kailangan sila, ako yung (pinadadala).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May previous employment ka ba bago mag-Yellow Cab?</i>
8	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala pa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so yun yung first job mo?</i>
9	Ms. NurseE	<i>More on trainings talaga...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so nagtrain ka as a nurse?</i>
10	Ms. NurseE	<i>Training lang ako as a nurse.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano ka katagal?</i>
11	Ms. NurseE	<i>One year din eh. Nag-ano ako, nag-Veterans (Hospital), nag-Lung Center pa ako...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano ka katagal sa Veterans?</i>
12	Ms. NurseE	<i>Veterans...buwan lang yun eh, ang trainings kasi nila 3 months. Lung Center din 3 months.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Three months ka rin dun (Lung Center)...</i>
13	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa Kidney (Hospital) lang yung matagal, nag-6 months.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, 6 months. Ayun yung may bayad 'noh?</i>
14	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, lahat naman ng ano may bayad eh (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw yung magbabayad, hindi sila yung magbabayad sa'yo... (Grins)?</i>
15	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hinintay ko yung hiring, kaso matagal pa kasi, sa dami daw ng nagttrain...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong month o year ka nagtake ng board exam?</i>
16	Ms. NurseE	<i>Right after ng graduation ko. November lang din, kasi that time November pa ang board eh, 2009. Tapos lumabas yung result nun February 1, 2010.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah okay. Tanda mo pa 'noh?</i>
17	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi memorable 'eh (smiles...)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siyempre. Ito optional 'toh, kung gusto mo lang sagutin, yung rating mo. Actually, dalawa lang naman ang nakalagay diyan, 75 to 80, or 80 and above</i>
18	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nasa 80 above ako...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>80 and above rate, galing ah! Private o public yung pinag...(aralan)</i>
19	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Interrupted) Ang SchoolE (University) is "private"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba yan full-private o may subsidized?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

20	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi ko sure ang SchoolE (University) eh. Ang alam ko, sa alahat ng sikat na universities, sila yung may pinakamababa ang tuition fee. Nung nag-iinquire pa'ko nun ha (smiles), nung panahon ko. Ewan ko lang ngayon...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So galing ka sa Pamantansan, nag-ladderized ka ng nursing</i>
21	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nursing:</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Itong second part ng demographics and educational background about knowing you as a person, so ang gustong malaman ko ay kung papano ka lumaki, ano yung mga values mo, beliefs, papano ka pinalaki ng magulang mo; may barkada ka ba, nung high school, kung baga papano mo..Hanggang sa naging college ka..</i>
22	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ako? (thinking)Nung bata? (smiling...)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit mo nagustuhan yung nursing, di ba?</i>
23	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hmm okay. Kasi nung bata kasi, kung baga ako laki sa pangaral sa magulang. Yun ang pinaka-sure ko, kasi nga maka- "mamma's girl" kasi ako eh. So siya yung nung bata pa lang, siya yung guide ko eh. Pero hindi naman siya nurse, pero para sa'kin part ng individual ko na values, more on, sa kanya galing. Kasi father ko, hindi naman siya masyado nag-stay sa Philippines, dahil seaman siya. So more on palaki ako ng mommy. As an eldest, eldest pa'ko, so parang ako lahat, parang responsibility. Yun yung feeling ko na hanggang ngayon meron ako eh. So kailangan e, dahil panganay ka, dapat ikaw yung halimbawa sa kapatid mo. Ikaw dapat yung responsible. Tapos parang ikaw lagi yung dapat na mangunguna sa lahat. Kaya nung bata ako, parang siguro, hindi naging hassle kay mama, nung tinatanong ko pano ako mag-aral nung bata. So parang alam nyang hirap ako sa Math, English, kasi nga parang ano ako eh, parang hirap mag-aral. Maaga kasi ako nag-aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Ilang taon ka nun?</i>
24	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala pang 5 years old, nag-kinder na'ko kaagad. Ang sama nun hindi pa'ko nagnursery, kinder ako kagad nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung elementary, highschool? Naging part ka ba ng mga clubs, or Orgs?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

25	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung high school, nasali naman ako sa extracurricular, yung "Tagsibol", na magazines, C.A.T.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Magazines, naging ano ka officer, o writer?</i>
26	Ms. NurseE	<i>Naging writer ako. Sa C.A.T, naging officer, high officer, naging Core Ex ako. Mga ganon lang naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naging Core ka? Core Commander?</i>
27	Ms. NurseE	<i>Cor-Ex O. 2nd to Core Commander</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Galing ah!</i>
28	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Smiles) Naging ganon ako hanggang sa grumaduate. Sa academics, hindi naman ako nasasama lagi sa top, yung individual na study ko lang, masasabi ko lang, yung sabi sa akin ni mama, ako yung matiyagang bata. Hindi matalino, pero matiyagang mag-aral. So kung may maipagmamalaki, yun nga, yung pagiging matiyaga ko sa pag-aaral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so yung upbringing mo ganon. Normally ba nagspend ka with mga kaibigan, o papano?</i>
29	Ms. NurseE	<i>Normal naman kasi sa high-school di ba yung pagdating ng first year, 2nd year, more on barkada talaga. Pero yung ano, ang pinipili kong barkada noon pa man, yung palaaral na. Kasi nga alam kong weak ako sa ano eh, sa ibang parts ng academics. Parang gusto ko, kahit papano yung magiging friend ko yung, hindi man makopyahan, yung mag-iinquire siya sa akin, tapos sasabayan kong mag-aral. Kasi nga palaaral sila, kaya dun din ako jumojoin. Kasi nga palagi kong iniisip kasi dati na, kasi nga panganay ako, dapat ako yung maging halimbawa lagi sa kapatid ko. Kasi may mga youngest akong kapatid.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan ba kayong magkapatid?</i>
30	Ms. NurseE	<i>Five kaming magkapatid.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos ikaw ang eldest?</i>
31	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ako eldest, tapos yung nag-iisa naming lalaki, pang-apat pa. Majority puro babae kaming lahat.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so nung high-school ka, pano mo naman nagustuhan yung nursing? Anong nangyari?</i>
32	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, hindi talaga nursing yung first ano ko eh, yung first love ko eh. Ang first love ko talaga na gustong pasukin, HRM. Mas gusto ko talagang business and management yung ano ko. Kaya nga bago kami grumaduate, tinanong kami, para kaming may essay or recitation, kung ano kami after 5 years, ang plano ko is business, more on HRM talaga. Hotel and Restaurant Management.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So papano ka nakapasok sa ano, sa nursing?</i>
33	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ayun, ang makulit na story kasi... kapag pinipili kong pumasok sa..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Makulit ha (laughs)</i>
34	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Smiles) sinubukan ko kasing pumasok sa ano eh, sa mga sikat na schools, sa PUP (Polytechnic University of the Philippines), UP (University of the Philippines), kasi ang style ng mga schools na yun, kung alam mo na, kahit na pumapasa ka sa exam, pero kapag merong mga quota, o pataasan. Hindi ako nakakapasok dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay...</i>
35	Ms. NurseE	<i>...ang kinukuha ko HRM hindi ako makapasok-pasok, so hanggang sa nag-open yung Pamantasan. Nagtry pa rin ako ng HRM, hindi pa rin, hindi talaga (smiling)...So nag-caregiver muna ako kasi, ang natirang courses caregiver saka Computer Programming. Kaya sabi ng mama ko, mag-ano ka na lang, mag-caregiver, kasi nga Auntie ko nasa ibang bansa, pupwede nila akong matulungan, kung sakali. E natapos ko yung caregiver, kung bago napagbuti ko naman yung pag-aaral, within 2 years ng caregiver. Yung teacher ko dun sa caregiver, yung parang pinaka-head naming dun; hindi siya Dean eh, kung bago parang instructor talaga siya, siya yung pinaka-head sa caregiver. Siya yung nag-encourage sa akin na mag-ladderized sa Nursing..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, wow</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

36	Ms. NurseE	<i>...sinasabi niya na naging maganda yung performance ko sa caregiver, siguro hindi naman top, parang kami nila Einel nun, kung baga naka-line up kami sa ano..kasi walang top sa ano eh, sa caregiver, kung baga highest ano lang, kung baga nakapasok ka sa top pero hindi ka nakacaregorized as Cum Laude, o Summa Cum Laude, ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kung baga top nung batch niyo?</i>
37	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kung baga nakaline up kami dun. Kaya sabi niya, tuloy ka ng nursing, feeling ko kasi kaya mo, ngayong caregiver ka na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung una HRM ang gusto mo tapos..</i>
38	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun talaga yung first love ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So mapag-aral ka lang talaga, na kahit na anong course, o nagustuhan mo na rin yung nursing?</i>
39	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi dahil sa kung anong sikat nung panahon, ang gusto ko talaga HRM, kasi nga hindi nga ako makapasok sa gusto kong course.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So bakit nag-excel ka sa nursing?</i>
40	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nagustuhan ko yung caregiver. Kasi tama naman noh, pwede rin ako talaga, parang destined rin ako siguro na, baka for ano talaga ako, medical. Kaya tinuloy ko, as encouragement na din nung teacher ko. Sabi niya na try mo lang mag-nursing. Pero dati nag-iisip na'ko kung pagpapatuloy ko yung HRM. Pero sabi niya, sige lang mag-nursing ka. Kaya sinubukan ko, nag-exam kami, nag-interview. Pumasa naman (smiles). Eh pumasa na'ko eh, kaya hindi ko na tinuloy mag-HRM.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Galing ah... Ako kasi diretso na, pero parang ganon din yung kwento ko. Parang ganon din naman yung mga kwento ng mga tao di ba?</i>
41	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pero totoo talaga na nahirapan ako nung mga first part as a nursing student. Kasi nga more on ano kasi demo, puro ganon eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa caregiver ba hindi ganon?</i>
42	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa caregiver meron, pero parang iba na yung concept ng nursing eh, parang mas malalim na dun sa caregiver. Mas nahirapan ako dun sa first at second (year).</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So naging third year ka kagad nung nursing?</i>
43	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi, 2nd year muna kami. One year sa second year, kasi yung curriculum pa before di 'ba, yung sa 2nd sem ng second year merong summer. Pero yung summer ko, dun ko na tinuloy sa SchoolE (University). So bale yung 1st at 2nd year ko sa nursing, sa Pamantasan, tapos yung 2nd year summer ko, lumipat na'ko ng SchoolE (University). Kaya parang dun na'ko nag-2nd year summer class. Parang opening na siya ng ano, ng mga major subjects.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung nandun ka sa caregiver, okay ang performance mo, kaya nasabi nung head niyo na pwede ka sa nursing, kasi nga nasa top ka 'di ba? So dib a nalipat ka ng nursing?</i>
44	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oh huh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung performance mo nung 3rd year, 4th year?</i>
45	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi focused na'ko nun eh, gusto ko siyang matapos. Mahirapan man ako, basta kailangang matapos ko yung kursong kinuha ko. Kasi nga nandun na ako eh. Yun talaga yung feeling ko, baka ditto ako destined eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung (performance) mo sa class ninyo? Yung (class) standing mo, o papano ka makitungo...</i>
46	Ms. NurseE	<i>Parang magkaibang-magkaiba sa (caregiving) kesa nursing, kasi nga sabi ko nahirapan ako sa kurso ng nurse. So kung dati palasagot ako sa klase, that time, mejo ako nun, low-profile ako sa klase.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung 3rd year?</i>
47	Ms. NurseE	<i>3rd year ganon lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung 4th year?</i>
48	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung 4th year, nag-excel na'ko kasi nagkaroon ako ng mga ibang kaibigan eh. Kasi 2nd at 3rd year, sila yung mga kasa-kasama ko, irregular kasi ako nun. Iba-iba yung kasa-kasama, kung baga hindi ako masyadong nag-adhere sa class.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so irregular ka nung una, nung 3rd year.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

49	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, so nung 4th year ko, dun lang ako nagkaroon ng fixed na (mga) kasama.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ba nakatulong yung mga kasama mo? O papano nakatulong?</i>
50	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi yung mga naging barkada ko nung 4th year mother na eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan kayo nun?</i>
51	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, nag-iisa lang siya, kasi may mga barka-barkada na sila nung mapunta ako ng 4th year eh. So parang nung makilala ko sila, yun nga may grupo na rin sila. Pero yung isa sa mga nakasama kong mga mother, naging classmate ko nung irregular ako. Yung isa na, parehas pala kaming single. So kung sino na yung barkada niya, dun na rin ako nasama. Siya lang yung kilala ko din, which is maganda naman yung naging output kasi nga palaaral din yung grupo nila. Kung baga yung isang mother dun, mahilig siyang mag-aral, second course na din niya yung nursing.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mula nung maging caregiver, hanggang maging nursing ka, ano yung mga favorite mong subjects, kung meron man? Meron ka bang naging favorite sa nursing?</i>
52	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa nursing ano, Medical-Surgical (subject)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>M.S.? Wow</i>
53	Ms. NurseE	<i>M.S., yun yung parang mas gusto ko. Para sa akin kasi yun ang pinakamadaling intindihin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pinakamadaling intindihin?</i>
54	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi mas gusto ko yung ano eh, kapag tinatanong ako, "Anong gamot dito? Anong sakit 'to?"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mas gusto mo yung nag-eexplain ka?</i>
55	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, mas gusto ko yung sakit nay un, alam ko. Sa family ko kasi may mga sakit eh: heart disease, diabetes, si mama, high blood. Kung baga nagbasa ako sa Medical-Surgical.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, kung ano yung sakit nila para mapag-aralan mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

56	Ms. NurseE	<i>kaya nafocused ako sa Med-Surg</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa atin di ba, normal na yung nagccase study? Grupo-grupo yun di ba? Normally anong naassign sa'yo? Di ba may mga parts dun like Pharma, Nursing Care Plan, MS, Patho, ganon..</i>
57	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi kasi ako sa mga ganon eh, kasi may mas maraming magagaling dati eh. Dun lang ako sa acknowledgement, yung eexplain ko yung lugar, yung sa ocular inspection. Yun lang yung na-assign sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yun yung mga unang part 'noh? Yung mag-iintroduce sa kanila.</i>
58	Ms. NurseE	<i>More on dun ako, pero sa mga ibang contributions, wala masyado. So kapag may mga pinag-aaralan, may mga inaassign kasi mas feeling ko mas expert siya dun. Ganon nangyari sa'min.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung pagkagraduate mo, kamusta naman yung tingin mo sa pinag-aralan mo ng buong apat na taon? Anong assessment mo sa education na nakuha mo sa apat na taon na yun? Masasabi mo bas a sarili mo na grumaduate ka na may alam ka?</i>
59	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo naman, kasi nga naging proud nga ako ng grumaduate ako as a nurse. Kasi nga hindi ko nga akalain dahil hirap na hirap nun eh, tapos heto na pala ako, nurse, na makakaya ko siya. Saka natutuwa pa rin ako na kasi nga hanggang ngayon, kahit sa work ko, sa family ko, nagagamit ko pa rin siya ngayon. Kahit hindi pa'ko nagwowork as a nurse talaga, sa mga hospitals, atleast may mga naiwan pa ring stock knowledge sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone? Gusto mo bang mag-isa, o gusto mong may kasama ka?</i>
60	Ms. NurseE	<i>Siguro hati, kasi nga may gusto nga ako na palaaral na tao, yung kasabay ko sila na nag-aaral, pero ang ayoko lang kapag groupings na review, yung tanungan. "Anong ganito, ganito?" Yung parang question and answer portion. Dun ako umiiwas.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit naman?</i>
61	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ayoko lang yung maguguluhan ako na mag-iisip ako ng matagal. Kaya gusto ko sabay-sabay lang tayo mag-aral, at mas gusto ko tahimik lang. tahimik ako magreview, pero may mga kasama ako.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, kung baga grupo pero merong..</i>
62	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kung baga individual; kung magbabasa ka, individual, pero kung magtatanungan kayo, okay kayo-kayo lang, pero huwag niyo ako isali kasi parang naguguluhan ako eh, like "ano nga ba yun?" So nag-iisip ako ng matagal. Tanungin mo'ko after ko sigurong magreview, o kaya after kong mag-ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After mong magreview, nagtatanungan din kayo?</i>
63	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi ako nakikipagtanungan eh, hinahayaan ko lang sila. Sila yung magreview, basta ako tahimik lang ako. Nakikicope lang ako sa mga sagot nila. Pero kung ako yung tanungin, at sagutin ko yung tanong nila, kung baga hindi ako masyadong nakikijoin dun. More on ano talaga, grupo pero review ako as individual.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>So nasa second part na tayo ng questionnaire. Ito naman yung sa experiences mo na. So tapos na tayo dun sa background mo, hanggang grumaduate ka. Di ba merong mga habits, tulad nyan gusto mo ng alone ka, o kaya may kasama ka pero gusto mo mag-isa ka lang magbasa. Ano talaga yung naging reason mo, o mga bagay na kinunsider mo kung bakit ka nagdecide to self-review instead of enrolling in a review center?</i>
64	Ms. NurseE	<i>First ah, ano kasi... (thinking)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba ang nangyari nun pagkagraduate mo?</i>
65	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi para sa'kin ang style kasi ng school ko sa SchoolE (University), kasi habang nasa nasa 4th year level na kami nun, may mga major subjects kami nun, duties, clinical, ganyan, kasi parang nagkakarun na kasi ng "pre-review" eh. Meron silang araw, actually araw-araw nga yun eh, na after ng mga klase namin, parang pinapahapyaw tungkol sa mga subjects namin, parang mga pre-reivew pero yung nagreview naming yung mga advisers din naming sa class, at saka yung Dean namin sa nursing. Ganun yung style ng SchoolE (University), may pre-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ganun na yata talaga lahat ngayon e, sa curriculum ganun na...Kasama na.</i>
66	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, subject siya pero hindi siya part ng curriculum. Kapag tiningnan mo kasi yung curriculum ko, wala siya dun eh, pero kapag tiningnan mo yung klase ko sa araw, kasama siya.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mula anong year yun?</i>
67	Ms. NurseE	<i>Fourth year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>First year o second sem?</i>
68	Ms. NurseE	<i>Second sem, nung gagraduate na'ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tuwing anong araw?</i>
69	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi ang pasok ko kasi sa SchoolE (University) maganda na kasi nun eh. From Monday to Friday yata pero wala ng panggabi. More on pang-umaga hanggang hapon. Sinuwerte ako that time na maganda yung nakuha ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos, anong schedule nung review ninyo?</i>
70	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, kasama na siya nun, parang wala akong patay na oras. Kung meron man, break lang, lunch time lang, pero may pasok bago ulit yung next subject, meron kaming pre-review. Lahat ng subjects naming na pwedeng part ng board exam nirereview na nila sa amin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung pwedeng maging part ng board exam? Yung specific sa board exam nay un?</i>
71	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, pero hindi ko din masabi na parang style ng review center kasi nga hindi naman ako nagreview center, pero yung topics naming nun pang-board na, parang pre-review na siya eh, kasi nga may lectures, may discussions, tapos parang may exam kami sa kanila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tuwing anong araw yun?</i>
72	Ms. NurseE	<i>Araw-araw.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilang oras?</i>
73	Ms. NurseE	<i>May three hours, may one and a half, mga ganong oras.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Walang fixed na oras?</i>
74	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi ano eh, per subject kasi yun eh. Heto bay un... (looking at her notes), parang andito siya.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May ganon pala 'noh?</i>
75	Ms. NurseE	<i>(After glancing her notes). TCAP pala, sorry, yun, TCAP ang tawag sa kanya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yun?</i>
76	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun ang tawag naming sa pre-review namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kelan binibigay yung schedule?</i>
77	Ms. NurseE	<i>Every week yan. Every week. Kasi nga marami nga kaming nursing graduating that time, so hinahati yun per section.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung ano yung vacant mo sa subject mo, yun ang nilalagay nila?</i>
78	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun ang nilalagay, yes. Yan, may mga dates nga eh (pertaining to the plotted schedule on her notes). Hayan oh, may M.S., Psyche, Pedia</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, iba-iba rin?</i>
79	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, iba-iba, pero parang pre-review na yan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So August ito, so umpisa pa lang ng second sem?</i>
80	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, noon pa lang meron na kaming ganun eh. Yung adviser naming sa class, yung adviser namin ng 4th year, siya yung kasama namin sa TCAP. Siya yung nagtuturo sa pre-review tapos may mga extra teachers sa 4th year, yung mga subject teachers na forte nila yung subject na yun, sila yung umaatend sa'min sa pre-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So when you graduated, what made you decide? Kasi pwede ka namang magreview center gaya ng mga kaklase mo di 'ba? Halimbawa, sabay-sabay kayong nagpre-review, yung tinatawag nyong TCAP, syempre nung grumaduate kayo pare-pareho din kayo nakareceive ng TCAP na yun. Anong dahilan para magdecide ka na, okay, ayoko mag-review center?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

81	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ano (thinking...), kasi ang school naming meron siyang talagang review center na rin, yung "ReviewCenterE". Meron silang hi-nire na review center sa school, kasi once na pinasa mo yung Comprehensive (exam), for graduation ka na, at the same time, meron silang review center sa school. Inisip ko naman kasi, waste of time, papasok pa'ko para dun. Near 2 hours kasi ang biyahe ko from home.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So naging factor yung panahon?</i>
82	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi kung ibabiyaha ko pa, 2 hours, what if sabahay na lang ako..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, so nakatira ka sa Marikina, ang school mo, Fairview pa...</i>
83	Ms. NurseE	<i>Two hours ang kinuconsume ko sa biyahe..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So after na ng graduation yun?</i>
84	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, parang waste of time, kasi yung naging foundation ko na kasi yung pre-review sa school. Kasi dun na'ko nagkaroon ng idea na... Possible... kaya ko siyang aralin mag-isa. Nakakuha na kasi ako ng tips sa mga teachers, sa mga pre-review nila. So nagdecide ako ako na lang mag-isa, kesa ibabiyaha ko pa. Kahit libre lang yung review center kasi nga provided na ng school yun once nakapasa ka sa Quali (qualifying exam) saka Compre (Comprehensive exam), libre na kami nun, kung sino yung mga pumasa na estudyante.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so wala ng tuition yun?</i>
85	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala ng tuition yun, libre ng school yun, once na ipasa mo yung two exams nila. Kasi hindi ka pwede magboard, kung hindi mo ipasa yung Quali (qualifying exam); kung baga super sala kasi yun. Kaya sabi ko, kung pupunta pa'ko mapapagod lang ako ng 2 hours, mauupo na lang ako sa bahay. Yung 2 hours na yun na binabiyaha ko, hindi man lang ako nakakapagreview sa biyahe, aaralin ko na lang sa bahay. Nagkaroon ako ng study habits sa sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yun ang naging dahilan? Kinonsult mo ba yan sa magulang mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

86	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi tinanong ko rin sila eh, na kung dito na lang ako sa bahay mag-aral. Kahit alam nila na meron namang libre na ibibigay ang school sa akin. Kaya natuwa nga sila na pasado nga ako sa Quali (qualifying exam), so sabi ko sa bahay na lang ako mag-review. Kasi nga that time may sakit pa si mama nun. Nagka-kidney problem siya, tapos nag-high blood pressure, nag-chichills siya. Kaya mas preferred ko nun dapat nasa bahay lang ako para habang nag-aaral, nakikita ko siya, kung may mangyayari. Atleast hindi gaya ng tatawagin pa'ko na "uy si mama may ganito". That time, sa bahay na lang ako siguro, kasi yung nga nag-occur yun sa akin na self-review na lang, kasi kung бага may idea na'ko nun sa pre-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung "ReviewCenterE" na yun na tinutukoy mo, hindi yun required? Optional yun?</i>
87	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi siya required. Basta ang maganda lang kasi libre na siya, kasi nga pumasa kami sa ano..(qualifying exam)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kailangan mong magsabi sa school na "Ma'am, hindi ako aattend."</i>
88	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi naman, kahit na may attendance siya, minomonitor lang nila mga estudyanteng pumasa ng Quali (qualifying exam) na umaattend ng review center nila. Yung ang tinitingnan nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So wala kayong pre-board (exam) after ng ReviewCenterE Review Center na yun?</i>
89	Ms. NurseE	<i>Meron, "Mock board" na tinatawag sa'min. Dun lang ako umattend.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, dun ka lang din umattend? Pareho pala tayo.</i>
90	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung nag-exam. Sinusubukan ko dun yung inarak ko ng self-review magiging effective sa mock board.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh kung hindi siya naging effective?</i>
91	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun ang assessment ko eh. Kasi yun nga hindi ako lumevel dun sa mock board", kung бага hindi (naging) effective yung review ko nun. Pero that time, ang naisip ko, kahit hindi ako mag-review center okay lang. Ang naisip ko yung mga aaralin ko pa, dadagdagan ko kasi tinandaan ko yung bawat... questions sa mock board.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so you graduate when?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

92	Ms. NurseE	2009 October.
Researcher:	Researcher	So November yung exam?
93	Ms. NurseE	November yung mock board (exam) ng SchoolE(University)
Researcher:	Researcher	Tapos, yung (board) exam, December?
94	Ms. NurseE	Hindi, November din. October kasi graduate na kami nun, pero nagsimula na yung review center nila, so parang one month..
Researcher:	Researcher	Ah one month lang siya... tapos yung board exam November. Tapos November din yung..
95	Ms. NurseE	Kung бага choice naman nung mga nag-qualifying (exam) kung gugustuhin naming magtake ng board, dib a, kung mag-aaply sila sa board (exam). Eh that time nag-apply na kami kagad eh. Pero yung length nung review one month lang siya, sa ReviewCenterE (review center).
Researcher:	Researcher	Pero yung review center na yun, ibang company yun, third party yun na kinuha ninyo?
96	Ms. NurseE	Oo, sa labas yun eh, kinuha lang nung school. Siguro yung ReviewCenterE(review center) na rin ang nag-inquire sa SchoolE (University) kasi ang alam ko bagong review center lang siya, kaya yun sinubukan nila. Eh kasi yung mga teachers dun nanggalin din kay ReviewCenterF (review center), saka ewan ko kung sino pa yung mga iba.
Researcher:	Researcher	Meron bas a family mo, o naging friend mo, na nagself-review rin?
97	Ms. NurseE	Wala, nakwento ko nga sa'yo kanina na halos yung mga naging kasabayan kong kabatch nun, mga pinsan ko sa fatherside.
Researcher:	Researcher	Kahit yung mismong batch mo?
98	Ms. NurseE	Wala, more on review center sila kasi nga kinuha nila yung (review) kasi nga libre na eh. Akal lang talaga yung bumukod na ('ay, saka na lang' [grins])
Researcher:	Researcher	So maski yung mga pinsan mo na tiga-Marikina rin, nagtravel pa sila sa (Fairview)

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

99	Ms. NurseE	<i>Iba-iba kasi eh, may Valenzuela (City), may (tiga) province. Sila alam ko dumayo pa sila ng Maynila para mag-review, sa ReviewCenterE (review center) kasi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung baga nagrent lang sila rito, o nagboard?</i>
100	Ms. NurseE	<i>May tiyahin ako sa Tondo, dun sila nagstay lahat. Nagreview center sila; sabay-sabay sila nag-review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So October ka gumaduate, normally di ba March yung graduation?</i>
101	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga ni-require ako ng school na tapusin ko yung minor ko bago ako tumuloy ng 4th year. Ang alam ko nagsummer ako ng 3rd year. Tinapos ko lahat ng minors.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Heto yung tanong na 'to "What is it like to self-review?" Yung primer lang siya na, ano ba yung naging pakiramdam mo habang nagreview ka? In general lang...</i>
102	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi ako aral lang talaga eh (smiles). Ganon lang yung pakiramdam ko na kailangan ma-accomplish ko siya. Parang estudyante rin na mag-eexpect lang na merong, parang exam lang, final exam. Kasi nga parang pressure kapag sinabi mong board (exam) eh. Estudyante pa rin na nag-aaral lang para sa exam; yung mga major exam lang. Hindi ko siya inisip na board (exam) kasi para sa akin pressure siya (smiles). Parang light review para dun sa exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga exams mo nung 3rd year (at) 4th year, pumapasa ka ba nun, o meron ding times na bumabagsak ka?</i>
103	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa 4th year kasi ako super focused na, so nakikita ko talaga na pumapasa na'ko dun, yung magandang result sa exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>When you say "nakakapasa" o "magandang result", let's say 1-100 yung exam...</i>
104	Ms. NurseE	<i>(interrupted) Sixty percent kasi ang passing lagi, so kung baga 1-100, pasok ako sa average na estudyante. So kung 80%, 80% (ako), nakakapasok ako dun. So hindi ako bumabagsak na, dati kung baga pasang-awa lang. That time 80% na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin mo ba naging reason din yun kung bakit ka nagsarili na lang? Na okay naman yung foundation mo, o dahil lang din sa layo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

105	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi lang dahil sa layo, dahil nga din sa pre-review nga sa school, dun ko din naisip na possible pala na kumuha na lang ako ng idea, na mag-aral na lang ako ng sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung pre-review, may mga exams din kayo 'di ba? So okay rin yung mga (results) mo run?</i>
106	Ms. NurseE	<i>May mga exams din yun, may 9 over 10, may 1-20. Mockboard lang talaga yung 1-100 o 200.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nag-umpisa ka magself-review anong month yun?</i>
107	Ms. NurseE	<i>Magself-review? Bago ako grumaduate. Nagself-review na talaga ako nun. Kung baga may mga prereview na, may mga idea na, nagsisimula na ako. Actually, gumawa ako rito (pointing to plotted schedule planner) nung mga sisimulan kong pag-aralan. Nagsimula kasi ako, sa case ko, yung pinakamahirap na subject sa'kin, dun ako nagfocus muna.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong pinakamahirap na subject sa'yo?</i>
108	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pharma (pharmacology), NRes (nursing research), yung hindi madalas daanan sa nursing. Tingin ko kasi ang pharma (pharmacology) sa akin noon naging mabilis lang kasi summer class ko lang siya kinuha. Parang dun ako hirap sa mga gamot.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano mo katagal tinapos yung Pharma (pharmacology)?</i>
109	Ms. NurseE	<i>Alin, sa minor o sa review?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa review.</i>
110	Ms. NurseE	<i>One week yung binigay ko nun eh. One week, pero kasama na rin ng NRes (nursing research) yun, pero hati sa oras yun. Kasi ang style ng review ko kasi--- nung nag-aaral pa ako, pagkauwi ko kasi sa bahay eh, pagpalagay na nating 5 (PM) ang uwi ko, 6:30 or 7 (PM) nasa bahay na. Ang ginagawa ko, nagpapahinga na'ko, natutulog, tapos 12 (MN) gigising ako ulit, dun ako mag-aaral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Twelve ng midnight?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

111	Ms. NurseE	<i>Midnight. Sinubukan ko mag-12 midnight. Yung madaling araw na review. Tulog, gising sa umaga, tapos bago ka uli pumasok ng 6 sa umaga. Matutulog uli ako ng 4 (AM), saka uli ako papasok.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So from 12 (MN) to 4 (AM)?</i>
112	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kumbaga hinahapyan ko na yung mga review nun, that time.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So bago ka grumaduate. Grumaduate ka October, so mga anong month yun?</i>
113	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nagsisimula na kasi ako ng August. August kasi nagsisimula na rin yung TCAP namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>As in consistent yung ginagawa mo na yun? Ah ganon na araw-araw na 12 to 4 (AM)?</i>
114	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, ganon na yung ginagawa ko. Nagprepreview na'ko sa sarili.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero di ba on-going pa yung pre-review ninyo nun?</i>
115	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, pre-review na nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag-rereview ka na dun tapos nagrereview ka pa sa sarili.</i>
116	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, nagsisimula na rin ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kelan ka nagdecide na magrereview ka sa sarili mo lang, o hindi ka pa nagdedecide nun?</i>
117	Ms. NurseE	<i>Actually, decided na rin talaga ako nun eh. Kumbaga hindi ko na rin ginusto na magreview center pa'ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So by August pa lang alam mo na?</i>
118	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, alam ko na na hindi na'ko magrereview center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kanina sinasabi mo na yung pre-review naging malaking mabagay sa decision mo, di ba? Pero yung August na yun nagdecide ka na rin na hindi ka na magre-review center, 'di ba?</i>
119	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, that time kasi nagsisimula na nun. Naisip ko na kayak o na rin siguro magreview mag-isa, nagsisimula na'ko magbasa-basa nun.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron bang mga bagay na, habang nagrereview ka, yung mga challenges, o nagkarun ka ba ng issue nun?</i>
120	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung challenges, sa father-side ko, kasi nga yung uncle ko, kumbaga sila yung pinakamayaman daw. Ang lagi niya kasing tinitingnan yung family ko, kasi nga yung father ko siya yung parang least sa magkakapatid. So parang inaabangan nila kami na mga anak niya na ano yung magagawa namin. Sila yung pressure ko, ng papa ko, kasi parang feeling ko minamaliit kasi kami nun eh. Kung baga iisipin nila na magaling yung kurso ko, kailangan ako din makahabol dun. Yun yung naging challenge sa'kin, yung panliliit nila kay papa, yung hindi ko nagustuhan. Hindi kasi kami naging close sa fatherside. <i>Kaya nung nakikita ko na yung sitwasyon naming, dun ako naging bibo na dapat sana mapasa ko 'tong board (exam). Na para may maipagmamalaki naman kami, kasi nga ako pa yung eldest. Kung baga pangalawang cou ko na 'to, hindi pa'ko nagtrabaho. Kumbaga nagkakaedad na, dapat may mapatunayan din naman ako this time sa pag-aaral.</i></i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung sa mismong review, meron ka din bang naging problema?</i>
121	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nag-aaral na ako nun eh. Kumbaga at ease na talaga ako. Wala, aral lang. Yung problema, si mama lang, sa family lang eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah oo, si mama mo maysakit sa kidney noh?</i>
122	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, pero sa pag-aaral, nag-eejoy ako nun, kasi nga maganda yung environment, maganda yung naging kaklase ko, kaya dati encouraged akong mag-aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Galing ah! So nung pre-review wala ka rin naging problema? Kayak o kasi nilagay ko 'to rito, kasi may mga bagay nab aka inisip mo, "ayoko na na lang mag-self review". Kumbaga mga challenges.</i>
123	Ms. NurseE	<i>Decided na talaga ako nun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nagrereview ka, hindi ka naman inaantok? Sabi mo alas-dose di ba?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

124	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nagkarun kasi ako ng study habits di ba? That time kasi, tuloy-tuloy naman ang aral kaya hindi rin ako nahirapan mag-cope. Yung hindi lang naging maganda na nangyari dun sa habit ko na yun yung inaantok ako nung grumaduate na'ko. Normal naman siguro yun, kasi nga nagbago kasi yung study habbits ko nung paggraduate ko. Nag-individual review na lang kasi ako sa bahay. Seven AM (morning) na rin kasi akong nagsimulang mag-review nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So hindi na 12, kasi wala ka ng pasok nun eh?</i>
125	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ginawa ko na siyang parang normal na habit na ng isang tao. Seven AM (morning), dun ako mag-aaral hanggang 8 PM. Sinunod ko yung nabasa ko dati na kapag mag-aaral ka..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Seven AM to 8 PM?</i>
126	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi naman straight yun, may nap yun. Kapag alam kong full na yung laman ng utak ko, kapag inaantok talaga, nagpapahinga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa bahay ka lang nag-stay? Ilan ba kayo sa pamilya?</i>
127	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pito, limang magkakapatid, tapos yung parents ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron kang sariling room? Pano ka nagstay dun kung may maingay? Papano ba yung style mo?</i>
128	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ang maganda kasi sa family ko, sinuportahan kasi nila ako habang nag-aaral. So nung nag-aaral ako, yung mga kapatid ko pumapasok naman sila sa school. So kahit bumalik man sila ng bahay, nandun lang sila sa kwarto nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so ikaw pa lang yung grumagraduate nun? Panganay ka nga pala.</i>
129	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa sala kasi ako nagrereview eh, o kaya sa dining. Kasi nga yung lang level sa upo ko eh, so dun ako nagrereview. So 'pag umuwi sila, nag-aaral din sila sa mga subjects nila. So parang tulong sa'kin, nag-aaral kaming lahat, ako nag-aaral, hindi sila nag-iingay. Minsan sa household chores, tinulungan nila ako nun eh. Binawasan yung mga load ko sa bahay. Yun nga lang, naging parusa ko sa sarili kom no cell phones, no TV, aral lang talaga. Yun yung naging focus ko. Sina mama, kasi may tindahan naman kami, kaya dun siya sa tindahan. Kaya yung bahay na yun, ako lang talaga mag-isa, hindi nila ako ginugulo; kakain lang sila.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siguro 'tong tanong ko na 'to hindi na 'to applicable kasi hindi ka natempt mag-quit (ng self-review), 'di ba?</i>
130	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi nga. Kahit na nung mock board na kahit na feeling ko nag-fail ako, dun ako lalo nag-aral yung mga hin di ko nadaanan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So October ka grumaduate, November ang (board) exam, mock board mo ay November din, di ba?</i>
131	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo nga parang after graduation na yun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ganu kahaba yung panahon para mas ginalingan mo pa?</i>
132	Ms. NurseE	<i>Two weeks na nga lang yun 'eh. Kasi after nun, nagrerey na'ko kay ReviewCenterE (review material); refresh na lang, yung ideas na lang, yung mga palatandaan na lang, so yun yung mga nirereview k okay ReviewCenterE (review material), kasi nga Saunder's (book author) yung nirereview ko nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga nireview mo ba, napag-aralan mo talaga nung nasa undergraduate ka?</i>
133	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nakikiramdang na rin kasi ako nun eh, kasi nga may mga payo na rin sa akin, saka yung mga ideas sa pre-review, saka yung kaibigan ko na grumaduate na as a nurse, kumuha ako ng ideas sa kanya, nag seself-review na rin kasi ako nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so graduate na siya?</i>
134	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nurse na rin talaga siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nurse na talaga siya sa hospital</i>
135	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi, trainee pa lang siya that time.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kelan ka nag-umpisang humingi ng ideas?</i>
136	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung nag-aaral ako, bago grumaduate.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong mga binigay sa'yong mga ideas?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

137	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tinanong ko sa kanya, kung ano ba yung lumbas sa board (exam), kung saan ba dapat ako magfocus. Pinayuhan niya ako, say communicable disease, na kung meron kang dapat pag-aralan dun, dapat yung related sa panahon. Sa communicable diseases kasi, ang lumalabas daw kasi sa board exam kung anong sakit nitong year. Dati sikat nung panagon ko, AH1N1. Nung sa panahon niya, dengue yata yung sa problem niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah sa yung sa China yun Ah1N1.</i>
138	Ms. NurseE	<i>So yun yung latest ng DOH (Department of Health) dati. Usap-usapan nila na ganon yun, kaya naisip ko na possible nga yun lumabas sa (board exam). Yung mga disaster. Nung nagboard ako may Ondoy eh! (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kumbaga yung mga "current events"</i>
139	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, yung mga current events, sabi niya yun yung dapat maging aware ka dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ibangsubjects?</i>
140	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa ibang subjects, kung ano yung madalas ipre-review. Kung ano yung madalas lumabas sa exam. Dun ako nagfail, kaya dun ako nagfocus. Yung mga topics na yun, dun ako nag-aral. Yung mga nababasa ko sa exam na 'laging ito na naman' laging may naiinclude na ganung tanong. So tinatandaan ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bawat exam sa pre-review ninyo?</i>
141	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa pre-review tapos sa mga exams sa major (subjects). Napapansin ko na "parang lagi siyang kasali"; kaya binasa ko yung part na yun, hanggang sa naaral ko heto pala yung nursing management, mga signs niya. Tinandaan ko na yun. Dun ako nagkaroon ng idea na, "oh possible pala na ganon lumabas", kasi lagi naman ganon yung tanong eh. Kaya yun yung mga nirereview ko lagi. Saka yung mga parts na hindi ko sure, so inaaral ko na yun. Kasi may mga parts na lumalabas sa pre-review eh, tapos hindi ko naman siya na-rereview. Tinitingnan ko kung ano yung mga yun. So yun yung mga naging style ko sa reviewing.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin mo, ano yung nakita mong advantages, although hindi naman tayo nagreview center 'di ba? Pero sa tingin mo ano yung mga advantages ng self-review na nakatulong sa'yo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

142	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung time management. Feeling ko dun ako lamang dahil syempre oras ko yun eh. Atleast nakakapagpahinga ako. Ang alam ko gaya ng eview center, tuloy-tuloy dun ang class 'di ba? Kung may break man sila, hindi ko alam. Sa self-review, kapag feeling pagod na ako, kapag feel ko overload na yung utak ko, makakapagpahinga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kailangan may disiplina ka dun ' di ba? Kasi minsan sa time management, minsan napapabaya na eh (smiles).</i>
143	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi kasi nakasulat na kung ano yung pag-aaralan ko that day. Kung Pharma (pharmacology), kung MS (Medical-Surgical), yung sa Monday na pag-aaralan ko, yun na yun, so hindi na'ko tatalon sa ibang book.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sinunod mo yung sa pre-review ninyo?</i>
144	Ms. NurseE	<i>Naging guide ko, yes, sa pre-review ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ginaya mo yung schedule?</i>
145	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi actually sa schedule eh. Ang style ko nun sarili ko, (inuuna ko) yung pinakamahirap na subject, sa pinakamadali. Kumbaga sinulat ko siya sa isang calendar sa libro na, ito yung pag-aaralan ko per week, saka per day.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung baga mula sa pinakamahirap, saka na yung pinakamadali?</i>
146	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nagfocused ako sa pinakamahirap, kasi nga feeling ko dun ako maraming dapat pag-aralan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban sa 'time management' ano pa sa tingin mo yung advantages, kung meron pa man?</i>
147	Ms. NurseE	<i>(thinking) Siguro sa pamasaha na rin, kasi nga magwawaste ka pa ng financial, kasi nga parang tulong mo na sa magulang mo yun, kasi nga graduate ka na eh. Atleast makakapagfocused ako kay mama. Yun kasi yung nakita kong advantages ko eh, sarili ko yung oras ko, hindi ako napapagod sa biyahe.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa disadvantages naman?</i>
148	Ms. NurseE	<i>Siguro yun nga hindi kagaya ng sa iba na kumportableng-kumportable, kasi nga wala kang kasabayang nag-aaral. Kasi nga kapag may mga kasama ka, ma-eencourage ka dapat mag-aral.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron bang naging disadvantage yung self-(review) sa'yo na hindi magandang naging impression sa'yo na 'sana pala hindi na lang ako nag-self-review...'</i>
149	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala eh, wala akong guts (i.e. regrets) na hindi ako nagreview center. Kahit na nagfailed ako sa mock board, hindi ko naisip na 'uy dapat magreview center na'ko'. Hindi eh. Mas nagfocus ako na 'ay naging weak ako sa subject na yun, so kailangan aralin ko pa siya. Lalo akong nagkainteres na dapat daanan ko yung subject na yun kasi nga talo ako dun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hetong tanong na 'to mejo subjective 'to: ikaw ha, kung meron kang makikitang graduate ngayon, halimbawa, kaibigan mo, pinsan mo, o naging kakilala mo, irerecommend mo ba yung self-review?</i>
150	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sinasabi ko "try mo kaya yung style ko", ginaganun ko sila. "Try ko mo kaya yung style ko na aralin mo lang yung palaging lumalabas sa mga exams mo?". Ganun ko siya irerecommend na gayahin mo yung pinayo nung kaibigan ko na aralin mo yung current events, dapat aware ka lang sa pailigd mo. Kasi ang review makikiramdam ka lang, as graduating, kung may pre-review sa school, kung ano yung tinuturo nila. Kasi naniniwala ako yung mga nagtuturo sa amin updated din sila sa mga possible na lalabas, saka kung sino yung mga clinical o board directors na gagawa ng exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, kung anong expertise ng board of nursing.</i>
151	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kung ano yung mga styles ng teachings nila. Kaya that time parang nagiging aware na rin ako; kumbaga inalalatag na rin nila kasi eh. Kumbaga nandun na rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung sinabi mo na 'try mong gayahin yung style ko', anong naging reaksyon niya?</i>
152	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa mga parents kasi, 'Oo nga naman 'noh'. Actually parents kasi nakakausap ko eh. Amazed nga sila eh, mula nung malaman nilang pumasa ako ng board. Tanong nila 'anong ginawa mo'? Sabi ko 'ganito po..'</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos anong sabi naman nila?</i>
153	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sabi nila "galing naman" (smiles). Sabin g magulang "Oo nga 'noh parang pinahirapan lang nila yung pag-aaral nila, yun lang pala yun.'</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga parents na yun hindi pa graduate yung anak?</i>
154	Ms. NurseE	<i>Graduate na pero hindi pa nakapasa ng board (exam). Nagtake na sila ng board (exam), nagfail, tapos tinatanong ako kasi nga nalaman na 'uy pumasa ka pala ng board exam'...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagreview center sila?</i>
155	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, nagreview center sila. Tinatanong nga nila kung saan ako nagreview center. Tapos sabi ko 'hindi po ako nagreview center', kaya nga nagulat sila "Hindi ka nagreview center?!" (smiling). Tapos nagtatanong, 'anong ginawa mo?' Yung mga style ko, tinuro ko rin sa anak niya, yung technique ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman sila ngayon?</i>
156	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala pa'kong balita dun sa isa. Yung isa kasi nagfailed eh. Tinatanong nga niya pano ako nag-aral, nung tita ko, pero hindi eh continuous pa rin siya nagreview center; hanggang ngayon failed pa rin eh. Third time na siyang nagfailed, hindi pa rin pumapasa. Yung isa, hindi ko alam kung nagtake ba ulit ng board exam, kasi dalawa pa lang naman yung nakausap ko eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ano ba sa tingin mo yung naging dahilan bakit sila bumabagsak ng ganon?</i>
157	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pinipressure nila yung sarili nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung ikaw nagreview, hindi ka feeling pressured?</i>
158	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pressured (din)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh pano mo nilalabanan yung pressure?</i>
159	Ms. NurseE	<i>Siyempre natatakot siya nab aka nga bumagsak ka, kasi nga meron naman talangang fear na ganun, kaya lang, kailangan kasi idivert ko siya eh, na hindi dapat ganun eh. Kailangan optimistic ka pa rin sa ginagawa mo na "nag-aaral naman akong mabuti eh", "hindi naman ako nagwawaste ng time eh", "so why not? Kayak o tong ipasa!" Nagseseryoso naman akong magreview, hindi ko naman siyang sobrang inaanalyze. So nandun yung guts ko na, pwede kakayanin ko yun.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So hindi ka talaga super pressured, kung baga nagfofocus ka lang?</i>
160	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, nagfofocus lang. Kung anong ginagawa ko, nag-aaral pa rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero may mga times din na naiisip mo na 'baka bumagsak ako'?</i>
161	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Smiled) Nung naghihintay na lang ako ng result. Dun ko lang naisip nag "Ha, pumasa kaya ako? Natatakot ako kung papasa ako..." Kasi may mga kabarkada ako na nagsasabi na "sana pumasa tayo", sabi ko "papasa yan, nag-aral naman tayo eh". Ginawa naman natin yung lahat eh. So parang faith na rin. Dun pumapasok yung deeper faith na 'papasa!'. Kumbaga may halong faith na rin saka yung contribution mo as individual na nag-aaral ka rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong naging effect sa'yo ng self-review, overall? Kumbaga, meron bang naging epekto sa'yo, yung tingin mo sa sarili mo, tingin mo sa mga tao, overall?</i>
162	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo naman! (smiles). Nagboost yung self-esteem ko. Kumbaga kung merong taong mayabang, parang feeling ko, pwede akong magyabang eh. Kasi sila ang dami nilang perang ginastos eh. Proud ako, lalo na sa uncle ko, kasi naramdaman ko na naging proud din siya sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah yung uncle mo na kinukwento mo kanina?</i>
163	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, yung kinukwento ko. Parang feeling ko naging proud din siya, kasi umattend siya nung 'thanksgiving party' ko eh. Kumbaga sa lahat ng graduation ko, nung pumasa lang ako ng board humingi ako ng handa kasi. Yun lang yung hinigan ko ng handa. Umaattend siya dun, kaya nakita ko na naging proud din siya sa akin. Proud ako na kinaya ko siya... Mabigat kasi yung pinagdadaanan k okay mama nun, saka sa kanya (Uncle), sila kasi yung parang challenge (motivation) sa akin. Kaya nung pumasa ako, kaya kung may mayabang, pwede akong magyabang, kasi nga may sinabi, kasi hindi naman ako yung basta pasado lang, kumbaga nahigitin ko yung, hindi man yung kung baga ultimate goal ko na rate, hayun na yun eh. Nakuha ko siya. Proud ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung reaksyon sa pamilya mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

164	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung sa father ko, sabi niya yung anak ko lang yung kumbaga maipagmamalaki, Kasi siya asensado siya before, bumagsak siya. Hindi siya pinag-igi yung trabaho niya. Parang naging dahilan yun ng parang minamaliit kami ng family eh. Ang sabi niya, itong anak kong 'to, siya yung maipagmamalaki na. Nakapasa siya, kumbaga gumawa siya ng paraan. Hindi nga nila iniexpect kasi nga sa magkakapatid hindi naman ako super talino, matiyaga lang talaga. Hindi niya akalain na papasa ako, kaya thankful siya kasi ng worthy yung hirap niya sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ibang tao, aside sa uncle mo, sa mga kaklase mo..</i>
165	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa ibang tao (thinking)? Sa kapitbahay namin? Nung malaman nilang nag-selfreview ako, sabi "ang galing mo naman!". Yung dating teacher ko, inencourage pa nga ako magdoctor. Sabi 'bat hindi ka nagdoctor?' (smiling) Sabi ko kakaaral lang ng nursing, next time na lang yung pagdodoktor (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung nagrereview ka sa sarili mo, yung school mo, meron ba kayong contact nun?</i>
166	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala eh. Kumbaga yung umattend sa akin ung thanksgiving (party) ko, yung teacher ko lang nung caregiver. Yung nag-encourage sa aking magnursing, sa Pamantasan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So hindi alam ng school mo na nag-self review ka lang?</i>
167	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, hindi nila alam. Siguro dahil marami naman kaming pumasa sa Qualifying (exam) at nag-aattendance nga sila sa review center, siguro yun lang ang iniintindi nila. Hindi nila hinahabol yung mga estudyanteng nag-selfreview</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nakibalita ka sa kanila? Siyempre mag'mock board kayo 'di ba?</i>
168	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi naman sila nakialam sa amin eh. Yung Dean namin nagmessage lang, encouragement, para lalo kaming magboost na mag-aral, yun lang ang kontribusyon nila, pero pangkalahatan yun. Yung last na lang nung pumasa na'ko sa board (exam), kasi nga ininvite ko yung teacher ko sa pamantasan. More on parents siguro, pero yung paying teacher wala; sa family ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ibang tao...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

169	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung naging barkada ko na naging nurse, siya yung nagbigay saakin ng tips..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah yung nagpayo sa'yo ng current events?</i>
170	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa buong review experience mo na lang, papano mo siya ideddescribe in a sentence? Naging exciting ba...ano bang adjective yung pwede mong gamitin?</i>
171	Ms. NurseE	<i>Self-review...? (thinking/smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung бага kung ilalagay mo siya sa isang salita, o sa isang sentence? Ano sa tingin mo yung magandang description sa nangyari sa'yo?</i>
172	Ms. NurseE	<i>Syempre "the Best" siya! The Best kasi self-review eh! Iba kasi yung impression ng tao kapag sinabi mong nag self-review ka. Iba yung dating sa tao kapag nalaman na nagself-review ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Dalawang parts yun 'di ba? Una, yung tingin ng tao. Second, yung tingin mo sa sarili mo?</i>
173	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun nga okay siya sa'kin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero naging dahilan ba yung impression ng iba para magself-review ka, o sarili mo lang initiative yun?</i>
174	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung nga nag-initiate na ako na magself-review na lang talaga ako. Ako na lang nagdecide kasi nga may mga pre-review na eh, Kung бага may idea na ako. Okay na yun. Hindi ko na gugustuhin pa magwaste pa ng pera, o ng panahon sa review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nice. Salamat sa story mo. Ako nga mismo naaalala ko. Kung ako lang iinterviewhin mo, ganun din ako eh.</i>
175	Ms. NurseE	<i>Medyo magkarelata ba tayo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>Oo, medyo! (exchanged smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hetong third part is about sa "Strategies". Hetong part na 'to ay detalye ang focus nito. Kung papano mo ginawa, ano yung una mong ginawa, yung mga bagay na ganun. Kung yung isang tao na titingin, kung magkakarun man ng guide, eh alam niya. Although kanina napahapyawan mo na yun eh. Yung mga tanong ditto: Una, siguro kwento mo na lang kung pano mo ginawa na naging effective yung (self-review)... Nabanggit mo kasi kanina, dun mo tinst nung nag-mockboard ka. Papano mo yun marerelate yun sa review mo?</i>
176	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa review ko? (thinking..) Sinabi ko nga kasi na meron na akong calendar review sa sarili ko. So say 'tong first week na 'to, heto yung pag-aaralan ko..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(Interrupts)..So nag-umpisa ka ng August? 'Di ba nag-aaral ka na?</i>
177	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung una tapon-tapun lang yun, kung ano yung pinag-aaralan namin sa pre-review. Kung бага wala pang sistema talaga na 'heto yung subject na uunahin ko'. Kung бага dun lang ako nagkakarun ng idea na 'ay hirap ako sa subject na 'to". Nung one month na lang before the board exam, dun na ako gumawa ng calendar, kasi nga yun na yung mabilisang aral eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>San mo binase yung schedule na yun?</i>
178	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun nga, mula sa pinakamahirap...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anu-anong mga pinakamahirap sa'yo?</i>
179	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung Pharma (pharmacology) at saka NRes...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>NRes?</i>
180	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nursing Research.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, Professional Adjustment (subject)?</i>
181	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, dun ako unang nag-aral. Tapos sinundan ko ng ...nandito yun eh (pointing to her actual schedule of review)...Heto, start of pre-review sa Pharma (pharmacology)</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ibig sabihin yung schedule na'to noon mo pa'to sinulat?</i>
182	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, October-November. So nag-start ako nung (October) 22.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Astig ah...</i>
183	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Smiles). After graduation ko na yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kelan mo 'to ginawa? One day lang 'to? Nakagawa ka na kagad ng schedule?</i>
184	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung first month, pagkagraduate ko, gumagawa na'ko. October 22, gumagawa na ako ng rereviewhin ko. Yung umpisa sa pinakamahirap, sa pinakamadali. Kung mapapansin mo yung mga pinakamadali ko—yung M.S. (Medical Surgical subject), Psyche (Psychiatric Nursing), yun yung mga last ko. Kahit happyawan ko na lang yun, kumbaga kaya ko na siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ito ay...ano 'to?</i>
185	Ms. NurseE	<i>Start ng review ko sa Pharma (pharmacology), tapos Funda (Fundamentals of Nursing)..Mga theories sa Funda (Fundamentals of Nursing) di 'ba marami din ang Funda? Basic nursing kasi yan. Communicable disease.. Kung baga inayos ko siya. Kasi nga pangit naman kung puro straight days, puro OB (Obstetrics), ganun, parang hindi naman makatwiran sa ibang subjects. Sinubukan ko rin siyang hati-hatiin talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan yung OB (Obstetrics) dito?</i>
186	Ms. NurseE	<i>Heto rito... Pedia (Pediatrics)...CHN (Community Health Nursing)... I.M.C.I.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>IMCI? Lumalabas talaga yan 'di ba?</i>
187	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, IMCI... Yun talaga yung consistent nung mga araw na yun, nag-aral talaga ako nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung Pharma (Pharmacology) anong mga natatandaan mo na inaral mo, na lumabas (sa board exam)?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

188	Ms. NurseE	<i>(thinking).. Kasi walang computation sa exam ko ng boad (exam) eh...Wala siyang computation. Kaya parang naging disappointed ako na, na parang walang Pharma (Pharmacology). Nakasama na siya sa mga askit na mismo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa M.S. (Medical-Surgical) kasama na.</i>
189	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasama na. Kung baga kasali na lang siya sa exam, kung ano ibibigay mo na gamot sa pasyente. Kung baga hinapyan ko lang yung Pharma(pharmacology) ko, yung mga possible na gamot sa bacteria. Yun lang yun mga inaral ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa Funda (Fundamentals of Nursing)?</i>
190	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung mga pinakafocus ko kasi nun—positioning, yung mga nursing theories. May pumasok na iilan-ilan. Kasi nga halos lahat nun iisa lang din, yung mga nursing management at intervention.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh sa communicable diseases?</i>
191	Ms. NurseE	<i>Lahat yun, pathognomonic signs (smiles). Lumabas yun. Yun nga ang pinakafocus ko talaga nun yung Ah1N1, kasi yun nga sabi ng kaibigan ko yung “current events”.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lumabas ba yun sa board (exam)?</i>
192	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, lumabas yun, yung signs and symptoms. Kung anong ginawa ng DOH (Department of Health) nung time na nagkarun ng AH1N1. Naalala ko may ganung lumabas. Pati yung tawag sa gas mask (i.e. N95). Lumabas lahat yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh sa CHN (Community Health Nursing)?</i>
193	Ms. NurseE	<i>IMCI ako, more on (smiles). Kasi ang CHN parang iniexplain lang yung sa community, definitions lang eh. IMCI yung more on lumabas dun sa board exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo nga pala, total nandito na naman tayo. Yung sa Pharma (Pharmacology), anong libro yung ginamit mo, review materials?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

194	Ms. NurseE	<i>Saunders (Book) yung ginamit ko nun eh. Ang pinakareview material ko na hiniram ko sa kaibigan ko "Saunders, 3rd Edition", at lumang edition pa yun. Hindi kagaya ng mga bago ngayon, yung mga editions. Nakita ko kasi, napagcompare ko na, parang mas madaling intindihin 'to, kesa sa gumamit ka ng iba pang reference. Kasi sa Saunders (book reviewer) nacompile na siya, iba-ibang subjects. Yun yung ginamit ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung buong tatlong araw na yun...Ilan ba yan? Pharma..</i>
195	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pharma, 2 days lang. Lahat yan Saunders, lahat ng kabuuuan ng review materials ko, Saunders.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano ba kakapal yung Saunders?</i>
196	Ms. NurseE	<i>Makapal yun! (smiles). Parang M.S. (Medical Surgical) na libro sa kapal. Kasi may mga practice sessions na rin yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saunders Review of...ano ba yung title nun?</i>
197	Ms. NurseE	<i>Basta...photocopy kasi yung gamit ko eh. Kung бага pirated na libro. Basta Saunders, 3rd edition review material. Yun lang yung ginamit ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, yun yun. Binalik mo na rin?</i>
198	Ms. NurseE	<i>Binalik ko na kasi siya eh. Pero sabi niya (her friend) may nabibili nga nun sa Recto (Avenue) nga, sa tapat ng PRC (Professional Regulation Commission's Office).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So itong (ReviewCenterEs Reviewer) na 'to, pagkatapos 'to nung Saunders?</i>
199	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ginamit ko na rin siya. Kung бага malapit na yung (board exam)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ba't mo rito 'to sinulat? (referring to the review schedule)</i>
200	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun yung mga target ko na (activities)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so kasabay mo 'to binili nung sa Saunders?</i>
201	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, binili ko na siya pero hindi ko siya binabasa.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah nilagay mo lang diyan (referring to the schedule of review)?</i>
202	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga nakarelata ako kay Saunders</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah...</i>
203	Ms. NurseE	<i>Binubuksan ko na lang 'to (referring to Balita's reviewer), kapag, halimbawa, "ano nga ba 'tong sakit na' to?" Sa halip na buksan ko kay Saunders na pagkakapal-kapal...Tiningnan ko na lang yung kay ReviewCenterE Balita. Kung may technique si ReviewCenterEna mas madaling tandaan. Yung may mga tinatawag siyang "caricature" ba yun? Yun mga palatandaan. Mas madali mo tandaan. Dito ko siya tiningnan. Pero hindi ko siya binasa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, yung mga mnemonics?</i>
204	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, mga mnemonics.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah okay, kuha ko na. So dalawa lang ang ginamit mo? Heto lang (referring to reviewer) at saka yung Saunders?</i>
205	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, pero more on Saunders ako. Heto (referring to reviewer) pang reference ko na lang 'to. Yung madadaling idea lang niya yung kinukuha ko. Para kasing hindi ko siya ganun nagamit. Mas madali ko siyang naintindihan kay Saunders.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang meron kay Saunders? ---(a girl asked for food)--- ©[Time Stamp 1:11:08]</i>
206	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun nga kapag may topic kay Saunders. Halimbawa, topic niya heart disease...Kay Saunders topic niya "Angina", meron siyang definition...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So mas malalim yung pagkaka (explain)?</i>
207	Ms. NurseE	<i>Parang feeling ko mas malinaw. Iniexplain niya kasing isa-isa. Nakalagay dun definition ni Angina, pathophysio (-logy) niya. Kung бага hindi kagaya sa libro natin ng M.S. (Medical-Surgical) na may mga arrow-arrow pa. Sa Saunders iniexplain niya...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(interrupts) Ah, so mas gusto mo ba yun nakadetailed kesa sa mga nakagraphs o diagrams/illustrations?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

208	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes. Kasi nga mas naintindihan ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kelan nag-umpisa yung ganun (referring to her preference)?</i>
209	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kahit na kapag nagrereport ako gusto ko yung detailed siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah kapag nagrereport ka ganun?</i>
210	Ms. NurseE	<i>Pero kapag sinusulat ko siya, naka-tabs na lang siya. Yung pinakaroot-words, yung nakahighlight na lang siya. Pero gusto ko kapag nagrereview ako, kailangan detailed para mas maintindihan ko. Hindi ko siya makukuha ng parang signs-signs lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aalamin mo kung anong nangyari talaga, kumbaga yung kabuuan?</i>
211	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kabuuan. Pero kapag pina-explain nila, dun ko lang ginagamit yung mga exact words lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano nakatulong yung mga yun sa board exam?</i>
212	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nga ang exam ng board ay situational. So dun ko nagamit yung parang "oo nga 'noh heto yung sakit niya, si Angina, so kailangan alam ko yung intervention niya. Kasi kay Saunders, nakaspecify yung first mong gagawin...what if kung situation mo ganito...nakalagay kay Saunders yun. Kaya nung nag-eexam na'ko sa situational, 'ah heto yun, nabasa ko kay Saunders 'to". Kasi kung minsan may mga pick-up lines na...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pick-up lines talaga ha? (smiles)</i>
213	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kunwari sa rescue, irerescue mo siya. Alam ko na gagawin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nag (hahanap) ka ng mga keywords?</i>
214	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, mga keywords, like first kong intervention o gagawin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>'Di ba may mga tanung dun na "what's the initial..."</i>
215	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo "initial". Nakay-Saunders kasi yun eh, kung ano yung mga gagawin.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So tinatandaan mo yung mga keywords na yun tapos kung ano yung intervention. Mga situational yun eh, 'di ba?</i>
216	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, basta alam mo kung ano si "Angina", ano si "DM" (diabetes mellitus); kung baga nakadefine na siya, may pathophysio (-logy) na rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nakatulong sa'yo yung mas detailed? Pero pano yung sa background mo sa studies mo..</i>
217	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ah, kasama yun, pero siguro yung sa stock knowledge lang. Part na yun, pero nung nagboboard (exam) na ako, mas natandaan ko na yung nakalagay kay Saunders, kasi yun yung more on lumabas eh. Stock knowledge, naretain naman, hanggang ngayon, yung iba dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ganun yung naging strategy mo?</i>
218	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, naging detailed yung review, which is naging helpful yung tools ni (Saunders)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say ikucompare mo yung studies mo for 4 years, tapos yung naging review mo with Saunders, which was, ilang months yun..</i>
219	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga nagppreview na kami eh, August. Kasi nung second sem, nahiram ko na yun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung ikucompare moyung education mo na nareceive from your school at yung review mo, saan yung mas nainternalize yung mga pinag-aralan mo?</i>
220	Ms. NurseE	<i>May natulong naman yung pinag-aralan ko, kasi nga may stock knowledge na dun, pero more on nung review na kay Saunders.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero naging detailed rin ba yung sa school mo kung pano dinidiscuss yung mga sakit na yun?</i>
221	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nagkaroon kami ng mga doctor (Medical doctors) sa M.S. Ewan ko kung ganon din sa iba, pero nga kung minsan sa sobrang galing nga nila, kumbaga mas lumalawak yung teaching nila kasi nga doctor sila eh. Parang pang-doctor na yung tinuturo nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero pano yung naging effect nun sa review mo?</i>
222	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tingin ko nakatulong din eh. Kaya nga lang hindi super ano.. kasi nga hindi mo naman siya marerecall na eh.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabagay estudyante ka pa rin lang naman nun eh.</i>
223	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, parang stock knowledge na lang yung nakuha mo sa kanila. Idea na lang nung sakit na yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nung nasa review ka, dun mo (mas naintindihan)?</i>
224	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, dun na lang lumawak yun, kumbaga "ah heto pala siya". Ninanamnam ko yung pinag-aralan ko, mas naintindihan ko siya nung nagrereview na ako mag-isa. Kasi yung gamit ko pang libro maganda pa na nakadetailed din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ngayon ba may Saunders pa?</i>
225	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, nakita ko nung 2011, nung tapos na'ko magboard (exam), may Saunders na bagong edition eh, 12th edition yata. Ang layo eh noh?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(exchanged smiles)</i>
226	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo nga, ang layo eh, kasi nga bagong-bago yung nakita ko makapal din diyan sa may Riverbanks (Marikina City), diyan sa Mirriam (bookstore). Ang mahal-mahal pa (smiling). May malaki saka may manipis, parang questions lang yata.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(looking at the review schedule list)...So yun yung mga gusto mo, yung M.S., Psyche, kaya hinuli mo yan?</i>
227	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, inuuna ko yung mga mahirap pag-aralan. Kasi nga si M.S. saka si Psyche may idea na talaga ako. Yun na yung last. Kumbaga kung babasahin ko man sila, maintindihan ko na. Hindi na yung parang "ay babalikan ko ulit kasi nga parang nalimutan ko nga"...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero di ba sabi mo yung M.S., mga doctor mo yung nagtuturo? Nagustuhan mo siya dahil sa mga nagtuturo, o nagustuhan mo mismo yung subject?</i>
228	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nagustuhan ko siya, kasi nga yung sa family ko. Kasi nga maraming sakit na...lagi akong tinatanong na "Anak, ano yung..." Ayoko naman yung wala akong masagot. Kaya dati naging palabasa na'ko...pero more on M.S.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(Examining the review material)...ang galing ah... may mga guhit pa talaga. Kelan mo sinulat 'to?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

229	Ms. NurseE	<i>October (2009) pa yata yan eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>October 2009?</i>
230	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, may mga pa-dream-dream pang ganyan (referring to her written vows for review motivation) (smiles...)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron bang point na nagduda ka na papasa ka? Ganito, una kong tanong: meron ka bang kakilala na bumagsak?</i>
231	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala eh...kasi nga yung bestfriend ko, yung kakilala ko, pumasa naman yun, one-take lang din yun, kaya lang siya nagreview center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So walang point maliban lang nung sabi mo kanina nag-aantay ka na nung result? Yun lang? So habang nagreview ka tingin mo nun papasa ka talaga?</i>
232	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, na papasa ako...may faith. Kasi nga yung sa Christian nga, na kung ano yungpaniwala mo, yun yung mangyayari sa'yo. Kaya faith ko nun "papasa ako", hindi ko hinayaan na yung negative vibes yung mangibabaw sa'kin (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga tumulong sa'yo yung kaibigan mo...</i>
233	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung family ko...More on sa family ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung sa time constraints—heto kasi parang one month lang ito, parang intensive na review na'to eh. Papano mo namanage na yung isang subject, isang sem mo pinag-aralan yun 'di ba? Papano mo pinasok sa loob ng dalawang araw lang?</i>
234	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun nga, may oras lang talaga ako ng aral eh. Kumbaga kung anong nakatokang subject ng araw na yun, yun lang yung pag-aaralan ko. From 7 (AM)-8 (lanPM), may kasama na dun tulog o may kain man. Ganun lang eh, hindi pa'ko nagrrelax nung time na yan. Wala munang TV, walang text-text</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, talaga?</i>
235	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kumbaga dineprived ko yung sarili ko sa ganun. Nagfocus lang ako sa aral.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nung bago ka magreview, ginagawa mo ba yun yung mga TV, texting, ganun?</i>
236	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi na, medyo minimal na rin ako nun. Siguro dahil sa oras na rin ng pasok ko, 7 (AM)-5 (PM), tapos uuwi gabi na, pahinga na lang. Tapos magppreview na'ko ng gabi. Saka syempre may mga exams din naman kami sa subjects namin, tapos iba pa yung TCAP namin, yung pre-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah so dun ka na talaga nakatuon?</i>
237	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nakafocus na'ko nun, kasi nga graduating na'ko eh. May pressure pa ng "Comprehensive (exam)", may ganun. May Qualifying exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, kasi naisip ko yung withdrawal eh. Kasi halimbawa kung sanay ka sa texting papano ... (smiles) mo iiwan bigla yun?</i>
238	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nung tumuntong na'ko ng 4th year, parang wala na naman ako masyadong katextmate na nun eh. Kung sa barkada, may kanya-kanya na rin kaming buhay; parang balitaan na lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung time management mo na yun, yung umpisa from 12-4 (AM), tapos sa buong month na yun naging 7 (AM)-8 (PM), although graduate ka na.</i>
239	Ms. NurseE	<i>Graduate na'ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ba mas maganda yung nangyari sa'yo na 1 month lang o mas maganda kung mas mahaba pa?</i>
240	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tingin ko mas okay na yung one month. Tingin ko kasi kapag pinatagal mo yung pag-aaral, parang mas malilimutan mo siya, kasi kung kakareview mo lang, atleast fresh pa sa'yo yung mga nireview mo, kesa sa pinatagal-tagal mo pa, ganon din naman katutuluyan mag-eexam ka rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ang (board) exam mo, anong date yun? November...</i>
241	Ms. NurseE	<i>Magkakatapusan na rin nun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagbigay ka ba ng time na, let's say two days before ng exam hindi na'ko dapat mag-aaral?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

242	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, kinuha ko yong quote na pinayo ng Dean ko na, kasi before nag-encourage siya na 'kapag magboboard exam naman 'na, itigil niyo na yung pressure. Magrelax din naman na kayo'. Kaya lang nung nagrerelax din ako nun, nanonood ako ng TV. Ang pinanood ko nun, yung Dr. House (TV series), saka sino ba yung sikat pa nun, si...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Grey's Anatomy (TV series)?</i>
243	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes. Yung related pa din sa kurso ko (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilang araw bago yung exam?</i>
244	Ms. NurseE	<i>Two days, kasi nga wala ng basa-basa yun. Lahat kami ng mga kaklase ko, saka nung nagsagot ako nung mga exam ni Saunders, nakita ko na 'ay pumapasok yung mga sagot ko'. That time, tigil na yung review ko, kailangan two days before, okay na ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So meron kang schedule for a particular subject, meron ka bang exam din para sa sarili mo na...post test, ganun?</i>
245	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung kay Saunders nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong approach mo nun?</i>
246	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kunwari nag-eexam (board) na ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Di ba may sagot din sa baba?</i>
247	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi siya ganun kay Saunders eh. May bukod siyang answer. Kaya hindi ka rin makakapandaya (smiles). Hindi ko tiningnan yung sagot. Kasi nga yung bukod niyang sagot, meron siyang rationale dun. Kapag nagsasagot ako, sagot lang, pero nag-aanalyze na'ko nun. Parang nagboboard exam na'ko nun, nung sinasagutan ko yung pre-test ni Saunders.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halimbawa, yung isang tanong, eh nagkamali ka, tapos tiningnan mo yung rationale...</i>
248	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Interrupts) pero kailangan sagutan ko muna lahat saka ko tiningnan yung rationale.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halimbawa, nalaman mo na yung sagot, tiningnan mo na yung rationale, after how many days binabalikan mo ba ulit siya, mag-eexam ka ulit?</i>
249	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi na. Basta tinandaan ko na siya, yun na yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka na bumabalik?</i>
250	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi na, kasi parang feeling ko kapag binalikan mo ulit yung pag-aaral mo na yun, malilimutan mo ulit eh. Basta tandaan mo na siya, yun na yun. Kasi baka magkaron ka ng confusion eh, kasi tumatalon ka na sa ibang subjects na inaaral, tapos babalikan mo pa ulit yung una mong inaaral, parang waste of time.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay. Pero let's say yung isang subject 2 days yung inalot mo, 2nd day ka ba nag-eexam?</i>
251	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, yung pinakalast day ng review ko sa subject na yun, iitake ko yung pinaka-post test ni Saunders. Yung pagkatapos mo yung subject niya, may exam sa dulo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung sa family mo, anong naging reaksyon? May review ka 'di ba nung mga panahon na yun? Tapos inaalagaan mo yung mother mo. Papano mo minanage yun?</i>
252	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi ang kailangan lang naman sa kanya monitoring eh, sa high blood pressure niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah dahil dun sa kidney (problem)?</i>
253	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, naghig blood pressure at chills. May gamot naman na siya nun, kung бага monitoring lang siya. Yun naman yung kahit papano yung binabantayan namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Si papa mo nun, hindi pa nagbarko?</i>
254	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nasa barko pa siya nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung venue sa sala saka sa dining ka lang nun 'di ba? Wala naman tao nun?</i>
255	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kung may tao man, nasa kwarto sila</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sinasabihan ba sila nung magulang mo na nag-aaral ka?</i>
256	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ah, nung pagkagraduate ko, nung sinabi ko sa mama ko na sa bahay na lang ako mag-aaral, humingi ako ng request na kung pwede huwag na muna ako bigyan ng pressure sa bahay. Kumbaga babawi na lang ako kapag pumasa na ako, which is hindi naman naging mahirap sa mga kapatid ko—kumbaga “pagbigyan muna natin si Ate na tapusin na niya muna yung pressure niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung review materials, yung kay Saunders saka yung ReviewCenterE. Dalawa lang talaga ha? (Smiles)</i>
257	Ms. NurseE	<i>(exchanged smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>At yung kay Saunders, kinuha mo sa kaibigan, heto (referring to Balita’s reviewer) binili mo ‘to...</i>
258	Ms. NurseE	<i>Binili ko ‘to.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero may iba ka namang libro?</i>
259	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nung college wala. Yun nga yung malungkot eh. Kasi naglalibrary talaga ako. Tagalang super-tiyaga ko nun (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pareho pala talaga tayo ha (smiles). Yung strategies nag-a lot ka ng time, one month yun.</i>
260	Ms. NurseE	<i>One month na focused talaga dun sa pinag-aaralan ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos nakatulong yung pre-review.</i>
261	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, yung pre-review. Kumbaga may mga ideas na ako na ‘ah ito yung lalabas.’</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halimbawa, yung mga updates, sa review center normally binibigay yun eh. Halimbawa yung sa Board of Nursing (members), heto yung specialty niya...nakikibalita ka rin bas a mga kaibigan mo?</i>
262	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa review center? Hindi ako tumingin sa exam nila, kasi nga baka madiscourage ako...Yung tinanong ko lang sa kanila, kung anong performance nung review center nila. Yun nga, may mga performance (show) pa nga daw yung mga instructor</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Performance?</i>
263	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo yung parang mga icebreaker</i>
Researcher:		<i>Ah, oo, yun nga rin naririnig ko eh.</i>
264	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tapos yung sinasabi nila advantage daw ni ReviewCenterE sa ibang review center ay yung shading. Kasi may material silang...let's say after ng review, siguro may exams din sila. Ang SchoolE (University) kasi, ang shading namin yung bilog, sa mga major exams lang yun, pero yung sa board (exam) kasi is rectangle na maliliit? Ayun, si ReviewCenterE na review center, meron nun. Nagpapractice sila ng tamang shading (smiles). Yun lang yung hiningi kong tip sa kanila: ano nga ba yung tamang shading?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh, papano daw ba yung tamang shading?</i>
265	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yun nga yung hindi sobrang gaan, hindi rin sobrang diin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung Mongol #2?</i>
266	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, Mongol # 2, yung side muna ng rectangular. Hindi yung kalat-kalat</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, side muna tapos papasok?</i>
267	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi, diretsong shade, from left to right. Basta kailangang straight.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kumbaga isang direksyon lang?</i>
268	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, isang direksyon lang. Hindi yung kalat-kalat. Tinanong ko," pano kapag erasures"? Ang technique daw nun, kapag binura mo sa harapan, burahin mo din daw siya sa likod, para hindi maiiwan yung bakat. Yun lang yung hiningi kong tips sa kanila, sa review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sinabi mo dalawa lang yung ginamit mo, heto yun (pointing to Balita's reviewer), saka yung Saunders, halimbawa natapos ka na ng review, sa tingin mo ba sapat na yung review materials na binasa mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

269	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi yung ibang classmate ko na maraming review materials, nagkakarun sila ng confusion dun sa sagot ni...halimbawa ni ReviewCenterE Balita. Meron pa kasi silang ibang ginamit eh, yung mga sikat na ibang libro..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ReviewCenterF?</i>
270	Ms. NurseE	<i>Meron pang isa... naguguluhan lang sila. Disadvantage yung explanation na iba-ibang libro yung binabasa mo. Kaya sabi ko mag-stick lang ako kay Saunders, kay Saunders lang. Hindi na ako magbabasa pa ng iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero hindi mo ba naisip na, baka mamaya conflict naman si Saunders sa mga sagot ng Board of Nursing (BON) na gumawa ng exams?</i>
271	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi naman...ang nakita ko ang dami-dami nila reference eh. Naguguluhan sila eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa isa ka lang talaga?</i>
272	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa isa lang ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero hindi mo ba naisip yung risk na yun na ila nga rito nagkakagulo eh. Authority na yan si ReviewCenterG, si ReviewCenterE, baka mamaya yung binasa kong Saunders, iba rin yung sagot sa Board (-of Nursing)?</i>
273	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi naman. Para sa akin kasi nung tiningnan ko yung materials nila, iba yung Saunders, detailed kasi siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagkarun ka ba ng relaxation moments in between?</i>
274	Ms. NurseE	<i>Wala ang hobby ko lang tulog lang (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano katagal yun?</i>
275	Ms. NurseE	<i>2-3 hours, pero kung 3 hours hindi ko pa rin kayang bumangon, itutuloy ko pa rin yung tulog ko. Inienjoy ko lang yung sleep moments ko. Kasi nga yun na lang yung parang (relaxation) ko eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang kinakain na mga chips?</i>
276	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ay totoo yan, hindi chips, candy. Yung bilog, butter----butter ball.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Butter ball?</i>
277	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ano ba tawag sa kanya? Yung lumang candy? Oo nga, yun yata tawag dun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit? Ano daw meron dun?</i>
278	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sabi nila nakakaincrease daw yun ng serotonin hormone (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>
279	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ewan ko kung scientific yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong pakiramdam mo?</i>
280	Ms. NurseE	<i>Siguro nalilibang ka kasi may kinakain ka. Hindi ka man ngumunguya, pero nasa bibig mo. Kumbaga iniincrease yung glucose. Parang na-energize ka ulit. Siguro all in the mind na lang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Parang psychological effect na lang.</i>
281	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, nakatulong naman siya sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Para magsupply ng glucose</i>
282	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, 45 minutes na'ko nag-aaral, di ba nakakapagod na...para magtuloy-tuloy yung aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung tulong sa school tungkol lang sa speech nung Dean mo, at syempre yung pre-review malaking bagay din yun na nakatulong sa'yo. Yung overall educational program o preparation mo, sa buong apat na taon mula sa Pamantasan, hanggang sa napunta ka sa SchoolE (University), ano yung naging effect nun dun sa performance mo sa board exam?</i> <i>(Some silence...) O inaattribute mo talaga mostly sa review mo?</i>
283	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo kasi more on solo ko na. Sabi ko nga stock knowledge na lang yung sa mga teachers eh. Kumbaga may idea ka na dun, mas nadagdagan na lang yun nung nagbabasa ka ng sarili mo. Hindi na yung inispoonfeed nila.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Sa tingin mo ba may mga bagay na plus points dun sa dalawang school mo na yun, o meron bang nakita mong inadequacy o kulang na dapat sana naibigay nila. Kumbaga objectively lang, hindi dahil sa gusto mong siraan, yung kakailanganin ng isang estudyante na dapat sana nareceive niya?</i></p> <p><i>Sa advantage muna, sa plus points muna...</i></p>
284	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Siguro maswerte na lang din ako dahil ang alam ko ang school ng SchoolE, focus sila sa mga medical fields. Oo, ang alam ko yun ang forte ng school na yun eh.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>May Medicine (course) dun 'di ba?</i></p>
285	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Oo, maski pati sa gamit, meron kasi kaming sa nag-aaral o nagrereview, hindi mo masabing classroom lang eh. Mararamdaman mo na iba yung environment nung school, habang nung nag-aaral ka ng mga major (subjects) mo, o nung minor mo.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Panong "environment"? Anong meron dun?</i></p>
286	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Parang conference room siya na malaki, iba kasi talaga siya, covered siya.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Library yun?</i></p>
287	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Hindi, hindi library, parang conference hall.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Dun ka nagpupunta?</i></p>
288	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Hindi, sa lahat ng nag-aaral. May subjects kami, sa pre-review namin. Meron siyang recreational hall din, basta (smiles)</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Pero merong mga recreational facilities? Meron ganun?</i></p>
289	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Wala, library lang meron sila eh. Walang masyadong ganun yung school namin. Yun lang library, classrooms. Kasi focus sila sa nursing saka medicine eh. May mga virtual lab, mga skills lab, yun lang.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Nakatulong naman ba yun sa board exam mo?</i></p>
290	Ms. NurseE	<p><i>Oo, kasi sa board exam 'di ba may theory and actual? Kahit papano nagamit ko yun.</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung bago ka mag-review, halimbawa galing ka lang sa regular na pag-aaral hanggang 4th year, yung confidence level in a scale of 1-10. Kung mag-eexam ka ng board exam, anong confidence level mo?</i>
291	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nasa 8.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nasa 8 ka na nun? Before the review?</i>
292	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga confident na'ko na yun nga before board alam kong kaya ko siya. Hindi ko siya (naisip) na magffailed ako kagad.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(Reiterating) So bago ka mag-review mga ilan yung confidence level?</i>
293	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nga nakagawa na nga ako nung (schedule) ko, 8 na kagad. Hindi ko kgada diniscourage yung sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After mong magreview?</i>
294	Ms. NurseE	<i>Alam kong 10 na yun! (Smiles), kasi nga papasa ako eh!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero di 'ba bago ka nagreview, sabi mo 8, pero nung nag mock board kayo, sabi mo mababa nakuha mo, pero yung confidence level mo pa rin 8 pa rin?</i>
295	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ah, oo. Isang araw lang kasi na nadisapoint ako eh, isang araw lang. Hindi siya yung kinabukasan ganun pa rin yung attitude ko. Parang encouragement lang sa akin yung pagkafailed ko nun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh okay. Sa tingin mo dapat ganun, na kapag bumagsak ka...</i>
296	Ms. NurseE	<i>(interrupts) Malalaman mo pa lang na kung sa assessment bumagsak ka, malulungkot ka na 'nagfailed ako dun'..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong naramdaman mo?</i>
297	Ms. NurseE	<i>Malulungkot ka na parang "Ah hindi ba ako papasa"?!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga ilang oras yung lumipas nung maisip mo na "hindi challenge lang 'to..."</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

298	Ms. NurseE	<i>Palabas ako ng classroom, after ng mock board, that day rin, may result kagad. Kasi nga nagpalitan kami ng papel, checkan lang, so nalaman ko kagad yung result. Paglabas ko sabi ko dun sa kasama ko "Dahil ba bumagsak ako ng mock board, hindi na'ko papasa?"--- "Hindi rin", sabi ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero pano nila pinirmahan yung credentials? Normally 'di ba kapag hindi ka pumasa...</i>
299	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ah, hindi. Sa qualifying kasi pasado 'di ba. Yun yung school yung nagccheck.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mock board yun yung sa ReviewCenterE?</i>
290	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi siya ReviewCenterE (review center), sa school din pero hindi siya yung basis.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah hindi siya yung basis para hindi ka makapagboard.</i>
291	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tinitingnan nila yung Compre (Comprehensive exam) saka Qualifying (exam). Tinitingnan nila kung sapat na ba yung nareview mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Satisfied ka naman dun sa naging result ng board (exam)?</i>
302	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi hindi ko nga iniexpect eh (smiles). Ang dream ko pa nga mag-85 above eh, kumbaga magtop notch. Kaya lang yun lang eh, yun lang talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Syempre, tapos hindi ka pa talaga nanghingi ng tulong talaga sa iba 'noh, sa sarili mo lang.</i>
303	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kaya nga sabi ko, ako na siguro yung pinakamayabang that time, nung pumasa ako! (Grins)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ang galing ah! So ano sa tingin mo yung mga factors na nakatulong? Rundown ko lang: yung pre-review, yung ginawa mong ito, ano pa? Kung meron man.</i>
304	Ms. NurseE	<i>(thinking) Meron pa ba 'kong naging preparation sa sarili ko...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kumbaga may iba pa bang taong nakatulong?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

305	Ms. NurseE	<i>Okay na yun eh, sila Uncle lang saka yung mama ko, sila yung naging motivation, na nag-encourage sa'kin na kailangan magawa ko nga yun. Parang isinasalang-alang ko yung pangalan ng family ko. Kasi nga yung papa ko nga, namamaliit siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo yun kinonvert sa pag-aaral? Kumbaga papano nakatulong yung mga motivation na yun para aralin mo talaga siyang maigi? Anong nangyari?</i>
306	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi kung discouragement lang, tama na yung isang araw lang, na ganito yung ano ko, parang dapat kinabukasan bago na, na kailangan mag-aral na'ko. Yun, yun na kagad naisip ko nun. No more hindrance na yun, kailangan focus na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So hindi ka na nagttexting, August pa lang..</i>
307	Ms. NurseE	<i>Nagttext naman, kapag importante, pero wala na yung chat-chat na 'uy friend...' wala na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron ka mang bagay na dapat sana ginawa nung nagrereview ka, looking from behind, n asana nagawa ko' to mas lalo pa sanang naging okay yung result ko. Di ba sabi mo kanina goal mo 85+ 'di ba? Ano yung mga bagay na hindi mo nagawa na ginusto mo sanang gawin na sana nakatulong para mas ma-hit mo yung goal mo?</i>
308	Ms. NurseE	<i>Eh kasi wala naman akong (regrets) nun eh, hindi ko na naisip na sana mas ginanito ko pa..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung ngayon na?</i>
309	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kung ngayon? (Thinking...)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron kang maiimprove dun sa ginawa mo...</i>
310	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi alam ko ginawa ko na, focus ng lahat na eh. Nung nagrereview na'ko nun, buong sarili ko na nun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>O sige, mag-umpisa na lang ako dun sa rating. Sabi mo goal mo 85+ 'di ba?</i>
311	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Syempre 80+ ka 'di ba? Sa tingin mo pano mo mas na-hit dapat yung 85? Meron ka bang naidentify na may nagkulang ka, o papano ba?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

312	Ms. NurseE	<i>Baka yung shading ko (laughs). Baka hindi ko naperfect, baka yung tamang sagot hindi nabasa nung ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung magbibigay ka ng tip sa iba, yung sa shading?</i>
313	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, yung shading, dapat maging careful ka din dun. Kasi nagkaron ako ng erasure dun. Parang "Oh no"...Sabi kasi nila kapag nagbura ka na sa isa, pwedeng maapektuhan na yung iba mong sagot sa baba. Parang yun lang, siguro.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka pa bang bagay na masasabi tungkol sa nangyari sa'yo? Kumbaga sa strategies, kung meron ditong nurse-graduate sa harap, ano masasabi mo? In few words lang...</i>
314	Ms. NurseE	<i>Ang masasabi ko sa kanya, kung mag-aaral ka, piliin mo muna yung part kung saan ka mas mahirapan, kumbaga yun ang unahin mong aralin, kasi nga yun ang mga mahirap eh kesa ileft behind mo. Kasi feeling ko dun ka mas maraming dapat itackle compared dun sa mas madali mong subject. Tapos, makiramdam-ramdam ka rin sa paligid. Tama nga naman na may current events, bukod sa mga sikat na sakit ngayon, yung mga naririnig mo naman sa mga teachers mo yun na malamang, kung sino yung mga magiging board members ngayon ng board (Board of Nursing); kung sino yung mga gagawa nung exam. Kasi nagkarun ako ng mga ideas dun. Dun sa mga major exams mo na lagi na lang iniexam sa'yo, kumbaga kunin mo na yung mga bites ng knowledge na---"parang lagi 'tong lumalabas', tingin ko meron na naman". Kinukuha ko siya...Parang tinatandaan ko lang, kahit hind ko alam kung tama yung sagot ko dun. Yung question na yun na tungkol sa sakit na yun tinatandaan ko siya. Siguro yun siguro yung isa sa mga ano ko... na parang possible. Bigyang pansin mo lahat ng iniexam mo, ginagawa mo, na pwede pa la 'to, na lalabas pala. Yun ang masasabi ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Masasabi mo ban a yung sa ginawa mo na kailangan talagang nakaplano na siya?</i>
315	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, gumawa ka ng plano. Planner talaga, saka Calendar Planner talaga ang tawag ko rito eh, yung araw na nireview ko. Saka huwag siyang mag-skip. Kung ano na yung nilagay mo na yun na yung subject na pag-aaralan mo that day, yun lang. Huwag ka munang tatalon sa isa pang subject kasi magkaron ng confusion na hindi ka makakapagfocus sa subject that day kasi nga tumulong ka dun sa isang subject.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh halimbawa, ang sabi mo kanina, eh kung nakatulog ako ng, let's say, 2 hours, tapos hindi pa sapat tumuloy-tuloy ako, pano kapag hindi mo natapos, tapos the following day...</i>
316	Ms. NurseE	<i>(interrupts) Kailangang habulin ko kung ano yung target ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So mag-eextend ka ng 8 (PM)?</i>
317	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kung matutulog ako nung araw na yun, that time wala munang tulog-tulog, kailangan habulin ko yung subject na naiwan ko. Parang pinaparusan ko yung sarili ko (smiles). Siguro parang super-ego, para dun sa psyche (psychiatric nursing) (Smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So anong naging epekto nun sa rating mo?</i>
318	Ms. NurseE	<i>(Smiles) Siguro naman naging effective siya, kasi hindi naman ako naleft behind sa board.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pwedeng-pwede 'noh? (Smiles)</i> <i>Patapos na ito eh, last part na siya. Apat na questions na lang. Ito na yung sa mga "traits". Kaya inincorporate ko siya, kasi sa tingin ko meron din talagang value yung traits, yung ugali, yung values, yung qualities na tao, para makatulong dun sa mga ginawa niya. Kumbaga, siya yung nagsisilbi na panggatong dun sa niluluto mong pagkain which is "pumasa" o makuha mo yung gusto mong result.</i> <i>Naniniwala kasi ako na may intellectual part, pero meron ding emotional side, o psychological side. Kasi as a whole, like yung theory na biopsychosocial and spiritual being. 'Di bas a nursing may ganung theory 'di ba? So hindi lang talaga yungbiological, intellectual part, meron pa ring mga ganito eh. Do you share the same beliefs? O anong naging role sayo ng mga ganung bagay?</i>
319	Ms. NurseE	<i>Spiritually? Hindi ko naman inaano yung Catholic ha, lumaki kasi akong Christian. Parang more on faith yung ano..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagppray kayo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

320	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi that time may prayer, kasi August na nun may pre-review na kami. Yung prayer-fasting sa Church namin, one month yun. So parang super sacrifice yun. Nagrereview na nga ako ng madaling araw, tapos meron morning devotion sa church namin na 4:32 hanggang 6 (AM). So after nun magprayer na sa church, saka didiretso ng pasok. So that time nabuo na rin yung deeper faith ko nun kay God na, kasi sinasabayan ko rin ng prayer, one month yun, August yun, parang sacrifice na tinatawag. Nagkarun kasi ng program ang church namin, na parang prayer-fasting month.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga? Wow, galing ah. Ang ganda ng nangyari sa'yo ah.</i>
321	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga sakripisyo talaga. Actually nasanay ang katawan ko dun na less tulong, more on aral. Kasi nga feeling mo na nakapagpray ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero wala ka namang ginagamit na, like Cobra, ganun?</i>
322	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi. Walang gamot-gamot. Dati nga gusto ko ngang habulin yung kay Kuya Kim na brain enhancer. Kaya nga sabi naman nila...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, yung ano... Anong tawag dun?</i>
323	Ms. NurseE	<i>Memo Plus Gold (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Memo Plus Gold (exchanged smiles)</i>
324	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sabi ko, bibili pa ba ako nun? Kaya lang sabi ng doctor ng mother ko, nagkakaran lang daw ng effectivity yung Memo Plus Gold, kailangan 6 months before mag-aral ka, umiinom ka na nun. So, nag-rereview na'ko eh. Iinom pa ba 'ko?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>'Di ba may gluta...</i>
325	Ms. NurseE	<i>Glutathione? (Smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron yun tatlong piso lang yata na pang...</i>
326	Ms. NurseE	<i>Glutaphos?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ewan ko.. Nagtake ka ba ng ganon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

327	Ms. NurseE	<i>Magtatake pa ba ako nun eh nagreview na nga ako...So parang more on ano na ako, yung nga yung habit ko na August lang naman, yung prayer-fasting.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mabuti hindi ka inaantok, tapos nagpupunta ka pa sa church?</i>
328	Ms. NurseE	<i>Eh nasanay nga yung katawan ko nun. Kasi nga nagpray ako ng umaga eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May pressure ba yun?</i>
329	Ms. NurseE	<i>No, kasi alam mo na nagppray ka eh, Kasi nga alam mo na yung bagay na yun pinagkakatiwala mo na kay God.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ano sa tingin mo yung mga qualities ng isang..sa'yo..na nakatulong para pumasa ka o mareach mo yung goal mo? In relation to your review.</i>
330	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung pagiging panganay ko. Yun nga, lumaki nga ko na responsable.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo na-incorporate yun sa review mo?</i>
331	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sa pag-aaral ko, kasi nga focused ako eh, hindi ko sinasayang yung bawat oras.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So responsible, focused...</i>
332	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yung pagiging matiyaga ko, yung siguro yung pinakamalaking factor. Hind kasi ako matalino, pero matiyaga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin ko naman napakita mo rin, kasi 'di ba', hindi ka natutulong eh! (exchanged smiles)</i>
333	Ms. NurseE	<i>Siguro nasanay din yung katawan ko nun, kaya nga nung after board (exam) ko, after pagpasa ko, dun bumabawi yung "magpahinga ka, magpahinga ka" (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nung dati ba, matiyaga ka na ba talaga?</i>
334	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, ganun na talaga yung ugali ko nun. Sa lahat, kahit sa extracurricular, kailangan tapusin ko siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung nasimulan mo kailangan mong matapos?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

335	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo, kasi nga 'di ba, sa nursing parang nung una hirap na hirap ako. Pero naisip ko na, pinasok ko 'to eh, kailangan tapusin ko 'sya kahit na anong mangyari.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bukod dun, meron pa bang iba na tingin mo qualities mo, special traits mo na nakatulong maliban dun?</i>
336	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kumbaga naalala ko lang yung sinabi ng teacher ko dun sa C.A.T., na kumbaga yung karangalan ko, nakikita niya talaga na solo ko lang siya eh. Mag-isa kong kinukuha yung achievement ko. Kasi nga matiyaga nga daw ako. Para sa ibang tao nakikita rin nila na itong taong 'to, mag-aachieve siya sa sarili niya. Kasi nga, ganon nga siya. Hindi man super-brainy sa school na nasa top siya, kaya nga nagulat din sila na yung batang simple lang, naging ganun siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hetong susunod na tanong, tungkol ito sa ibang tao. Ano sa tingin mo yung mga qualities na dapat meron yung isang tao para maging effective, just like you, yung review niya?</i>
337	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sana matiyaga rin siya. Kasi nga naniniwala ako na hindi langkasi matatalino yung pumapasa ng board exam eh. Kasi may nakikita ako na yung matatalino yun pa yung lumalagapak. Kaya yung taong nagtiyatyagang mag-aral, sila yung nag-eexcel sa board exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May dilemma kasi ako eh: let's say sa isang graduate, hindi talagang pala-aral, sa tingin mo ba magiging effective sa kanya 'to? O kailangan niya talagang magrely sa review center?</i>
338	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kahit naman magreview center ka eh, kung makikinig ka, hindi ka naman pala-aral. Kasi kailangan mo pa ring magbasa, mag-effort. Hindi ako naniniawalang spoon-feed lang lagi. Kailangan ikaw yung magdedecide na heto yun, mag-aaral na talaga ako. Kumbaga ininternalize mo sa sarili mo na 'kailangan kong mag-aral'. Yung decided ka, yung sincere na yun na kailangan mag-aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mga taong pabanjing-banjing lang, ano yung mapapayo mo sa kanila? Kumbaga hndi naman yan papasa ng 4th year, kahit papano may galing din yan, pero alam naman natin na hindi talaga lahat pumapasa ng board exam, ang baba ng rating. So yung ibang mga taong ganun na hindi pumapasa, papano sa tingin mo ang dapat?</i>
339	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sayang kasi eh...nag-effort ka na eh, ba't hindi mo pa itodo... Sayang eh. Kasi nga naggraduate ka na, heto na yung board (exam), months na lang kasi 'to eh. Ang hirap naman kung paulit-ulit ka eh. Itake mo na yung pagkakataon na. heto na, para isang hirap na lang.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Isang hirap... naalala ko tuloy yung nangyari sa akin na, muntik ko na itigil 'to eh. 2 months akong tunigil. Sabi ko 'kailangan kong mag-umpisa ulit. Sayang yung pagkakataon'. Kaya dapat siguro, matanim din sa iba na, dapat yung sinimulan nila, tapusin talaga, which is napakita mo naman.</i>
340	Ms. NurseE	<i>Yes, yun nga nakakahiya din sa magulang mo eh. Kung pera-pera ang usapan, maswerte na lang ako dahil yung school namin provided nila yung review center. Pano kung hindi 'di ba? Pano kung wala namang kakayahan yung magulang mo? Sayang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung ulit ka uli, let's say, wala pa ring bayad yung review center, mas pipiliin mo ba yung self-review o magiging okay rin yung sa review center? Meron ka bang panghihinayang? Any regrets?</i>
341	Ms. NurseE	<i>Sabi ko nga sayo kanina, hindi nga ako nagkaroon ng (regrets), kahit na naexperience ko na bumagsak ako minsan (referring to her mock board), pero hindi ko naisip na magreview center, kasi hindi ko pa la siya kaya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ba yung sagot mo na yan walang kinalaman dahil sa mataas ang nakuha mo sa board exam?</i>
342	Ms. NurseE	<i>Hindi, hindi. Kasi hindi naman ako nun nag-eexpect ng mataas eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung mababa ang nakuha mo...</i>
343	Ms. NurseE	<i>Passing lang? Hindi, dun pa din ako sa self-review ko. Okay na'ko dun. Sabi ko may mga idea na ako eh. Yun na yun. Focused na'ko sa self-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano nakaapekto sa'yo, kanina intellectually, ngayon psychologically sa work mo ngayon yung retention nung knowledge na natutunan mo. Kasi naririnig ko lang ha: ang impression kasi, na sa review center saglit lang nareretail yung information.</i>
344	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi nga natatandaan mo dun yung pinerform nung mga instructor eh (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano, sa tingin mo, yung naging epekto sa'yo nung Saunders, nung pre-review, nung lahat-lahat na? That's my last question.</i>
345	Ms. NurseE	<i>Tingin ko mas mareretail siya kung self-review.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa papanong paraan?</i>
346	Ms. NurseE	<i>Kasi ikaw nag-aral mag-isa mo, kasi ninanamnam mo yung nirereview mo kasi nga ikaw lang mag-isa. Wala kang naging katulong sa pag-aaral mo na yun. So hanggang ngayon, siguro patanungan na lang, siguro kahit papano makakasagot ka compared dun sa may mga nakita silang mga examples. Ikaw, siguro kakayanin mong iexplain yun kasi nga naaral mo siya individually, yung bawat details kasi nga iniimagine mo mag-isa nung nag-aaral ka. Hindi pinaimagine sa'yo ng iba, kundi ikaw yung nag-iimagine mag-isa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So tapos na ang interview natin. Maraming Salamat. I have to let you go.. Salamat sa contribution mo, at malaking bagay 'to, hindi lang sa akin ha, personally. Natutuwa talaga ako makahanap ng mga taong kagaya ko 'di ba, yung pareho kayo ng pinagdaanan. Iba yun eh, iba yung pakiramdam nun. Pangalawa, me being a researcher, naexperience ko yung gumawa ng ganito na hindi naman ordinary na naexperience. Pupunta ka pa rito para lang mag-interview 'di ba? Hindi ka naman journalist! (Smiles), pero yung ano rito yung mga makikinabang, kung saka-sakali man, although hindi ko iniexpect na mapapublish o ano. Basta kung meron man tumingin na isang tao, at makatulong sa kanya okay na yun.</i>
347	Ms. NurseE	<i>Oo kasi para ma-encourage man lang sila na 'ah kahit hindi pala akomagreview center'. Feeling ko yung makikinbang niyan yung mga tao siguro na nagtitipid, o yung wala rin talagang panahon magreview center. Sa tingin ko pwede nilang magamit yan, o kaya sa mga taong ilang beses na nadiscourage na magreview center, hindi pa rin pumapasa sa board (exam), baka subukan nilang mag-selfreview. ☺</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maraming Salamat ulit.</i>
		--END-- [Time Stamp 02:09:00]

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
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ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, magandang gabi.</i>
1	Mr. NurseB	<i>Magandang gabi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Magandang gabi rin (smiles). My name is Neri Ocampo from St. Paul University, Manila. Tonight I'll be interviewing you about your experience with self-review. I have divided the interview into 4 parts. Yung 1st part is about your demographics and your educational background, anything about you. 2nd part is about your experience with self-review. The 3rd part is about some strategies that might help you, kung meron man, and lastly is about some traits that you may have identified that helped your review. My 1st question is about your name, your nickname... (Exchanged smiles).</i>
2	Mr. NurseB	<i>My nickname is "Mr. NurseB"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Age, optional</i>
3	Mr. NurseB	<i>26 years old</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>26 years old. Year of BSN graduation?</i>
4	Mr. NurseB	<i>2007, March.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was it your 1st course or 2nd course?</i>
5	Mr. NurseB	<i>1st course</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Your current occupation</i>
6	Mr. NurseB	<i>Call-center agent</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Any other previous employment, if any?</i>
7	Mr. NurseB	<i>None, but I volunteered for 2 months in Bulacan Provincial Hospital now the Bulacan Medical Center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So after you graduated in 2007, where were you?</i>
8	Mr. NurseB	<i>After I graduated my sister told me to take NCLEX then after passing NCLEX I started to apply in hospitals, but unfortunately I</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>wasn't able to get a job so I decided to volunteer in Bulacan Provincial Hospital for 2 months.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan yun?</i>
9	Mr. NurseB	<i>2008</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan ka nagtake ng NCLEX?</i>
10	Mr. NurseB	<i>February 2008.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay year or month your licensure exam was taken?</i>
11	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahmm, June 2007.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung license rating mo... It's only from 75-79, or 80 above</i>
12	Mr. NurseB	<i>80 and above</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung school mo, was it private or public?</i>
13	Mr. NurseB	<i>Private, ahh kailangan pa ba sabihin..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>It's up to you</i>
14	Mr. NurseB	<i>It's a SchoolB</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh SchoolB</i>
15	Mr. NurseB	<i>SchoolB Campus</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May kilala ako dun. Briefly can you tell me something about you; who you are as a person? More about upbringing, you main beliefs in life or education or anything that you value as a person; your main reason why, or the story behind why you took up nursing?</i>
16	Mr. NurseB	<i>Okay, pwede bang Tagalog?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay lang.</i>
17	Mr. NurseB	<i>Lumaki ako sa pamilya na...pano ko ba masasabi... Actually kasi sa aming magkakapatid 3 kaming nag-nursing. Yung tita ko nursing</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>din, kung baga siya yung naka-impluwensya sa amin na mag take ng nursing. Nasa states kasi siya so nakikita namin lagi siya umuuwi, lagi siya may pasalubong sa amin, ganyan-ganyan, so kumbaga nasabi niya din sa amin kung gusto ninyo mag nursing kayo para makapunta kayo dito tutulungan ko kayo para makapunta dito.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pang-ilan ka ba?</i>
18	Mr. NurseB	<i>Bunso</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan kayong magkakapatid?</i>
19	Mr. NurseB	<i>Apat. Bali yung eldest sister ko, tsaka yung sister na sinundan ko, sila yung dalawang nurses din. Tapos ako nag nursing din ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anything that you value in life or education?</i>
20	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh ayun, ahh ano ba yon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Upbringing mo paano ka lumaki sa isang..</i>
21	Mr. NurseB	<i>Upbringing?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Palalabas ka ba or paano ba yon?</i>
22	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayon, ano ahm kasi kami yung family na yung hindi masyadong... hindi naman masyado nakiki socialize, pano ba ito pano ko ba sasabihin, ano kung bago parang laging sa bahay lang kami kung lalabas kami siguro may family gathering, may lakad yung pamilya yon hindi kami masyadong nakiki ano sa ano... sa labas ng bahay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lumaki ka ng ganon, mula nung elementary hanggang kelan?</i>
23	Mr. NurseB	<i>Actually hanggang college, pero nung college syempre nakalabas-labas na ako syempre pag may pasok, uwian ganyan nakakapunta ako kung saang lugar ko gusto. Nung high school din naman na pag halimbawa yung mga barkada namin nung high school nakaka socialize din naman kami. Siguro kung meron man particular date or period of time na yung parang puro bahay lang siguro nung elementary.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>How was your student life? How did you fair in your studies?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

24	Mr. NurseB	Study?
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mula elementary, kamusta yung pag-aaral mo?</i>
25	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayun, aral kung aral, pagdating sa bahay assignment. Parang ano siya parang may... hindi naman strict na reward or punishment yung mga ganon ba. Hindi naman kailangan mataas yung grades mo or kailangan pasado lang. Kapag pasado ka meron kang something ganyan-ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag-peperform ka naman sa school like...anong section ka?</i>
26	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, nung elementary ahm like siguro from grade 2- grade 6 nasa star section ako. Tapos nung grade 6 ako nag ano ako 3rd, meron bang 3rd honorable mention?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron</i>
27	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>3rd honorable mention</i>
28	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo yon, yun ang na achieve ko nung grade 6 ako nung grumaduate ako ng elementary. Tapos nung high school sakto lang wala naman akong award pero may mga subjects na nag e-excel ako like...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like what?</i>
29	Mr. NurseB	<i>nung 2nd year gusting-gusto ko kasi yung biology</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>aha</i>
30	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh</i>
31	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayun dun ako nag e-excel. Gusto ko nagkakabisado nung mga scientific name ng mga hayop, mga plants, mga ganyan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sinabi mo nag e-excel ka, like ahh nababanggit ka sa klase, papano ba yon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

32	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayon, pagka halimbawa sa mga periodic exam, mga ganyan, matataas or highest nakukuha ko, yun nga lang medyo sablay ako sa Chemistry saka Physics kasi may involve na math, medyo mahina kasi ako sa Math (smiles).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba yung mga gusto mong mga subjects?</i>
33	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayon most likely, yung basta kapag Science, huwag lang yung may involve na Math</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
34	Mr. NurseB	<i>tapos iba pa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>English?</i>
35	Mr. NurseB	<i>English okay din tapos yung iba ko pang gustong subject nung sa Technology and Home Economics.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
36	Mr. NurseB	<i>Gusto ko yung baking na part ng Technology and Home Economics. Gusto ko yung nagbake bake din ganyan, kung бага natutunan ko, o ganito lang pala madali lang pala mag-bake ng banana bread, mga ganyan, madali lang pala magluto ng ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung naging college ka, sabi mo na impluwensyahan kayo ng aunt mo. Was it really your 1st choice or napilitan ka or I mean..</i>
37	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi naman actually parang napilitan, parang hindi actually ako pinilit na mag nursing, kung бага personal choice ko na rin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>okay</i>
38	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi naisip ko "Oy, malaki pala sasahurin ko nito tsaka makakapag-US pa ako pag nagkataon diba so ang tinake ko nursing, pero siguro kung hindi nursing ang pinili ko ang tinake ko siguro is ano Linguistics... naalala mo pa ba yon? Ay hindi, yung ano pa nga pala yon nung</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pre- FT (Foundations training)</i>
39	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi nung FT, nasabi ko kasi sa klase ko yon..</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh Linguistics...</i>
40	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh Linguistics...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo nga pala, oo, yun yung interest mo diba?</i>
41	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yun pa yung isa ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Can you tell me more about it? Paano nag-umpisa yon?</i>
42	Mr. NurseB	<i>Alin?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung hilig mo sa Japanese art</i>
43	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh ano, kailan ba nauso yung anime? Nung elementary may anime na yon, Dragon Ball, Ghost fighter yon parang na-amaze ako nakikita ko yon tapos alam mo yon na parang stress reliever na din siya and the same time may values kang nakukuha, yon para sa akin ha..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May values</i>
44	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What values?</i>
45	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, yung iba kasi sinasabi puro violence daw ganyan pero ano kung titingnan mo sa ibang perspective or ano yun nga makikita mong may values like yung friendship, ahh camaraderie, yung essence na huwag kang susuko, na may pag-asa pa ganyan-ganyan, huwag kang mawawalan ng pag-asa yung mga ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano nagiging epekto sayo kapag nanonood ka ng mga ganon?</i>
46	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayun, yung pinaka major effect sa akin like yung ahh huwag ka mawawalan ng pag-asa, kung бага...hindi pa katapusan ng mundo pag may, pag may halimbawa particular event sa buhay ko parang hirap naman nitong takasan or ano kung бага nagbibigay siya ng... ano ba tawag dyan kung бага..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Inspiration</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

47	Mr. NurseB	<i>Inspiration kung baga nag-strive hard ako para malampasan ko yung particular event sa buhay kong yon na nahihirapan ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You draw anime's or..?</i>
48	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yun ang problema ko lang, hindi ako magaling magdrawing.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong gusto mo dun ahh sa anime?</i>
49	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa anime ang gusto din. Nasabi ko na ba sayo na nag co-cost play din ako pero</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh</i>
50	Mr. NurseB	<i>Twice ko pa lang siya nagawa yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabagay maganda rin naman talaga yung...even me Naruto hanggang ngayon, Samurai X, gusting-gusto ko pa din.</i>
51	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, diba nagka movie pa nga?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, oo. Maiba tayo ng konti, when you went to college ano yung mga naging hilig mo na subjects, kung meron man?</i>
52	Mr. NurseB	<i>Anong nahiligan kong subject? Ano nga ba? ahm ano ba ito nung 1st year, 2nd year</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>oo nung 1st year</i>
53	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano ba ito, proper na?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kahit saan</i>
54	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano nga ba nakalimutan ko na...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay proper or anything na naalala mo</i>
55	Mr. NurseB	<i>Anything na naalala ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...na magaan sa loob mo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

56	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh nutrition (smiles), ano ba yon, oo Nutrition and Dietetics, nakalimutan ko na. Yon okay din yun, yung sa mga pagkain.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
57	Mr. NurseB	<i>Tapos ano pa ba, ahh yung Foundation 100 ba yon o 1, o 100</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>N100</i>
58	Mr. NurseB	<i>NCM 100 ba yon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>NCM 100.</i>
59	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kung бага parang yun yung pinaka basic tsaka nag enjoy din kami dun wala lang kung бага 1st encounter mo dun sa ahh ganito pala pag sa nursing may mga ganito ganyan, pero eventually nong latter part na ng nung ano siguro mga 4th year ano ba yung Staffing ano bang tawag don?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Leadership?</i>
60	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, yun mga ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How were your studies like, in your class? Ikaw ba yung pala tanong gaya ko o</i>
61	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayan, ako yung silent type malalaman mo naman din dib a yung sa activity natin, hindi ako masyadong matanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ka natututo sa isang concept?</i>
62	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano ako eh, ano ko audio-visual learner ako e, ano pa ba yung isa kung бага gusto ko nakikita ko, naririnig ko, to the point minsan pag sinusulat ko na ano dun ako natututo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh sinusulat mo siya uli, inuulit mo?</i>
63	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo pero not all the time</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Let's say sa MS (Medical Surgical Nursing), halimbawa sa isang topic sa MS ahh let's say electrolyte imbalance, papano mo siya inoorganize sa isip mo na matutunan mo siya?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

64	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano yon, ginagawa ko minsan don, diba sinusulat ko siya?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uh huh,</i>
65	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi not by word by word sinusulat, minsan sinusulat ko siya na, hindi naman steno, kung baga sariling akin na shortcut.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
66	Mr. NurseB	<i>Halimbawa yung mga concept na hindi ako ma...yung parang madali kong matandaan, natatandaan mo pag halimbawa, ahm ano ba yon yung left at tsaka right sinister, dexter</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay OD ganun.</i>
67	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo ginagawa ko Sleft, Dright parang sleft diba sinister</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh may mnemonics ka</i>
68	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, sinister left, dright diba dexter right yung mga ganun, gumagawa ako ng sarili kong way para matandaan ko yung concept nung isang particular na topic, mga ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ikaw yung tipo ng analytical o you memorize o</i>
69	Mr. NurseB	<i>parang combination yata ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Combination pero kung may 50-50 o merong kang preferred?</i>
70	Mr. NurseB	<i>50-50 kung baga tinitingnan ko yung kung ano yung way na matututo, hindi ako nag stick sa isang ano sa isang strategy or ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like apart from that anong strategy yung tingin mo nagawa mo na?</i>
71	Mr. NurseB	<i>Nagawa ko na, ano nga ba, actually wala akong iniisip na kung anong strategy basta kung ano yung maisip ako dun ako kung baga, walang particular na strategy akong pinipili or inaano basta just go with the flow, parang ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung like yung grades mo ganun ahh when you were 1st year, 2nd year</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

72	Mr. NurseB	<i>1st year? Okay naman..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...going forward</i>
73	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, wala meron ba akong 3.0 nun? Echos, may Tres naman ako ano bang subject yon, nakalimutan ko na parang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Minor?</i>
74	Mr. NurseB	<i>Minor lang naman siya hindi siya, siguro kung meron man akong mababa nung nasa nursing proper na ako, 3rd year, 4th year, ang mababa ko is 2.75 or 2.5 ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay yung mga subjects mo, old curriculum ka ba o ano yung bago na?</i>
75	Mr. NurseB	<i>Old yata ako, yung meron pang Zoology. Ay hindi ano nga ba..?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Old yata ako, yung meron pang Zoology. Ay hindi ano nga ba..?</i>
76	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ha?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Patho</i>
77	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh oo, okay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, nag Pathophysiology ka.</i>
78	Mr. NurseB	<i>Anatomy and Physiology o Pathophysiology, ahh basta hayaan mo na, basta yung old pa rin yon, nag-disect pa rin kami ng palaka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talaga. Paano ka ba mag-aral non, by group or mag-isa ka lang?</i>
79	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ay mag-isa lang ako. Alin yung halimbawa yung magrereview ako ng exam ganun? Mag-isa lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say for periodicals (exam)</i>
80	Mr. NurseB	<i>Mag-isa lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mag-isa lang kahit nung college ka?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

81	Mr. NurseB	Oo, oo.
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Although medyo nasabi mo na eh pero just to make it clear, do you consider yourself as a people person or someone that prefers to do things alone?</i>
82	Mr. NurseB	<i>Mas more ako dun sa ano work alone, pero I can work in groups din naman. Mas preferred ko lang talaga yung mag-isa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang nakikita mo pag mayroon kang kasama? Ano bang nangyayari?</i>
83	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro pag may kasama ka mas okay kasi 'cuz enjoy. Mas enjoy pero meron din minsan hindi maganda pagka-group eh. Mas less mong maaccomplish yung... kung baga may time sa iba, kung mag study kayo in groups may tendency na pag puro daldalan, hindi ninyo maaral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kung pare-pareho naman kayo, like okay din naman yung mga kasama mo?</i>
84	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro kung yung mga kasama ko ano ahh focused din sa pagrereview okay din pero mas prefer ko rin talaga na by myself.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito yung 2nd portion is about your experiences na, like fast-tracked na 'to after your graduation and then finally you will now be taking, supposedly, kung baga mga panahon na ito, you will now taking the board exam, nagseself-review ka na.</i>
85	Mr. NurseB	Oo
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh the question is "what were the factors or reasons that may have influenced you to decide to self review?"</i>
86	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh...Course?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like possible personal reasons, individuals or situations that might have influenced you in making a decision..</i>
87	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi dun sa amin sa SchoolB kasi ano meron na kaming review program para sa aming mga graduating na yun nga na pag last sem na namin every Saturday, Sunday basta every weekend meron kaming review program, ayun uma-attend kami dun tapos yun nagrereview kami binibigyan kami ng mga exam ganyan tapos after the exam, idi-discuss yung mga item ganyan, yung rationale, ganyan tapos</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
88	Mr. NurseB	<i>Pero hindi siya yung sinasabi mo na nagreview center, hindi naman, parang ano lang kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In-house yon?</i>
89	Mr. NurseB	<i>In house kasi iba yung review-center yun yong pagkatalagang after na ng grumaduate ka na talaga, yun yung talagang review center diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw papano ka nagself-review, bakit ka nakapag decide na okay na magreview na sarili na lang?</i>
90	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sabi ko sa sarili ko, "okay din naman kasi yung since may 2 akong sisters kasi diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
91	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sila kasi hindi din nagreview center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh</i>
92	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, ang sabi nila sa akin, ano basta mag review ka lang ng magreview, magpractice ka ng mga questions, ganyan kung baga makakaya mo din yan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talaga?</i>
93	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi sila nag review?</i>
94	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, hindi sila nag review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Same school kayo?</i>
95	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, SchoolB din..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow, astig ah!</i>
96	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yung ate ko kasi PT, grumaduate din siya ng SchoolB. Licensed Physical Therapy din siya eh yung mga time na nag PT siya yun</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>yong boom na boom yung PT tapos nung ga-graduate na siya medyo nag li-low na yung PT so nung after niya grumaduate wala siyang makitang work ganyan, nag nursing siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh, dalawa course niya.</i>
97	Mr. NurseB	<i>Double degree siya tas yon, yun nga sinuwerte siya naipasok siya nung pinsan namin sa US dun na siya ngayon like for...since 2006-7,8,9,10,11,12</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>6 years na.</i>
98	Mr. NurseB	<i>6 years</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So naimpluwensyahan ka nila na mag self-review. Hindi ka ba natakot sa panahon na yon?</i>
99	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi naman ahh, kasi kung baga na prove ko naman sa sarili ko na lumampas...Sa amin kasi sa SchoolB bago ka mag board exam, papasok ka muna sa isang series of, ano yun, pinaka compre (comprehensive exam) yata yun...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
100	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kung baga ang umpisa mo niyan sa finals, kung baga dun ka na magsisimula eh, kung baga dun na prove mo na pasado ka ng finals ibig sabihin okay kaya ko ito tapos review review ng para sa compre. Kung pumasa ka ng compre, ahh okay, sige okay pwede na kung baga kaya ko ng mag board exam yon. Kasi sa amin pag nakapasa ka dun sa exam na yon, papakuhanin ka nila ng board (exam) pero pag di ka pumasa...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pre-board exam yon?</i>
101	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, parang ganun, kung baga next time ka na lang uli mag te-take ng board exam, pag di ka pumasa dun sa exam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school, after in house?</i>
102	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano kasi, yung eto eto, yung isa sa mga reviewers naming nung exam, yung sa in house namin na nung bago kami grumaduate ano siya, ahh graduate din siya ng SchoolB tapos di ko alam kung sa ReviewCenterB (a review center) ba siya nag nagrereview, ano ba tawag dun sa nagrereview?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Reviewer?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

103	Mr. NurseB	<i>Reviewer... hindi ko alam kung sa ReviewCenterB1 siya or sa ReviewCenterB2 (review center) siya reviewer parang ganon, yon kung бага nabanggit niya lang. Hindi naman niya kami inencourage na magreview kayo dito after ninyong grumaduate.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Hindi naman required?</i>
104	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi naman, hindi naman required.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So after you took the preboard exam saka you passed, ahh wala na okay na sa kanila yon?</i>
105	Mr. NurseB	<i>Wala na oo, okay na sa kanila yon, as long as makapasa ka dun sa exam na yon papayagan ka na nila magboard exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you decide to self review? Way before graduation, immediately after graduation or</i>
106	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh, actually bago pa ako grumaduate eh, nagdecide na ako na hindi na ako mag- review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano kalaki yung epekto sa'yo ng mga kapatid mo na di nag review (center)?</i>
107	Mr. NurseB	<i>Malaki, as in malaki talaga yong epekto kung бага, it runs in the family...joke (smiled)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh</i>
108	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro isa yun sa mga pinagkakatiwalaan. Hindi, pano ko ba sasabihin? Kung бага confident ako sa sarili ko na makakaya ko yung board exam kasi yung mga kapatid ko nakaya din nila eh kung бага nagigauge ko naman yung sarili ko na kung бага naikukumpara ko naman yung sarili ko dun sa dalawa kong kapatid. Sabi ko, okay kaya ko ito, basta kailangan lang talaga may focus ako dun sa pag-rereview makakaya ko yun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay nabanggit mo nga mga kapatid mo diba, nabanggit mo ba sa parents mo at ano naging reaction nila?</i>
109	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yun dun sa hindi ako mag rereview-center? Ano kasi sa kanila din kung бага confident din sila na makakaya kong makapasa sa exam, sa board exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi minsan pumasok sa usapan nila na magreview center ka na lang?</i>
110	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa isip, sa usapan nila na halimbawa yung magreview center ako? Hindi, hindi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga? Wow ha</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

111	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi, alam mo...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>O sige kwento mo na.</i>
112	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ang nakakatawa niyan... alam mo kung ano kung saan ako nag review center? Nung nagtake ako ng IELTS (laughs).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
113	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi dun ako di masyadong kuwan... kasi ibang usapan na yon. Yon eh nakakatakot eh, may bayad diba? Magkano ba bayad sa IELTS, parang basta lahat lahat na kasama yung review parang 12 (thousand) ba yung nabayaran ko... 13, 14 (thousand) ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May nabanggitan ka ba na kaibigan or kaklase or like from the faculty about your decision? Ano naging reaction nila, kung meron man?</i>
114	Mr. NurseB	<i>Alin yung hindi magreview?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
115	Mr. NurseB	<i>Wala. Kasi ewan ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kanya-kanya na kayo?</i>
116	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kanya kanya lang kung meron mang nagreview center sa amin siguro iilan lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talaga maraming di nag review sa inyo sa review center?</i>
117	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, kasi kung бага kontento na sila dun sa in-house (review) ng school namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta pala yung passing rate nung kayo?</i>
118	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa school? Okay naman, alam ko hindi naman kami ano eh, pagkakaalam ko ahh hindi naman kami hindi bagsak sa pagkakaalam ko, pero ewan ko lang yung mga sumunod na ano yung sa batch namin alam ko pasado naman yata, yata.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban dun sa mga kapatid mo, meron ka pa bang kakilala na iba na hindi nag review center?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

119	Mr. NurseB	<i>Iba na hindi nag review center? Yung pinsan ko kaso nung ano pa... nito medyo na hindi ko alam 2011 yata siya nagtake ng board, pumasa naman siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If you can put your experience in like one sentence or phrases or words ano yon, what could that be?</i>
120	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano ba ito parang...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like yung description mo lang what happened to you?</i>
121	Mr. NurseB	<i>Parang advise ba ito?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ano ahh how can you describe, what happened to you in one sentence?</i>
122	Mr. NurseB	<i>In one sentence</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, one phrase or one word</i>
123	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo ahm well, hmm... pano ko ba iaano, basta nag focus lang talaga ako dun sa review tapos ano mystery, ano kasi ahh faith, kung бага parang sabi ko ahm 'Lord tulungan ninyo akong mapili ko yung tamang answer kung бага, kaya ko naman ito' ahm nag-aral naman ako, nagreview naman ako, kung бага tulungan ninyo ako na masagot ko ng tama yung mga questions na ma e-encounter ko ganun'.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If you can put like an adjective to that statement?</i>
124	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Adjective.</i>
125	Mr. NurseB	<i>Adjective? ano nga ba ahm 'perseverance', hindi perseverance hindi naman adjective yung eh (smiles), ano nga ba ahh adjective</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like for me, ahh "fulfilling"</i>
126	Mr. NurseB	<i>Fulfilling</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anything na ikaw kung, ano gusto mo?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

127	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala ba?</i>
128	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano nga ba, wala ako maisip na.. sige "fulfilling"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay ahh, nagkaron ka ba ng mga challenges nung mga panahon na yon?</i>
129	Mr. NurseB	<i>Challenges...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like anything nung bago ka magreview,</i>
120	Mr. NurseB	<i>Bago ako magreview</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tsaka during review..</i>
121	Mr. NurseB	<i>During ako magreview, ahm siguro kung challenge man yun siguro yung iniisip ko kung ano yung mga questions na maaring pero hindi eh... challenge eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like nagkaroon ka ba ng problema na maghanap ng review materials, tapos nahirapan ka bang magreview, maingay ganon...</i>
122	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi naman, ang medyo na ha-hassle lang ako yun nga nung last sem namin, yun weekends pumapasok kami ganun dahil dun sa in-house review, pero masasabi ko sayo hindi kami salat sa review materials kung bago talagang busog kami sa review materials kung bago dun din kaya confident ako na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa school yon?</i>
123	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, hindi na namin kailangang magreview center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung habang nagrereview ka na may na encounter ka bang problem?</i>
124	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May nakaabala sayo, naka-antala sayo?</i>
125	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro nung ano, nung after nun nung grumaduate na kami, tas we're on our own na yung nag pre-prepare na kami for exam ahm siguro pag sa bahay kung sa magulo di ako makapag concentrate</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>pero most of the time naman nakapagreview ako sa bahay nakakapag focus ako, ahm kailan nga ba nagpapa rehistro sa PRC?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After na or before pa ng during exam</i>
126	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ay hindi yung magre-register for exam, nakalimutan ko na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay, hindi naman yun yung cases diba?</i>
127	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo nga pala...Hindi naman pala related sa exam yun, yaan mo na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay were you at any point during the course of your review tempted to quit self review and just enroll at a review center instead?</i>
128	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi ko na naisip</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo na naisip?</i>
129	Mr. NurseB	<i>Para kasing sayang sa ano yan...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You graduated 2007 diba, tapos nag te-take ka ng June ilang buwan yon dalawa?</i>
130	Mr. NurseB	<i>Grumaduate ako March</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh March ba</i>
131	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahm, March 15 ba o basta kalahatian ng March nung 2007</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2 ½ months ganun? How did you feel about the outcome of your review?</i>
132	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say in a scale of 1-10, 10 is the highest, ahh ano yung satisfaction mo</i>
133	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa review ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siguro compared with your yun rating mo na nakuha mo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

134	Mr. NurseB	Ano
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like personal feeling</i>
135	Mr. NurseB	<i>mga 6.5 – 7, ay hindi 7</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>7 oo. Ba't mo nasagot yon</i>
136	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi napasa ko naman yong board exam at tsaka yung resulta for test okay naman, ang sablay ko lang anong part, hindi ko alam eh. Saan yung NRES, Nursing research</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nursing Research?</i>
137	Mr. NurseB	<i>5 ba yon o 4?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>4 yata</i>
138	Mr. NurseB	<i>Basta kung alin sa 2, alin sa 2 may sablay ako sa 4 or 5, 5,4 4,5</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero overall malaki naman</i>
139	Mr. NurseB	<i>Okay naman, yung pinakamataas ko sa part 1</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Foundation?</i>
140	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ohh</i>
141	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yeah, yun nga kasi nga earlier Na sinasabi KO Na Na appreciate KO Na yung N100</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano sa tingin mo yung advantages ng pagsasarili ng review tsaka yung disadvantage, advantages kung meron man?</i>
142	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro kung ang advantages nung self review hawak mo yung oras mo, siyempre tsaka pwede kang magreview anytime and anywhere, tapos ang disadvantages naman maaring may mga materials ka na ma miss or mga tips or na pwede mong makuhanan ng strategy or something kung self-review ka lang, kasi pag sa review center</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>marami kang makukuhanan ng tips, mga testing strategies ganyan, pag self review syempre di mo magagaw yon pero nandyan naman yung internet diba, diba now a days diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakakatulong ba sayo yung internet dati?</i>
143	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi, hindi masyadong nakakatulong yung internet pa non diba, though meron na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mahal pa ang internet nun.</i>
144	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, 2007.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong naging epekto sa'yo ng experience na yon, if there was any, ahm the entire experience to you as an individual or as a nurse?</i>
145	Mr. NurseB	<i>Nung self review na yon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron o wala, alam ko short span of time lang yun eh pero kung meron man like after you passed the exam, pumasa ka pala, tapos nag self review ka</i>
146	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano , ano ba yung question, ano ba yung naging</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>effect</i>
147	Mr. NurseB	<i>Effect? Kung baga... Tama ba... tumaas ang self steem? Hindi, ano ba, ahm hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>nagboost</i>
148	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayun nag boost yung self-steem, or something tapos ano yun nga mas na ahm sorry naman (cellphone ringing)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sige lang</i>
149	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hello</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sige lang</i>
150	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yes nandito ako wait lang ini interview ako (Participant taking up call)...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Si Rodj</i>
151	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo si Rodj, parating na siya, ahm saan na ba tayo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Going back, yung effect sa'yo diba ng review experience, nag boost yung self-steem mo, in what way?</i>
152	Mr. NurseB	<i>Pano nga ba? Hindi ganito na lang--- ahm kung baga parang I can deal, hindi naman I can deal with anything, siguro pag may dumating na isang bagay na mahirap or ano kung baga madali kong... I can find ways na ma accomplish ko yung isang bagay or malampasan ko yung isang bagay na na darating, 'yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay let's proceed to ano na lang sa strategies. Papano mo nagawa yung review? How did you, how did you do it made it effective for you?</i>
153	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ha?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano mo ginawa yung review mo?</i>
154	Mr. NurseB	<i>Paano ko ginawa yung buong review?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, oo</i>
155	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano, kung baga ginawa ko rin ito ng ano eh, kung baga in-apply ko din nung nag NCLEX ako basta ang ginagawa ko lang ay halimbawa magbabasa ako ng topic sa book, tapos after that mag te-take ako ng mga sample questions ganyan, ganyan. Sinasagutan ko tapos after that chini-check ko kung tama yung answer yung mga sinagutan ko tapos binabasa ko yung rationale kung baga from dun sa book in-apply ko dun sa test questions kunyari.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like for example, isang araw yon?</i>
156	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Merong ka bang like schedule o plan activities for the whole o sinulat mo ba yon o ano lang?</i>
157	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahm gusto ko kung ano lang yung nadatnan ko sa book na ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagkaroon ka ba ng planning or anything?</i>
158	Mr. NurseB	<i>Merong kasi ang ginagamit ko non ano eh Saunders (book), 2 yon Saunders na yung Saunders na puro topic muna, topic tapos merong ding may mga light 10-15 questions after every topic tapos may isa</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>na Saunders na puro Q & A, questions and answer na book yun lang yung pinagreview han ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka nagkaron ng ibang libro?</i>
159	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi, may iba akong review material like syempre sa atin diba mga NRES (Nursing Research) mga ganyan, eh wala namang masyadong dun sa Saunders. Kapag mga ganun hindi Saunders yung ginagamit ko, yung mga bigay na material ng school, galing sa school ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Previous like your notes sa schools...</i>
160	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ah, kasi more on ano kami, handouts, mga xerox ganyan ganyan, kung hindi man Xerox, yung mga may mga books kasi kami school na re print yung mga sinerox lang nila soft bound ba yon or something yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron kayong ganon, yon ang mga ginamit mo?</i>
161	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano ka ba usually nag-aaral sa isang araw, like anong oras?</i>
162	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano umaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...nagpapahinga ka ba o ano ginagawa mo?</i>
163	Mr. NurseB	<i>Depende ano, kung halimbawa, walang ginagawa sa bahay usually siguro mga 8 or 9 tapos siyempre may mga lunch break yan ganyan, merienda pag sa gabi siguro pinaka late ko na siguro 12 or 1 (midnight).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mula 8 or 9 ng umaga? Until what time?</i>
164	Mr. NurseB	<i>8 or 9 tapos hanggang 12 tapos ah siyempre tanghalian yon lunch break</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
165	Mr. NurseB	<i>...co-continue na ako siguro mga 2 (PM) tapos 2 kasi may meryenda pa na alas 4 dun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>oo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

166	Mr. NurseB	<i>Tapos minsan kasi paputol putol din</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
167	Mr. NurseB	<i>...tapos after dinner, siguro dinner ko mga 7-8, minsan 8-12 (midnight)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Monday to Friday yon o Monday to Sunday?</i>
168	Mr. NurseB	<i>Actually Monday to Sunday. Nung actually halos pareho lang siya nung nag board (exam) ako tapos nag NCLEX ako almost everyday.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Almost everyday? May portion ka ba sa bahay ninyo na dun ka nagstay or sa labas ka ba or sa kwarto ka lang?</i>
169	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa bahay lang talaga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I mean saang part ng bahay?</i>
170	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano sa... kasi sa bahay namin meron kaming yung parang dining table, naging parang study table na namin kasi hindi kami kumakain dun sa dining table, parang may dirty kitchen kami sa labas, dun kami kumakain, dun ako nag study dun sa malaking dining table yun talaga yung pwesto ko non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta yung lighting?</i>
171	Mr. NurseB	<i>Okay naman maliwanag naman, malaki yung ...light</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>flourescent light</i>
172	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nagreview ka nandun yung mga kapatid mo?</i>
173	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala na</i>
174	Mr. NurseB	<i>Wala na rin eh, yung sister ko wala na, eldest sister ko wala na, yung isa ko naman sister... ano nga ba ginagawa niya non? Wala rin siya dun eh, ano nga bang ginagawa niya... teka graduate na ako, graduate na rin siya nakalimutan ko basta wala naman siya dun eh.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh</i>
175	Mr. NurseB	<i>Di ko siya nadadatnan, basta usually nasa bahay lang nanay ko at tsaka tatay ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron bang mga tips na sinabi sayo o guide mga kapatid mo?</i>
176	Mr. NurseB	<i>...yung mga kapatid ko?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maliban dun sa sinabi niya kanina na mag question and answer</i>
177	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano yun nga, saka testing strategies, yung mga ganyan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Alin ba yung mga testing strategies na ginawa mo?</i>
178	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahm kasi nga parang in-adapt na din ng local boards natin yung NCLEX diba so parang yun nga yung mga select all that apply, or mga ganyan or halimbawa kung ano yung pinaka mahabang, pinakamahabang option or yun yung sagot, pero not all the time siyempre yun yung sagot talaga, basahin mo din talaga tas yung mga eliminations ganyan ano pa ba, nakalimutan ko na yung mga testing strategies na yon eh, yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo kanina yung one of the disadvantages of self review is like you didn't have yung mga tips na nanggaling sa review center mga ganon, papano mo how did you deal with them?</i>
179	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yun nga, yun sa mga kapatid ko, tsaka yung sa mga friends ko din diba tinatanong ko sa kanila ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...friends mo na?</i>
180	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yung mga friends na classmate ko din sa Fatima</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag review center sila?</i>
181	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi rin</i>
182	Mr. NurseB	<i>...kung бага ano lang kasi eh, parang naging... ang pangit pakinggan, kung бага kung ano yung natutunan namin sa in-house review nag she-share ran kami kasi yung mga friends ko,</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>yung karamihan ng mga friends ko, irregular section eh kung baga iba-iba kami ng schedule sa in-house review, iba iba rin kasi yung mga nag i-inhouse review sa amin, mga professors din sa University yon kung baga share-ran kami, halimbawa kay Mrs. Lopez...ganito yung mga tinuturo niya sa amin, kay Mrs. Cruz ano pa, ano pa yung mga tinuturo ni Mrs. Cruz ganyan, ganyan, ganun yung pag she-share namin ng mga ideas.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so maliban lang dun sa mag-isa ka nagreview, nag di-discuss din kayo?</i>
183	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ah, so maliban lang dun sa mag-isa ka nagreview, nag di-discuss din kayo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh sa school</i>
184	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, pagkamagkakasama kami, sa isang subject kasi may mga kasama ako, sa isang subject naman may iba din akong set ng mga kaklase ganun kasi pag irreg (irregular student) eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Per after na ng graduation yon?</i>
185	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi, yun yung last sem.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
186	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi diba in-house review pagka weekends?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero nung mag-isa ka ng nagreview wala na sila?</i>
187	Mr. NurseB	<i>Wala na, hindi na rin kung baga kung ano yung tinuro sa amin nung in-house review, ganyan ganyan, yun na yon dinala na namin hanggang mag-review kami ng board (exam).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano ka ba, paano mo ba inaral yung mga topics like ahh MS muna o halo halo?</i>
188	Mr. NurseB	<i>Halo halo na rin eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Halo-halo isang araw, halo-halo.</i>
189	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi naman halo-halo, parang kung ano lang yung matripan mo, sige ngayong aral MS ganyan-ganyan o halimbawa meron akong minsan kasi may mga bagay akong halibawa ito kailangan ko yata</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>itong ahm pagtuunan ng pansin ngayon, ganyan-ganyan may mga bagay akong parang mahina pa dito ganyan-ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mahina doon</i>
190	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo mga ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagkaroon ka ba ng relaxation moments o techniques between or while reviewing?</i>
191	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano nakikinig ako ng music.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong genre ng music yun?</i>
192	Mr. NurseB	<i>Nakakatawa ang mga pinakikinggan ko non mga Japanese (music).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh Japanese</i>
193	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, yung mga soundtrack ng ano (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba naging effect non sayo?</i>
194	Mr. NurseB	<i>Parang nakakaano eh, pano ko ba idi-discribe, nakaka energize ba or ano basta parang nakaka stimulate, hindi naman nakaka-stimulate (smiles), in a way na nakaka relax din at the same time o minsan pag gusto kong magbreak nanonood ako ng anime ganyan. Yung time na yon uso yung dvd, nauuso yung anime, pero ngayon makakapanood ka na naman sa online eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, kapag nagrereview ka ba may kinakain ka ba o talagang focus ka lang</i>
195	Mr. NurseB	<i>Talagang focus lang, hindi ako kumakain pag kumakain ako nagbe-break ako, nagpupunta ako sa kusina kakain ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano sa tingin mo naka apekto yung educational program mo sa... unang-una sa pagrereview mo, pangalawa sa licensure examination mo; pangatlo yung sa buhay mo, papano naka apekto yung school mo in terms of like academic preparation?</i>
196	Mr. NurseB	<i>Paano nakatulong?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano nakatulong.</i>
197	Mr. NurseB	<i>Paano nakatulong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung masasabi mo na sapat yung napag-aralan ko don o ano..</i>
198	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo masasabi ko naman na sapat yung napag-aralan ko don, mas sapat naman yung napag-aralan ko dun lalo na yung na-appreciate ko yung time na nagvo-volunteer ako sa Bulacan Medical Center, na-apply ko talaga yung lahat ng napag-aralan ko nung na rotate ako sa mga ward like nung sa ano sa OB, sa DR naku appreciate ko kasi pag provincial kasi parang maya't maya kada oras may mga nangangailangan ganyan-ganyan na apply ko yon na appreciate ko din nung ano, anong tawag dyan, kasi nag IV therapy chorba din ako licence, pero expired na ngayon di ko pa narerenew, yon maya't maya nakapag- insert ako, parang shooter na nga rin ako pero ewan ko lang kung kaya ko pang gawin mag insert yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ba't ka nga ba pala natigil don, two months lang?</i>
199	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ano kasi dapat for 3 months yung volunteer program nila eh tinamad na din ako kasi alam mo yun parang since volunteer ka lang yung experience talaga overwhelming nakakatuwa. Yun nga lang parang kulang walang, alam mo yun walang financial charge pero kahit sino naman diba</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
200	Mr. NurseB	<i>Who would want na ganon diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, bago ka magreview, bago ka magreview in a scale 1-10 ano yung confidence level mo na papasa ka? right after graduation?</i>
201	Mr. NurseB	<i>After graduation? ahm siguro mga 65 echos or 70 ang safe (smiles) ano before grumaduate?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After ka grumaduate</i>
202	Mr. NurseB	<i>After ako grumaduate</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Scale of 1-10</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

203	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi ko masasabi ahh scale 1-10 pala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo 1-10</i>
204	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi hindi ko rin masasabi, hindi mo kasi alam ang lalabas na question duon eh, pero siguro masasabi ko yung chances na pumasa ako in the scale of 1-10 mga 6 siguro mga 6.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1-10, six.</i>
205	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo mga 6</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After magreview ilan</i>
206	Mr. NurseB	<i>After kong magreview siguro mga 6.5 to 7 after ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Low expectation ha. Okay halimbawa ako ka gagraduate ko lang, wala akong alam</i>
207	Mr. NurseB	<i>May alam ka pero hindi hasa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, ano ma aadvise mo sa akin, bago ako mag-exam , let's say I have plan to selfreview</i>
208	Mr. NurseB	<i>Self review ayon magbasa ka ng materials na ano bang dapat kong I recommend sayo, usually yung panahon namin yung nauuso yung kay Carl balita mahabang ganon na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Alam ko yan oo</i>
209	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro kumuha ka ng latest na material na kung бага lahat nandun na, pero hindi naman siyempre lahat nandon, kung бага kumuha ka ng materials makakatulong sayo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>reliable</i>
210	Mr. NurseB	<i>...na reliable na makakatulong sayo and then kasama non mag practice ka din Q and A ganyan pero before Q and A magbasa ka muna ng diba particular topic kang gustong i-master o magbasa basa ka muna after nun i-apply mo sa Q and A kung бага parang ano lang ahh basa take ng question tapos after mo mag take ng question check mo yung ano yung tamang sagot tingnan mo kung rationale ganyan-ganyan.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo nasigurado na yung isang topic ay na cover mo na lahat ng tanong, nagagawa mo ba yon o let's say...</i>
211	Mr. NurseB	<i>Actually hindi ko naman na aano na okay tapos ko na lahat ito, ganyan ganyan, na pag may isang bagay na, halimbawa, parang hindi ko yata alam ito, ito muna yung aaralin ko ganon. Kung baga yun nga sabi ko nga hindi naman lahat ng topic ma cocover sa exam kung baga very random ano yon eh di mo masasabi eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano mo masasabi sa sarili mo na prepared ka sagutin yon na tanong na yon na random?</i>
212	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm experience na rin (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Experience.</i>
213	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron kang techniques o ano pa</i>
214	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yun nga parang combination na din ng napag-aralan mo before tapos may kaakibat na ring testing strategies yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Test-taking strategies</i>
215	Mr. NurseB	<i>Tsaka yun na nga kasama na din kung ano yung napag-aralan mo dati yung mga stock knowledge noon, mga ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay sa strategies like if you can list 3 of them ano yung top 3 mo na naging strategies?</i>
216	Mr. NurseB	<i>Strategy? Elimination ahm ano pa ba, kasi ang tagal na non hindi na ako nakapag ano uli, ahm ano nga ba ang lakas ng loob kong mag ano no tapos nakalimutan ko lang (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay lang yun</i>
217	Mr. NurseB	<i>So far yun yung elimination nakalimutan ko na yung iba pa eh, basta dati ang dinig dinig ko sa pag aano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...yung may mga global (technique)</i>
218	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, nkalimutan ko na lang yung iba eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo in-apply mo din sa NCLEX yun?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

219	Mr. NurseB	Oo, oo
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ba't mo in-apply, ano naging dahilan mo?</i>
210	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kasi nga since yung local board (exam) kasi in-aadopt na rin nila yung NCLEX, so parang ganun na rin yung ginawa ko, saka yun nga, kung baga kung ano rin yung naging naimpart sa akin nung 2 kong kapatid, kasi parehas din silang pasado ng NCLEX eh, kaya yun na rin ang in-apply ko sa ano nag review ako for NCLEX.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In-impart nila like what?</i>
211	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yon nga gawin mo yung ganito, pag-aralan mo yung ganyan, mag practice questions ka kasi di ba dati bukod dun sa book na may Q and A meron din yung sa, sa computer na Q and A ganon, mag ganon ka kasi parang sina-simulate nung yung mismong exam kasi pag sa NCLEX click click mga ganyan -ganyan ,ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ba naging effective yung review mo?</i>
212	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo naging effective naman yung review ko for NCLEX ba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo kahit yung local</i>
213	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo effective naman siya, yun nga kasi nga may nangyari sa okay naman siya except sa test 4 or 5 ba yon ganyan-ganyan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron kang bagay na... looking back, ngayon ha anything you could have done that must have helped you more on your review, if there were any, what were they? Halimbawa kung meron kang bagay na mababago dun sa review mo na sa tingin mo mas naging okay pa sana.</i>
214	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa tingin ko na mas naging okay?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...kung may pagkakataon kang baguhin yung nakaraan</i>
215	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro kung meron man akong gustong baguhin or idagdag... siguro yung pagrereview ko with my friends, siguro parang ano lang, siguro I find my review routine dati na parang ang boring parang ano kasi siya don mag-isa lang pero if siguro kung ti triy ko with my friends na yung seryoso naman mag review siguro lalo ko pang ma-appreciate kasi siyempre sharing of best practices ganyan,</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>although nung hindi pa naman kami nung nasa review program pa naman kami ng in-house nakakapag share na kami kung baga iba pa rin yung after nung graduation meron pa rin kaming consistent na pagrereview in group, parang ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Merong bang mga lumabas sa board exam na hindi mo naaral?</i>
216	Mr. NurseB	<i>ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung matatandaan mo pa</i>
217	Mr. NurseB	<i>Kung natatandaan ko pa...siguro dun sa ano yung sa part ng sa NRES ba yon or</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung natatandaan ko pa...siguro dun sa ano yung sa part ng sa NRES ba yon or</i>
218	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo tsaka may isa pa ano ba yong sa baby</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pedia</i>
219	Mr. NurseB	<i>Hindi hindi ICMS ba yon hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ICMS?</i>
220	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ay hindi ICMS, IMCI yon parang yon ata oo parang yun ata yun ...though tinacle naman namin yun nung review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay ahh hindi mo pa ito na ano eh, yung sa traits.</i>
221	Mr. NurseB	<i>Saan?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think were the important qualities or quality you possessed that made you pass the exam and how did it or they help you pass?</i>
222	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro yun nga ahm ano ahh perseverance ahm yung mentality na wag susuko may pag-asa pa. Ano pa ba ahm trust your instinct kasi minsan may mga pagkakataon hindi mo tina-trust yung sarili mong ano eh yun pala tama ka na yung mga ganon, at tsaka wag kang masyadong mag-isip sa isang simpleng bagay, parang ganon</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paanong simpleng bagay?</i>
223	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh, diba yung isang question masyado mong iniisip huwag mong masyadong ano kasi magtatagal ka dun sa isang question na yun kung baga sayang naman yung ibang mga questions na mae-encounter mo ganun kung baga mauubos yung oras mo sa isang question na iyon, ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano ka ba magsagot, yung pag di sigurado lalagyan mo ng tanda o kung ano na yung nasagot mo deretso ka na?</i>
224	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ganon ako usually, kung ano yung nasagot ko yun na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun na yon.</i>
225	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo minsan kasi pag masyado kong inisip, alam mo yun, masasayang yung oras. Imbis na mag uumpisa ka dun sa ibang answer magtatagal ka lang dun sa isang tanong; tapos yung nagtagal ka ng mag-isip tapos mali pa diba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano sa tingin mo mapapakita yung perseverance?</i>
226	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ayun parang kontrabida. (phone ringing</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>sabihin mo malapit na...few questions na lang</i>
227	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, oo cge</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo napakita yung sinabi mong qualities na yun?</i>
228	Mr. NurseB	<i>Parang contradicting yung perseverance eh no?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tsaka yung di ka sumusuko.</i>
229	Mr. NurseB	<i>Yung di sumusuko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang na encounter na problema noon na hindi ka sumuko?</i>
230	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahh, siguro kung meron man akong way na ako hindi sumuko, siguro dun sa mga question na yung alam mo yun na parang ahn malapit ka na dun sa answer kung baga tina-trust mo na lang yung</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>sarili mo dun sa, yun dun sa answer na yon ahm tsaka may kasama na ring ano ahm faith, or yun nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In terms of faith pano mo ba mapapakita yung faith?</i>
231	Mr. NurseB	<i>Ahm</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagsisimba ka ba?</i>
232	Mr. NurseB	<i>Actually hindi ako yung every Sunday nagsisimba. Ano lang kami parang yung with the family tsaka kung baga, hindi naman kami yung basta nagre-rely na lang kay God okay na tulungan ninyo po akong masagot ko ng tama, kung baga nasa sarili din kasi iyon ahm kung baga I do my part basta I guide ninyo lang po ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, what do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective? Kanina yun yong tanong ko sayo diba, sa tingin mo anong dapat na qualities ng isang tao?</i>
233	Mr. NurseB	<i>Isang tao para pumasa of course be confident and at the same time ahm be open, kailangan mong kung baga huwag mong isarado yung sarili mo sa mga options or mga bagay bagay na maaring makatulong sayo na ma achieve yung goal.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailangan ng tulong ng iba, ganyan?</i>
234	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo kailangan yung tulong, pero siyempre ahm nasa iyo ding mga kamay yung ikakaunlad, kung baga nasa Diyos ang awa nasa tao ang gawa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any regrets that you chose self study instead of going to a review center?</i>
235	Mr. NurseB	<i>Wala naman regret na nag self-review, wala naman regret, wala naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung may option ka let's say I'll give you 15,000 right now, mag enroll sa review center. Honestly and objective speaking, ahh give me your assessment to your self.</i>
236	Mr. NurseB	<i>Siguro kung bibigyan ako ng pera ng pang review why not at kung may time ako diba depende pa rin sa akin yung</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano ba tingin mo katagal yung review?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

237	Mr. NurseB	<i>Sa review center? Siguro yung in the span of time na yon na after graduation yon mga 2 months...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung sayo 2 months yon diba?</i>
238	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So in comparison with the time frame ng review center almost the same.</i>
239	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So my time ka din don, kung may pera ka pipiliin mo rin iyon?</i>
240	Mr. NurseB	<i>Oo, kung bibigyan mo pero sa akin kasi parang ayoko ng umalis pa ng bahay parang gusto ko sa bahay na lang eh. Yon so parang it's a 50/50 for me kung bibigyan mo ako ng chance.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, my last question is...</i>
241	Mr. NurseB	<i>Okay kasi nga parang bahay person ako, hindi ako yung lalabas pa ako ng bahay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did it affect you psychological, mentally, emotionally as a person?</i>
242	Mr. NurseB	<i>As a person, ahm paano naka apekto sa akin, echos. Hindi yun nga kung meron mang isang bagay na naka apekto talaga sa akin yun yung ahm dealing with anything na ma e-encounter mo sa buhay ahh yun nga kung baga hindi ganun ka.. ka kalaki yung effect sa akin kung baga I can find ways to manage those problem in life ganon yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Maraming salamat</i>
243	Mr. NurseB	<i>You're welcome</i>
Researcher:		<i>Thank you for your interview, thank you for your time</i>
244	Mr. NurseB	<i>Salamat din sa'yo.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

--END--

Time Stamp 1:07:00

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Good afternoon. My name is Neri Ocampo from St. Paul University Manila. Today I'll be interviewing you about your experience with self-review. First, let me explain the parts of the interview: number one, it is divided into four parts, yung una, yung demographics and educational background. The second part would be your experience during your self-review; the third part is for the strategies, kung meron man, and lastly, if you can identify your traits that helped you during your review. Yung first question about the demographics, of course, yung name mo, o nickname, optional lang siya, if you'd like to answer.</i>
1	Ms. NurseG	<i>I'm Ms. NurseG, 26 years old.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you graduate? What year?</i>
2	Ms. NurseG	<i>2007, April.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2007, April. First course or second course?</i>
3	Ms. NurseG	<i>First course</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, what's your current occupation?</i>
4	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nurse.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nurse in a..</i>
5	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nurse in a birthing clinic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Birthing clinic? Okay, how long have you had that job?</i>
6	Ms. NurseG	<i>In that job? 3 months.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, 3 months ka pa lang dun</i>
7	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kauuwi ko lang eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo nga pala, okay. Prior to your job right now, ano yung mga jobs mo, if you had any?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

8	Ms. NurseG	<i>I was an EMT (Emergency Medical Technician) Nurse, in Saudi (Arabia).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gano katagal sa Saudi?</i>
9	Ms. NurseG	<i>Two years. More than two years.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>More than two years. You graduated 2007, ah nagkaron ka kagad ng work after you graduated in 2007?</i>
10	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi. Nagstop ako for a year, tapos naengage ako sa isang hospital starting 2008 ng April. Nag-end ako sa kanila ng October ng 2010.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So, two years ka sa hospital na yun, and then you went to Saudi (Arabia), two years ka rin dun?</i>
11	Ms. NurseG	<i>Two years din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kababalik mo lang, ngayon nasa birthing clinic ka.</i>
12	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, kelan ka nagtake ng board exam?</i>
13	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano, June 2007.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>June 2007. If you can identify, optional lang din 'to, actually nakabacket 'to, yung licensure rating mo. Was that 75-79 or 80 and above?</i>
14	Ms. NurseG	<i>75-79.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung school mo ba, private or public?</i>
15	Ms. NurseG	<i>Private.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung next set of questions is about who you are. If you can tell me kung anong klaseng tao ka ba; yung upbringing mo mula nung elementary-high school; kung pano yung sa parent side mo, yung role mo sa family, bakit ka nagnursing. Anything about you, kwento mo lang... papano ka naging ikaw?</i>
16	Ms. NurseG	<i>Naggrew ako sa family...yung mom ko nasa medical field din. Parang since nagkaisip ako, gusto ko din na nasa medical, kasi idol ko nga yung mom ko. Ngayon, apat na kami na nasa medical field. Tapos... (thinking)..Studios ako nung estudyante, simula high school.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagkaron ka ba ng role sa school, say sa student council, or anything?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

17	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi ako sumasali sa mga ganun kasi usually talaga, bound ako sa books.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When you say "bound sa books" saka "studious" papano mo ginagawa?</i>
18	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hobby ko talaga yung magbasa..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung mga binabasa mo?</i>
19	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nung high school ako, mahilig ako magbasa ng novel, tapos pagdating nung college, more on medical books. Tapos ang laging ginagawa ko kapag nagpupunta ako ng mall, kahit hanggang ngayon, sa mall, national (bookstore) talaga, nagbabasa ng books.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano na yung mga binabasa mo na ngayon?</i>
20	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano na ako, novel, balik ulit ako sa novel.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ba yung set-up sa family niyo, mahilig ba kayo magsimba, papano ba kayo mag-get together?</i>
21	Ms. NurseG	<i>Usually, on Sunday magkakasama kami. Yung Monday to Friday, kasi di ba, school. Yung Saturdays and Sundays, nag-out of town kami. Kasi sa other house kami, sa iba-ibang namin kami nagpupunta. Para yun yung nagiging ano namin, family day.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung college ka na, kamusta naman yung studies mo nun? Let's say when you started college, how did you fair in your studies?</i>
22	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nung magstart na'ko magcollege, naging pasaway na'ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pasaway? (Smiles)</i>
23	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, sabi nga ng mga classmates ko, 'ano ka ba hindi ka naman napasok'; sabi ko 'tingnan niyo na lang kapag exam; sa exam lang, usually, dun lang ako pumapasok. Kasi hindi nila ako makita na nag-aaral ako, kapag hinahunting nila ako, nasa library lang ako. Pero hindi ako nagsasabi sa kanila na nandudun ako. Pero kapag ano naman, kapag kinakatok ako, gumagala ako, lumalabas, ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>So gusto mo yung mag-isa ka lang mag-aral?</i>
24	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, nung early, gusto ko solo lang ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Until what point yun?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

25	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hanggang sa pagdating ko ng third year, second sem. Parang ginusto ko ng may kajamming.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ba't nagbago yung gusto mo?</i>
26	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi parang ano, nagbbrainstorming kami ng mga friends ko. Mas natatandaan ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You graduated 2007, anong mga section niyo, may block section ba kayo?</i>
27	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi sa school namin, divided into three yun, usually, ano ba yun, nakalimutan ko yung una eh, yun yung mga pasaway. Sila yung mga ano, "hanging" kung tawagin, sila yung mga...tatanggalin na sila sa next sem. Yung pangalawa,..yung una pala, yun yung "pilot", yung tatanggalin, Yung pangalawa, yung regular. Yung regular, alam ng Dean na aabot hanggang dulo. Yung pangatlo, sila yung second coursers, yung transferees, sila yun, pinaghiwa-hiwalay kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero alam ba nila, say sa "pilot" (section) na yun na tatanggalin na sila?</i>
28	Ms. NurseG	<i>Alam nila. Sinasabi kasi na bago sila tanggalin, kinakausap na sila ng Dean, na 'oh may red mark ka na', kung gusto mo maretain, mag-aral ka'. Parang ano, may warning talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero within the class yun, o iba-ibang sections yun?</i>
29	Ms. NurseG	<i>Iba-ibang sections, may interview talaga. Nung batcj namin, ininterview talaga per estudyante. Kaya halos lahat kami kilala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ba ang set-up ng school ninyo, papano ba ang curriculum dun, papano ba ang duty dun?</i>
30	Ms. NurseG	<i>Usually, per surname tapos ibablock kayo, paghahaluin kayo. Kunwari, isang regular tapos isang 'pilot' paghahaluin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>San ka ba dun?</i>
31	Ms. NurseG	<i>Regular. Regular na pasaway.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(Smiles).. Nung college, kung natatandaan mo pa, ano ba yung gusto mong subjects?</i>
32	Ms. NurseG	<i>Favorite ko "Anatomy" Anatomy talaga. Hanggang ngayon, favorite ko pa din yung anatomy. Saka ano, okay lang yung Pharma (pharmacology), pero nung second year, Anatomy. Pagdating na ng 4th year Psyche (Psychiatric nursing).</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>M.S. (Medical-Surgical) kamusta?</i>
33	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi yung M.S. kasi di ba masyadong broad? Okay lang din, kaya lang nakakaantok kasi (smiles), inaantok ako sa M.S.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Inaantok ka sa mismong subject o sa professor niyo?</i>
34	Ms. NurseG	<i>Magaling yung professor namin, kaya lang yung mismong subject ng M.S. Pero yung topics na tungkol sa O.R. (operating room), ganon, yun buhay ako nun, pero yung mga cardiovascular, yun tulugan na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan ka ba banda nakaupo nun?</i>
35	Ms. NurseG	<i>Gitna.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>By surname kayo?</i>
36	Ms. NurseG	<i>By surname.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Heto, do you consider yourself as a people person o gusto mo mag-isa ka lang?</i>
37	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hayon, before nga soloista ako. Mas gusto ko na mag-isa ako, kasi wala kang iintindihin. Yung "ah sige ako lang". Yung time management nasa sa'yo talaga. Yung wala kang iintayin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kelan nag-umpisa yun?</i>
38	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nung first year, ganun ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala kang ka-buddy?</i>
39	Ms. NurseG	<i>Meron, pero lumalayo ako sa ka-buddy ako. Kasi nga pagkadating ng, kunwari mag-eexam na, inaaya ako magreview, tara group study tayo. Hindi, busy ako. Pero ang totoo, nag-aaral ako mag-isa. Tapos usually, yung pattern talaga, between 2 AM hanggang 5.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yun Monday to Friday?</i>
40	Ms. NurseG	<i>Halos everyday, kasi nga pagputok na nung araw, gagala na'ko. Ganun yung ginagawa ko, kung hindi nasa library. Yun yung earlier, tapos nung huli na, sumasali na'ko sa group study kasi nga yung time, tapos pantay-pantay kayo ng naiintindihan. Yung hindi mo maintindihan, may magpapaliwanag sa'yo. Kaya ako sumali sa mga friends ko.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero for two years effective sa'yo yung mag-isa ka lang. Okay, compare ko na lang: yung performance mo nung first and second year compared to 3rd and 4th year.</i>
41	Ms. NurseG	<i>Mas maganda nung ano, 3rd year and 4th year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah nung sumali ka na sa group?</i>
42	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, kasi nung first year, 25% lang sa pagiging DL (deans lister), 25 lang yung nakukuha ko, e nung sumali ako sa friends ko, nag-half na'ko. Kaya sabi ng mommy ko, mas maganda pala na may kasama.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, yung second part na ng interview, yung experience mo na. Ano bang naging dahilan kung bakit ka o kayo nag-selfreview?</i>
43	Ms. NurseG	<i>Chinallenge kasi kami ng professors namin. Kasi nga nasa regular student's kami. Chinallenge kami, total unlimited na naman. Wala ng refresher course. Try nga natin kung sino talaga yung papasa sa inyo. Trip-trip lang. Sabi nung professors namin. Tapos ano, halos half nung class namin sumang-ayon naman. Kaya halos half sa amin, nagreview yung iba, tapos kami nag-selfreview. Yung mga friends ko talaga, pinagpustahan namin yun kung sino yung papasa o hindi. Kaya five kami nun na nagboarding house.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sinong professor yun? Yung Dean ba yun o isa sa mga professors niyo?</i>
44	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ilang professors kasi yung nagchallenge sa amin nun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, marami sila?</i>
45	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, marami sila. Mga 4 to 5 sila. Sabi nga namin, 'pinag-usapan niyo kami ha'. Pero selected na section lang yung ginaganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, yung regular?</i>
46	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa regular lang yun ginawa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan ba kayo sa regular? Ilan ba kayong grumaduate pala? Yung batch niyo.</i>
47	Ms. NurseG	<i>1000+ kami e, marami kami eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>
48	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi may second coursers kami, may shifters, transferees.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, nakasegregate talaga yun?</i>
49	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tapos hindi kami hinahalo sa shifters, yung regular. Ang ka-block namin lagi "pilot". Yung pilot naihalo sila sa shifters, kami hindi kami pwedeng ihalo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan kayo dun sa mga regular?</i>
50	Ms. NurseG	<i>Madami, from A-Z. Madami kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Umabot kayong 100+?</i>
51	Ms. NurseG	<i>Lagpas..Madaming letter A ha.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang first letter ng apelyedo mo?</i>
52	Ms. NurseG	<i>"J".</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>"J" as in "Juliet"? Ah nasa kalagitnaan ka nga. Pero wala namang inindorse na ReviewCenterG yung school niyo? Dun sa mga iba..</i>
53	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala. Wala silang sinasabi na "oh ganito, kung gusto niyo magreview, sa ganitong ReviewCenterG kayo", pero may pumupunta sa school....na 'oh may percentage kayo, discount, kung sa amin kayo magrereview". Ano yun eh, mga four yata na ReviewCenterG yung nagpunta sa'min. pero yun nga, hindi kami pumasok sa ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yun yung buong klase mo lang, o yung buong regular?</i>
54	Ms. NurseG	<i>Five kaming sections na ginanun ng 4-5 na professors namin. Kasi yung section namin, $\frac{3}{4}$ nun halos nasa DL.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong DL?</i>
55	Ms. NurseG	<i>Dean's Listers, kaya kilala kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kelan ka nagdecide na magself-review? Before graduation, after, o say mga 2nd year ka pa lang?</i>
56	Ms. NurseG	<i>Balak ko nun, magReviewCenterG sana ako nun, pero sige, chinachallenge niyo kami kaya nagbukod kami, kami-kami na lang. Tapos nung January to March, pumapasok ako kasi nga compulsory na pumasok sa, parang Nursing Audit kung tawagin. Yun pumapasok kami kasi nga "attendance is a must", pero tinutulugan ko lang siya. Nakakaboring eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Panong nakakabore?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

57	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi nga ang pangit ng turo ng teacher. Kasi nga inanalyze mo naman yun eh. Kasi nga wala kaming natutunan sa kanya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero yung teacher na yun teacher mo yun di ba?</i>
58	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, kasi ano eh, iba-iba nag-iiba. Bawat subject iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So January to March, yun yung Nursing audit niyo, parang in-house yun; mga teachers niyo nagtuturo. Kelan kayo chinallenge, anong buwan?</i>
59	Ms. NurseG	<i>Feb (February) gitna. Kasi nga di ba magtatapos na yung audit. Pagdating ng March, mag-aayos ka na ng papers, dun kami nagstart na 'uy tara chinallenge tayo ni prof. Tanong niyo sa mga magulang niyo kung okay lang ba'. Yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong reaction ng mga magulang mo?</i>
60	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung nanay ko ang sagot sa akin 'Bahala ka sa life mo. Kasi ikaw naman yan eh. Kung confident ka na makakapasa ka, okay lang. Hindi naman kami umaasa na with flying colors naman yung bibigay mo sa amin eh. Basta ang sa amin, makapasa ka.'</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sa ngayon apat kayong nasa medical field di ba? Pang-ilan ka dun?</i>
61	Ms. NurseG	<i>Una yung mom ko, pangalawa ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bago yung sa batch ninyo, meron ka bang nakilala na nagselfreview din?</i>
62	Ms. NurseG	<i>Meron, friend ko siya, kaso sa ibang school siya. Pero kabatch ko siya nung nagtake.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ka batch mo.</i>
63	Ms. NurseG	<i>...pero hindi ko siya ka school-mate</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Okay, hindi mo siya ka school mate.</i>
64	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi ko siya ka school</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakatulong ba sa'yo yung review ninyo?</i>
65	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano kasi, ano siya self review din siya, parang sa amin din inhouse, sa audit siya pumapasok lang siya ng nursing audit. Tapos ang ginagawa naming, kasi nga kagaya non, yung ibang mga kaibigan namin nasa (ReviewCenterG) yung iba (ReviewCenterG), yung iba (ReviewCenterG) ReviewCenterG (ReviewCenterG) binibigyan kami</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>ng pointers kung ano yung lalabas so palitpalitan kami, kaming dalawa ng kaibigan ko talaga, kami yung binibigyan kasi nga wala naman silang makukuha sa amin tas mas magsasabi na uy possible daw yung lumabas yung ganitong subject, yun yung aralin ninyo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So you graduated April 2007, ahh July ka nagtake?</i>
66	Ms. NurseG	<i>June.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>June, so kelan nag-umpisa yung review ninyo?</i>
67	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung self-review talaga?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
68	Ms. NurseG	<i>April</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>April, after graduation?</i>
69	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi pagka tapos namin ng (nursing) audit, nag start na kami non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, ilan kayo nun?</i>
70	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano kami, 5 kami non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
71	Ms. NurseG	<i>5 sets kami nung mga friends ko ang ginawa namin nag rent kami ng house, ay nag rent ng sa dorm, nag rent kami ng room, tapos ano yon 8-5 lahat dapat nandon na kami sa loob basta 8-5 basta yung loob na yun vacant.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa loob?</i>
72	Ms. NurseG	<i>Vacant lang siya, books lang yung nasa gitna. Yung ginagawa namin, books lang yung sa gitna tapos lapis at saka papel tapos sa room may mga naka post na manila paper.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, so umuwi pa rin kayo sa bahay ninyo?</i>
73	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero dun lang kayo nag-aano...</i>
74	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung lang yung study room namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

75	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung ano, yung room.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay yun ah!</i>
76	Ms. NurseG	<i>Pag pumasok ka sa room lahat makikita mo, ano yon malalaki yung ano niya, malalaki yung handwriting kasi yung naka unang set ng pinost namin yun may values kasi diba ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Normal values?</i>
77	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yun yung ginawa namin tapos every now and then nagpapalit kami, nagpapalit kunyari</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like gaano katagal?</i>
78	Ms. NurseG	<i>Every week nagpapalit kami ng Manila paper. Usually kung sino yung gustong magsulat sa manila paper, una blangko yon, blanko yon yung books diba nasa gitna tsaka yung mga pens nasa gitna ganon. Tapos ang gagawin may white board din don, may white board, may white board marker sa isang dingding nan dudun yung kasi nandudun yung schedule ng magtuturo, 5 kami parang per subject may professor.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kayo yun? Okay okay.</i>
79	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo ganon kami, para kaming naglalaro.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow</i>
80	Ms. NurseG	<i>Pero nakakatuwa naman kami, edi yun nung unang araw, Monday, blank lahat ng paper tas kunyari ako yung 1st day Monday kasi 5 kami ako yung Monday oh ito yung ituturo ko sa inyo, Pharma (Pharmacology). Ito bawat isang dingding may kanya kanyang nakatutok sila yung nagsusulat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung mga itinuro mo, ahh natatandaan mo pa?</i>
81	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung kinuha ko noon sa akin emergency meds, sa akin pumalo yung emergency meds tas ano... yun lang yung natatandaan ko eh... sa ECG sa akin din yon kasi sa ECG reading, kasi diba dapat marunong ka din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, from your school, how many minutes away from bahay mo?</i>
82	Ms. NurseG	<i>Bahay ko talaga?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bahay ninyo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

83	Ms. NurseG	<i>Depende sa traffic, 15 kung hindi traffic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh malapit lang. Papano kayo pumili? Meron ba kayong kinunsider na lugar, like standards dun sa lugar ninyo na yon?</i>
84	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa dorm, kasi yung dorm, dorm yun ng kasama dun sa 5. Nag rent lang kami ng isang room don.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh extra dorm</i>
85	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, tas don, dun kami pumapasok.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano kayo nag decide na yon na lang?</i>
86	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayon kasi parang mas convenient din don sa tropa ko na nag dodorm kasi diba yung dorm puro nurse</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
87	Ms. NurseG	<i>...yung nag dodorm, tas puro girls, yung kanya yung room niya katabi lang nung nirent namin kasi parang yung mga resources madali kami makahiram, malapit may access kami sa library Kasi malapit lang kasi siya sa ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Malapit sa school</i>
88	Ms. NurseG	<i>...school.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh humihiram din kayo ng resources?</i>
89	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ng resources sa library tapos kami na yung nag-aaral</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga gaano ba policy ng library ninyo, gaano katagal yung mahihiram ninyo yung isang libro?</i>
90	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi yung librarian don friend namin, kaya parang ano kahit matagal kami matapos siya yung nagbabalik.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung kaibigan mo</i>
91	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, nagkaroon ba kayo ng issues during your review?</i>
92	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano minsan yung ano, yung nakatakdang magtuturo, walang ano hindi prepared.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi prepared. Pano bang set up ninyo let's say in-assign ka, na assign ka ngayon sa emergency meds yung araw na ito, papano mo ba inaaral siya?</i>
93	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano sa house nag-aaral na ako tas ko yung magre-refill sa kanila, sila din nagbabasa din sila parang magiging brain storming sa amin.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Brain storming pero meron lang magfa-facilitate?</i>
94	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tapos dapat yung magfafacilitate talagang knowledgeable talaga siya dun sa topic.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, kung baga per forte?</i>
95	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung forte mo yung emergency meds sayo yun, pinipili niyo yung gusto niyo rin?</i>
96	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, nung una kasi nahirapan kami, fish bowl ginawa namin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh bunutan</i>
97	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo bunutan sa plastic pero minsan sumasablay, parang ano ba yan mali ito ayoko, mali sabi ni Brunner, mali yung ganito. O sige na kung saan na lang yung gusto kuhanin ninyo mag ano kayo, halos lahat din naman na tackle namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh so halos lahat ng subjects?</i>
98	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yun nga lang kasi yung MS sobrang ang lawak marami sa MS ang hindi namin kinuha.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So April ka nag-umpisa, last week ba ng April?</i>
99	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi mga 1st week kami</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1st week..May...June, 2 months lang kayo nagreview?</i>
100	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo 2 months lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano katagal yun, anong oras kayo nag-uumpisa?</i>
101	Ms. NurseG	<i>Usually 8-5 pagdating, pag-ano na ng 5 gagala na kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi usually 8-5 minsan hindi 8-5</i>
102	Ms. NurseG	<i>Minsan nagiging 9, kasi may...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh yung iba late, oo.</i>
103	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi malayo pa yung ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Pag may na late, di kayo nag e-extend?</i>
104	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi kami nag start ng kulang kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pag may late di kayo nag e-extend</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

105	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nag e-extend din, pero ano minsan lang yon, nag e-extend din kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naisip niyo ba na kung may choice kayo, halimbawa, may issues na ganon halimbawa yung iba hindi handa ganon naisip ninyo ba na magkakaibigan, o ikaw personally, na okay na lang sana kung nag review-center na lang ako o ano?</i>
106	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi</i>
107	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi parang ano, parang ano "hoy hindi ka prepared" parang inaasar lang namin "sana next time ano ganito ha" parang nag sasuggest din, parang ako parang hindi pumasok sa mind ko na magreview-center, wala hindi ko alam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo naisip yon kailangan tuloy-tuloy lang ganon?</i>
108	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo kasi parang naging ano, enjoy yung pag-aaral. Mas mag-e-enjoy kasi diba, ReviewCenterG ka spoon-feeding ka nun, parang ano ba yan pakain ka na talaga nila... sinusubo na nila sa'yo yung sagot. Sa amin kasi parepareho kami ng inisip na "pangit naman yung ganon halos lahat naibigay sayo maganda na rin yung pinaghihirapan" kaya pare-pareho kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Natapos yung review... kailan ka ba nag take ng exam, anong day?</i>
109	Ms. NurseG	<i>June 10, June 11</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>June 10, 11, kailan ninyo tinapos yung review?</i>
110	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano... parang 1 week before the board exam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh 1 week before</i>
111	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, naggala kami, naggala na kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi na kayo nag review?</i>
112	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi na kami humawak ng books.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, so after mo mag, let's say, a week before board exam, natapos ninyo na yung review ninyo, anong pakiramdam mo nun, in terms of confidence, in terms of over all feeling mo na halimbawa handa ka na bang mag take?</i>
113	Ms. NurseG	<i>Anxiety, may mild anxiety talaga, na ano ba yon tama ba lahat ng kinuha ko, tama ba lahat ng napag-aralan ko, ano na ba kami, knowledgeable na ba? Ganon. Yun yung inaano ko, may mild anxiety</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>talaga, tas nagkikita kami... ano "Oy okay ka na? Sa tingin mo makakapasa? Oo, gumaganon lang kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang standard nun, na tingin mo makakapasa ka? Meron bang standard na...</i>
114	Ms. NurseG	<i>Na may confidence ka?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, kung baga kanino mo kina compare yung standard na yon na ano para makapasa ka, pano mo nasabi na okay na ako?</i>
115	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa isa naming classmate, matalino talaga siya eh. So kung alam ni ate, dapat alam natin, yun yung sinasabi naming lima, pag alam ni ate dapat alam natin. Hindi pwedeng alam lang ni ate, dapat alam din natin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasama ba siya dun sa 5 na yun?</i>
116	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nag ano siya eh nag ReviewCenterG(ReviewCenterG) siya eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh nag ReviewCenterG siya, kamusta naman siya? Pumasa naman siya...</i>
117	Ms. NurseG	<i>Pumasa rin naman siya, pero halos pare parehas kami ng rating.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano sa tingin mo yung advantages, kung meron man ha, or disadvantage sa ginawa ninyo?</i>
118	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung advantages, kasi nga ayon konti kayo. Pag meron kang hindi maintindihan may magtuturo sayo tas buddy, nagiging buddy-buddy kayo. Yun yung advantages non tapos flexible yung time, halos parang pwedeng maging flexible yung time depende sa inyo, kunyari kung gusto ninyo wala kayong pasok ng Wednesday papalitan ninyo ng Saturday. Hindi kagaya ng ReviewCenterG, fixed diba hindi pwedeng, 'hay pag absent ka nito. Pag ReviewCenterG one day lang yung topic, hindi pwedeng magrepeat. Sa amin, may repeat, nire-repeat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May na identify ka bang disadvantages don</i>
119	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala</i>
120	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala naman</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi yung mga pointers, ganon.</i>
121	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi nga binibigyan kami ng pointers eh, binibigyan kami kaya parang wala din. Minsan sa resources...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang, kung meron man ha, meron bang naging epekto sayo yung mga ginawa mo, sa buhay mo?</i>
122	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, parang nabigyan ka ng ano... yung ginawa mo parang tumaas yung confidence mo sa sarili mo na may alam ka. Na pwede kang, oo may alam ka kasi nga nag-aral ka, mas higit pa don yung alam mo kasi hindi ka naman, halos lahat kami ganon, ganon yung ngayon nararamdaman namin. Ahh mas higit yung alam ko sa kanila kasi kagaya ko ilan na yung lisensya ko, hindi naman ako nagreview-center. Kagaya din nila, ilan na yung lisensya nila. Kasi sa batch namin nagstart yung paramihan na ng lisensya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ha?..(hahaha)</i>
123	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, hindi sa amin usually talaga, lalo sa school ko. 'Oh may lisensya ka na ba sa ganitong country?' Tinatanong ka ayon parang ano.. di ba kunwari nag NCLEX ka, dapat Kaplan (ReviewCenterG) ka diba? Kaplan (ReviewCenterG) dapat yung iba. Hindi ako nag NCLEX kasi parang masasayang, ang ano yung ibang mga kaibigan ko, yung hindi sila nag Kaplan, nagself review lang! Oo ganon lang, nakapasa nga ako ng board exam dito eh? Parang ano lang, 'bakit wala naman mawawala ha'yun ang laging sinasabi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung pumasa ka ng board exam, anong naging reception o reaction nung mga tao ahh sa family mo, sa friends mo, kayo-kayo o ibang tao?</i>
124	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung ano kasi..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung chinallenge kayo diba?</i>
125	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi yung sa mga professors namin, alam na talagang papasok, pero yung sa pamilya ko, hindi nila alam na mag e-exam ako. Never kong sinabi na 'uy magbobo-board-exam ako' ganito nalaman nila tapos na. Yung na release na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero alam nila nagreview kayo?</i>
126	Ms. NurseG	<i>Alam nila na , ang alam nila na sa school pa rin yun, hindi ko sinasabi. Secretive nga kasi kami. Secretive kasi ako. Nung sinabi ko nung gabi na "Ma, alis ako ha". Di nga nila alam na nag file ako. Di nga nila alam, kasi nga kami ngang 5, ano yon ganon, din di alam nung parents nila</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siguro diba, siyempre alam naman nung parents na kelan yung board exam, nagtatanong na o nag file ka ba ngayon?</i>
127	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nagsisinungaling.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talaga?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

128	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nagsisinungaling</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong sabi?</i>
129	Ms. NurseG	<i>'Ma, pupunta ako sa friend ko may itatanong ako.' 'Oh, sige tas nung mag bo-board exam na, " Oh anak bakit nakaputi ka? May pasok ka? 'Oo Ma eh, may duty ako eh.' Eh yung mama ko, 'Sige lang, ingat lang' ganon lang siya hindi siya yung nagtanong basta nalaman na lang nila na magbo-board exam ako nung lumabas na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong una nilang reaction?</i>
130	Ms. NurseG	<i>Edi dumating na yung bulletin (newspaper), 'Ma.. o wanted ako sa Manila Bulletin'.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
131	Ms. NurseG	<i>'Ma... wanted ako tingnan mo?' 'Ano naman ito, ano ginawa mo?', ayun o may news ayan oh ahh talaga ayun lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
132	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tas yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag celebrate ba kayo with your friends?</i>
133	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kami ng mga friends ko oo, pero yung pamilya ko hindi, wala ayoko eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga friends mo pumasa din? Kayong 5 pumasa kayo?</i>
134	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nice. Kung idi-discribe mo yung overall experience mo sa self-review, in a sentence ano yon, one sentence o anything ano yon?</i>
135	Ms. NurseG	<i>sa..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung buong experience mo?</i>
136	Ms. NurseG	<i>Challenging, challenging siya kasi para sa akin ayun kasi nga ano parang mas gusto ko yung na cha-challenge ako. Kasi may thrill, yung gusto ko may 'thrill'.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano bang thrill don?</i>
137	Ms. NurseG	<i>Diba sa board exam yun nga, yung makakapasa ka, kung makakapasa ka na sarili mo lang yung katulong mo. Wala kang</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>katulong na iba sa paghahanap ng trabaho, yung hindi ka hahanap ng ano mo ng kasama, huy tara apply tayo walang ganun-ganun sa akin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Itong part na ito ay 3rd part yung sa strategy. So itong part na 'to is about more on technicality, kung anong mga specific na ginawa, kung matatandaan mo lang naman. Hindi na siya about the experiences, more of like questions and answer. Sa tingin mo papano nagging effective yung review mo?</i>
138	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi may ano may discipline din ako. Kasi nga disiplina pumapasok ako kahit na inaantok ako yung nag self review kami kasi diba hindi naman ano pag uwi mo ng 5 makakauwi ka, minsan gagala ka. Minsan may iba ka pang siyempre friends na uy tara labas tayo siyempre hindi ka naman makakatangi kasi. So parang ano ka papasok ka dun sa dorm na ganon, na may tama ka, may ganon yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May tama ka, nakainom ka?</i>
139	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo tas buti na lang hindi pumapalo na ako yung facilitator naming. Yung na ta-timing na studyante ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano ba kayo mag brain storming, paano nangyayari yung ganon, ano ginagawa ninyo sa..</i>
140	Ms. NurseG	<i>Example magbibigay ako ng gamot, yung gamot tatawag ako ng 1 sa 4 'Oh, ikaw ano yung indications? Bago sila pumasok kasi sa amin nag ano ka nagbasa, dapat nagbasa ka kasi matatanong ka, parang nag re-recite kayo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kumbaga ku-questionin mo yung nagpa-facilitate?</i>
141	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi, ako yung magtatanong sa kanila diba, tatanungin ko sila tas yon palalawakin ko tas kunyari</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, kung ikaw yung reporter?</i>
142	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ako yung magtatanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mag pre-present ka muna?</i>
143	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos magtatanong ka uli.</i>
144	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After non...</i>
145	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tapos pag may hindi kayo naintindihan, kunyari nagpresent ako nagtanong ako sa kanila, ang sagot nila sabi ko 'Gets mo ba talaga?' hindi may ganito parang isa-sub ka pa nila, sina-sub ka talaga nila, ganon. Kunyari, sa gamot example para sa Clonidine o para saan siya?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
146	Ms. NurseG	<i>Parang papasok na dun yung nagreview sa MS siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay integration</i>
147	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo inaano namin...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hinihimay.</i>
148	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, hanggang dumating na kami na tina tackle na yung sakit na yon, sumasama, para pagka sa susunod pag nag topic siya, di mo kailangan mag report kasi may alam na yung mga yun, mag aano na lang sila 'Oy alam ko yan'. Nakakatawa lang kasi minsan sabay-sabay sila. Sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita. Sabi ko 'isa-isa lang' kasi sabay-sabay silang nagsasalita.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
149	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nakakatawa, 'paano tayo matatapos sabay-sabay kayong magsasalita?' Yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo kanina after ng review ninyo, merong issue ng mild anxiety. Siyempre hindi naman sigurado kung papasa tayo diba, nagte-take ka pa lang... papano... how did you deal with them? Yung mga issues na ganon, yung failing the exam?</i>
150	Ms. NurseG	<i>Feeling during the exam?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi, failing the exam. Ibig sabihin papano mo nalampasan yung pakiramdam na "papano kung bumagsak ako?"</i>
151	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano yung sa amin kasi nag stop kami 1 week prior ng board exam. Ano nagchurch kami, oo naniniwala pa rin naman kami don. Kaya kami nagbigay ng 1 week na pagitan, kasi yung 1 week na yon, may mapuntahan kaming mga churches. Yung parang ano na lang, yung si God na lang ang mag guide sa atin. Siguro naman ano, ibibigay niya naman kung ano gusto natin tas kung ano makakaraos sa atin. May isang araw don na talagang diba, hindi nga kami humahawak ng books, yung lahat ng gusto namin gawin, ginawa namin kagaya</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>nung isa kong friend, hala nag take siya nung ano Valium (sedative) oo para matulog.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
152	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, tulog siya ng tulog 24 hrs. 'Ano nangyari sayo?' 'Natulog ako eh, yun ang trip ko eh' Yung ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw, ano ginawa mo?</i>
153	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nag-gala, naggala lang, naggala lang talaga, yun nga yung isa nag take siya ng Valium (sedative), yung iba nagpunta ng beach kasi para ma-lesen yung anxiety tas pagdating na ng exam, kasi diba pare-pareho kami, halos "J" (start of last name) kami, pare-pareho kami ng school na pupuntahan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo.</i>
154	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ang ginawa namin, yung friend ko hiniram namin yung sasakyan para sabay-sabay kami papunta don. Sabay-sabay kami, nagkita-kita kami sa isang certain place na lahat kami kukunin sabay sabay kami kukunin, sabay-sabay dun din kung saan kami mag e-exam, sabay sabay din kami aalis parang ano naging sundo yon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hatid-sundo kayo.</i>
155	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ganon ginawa namin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nandon ka na sa exam, papano mo sinasagutan yung mga questions like, elimination ba o paano ba strategy mo don o hindi mo muna sinasagutan yung hindi sigurado?</i>
156	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung hindi ko sigurado naka mark. Naka mark talaga siya tas kasi diba ang kagandahan kasi pag may kasama kang mag-aral kunyari diba. Hindi naman maiwasan yon eh, natatandaan mo siya kasi may comeding nangyari. Pumapalo dun yung 'Ay naalala ko, ganito yung ginawa ni ganito nun ah'. Heto yung sagot non kasi nagpapatawa siya, may sinabi siyang hindi namin naintindihan, pumunta siya ng ganito. Pumapasok talaga yung ganon parang narerecall mo na may ginawa talagang palatandaan, may ginawang palatandaan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh so kung бага may pick-up line?</i>
157	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, may palatandaan, may ginawa talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So, tinulungan din kayo ng mga kaibigan ninyo yung mga pointers?</i>
158	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So paano ninyo kinukuha yon? May contact ba, kaklase mo ba yon? Yung kinuhaan ninyo?</i>
159	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi, high school friend ko siya taga-San Juan De dios siya...sabi ng in-house nila may binigay na paper na possible na lumabas. Yung</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>mga possible na lumabas, binigyan niya ako ng kopya. Tapos nung kami din, kasi may nagbigay sa amin ng ganun din, exchange na kami, tas yung ibang kaibigan ko dun na nasa review-center nagbibigay din. Yung mga kasama ko ganon din ang ginagawa, talagang naghahanap din kami. Yung iba na, 'Oy may pointers ha' hindi kami sinasabihan na ito talaga lalabas, sabi lang nila mag-aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano ba yung mga pointers na iyon? Ano ba parang itsura non?</i>
160	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano siya naka outline.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Outline</i>
161	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo tas sabi nakalagay don ano, "Must read" yung ganitong topic parang naka highlight na "Very important" babasahin yon, tas mayron don may isa kaming nahawakan na meds talaga. Siya yung lumabas! May meds na binigay, ilan lang yun eh, may mga meds meron din mga computation na siya yung lumalabas siya yung lumabas during the exam, Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano nangyari yun?</i>
162	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayon (ReviewCenterG) yun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh talagang kung ano yung ano nila..</i>
163	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kung ano yun yung lumalabas tapos may</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung ano mismo yung tanong dun, kung ano mismo yung problem?</i>
164	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo yun na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mismo yung problem?</i>
165	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yun na yong lumabas.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Panong nangyari yon...</i>
166	Ms. NurseG	<i>meron nga sila diba, meron sila eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Grabe (hahahaha)</i>
167	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo lumabas yun sa amin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lumalabas, anong percentage sa pointers, mga gaano ka ano yung mga pointers na yon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

168	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano siguro mga 25% din, nanggaling don.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lumabas</i>
169	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo halos... diba 1-500 yun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>All of you, yung 5 kayo, how did you deal with yung time constraints? Ahh papano o gaano katagal yung isang subject?</i>
170	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano hindi kami kasi nagbibigay ng oras na 'ito dapat tapos na tayo ha'. Yung sa amin kasi dapat makuha niya kahit na paulit-ulit di pwede na bibigyan mo siya ng oras kasi hindi naman tayo pareparehas ng pick-up eh, kailangan i-consider yung kasama natin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero 2 months yung review ninyo ano?</i>
171	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, halos.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh paano kung hindi ninyo pa matapos yung isang subject? I mean yung lahat ng coverage...</i>
172	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi nasa loob kami ng kwarto, tapos pagka sa bahay, kagaya ko, ako kunyari gagala may parang naging habit ko na yung mag-aaral ng ano ng madaling araw. Parang yon ikaw na sa sarili mo kung ano, kung mag-aaral ka ba talaga, kung tingin mo, ako ini-estimate ko kung lahat ba makukuha eh. Yung sa amin, sabi ko nga eh puro babae naglalandian din, tapos minsan nagkakaayaan na lumabas siyempre parang na e-echepwera yung review. So parang kino compensata ko na 'dapat dahil hindi tayo nag-aral, dapat mag-aaral ako'.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So 8-5 yung review ninyo then afterwards may gala diba?</i>
173	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo depende kung uuwi ka, o gagala ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano yung... diba sabi mo nag aaral ka dati ng...</i>
174	Ms. NurseG	<i>Umaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2-5 ba?</i>
175	Ms. NurseG	<i>2-5 ng umaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nagrereview ka ba, ginagawa mo pa rin iyon?</i>
176	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung inaaral mo non?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

177	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano, usually books yung talagang ano. Kasi yung sa akin, yung study habit ko, diba iba pa yung nandodon sa dorm, sa bahay din may calendar na itong books na ito dapat mabasa mo siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw gumawa non?</i>
178	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo tas tinitick ko yung "yes".</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan mo ginawa?</i>
179	Ms. NurseG	<i>Nung nag start na kami magreview, may ganon na dapat mabasa mo siya. Lalo sa CHN (Community Health Nursing) kasi diba makapal yung sa CHN eh sabi nga ng friend ko 'Uy may lalabas dyan'. Ayun nga may lumabas nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa bahay, saan kang part nag-aaral?</i>
170	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa room.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa room mo.</i>
181	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung room ko parang ganon din, ano rin, oo ang kulit nga namin eh, ang kulit ko kaya non.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung mga kasama mo ganon din?</i>
182	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, ganon din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>
183	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi mas maganda, sabi nga ng nanay ko 'ang alam ko ang anak ko nurse, bakit naging teacher?'</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, talaga</i>
184	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sabi ng nanay ko. 'Sabi ko bakit ba, gusto ko mag-aral eh.' Kasi pati yung kapatid ko, kaya naengganyo din maging nurse kasi nakikita niya na natatandaan ko, "inaral niya ito eh, inaral ni ate ito eh", kasi kung saan saan nakadikit pero sa kwarto ko, sa room din, sa CR meron nakakabit.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pati CR?</i>
185	Ms. NurseG	<i>Lahat</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh yung room mo may CR.</i>
186	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi, kunyari sa room ko may ganon.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh</i>
187	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung mga bisita namin natatawa na lang kasi yung CR namin eh pag ganon may nakadikit, may nakapaskil. Sabi ng nanay ko "Anak naman bakit pati naman yan?", nakakahiya daw. 'Bakit, sila lang nakiki CR ha' para matandaan ko ng bonggang-bongga. Kaya nga yun nga, ano pagdating ng board exam makakakuha na ako ng mataas</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May natatandaan ka bang materials mo nun, say for like FUNDA (Fundamentals of Nursing), anong mga ginamit mong ano?</i>
188	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi kami nag aral ng FUNDA (Fundamentals of Nursing), na FUNDA na purong FUNDA, parang ano lang yung tamang browse, yun lang tamang FUNDA lang pero ang pinokus kasi namin dun sa Maternal, sa MS (Medical-Surgical Nursing).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit ninyo pinokus yun?</i>
189	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi sila yung alam namin na halos abot na 200 items yung lalabas sa kanila. Sa CHN, yung nga yung isang book before kami mag start nung book na iyon ano</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Community Health Nursing</i>
190	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo yung sa bagong Community kasi nga diba bagong labas yon, nag-ano kami na o next week ito ha itong libro na ito dapat matapos ito. Siguro alam ninyo naman na color yellow diba, color yellow yun dati, revised yung ngayon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yellow green</i>
191	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo yun yung una diba, pangalawa ngayon yung nurse?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh meron ng bago nun</i>
192	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yun yung nurse sa amin, yun nurse sa atin yung nurse na naka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
193	Ms. NurseG	<i>...naka collage parang collage</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
194	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yun na yun eh, o 'dapat mag-aral kayo ha'.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So Community, Maternal...</i>
195	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa FUNDA hindi gaano?</i>
196	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi, kasi nga diba sa FUNDA</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pano yung mga theory ng nursing non</i>
197	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi alam mo naman na hindi lalabas yung theory eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
198	Ms. NurseG	<i>Alam mo naman na, diba hindi lalabas yung theories sa ganon kasi parang nursing intervention story lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nursing intervention</i>
199	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sa FUNDA, so yung mga skills dun sa FUNDA?</i>
200	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayon hindi inaral din yon, pero hindi siya yung intensive, pahapyaw lang siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung inaral mo talaga, maliban sa CHN at saka FUNDA...ay sorry sa Maternal pala.</i>
201	Ms. NurseG	<i>Psyche (Psychiatric), lahat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Psyche (Psychiatric), lahat</i>
202	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo sa Psyche (Psychiatric) din, sa Psyche (Psychiatric) kami nagtagal kasi diba complicated yun? Yung Psyche (Psychiatric). Sa gamot, kasi kailangan alam mo yung anong lab (laboratory) yung before, anong laboratory yung ipeperform before ka magbigay ng gamot.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
203	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi ang inaano namin per kunyari, per sakit, yung normal values, nursing intervention sa pharma (Pharmacology) tamang pharma lang, kasi nga diba nurse ka naman hindi ka naman kung baga doctor, eh bakit mo ite-take yung Pathophysiology? Di naman yun lalabas dun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mechanism of Action</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

204	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi naman yun lalabas eh parang alam namin na... kasi diba nga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Patho (Pathophysiology) ng MS?</i>
205	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo sa Patho yung mga ganon, hindi kami naggaganon... tamang ano lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say sa isang subject ahh like Psyche, ilang libro ang kinukuha ninyo?</i>
206	Ms. NurseG	<i>Isa sa Psyche isa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Isa lang.</i>
207	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sino ba yon yung sa Psyche natin? Meredith (book author) ano yun diba Meredith?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala kasi akong libro</i>
208	Ms. NurseG	<i>Masyado ka, wow sosyal.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ako naglibro mula nung 1st year</i>
209	Ms. NurseG	<i>Anong ginawa mo, library?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Library, kaya hindi ko alam yon</i>
210	Ms. NurseG	<i>Eh ano yon yung books</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh books lang? Marami kang books.</i>
211	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa Psyche, isa lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ba sapat na yon?</i>
212	Ms. NurseG	<i>Lahat ng ano lahat ng ginamit habang nag-aaral kami yun yung ginagamit namin during review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>ahh</i>
213	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tapos paglalabas kami kunyari sabi ni ganito maganda daw ito, pa Xerox tayo hindi kami bumibili ng ano 'uy kailangan natin bumili', bilhin natin yung bagong libro ang ganda ganda', hindi photocopy na lang. Ahh ano na, dun na lang magkakaalaman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay so let's say after na magfacilitate, nag e-exam din ba kayo sa sarili ninyo mga questions and answer?</i>
214	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano ninyo ginagawa yon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

215	Ms. NurseG	<i>Meron kaming binili na ano, kami tig isa-isa kami, nung ano parang compilation ng board exam result.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
216	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tas yon sinasagutan walang dayaan yung parang o assignment parang ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So assignment ninyo. Hindi ninyo in-assign during the...</i>
217	Ms. NurseG	<i>Bahala ka na kung gusto mag cheat. Nasa sa iyo naman iyon eh. Yung book na yon o ito 1st set kunyari 1st 5 nung compilation mo ganitong page sagutin nyo tas kayo bahala kung gusto ninyo mag cheat tapos kinabukasan ano dalahin ninyo yung sagot dun tayo mag check tapos dun na hihimayin yung bawat tanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh so may portion yun na ganon</i>
218	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like kailan ninyo ginagawa yon? Pagkatapos ng discussion, like end of the day, papano or like pre-discussion?</i>
219	Ms. NurseG	<i>Pag pauwi na, kasi hindi pwede ng before mag discuss eh sasakit na yung ulo nung bawat isa diba? Fully-loaded agad, hindi kagaya non pag-ano na, parang "Oy bakit ito yung sagot?" atleast don kahit hindi masyadong magfunction yung brain ng isa, atleast nakuha na nila yung isang unang subject namin, ayon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Natatandaan mo pa ba yung organization ng review ninyo? Ahh ano yung mga una ninyong nireview? Saan banda, kasi kung inuna nyo ba yung subjects ninyo nung 2nd year bago yung mga 4th year (subjects) o depende kung saan kayo mahina o kung san na assign? Papano ba</i>
220	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ang ginawa kasi namin nun, kung saan kami mahina. Kunyari mahina ka sa ganitong subject, siya yung mapupunta sayo. Kunyari mahina ka sa ganito, example, sa renal, mahina ka don sayo mapupunta yon. Hindi pwdeng dapat renal ako kasi ano magaling ako dun hindi sayo ibibigay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero diba ang sabi mo yung experience nyo kanina na merong pagkakataon na hindi niya pala alam o mali dun sa Brunners (book author) na hindi nag ma-match?</i>
221	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, tinutulungan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh tinutulungan.</i>
222	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo tinutulungan yon kasi para pag ikaw naman tutulungan ka din nila pero nagkakaano na may times din na nagpapalit palit kami kunyari "Uy may ano magpalit naman tayo pag hindi ko talaga kaya</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>eh, pwede bang yung akin na lang talaga. Depende sa ano kung papayag lahat "sige pagbigyan siya", ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>During that 8-5 session, meron ba kayong breaks?</i>
223	Ms. NurseG	<i>May lunch break</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kumakain ba kayo habang nagre-review o nag pica-pica?</i>
224	Ms. NurseG	<i>Lunch break lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lunch break lang, walang CR break</i>
225	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala. May bladder break, lunch break yun lang pero yung mga snacks.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron kayong mga kinakain habang nagrereview?</i>
226	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh wala</i>
227	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi naka-focus ka sa kakainin eh, pag ganun eh, kaya hindi kami nag-aano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin mo ba ahh siyempre yung school nyo dun kayo grumaduate papano nakatulong yung educational program that you received from 1st year to 4th year ahh dun sa ginawa ninyo?</i>
228	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In what way? Let's say yung foundation mo, anong factor nung foundation ninyo dun sa ginawa ninyong experience na yon?</i>
229	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung sa amin, yung Dean kasi namin, may paka mahigpit so parang talagang... tapos yun nga diba, parang ano pa ika-categorize kayo, so may kaba baka matatanggal ganon kahit na nasa regular ka pwede kang malipat sa iba.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pilot (lower category)?</i>
230	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo pwede ka, tapos laglag ka diba, kaya yung ganon, parang ano tinitignan ka, talagang china-challeges nila bawat estudyante o tingnan nga natin ganito, yun mga ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Teka, sa first year ninyo mayroon na ng Pilot?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

231	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sa 1st year ano yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pare-parehas</i>
232	Ms. NurseG	<i>Wala, oo pantay-pantay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, tumataas medyo pag nalaman ng ano...</i>
233	Ms. NurseG	<i>Diba parang preliminary?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, yung scale of 1-10, 10 being the highest and 1 is the lowest, bago ka magreview, anong confidence level mo na papasa ka?</i>
234	Ms. NurseG	<i>6?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit 6?</i>
235	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi yung iba naman kasi na itinuro naintindihan naman, na ge-gets ko naman tapos parang may alam talaga ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung pinagkaiba nung from January – March na inhouse na ginawa ninyo?</i>
236	Ms. NurseG	<i>Mas maganda nung kami kami, kasi maingay.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
237	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi nung ano, diba marami kang kalaban, kasi nakakahiya namang magtanong ang dami dami ninyo. "Mam hindi ko po naintindihan", nakakahiya ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo kasi baka yung katabi mo alam, sabihin 'ang bobo naman nito'. (Smiles)</i>
238	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo yun yung isa din na iniwasan namin pwedeng ma.. Ano ba yan, ano ba yan, ano ba yan, mga ganon kaya din nag kanya-kanya kami.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After nung review ninyo, ano confidence level mo?</i>
239	Ms. NurseG	<i>7-8</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>7 or 8? Sa tingin mo, halimbawa kung hindi ka sumama dun sa grupo na yon, papasa ka rin ba?</i>
240	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yung mag-isa ako?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

241	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi ko alam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo alam.</i>
242	Ms. NurseG	<i>Malaki talagang tulong sila, malaking tulong sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tingin mo ano ba yung tamang pagrereview? Halimbawa ako, kaga-graduate ko lang hindi ko alam gagawin ko magreReviewCenterG ba ako o ano. O sabihin na nating mag se-self review na ako, nagdecide ako, ano bang dapat kong gawin?</i>
243	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kung ikaw studios ka nung studyante ka, sa bahay, sa bahay ka na lang pero kung talagang pasaway ka, pwedeng gumamit ng library. Sabagay masarap din mag-aral sa library.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit?</i>
244	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tahimik. Nasa isang corner ka lang kaya lang nakaka-antok yun ang kalaban ko lagi ganon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah kaya...</i>
245	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kaya humiwalay na ako sa library, nag break kami ng library</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag break kayo ng library. Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE?</i>
246	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
247	Ms. NurseG	<i>Okay naman kasi hindi ko naman ina-achieve eh. Kahit kami, lahat kami hindinag a-achieve ng mataas. Ang sa amin, ang sa amin lang makapasa ka tapos ano mapakita mo na kinaya mo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay kung meron isang bagay, o ilang bagay, o kung ano mang bagay na tingin mo, kung titingnan mo yung experience mo ha na dapat sana ginawa ninyo, na dapat ginawa mo, na hindi mo nagawa, ano yon?</i>
248	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano daw ulit? Example</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say sana hindi pala kami nag ganito, mas okay sana yung result ganon. Sana isang portion don, example...</i>
249	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ah, regrets?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Not really regrets. Kung may naidentify ka bang bagay dun na kung i-improve mo yung ginawa ninyo, papano mo i-improve?</i>
250	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano... yung ano, yung study time</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano</i>
251	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sana longer</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Longer?</i>
252	Ms. NurseG	<i>Dapat kasi longer yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi 8-5?</i>
253	Ms. NurseG	<i>8-7 dapat</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>8-7?</i>
254	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi kaya maburnt-out ka non?</i>
255	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayun nga eh, pero sabi namin, ano tawag nito, parang sasakit naman utak natin nito, kaya hindi na, 8-5 na lang. Pero siguro kung ganon, mas higher siguro makukuha namin pare-pareho talaga kami non ng ratings, ang kulit nga eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ibig sabihin pare-pareho kayo ng natutunan? (smiles)</i>
256	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo pare-pareho talaga kami kaya nga tawa kami non eh, pare-pareho, ay naku pag nakita mo talaga yung namin, pare-pareho talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh sa tingin mo... nasa last portion na tayo-- 2 question na lang yata. Ito yung mga traits. May naidentify ka bang bagay na quality or any traits, anything that helped your review, anong meron ka sa sarili mo?</i>
257	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ano, example mo...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sabi mo kanina self-discipline, mga ganon, mga ganong traits.</i>
258	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayon tas ano, gutom sa kaalaman, kahit nung estudyante kami. "Para saan ito?" "Anong pangalan niya?" Yung mga doctor naasar na nga sa akin kakatanong.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

259	Ms. NurseG	<i>Matanong</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Matanong ka</i>
260	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo, matanong ako kahit sa hanggang ngayon matanong pa rin ako, 'bakit ganon, bakit ganito?' si "bakit" si bakit ako eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw si bakit?</i>
261	Ms. NurseG	<i>Bakit, bakit yung tawag sa akin si "Ms. Bakit" talaga ito.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga?</i>
262	Ms. NurseG	<i>Yon bakit nangyayari yung ganyan, curiosity yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano sa tingin mo nakatulong yon sa pagrereview ninyo?</i>
263	Ms. NurseG	<i>Kasi diba kung may curiosity ka parang pati yung kasama mo "Ay oo nga ano?", ganon. Kunyari may sinabi ka na ito para sa ganito, ganito, ganito may ano sila parang mas madaling parang natatandaan nila agad-agad pagka ganon ang ginagawa ko "Oy ang sabi ni prof ganito, oy sabi ni doc ganito sabi ni doc" kasi maganda sa amin kasi nga magkaka start kami ng apelyido, classmate kami so since 3rd year kami-kami talaga as in kasi nga sunod sunod kami so during duty hours kami, talagang ang hiwalayan lang namin tulog.</i>
Researcher:		<i>Ano yon bff's kayo?</i>
264	Ms. NurseG	<i>Oo ang hiwalayan lang namin tulog.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
265	Ms. NurseG	<i>Tulog lang kaya nga hindi na kami nag dorm eh, kasi parang, 'Ano yan magkakapatid?', talagang magkakasunod kami sa upuan, sa duty. Kunyari affiliated kami sa batangas, lahat kami magkakatabi ganon parang..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi naman kayo nagkakasawaan?</i>
266	Ms. NurseG	<i>Hindi, hindi naman minsan nag jo...yung mga jowa namin nagagalit na sa mga kasama namin kasi mas pinipili namin yung friends kesa sa kanila. Mas gusto namin kasi, sabi nga namin, kailangan eh tinitimbang namin na mas kailangan kami nila, at kailangan ko sila. Sabi ko siguro naman naintindihan mo naman kami ngayon na mas kailangan naming magsama-sama ngayon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Last question ko, partly nasagot mo ito kanina eh, gusto ko lang maano mo yung parting words na ito.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

267	Ms. NurseG	<i>Ayoko nga, ayoko (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano nakaapekto sayo yung lahat na yun? Yung experience mo psychologically, mentally, emotionally sa buhay mo ngayon?</i>
268	Ms. NurseG	<i>Sinasabi ko sayo, para alam mo yung capacity mo. Kasi pangit naman kung stable ka kunyari, lagi kang nasa comfort zone. Pangit yung lagi kang nasa comfort zone, mas maganda na habang lumalaki ka, habang tumatanda ka, yung sini search mo sarili mo</i>
		--END-- Time Stamp 1:05:00

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Okay Good Afternoon. My name is Neri from St. Paul University of Manila, Graduate School. Ah today I'll be interviewing you about your experience in your self-review. Explain ko lang yung four parts ng interview. Number 1 is ah your demographics and educational background in the first part. Second part is about your experiences when you had your review. Ah yung third part, will be specific strategies that you may have or you may have used uhm to effectively carry out your review. And the last one is about some traits that might have helped you uhm during your review that you might have identified, that helped your review.</i></p> <p><i>So the first part, I just like to understand the person that is in you, specifically, the social and educational background that might have influenced in some way or another, your decision to self-review. So yung una if you'd like to tell me your name, optional naman siya. Yung nickname lang kung ano ang gusto mo.</i></p>
1	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Okay. Ah Good Afternoon. My name is Mr. Nursej. I graduated from Pamantasan]. Ah year 2008. Actually yung mga factor kaya hindi ako nakapagreview center nahirapan ako sa financial. Kasi during sa time namin, siguro fifteen thousand (15,000) iyon eh. Para sa'min malaking bagay yung fifteen thousand 15,000 so hindi naman sa ginusto o gusto ko mag-review. Kungbaga yung naging ano sa school namin ang priorities nila, priority nila ay yung mga nag-review center yun lang yung pag-eexamine nila. June yung examination. Sila yung priority. Pero ako naman ahhh yun hindi ako nakapag-review kasi nga hindi ako nakapag-take ng exam after I graduate nga kasi nga sa'min parang ni-re-required nila before nga before mag-take ng... parang ma-guarantee nila yung result ng ano. So, after akong grumaduate</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>nagtrabaho ako sa Citibank for eight (8) months. After that, naging supervisor ako sa SM then yung 2010 na-hired ako as company nurse dito sa Ortigas and Company.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhm. So from 2010 hanggang ngayon ah....</i>
2	Mr. Nursej	<i>Company Nurse ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If I may ask, how old are you right now?</i>
3	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ahm I'm twenty-six (26).</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Twenty-six (26)?</i>
4	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yes.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah yung una, sa bangko...</i>
5	Mr. Nursej	<i>..sa Citibank</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Noong una sa bangko for eight months. Naging Supervisor ka sa SM. Since 2010 hanggang ngayon? Tapos? Ah nag-company nurse ka na?</i>
6	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Company Nurse. Bale mga dalawa o tatlong job na ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah</i>
7	Mr. Nursej	<i>Tapos 2009 ako nag-take ng review. During that time ano na ako... supervisor na ako sa SM.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah</i>
8	Mr. Nursej	<i>O bale yung ano ko lang kaya ako nag-take.. kaya ako kumuha ng ano.. ng exam actually parang experience ko lang eh kung paano ba yung.. kung paano ba para the next na.. parang feeling ko babagsak ako ng first time eh. Inisip ko parang magkaroon ako ng idea para next time paghahandaan ko na. Lyon lang yung plano ko. Pero syempre bigyan ako ng three (3) days leave ng manager namin so I took that opportunity para magbasa ng libro tapos ma-browse yung mga ano.. mag.. review materials ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nasaan ka nun?..</i>
9	Mr. Nursej	<i>Nasa SM Supervisor.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh. Okey. So 2008 ka grumaduate noh?</i>
10	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos 2009 ka nag-take?</i>
11	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yes.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay. Ah... November ka ba or June?</i>
12	Mr. Nursej	<i>June.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>June 200...?</i>
13	Mr. Nursej	<i>2009. So, after ko kasing grumaduate nagtrabaho ako sa Citibank for eight months. Then siguro until December ako. By January, na-hired agad ako na Supervisor sa SM. So, yung time ko 2009 kasi diba ..June iyon 2009. Supervisor na ako iyon nga nag-take ako para malaman kung paano yung sistema. Three (3) days ako nag-ano nag-leave. Syempre gusto ko rin anuhin yung kakayahan ko. So nag-browse ako ng mga ano ko.. ano ko materials ko. Kasi ako iyong tipo ng estudyante noon na wala talaga akong libro. From the start talaga. Anatomy first year second year yung Funda. Third year, fourth year wala talaga. Yung ano ko lang is basa-basa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano yung mga activity mo like...</i>
14	Mr. Nursej	<i>Xerox. Photocopy. Sa...diba sa Chem sa Lab natin. Photocopy lang iyon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay (laughs).First course mo yung nursing noh?</i>
15	Mr. Nursej	<i>First course ko yung nursing. Kung baga iyon. Eh sa'min kasi sa PamantasanJ. Mayroon kaming may... mayroong kaming ah parang.. mini-maintain na grade or else papa-alisin ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ano yung mini-maintain nyu na grade?..</i>
16	Mr. Nursej	<i>Two point twenty five sa'min. (2.25)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Two point twenty five uhm..</i>
17	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ah first... first year ko one point seventy-five (1.75) yung GWA ko. So, dapat Dean's Lister ako 'nun eh. Pero mayroon akong isang as a... subject na tres (3.0) ako eh. Two point seventy-five (2.75) sa Math. I hate Math talaga kaya hindi ako nag-enjoy noon eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong Math?.. Trigo o ano iyon?</i>
18	Mr. Nursej	<i>Algebra nga lang iyon. Nag-two point seventy-five (2.75) ako doon. So once na may two point seventy-five (2.75) automatically although yung GWA o general mo is one point seventy-five (1.75) or less than</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>hindi ka na magiging dean's lister. Ano naman eh consistent ako hanggang fourth year two point twenty-five (2.25) ako.. yung GWA ko. So based sa mga tests namin, results namin although wala akong libro, wala ako mga ganun parang kaya ko parang ganun. Parang kaya ko 'to ganun lagi ako. Ayun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So bago ko painitin yung ano mo...</i>
19	Mr. Nursej	<i>sige (laughs)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>..mga kwento mo at mukha talagang interesting. So bago sa lahat...una sa lahat, gusto ko maintindihan kung papaano ka lumaki? Ano ba mga beliefs mo sa buhay mo? Yung mga values mo kung mayroon man. Ah yung... personal mo and then how.. what happened why you chose nursing diba? Ahh bakit sa PamantasanJ. Saan ka ba nag-aral noong umpisa?</i>
20	Mr. Nursej	<i>Okay sige ano ahh actually pito kaming mag-kakapatid.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay.</i>
21	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yung father ko is driver siya. Parang namamasada lang. Mother ko sa ---- sa Pasig. Pang-apat ako. Yung kuya ko, undergraduate ng college. Ate ko, graduate siya. Ate ko ulit, undergraduate ng college tapos ako yung sumunod.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pang-apat ka noh?</i>
22	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi during that time yata. When you say nurse ka, nursing ka automatic abroad ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay (laughs)</i>
23	Mr. Nursej	<i>Iyon yung alam ng parents natin diba?</i>
Researcher:		<i>Oo..</i>
24	Mr. Nursej	<i>Eh ako naman, kung ano ang gusto ng parents ko okay naman sa'kin. Hindi naman ako ano e..Pumasok kami ng PamantasanJ kasi iyon nga yung pinakamura eh. 1,500 yata kada ano sem ganun yung pinakamura. So, okay lang nagustuhan ko ang nursing. Tapos..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung elementary, high school. Ahm kamusta yung student life mo nun? Atleast yung student life mo.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

25	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ano typical student. Ahh sige noong elementary ako ah 1, 2, 1, 2 lang yung section ko. Naging top 1 naman ako during grade five ako. Grade six ako, nasa top ten., public sa may Rosario. High school, public rin sa may Rosario Annex. Nasa 1,2,1,2 lang din yung section ko. Grumaduate ako top six sa class namin section two. Ano lang typical student lang ako. Actually ano ako eh, ako yung tipo ng guy na ano alam mo yung wala lang. Yung hindi ako pumapasok ng first day ko ng school noong third year ako. Kasi parang ano ako eh yung parang yung ano ka. Ako yung lalaki na... wala lang. Light lang ang uso. Typical lang din na hindi ako yung.. easy, ayun easy go lucky. Kunwari may mga exam-exam tinatanong yung teacher sinasagot ko pero kayang-kaya ko naman parang nilalaro ko lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bale may talento ka na talaga kaya nga lang pero medyo...</i>
26	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro mas maganda yung talent ko kung nag-aral pa ako ng mabuti mas maganda yung kakalabasan ko. Pero iyon nga ayaw ko kasing... ayaw ko ng seryoso. Ayoko ng ganun gusto ko yung laro-laro lang. Siyempre as highschool ano ka may mga inuman-inuman kayo... Ganun ako although section two ako ha. Ganun parang ganun lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa Rizal High School ka?</i>
27	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung Annex?</i>
28	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo nag-aral ayun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So noong ano? Papaano mo naman yung gusto mo ba talaga yung nursing? Initially or what happened? Ano ba yung first choice mo talaga?</i>
29	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi actually sa first choice ko talaga is nursing. Kasi iyon ang gusto ng parents ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aha.</i>
30	Mr. Nursej	<i>Then kung hindi ako makapasa ng nursing. ECE, second choice ko ECE. E luckily yung average ko eight-six point one (86.1) pumasa naman sa eighty-five (85) pati yung written ko sa exam pumasa rin. Then yung exam ko sa nursing department pumasa rin ako. So, nag-stick na ako sa pagiging nursing student. Grinab ko na iyong nursing.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay. My next question is about ah do you consider yourself as a people person o someone who prefers things to be alone? Mga bagay na mayroon ka bang ginagawang mag-isa ka?</i>
31	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro ano... depende.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Depende?</i>
32	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo Depende.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Just like..? For instance what?</i>
33	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kunwari sa pag-aaral, gusto ko ako lang mag-isa. Ayoko nang may kasama ako e. Mas focus ako pag-ako lang mag-isa. Ang ginagawa ko sa pag-aaral parang iyon nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw ba yung tipong nasa bahay na nagbabasa lang? Tapos hindi nagdadala ng libro sa school? O..</i>
34	Mr. Nursej	<i>Wala lang. Actually ako lang magbasa. Listening lang talaga ako. Kung ano lang iyong tinuro mo sa'kin, mare-retain lang sa utak ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan nag-umpisa ang talent mo na iyon? Iyong ability mo na iyon?</i>
35	Mr. Nursej	<i>Actually noong highschool pa ako ganoon na talaga ako e. Hindi ako yung tipo ng lalaki na kasi diba normally iyong ibang guy ang daming bag, ang laki ng bag. Kompleto yung libro. Ako yung lalaki na isa lang ang notebook ko, lahat nandoon. Ako iyong ganoon. Tamang... Paano ba iyon? Parang pag-kasi nakita ka ng babae na ang laki ng bag mo parang ano ka e. Pero pag-isa lang libro mo, the more maliit iyong bag mo the more na sikat ka parang ganoon mas in ka sa mga babae.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay (laughs)</i>
36	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon ako noong highschool. Okay naman. Hindi naman ako nawawala sa higher section kahit ganoon. Nadala ko iyon hanggang college. Kaya noong college ako ganoon ako. Hindi ako iyong notes ng notes basta nakikinig lang ako. Kung ano sinasabi ng professor na reporting ayun nga nakikinig lang. More on listening lang talago.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say major exams, nagbabasa ka pa rin ba o?</i>
37	Mr. Nursej	<i>Major exams?! Siyempre nagbabasa pa rin talaga ako. Based sa ano ang i-exam.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When you say you only have one notebook? Doon mo sinusulat lahat o paano iyon?</i>
38	Mr. Nursej	<i>Parang iyon nga parang sina-summarize ko yung alam mo iyon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sina-summarize mo na?</i>
39	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kunwari yung teacher ah sa maternal...Kung ano ang ni-lecture niya, kung ano ang narinig ko, kung ano iyong naintindihan ko na isa sa itinuro niya ayun ang sinusulat ko sa notebook ko.. sa notebook ko. Iyon lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So pa-paano mo siya binubuo sa utak mo? Gumagawa ka ba ng construct ng... let's say iyong papaano ang definition mo sa bagay na iyon o? Paano ba iyong approach mo?</i>
40	Mr. Nursej	<i>Empirical person ako e based sa objective data ako e. Hindi ako nag-rerelay sa mga subjective na ganoon. So iyong reasoning ko kasi is focus ako kung ano iyong narinig ko na alam kong tama doon lang ako. Pero pag may narinig ako na lam kong mali based sa reasoning ko hindi ko siya kukunin. Hindi ko siya i-adapt.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So in an application to your subject, let say sa.. Maternal na lang?</i>
41	Mr. Nursej	<i>Sige.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah pag may narinig kang halimbawa may isang teacher...</i>
42	Mr. Nursej	<i>Based sa knowledge ko, based sa fundamental na alam ko ha, pagsinabi niya pagsinabi niya yung statement against may beliefs, against my fundamental na alam kong tama sa sarili ko..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hayaan mo lang?</i>
43	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hayaan ko lang. Pero i-evaluate ko siya kung tama o mali.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>O hindi ikaw iyong tipo na nagta-taas ng kamay na 'Ma'am parang teka hindi yan ang nasa libro?' ganun.</i>
44	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon din ako e. Gusto ko mag-oppose palagi e. Gusto ko iyong nag-ooppose sa lahat pero kaya kong panindigan iyong ano ko. Pero pag-alam kong mali ako, hindi naman sa mali kungbaga, pag-inooppose mo it doesnt mean tama o mali siya gusto ko lang din malaman kung hanggang saan iyong kakayahan ng ino-oppose mo. Classmate mo professor mo. Lang talaga. Although alam mong tama siya parang ganoon.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa course natin masyadong theoretical maraming libro, maraming kaialngan aralin. So, yung gusto ko maintindihan ko papaano diba sa bi mo kanina bihira ka magdala ng libro o ano? Pero lets say kung gusto mo i-oppose ang isang tao diba may backing ka?</i>
45	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo well alam mo dapat ang tama.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Alam mo dapat iyong tama.</i>
46	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siyempre pinipili ko iyong mga ibabato ko sa kanya na alam ko lang. Pag-hindi ko alam bakit ko siya i-oppose. Kung hindi ko alam pero sinabi niy sa'kin paniniwalaan ko iyon. Alam ko ito ang tama pero pag may alam ako na iba sa sinabi ko sa.. I-oppose kita.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So, clarify ko lang noong sabi mo..Noong..Noong higschool ka medyo easy go lucky ka sabi mo? Pero noong college ba ganoon rin ba o pumupunta ka ba sa library may pagkakaiba ba o pag may pagkakataon?</i>
47	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro iyong ----- ko sa college siguro tatlong beses lang ako pumunta ng library.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(laughs) ah okay.</i>
48	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon lang talaga. Iyong library card ko siguro wala as in wala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm.. Okay salamat. So, ah actually we're approaching the second part of this ah interview. Iyong experiences mo so ah briefly medyo naintindihan ko na kung ano iyong background mo. Papaano iyong demographics mo ah. Anong reason mo kung bakit ka nag-nursing diba?</i>
49	Mr. Nursej	<i>Uhhh..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ngayon, papasok sa punto na iyong mismong experience mo na self-review. So siyempre iyong unang-unang tanong ay ano ba iyong mga factors or reasons that influence you to decide na self-review? Although sinabi mo na kanina diba na...</i>
50	Mr. Nursej	<i>Financially..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Financial?</i>
51	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So can you tell me more about it?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

52	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hmm iyon..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong nangyari nang mga panahong iyon? Kasi minsan kahit naman o tayo gipit ngayon minsan may pagkakataon rin namang na medyo maluwa din diba?</i>
53	Mr. Nursej	<i>Actually...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero iyong mga panahong iyon ano ang nangyari?</i>
54	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kaya ako nag-work para maka-ipon ako ng pang-review center. Gusto ko maging disente para siyempre iyong resluta ma... manipulate ko na pasa ako. Kasi gusto ko one take lang pasado ako e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nagwork ka after ng college right?</i>
55	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Right after talaga. Iyon ang purpose ko para makaipon. Para maka-take ng review para makapasa. Iyon nga luckily nakapasa ako ng one take lang without reviewing na kumuha ako ng review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh..Nice. Very nice. So sabi mo kanina may iyong school ninyo hiondi ka makaka-take ng board exam kapag hindi ka nag-review center diba?</i>
56	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yes.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So, requirement iyon? At iyon yung dahilan kaya ka hindi nakapag-take ng June that year?</i>
57	Mr. Nursej	<i>Saka iyon pa ang isa. Pangalawa kasi mayroon.. alam ko may utang pa ako doon e. Siguro mga two thousand (2000) yata sa school namin. Hindi i-re-release iyong ano mo e parang may requirements something like that. E mayroon pa akong two thousand (2000) na utang sa school. Iyon pa ang isang reason kaya hindi ako nakapag-take.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakapag-take agad? So una?</i>
58	Mr. Nursej	<i>Requirements..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka nakapag-enroll sa review center?</i>
59	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pangalawa sa requirements?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

60	Mr. Nursej	Oo.
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Medyo mabigat nga ang dalawa na iyon noh?</i>
61	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kungbaga ano that time walang-wala talaga kami. Parang nahuli iyong padala ng tito ko abroad. Parang ganoon talaga.. nagkataon talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>At tumutulong din iyong tito mo? Pero iyong dalawa mong kapatid graduate din ng college?</i>
62	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi iyong isa lang kasi may mga family na sila e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May mga family? Noong panahong iyon? Ah so sa bahay ilan na lang kayong natira? Pito kayo plus dalawa?</i>
63	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pito?! Bale apat kaming magkakapatid na nasa bahay ngayon.</i>
Researcher:		<i>Hmm.. Ikaw iyong panganay ngayon...</i>
64	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ako iyong panganay ngayon sa'min. Tapos, extended family kami. Uncle ko, tito ko may pamilya din so iyong bahay namin hinati sa.. Dalawa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay so iyong.. iyong review center. Pero wala ba kayong let say mga pre-review or noong fourth year?</i>
65	Mr. Nursej	<i>Mayroon naman. Mayroon. Mayroon. Iyon nga during that time nasa top iyong pangalan ko e. Una top three ako, top five. Kungbaga...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa pre-review?</i>
66	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo, sa pre-review. Parang iyon nga siguro na-over confident ako sa sarili ko na feeling ko kaya ko kaya hindi ako natatakot na mag-take ng exam iyon din siguro.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay so ahm Funda tsaka nabanggit mo sa'kin noong una na hilig mo ang IMCA diba? So, buong duration mo noong nursing, anong mga hilig mo kung mayroon man na anything na subjects at kung if you can explain why ay better?</i>
67	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro Funda.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Funda?</i>
68	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ahmm ako if ever ang ma-ishare ko lang siyempre pag-Funda, nursing... Foundation of nursing. Iyon yung ibig kong sabihin e. Pag ito lumapit ka the rest will follow. Parang ano ko, sa Funda kasi iyong iyong ano ko pinagbutihan ko talaga fundamental of nursing. Kasi nandoon na lahat e bibigay sa'yo iying basicstandard as a nurse to be. Being a nurse nandoon na lahat. So iyong mga maternal, mga ----, MS will follow na lang iyon e. Pag-alam mo iyong Funda, pag mayroon</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>kang ah foundation sa Funda ng Nursing, the rest ng subject mo sa nursing okay na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh.. Mayroon bang tao na nag-inspire sa'yo let say professor mo, estudyante o kilala mo na nakitaan mo ng parang naging motivation mo para magustuhan iyong course, iyong subject na iyon? Iyong mismong course na iyon?</i>
69	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ah iyong nursing. Actually nga magulang ko may gusto nun pero eventually nagustuhan ko na rin kais masaya rin naman e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm.</i>
70	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kungbaga iyong ibang tao, ibang lalaki ayaw.. nandidiri sa dugo ganoon. Parang iyong nandoon na ako hindi naman nakakadiri parang siguro iyon nga (laughs) masaya. Masaya maging nursing student. Parang ahead ka tingnan mo naging... sa.. Citibank naging officer na ako doon knowingly na nursing graduate ako. So paano ako nag-excel sa banking word e nursing graduate ako? Paano ako nag-excel sa pagiging supervisor e nursing graduate ako. So ahead iyong pagiging nurse ko compared sa other course which ever or whatsoever kasi kaya natin lahat e. Pero sila hindi nila kaya pagiging nursing student. Iyon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmmm...galing sige. So iyong ano aha-after you graduate nag-work ka na agad.. ah kasi yung tita?!</i>
71	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi mayroon kasi akong anak. Kungbaga graduating ako nabuntis ko iyong girlfriend ko so kailangan ko mag-trabaho.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah okay.</i>
72	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kaya kung sabagay pagka-graduate ko magtra-trabaho talaga ako ayun. Naging factor din iyon kaya after ko grumaduate nagtrabaho agad ako dahil may anak ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So iyong cae mo hmm noong sabi mo nga kanina dahil nga doon sa una, financial. Pangalawa, iyong sa may kulanga ka nga sa school. Kailan ka nag-decide? Diba sabi mo mag-iipon ka sana kaya ka nag-trabaho...</i>
73	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kaya ako nag-trabaho para maka-ipon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>.. sa review center. Kailan ka nagdecide na mag-review center ay self-review na lang? Ahm noong mga panahong..</i>
74	Mr. Nursej	<i>Sabi ko nga kaninaiyong examination noong 2009, mag-eexam ako para hindi pumasa. Mag-eexam ako apra malaman kung paano ba, ano ba iyong ginagawa doon? Iyon lang paano ba ang sistema?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh.. uhmm</i>
75	Mr. Nursej	<i>Iyon lang, iyon lang ang inano ko yung parang target ko kayaako nag-exam. Para atleast makita ko iyong grades ko alam ko na kung saan ko titirahin e parang ganoon. Parang gusto.. parang iyong 2009 June evaluation ko sa sarili ko lang iyon.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh. Uhhh..</i>
76	Mr. Nursej	<i>..Para sa November next year 2010 alam ko na iyong titirahin ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero did it ever occur to you that iyong mga policies ngayon ng hospitals na ganun..?</i>
77	Mr. Nursej	<i>Na...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kapag hindi ka nag-one take medyo ano mababa.</i>
78	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi ako iyong tao na wala akong pakialam sa ganoon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
79	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi ako naapektuhan ng ganoon. Kunyari, Pare ako first taker ako isang... Second take. Hindi ako naapektuhan. Kungbaga wala sa'kin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi. Ang gusto ko maintindihan doon kung diba sinabi mo na parang gusto mong i-try muna na..</i>
80	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. I-try ko lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>E siyempre may risk doon na..</i>
81	Mr. Nursej	<i>Bumagsak ka doon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>.. kapag hindi mo meyo pinag-igihan pwedeng..</i>
82	Mr. Nursej	<i>May chance...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo.. Pwede ring maging second taker ka ganoon.</i>
83	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero papano mo siyang na-kontrol o?</i>
84	Mr. Nursej	<i>What do you... Paanong na-kontrol?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ibig ko sabihin, paano mo na-maanage iyong ano na iyon na i-maintain mo pa rin na kaialngan may pag-nagexam ako, mayroon akong prior knowledge?</i>
85	Mr. Nursej	<i>E ayun nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>..na may alam rin ako talaga na masasagot ko ito.</i>
86	Mr. Nursej	<i>Iyon nga nag-file ako ng leave 3days.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>3days?</i>
87	Mr. Nursej	<i>Before the exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo.</i>
88	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ah first two days nag-review ako sa mga sa notes ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh.. Uhhh..</i>
89	Mr. Nursej	<i>Then, iyong one day before the exam nagpahinga lang ako sa bahay namin. Iyon. First ng exam, ang aga-aga ko as in alas-singko pa alang nanadoon na ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo kailangan nga. Oo.</i>
90	Mr. Nursej	<i>E pag-first day excited tayo. Ah tatalo iyoing exam noon kung hindi ako magkakamali. Tatlong part ng exam, hindi naman sa mayabang ako (laughs) kungbaga parang ang dali sa'kin ng exam talaga. Iyong first, second, third na exam. Kaya the next day nga alas-sais yata iyong time siguro mga seven na ako pumasok. Nagulat iyong mga kasamahan ko e late na pala hindi na ----. Tapos ako pa iyong unang-unang natapos. Parang ssinadya talaga ng ---- na umabot pa ako. Siguro ewan ko kung ano kung totoo iyong papasa, papasa ka kahit hindi ka mag-aral.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Medyo parang..</i>
91	Mr. Nursej	<i>Medyo.. sa tingin mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin ko?</i>
92	Mr. Nursej	<i>Parang swerte e parang luck o chance lang noong pumasa ako?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa tingin ko iyong parang kapag mayroon kang talento talaga minsan iyong mga clues lang makikita mo na. Ahm.</i>
93	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ikaw e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mayroon..</i>
94	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mayroon din kasamang, ako ang...</i>
95	Mr. Nursej	<i>May swerte...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May swerte at may kasamang tiyaga e. IYOn, iyon naging approach ko e.</i>
96	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siyempre iyong mga favored namin tinuturan kami ng mga strategy, elimination. Nag-based ako sa elimination e for possible answers. I-eliminate mo iyong two answers na talagang imposible na e. Siguro iyon iyong naging ano ko.. naging..strategy ko iyong answering the exam. Elimination. Parang for possible answer ini-eliminatae ko iyong dalawa na kalokohan na ang sagot.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh..</i>
97	Mr. Nursej	<i>Doon iyong dalawa nang matitira... Mapipili. Doon i-aanalayze iyong sagot ko based sa question.Ganoon iyong start ko during the examination. Actually lahat ng exam ko ganoon e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah ganoon iyong approach mo?</i>
98	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon ang approach ko. Elimination.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero so tanda mo pa rin talaga iyong ano mo iyon kasi graduated 2008 ah...</i>
99	Mr. Nursej	<i>One (1) year lan. Medyo fresh pa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Medyo fresh pa. At assuming na considering that three days ka lang nag-leave diba? At one day ka lang nagbasa?</i>
100	Mr. Nursej	<i>Two days.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay two days ka nagbasa?</i>
101	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kaya iyon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow ha. Iyon ay kakaiba iyon diba?</i>
102	Mr. Nursej	<i>So, diba sabi nga nila mas maaano sa isipan mo iyong pinag-aaralan mo pagnakiking ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhm..</i>
103	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro sa ninety-five percent (95%) na narinig mo, mare-retain sa utak mo. Siguro once na nagbasa ka, siguro twenty to thirty percent lang iyon. Ayon kay Karl Marx iyon ha. Ayun.</i>
Researcher:		<i>Okay.</i>
104	Mr. Nursej	<i>Idea lang na ma-ga-gain ang knowledge mo twenty, thirty kapag nagbasa ka.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero papaano mo siya ni-re-retain?</i>
105	Mr. Nursej	<i>Wala...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>..Para ba siyang? Siyempre ang board exam ay situational. Hindi lang a one plus one equals two yan. Mayroon din ten divided by five equals two. Medyo by logic siya e. So papaano mo siya ino-organize sa isip mo?</i>
106	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro ano. Kasi noong bata ako parang mahilig ako mag-imagine e. Mahilig akong mag-rationalize. Parang kaya kong i-rationalize ang isang bagay na napakaliit. Let's say ano...ako yung tao na isang bagay lang ang dami kong pupuntahan. Ang dami kong explanation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh...</i>
107	Mr. Nursej	<i>Na... kunyari, diba example na lang dito sa clinic setting. Kunyari dito may pasyente ako dito ah nagtanong siya kung bakit masakit iyong tiyan niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh..</i>
108	Mr. Nursej	<i>As a nurse, ano tayo eh iyong approach natin dapat hindi as a doctor e. Pero parang tinatanong ko ano ba iyong history niya. Ang dami kong tanong sa kanya para mag-come up ako sa anong kinasakit ng tiyan niya. Same ng pag-aaral ko, ganoon din ako parang I over rationalize small things na at the end maganda naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you mean with over rationalize? Ano..</i>
109	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kungbaga ano ah over rationalize.. kumbaga iyon nga iyong isang bagay na napakaliit kaya kong gawan ng kwento.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm...Let's say pumasok ako masakit ang tiyan ko tapos tinanong ko sa yo na bakit ba masakit,' ano ba ang nangyayari masakit ang tiyan ko?' So, tatanungin mo ko kung ano ang mga..</i>
110	Mr. Nursej	<i>Lahat ng possible question na related sa pananakit ng tiyan mo including time of sleep mo, anong kinain mo? Anong history mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aha.</i>
111	Mr. Nursej	<i>Family histroy. Lahat-lahat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So tatanungin mo muna iyon? Bago ka magsabi ng reason kaya masakit..</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

112	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Katulad noong atleast mayroon na akong basis ayun mayroon akong assessment sa kanya kung bakit masakit nag tiyan niya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh. Let's say pagdating sa... iconvert natin naman sa pag-aaral 'di ba? Although maigsi lang iyong review mo diba? Pero noong nag-aaral ka papapano mo iyon nagagamit? Let say sa M.S. (Medical Surgical Nursing) o mayroon kayong case study ganoon o case presentation or...</i>
113	Mr. Nursej	<i>Case presentation? Siguro...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag-kecase press (presentation) ka ba noon dati?</i>
114	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Iba talaga siguro may ano e parang may talent ka na talaga na hindi mo ma-explain na paano mo naalala, kung paano mo na-re-retain sa utak mo iyong mga bagay na ganon. Actually kung ikaw nasa part ko hindi ka mahihirapan sa nursing. Kaya pag may nagtatanong sa'kin, ang hirap ng nursing, sabi ko hindi yan, hindi nga ako nahirapan sa nursing eh. Parang ganun.. ganun ako ka-simpleng estudyante na ano ganoon ka-simple ang buhay estudyante ko sa loob ng apat na taon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh..Um</i>
115	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon talaga parang.. Mayroon akong goal, gusto ko pumasa ng nursing. Mayroon ako.. Pero iyong resources ko kulang e para makapasa. So, kung anong mayroon ako doon ko lang pino-pokus kung anong mayroon ako e. Doon ako gumagawa ng paraan para makapasa ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung nag-focus ka sa iyong anong kaya mo na kung anong mayroon ka.</i>
116	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kung anong mayroon ka. Hindi sa kaya ko. kumbaga, kung anong mayroon ako kasi nga wala akong libro iyon lang. Kung ano lang ang mayroon ako doon gumagawa ako ng...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mina-maximize..</i>
117	Mr. Nursej	<i>Mina-maximize ko kung anong mayroon ako. Iyong resources ko para magamit ko in return sa.. sa sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So let's say sa mga klase mo noon palasagot ka ba? Paano pba iyong sa normal class mo? Paano ba iyong ano mo?</i>
118	Mr. Nursej	<i>Favorite subject ko ano Psychology. Parang..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>General Psych iyon diba?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

119	Mr. Nursej	<i>General Psych nga iyon iyong favorite subject ko. Kungbaga gusko ko kasi iyong ano e.. gusto ko iyong.. gusto ko kung hanggang saan lang sarili ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naiintindihan mo iyong sarili mo kung saan ang limitations mo?</i>
120	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo ganoon. Kungbaga..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Potentials?</i>
121	Mr. Nursej	<i>..Alam ko naman na heto na ako hindi ko na kaya seat down na lang pero before mangyari iyon, before ko malaman na iyon na lang ako ang dami ko ng tanong sa professor ko bakit ganoon. Parang wala akong lubro tinaanong ko lang sa teacher ko. Katulad iyong appendicitis.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh Uhhh..</i>
122	Mr. Nursej	<i>Alam mo ba iyong appendicitis sabihin mo sa professor mo ganyan. Ano ba iyong nursing approach doon. Ano ba iyong gamot doon? Sa pagtatanong ko, nakikinig ako sa'yo doon ako nakakakuha ng knowledge.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahhhh..</i>
123	Mr. Nursej	<i>Tapos may reasoning.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pwede mo bang sabihin na lets say iyong kanina iyong dumating ako'y masakit ang tiyan ko ay parang holistic iyong tanong mo. Marami kang tanong diba? Kungbaga lahat inaatake mo e. Lahat inaano mo paano nangyari sa kanya? Kapag dating sa klase ganoon din?</i>
124	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon din.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tatanungin mo siya tapos...</i>
125	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ginagamit.. Ikaw iyong libro ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh..</i>
126	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero ano ka uhhh...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Matututo ka dahil.. sa pagtatanong mo?</i>
127	Mr. Nursej	<i>Parang ganoon na nga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Informer ako, ikaw .. ay recipient.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

128	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Parang ginamit kita para matuto ako. Parang ikaw ay librong nagsasalita.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman ang mga reaksyon ng mga kaklase mo noon kapag nagtatanong ka ng ganoon?</i>
129	Mr. Nursej	<i>Nakikinig lang sila. Na-a-amaze sila bakit. Actually...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm?</i>
130	Mr. Nursej	<i>Iyon iyong style ko ng pag-aaral. Sila kasi mga classmate ko, bookworm sila e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aha.</i>
131	Mr. Nursej	<i>Alam mo iyong mga iyon? Nagbabasa kahit makakapal. Kahit lalaki nagbabasa puro book talagang ganoon. E since highschool nga ako hindi ako ganoon e. Kungbaga hanggang college nga e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hanggang mag-college. Iyong pagdating sa although na-explain mo na tri-nay mo lang. Mayroon ka bang... Mayroon ka bang kakilala na pumasa o na hindi siya nag-review kaya tri-nay mo iyon?</i>
132	Mr. Nursej	<i>Wala. Wala akong kilala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah wala kang kilala.</i>
133	Mr. Nursej	<i>Talaga iyon nga ang purpose ko nga para kaya ako nag-take...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I-test iyong sarili mo?</i>
134	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Kung saan ako at sa sistema ng exam. Kung paano gagawin. Iyong shading (laughs) iyong ganoon lang i-sha-shade ko. Iyong ma-experience ko lang ba iyong mag-ta-tkae ng board. Iyon lang talaga pare.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(Laughs). Iyong next question dito actually...</i>
135	Mr. Nursej	<i>Parang wala kang makukuha sa'kin noh? May mga ---- ba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay hindi... Hindi. Ito ang lahat ay parang maintindihan mismo iyong phenomenon. It's not about kung ano ka, sino ka and ang goal dito ay ano ba ang ma-sha-share natin sa susunod sa'tin diba? Kasi iyong experience mo magiging contribution yan. Magiging parte yan kung mabubuo ko man ang thesis na 'to diba? So, kung... Mahalaga iyon. Kung ano ang mga kwento natin, kwento nila baka may isang tao na maka-relate din o kaya makarelate na siya, gumawa siya ng sarili niya based on what we have and what we have experienced. So iyon</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>yung part of my goal kaya gusto ko lang maintindihan mismo kung ano ba ang nangyari.</i>
136	Mr. Nursej	<i>So parang gusto mo rin ibahagi na..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siyempre.</i>
137	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kunyari ako pa iyong parang experience mo iyan e. Tama ba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo.</i>
138	Mr. Nursej	<i>Experince mo ginawa mo lang in formal tama? Parang experience mo i-share in the way na ah standard?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Iyon. Tama. Sa formal, oo.</i>
139	Mr. Nursej	<i>So naging dahilan lang din iyong experience mo kaya..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhhh.. Uhm</i>
140	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kaya nag-come up ka sa ganyang thesis?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yeah. Kasi maraming tao. Parang siguro naman bago sila mag-review center naisip nilang mag-self review kaya ako pero mat takot e dahil walanmg mababasa. Dahil hindi nila alam paanong gawin baka mag-fail. Ang laki ng risk dahil percentage bumababa e. Bumababa, last time thirty-eight percent (38%) tapos kungbaga mayroon talagang risk.</i>
141	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So itong goal nito para know-how..</i>
142	Mr. Nursej	<i>I-uplift?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo para bang magkaroon sila ng idea kung papano gawin itong isang bagay. At magkaroon sila ng idea para ma-experience mismo ang pakiramdam ng mga tao na effectively nagawa ang self-review at pumasa.Iyon yung pinakabuod ng study ko. Hindi ko alam kung sa logical o make sense pero iyon ang gusto ko ma-achieve.</i>
143	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero tangible ba iyong magiging ano mo dyan?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So far, gawa na iyong first part medyo alam ko na rin kahit papaano although inaabangan ko iyong mga experiences. Natutuwa ako parang nabibigla ako sa mga experiences ninyo. Tingin ko tan.. Hmm... Attainable naman siya. Kaya ko siya. Oo.</i>
144	Mr. Nursej	<i>Attainable?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo attainable.</i>
145	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi parang subjective iyong ano mo e. Hindi ba?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi kasi ang magiging ano kasi nun ah gagawa ako ng mga themes. So ang process ay i-analyze ko ang isang case which say iyong case mo tapos i-co-compare compare iyon sa ibang cases. Kung may uniqueness doon, ibubukod iyon o kaya kung mayroon mang commonalities so ganoon. Parang triangulation. Lahat ng mga ano parang ma-analyze mo siya at magkaroon siya ng its not really a conclusion e parang generalization lang siya na mag-aassume o kaya i-state mo lang siya na ganito ang nangyari.</i>
146	Mr. Nursej	<i>So ito ang guide mo para makakuha ka ng ano para somehow makuha mo iyong dapat mong kunin based sa interview mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhm Uhm.. Iyong next question dyan nasa ano na tayo. Iyong although na-explain mo kanina na it was only three days, in facet two days nga lang pero hindi ko alam siguro thoughts mo na lang about reviewing. Papaano mo kinompress iyong lahat ng inaral mo sa loob ng two days na iyon?</i>
147	Mr. Nursej	<i>Mahirap. Mahirap. Two days na iyon ano. Simula first ko hanggang fourth year ko nandoon na lahat. Kungbaga ang siyempre mayroon akong timeline. In two days na iyon may timeline ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Aha. Aha</i>
148	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siyempre sa apat na taong pagk-aaral ko alam ko iyong saan ako mahina e. Based sa mga exam namin, sa mga pre-board exam namin sa school namin alam ko kung saan ako mahina. So doon ako nag-focus sa mahina ko in two days ako. So, kung kunyari sa limang subject na iyon, mahina ako sa gamot e. Sa Pharma, mahina ako sa pharma binigyan ko sarili ko sa pharma na lam ko naman na kaya ko naman. Objectively based sa exam result namin, pre-board exam kaya ko so parang kaya ko itong subject na ito. So hindi ako masyadong nag-focus doon. In two days na nagfocus ako sa para maging accurate lang tayo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ayan.</i>
149	Mr. Nursej	<i>Sa funda. Kung i-rate man ako ng one to ten, eight or nine ako dito kaya hindi ko na siya ni-review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo na siya ni-review?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

150	Mr. Nursej	<i>Nahirapan talaga ako sa maternal..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pwedeng sulatan iyan okay lang.</i>
151	Mr. Nursej	<i>.. saka sa MS. Doon talaga ko nag-focus. Tsaka iyong pharma kasi e based sa mga exam namin napaka-limited iyong mga question e. Parang nursing aral mo naman iyon e. Pagiging nurse na lang na parang.. madali lang. Sa pharma, sa tanong dun hindi anman sa gamot e napaka-ilan lang e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo. Naka-incorporate siya sa ano e..</i>
152	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo e ilan lang iyon e. So iyong mga basic ba. Mga antidote, na-overdose ka sa particular na meds ano iyong antidote doon? Mga typical na ganoon lang ni-review ko. Tapos dito naman sa maternal mahaba kasi ang maternal e. Nagfocus ako sa nursing action kasi alam ko sa mga book natin parang medical approach ito e parang ganoon. Nagbukas ako sa nursing approach natin. Ano ba iyong approach natin? More on caring lang tayo e, caring approach natin. Iyon yung method natin e. Nursing is caring e. Parang doon ako nag-focus talaga although mayroon akong ahhh ilang nalalaman foundation sa mga.. sa ano niya sa sakit niya mismo kunyari sa sakit alam ko basic niya pero the rest nagfocus ako sa nursing action natin. Kunyari, ah ano bang magandang example? Sige!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ano.. sa ano?</i>
153	Mr. Nursej	<i>Sa nursing action. Kunyari...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pagdating sa ano, let say pumasok iyong ano masakit na tiyan ng buntis.</i>
154	Mr. Nursej	<i>Normally, ang doctor tatanungin ano ba iyong gamot mo o gamot ng doktor. Tayo hindi, parang kung ano ang standard nursing care doon lang ako nagfocus talaga. E..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pati na rin sa maternal?... Iyong mga ano let say iyong professional adjustment iyong mga research na yan diba lumalabas yan sa mga ano?</i>
155	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. Okay lang naman sa'kin ang research e. Ewan ko ba para sa'kin parang po-pop-up na lang sa utak na ito naaalala ko ito. Yung ganitong senaryo naaalala ko. Biglang nag-po-pop up na lang sa utak na iyon kasi naaalala ko siya kasi nga nag-po-pop-up, naaalala kasi</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>nakikinig ako e. Iyong pakikinig ko, talagang thorough listening talaga iyong giangawa ko. Fault finder ako. Hindi ako sa tama. Tama na nga siya bakit mo pa iintindihin e. Fault finder ako sa lahat. Iyon yung tag sa'kin sa school. Fault finder, ako yung naghahanap ng mali. Pagnahanapan kita ng butas, doon kita titirahin. Ganoon iyong style ko. Hindi dahil.. hindi dahil.. hindi dahil na...gusto kita ipahiya or what so ever. Gusto ko i-defend mo iyong sarili mo kung bakit nasabi mo iyon. Ganoon iyong style ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ang ibg mong sabihin, let say ah iyong isang bagay kunyari nag-expalin siya, kung ano iyong difference nun sa anong nakaraan ganoon kinukuha mo iyong denominotor nun? Saka na-aano sa utak mo?</i>
156	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo ganoon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>.. naiwan sa utak mo?</i>
157	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo. In the sense na mas naalala ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi nga experience?</i>
158	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi naalala ko iyong sinabi sa'kin na iyong una kong ano sa Psychology ay kapag daw tumatagal daw ang isang ano kapag meaningful daw ang experience.</i>
159	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yes.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So kung nagkaroon kayo ng debate o ano..</i>
160	Mr. Nursej	<i>E ang kaso everyday ay meaningful day sa'kin e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(laughs)</i>
161	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi nga hindi ako nagbabasa. Unang-una siguro kung may libro rin ako hindi rin ako magbabasa e. Diba ang kapal-kapal niyan?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm..</i>
162	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ewan ko. Siguro sila talagang ano bookworm sila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm..Iyon iyong naging approach mo?</i>
163	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo iyon na iyon. The meaningful experience.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Uhm sabi mo kanina noong una ay noong tinanong kita iyong two days na iyon ang term mo ay "mahirap"?</i>
164	Mr. Nursej	<i>Mahirap.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ano iyong mga challenges mo? Papaano mo nasabing mahirap at anu-ano ang mga mahihirap na iyon kung mayroon man?</i>
165	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi iyon nga diba sabi ko objective person ako. When I say mahirap, mahirap talaga in a way na hindi ko alam. Kunyari... hindi ko alam. Kungbaga, wala kong alam sa bagay na iyon e kaya mahihirapan ako. So, iintindihin ko siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala kang alam sa...</i>
166	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kunyari particular na subject matter sa nursing. Kungbaga wala kong meaningful experience dito. Kungbaga ito iyong aralin ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anu-ano ang mga subjects na iyon?</i>
167	Mr. Nursej	<i>Diba sabi ko nga sa'yo mas natututo ako kapag...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May interruptions?</i>
168	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo kapag may attraction may ganoon . Mayroon akong mas makikinig ako sa'yo, mas natututo ako kesa mag-self review ako. Nagbabasa ako, nag-take down notes ng sarili ko nahihirapan ako doon kaya iyon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So, naging challenge sa'yo iyon?</i>
169	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo parang ngayon ko lang na-experience na mag-aral ng ako lang sa sarili ko. Kasi nga ang strategy ko nga, makinig, magtanong, ma-retain. Ganoon naging strategy ko. I-evaluate ko siya sarili ko na lang kung paano ko ilalabas kaya nga lang nag-po-pop- up na lang siya ng ganoon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hmm okay. So sinabi mo kanina na binigyan ka ng three days na leave ng super o ano man..</i>
170	Mr. Nursej	<i>Management.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Management ninyo. Ah iyong tanong ko doon. Siyempre bago ka mag-leave medyo alam mo na mag-re-review ka. So ano ang mga handa na ginawa mo bago ka mag-leave.</i>
171	Mr. Nursej	<i>Lahat ng notes ko kinuha ko kasi ako may pagka-OC ako e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

172	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ako iyong alam mo iyong tawag sa term na iyong small things na tinatago ko siya kasi alam ko magagamit ko ito.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah.</i>
173	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ganoon ako. So..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mapagpahalaga ka sa dati mong...?</i>
174	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo tsaka alam ko na at the end wala akong rsources. Ito lang iyong resources ko e. Ito iyong kayaman ko itatago ko ito. Iyon.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero kamusta naman iyong excuse me for the word ha.</i>
175	Mr. Nursej	<i>O?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi ako ganoon ako e sinusulat ko pero pagkatapos ko maisulat hindi ko na mabasa. Kamusta naman ang hand-writing mo? Hindi mo naman..?</i>
176	Mr. Nursej	<i>Actually steno iyong sulat ko e.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero naintindihan mo naman pagbinalikan mo na?</i>
177	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo naman siyempre.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nagamit mo talaga iyon?</i>
178	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kungbaga, kung ikaw titingin ng review materials ko hindi mo maiintindihan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay.</i>
179	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero ako syempre, sinulat ko pa e kaya alam ko kung paano ko sinulat kung ano..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So noong nagbabasa ka papaano mong tinatandaan iyong, inaalala mo ba iyong mga pangyayari dati o papaano?</i>
180	Mr. Nursej	<i>Iyan na-rerefresh na lang sa'kin. Na-rerefresh parang amdali kasing maintindihan kapag sinummarize mo na. Let say ito novel 'to nabasa ko siya o sabihin nating narinig ko ganito pala 'to. Sa-summarize ko siya. Isusulat ko siya. So, mas maiintindihan ko iyon lalo kapag sinummarize ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ganoon ang approach mo?</i>
181	Mr. Nursej	<i>So kapag binasa ko siya, naka-summary siya pero kung paano ko siya sinummary ma-re-recall ko sa utak ko. Iyon ganoon. Parang recalling!</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Iyong retention mo gaano kahaba? Let say natatandaan mo pa yung last 3 years?</i>
182	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pag-meaningful maaalala mo.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oh siyempre ganoon e. Pero iyong sayo..?</i>
183	Mr. Nursej	<i>Once na nag-take down o sinummarize ko 'to. Alam mo iyon kunyari, ano ba iyong hindi mo makakalimutan mo sa sarili mo? Ikaw?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa'kin? Let's say yung sa isang experience ko na lang, bigla ko lang naaalala iyong.. naalala ko iyong "lotus". Nandoon ako sa U.P. (University of the Philippines) nagbabasa ako tapos biglang may lumapit na lalaki. Actually nagtingin-tingin lang ako kasi nga nag-rereview nga ako noon e. Tapos medyo gusto ko magrelax tapos naglakad-lakad ako sa lotus. Tapos may biglang lumapit na lalaki, ganu din yung ginagawa niya...Iyon yung umpisa na maging magkaibigan kami hanggang ngayon.</i>
184	Mr. Nursej	<i>Anong taon yun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>That was back ah 200...? 2007.</i>
185	Mr. Nursej	<i>Tingin mo bakit mo naalala iyon hanggang ngayon?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi iyon yung umpisa namin kung paano kami nagkakilala. Kumbaga naging mahalaga siya na kapag nakikita ko yung "lotus", naalala ko kagad yung kaibigan ko na yun. CPA (Certified Public Accountant) siya ngayon. Minsan kapag nagkikita kami ah nililibre niya kao, o kaya ako ang nanlilibre. Every time na nakikita ko yun, nagiging palatandaan ko siya, kumbaga pathognomonic ko siya.</i>
186	Mr. Nursej	<i>So once may nakikita kang lotus, ang una mong naiisip yung ganyang pangyayari? Same goes with me. Kunyari, kapag sinulat mo siya in writing lalo mo siyang mas maalala. Kunyari, nagkita kayo, nagbabato ka ng bato sa lotus, why not sinulat mo--- "lotus, nagbato ako ng bato, nagrereview ako". Kapag nabasa mo yung "lotus", suddenly maalala mo yung lotus, ito yung place sa U.P. na mag-isa ako nagrereview ako, kasi meron ka ng something na tumutulong sa'yo para mas maalala mo pa. Ganyan din sa akin, ganyan yung naging pag-aaral ko, sa mga notes ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung sinusulat mo sila habang nasa klase ka, naiisip mo na ba na magagamit ko 'to balang araw, o talagang ganun ka lang magsulat?</i>
187	Mr. Nursej	<i>Okay, magandang tanong yan... (thinking). Siguro inisip ko na magagamit ko 'to kasi alam ko na wala ako eh, wala akong magiging resources eh. Alam ko na, kapag nagreview cdnter, alanganin akong makapagreview center eh. Alam ko na. Kagaya ng sinabi ko, nirarationalize ko na yung mangyayari sa akin sa hinaharap eh. So alam ko na na baka hindi ako makapagreview, so kailangan kong makapagtake down notes. Kailangan kong alagaan yung mga notes ko para magagamit ko. Yun nga, nagagamit ko nga talaga siya.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		[Time Stamp 52:56]
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>To give a run down, yun yung mga part na sa pre-review inipon mo yung mga notes mo, ganun. So yung 2 days na yun, sabi mo kanina may baby ka na, papano mo namanage yung time mo? Nasa isang room ka ba, para makapagfocus ka o papano?</i>
188	Mr. Nursej	<i>Nasa isang room ako. Nun ko lang ginawa sa buhay ko na nasa isang room ako. Kinausap ko ang family ko, na huwag niyo akong iistorbohin, bigyan niyo ako ng pagkain during, kapag kakainan na. Ganun sila tumulong sa akin. Hindi nila ako inistorbo. Lahat binigay nila, pag-aasikaso, tahimik dahil sa nagreview ako in two days. Kasi although ang una kong naisip ay para malaman lang yung sistema ng board exam, andun pa rin yung pride mo na papasa ka. Two days review, andun pa rin yung pride mo na "kaya ko 'to". So nag-effort pa rin talaga ako. Hindi ko naman sinasabi na (inasa) ko lang sa memory ko yung pagpasa ko ng board (exam). Nag-effort talaga ako, dahil yung review na ginawa ko nun...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(interrupts)..intensive talaga..</i>
189	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi lang, more than ICU (Intensive Care Unit), pare..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>More than ICU... (smiles) Good term.</i>
190	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kung ginawa ko yun during nung nag-aaral ako, siguro mas maganda, mas maganda. Pero yun nga, hindi naman ako ganun eh. Come what may talaga ako eh. Come what may kasi alam ko na kaya ko, pero kapag hindi ko kaya, nagtatanong ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gusto kong maintindihan yung "more than ICU" na yun. Yung "more than ICU" na yun ay two days yun. Kumbaga, nagagawa mo ba sa buhay mo yun na napoprolong mo yun? Na kaya mo yung more than ICU let's say within a week, a month, or so? O talagang babalik pa rin yung dati mo na medyo, ano lang..?</i>
191	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo, nagegets kita, pare. Siguro ano, depende sa gagawin ko. Depende sa pinaghahandaan ko. Board exam, kumbaga, do or die. Andun nakasalalay yung ano ko eh, mapride kasi ako eh. Nakasalalay dun yung pride ko. Yun nga, hindi ako nagreview, nakasalalay dun. Kumbaga pinaghirapan ko rin talaga siya. Kung бага yung two days na yun, deserve ko rin pumasa dahil sa two days na yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta naman yung physical place? Sabi mo tahimik yung bahay niyo, malayo ba yun sa kalsada?</i>
192	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi. Di ba sabi ko extended family kami? So andun yung mga pamangkin ko. Siguro sa bahay namin, 'di ba friend mo siya, siguro mga 30 kami sa isang bahay. Sa amin, kumbaga 24 hours maingay.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>Pero nirequest ko sa kanila, two days lang bigyan niyo ako ng time magreview.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta yung lighting?</i>
193	Mr. Nursej	<i>Normal lang. Kung ano yung normal na kwarto na ilaw, yun yung ginamit ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakabukas ba yung bintana?</i>
194	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yung normal lang, fresh air. Kasi may nabasa akong libro, na in two hours nagreview tayo, dapat maximum two hours lang, kasi kapag lumagpas na yung two hours, hindi na maretain sa utak mo, kaya kapag nagrereview ako, two hours lang ng two hours. After two hours, pahinga naman ng 30 minutes, 15 minutes then two hours ulit. Hindi ako nagrereview ng straight 3 hours. Kasi nga, bakit kamo, kasi nga may nagsabi saakin, narinig ko sa kanya na yung threshold lang ng utak natin, para maretain yung particular matter na gusto mong aralin is two hours lang. So dahil narinig ko sayo yun, tinandaan ko yun. Ginamit ko yung two hours na yun, ganong strategy.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka bang kinakain nun, let's say, chips?</i>
195	Mr. Nursej	<i>Wala, yung mga memory plus? Wala.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kahit na yung candy, o mga chips na mangangata?</i>
196	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ah, habang nagrereview ako..wala hindi ako mahilig dun eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Eh tubig?</i>
197	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro yung typical na, kapag nauhaw ka, yun lang.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Heto subjective 'to talaga, how did you feel with the outcome of your review? Were you satisfied or dissatisfied? Kanina sinabi mo na kung nag-aaral ka eh nagmore than ICU ka, mas okay pa sana yung kinalabasan. Sa ngayon na pumasa ka na, hindi mo maibabalik yun eh, na pwede bang magtake ulit para mas makita ko na mas mataas yung rating ko. Kamusta yung assessment mo sa sarili mo, naging satisfied ka ba, o anong naging pakiramdam mo after ng board exam?</i>
198	Mr. Nursej	<i>Do you mean kung may regrets ako?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung satisfaction na lang, in general</i>
199	Mr. Nursej	<i>Naabsorb ko yung satisfaction na sinasabi mo after nung first day ng exam. Dun ko naisip na, ang saya pala, ang dali lang pala ng nursing</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>board exam, ang daming nahahirapan, ganyan-ganyan. Dun ko naramdaman yun, pero two days after ko magreview, hindi ko naramdaman yun kasi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...may pressure?</i>
200	Mr. Nursej	<i>May pressure talaga eh. Kumbaga two days, tapos one day pahinga ko after that exam na eh. May pressure ako, pero although andun yung pressure kaya ko namang ihandle.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo hinandle yung pressure?</i>
201	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ano lang, malakas kasi tiwala ko sa sarili ko eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say baka bumagsak ako, o parang may mali ako dun ah..</i>
202	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ano yun nung first day, o before the exam?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Before the exam muna..,</i>
203	Mr. Nursej	<i>Actually, hindi ko inisip na babagsak talaga ako, hindi ako pessimistic eh. Wala akong idea na babagsak ako. Ang idea ko is nagfocus ako, alam ko yung kakayahan ko, kaya ko 'to. Syempre, sa tulong na rin ni God. Nagpray ako sa kanya na kung anong kakalabasan nito, kagustuhan niya. At the end talaga ng lahat ng bagay sa akin, lahat ng desisyon ko, gagawin ko, nagppray ako. Kung ano mang kakalabasan, pangit o maganda, failure o hindi, iniisip ko yung kagustuhan ng Diyos, para wala akong regrets. Ganun sa'kin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pagdating sa mga naaral mo, although sabi mo nga, syempre may prior knowledge o stock knowledge ka na. Sa tingin mo ba yung mga inaral mo na yun sapat na para makacover mo lahat, almost all of the topics in nursing?</i>
204	Mr. Nursej	<i>Nirereview ko yung mga topics na mahina ako. Dun ako nagfocus. Sa tingin ko, yung word ko na "more than ICU", sa tingin ko tinackle ko lahat, in every simple details tinackle ko talaga, sa sarili ko lang. Ang ginawa ko nun, nagbabasa ako, sinasummarize ko, binabalikan ko ulit. Ganun yung strategy ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga notes mo, tapos mo basahin, sinasummarize mo...</i>
205	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yung mga sinasummarize ko kasi, alam ko na eh. Ang binabasa ko yung hindi ko alam. Ang strategy ko kasi, yung nga sabi ko kanina, nakikinig lang ako, nagtatanong ako, sinasummarize ko, alam ko na yun. Ginawa ko yun siguro pang-second day ko na lang. Parang brinowse ko na lang lahat eh. Pero syempre nung first day ko sa pagrereview, syempre inidentify ko kung ano yung mahina ako. Prior</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>to that, alam ko naman kung ano yung mahina ako eh. Bumili nga ako nung xerox (review material), yun nga yung binili ko talaga. Nagfocus ako dun...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong reviewer yun, kung matatandaan mo pa?</i>
206	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yung photocopy sa M.S. (Medical Surgical Nursing), saka Psyche(Psychiatric nursing)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Natatandaan mo yung author kung sino?</i>
207	Mr. Nursej	<i>I can provide you yung mismong ginamit ko, review materials.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sayang, hindi mo nadala.</i>
208	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kelan ka ba pwede? Siguro kahit hindi ano..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Actually kahit mapicturan mo lang siya..</i>
209	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kahit picturan mo na lang? Sa email kasi, try kong i-zip ko na lang. Actually gusto kong makita mo yung review ko eh. Kung gano ka gulo, kung gano karami..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun nga kaya ko nga sinabi eh.. (smiles) magiging interesting talagang makita yun. Ang tawag namin dun ay archival documents. Kumbaga siya yung magpapatibay na ginawa mo yung review. Evidences siya.</i>
210	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro bukas kung may time ka, dadalhin ko lahat. Pati yung notebook ko na napakaluma na, nandun pa yun sa bahay. Yun lang, experience is the best teacher talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So satisfied ka sa outcome (of review)?</i>
211	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron bang regrets?</i>
212	Mr. Nursej	<i>Regrets? Actually, hindi siya regrets eh. Ayokong gamitin yung term na "regrets" eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>"Opportunities" dapat?</i>
213	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kumbaga, kung meron lang sana akong kagaya nung iba na may resources, tingin ko mas okay rin yung kinalabasan.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa ngayon ba dinadala mo pa rin ba yang damdamin na yan na kung meron sanang resources mas maganda yung kinalabasan?</i>
214	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ngayon?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, ngayon. Sumasagi pa rin ba sa isip mo yan? Naiisip mo pa rin ba yan? O dahil lang ininterview kita?</i>
215	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi na. Kumbaga pangarap na lang siguro na magkarun ako ng ganun. Pangarap na lang. Pinapangarap ko na someday, magkaganito ako. Ganun na lang siguro.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>kasi naalala ko nabanggit mo kanina, na sabi mo na, pagboard (exam) ko, inexpect ko na magtop ako eh. Nung makita mo yung (rating) mo...Yung mismong experience na yun, papano mo madedescribe yun?</i>
216	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yun nga, hindi ko alam kung kelan nilabas yung (result), yung nag-inform sa akin, yung mother ko, tinext ako. 'Di ba, yung mother ko sa BHW (Barangay Health Worker)? Yung doktor yung nakaalam eh. Kasi lahat sila inaabangan kung papasa ako eh. Yung mama ko kasi proud siya na meron siyang anak na nursing student, na magiging nurse. Kumbaga lahat ng tao inaabangan yun eh. Yung doktor nga yung nagsabi sa kanya na "anak mo nakapasa". So tinext ako ng mama ko, nakapasa raw ako. Bumili ako ng....ano ba yun? Manila Bulletin ba yun?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Manila Bulletin, Oo.</i>
217	Mr. Nursej	<i>Tiningnan ko yung name ko sa top, sa top talaga eh! (smiles) ..(exchanging laughter). Tiningnan ko yun sa top talaga. Wala yung name ko.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sunday yun alam ko, lumalabas eh.</i>
218	Mr. Nursej	<i>Inumpisahan ko sa top 10 eh. Yung sa top ten wala pa rin eh.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(smiling)</i>
219	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero okay lang, kumbaga, that fact na pumasa ako, dun pa lang, achievement na eh. Kumbaga, yung sa cream of the top lang, sa top ako—wala. Okay lang. (Silence)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung meron ka mang maidentify, ano sa tingin ko mo yung mga advantages o disadvantages. Hindi tayo pareho nagreview center, so ano sa tingin mo yung "advantages", first?</i>
220	Mr. Nursej	<i>Advantages? Siguro, para sa akin ha, kasi nga ako yung tao na, gusto ko yung kinakausap kita eh. Mas natututo ako dun. So yung self-review sa akin, parang naging mahirap para sa akin yun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, so if we qualify it, naging mahirap sa'yo, in other terms, papano naging advantage yun?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

221	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Siguro ang advantage sa pag-selfreview, hawak mo oras mo, hindi ka mappresure, kung ano yung irereview mo, may sarili kang timeline eh. Kung ano yung subject na irereview mo, masusunod, kung ano yung gusto mong ireview. Unlike kapag nagreview center ka, meron kayong particular subject for that day. Ayaw mo, o sa gusto mo kailangan mong matutunan. Unlike kapag nag-selfreview ka, may focus ka. May focus ka kung saan mo gusto magreview; kung saan mo dapat ienhance yung sarili mo. Tapos yun nga, hawak mo oras mo, less pressure ka, siguro, kasi nga mag-isa ka lang.</i></p> <p><i>Ang disadvantage naman sa review center, kasi kapag nagreview center ka spoon-feeding ka eh. Kumbaga tumataas yung confidence mo, pero confident ka lang na papasa ka dahil nagreview center ka eh. Eh yung pangit nun, kumbaga, e kung hindi ka naman papasa? Kumbaga hindi siya basehan para pumasa ka. Kumbaga sa requirements lang yung review center, hindi yung para pumasa ka talaga. It (will) help you pero hindi pa rin siya yung pinaka-main ingredient para pumasa ka, sarili mo pa rin. Kailangan mo pa rin mag self-review.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Naniniwala ka ba na regardless of the setting, review center man o sa self-review may chance ka pa rin na pumasa? O anong advantage o benefit, although medyo bias 'to, ng nagself-review maliban sa time management, pagdating sa natutunan, o retention, pagdating sa nagagamit mo mismo sa board exam? Sa experience mo...</i></p>
222	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Siguro mas magfococus ka, kapag nagselfreview ka, kasi may time-management, pati yung subject matter, magfococus ka rin dun eh. Kumbaga dun sa hindi mo alam masyado, dun ka magfococus. So hindi ka titigil, hangga't hindi mo nalalaman talaga kung 'pano 'to, kung 'pano yun, kapag nagselfreview ka lang, unlike sa review center. Parang padadaanin lang kayo sa lahat ng subjects dun eh. Walang pakialam ang review center kung matuto ka o hindi eh. Basta sila, "ibibigay namin sa inyo 'to, illecture namin sa inyo 'to, wala kaming pakialam kung maabsorb niyo o hindi." Feeling ko ganun sa review center eh. Kasi sa mga kabatch ko kasi, silang lahat nakapagtake ng review center eh.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Ikaw lang yung hindi nag-review?</i></p>
223	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Actually, dalawa kami, yung barkada ko. Pareho kami, nung college namin, more on chicks kami eh. Ayaw ng chicks ng may libro eh. Alam mo yun? Ganun siya, pero nakapasa rin siya! Walang review center din yun. Red-horse lang...</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>(Laughs)</i></p>
224	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Oo (laughs), pero talagang matalino yun, nagtatop din yun. So halos naging pareho kami, wala rin siyang libro. Parang ganun din yung naging ano niya, hindi niya sineryoso, pero kapag dapat seryosohin,</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>major exam, nagbbrowse kami ng subject namin. Nakakapasa kami, ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When it comes to timetable, yung sa'yo ay two days. Ideally ba no sa tingin mo ang, although opinion mo na lang 'to ha, ano ba tingin mo dapat ang haba ng self-review considering the subjects of nursing ha?</i>
225	Mr. Nursej	<i>Self-review ha? Siguro ideantify mo muna yung weaknesses mo. Once naidentify mo na yung kahinaan mo, dun ka magcome up kung how long. Syempre, alam mo yung sarili mo 'di ba? Alam mo yung kakayahan mo sa sarili mo, kung hanggang saan ka, hanggang kelan mo para maabsorb yung isang subject matter. So after identifying kung saan ka mahina, dun ka pa lang makakapagcome up kung ilan talaga.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, kung gano kahaba?</i>
226	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero siguro, kung maging ano tayo...siguro (thinking), half month per subject. Kung five (areas) tayo rito, siguro mga two and a half months--Guaranteed, papasa ka! sa self-review. Assuming na naidentify mo na yung kahinaan mo, alam mo yung weaknesses mo at strengths. Siguro, yun, two and a half.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Makakatulong rin ba yung mga pretests of post tests at the back of a book, may mga exam dun?</i>
227	Mr. Nursej	<i>Makakatulong siya. Makakatulong siya na ma-recall mo. Recalling kasi yung mga ganyan eh, para sa akin eh. Kunwari, may tanong dun na..one patient nag-overdose dun sa particular drug..ano ba, magbigay ka nga?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Let's say 'amphetamine'.</i>
228	Mr. Nursej	<i>Oo, so may mga answer dun na, apat 'di ba, ABCD? Isa dun tama. Tapos at the end, sa likod nun 'di 'ba kung ano yung tamang sagot. Normally, sasagutan mo siya. "Tama ba ako?", "Ay mali", iba yung tamang sagot. Let's say letter B yung tamang sagot. Para sa akin ha, recalling lang yun eh, hindi mo alam mo mismo yung antidote sa gamot na yun, pero tanda mo siya kasi naexperience mo. Pero kapag tinanong ka kung anong antidote sa Amphetamine, hindi mo masasagot not unless nakita mo talaga yung sagot, dun mo marerecall.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sa tingin mo, although hindi na'to sa topic, mas maganda sana sa board exam kung walang options?</i>
229	Mr. Nursej	<i>Mahhirapan sila.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mas mahirap?</i>
230	Mr. Nursej	<i>In general.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi minsan, isang tingin lang, parang ganito yung nabasa ko dun, natatandaan lang niya yung thought, o yung part lang, pero kapag tinanong mo sa verbal, wala.</i>
231	Mr. Nursej	<i>Parang tayo, kung mapapansin mo, hindi ko masagot yung tanong mo sa per subject eh. Pero kapag pinakita mo sa akin yun, alam ko na.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>(smiles). Okay. Halimbawa, meron isang estudyante na kakilala mo, kakagraduate lang, will you recommend selfreview to that person? O ano irerecommend mo? Halimbawa ako hindi pa'ko nakapasa, lumapit ako sa'yo...</i>
232	Mr. Nursej	<i>Sabihin ko sa kanya, magreview center ka. Pero hindi nangangahulugan na nagreview center ka is papasa ka. Kailangan mo pa rin mag-selfreview.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So mas okay yung combination?</i>
233	Mr. Nursej	<i>Yes. Mas okay yun. Ang naging problema kasi sa akin, wala akong choice eh. Pero kung may choice ako magreview center din ako. Kumbaga, nagkataon lang talaga during that time, may problem kasi. Hindi ako nakapagreview center. Pero kung may choices ako, why not? Kumbaga makakatulong din siya, somehow, pero hindi siya yung cream of the top eh, para makapasa ka.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I'll take it as it is.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Anong naging epekto sa'yo, if there was anything, of the entire review experience, as an individual, or as a nurse, o anong naging reaction ng family mo, naging reaction ng mga tao sa paligid mo? Papano mo siya naappreciate? Anong nangyari?</i>
234	Mr. Nursej	<i>Humanga sila sa akin, kasi alam nila ang board exam mahirap eh. Eh ako, hindi ako nagreview center, two days ang review ko, tapos pumasa ako. Parang Masaya sila sa akin. Yun, pinagmamalaki nila ako.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa sarili mo, anong naging epekto? Personally...</i>
235	Mr. Nursej	<i>Syempre, umangat yung pride ko, yung self-esteem, umangat pa lalo, lahat yun. Kasi feeling ko, kung nagawa 'ko to sa sarili ko, sa iba nahihirapan sila, hirap na hirap sila, ako nakaya ko isa lang, tapos limited resources pa ako, limited time...Sa ibang bagay siguro kaya ko ring gawin. Kagaya yun nga, nagtrabaho ako sa bangko, wala akong ka-alam-alam, pero dahil nga sa naging lifestyle ko na 'kaya 'ko 'to', nagtiwala ako sa sarili ko, kaya ko. Ganun din sa pag-aaral ko, ganun</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>din nung nagtake ako ng review, tiwala lang sa sarili. Pero syempre, meron kang back-up dapat, na knowledge kahit papano.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, meron ka pa bang idagdag sa experience mo, anything. Siguro kung anong masasabi mo sa ngayon, bumabagsak, ang daming bumabagsak...</i>
236	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro kung magsusurvey ka, yung mga bumabagsak, nagrereview center. Kung titingnan mo yung statistics.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala rin kasing statistics kung sino yung nagrereview, o self-review lang eh. Kagaya niyan, konti lang talaga tayo.</i>
237	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi nga, ang inisip nila once na nagreview center sila, capable na sila. Parang enough na yung review center sa kanila para pumasa, which is hindi.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito mahalagang tanong ko 'to, interesado ako sa sagot mo... Tingin mo ba dahil dati pa talented ka na, o matalino ka na, per se, yun na naging dahilan kaya naging effective yung review mo?</i>
238	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi kung titingnan mo yung two days review pare eh, hindi ka papasa. Kung titingnan mo yung timeframe, yung two days na yun, walang maniniwala sa'yo na 'pumasa ka two days?' Di ba walang maniniwala? Siguro, andun na rin yung ...</i> <i>[Person/employee entered]</i> <i>Asan na ba tayo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Two days review. Wala bang kinalaman yung, sabi mo nga, 'more than ICU', yung mismong ginawa mo?</i>
239	Mr. Nursej	<i>In general? Mahihirapan talaga ako. Siguro kaya ko nasabing more than ICU, kasi nga hindi ako sanay sa self-review eh. Hindi ako sanay sa ganung klase na ako nagreview sa sarili ko. Kaya siguro nasabi ko rin na nahirapan ako dahil nga first time kong ginawa. Pero siguro 80% kaya ako nakapasa, ay dahil sa experience ko na, elementary, high school pa lang ganun na ako. Parang 'alam ko to', lumalabas na sa isip ko yung sagot.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung next question ko diyan ay "alam naman lahat natin na hindi lahat ng tao ay magaling, hindi lahat ng tao na matalino gaya mo, gaya ko, gaya natin. Let's say yung isang typical na graduate, syempre yung mga yan medyo may kaya, ganun, sa nursing maraming ganun 'di ba? Kung gagawin niya yung ganitong strategy, papano niya iaapproach 'to?</i>
240	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro, mahihirapan siya. Unang-una na, yung sa lifestyle nila. Kasi kung lifestyle mo from the start pa lang is meron kang resources, lahat binibigay sa'yo, tapos sabi mo biglang naging ganito yung strategy mo sa pag-aaral, mahihirapan ka.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kasi yun yung una kong ano eh, gusto kong idisprove na financial lang ang cause eh. Kasi meron din naman akong naging kakilala na, may kaya.</i>
241	Mr. Nursej	<i>(interrupts) financially capable</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>...financially capable but that person chose to self-review instead.</i>
242	Mr. Nursej	<i>Pero nakapasa siya?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, pumasa siya. Kumbaga given na yun eh, na meron talagang tao na dahil dun financially, pero merong iba na tulad ng iba na gustong may mapatunayan. At kung ganon man, let's say, ako galing ako sa maykayang pamilya, anong dapat kong gawin? Anything, yung advice na lang</i>
243	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro, kung meron ka naman, why not, huwag kang magfocus sa iisang option lang. Kung capable kang makapagreview center, why not? Gawin mo, pero yun nga, kailangan mo pa ring magself-review. Magbigay ka pa rin ng malaking panahon sa self-review mo. Kasi dun ka papasa, sa self-review, hindi sa review center.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nasa third part na tayo although most of these questions, tapos mo ng sagutin. Yung "strategies" actually, yung third part, third portion nito. Ireiterate ko na lang, yung sa Funda (Fundamentals of Nursing) na ginamit, ay sa notes mo pa rin? Natatandaan mo pa ba yung mga ganitong bagay, yung specifics, yung details?</i>
244	Mr. Nursej	<i>Gaya ng sinabi ko sa'yo...</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi, yung mismong strategy na lang? Hindi na mismong subject matter. Pano m na siya inapproach na lang? Kasi may question, syempre maraming nakalagay dun 'di ba, incorporated na lahat. Nung nagsasagot ka na sa mismong board exam na, papano mo iniliminate? Sabi mo kanina elimination ginamit mo.</i>
245	Mr. Nursej	<i>Syempre, nasa dalawa lang yung sagot eh. So sa apat na sagot, dalawa dun talagang malayo na sa tamang sagot. Lagi akong may tinitirang dalawa na possible correct answer for that particular question. Dun ko irarationalize yung stock knowledge ko, yung experience ko, dun ko siya pipiliin.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kapag may hindi ka ba siguradong sagot, hindi mo muna sinasagutan?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

246	Mr. Nursej	<i>Hindi, tuloy-tuloy ako. Kasi once na nagsagot ako, shade ka'gad eh. Wala akong second thought na ' baka mali ito, babalikan ko' wala. Yun parang dot dot muna, wala akong ganun. Tulog-tuloy yun, shade ako ng shade.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah ganun yung (style) mo. So masasabi mo ba sa sarili mo na yung educational program na you underwent for 4 years in college, ay nagpreprare ba sa'yo para maging isang nurse, at ikalawa nagpreprare ba sa'yo para makapasa sa board (exam), o meron ka bang naidentify na inadequacies? Objectively lang 'to ha, hindi dahil gusto mong siraan yung school. ano sa tingin mo yun?</i>
247	Mr. Nursej	<i>Subjectively?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Objective lang, kung meron man.</i>
248	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro yung school namin kasi, pinasok sa utak namin na yung school ng Pamantasan] is a public school, na gobyerno nagpaparal sa'min, taxes ng tao sa Pasig. Tumatak sa amin na ganun. So kailangan namin pagbutihan. Saka maganda yung turo sa Pamantasan]. Yung strategy nila.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ba yung strategy nila?</i>
249	Mr. Nursej	<i>May mga battery exam kami, every year.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ilan kayo nun?</i>
250	Mr. Nursej	<i>Two sections. From three sections naging two sections. So maganda yung foundation namin sa school. Okay lang na i(promote) ko sa ibang mag-aaral na dun mag-aral sa Pamantasan], okay lang. Wala akong nakitang conspiracy sa school.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Heto nabanggit mo na siya, na-touch mo na siya. In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what was your subjective take of your confidence level before the review, and after the review?</i>
251	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kung papasa ako sa board o hindi? Siguro 8. After the review, siguro 9 o 9.5. Taas na ng 8 e 'noh (exchanged smiles)? Parang pasado na rin eh no?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Heto, kung meron ka mang bagay na hindi mo nagawa, na dapat sana naisip mo na ginawa mo sana, na nakatulong sa review mo, sa results ng NLE (nursing licensure exam) mo, ano 'yun? Kung meron man.</i>
252	Mr. Nursej	<i>Siguro mas hinabaan ko yung time frame ko sa self-review. Kasi nga I only gave two days sa review ko eh, although I passed. Kasi nga, hindi ako satisfied sa score ko eh. Kumbaga, kung naglaan ko ng more time frame sa review ko, baka mas mataas yung nakuha ko.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Meron pala dito niyan eh, kasi ang balak ko ilalagay ko sa isang graph, yung location, yung public o private, kung ilang taon. Part yun ng presentation ko.</i></p> <p><i>Yung last na lang, gaya ng sabi ko kanina yung kay Orem ba yun, yung biopsychosocial and spiritual being. Maightify mo ba yung traits mo na nakatulong ng malaki, not just sa review, yung mismong sa sarili mo na mula nung high school ka until now, nagagamit mo pa..</i></p>
253	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Siguro yung traits ko is no...optimistic ako. Lahat ng ginagawa ko, alam ko magiging maganda yung outcome. If ever na pangit ang outcome, o hindi sa gusto ko yung naging outcome, sabi ko nga sa'yo may faith ako, so whatever happens, may purpose, kung ba't hindi ko nakuha yung gusto kong outcome. Pero prior to that, ang alam kong magiging outcome is kung ano yung gusto ko, pero syempre hindi lahat ng bagay nakukuha natin. Inaano ko na lang, para hindi ko maging regrets, parang sublimation na lang na hindi ko matawag na regrets 'to, iniisip ko na lang na yan gusto ni God.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Iniisip mo na lang na "will" ni God 'to?</i></p>
254	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Oo, hindi ko inisip na "kasi hindi ka nagreview eh, kung nagreview ka sana...(mas mataas)</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Pero meron bang instances na naiisip mo na 'sana tinodo ko pa'? Meron bang ganun?</i></p>
255	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Naramdaman ko yun nung hindi ko nakita yung pangalan ko sa top ten. Naramdaman ko na 'siguro kung mas nag(effort) pa ako, nasa top ten din ako.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Siguro ito na yung huling tanong ko: Ano bas a tingin mo yung nagkulang? Academically okay ka, pagdating sa strategies, matinik ang utak mo. Anong mga naidentify mo, sa tingin mo anong mga factors nung mga nagtatop?</i></p>
256	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Resources. Based sa experience ko, saka syempre yung ano...Sa batch namin dalawa yung naging Cum Laude eh. Classmate ko siya from first year talaga. Lahat meron siya eh, lahat ng kailangan mo sa pag-aaral meron siya. Books, computers; syempre kapag financially stable ka, parang healthy ka, parang factor na rin yun, tapos meron ka pang ganung talent. Siguro mas magiging maganda siguro talaga.</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p><i>Pero sa tingin mo ba kung ikaw naging ganun, mag-end up ka sa ganyan, kung ano ka ngayon?</i></p>
257	Mr. Nursej	<p><i>Panong ganun? Ah, siguro ganun nga. Tama ka rin, may point ka rin.</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yun nga rin inisip ko sa akin eh (exchanged laughter).</i>
258	Mr. Nursej	<i>Kasi kung meorn tayong resources, baka hindi tayo ganito. May point ka rin, tama yung way of thinking natin eh, yung logic. Siguro sabi siguro ni God, huwag ko na lang 'tong bigyan kasi mas maganda yung ganito. Nakatulong naman.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah yung huli ko na lang, gusto ko lang magpasalamat sa'yo at pinaunlakan mo. Actually, sobrang hirap ko rito, ang dami kong pinuntahan. Kumbaga kasi ang lahat ng ginawa ko, push lang ako ng push eh. Hindi ko alam nung una kung makakagraduate ako, tapos hindi ko alam na lang na nandito nap ala ako. Ang gusto ko maging doctor pero nandito ako sa field na 'to. It's a good thing that I have experienced interviewing you. Although ang mahalaga dun ay kung ano yung matututunan ng kung, ewan ko, kung meron mang babasa kahit isa man lang, na matuto 'di ba? (Smiling)</i>
259	Mr. Nursej	<i>Ako gusto ko kumuha ng kopya... Pero nga 'tol self-review ka?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, syempre.</i>
260	Mr. Nursej	<i>Panong self-review? Ano yung strategy mo?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mababasa mo na lang yan sa ano (result)---exchanged laughter</i>
261	Mr. Nursej	<i>Akala ko magiging boring...narefresh ako, nakwento ko sarili ko sa'yo, ngayon lang tayo nagkita. Approachable ka, easy to be with ka.</i>
		--END-- Time Stamp 1:44:00

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So good morning again my name is Neri Ocampo from St. Paul University Manila I'll be interviewing you about your self experience in self review. So just like what I explained earlier this will be divided into 4 parts: 1st part would be demographics and your background, 2nd would be for your experiences, 3rd is about your strategies, kung meron man, and lastly about some traits that you may have identified that have helped you, kung meron man, in during your review, so yung first question is demographics about your name, nickname kung optional lang</i>
1	Mr. NurseO	<i>So you're going to ask questions then?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yes, oo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

2	Mr. NurseO	<i>So name Mr. NurseO, nickname is Mr. NurseO</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mr. NurseO, ahh Mr. NurseO your age optional din siyempre</i>
3	Mr. NurseO	<i>22</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>22 yrs old ka lang. Nice supervisor ha, the year of graduation in BSN</i>
4	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh,2010</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2010 was it your first course or second course?</i>
5	Mr. NurseO	<i>Actually first course</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>First course, ngayon what is your current occupation</i>
6	Mr. NurseO	<i>I'm working as a supervisor as a team leader from other company and Teleperformance at Shaw Boulevard. I have been an employee for about 3 years na</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>3 years</i>
7	Mr. NurseO	<i>Almost 2 years for same post supervisor or supervisor level mag 2 years pa lang ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow considering your age tapos naging supervisor ka kagad</i>
8	Mr. NurseO	<i>First job</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>First job, ahh kailan ka nag take ng nursing board exam?</i>
9	Mr. NurseO	<i>That was July 2010</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>July 2010</i>
10	Mr. NurseO	<i>June or July 2010</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito optional lang may bracket siya, ahh yung licensure rating mo 75-79, or 80 and above</i>
11	Mr. NurseO	<i>75-79</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung school mo was it private or public?</i>
12	Mr. NurseO	<i>Private</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Private school, yung next questions ko is about yung knowing you as a person</i>
13	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ok,</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung if you tell me more about your upbringing kung yung beliefs mo about your life about your education, ahh kamusta ba yung background mo nung elementary, nung high school and what made you decide to take up nursing..</i>
14	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ok, first of I'm... my dream was to become a doctor actually that drove me to become a nurse but apparently being a physician or a doctor really needs brains and guts, siyempre wala naman ako masyado nun, so I just took up a course na in line with nursing kasi I believe nung bata pa ako na health is really one of the important things in life na pwede mong i- share or pwede mong gawin for others then hindi naman talaga ako... I'm not a responsible person technically I'm not a responsible person but through life when I was taking BSN course I learned the value of being a responsible person being a leader and siyempre mag step-up ka naman kahit papano, so ang daming naitulong sa akin nung course na BSN.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, so kamusta yung sa family mo nung maliit ka, pano ka how were you?</i>
15	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yon, my mom's dream was to become a doctor as well so I adopted that dream to become a physician but she decided to take up another course or another profession teaching, but still she is pursuing to be a PHD at least doctor pa din</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow</i>
16	Mr. NurseO	<i>She is working at La Salle, and I'm...tatlo kaming magkakapatid and then I'm the middle child. My brother is taking up Law at University of the East but I'm very lucky and blessed to have my little sister she is now taking BS Biology in Ateneo de Manila. She is going to pursue my failed dream of being a doctor.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Your mom's dream too.</i>
17	Mr. NurseO	<i>We were born and raised as Catholics. Elementary, high school, but when I entered college in Philippine Christian University which is Born Again, their religion is Born Again, so na convert ako dun. I'm now also a Born Again Christian but at the end of the day isa lang naman yung belief natin kasi one God lang naman so yun lang</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kamusta yung performance mo during your school years?</i>
18	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yon, school years ahh college I'am really a typical college student na natutulog, aaral konti, then barkada pero first and second year was very tough for me kasi I had a lot of vices ahh smoking and drinking but during the course of my stay in UniversityC since it's a born again Christian religion institution I stopped those vices yun nga naging maayos buhay ko non 3rd year, 4th year I stopped everything wala ng smoking wala ng drinking pero yun nga I tried to become a more responsible person though I am not really not into a leadership that's why nagulat nga din ako naging supervisor ako but definitely ang natutunan ko dun sa college na yon is siyempre you should not settle for something less. You always look up and beyond, laging mag go-goal ka ng mataas but definitely dapat feasible yung mga goals mo. They were training us, all of us, to become leaders future leaders that's why siguro naging ...though hindi ako ganon ka competitive nung college ako, siguro na adopt ko na lang sa environment na we were born to become leaders, born and trained to become a leader.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nice ha, pero during previous days before nung elementary kamusta yung ano mo panong...</i>
19	Mr. NurseO	<i>Wala, parang typical childhood lang papasok ka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung hobbies</i>
20	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh hobbies? Wala (smiles)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May computer ganon</i>
21	Mr. NurseO	<i>O sige, mga computer games, konting basketball ganon lang typical childhood lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung college, did you have any favorite subjects kung meron man?</i>
22	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh favorite subject, ahh kasi I'm the type of a person na more on memorization, I'm not good with analytical situation. I'm more of memorization, so ang favorite ko noon yung mga pure memorization anatomy, biology yon but what I really hate most is anything deals with math: chemistry, algebra yun mga ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Trigo</i>
23	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yun mga ganun, ayoko ng mga ganun, yun yung first ever</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Physio?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

24	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ayon anatomy, physiology, ahh yung all about math ahh yung pinaka first failing grade ko nung high school. Math lang yung 75 yon dahil sa Math hindi ko talaga siya gusto pero nung college more of memorization ako, more of definition of terms and ang pinaka isa ko pang pinaka forte ko as a student nurse nung college is Pharmacology.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pharma</i>
25	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, more of action nito, reaction and adverse effects, yung generic branding ng mga gamot yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>MS (Medical-Surgical Nursing) kamusta?</i>
26	Mr. NurseO	<i>MS, pwede na din MS siguro yun ang top 5 ko is Anatomy, Biology then MS, Pharma then pinakahuli na yung Psychology kasi medyo bagsak ako dun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Psychiatric</i>
27	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo Psychiatric Nursing</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit nga pala napasok ka ng UniversityC?</i>
28	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh that's a good question, actually late enrollee ako di ko din talaga alam kung anung school ang papasukan ko then yun nga sinamahan lang nila ako sa Manila kasi born and raised ako dito sa Cavite and I'm not really going outside of town so I didn't have any idea kung ano yung mga schools na papasukan then napunta lang kami sa UniversityC. Actually, when I took the entrance examination for BSN, I failed then we ended up, since the dean of Nursing and HRM was also the same and so we approach her what were my options then I realized na siguro kaya I failed kasi I'm not for nursing so I decided to take up HRM, but since parehas nga yung dean, the dean of BSN and HRM gave me the chance na pumasok as one of BSN students, kaso nandun ako sa pinaka last section.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So ang sabi sa akin ay grumaduate kayo konti na lang kayo</i>
29	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You came from the last section</i>
30	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ka... natira ka?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

31	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh dun sa last section actually composed of late enrollees and yung mga bumagsak talaga ng entrance exam. So pwede rin na late enrollee lang siya pero bright naman siya.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, okay</i>
32	Mr. NurseO	<i>So nakasama siya sa last section so yun ahh nag start kami ng 150 plus something 1st year then nag cut kami ng heads from 4 sections naging 3 sections na lang kami ng second semester so dun ko nakilala si Vincent ahh he was the one of the brightest students dun sa section namin so siyempre kung sino magiging barkada mo yun na din magiging reflection mo so nakita ko naman sa kanila yung eagerness na mag-aral naging competitive sila so siguro na adopt ko din yung pagiging competitive</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nakilala mo siya o naging kaklase mo siya?</i>
33	Mr. NurseO	<i>Classmate ko siya, dun ko din lang siya nakilala 1st year</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>2nd sem</i>
34	Mr. NurseO	<i>1st year first sem mag classmate na kami</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero last section kayo nun?</i>
35	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo yun nga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga</i>
36	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, baka yun nga late enrollee lang siya kaya siya napunta sa last section. It's either late enrollee ka or you really failed the qualifying examination</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, nung like circle of friends kayo ilan kayo, mga ilan kayo</i>
37	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh ilan kami siguro mga ahh si Vincent, ako, si Patrick and Jarred...siguro mga 5</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga 5 kayo si PeeJay di kasama?</i>
38	Mr. NurseO	<i>Hindi kasi he came from another batch, mas nauna siya sa akin .</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh oo nga pala, na kuwento niya, oo nga. Sa'yo, did you consider yourself as a people person or rather prefers alone sometimes depende kung...</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

39	Mr. NurseO	<i>I am not a people person I'd rather be praised in private kesa sa public, ayoko lang ng may issue ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, pero yung 5 na yon, okay naman kayo?</i>
40	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, we lasted, kami yung parang Starstruck na survivor . We survived UniversityC; buo kaming lima</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Buo kayong lima?</i>
41	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, tapos ako yung last</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero meron kayong kasama same sections dati na naano rin</i>
42	Mr. NurseO	<i>Na natsugi?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, hindi, hindi yung nakatapos din</i>
43	Mr. NurseO	<i>Meron lima lang kami, ay meron mga babae</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh mga babae, ahh yung section na ito, actually we just entered the second portion of it ahh experiences naman</i>
44	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh okay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>This is more about your insights; ahh yung views mo or opinions about self review what happened; not really the technical part yet kung ano inaral mo, yung experience lang as a whole</i>
45	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nung nag se-self review na ako?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, ito na yung part ng after you graduated</i>
46	Mr. NurseO	<i>Okay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ang haba niya no yung 4 years na yon, skip ko muna siya so I'll just like to focus on the experiences themselves after you graduated</i>
47	Mr. NurseO	<i>Okay</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh na identify mo what were the factor reasons, why you decided to...that influenced you to decide to self review?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

48	Mr. NurseO	<i>Actually ano siya eh, those were not really the factors, I didn't have a choice talaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You didn't have a choice</i>
49	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo kasi nung after graduation siyempre kasi taking up BSN is really pricy diba gastos tayo diyan and I'm not the only child who was studying at tertiary level so I have my brother and my younger sister. So after graduation, we were really on a tight budget ahh my daddy was expecting income after my graduation pero di siya lumabas. Kasi my dad was a CPA, may mga clients siya na hindi timely na magbayad</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
50	Mr. NurseO	<i>So I tried to ask assistance from my relatives abroad pero my recession ata nun sa US they were really in a tight budget so yun lang siyempre parang naawa ako sa sarili ko na...ang sabi ko yung mga classmates ko nag- eexam, ako nakatengga wala akong ginagawa. Sila nagre review, ako wala so parang ang baba ng morale ko non, sabi ko kahit anong trabaho na lang a applyan ko. Ang naisip ko nga kahit sa panaderya na lang nagbebenta ng bread para lang magkaroon ako ng income but then again siyempre another opportunity came after graduation 3 weeks lang ako nawalan ng ginagawa but within that 3 weeks I tried applying to different call centers. Ahh first attempt I failed, second attempt I failed, third attempt sa ibang company Teleperformance I passed so yun, para siyang naging sign sa akin na this is it siguro kung magkakaroon ako ng income and yet I'll have time to think about what I'm going to do dun sa incoming board exam pero after graduation tsaka kahit wala akong wala kaming means for review sabi ko naisip ko kung ano man yung natutunan ko nung 4 years ko siguro sapat na yon or it's really more than done enough kasi sobrang ganda ng training sa amin noon, so yon I started as an agent. Nung training namin I asked my mom to buy me a small pocket book, Nursing Review Guide. Parang questions then answer sa likod so while we were on training most of my team mates or wavemates during breaks or lunches gigimik sila o kaya mag yo-yosi ako naman I was sitting on one spot siguro sa canteen or sa pantry then I'm reviewing so yung handbook na yon sasagutan ko tas titingnan ko sa likod.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano kakapal ba yon?</i>
51	Mr. NurseO	<i>Manipis lang siya as in hand book lang siya siguro mga, ahh siguro mga 200 pages</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	200 pages
52	Mr. NurseO	<i>Maliit lang siya ganon so yun yung ginamit kong guide yung handbook na yon then pag-uwi sa bahay during my spare time or off during rest days aside from using the handbook I still have my previous notes nung college ako so bina browse ko siya pero sobrang hirap nya kasi hindi mo alam kung ano lalabas sa exam so you really on your own ako ang pinokus ko ahh MS yon more of MS yung pinokus ko so yun lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So nag-aral ka tuwing ano rin</i>
53	Mr. NurseO	<i>Brunner & Suddarths, oo yung MedSurg na libro</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Na libro mo dati nung college?</i>
54	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo dati nung college yun yung ginamit ko during idle momens instead of going out having fun ako nagreview ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo pero decided ka na mag take ng board exam?</i>
55	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo decided pero that time kasi yung mga ano ko yung mga classmates ko nagpupunta sa school, ay aside from that pala, before I went to work meron kaming sariling in house review parang siguro 1 week lang, 1 week lang sila parang give you updates share information so nag attend ako non 1 week then after nung 1 week I'm on my own na so yun kinuha ko lang yung lahat ng papers don ginamit ko sinama ko siya as guides kasama nung pocket book ko. Then yon ahh tapos sabi ko sa sarili ko hanggat hindi ako nakakapasa sa board exam wala akong right na makipag communicate o pumunta man lang dun sa school namin kasi siyempre nahihya ako eh, ako lang feeling ko ako lang yung hindi nagreview non feeling ko ako lang yung may chance na hindi pumasa kasi ako lang yung hindi nagreview and knowing na yung school namin is really one of the top schools in Manila yung bracket na lower bracket so yun medyo mababa nga yung steem ko non natatakot nga ako na baka ako yung maging ano, maging failing student nila so hindi ako nagpunta dun sa school na yon ako lang mag-isa no communication with anyone else of my classmates I'm really on my own ako lang talaga mag-isa.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung school mo sabi sa akin meron silang in house review center from EastWest nakipag ano sila another school...</i>
56	Mr. NurseO	<i>With Lyceum</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Lyceum, sabi sa akin, paano ka bigla ka na lang hindi nagpakita hindi ka pumunta ng academe?</i>
57	Mr. NurseO	<i>Hindi na lang ako nagpakita kasi nga I believe the tuition was P10-15,000 parang ganon so after nung in house namin nung 1 week ahh most of the student required to go back to school para mag enroll na with Lyceum students so yun, ako hindi ako bumalik nun, naghanap na ako ng trabaho non</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, pero normally may mga pinapipirmahan bago ka magboard exam yung mga paperworks na ahh from the dean</i>
58	Mr. NurseO	<i>Wala naman</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ginawa mo ba yon diba may mga ginagawa na completion ganon</i>
59	Mr. NurseO	<i>AhOo, oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo yung ginawa eh, o ginawa mo yon bago ka...</i>
60	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ginawa ko na yon bago, bago nag board exam pero ang sa pagkakaalala ko they were really not hindering anyone from taking the board exam yun ang sa pagkakaalala ko wala akong naalala na pinigilan ako ni dean na mag board exam kasi hindi ako nagrereview wala, wala akong maalala na ganon, so after the graduation na kompleto ko lahat ng requirements yung mga cases lahat.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>After ng graduation o before</i>
61	Mr. NurseO	<i>Before graduation kompleto ko na sa lahat</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh kompleto ka na non</i>
62	Mr. NurseO	<i>So magmamarcha ang kulang ko na lang magmamarcha na lang ako saka magte take na lang ako ng board exam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan ka bumalik ulit?</i>
63	Mr. NurseO	<i>After the news na pumasa ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Ahh okay</i>
64	Mr. NurseO	<i>Actually umiyak pa ako sa bus nun eh, sabi nila ano 100% tayo so I'm not sure kung kasama ba ako dun o hindi pero</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siyempre 100 eh</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

65	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo 100% eh pina search ko kagad kay mommy, check mo nga yung pangalan ko tas nandun yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kailan ka nagdecide na mag self review was that, I know what happened to your family sa... kailan yung</i>
66	Mr. NurseO	<i>Finances</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo finances, kailan yun nangyari after graduation or before graduation?</i>
67	Mr. NurseO	<i>After graduation, kasi I was really expecting na kasama ako dun sa review center</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh after, like how many weeks or days after graduation</i>
68	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yung buong 1 week na yon, yung after graduation mayron kaming in house, libreng in house review dun within that span of 1 week I heard the news from my dad na di daw niya ako kayang suportahan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, how did your parents or your family members react to your decision to self review, paano mo in approach yung parents mo, paano anong</i>
69	Mr. NurseO	<i>Kaya siguro ano na lang nila confident na lang sila na... kasi sa aming magkakapatid, I'm really the one who yung hindi masyadong ganon ka intellectual pero sa aming 3 magkakapatid siguro ang pinakamagandang trait na lang sa akin is kapag may nasimulan ako, gusto ko tatapusin ko siya so sobrang tiyaga ko, siguro naniwala sila na kaya ko naman, siguro its more of trust na lang and confidence from my parents, kung ano yung gusto mo sige yun na lang susuporta kasi wala naman silang magagawa diba</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero in approach mo sila na hindi na ako mag aano tutuloy na lang ako ng trabaho tapos</i>
70	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo in approach ko sila</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
71	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ang sabi naman nila kung yon naman daw yong sa tingin ko yung tama kung gawin then they just needed to support me whatever decision</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May kakilala ka bang nag ganon din katulad mo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

72	Mr. NurseO	<i>Wala nung during ng stay na yon kaya nga sabi ko baka ako yung maging</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ikaw lang</i>
73	Mr. NurseO	<i>Failing student, oo kung sakaling hindi ako pumasa</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like yung higher year, so yung ibang kakilala</i>
74	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh meron naman, meron</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh meron ka din</i>
75	Mr. NurseO	<i>Meron din, yun nga tama ka then may point din yon na ahh yung iba nga pumasa ng hindi nag aano eh, anung meron sila na wala ako siguro yung naging parang kapit sa patalim na lang ako non, sila nga nakapasa eh, we came from the same school naman so</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>The same school</i>
76	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, so kung ano man yung alam nila siguro alam ko naman din yun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Naging close kayo o paanong may communication ba kayo nung mga kakilala ano</i>
77	Mr. NurseO	<i>Communication siguro "hi hellos" and konting since senior sila konting tips ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito next question is about description</i>
78	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nasasagot ko ba yung mga tanong?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
79	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ang layo eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo nasagot mo, oo, what is it like yung over all experiences mo if you can put in one sentence or one phrase or anything that you think describing your experience..</i>
80	Mr. NurseO	<i>Over all experiences</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
81	Mr. NurseO	<i>Dun sa self review and dun sa pag passed ko? Siguro ano "Hard work beats talent when talent does not work hard. Hardwork beats Talent.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Beats talent</i>
82	Mr. NurseO	<i>When Talent does not work hard.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hahaha nice!</i>
83	Mr. NurseO	<i>Kasi may mga matatalino naman dyan e na siguro puro yabang lang nag cling na lang sa katalinuhan nila siyempre you should not only be reliant with your own wisdom eh kasi kailangan mo din yung magpursige</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Magpursige</i>
84	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, hard work lang talaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano ba katagal yung review mo?</i>
85	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah, e time line ko lang ha: you graduated April diba</i>
86	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo April</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Then July ka nag take then after 3 weeks, 3 weeks after April nag ka work ka na</i>
87	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tapos dun ka nagrereview sa let's say caffè teria o dun sa ano ninyo pantry ganon</i>
88	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hanggang kailan yon?</i>
89	Mr. NurseO	<i>Hanggang the night before the board exam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>The night before board exam?</i>
90	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ay hindi 2 days before board exam, kasi binigyan ko naman ng time na mag rest ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
91	Mr. NurseO	<i>And actually ang pinaka challenging galing ako sa shift from closing 3-12 ang shift ko non so I ask my previous supervisor na baka pwede naman gawin akong opening from 10 ay I mean 9, ay hindi 8-5 para makahabol ako sa exam so nag shift ako ng 2 araw 8pm-5am ako</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>lang mag-isa kasi my teammates have a different shift which is 3-12 so ang baon baon ko lang noon 8-5 ba yon is Extrajoss and paracetamol para di sumakit ulo ko, galing ako shift non</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nagtake ka?</i>
92	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo so puyat pa ako non</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka man lang pinayagan man ahh kasi</i>
93	Mr. NurseO	<i>Bago pa lang ako</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pro-b ka pa lang, ahh okay</i>
94	Mr. NurseO	<i>Buti pinayagan ako mag shift slide or mag change ng shift ang katawan ko is extrajoss at paracetamol para di ako makatulog at tyaka hindi sumakit ang ulo ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paano mo ginawa yung ano ahh, minsan nasa pantry ka tapos pag off mo ganon pero yung distribution nung ano na yon yung pagrereview mo meron bang pagkakataon na humaba na o malapit na yung exam ahh kasi sa span of time mo na nag de devote ka dun sa subjects or ganon pa rin all through out</i>
95	Mr. NurseO	<i>Hindi ahh nung malapit na yung exam medyo dinadagdagan ko na yung pagrereview before kasi during sa break, lunches saka uwian pero nung magbo board exam na siya bago ako pumasok habang kumakain ako breakfast during breakfast nagrereview na ako sa biyahe nag rereview ako non</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Mga gaano katagal bago mag board exam ninyo? Gaano katagal ilang weeks pa o days bago yung</i>
96	Mr. NurseO	<i>1 week before the review nagdagdag ako ng ano ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>1 week before the exam</i>
97	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo the exam pala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>The exam, so napag-usapan yung trabaho ganon, did you encounter any challenges or issues na nagrereview ka or prior to your review, during the review</i>
98	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh siyempre challenges ahh wala akong sariling syllabus or pattern kung ano yung lalabas sa exam its rely more on feelings ko na lang kung ano yung lalabas na ahh baka ito, baka ito ganon yung challenges kasi hindi ko alam point black talaga siya hindi ko alam</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>kung ano yung I fa-follow kong steps basta ako ang ginawa ko nagsimula ako basics hanggang dun sa so nagsimula ako ng first year kung ano meron sa first year anatomy, physiology then fundamentals</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ganon yung approach mo</i>
99	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ganon from first year to fourth year kasi wala akong idea talaga eh then isa pang challenge yung siyempre yung work environment taking calls is different, is really away from nursing eh so yun tapos nalaman nga ng mga teammates ko na mag bo-board exam ako so pressured yon kasi tinutukso nila ako baka ikaw lang yung hindi pumasa kasi andito ka sila nagreview mga pressure na ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay and in connection with that, were you at any point during the, your review ahh tempted to quit or at least man lang naisip mo na lang sana nagreview na lang ako sana wala na lang itong nagkaron ako ng pera ganon, ahh</i>
100	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro yung bitterness ng walang pera pero yung idea na mag quit never basta ako nag start ako ng isang bagay gusto ko yung tatapusin ko siya whatever the outcome may be andun na ako and parang yung decision kasi na yon ano yung parang ang daming naka cling dun sa decision na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Paanong</i>
101	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh paanong masasabi yon, ibig mong sabihin nung sinabi ko sa parents ko na I'll be taking the board exam so siyempre yung buong trust nila kung бага nakakapit na sa akin so I let them down I let myself down them kung nag quit ako in the middle of the battle</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung feeling na yon na buo na naging loob mo yung malapit na ba yung nasa kalagitnaan o nung una pa lang ganon na talaga</i>
102	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nung una pa lang decided na ako ahh ayoko mahuli, gusto ko sabay sabay kaming nag graduate sabay sabay kaming magiging nurses.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you feel about the outcome of your review, ahh in terms of siguro yung satisfaction may okay ba sayo yung pakiramdam na experience mong yon</i>
103	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh siyempre that was big challenge talaga so nag boost naman yung self steem ko after parang stand straight taas noo yabang parang ganon ay kaya ko naman pala eh parang ganon</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>O sige tanong ko na lang muna yong span of time na after mong mag review siyempre hindi mo alam kung paano diba</i>
104	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh oo, that was the very crucial part, it is the waiting that kills talaga eh hindi ko talaga alam I was clueless ang ginawa ko lang siyempre everyday prayers para lumakas yung loob tapos ginawa kong busy yung sarili ko sa pagtrabaho oo kasi I don't want to think the result of the board exam pa siyempre nandun din yung second thoughts na bakit ko sinagutan 'to bakit ganun yung sagot ko dito parang nagkakaroon ka ng realization yung parang nag fa-flashback lahat ng sinagot mo dun sa board exam kasi maaalala mo yung ibang questions dun eh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay</i>
105	Mr. NurseO	<i>Bakit ganito yung sinagot ko bakit hindi letter B ba't hindi letter A</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero tumitingin ka na sa parang key ganon, na yung tama talaga</i>
106	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ay, hindi parang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nasa isip mo na</i>
107	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nasa isip ko lang talaga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung may masasabi ka what did you think are the advantages or disadvantages of a self review?</i>
108	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siyempre ang advantages it's cost effective wala ka naman gagastusin diba ahh isa pang advantages nun is siyempre you learn to trust yourself, yung trust sa sarili mo, saka yung trust ni God siyempre ganun, ahh actually konti lang talaga yung advantages niya, siyempre for disadvantages ahh yun nga wala kang wala kang guide kung ano yung lalabas sa exam wala ka din assurance na you're going to pass the exam tapos yung pressure from the environment is there kasi they are really expecting you would be the one of the failing student or failing person kasi hindi ka naman nag review center so ganun yung thinking ng society if you did to review if not have enough support from the review center babagsak ka parang ganun yung thinking ko so yung pressure talagang nandon saka ano pa bang disadvantages dun siyempre yung fears</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siyempre yung updates yon sa board exam ahh sa review center may binibigay silang tips</i>
109	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yun nga ako wala yun nga yung sinasabi ko na</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo pinunan yon o hinayaan mo lang o papano</i>
110	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yun nga ang ginawa ko don hindi naman sila nagbibigay ng updates sabi ko wala akong communication sa classmates ko so I really started from the basic foundation of nursing kung ano man yung natutunan ko nung 1st year nag start ako hinalungkat ko lahat ng luma kong notes so ginawa ko lahat so nag start ako dun</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh mula nung ano</i>
111	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo pero nag focus ako nung 3rd year, 4th year mga duties, major ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito na yong after you passed what was it o dun may nasabi ka na rin kanina what was the effect of your experience to you as a individual or as a nurse?</i>
112	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siyempre ahh na boost yung self confidence ko then yung pangako ko sa sarili ko na hindi ako papasok ng school hindi ako babalik ng school hindi ako pumapasa so when I passed the board exam siyempre ang yabang ko na non so nag</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Na</i>
113	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nag high hello pasado ako then pinagmalaki ko sa kanila with all of my relatives and friends kung ano yung achieve, kasi naman sa akin ang achievements ko no hindi ka nag board exam tapos pumasa ka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi ka nag review center</i>
114	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yun, hindi ka nagreview center pala then yun my parents was very proud dun ko sila nakita na sobrang proud sa akin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Panong reception sa inyo?</i>
115	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yon yun nga sila yung nagyayabang sa co workers nila sa relatives namin tapos yung tarpaulin nagpagawa sila ng isang malaking tarpaulin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Talaga sa inyo?</i>
116	Mr. NurseO	<i>Sa bahay namin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wow</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

117	Mr. NurseO	<i>Tapos dun sa high school na pinag high school-lan ko, may tarpaulin din don sobrang laki yun, sobrang proud talaga sila</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nun medyo okay na finances ninyo</i>
118	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, okay na siya, bali nag late payment lang talaga yung isang client</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, oo nakuha ko na, wow talagang pinagawan ka pa ng ano</i>
119	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo tarpaulin ng parents ko sobrang proud nila dun nga sa school nakaka "hi" na ako dun sa dean namin sa mga teachers sa mga get together ng mga reunions nakakapunta na ako kasi may pagmamalaki na ako ba't nurse din naman ako ha, proud din yung mga classmates ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Siyempre lahat kayo, tsaka 100% din ng class ninyo ng school ninyo diba</i>
120	Mr. NurseO	<i>Dun ko din pala nalaman na mayron din palang hindi din pala nagreview, sila Vincent dun lang kami nagusap-usap</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yah ang tingin ko talagang anu yan dahil considering the like yung rating ngayon like 30+% lang, so thousands really failed, ikaw pumasa ka.</i>
121	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ganun.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito na yung 3rd part nung ano about strategies so ito yung technical na, more on what did you do, yung mga details since the purpose of this is to inform others, kung ano mang may mai-she-share tayo o ikaw so tingin mo what made it effective for you or how did you do it ahh naging effective sayo, kung meron ka mang mai-she-share about it</i>
122	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh so sa technical na tayo no?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
123	Mr. NurseO	<i>So yun ahh, gaya nga na sinasabi ko kanina nag start ako from the very foundation of nursing subjects from 1st year bin-browse so I started with anatomy, fundamentals of nursing, then pataas siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay</i>
124	Mr. NurseO	<i>Then my focus more of yung mga higher level of subject such as med surges and nakalimutan ko basta med surg siya</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Psyche or pharma so yun yung mga approach mo</i>
125	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo, from the basic foundations sa mga medyo technicalies</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you spend your time frame mo paano let say mahaba itong subject na ito binigyan ako ng time or pare pareho sila</i>
126	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahm ang pinaka pinagtuunan ko ng pansin yung mga subjects ng 3rd year and 4th year, yun nga yung mga pharmacology, med surgs, ahh phychiatric nursing kasi dun sa mga examination namin sa school more of analytical talaga so bihira lang yung definition of terms, it's more of in-analyze mo yung situations yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano ka ba mag analyze ahh, papano yung naging approach mo dun sa analysis na yon</i>
127	Mr. NurseO	<i>Meron akong natutunan sa ano isang research presentation dun sa amin, how we're going to pass the board exam, dun lang din yun sa college namin, so ang ginamit kong "umbrella effect" ang tawag nila sanbeda, so my choices tayo diba a,b,c,d meron dun laging 2 or 3 choices na almost the same lang yung idea so siyempre kung almost the same lang yung idea i-eliminate mo yung 3 pipiliin mo yung pinaka unique dun sa 3, so yun yong tinatawag na "umbrella effect"</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo na cancel out o na eliminate yung 2 dun sa 3 na yon?</i>
128	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh, siyempre it will depend naman dun sa question, so talagang i-analyze mo yung question let's say for example ang situation is more of ahh bed side nursing, siyempre I eliminate mo yung bed side nursing kunyari ahh health education kasi post operation na yun eh, or education or teaching the client to ambulate mga ganung stuff, so it will really depend on dun sa topic and dun questions</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Gaano naging kahalaga yung prior knowledge mo dun o inaral mo dun sa pagsagot mo dun sa may analytical questions na yon</i>
129	Mr. NurseO	<i>Paano siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh yung naging role yung previous knowledge yung prior knowledge mo dun sa mga topic na yon para, more on logic lang ba siya o parang kailangan mo pa ng prior knowledge?</i>
130	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siyempre kailangan yung base on facts talaga hindi lang siya puro logic kasi yung logic anu lang yong puro support support lang ng way ng pag a-answer siyempre yung pinakamalaking role dun yung facts, science lahat nung previous knowledge yun yung naging kailangan</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>mo talaga when your taking any exam naman eh kailangan knowledgeable ka</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So sabi mo kanina gusto mo yung mga memorization those like yung mga pharma, papano mo ini store yun sa utak mo, papano siya tatandaan?</i>
131	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh I create my own ahh ...kasi I believe in the power of writing so gumagawa ako ng sarili kong reviewer, so nagsusulat ako ng questions then yung answer</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Reviewer sa nung nag self review ka na ba ito o dun pa din nung nasa school ka pa?</i>
132	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nung nasa school ako then nadala ko na din siya nung nag rereview ako gumagawa ako ng sarili kong reviewer so I'll take time to write down yung mga important things gagawin ko yon questions, answer, questions, answer siguro magkakaroon ako ng mga 5 pages na yellow pad or 5 bond papers, siyempre habang nagsusulat ka nagmememorize mo yung sagot then kapag I rundown mo uli siya almost perfect na yung sagot mo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Question, answer yung like typical literal na questions o gumagawa ka ng papanong questions- answer?</i>
133	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh, its either galing siya sa notes ko mga definitions of terms sa notes ko kunyari what is cell or</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Angina what is ganito</i>
134	Mr. NurseO	<i>What is angina ganyan mga ganon, lalagay ko yon tapos kung ano pa mare-recall ng isip ko lalagay ko don then sasabayan ko ng yung sa pocket book ko yung maliit na reviewer isasabay ko siya don</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
135	Mr. NurseO	<i>Isusulat ko din para mabilis kong ma memorize o maalala kung ano yung sagot</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sa isang subject like sa 5 pages</i>
136	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung isang subject ay itinuturo sa isang sem papanong mo siya, anong nilalagay mo dun in order priority mo papano mo siya pinipili na yun lang ilalagay mo</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

137	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yun yong medyo crucial kasi tama ka dun kasi in 1 sem sobrang dami</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Sobrang dami talaga diba</i>
138	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro sa akin na lang as a student ahh parang ano na yan eh parang sa experience mo lang as a student na parang you get to know kung ano yung mga important details na kailangan mo isulat isa pa ahh dun sa mga notebook ko may mga special notes dun siguro is either inlighted in red or with other ink so iyon ang isusulat ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh, yung notes mo nung college</i>
139	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo college may mga anu don extra notations so yun yung dinadagdag ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>May mga libro ka naman nung college ka?</i>
140	Mr. NurseO	<i>Dalawa lang yung book 1 and book 2 ng Med Surges</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah Suddarths?</i>
141	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo saka isang Udan handbook</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ah hindi ka bumili ng iba talaga?</i>
142	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yung pocketbook ko na maliit</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh after you had your review did you have doubt in failing the exam, yung confidence level mo 10 is the highest level 1 is the lowest anu yun, kung madi- describe mo lang</i>
143	Mr. NurseO	<i>Madi-describe ko siguro</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I mean kung hindi ka pumasa ha, honest assestment mo sa sarili mo na hindi ka palang pumapasa, naghahantay ka pa lang ng ano</i>
144	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro 50-50, 5,5 kasi siyempre I was clinging on my basic knowledge na lang kung ano yung natutunan ko dun sa school parang naisip 4 years ako nag-aral oh 4 years na gumasta yung parents ko imposibleng wala naman ako natutunan dyan or posibleng hindi naman nadaanan ito nung college ako aside from that siyempre yun nga the power of prayer na lang siguro yun na lang din yung nagbigay sa akin ng hope my own knowledge tsaka coming from above</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nung nagaantay ka ng rating may naisip ka ba nung ay mali na yung nasagot ko</i>
145	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yung mga ganon kasi..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Confirm mo na, na mali yung sagot mo</i>
146	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh nung ano yung kasi..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Hindi mo muna inisip yon</i>
147	Mr. NurseO	<i>Hindi kasi diba pagka sa ano ahh sa board exam ang kasama mo palagi yung malapit apelyido mo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo malapit</i>
148	Mr. NurseO	<i>Sa O, ako O ako Orbe ako so may classmate din ako kasama ko dun sa ano sa event sa venue ng board exam so pinag-uusapan namin mga sagot namin, ay oo nga no dapat nga pala yun yung sagot ko so yun pag nabigay sila ng rationale tas pag naisip mo ay oo nga tama yon dun ko lang dapat co-compare</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So yung mga panahon na yon naisip mo na, na 50-50 pa rin</i>
149	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo 50-50</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ay ito walang tumulong sa iyo no kahit mag-isa ka lang talaga, okay may job may work ka at, ahh siyempre hindi biro yun so how did you manage your time, yung how did you deal with time constraints ahh gaano ka kahaba nag-aaral let say sinasabi mo nasa breakfast o ano ahh yung time frame mo meron ka bang relaxation techniques o papano</i>
150	Mr. NurseO	<i>So yung pinaka relaxation ko na lang yung tulog na lang</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Tulog na lang</i>
151	Mr. NurseO	<i>Basta ako kung may libreng oras as much as possible nakaupo ako nagbabasa ganon I really devoted most of my idle moments reading or reviewing</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay, so yung next ko sayo yung study habits yung time of day, ahh ka nag-aaral and why</i>
152	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh sabi daw nila kasi base on statistics on research hindi ko maalala sa Reader's digest ko o nabasa yon sabi nila pagka fresh mag start ka ng pagkagising mo kasi parang sponge pa daw yung brain mo nun eh</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>pagkagising mo sa umaga or basta pagkagising na pagkagising mo ahh very absorbent yung brain mo non so I really starting my review my study everytime I wake up in the morning ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Pero pang gabi ka non diba so like hapon ka na</i>
153	Mr. NurseO	<i>So ganon parang binaliktad ko lang pagising ko galing ng pahinga</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay, okay</i>
154	Mr. NurseO	<i>Yun na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo kasi in between then pati din yung kapag nagla-lunch ka papanong ano</i>
155	Mr. NurseO	<i>Pagka sa yun yong pinaka primary ko everytime I wake up start na kagad yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Like how long</i>
156	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro an hour or 2</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>An hour</i>
157	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo tapos paka during breaks and lunches yun review uli ako 15 minutes, 30 minutes after kong kumain review then pagka-uwi ahh I spend 1-2 hours bago matulog</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So 1-2 hours bago matulog</i>
158	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo kasi kailangan ko rin siyempre kasi papasok na naman ako kinabukasan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo siyempre, trainee ka pa rin non</i>
159	Mr. NurseO	<i>Nag te-training pa ako non</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Saan maliban doon sa pantry, sa bahay saan ka nag-aaral?</i>
160	Mr. NurseO	<i>Sa study table basta sa something na tahimik lang saka maganda yung lighting tsaka ng yung ventilation maganda rin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh ventilation</i>
161	Mr. NurseO	<i>Para yung brain mo makaka function siya ng...maayos</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ito medyo ano na ito ahh... if you can pwede mo ba makuwento kung papano yung educational program sa inyo anong papanong nakatulong iyon sa pag-aaral ahh sa review mo let's say ano bang..</i>
162	Mr. NurseO	<i>Training sa amin</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo feedback ninyo sa masasabi halimbawa I don't know the school hindi ko din talaga alam eh papano mo siya madi-describe?</i>
163	Mr. NurseO	<i>Sa amin kasi its really more on hands on kami as in kami yung ahh kapag nasa hospital kami homebase hospital yung mga staff nurse dun pag dun na kami wala na silang ginagawa kami na yung nagbibigay ng gamot siyempre with the supervisions of our CI, magbigay ng gamot ahh charting tapos mga doctors order kami na yung nag ke-carry out kapag nandyan na yung doctor kami yung nakikipag-usap more on hands on talaga so yon yun yung training namin siguro naging equipped ako ahh dun sa pag bo-board exam and then aside from that ahh weekly kami nag ke-case presentation, case study case presentation tapos yung examination namin ahh everyday din yon, after duty mag e-exam pa kami then during Saturdays may extra, extra subject pa ako dun sa mga hindi ganon kagaling na students yung mga nakakakuha ng 3 may tawag sila make up duty volunteer work ang tawag nila don volunteer pero you are forced..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
164	Mr. NurseO	<i>To attend ahh so yun part ako non kasi hindi ganon kaganda grades ko nung college so lagi ako nasa volunteer work so magduduty ako imbis na umuwi ng bahay nasa hospital ako, taking 4 hours of duty helping yung mga staff nurses on the other hand natututo na din ako extra time ko para makapag reflect.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay. when you were reviewing after the in your education after 4 years education nagrereview ka ba papanong nare-relate mo ba yong binabasa mo dun sa ginagawa ninyo sa duty o tsaka yung late ka na during the examination selfnung sa board exam, papanong... anong naging role sayo ng pag-aaral mo?</i>
165	Mr. NurseO	<i>Kasi yung sa amin sa UniversityC binigigay nila yung 2 sides of reality: yung una yung hospital base dito sa Philippines kung ano yung practice and kung versus practice in America so alam mo yung standards saka alam mo kung papano ka magiging flexible kasi ang iniisip nila siyempre pag nagbibigay sila ng board exam kung ano yung pinapractice dito sa Philippines.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	Oo
166	Mr. NurseO	<i>And some of the same time may practice din sa yung as a whole yun ang pinaka standards of nursing practice, so yun I get to know the 2 faces of nursing field or nursing practice yung siyempre dito sa Pilipinas ahh kulang tayo sa kagamitan kulang tayo sa technologies so tinuturo din sa amin paano ka mag-a-adjust dun papano din kung walang ambubag anong gagamitin mo siyempre pwede ka ng mag paper bag na lang pag nag hyperventilate kapagka walang defibrilator anong pwede mong gawin? Siyempre at the same time kung meron ka nung mga gamit papanong magre-respond dun sa mga gamit na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So let's say isang subject MS gaano mo siya katagal na inaral</i>
167	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro mga 60% nung pagrereview ko focus ako ng MS</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	MS
168	Mr. NurseO	Oo 60%
Researcher:	Researcher	So around
169	Mr. NurseO	40
Researcher:	Researcher	To 1 month ganon
170	Mr. NurseO	Oo ganon, tas pasundot sundot na lang ng..
Researcher:	Researcher	Iba
171	Mr. NurseO	<i>Iba kung ano yung maalala ko baka feeling ko masasama sa board exam</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Papano mo siya inaral as in per subject o yung pasundot sundot iba-iba</i>
172	Mr. NurseO	<i>Per subject siya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh per subject binabalikan mo ba yung subject na yun kapag merong kang tingin mo nakalimutan ka</i>
173	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo parang ganon, parang diba ang MS para din magstart ka sa basics o kaya muscular skeletal syatem, yung 11 system papano ba 11 ba</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Oo

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

174	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo yon mag start ka muna don kung anu yung pinaka basics hanggang don lang sa pinaka medyo complicated na per system ang pag-aaral ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh oo, nag te-test questions answer ka yun ba sa like at the end of your review for that subject ganon</i>
175	Mr. NurseO	<i>Dun na lang bini-base ko na lang sa handbook</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung handbook mo</i>
176	Mr. NurseO	<i>Tinitingnan ko na lang sa likod kung tama yung sagot</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
177	Mr. NurseO	<i>Pag mali sagot ko I'll dig deeper bakit mali yung sagot ko kung bakit ito yung sagot na tama</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh</i>
178	Mr. NurseO	<i>A, B, C, D ahh anu yung kunyari for emergency anu yung pinaka primary intervention eh breathing or circulation kunyari ang sinagot ko circulation kasi tatanga tanga kasi</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo</i>
179	Mr. NurseO	<i>I di-dig deeper ko bakit airway yung summary ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Bakit airway ahh ganon</i>
180	Mr. NurseO	<i>Lalo't pag mali ako, kasi I have the feeling nung sinasagot ko siya na confident ako tama yung sagot ko na yon eh, ayon so parang gina judge ko yung book mali itong book na ito so kailangan kong hanapin yung reason na mag re-reason out tatama talaga yung book na yon, yun dun ako nagkakamali lagi naman ako mali hindi naman yun yung author ng book</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Nag che-check ka rin ba sa ibang libro o yun lang</i>
181	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo sa ibang libro yun nga pag nag i-imbistigate na ako lalo pag mali yung sagot ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>So in a way papano na yung exam na, nakatulong ba yon</i>
182	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Yung style mo yung strategy mo nung nag-e-exam ka na</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

183	Mr. NurseO	<i>Some, siyempre nakatulong siya, yung knowledge mo nadadagdagan kasi parang yung type ng questions nung nagreview ako parang nandun din siya sa board exam yung type din ng questions din nandon its more of multiple choice bibigyan ka nila ng almost the same answer so kailangan ano yung priority mo dun sa answer na yon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh kung mayroon kang let's say last two questions for this section kung meron kang bagay na na identify na sana ginawa mo na hindi mo nagawa noon let's say its like looking back or was there anything that you could have done that may have you improved yung ano mo ginawa mo</i>
184	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ayon siguro ah</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Meron ka ba non?</i>
185	Mr. NurseO	<i>Meron nga kasi nung board exam more of community based yung nakita ko so hindi ako masyadong nakapag focus dun nung nakita ko yung board rating ang pinakamababa ko community tas nagkaroon na lang ako ng realization ah Philippines rating ang ibibigay nila ah much as possible Philippines rating then parang nurses kasi is really designated to community, promoting health, ah preventing further disease so yun di ko na fo-focus maigi yung community kaya mababa sana nag focus ako sa community nurse</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ahh okay actually yung part nung yung second question ko kung satisfied ka ba dun sa result ng exam mo at kung meron kang na identify na factors or reasons that you can attribute that satisfaction</i>
186	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siguro ako satisfy ako in a way nal pass pero siguro naisip ko I can do better kung tama lang yung way ng pagreview ko kung may mga ganitong research parang maibibigay sa mga nurses or future nurses ng guide para makapag self review siguro kung may ganitong research noon pa may guide ako mas mataas yung nakuha kong grade imbes na 76 siguro mga 80 ganyan kasi yung score ko na 76 is almost failing na din yun diba</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo, oo ah kung ako graduate nurse di pa ako nag te-take ng exam and then I'm very willing na desidido ako na mag self review meron ka bang kung meron kang bagay na gusto mong mai-share sa akin ngayon... like what should I do ah konting summary lang saan ba ako dapat mag focus</i>
187	Mr. NurseO	<i>Ahh yun nga sa akin kasi nung after board exam nung nakita ko yung resulta kung saan ako mababa community I tried to ask several</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>seniors kung ano yung type nung examination nila ganun din yung sinasabi nila more of community base nursing nga then medyo mas madami yung community so siguro kung ikaw yung graduate nurse ako nurse na sabihin ko focus on Philippines setting, community ganyan</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Ayun yung mga ano mo</i>
188	Mr. NurseO	<i>Oo</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Okay last part na ilang questions na lang ito sige hanggang dito na lang this is the last part of the interview it's about yung traits kung meron man ahh nakatulong sa iyon tingin mo ahh dun sa ginawa mong review, what, if there were any, what do you think would be important qualities that you posses in taking pass the exam</i>
189	Mr. NurseO	<i>"Determination" siyempre from the very start parang naka goal set na ako na kailangan pumasa ako ng board exam kailangang di ako mahiwalay ahh "perseverance" ahh naisip ko na nalaman ko na may nurses din na pumasa na nag self review so naisip ko kung ano man yung meron sila malamang meron din ako non so siyempre "hard work" it really boils down to hardwork kasi kung wala ka naman maatim kung parang wala namang bagay na madaling abutin eh lahat talaga pinaghihirapan ayun yung three factors ko</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any regrets?</i>
190	Mr. NurseO	<i>Wala</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Wala</i>
191	Mr. NurseO	<i>Regrets lang siguro I can do better kung may guidelines nga talaga akong sinusunod pero as far as reviewing ahh with my ano decision na mag self reviewer wala akong..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>My last question is about, how did it affect you psychologically, mentally and emotionally overall</i>
192	Mr. NurseO	<i>Siyempre after pumasa ito na yung ano ahh</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Oo yahh, looking back</i>
193	Mr. NurseO	<i>Na boost lahat psychologically kasi I prove them wrong ahh kaya ko kaya ko pala; mentally I prove na kaya din ng utak ko kaya ko as a person, and emotionally siyempre I prove to my parents na tama yung naging decision nila na pagtiwalaan ako lahat talaga siya nag</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>improve na boost talaga siguro that's also the result of what I am right now I mean confident ako, lumakas yung loob tumapang parang ganon</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Kung hindi ka nag... kung nagreview center ka meron bang pinagkaiba? Let's say you passed the board exam with same with the review center then compared to what you are now; do you think my difference ba?</i>
194	Mr. NurseO	<i>May difference parang kasi sa pag ikaw lang sa sarili mo proud ka na nagawa ko ito ng ako lang ahh though ang daming obstacles nakaya ko na mag-isa compared sa nagreview, hindi naman sa yumayabang lang ako ha, pero parang naisip ko na 'oh..pumasa ka lang dahil nagreview center ka, binigyan ka lang ng guide eh ang dami ninyo kasing tinuro eh' ako parang I passed this on my own, siyempre with the help of God</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>You value yung spiritual. Okay thank you very much, that concludes my interview. One hour and 2 minutes. Thank you so much for your time.</i>
		--END-- Time Stamp 1:02:00

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Briefly narrate who you are as a person. If possible, kindly tell us a little more about your upbringing, your main beliefs about life and education, or anything that you value as a person, and the story why you took up nursing.</i>
1	Ms. NurseK	<i>Cliché as it may sound but I try to live my life to the fullest. Nowadays I am fond of traveling as I get to experience new culture and just escape from normal routine. Family is very important to me and I am very close to my mother who I treat as one of my close friends and travel buddy as well. I see each day as an opportunity to grow and to learn. I am thankful that I was given the chance by my parents to have a good education. I take my studies seriously and I try my best to go beyond the average to get good grades and be on top. I love my parents so much that I took up nursing because of them. Honestly, it was their choice that I take up this course. I wanted to</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>take up Computer Science or Mass Communication. The thought of hospitals, blood and needles used to scare me but I think it was my destiny to take up this course because of the life lessons I learned both in and out of the classroom.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Overall, how did you fair in your studies? What was your class standing during school years (in elementary, high school and/or in college)? What was your class like?</i>
2	Ms. NurseK	<i>I believe that I did fairly well in my studies. During elementary, I was always part of the honor roll and in high school I graduated as valedictorian. In college, I also managed to become a semestral dean's lister. Also, I was active in extracurricular activities as I used to join quiz bees and was part of the school publication as editor-in-chief.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were anything, what were (was) your favorite subject/s back then, & why?</i>
3	Ms. NurseK	<i>I actually have two favorite subjects: English and Computer. In our English subjects, I truly enjoyed writing and doing roleplaying. Meanwhile, in our Computer class, I was very excited to tinker around with computer programs and learn more about software.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone?</i>
4	Ms. NurseK	<i>Before I would consider myself as a loner but as I grew older, I became more of a people person. I think it's because I have gained confidence in myself and my capabilities as opposed to my shy and meek demeanor in the past.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What were the factors/reasons that influenced you to decide to take self-review? (i.e. possible personal reasons, individuals and/or situations that might have influenced you)</i>
5	Ms. NurseK	<i>1. Study habit – I believe that I can study harder if I am alone. I get distracted easily and do not find studying in an auditorium full of people conducive to learning. 2. Budget – Enrolling in a review center can be very expensive. Why put my parents the burden of additional expenses when there is no guarantee that I will pass if I enroll in a review center? In the end, it is me who will take the exam so I control my own destiny. 3. Convenience – I wanted to study at my own pace so self-review was very convenient for me. If I will get too tired, I can just sleep to refresh</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>my mind for another day of learning. It is unlike review centers where there are times that one can't concentrate because of information overload.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school? Or were you required to attend the review center? If there was, how did you go about it?(If yes, please explain what happened)</i>
6	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, our school endorsed ReviewCenterG and we were required to attend the review session held every weekend in the auditorium during our senior year in college. It was helpful but honestly, sometimes I would not attend or leave early because I wanted to go home as I was living in a dorm before. At times, I felt that it was a burden to me since I wanted to study at my own pace. After graduation, our school also had another in-house review but I declined to enroll.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you decide to take self-review (way before graduation? Immediately before graduation, or after graduation?)</i>
7	Ms. NurseK	<i>I decided to take self-review before graduation so that's why I didn't scout for review centers.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did your parents/family members/friends (or classmates) react to your decision to do self-review? Please specify.</i>
8	Ms. NurseK	<i>They were very supportive to me and helped me with gathering study materials for my review.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any family member/close friends who took the same path (method of review) like you? How did it affect you, if any?</i>
9	Ms. NurseK	<i>No.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What is it like to self-review (overall description of your review experience)?</i>
10	Ms. NurseK	<i>For me, self-review is like giving oneself freedom. You control your own destiny, creating study schedules and gathering study materials. If you slack off from studying, you have no one to blame but yourself.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Can you share your experience on the challenges/issues, if there were any that you faced before your review? What about during the review? How did you cope and deal with those issues/challenges?(Please answer below)</i>
11	Ms. NurseK	<i><u>Pre-Review</u> I was one of the few who took the Nursing Licensure Examination right away in June 2009. The school expected the students to take the December NLE so I had very few time to prepare my requirements and register in PRC. Thankfully, I was able to register the day before the last day of registration.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Can you share your experience on the challenges/issues, if there were any that you faced before your review? What about during the review? How did you cope and deal with those issues/challenges?(Please answer below)</i>
12	Ms. NurseK	<i><u>Intra-Review</u> It was hard that I had very few people to talk to during the review process as a lot of my peers took the December 2009 NLE. Sometimes I would not be able to follow my schedule since I would be distracted by the TV or internet. There was even a time that I dozed off in the middle of my review!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you, at any point during the course of the review, tempted to quit self-review and just wanted to enroll to a review-center instead?</i>
13	Ms. NurseK	<i>No.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you feel about the outcome of your review? Were you dis/satisfied?</i>
14	Ms. NurseK	<i>In a way, I was satisfied but then, I could have done better in terms of time management.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?</i>
15	Ms. NurseK	<i>Advantages (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any) - Budget friendly - Convenient - Flexible Schedule - Effective for those with a study habit like mine</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

16	Ms. NurseK	<p><i>Disadvantages</i> (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Distractions such as TV, internet - No tips from review centers - Can be boring for some people
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Will you recommend self-review to others? Why, or why not?</i>
17	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, I recommend self-review as it is very budget-friendly and convenient. Besides, reviewing is just a culmination of our four years in school. No review center can pack in four years of knowledge in a few weeks so the main advantage of self-review is that you can have the flexibility to focus more on your weak areas.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you as an individual and/or as a nurse?</i>
18	Ms. NurseK	<i>The knowledge gained in my self-review was enriching as I also get to focus on topics that were not taught in school. Also, it gave me the confidence that I can do whatever tasks given to me as long as I put my heart in it.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the reception/reaction, if there was any, of the people around you when you passed the licensure examination (family, academe, friends, etc)?</i>
19	Ms. NurseK	<i>They were very happy for me. When I got home from church, I learned that I passed the exam through a text message from my schoolmate and then the text messages and FB greetings poured in.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If you can describe your overall experience in a sentence, what would it be?</i>
20	Ms. NurseK	<i>It was a truly enriching experience where the impossible became possible through confidence in one's knowledge and capabilities.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you do it that made it effective for you?</i>
21	Ms. NurseK	<i>I believe that it became effective through my determination. When I was reviewing, I pushed myself harder by reminding myself that I should pass the board on my first try since I did not want to undergo the grueling PRC exam registration again.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have doubts/ issues in failing the exam? How did you deal with it?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

22	Ms. NurseK	<i>I admit, I had doubts that I would pass since I was not that confident on my second exam. I just tried to avoid thinking about the results by making myself busy with work.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did someone (or individuals, groups) help you throughout the review? ___ If yes, in what way?</i>
23	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, my mother helped me financially by buying me reviewers and accompanying me in a hotel the day before the NLE. She was also my emotional and spiritual adviser.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>Did you seek advice from others or you just relied solely on your own? ___ If yes, what information/advice did you receive?</i>
24	Ms. NurseK	<i>I sought advice usually from internet forums like dos & don'ts of test taking plus subjects where I need to focus on.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you deal with time constraints (the duration between the Time after graduation until you finally took the exam)/how did you manage your time?</i>
25	Ms. NurseK	<i>The time I had after graduation and examination day was just right for my self-review since I took the June 2009 NLE. Right before the self-review, I made a schedule complete with deadlines so that I can cover as much subjects as I can before the exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What were your strategies in terms of:-<u>Study habits</u> (time of the day, and why?)</i>
26	Ms. NurseK	<i>I usually studied around afternoon to evening since I am not a morning person.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i><u>Venue</u> where you usually study at (do you stay at one place, or different places? Did you seclude yourself, or you did it with a group, and why did you do it in such way?) ___ Why? ___</i>
27	Ms. NurseK	<i>I usually studied in my bedroom or living room. I would try to seclude myself from others to avoid distractions.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What review materials did you acquire? Where did you get those review materials from?</i> <i>I. Fundamentals of Nursing including Professional Adjustment -Legal -Research -Ethico-Moral</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

28	Ms. NurseK	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Fundamentals of Nursing by Kozier</i> <i>RCAP Compilation of Local Nursing Board Exam</i> <i>Carl Balita's Ultimate Guide to Nursing Review</i> <i>Udan's Fundamentals of Nursing and Medical Surgical Nursing Book.</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>FOCUSED ON:</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Basic Nursing Procedures</i> <i>Sterile Technique</i> <i>Blood Transfusion</i> <i>Flow Rate</i> <i>History of Nursing</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>II. Maternal and Child Health Nursing</i>
29	Ms. NurseK	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Maternal and Child Healthy Nursing by Pilliteri</i> <i>Sia's Outline in Obstetrics</i> <i>Carl Balita's Ultimate Guide to Nursing Review</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>FOCUSED ON:</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Pregnancy Timeline</i> <i>Stages of Labor</i> <i>LMP</i> <i>Apgar Score</i> <i>Stages of Development</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>III. Community Health and Communicable Disease Nursing</i>
30	Ms. NurseK	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Integrated Management of Childhood Illnesses: A Condensed Module for Nurses by Rouena Villarama</i> <i>Public Health Nursing</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>FOCUSED ON:</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>IMCI Chart</i> <i>Levels of Prevention</i> <i>Nature of the Problem</i> <i>Home Visit</i> <i>Epidemiology</i> <i>Traditional Medicines</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>IV. Nursing of Adolescents, Adults and Aged</i>
31	Ms. NurseK	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Brunner's Medical-Surgical Nursing</i> <i>Carl Balita's Ultimate Guide to Nursing Review</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>FOCUSED ON:</u></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Hypertension</i> <i>Diabetes</i> <i>Renal Failure</i> <i>Cardiovascular Diseases</i> <i>Common Drugs</i> <i>Nursing Interventions</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>V. Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing</i>
32	Ms. NurseK	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Carl Balita's Ultimate Guide to Nursing Review</i> <i>Psychiatric Mental Health Nursing by Videbeck</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">FOCUSED ON:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Personality disorders</i> <i>Defense mechanisms</i> <i>Anorexia and Bulimia</i></p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Had there been any issues where to get the review materials from? Did you think what you initially had were sufficient to cover all the topics in nursing? If not, what did you do about it?)</i>
33	Ms. NurseK	<i>No, I did not have issues in getting the review materials. Yes, I felt that what I had was sufficient because given the timeframe; I knew that if I add more, I can never finish studying the materials completely.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Specifically, how did you organize the review (what did you study first & why did you do it in such way? Was there any specific reason/s, or none?)</i>
34	Ms. NurseK	<i>I started with the fundamentals first and then on my least favorite subject which is maternal nursing. I believe that starting with the basics is ideal and I wanted to get over the subject which I was not fond of.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you go through with the bulk of topics? Did you study each topic in detail or you just browsed everything?</i>
35	Ms. NurseK	<i>I gave a timeframe for every topic and I would try as much as possible to squeeze in as much knowledge as I can. However, for my weak subjects, I would allot more review time for it.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>Did you have relaxation moments/techniques in between or while reviewing? Please specify.</i>
36	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, if I felt tired, then I would take a short nap or snack break because I know that it would be useless to study if I was not in good condition.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you receive any help from your school? Please specify.</i>
37	Ms. NurseK	<i>No.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How well did your educational program(s) had prepared you to pass the Licensure exam, and what, (did you identify strengths or any inadequacies in your education?)</i>
38	Ms. NurseK	<i>I believe that the school educational program has prepared me enough but there are still inadequacies such as the teaching method can be better and not so boring to make students interested to learn.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you confident that you can make it? (In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what were your subjective take on your confidence level before the review? After finishing the review?) Please explain your answer...</i>
39	Ms. NurseK	<i>Before the review, I rate my confidence level as 6 and after finishing the review it was an 8 since I managed to cover as much subjects as I can especially on my weak areas.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In your perspective, how does one should do self-review to be effective?</i>
40	Ms. NurseK	<i>For me, it's all about discipline. If you don't instill discipline in yourself and just slack off then self-review would not be effective.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If any, what tip/s can you give to licensure exam takers during the actual board exam? Please specify.</i>
41	Ms. NurseK	<i>Before the actual exam day, don't cram. Try to relax since you will just have exam jitters on the actual board exam. Pray and just be confident. Don't mind others around you and concentrate on your paper. Don't rush and double check your answer key. Be mindful of erasures and try to count the items you answered with the actual items to see if they match. Bring light snacks and water. Have your pencils ready.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE? If yes, what factor/s do you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to identify the reasons/factors that might have caused it? If yes, what are they?
42	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, though I know I could have done better, I am satisfied because given the timeframe and the numerous distractions from my self-review; it is still a good grade.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you learn something from it? Was there anything you could have done that you think must have helped you more in your review? If there were any, what were they?
43	Ms. NurseK	<i>I believe I could have been more focused and should have spent more time on reading books.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Is there anything you want to add or say about self-review as a whole?
44	Ms. NurseK	<i>Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	If there were any, what do you think were the important quality/-ies you possessed that made you pass the exam? How did it (they) help you pass? (Please specify...)
45	Ms. NurseK	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Determination – I studied seriously because I was determined to pass on the first take.</i> 2. <i>Confidence – In the end, I became confident in my own knowledge and capabilities which truly helped on the day of the exam where exam jitters is your enemy.</i> 3. <i>Resourcefulness – I was not content with my own materials so I searched the internet for more study materials.</i> 4. <i>Independence – In self-review, there are no instructors to guide you, only yourself. You create your own schedules.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	What do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective?
46	Ms. NurseK	<i>I believe that the 4 qualities I stated above are needed for a self-review to be effective.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you have any regrets that you chose to do self-study instead of enrolling in a review center?(Please specify...)
47	Ms. NurseK	<i>No.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	How did it affect you psychologically, mentally, and emotionally?
48	Ms. NurseK	<i>Self-review made me not only gain knowledge but taught me the art of discipline as well. It also boosted my self-esteem which is good for my health as I became more confident in myself.</i>
		--END--
		<u>MOTHER</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	What can you say about the academic performance of your son/daughter during the time that she/he was still studying?
49	Ms. NurseK	<i>I am very proud of my daughter's academic performance. Ever since kindergarten, she has always been part of the honor roll and top section. Even though Nursing was not her first choice, she still took her studies seriously, getting high grades and even managed to be a Semestral Dean's Lister</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Do you still recall the reason why he/she has self-reviewed?
50	Ms. NurseK	<i>Yes, she told me that she found self-study to be more effective for her as she does not want to review in a crowded auditorium.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	How did you react to his/her decision? Were you part of that reason?
51	Ms. NurseK	<i>I supported her decision wholeheartedly because she herself knows what study habit is most effective for her.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Can you tell me how was your son/daughter like when he/she was reviewing?
52	Ms. NurseK	<i>While reviewing, I can see how determined my daughter was. She had this schedule of nursing subjects to study and would try to follow it to the brim. Aside from buying reviewers, she would also do self-exams and research on the internet for additional study materials.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	Do you recall any issues he/she had?
53	Ms. NurseK	<i>There would be times that she would be too lazy to study or be distracted by the TV. Sometimes I can see that she would be sleepy while studying.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What did you do to assist/help him?</i>
54	Ms. NurseK	<i>To assist her, I would try to clear distractions such as the tv or computer. I would let her use the room freely to study and would give her some energy drinks & snacks when I can see she is too tired. I also provided financial assistance for the books that she used during the review.</i>
		--END--

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Briefly narrate who you are as a person. If possible, kindly tell us a little more about your upbringing, your main beliefs about life and education, or anything that you value as a person, and the story why you took up nursing.</i>
1	Ms. NurseL	<i>I believe the saying "I am the master of my fate, I'm the captain of my soul". My dad is a doctor, my mom is a pharmacist (though she is not practicing), my eldest sister is a nurse, my brother is a medtech and lastly my older sister is a management graduate. I took up nursing and after graduating I entered medical school but I left last 2010. I plan to finish it by 2014.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Overall, how did you fair in your studies? What was your class standing during school years (in elementary, high school and/or in college)? What was your class like?</i>
2	Ms. NurseL	<i>College was a great time for me, I had a lot of friends with different taste and opinions about life. I learned a lot from them and I still keep in touch with them. My gpa is 2.01, During my 2nd yr. in nursing I had the chance to opt to a scholarship but I didn't push through with it.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were anything, what were (was) your favorite subject/s back then, & why?</i>
3	Ms. NurseL	<i>Favorite class would be med-surg. I always wanted to know how this disease works, how we can manage it and the steps we need to cure it.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone?</i>
4	Ms. NurseL	<i>Im a people person but at the same time there are some things I prefer to do on my own. I like talking to people with different ideas but shares respect towards others belief.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What were the factors/reasons that influenced you to decide to take self-review? (i.e. possible personal reasons, individuals and/or situations that might have influenced you)</i>
5	Ms. NurseL	<i>I was already taking classes from SchoolofMed when i took up my boards that's why I wasnt able to avail to any review centers. So i decided to just review on my own and just ask for review test papers to my friends who had been with a review center (such as pentagon and carl balita)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school? Or were you required to attend the review center? If there was, how did you go about it? (If yes, please explain what happened)</i>
6	Ms. NurseL	<i>We had our own review during my 4th yr. with SchoolL, it is an inhouse review that has our professors as the teachers. It ran every sun of the month for 3 months i think.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you decide to take self-review (way before graduation? Immediately before graduation, or after graduation?)</i>
7	Ms. NurseL	<i>Choosing self review for me was a neccesity since I can't afford to go to a review center because i was a 1st yr. med student back then.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did your parents/family members/friends (or classmates) react to your decision to do self-review? Please specify.</i>
8	Ms. NurseL	<i>My family supported me for taking a different path. They understood that I can't go to a review center since Im a medical student. They gave me a lot of encouragement whenever i felt that I was not reviewing enough. I had a lot of free starbucks and food from my family when I was reviewing:) haha</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any family member/close friends who took the same path (method of review) like you? How did it affect you, if any?</i>
9	Ms. NurseL	<i>I had a friend who opted out of her review center and just reviewed on her own. She passed the june 2007 board exams.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What is it like to self-review (overall description of your review experience)?</i>
10	Ms. NurseL	<i>Self review for me is an interesting experience. It saves time because I get to concentrate to the topics that I dont really know rather than going to a center that goes over all the topics. Plus i can adjust everything to fit my study schedule rathen than adjusting to a review center's sched.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	
11	Ms. NurseL	<i>My sister was the first one who knew that I passes. I remembered I was at school the class was physiology and she called my cell and delivered the good news! I was jumping up and down the hallway. I entered my calssroom and told my close friends their the good news as well. When i went home we celebrated and of course during the weekends we drank!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	
12	Ms. NurseL	<i>Self-review: Epic! one of those things that you thought you can never do but when you finally did it. It feels like your superman and kryptonite can't hold you back</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	
13	Ms. NurseL	<i>I guess the big challenge for me is that I don't have that much test papers to answer on. So i had no idea on how the wuestions are gonna be raised. That time i relied a lot from my friends since they shared their papers with me as well the answers.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Can you share your experience on the challenges/issues, if there were any that you faced before your review? What about during the review? How did you cope and deal with those issues/challenges? (Please answer below)</i>
14	Ms. NurseL	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Pre-review</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - how to apply for the board exams - getting all the requirements needed <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Intra-review</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - looking for test papers i could answer on - my friends gave me advices on test-taking strategy

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you, at any point during the course of the review, tempted to quit self-review and just wanted to enroll to a review-center instead?</i>
15	Ms. NurseL	<i>I don't have a choice to opt out of self-review since that was my only choice back then if i wanted to take the board exam. There was no time for me to apply to a center. So when I applied for my boards I already knew that Im gonna work harder during the weekends to study.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you feel about the outcome of your review? Were you dis/satisfied?</i>
16	Ms. NurseL	<i>I was satisfied when I got the results. I was really happy and I thanked God. When I took the boards I talked to God and I told him that I'm leaving everything to him. If he could just point me to the right directions.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?</i>
17	Ms. NurseL	<i>I guess the <u>disadvantages</u> are: No trained professionals to tell you what they know, to teach you the short cut to memorizing this or that, tips on taking the exams, extra knwoledge plus a fun time reviewing.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?</i>
18	Ms. NurseL	<i><u>advantages</u>: your time is your own, you save money because you dont need to pay anything for the review. You get to concentrate on the topics that is harder for you to understand.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Will you recommend self-review to others? Why, or why not?</i>
19	Ms. NurseL	<i>Yes, I would recommend self-review to others if they don't have a lot of options. But if they do then, Taking the boards is a big deal so I</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>think that if they can get a different kind of help and if they can afford it then why not, right?</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you as an individual and/or as a nurse?</i>
20	Ms. NurseL	<i>Self review gave me the determination and the confidence to know that anything is possible if you just do the work and believe in God. As a nurse (since I was just a student back then) this review made me realize that we are on the verge of being professionals who are about to take care of people's lives so I know that I had to take it seriously.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the reception/reaction, if there was any, of the people around you when you passed the licensure examination (family, academe, friends, etc)?</i>
21	Ms. NurseL	<p><i>I concentrated on my weak points which is test 5, and you can include test 1 as well. test 3 and 4 are my strengths.</i></p> <p><i>Doubts are normal if we dont have it then how will we strive to do more. I cope up by reading a lot and making time to really understand my weak points during the course of the review.</i></p> <p><i>My friend helped a lot! we used to have a starbucks session where we stayed their and compare notes on how we reviewed this and that (because back then they were all enrolled in a review center) so my time with them usually starts after my classes.</i></p> <p><i>I asked from friends for their test papers and some test taking strategies (the very popular, if you don't know it choose the longest answer as well as the letter C)</i></p> <p><i>I sucked at time management, hehe So what i did was when i got home I sleep for about 3 hours then I studied until 2am (which gave me 5 hours of review time)</i></p> <p><i>My study habit during school days are from 9pm till 2 am (pero hinde to nasusunod palagi) over the weekends I usually get up at 10 am but my review will start at 2pm onwards. I usually ends up sleeping at around 4am during the weekends.</i></p> <p><i>our terrace and starbucks (araneta branch before it got shut down, west ave and congressional branch) usually were in a group of 3 people whenever i got to starbucks</i></p>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>I. Fundamentals of Nursing including Professional Adjustment -Legal -Research -Ethico-Moral</i>
22	Ms. NurseL	<i>review material: I - Kozier/ test paper from pentagon and gapuz I remembered memorizing about the theories of care. I dont remember much about test 1 since i really dont like it hehe</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>II. Maternal and Child Health Nursing</i>
23	Ms. NurseL	<i>II - pilliterri/ test paper from pentagon and gapuz i reviewed about the vaccines, used a lot of tips and pnemonics from pentagon and gapuz (sorry neri hinde ko malagay yung lahat ng tinutukan ko, basta ang naalala ko ay vaccines at yung development ng mga bata. Yung sa panganganak yung about sa eclampsia and pre-eclampsia. mga newborn tests.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>III. Community Health and Communicable Disease Nursing</i>
24	Ms. NurseL	<i>III - I used the review notes that i had during our in house review as well as pentagon and gapuz's notes i memorize a lot of the populars s/sx like kopliks spots :) looking back this was one of my faves because i had a thing for infectious diseases:) neri may yellow ako na book na ginamit dito, maliit lang sya pero pang communicable sya</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>IV. Nursing of Adolescents, Adults and Aged</i>
25	Ms. NurseL	<i>IV - ofcourse brunner and sudarth, ihalo mo na yung physiology book ko sa med :) I guess a part of my med courses really helped me with studying for the boards. It might not be the exact thing but it is still related to the things that i needed to know :) like how the blood flows from the heart and such</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>V. Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing</i>
26	Ms. NurseL	<i>V - review notes from in-house as well as pentagon and gapuz i learned from my friends the pnemonics to the drugs (a really great help!!!) the delusion of grandeur, bipolar, schizo, a lot of terms to learn but with the help of my friends it was fun bec. we would make fun of each other and relate the terms to ourselves (ex. histironic)</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Had there been any issues where to get the review materials from? Did you think what you initially had were sufficient to cover all the topics in nursing? If not, what did you do about it?)</i>
27	Ms. NurseL	<i>I sometimes go to morayta to buy the very cheap test papers of the boards from 2000 to 2005, there i answered and tried to learn the test taking strategy that my friend taught me.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Specifically, how did you organize the review (what did you study first & why did you do it in such way? Was there any specific reason/s, or none?)</i>
28	Ms. NurseL	<i>I studied test 1 and 5 first because they are my weakness then every weekends it would be test 3 and 4, the test 2 was the last one that i studied.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you go through with the bulk of topics? Did you study each topic in detail or you just browsed everything?</i>
29	Ms. NurseL	<i>Aamin ako may mga topics sa test 1 na nagbrowse lang ako para masabing nabasa ko lang siya, haha pati sa test 5 kasi un iba mejo self-explanatory kaya hidne na dapat dibdibin pa. But for test 3 and 4 i memorized and learned a lot :)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have relaxation moments/techniques in between or while reviewing? Please specify?</i>
30	Ms. NurseL	<i>my relaxation tech consists of watching funny t.v series or reading my fave book. Isama mo na yung going out with friend to drink din :)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you receive any help from your school? Please specify.</i>
31	Ms. NurseL	<i>no help from my school.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How well did your educational program(s) had prepared you to pass the Licensure exam, and what, (did you identify strengths or any inadequacies in your education?)</i>
32	Ms. NurseL	<i>The duties from different hospital helped me be exposed to the real nursing world, I have no regrets choosing SchoolL for my college I think God led me there. For what purpose? I still dont know but im thankful that i went there. Proud to be a tangaraw :) haha as for the review, lahat naman may pros and cons e. Minsan yung teacher hidne marunong magturo, kaya you need to adjust.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you confident that you can make it? (In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what were your subjective take on your confidence level before the review? After finishing the review?) Please explain your answer...</i>
33	Ms. NurseL	<i>i was not confident, like what i said earlier i left it all to God. I wasnt confident then but I knew that i was giving it my all. so my score would be 6. starting the review : 3 after the review: 6</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In your perspective, how does one should do self-review to be effective?</i>
34	Ms. NurseL	<i>Self-review for me is like highlighting a book the you need to review so that you can remember the terms. The only difference is the ink is black, hehe</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If any, what tip/s can you give to licensure exam takers during the actual board exam? Please specify.</i>
35	Ms. NurseL	<i>Actual boards: deep breaths, pray and leave it to God and 2 days before the exam (don't review anymore). The last 2 days i was not able to do because i was still at that point that i think I still have a lot to go so i still read during the 2 days.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE? If yes, what factor/s do you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to identify the reasons/factors that might have caused it? If yes, what are they?</i>
36	Ms. NurseL	<i>I was satisfied that I pass, the only question that I have is my score. hehe I was not able to process my board rating. They told me that it was supposed to be mailed to our home but i havent received anything.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you learn something from it? Was there anything you could have done that you think must have helped you more in your review? If there were any, what were they?</i>
37	Ms. NurseL	<i>I learned a lot during my self-review days, its like a preparation for me during med proper. This review helped me to focus more on what is essential.</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were any, what do you think were the important quality/-ies you possessed that made you pass the exam? How did it (they) help you pass? (Please specify...)</i>
38	Ms. NurseL	<i>Qualities: curiosity? - if something is nagging me whenever we have the q and a with my friend and i dont know the answer. I'd looked for it the answer right away stubbornness - they told me to stop but i still went forward :) patience - w/out it were all goners :) Never give up mantra</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective?</i>
39	Ms. NurseL	<i>qualities a person must have: the dedication to put the review above everything else the know how to balance your review with your life the hunger to reach for the stars</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any regrets that you chose to do self-study instead of enrolling in a review center? (Please specify...)</i>
40	Ms. NurseL	<i>Regrets: No regrets (since i passed) though it would have been fun if i could go have gone to a review center, i heard the last day was like a production number, :)</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did it affect you psychologically, mentally, and emotionally?</i>
41	Ms. NurseL	<i>one word: stronger (on all factors)</i>

<u>Reference Number</u>	<u>Speaker</u>	<u>Incident</u>
Researcher:	Researcher	Briefly narrate who you are as a person. If possible, kindly tell us a little more about your upbringing, your main beliefs about life and education, or anything that you value as a person, and the story why you took up nursing.
1	Mr. NurseMM	I wanted to be a lawyer but my mom wanted me to follow her footsteps and took up nursing. I never thought that I will be a Nurse but eventually learned to love it. The passion of care to an ill or dying person and deal with their family members, even though

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		it takes a lot of effort on your part sometimes, it is very rewarding when they appreciated your service.
Researcher:	Researcher	Overall, how did you fair in your studies? What was your class standing during school years (in elementary, high school and/or in college)? What was your class like?
2	Mr. NurseMM	RATE: from 1-5 as 5 would be the highest, I would rate myself as 4.5 as my class standing. I considered my self as a competitive student.
Researcher:	Researcher	If there were anything, what were (was) your favorite subject/s back then, & why?
3	Mr. NurseMM	MEDICAL/SURGICAL NURSING – Challenging
Researcher:	Researcher	Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone?
4	Mr. NurseMM	I would prefer to do things alone... but I can also work in a team.
Researcher:	Researcher	What were the factors/reasons that influenced you to decide to take self-review? (i.e. possible personal reasons, individuals and/or situations that might have influenced you)
5	Mr. NurseMM	I worked immediately after graduation and didn't want to spend money for a review center.
Researcher:	Researcher	Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school? Or were you required to attend the review center? If there was, how did you go about it? (If yes, please explain what happened)
6	Mr. NurseMM	None.
Researcher:	Researcher	When did you decide to take self-review (way before graduation? Immediately before graduation, or after graduation?)
7	Mr. NurseMM	After graduation during my rest days from work.
Researcher:	Researcher	How did your parents/family members/friends (or classmates) react to your decision to do self-review? Please specify.
8	Mr. NurseMM	No one knows, never informed them about my decision of doing self-review and/or even taking NLE because I wanted to surprise them after I passed the NLE. It did work though!!
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you have any family member/close friends who took the same path (method of review) like you? How did it affect you, if any?
9	Mr. NurseMM	None
Researcher:	Researcher	What is it like to self-review (overall description of your review experience)?
10	Mr. NurseMM	It was very challenging in terms of time management and resources because I had a job.

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	Can you share your experience on the challenges/issues, if there were any that you faced before your review? What about during the review? How did you cope and deal with those issues/challenges? (Please answer below)	
11	Mr. NurseMM	<i>Pre-Review</i>	<i>Intra-Review</i>
		Resources/Review materials : read sample questionnaires from a nursing website, used my previous notes when I was in a nursing school, borrowed review materials from a friend who attended from a review center and passed the NLE and consolidated everything	Time Management: since I was working at night and would prefer to sleep during the day, I made my own time table when to scan my review materials.
Researcher:	Researcher	Were you, at any point during the course of the review, tempted to quit self-review and just wanted to enroll to a review-center instead?	
12	Mr. NurseMM	None	
Researcher:	Researcher	How did you feel about the outcome of your review? Were you dis/satisfied?	
13	Mr. NurseMM	Very Satisfied!!!	
Researcher:	Researcher	What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?	
14	Mr. NurseMM	Advantages (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)	Disadvantages (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Save your money • Manage your own time • Free yourself from information overload since you can take a break any time you want. • Gain discipline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you're looking for memory tricks and mnemonics, you might not have as many of those as other review centers. ☺
Researcher:	Researcher	Will you recommend self-review to others? Why, or why not?	
15	Mr. NurseMM	Yes, for those people who are working and no time to attend in a review center.	

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you as an individual and/or as a nurse?
16	Mr. NurseMM	Gained discipline and got more confidence! Very Proud!
Researcher:	Researcher	What was the reception/reaction, if there was any, of the people around you when you passed the licensure examination (family, academe, friends, etc)?
17	Mr. NurseMM	Surprised and proud
Researcher:	Researcher	If you can describe your overall experience in a sentence, what would it be?
18	Mr. NurseMM	It was priceless!!
Researcher:	Researcher	Is there anything else that you would like to add or share about your review experience? Optional.
19	Mr. NurseMM	No answer
Researcher:	Researcher	How did you do it that made it effective for you?
20	Mr. NurseMM	Please see answers from pre-review and intrareview challenges. Thanks
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you have doubts/ issues in failing the exam? How did you deal with it?
21	Mr. NurseMM	None
Researcher:	Researcher	Did someone (or individuals, groups) help you throughout the review? ___ If yes, in what way?
22	Mr. NurseMM	none
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you seek advice from others or you just relied solely on your own? ___ If yes, what information/advice did you receive?
23	Mr. NurseMM	Yes, read questions carefully and do not overanalyze
Researcher:	Researcher:	How did you deal with time constraints (the duration between the Time after graduation until you finally took the exam)/how did you manage your time?
24	Mr. NurseMM	Made my own time table
Researcher:	Researcher	What were your strategies in terms of: -Study habits (time of the day, and why?)
25	Mr. NurseMM	Nothing in particular during my avail time regardless of time of the day.
Researcher:	Researcher	-Venue where you usually study at (do you stay at one place, or different places? Did you seclude yourself, or you did it with a group, and why did you do it in such way?) ___ Why? ___

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

26	Mr. NurseMM	At home, in my room alone because I can concentrate more if no one is disturbing me.
Researcher:	Researcher	Had there been any issues where to get the review materials from? Did you think what you initially had were sufficient to cover all the topics in nursing? If not, what did you do about it?)
27	Mr. NurseMM	None
Researcher:	Researcher	-Specifically, how did you organize the review (what did you study first & why did you do it in such way? Was there any specific reason/s, or none?)
28	Mr. NurseMM	I concentrated more on Medical/Surgical Nursing- because this is more complicated
Researcher:	Researcher	How did you go through with the bulk of topics? Did you study each topic in detail or you just browsed everything?
29	Mr. NurseMM	Just browsed everything
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you have relaxation moments/techniques in between or while reviewing? Please specify.
30	Mr. NurseMM	Yes, eat and eat and eat
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you receive any help from your school? Please specify.
31	Mr. NurseMM	None
Researcher:	Researcher	How well did your educational program(s) had prepared you to pass the Licensure exam, and what, (did you identify strengths or any inadequacies in your education?)
32	Mr. NurseMM	I personally believed that I came from an institution with strong educational foundation.
Researcher:	Researcher	Were you confident that you can make it? (In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what were your subjective take on your confidence level before the review? After finishing the review?) Please explain your answer...
33	Mr. NurseMM	Before the review- 10- I thought I covered everything After the review- 8- after the exam there were questions that were very tricky..
Researcher:	Researcher	In your perspective, how does one should do self-review to be effective?
34	Mr. NurseMM	Manage your topic to be reviewed and make sure to focus more on a topic that you think is complicated for you.
Researcher:	Researcher	If any, what tip/s can you give to licensure exam takers during the actual board exam? Please specify.
35	Mr. NurseMM	Don't over analyze!
Researcher:	Researcher	Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE? If yes, what factor/s do you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		identify the reasons/factors that might have caused it? If yes, what are they?
36	Mr. NurseMM	Satisfied! Because not part of the top notchers though but fair enough because of the board rate.
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you learn something from it? Was there anything you could have done that you think must have helped you more in your review? If there were any, what were they?
37	Mr. NurseMM	No answe
Researcher:	Researcher	Is there anything you want to add or say about self-review as a whole?
38	Mr. NurseMM	No answer
Researcher:	Researcher	If there were any, what do you think were the important quality/-ies you possessed that made you pass the exam? How did it (they) help you pass? (Please specify...)
39	Mr. NurseMM	IQ
Researcher:	Researcher	What do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective?
40	Mr. NurseMM	Patience
Researcher:	Researcher	Did you have any regrets that you chose to do self-study instead of enrolling in a review center? (Please specify...)
41	Mr. NurseMM	none
Researcher:	Researcher	How did it affect you psychologically, mentally, and emotionally?
42	Mr. NurseMM	It made me stronger- mentally and emotionally
		--END--

Reference Number	Speaker	Incident
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Briefly narrate who you are as a person. If possible, kindly tell us a little more about your upbringing, your main beliefs about life and education, or anything that you value as a person, and the story why you took up nursing.</i>
1	Mr. NurseM]	<i>I would like to describe myself as wholehearted person who is willing to learn something, im eager to learn new things and flexible in a changing enviroment. Im very inquisitive in astronomy and anything about nature, I love to read adventure novels and also music it made me relax and calm. Life for me is like a star, without darkness it will never be bright. Like us we will never be bright or successful without</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

		<i>obstacles and trials. In the realm of life it is full of darkness(trials and obstacles) and it depends on us on how we'll adapt into it. I took up nursing because this career made me in a way I can never imagine. Actually nursing is not my preference before honestly it's my mother's choice but in the end I really enjoyed this career and im very proud that I am a nurse. It trained me become a professional and how to empathized other people.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Overall, how did you fair in your studies? What was your class standing during school years (in elementary, high school and/or in college)? What was your class like?</i>
2	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>When I was in gradeschool and highschool I did not stand out that much. I love math and science.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were anything, what were (was) your favorite subject/s back then, & why?</i>
3	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I love math coz I enjoyed computing or solving a math problem, I love trigonometry. I love science especifically,biology and astronomy. I love to experiment and I love to discover the heavenly bodies.... Im sorry Sir Neri if Im weird.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Do you consider yourself as a people person, or someone who prefers to do things alone?</i>
4	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Yes I prefer to do things alone.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What were the factors/reasons that influenced you to decide to take self-review? (i.e. possible personal reasons, individuals and/or situations that might have influenced you)</i>
5	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>4 years of studying was good enough.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Was there any review center that was endorsed by your school? Or were you required to attend the review center? If there was, how did you go about it? (If yes, please explain what happened)</i>
6	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Yeah, gapuz review center our school did not required us to attend the review as long as u pass the preboard... im not really sure!</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>When did you decide to take self-review (way before graduation? Immediately before graduation, or after graduation?)</i>
7	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Immediately before graduation.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did your parents/family members/friends (or classmates) react to your decision to do self-review? Please specify.</i>
8	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>My family and friends supported me about my decisions.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any family member/close friends who took the same path (method of review) like you? How did it affect you, if any?</i>
9	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>None,they all decided to take a review center. No regrets that I din't not take a review center</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What is it like to self-review (overall description of your review experience)?</i>

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

10	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I woke up early in the morning then review for about 1 hour...actually 1 hour per day.</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you, at any point during the course of the review, tempted to quit self-review and just wanted to enroll to a review-center instead?</i>	
11	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>none</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you feel about the outcome of your review? Were you dis/satisfied?</i>	
12	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Im not satisfied on my exam 5 grade is not good. Maybe im not that good in psychiatric health</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the dis/advantages of self-review as against to a review center?</i>	
13	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Advantages (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)</i>	<i>Disadvantages (Please list down as much as you can, if there's any)</i>
		<i>You can study anytime you want... You can read bookasmuch as you can. You don't need to woke up early to go to the review center. You can focus on your subject that you are not excelling...</i>	<i>You can't assess yourself if you did well on a specific topic or subject.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Will you recommend self-review to others? Why, or why not?</i>	
14	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>It depends on the stuednt or person's choiceif he/she want to take review center....Much better if he/she can do both.</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the effect, if there was any, of the entire review experience to you as an individual and/or as a nurse?</i>	
15	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I prove to myself that I can do anything without the help ofothers.</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What was the reception/reaction, if there was any, of the people around you when you passed the licensure examination (family, academe, friends, etc)?</i>	
16	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>They are proud of me, not because I did self review but because I passed it. Some were amaze because I did self review.</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If you can describe your overall experience in a sentence, what would it be?</i>	
17	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>It's a great achievement.</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Is there anything else that you would like to add or share about your review experience? Optional.</i>	
18	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>No answer</i>	
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you do it that made it effective for you?</i>	
19	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Make a time plan and set a goal to become organize or systematic</i>	

ST. PAUL UNIVERSITY MANILA
(St. Paul University System)

Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have doubts/ issues in failing the exam? How did you deal with it?</i>
20	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Yes, because I did not encounter or read some topic in the examination. I just pray that I will pass the exam.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did someone (or individuals, groups) help you throughout the review? ___ If yes, in what way?</i>
21	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Yes, some of my friends... they will ask a question then I will answer it..</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you seek advice from others or you just relied solely on your own? ___ If yes, what information/advice did you receive?</i>
22	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>no</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did you deal with time constraints (the duration between the Time after graduation until you finally took the exam)/how did you manage your time?</i>
23	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I made a time plan and setting a goal is so important.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher:	<i>What were your strategies in terms of: -Study habits (time of the day, and why?)</i>
24	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Every morning after breakfast, 1 hour per day.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>-Venue where you usually study at (do you stay at one place, or different places? Did you seclude yourself, or you did it with a group, and why did you do it in such way?)___ Why?___</i>
25	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I usually stay at one place....At home (reading area) the environment is quiet and no disturbances.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Specific Strategies/Pointers you focused more on (Please list down as much as you can) I. Fundamentals of Nursing including Professional Adjustment</i>
		<i>-Legal -Research -Ethico-Moral</i>
26	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>FUNDA of Nursing by KOZIER and UDAN -theorist/theories</i>
		<i>-nursing intervention -NCP</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>II. Maternal and Child Health Nursing</i>
		<i>Maternal and Child by Pillitteri DOH book</i>
27	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>-Vision/mission/principles -maternal complications -pedia disorder and diseases -genetics -growth and development</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>III. Community Health and Communicable Disease Nursing Specific Strategies/Pointers you focused more on (Please list down as much as you can)</i>

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28	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">DOH book Microbiology book Pathophysiology -communicable disease -pathophysiology</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">IV. Nursing of Adolescents, Adults and Aged Specific Strategies/Pointers you focused more on (Please list down as much as you can)</p>
29	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">Medsurge book Pathophysiology Perioperative nursing Patho of diseases Nursing interventions</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">V. Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing Specific Strategies/Pointers you focused more on (Please list down as much as you can)</p>
30	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">Med surge book -pathophysiology of psychiatric disorder</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">Had there been any issues where to get the review materials from? Did you think what you initially had were sufficient to cover all the topics in nursing? If not, what did you do about it?)</p>
31	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">I only used my old books during my undergrad studies</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">Specifically, how did you organize the review (what did you study first & why did you do it in such way? Was there any specific reason/s, or none?)</p>
32	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">I focus on the topic that im not familiar with.</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">-How did you go through with the bulk of topics? Did you study each topic in detail or you just browsed everything?</p>
33	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">I only read some important details of each topic I made.</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">-Did you have relaxation moments/techniques in between or while reviewing? Please specify.</p>
34	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">Yes, a cup of coffee...</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">-Did you receive any help from your school? Please specify.</p>
35	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">None</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">How well did your educational program(s) had prepared you to pass the Licensure exam, and what, (did you identify strengths or any inadequacies in your education?)</p>
36	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">It molds me to become a competent and responsible nurse in the future.</p>
Researcher:	Researcher	<p align="center">Were you confident that you can make it? (In a scale of 10, 10 being the highest, what were your subjective take on your confidence level before the review? After finishing the review?) Please explain your answer...</p>
37	Mr. NurseMJ	<p align="center">Before and after review: 8... my RLE experiences and studies is a good preparation for the exam.</p>

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Researcher:	Researcher	<i>In your perspective, how does one should do self-review to be effective?</i>
38	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Self discipline</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If any, what tip/s can you give to licensure exam takers during the actual board exam? Please specify.</i>
39	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Pray and have a confidence to pass the exam...think that its just a quiz in the class.hehhehe</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Were you satisfied with the result of your NLE? If yes, what factor/s do you attribute such satisfaction? If not, were you able to identify the reasons/factors that might have caused it? If yes, what are they?</i>
40	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Not satisfied, my grade in exam V is too low, maybe I don't have enough time or reference to review on psychiatric health nursing</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you learn something from it? Was there anything you could have done that you think must have helped you more in your review? If there were any, what were they?</i>
41	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>I need to focus more on my weakness topic/subject.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Is there anything you want to add or say about self-review as a whole?</i>
42	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Self review is self fulfillment.</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>If there were any, what do you think were the important quality/-ies you possessed that made you pass the exam? How did it (they) help you pass? (Please specify...)</i>
43	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Self discipline Confident enough to pass the exam....</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>What do you think are the qualities a person must have in order for a self-review to be effective?</i>
44	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Self discipline</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>Did you have any regrets that you chose to do self-study instead of enrolling in a review center? (Please specify...)</i>
45	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>No regrets</i>
Researcher:	Researcher	<i>How did it affect you psychologically, mentally, and emotionally?</i>
46	Mr. NurseMJ	<i>Self fulfillment</i>
		--END--

Marks of an NLE Self-Reviewee Board Passer

“SELF-REVIEW IN THE PHILIPPINE NURSING LICENSURE EXAM (P.N.L.E.): IS IT FOR YOU?”

The self-review stories of seven first-taker board passers in the Philippine Nursing Licensure Examination (P.N.L.E.): a multiple case study output

St. Paul University Manila Graduate School

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Contents

The Researcher's Note ----- 619

Situationer: A Look at the Recent Years ----- 622

The Present Study: "I have a question..." ----- 624

What did we find out? ----- 624

Personal and academic backgrounds -----624

Self-review experiences ----- 626

Fourteen Self-review Strategies and Techniques----- 628

Seven Self-review Models----- 632

Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach----- 632

Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach----- 634

Ms. NurseG's "The Combo Approach" a.k.a.
"The Vacant Room" ----- 636

Mr. NurseJ's Recalling Approach----- 637

Mr. NurseB's "Traditional Q & A Approach"----- 639

Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach ----- 640

Ms. NurseE's "Textbook Approach"-----642

A closer look: What do they mean? ----- 644

The Present Understanding: "What do they say...?"-----645

Self-reported traits of Self-reviewee Board Passers-----646

Self-review in the eyes of the participants ----- 649

Closing notes: To the prospective self-reviewee----- 650

“...the review of this document is hoped to evoke the self-reviewee on self-analysis and, as a result, pinpoints the traits, abilities, and strategies on which he/she is strong at and with the help of these pointers, determine those which call for modification or enhancement.”

The Researcher's Note

Meet Dan:

“I want to enroll in a review center, but we don’t have enough money at this time. My siblings are about to enter college this coming school year and my parents are in a tight budget.”

Here’s Ana:

“My uncle has supported my studies ever since. I am grateful I graduated because of him. He just told me that three of my cousins will be entering college this coming school year and he can no longer support my review. I really want to take the board exam, but I’m out of options and don’t know what to do.”

Ben:

“I am a second courser and a bread-winner. Like many others, I studied nursing so I can give my family a better life. It has been a year now since I graduated from Nursing and I still haven’t taken my board exam yet. I’m afraid I might start to forget all that I have learned in Nursing. I can’t leave work to review. I have a family to support.”

And Bea:

“At last, I finally graduated! Everything was working great all these time until I received the news that my mom was diagnosed with an acute illness. I am the eldest and my dad is working abroad and no one will look after my mom. I am bothered. Can I afford to leave my mom so I can attend review, or can I stay and review at home instead?”

Here’s Lea:

“I consider me and my close friends competitive at school. We have been classmates since first year. We were challenged by our professors to take the licensure through self-review. We seriously talked about it and decided we’ll accept the challenge. I am excited and thrilled as to what will happen next, however, I can’t help but ask, how exactly prepared are we? Are we ready to take the risk and consequence of this decision? This is not just an easy game to play. Our license is at stake.”

Finally, Kayla:

“The board exam is do or die. And I know myself, I can study harder if I am alone. I get distracted easily and do not find studying in an auditorium, full of people, conducive to learning.”

The Researcher's Note

“What does it take for a reviewee to pass the NLE through self-review? Is self-review for everyone? Knowing the inherent risks and the anticipated challenges it could bring, is it worth it to self-review for a major examination such as a licensure exam in the first place?”

Like the scenarios above, these and some more, were the considerations the researcher had in mind when he conducted a study with eleven self-reviewees who passed the Nurses' Licensure Exam all on their first-take. Their answers and insights are contained here. This document is a simple, practical-based, not to mention, collective contribution of those who passed on their own in the NLE. This was a product of a Master's thesis at St. Paul University Manila Graduate School.

This document was modestly put together in the hopes of informing future self-reviewees of what could be the marks of a successful self-reviewee in the PNLE—for them to emulate and ponder on should they prefer to, or should there be a need for them to take the “solitary” route—in passing the PNLE.

More than likely, we all have different mental models of what a perfect review is and, therefore, how it should be done. These models cater to our specific taste, flexibility—a specific style or our “signature”, so to speak, to help us optimize not just our time and resources, but ourselves to begin with. Should we embark and decide to take it on our own because of reasons we find justifiable at the time, or even without any clear reason at all, we put on the line the chance to practice the profession that we have invested for at least four years in school.

The reason for individuals choosing to study on their own or participating in a group review, like those who enroll in review centers, may vary based on a number of factors. Some choose to do it as they have a firm grasp on what works or doesn't work for them. Some may involve circumstantial variables like the inability to finance attending a formal review center. Others may simply prefer to work alone as they work better on their own. Some more may have a concrete idea of their limits in terms of self-discipline and understand that time management is something they can handle well, or others may just try it for the thrill and challenge it may bring. On the other hand, there are also those who know that without the straightforward sessions offered by a review center, they may not be able to manage their time spent on studying well.

Regardless of the reasons, review strategies and approaches, personal motivations and the likes, self-review is the “default.” That being said, this document was created in the hopes of being able to reach out to everyone who may be considering sticking to this “default,” or simply provides some transferable insights to those who are considering their options.

Continued...

Whether a Candidate Nurse does self-review or something else, the convention is — there is no easy magic formula to success in the licensure. That being said, this document will not make absolute statements nor will it seek to advance a "one best way" of reviewing and anything written here does not carry any sort of "satisfaction guarantee". At the end of it all, the desired output may only be as good as the input of the reviewee him/herself.

Like baby sea turtles who went out to the open sea alone and unaided, this document charts the successful journeys on the "highways and roads that are less traveled by" by a select number of people who have proven to have reviewed on their own and have passed the PNLE successfully, all within their first attempt of the exam. And with their experiences, their responses have been collated so as to inform and allow its readers to justify for themselves if reviewing on their own would be best for them; if so, how to go about it, and if not, perhaps allow them to understand the reasons why.

Lastly, the review of this document is hoped to evoke the prospective self-reviewee on self-analysis and, as a result, pinpoints the traits, abilities, and strategies on which he/she is strong at and with the help of these pointers, determine those which call for modification or enhancement.

As a self-reviewee board-passer myself, I welcome you to this test of discipline.

~N.M.O. (summer, 2015)

Situationer: A Look at the Recent Years

Every year, thousands of nurse aspirants take the Philippine Nurses' Licensure Exam. Looking at the Professional Regulation Commission's (P.R.C.) website, out of 1,176,442 licensure examinees from the years 2004-2014, 42.48% (average) passed or an equivalent of 499,735 R.N.s in the last ten years. In the past five years, only 40.40% (226,107 passed out of 559,726 examinees) passed. Last December 2013, only 30.94% made it, the lowest so far in the nurse licensure history.

Passing Percentage from the year 2004-2014

Comparison between the Number of Examinees vs. N.L.E. passers (2004-2014)

Comparison between No. of Examinees vs. No. of Passers per Month/Batch of the Year (2004-2014)

An exploratory study to examine the impact of coping, locus of control, and academic worry on first-attempt passing rates on the Board of Certification (BOC) examination was done by Breitbach, Downey, and Frager (2013) and their data suggest that candidates experiencing psychological factors, such as high academic worry, emotion-focused coping mechanisms, and an external locus of control, have a lower first-attempt pass rate on the examination. Further, in a classic study done by Poorman and Webb (2000), the researchers interviewed 10 nursing graduates who had failed the NCLEX-RN® to gain an understanding of their experience. Several themes emerged including: *“carrying failure as a daily burden; losing the identity of being a nurse; doubting past accomplishments; seeing self as damaged goods; wanting support; and daring to hope”*.

The Present Study: “I have a question...”

Notwithstanding the licensure rating status, the study began with three simple questions in mind: “(1) amid the overwhelming risks of failure in the Nurses’ Licensure Examination, why do examinees conduct self-review in the NLE?, (2) could “self-review” make a Candidate Nurse pass the Philippine Nurses’ Licensure Exam (P.N.L.E.)? And (3) if so, how?”

A total of eleven nurses belonging to public and private universities in Metro Manila who passed the nurse licensure through self-review on their first take were scouted. Data were collected primarily through interviews and online survey questionnaire. The result was 575 minutes and 17 seconds of interview, or equivalent to 361 single-spaced pages of interview transcripts, and 30 single spaced pages of the retrieved email survey responses.

What did we find out?

The reasons why they embarked on self-review were first examined.

After data analysis, findings revealed that participants had two main self-review reasons: (1) **Circumstantial** and (2) **Preferential**. “Circumstantial reasons” was operationally defined as reasons to self-review because of the “need to do so”, whereas “Preferential reasons” describe reasons to self-review because of the ‘choice or preference to do so’.

Circumstantial reasons reported include short of funds, time constraints (i.e. working while reviewing, started taking another course, need to take care of a family member), and lastly, being challenged by professors and brother to self-review.

As to the *preferential reasons*, participants reported academic preparedness to take the licensure even prior to graduation, study habit and learning style were in line with self-review, set low expectation to peers and family, a belief that no review method can guarantee success and so participant did not want to spend money for review, and lastly, a participant reported self-review because of the influence of two siblings who also passed the P.N.L.E. and NCLEX-RN® through self-review.

After establishing self-review reasons, the next question that was asked was:

What are the personal and academic backgrounds of the case participants?

Here’s what the findings revealed:

- ✓ *Preference in constructive learning strategy over rote learning.*

Findings suggested that the self-reviewees learning strategies were more of constructive over rehearsal or rote learning. Constructive processes imply that the learner transforms the

information from its original form and constructs a new representation of the information in long-term memory, which includes linking the information into existing know-ledge structures. Constructive processes include strategies for encoding information through the elaboration of prior knowledge, structuring or organizing information, personalizing information to make it meaningful, and creating visual representations of information (Driscoll, 2005; Ormrod, 2004). Keywords such as “context”, “comparison”, “use your reasoning”, “simpler explanation”, “situational”, “how body works”, “fault finder”, “picture in mind”, “association”, “summary”, “root it from the basics” and “connection” were present in the responses. Also, while two of the participants openly stated preference to memorization, further questionings revealed exposure to situational and abstract type of scenarios during classes and related learning experience.

✓ *Preference in solitary over outgoing activities*

Seven participants or 64% had a strong preference studying alone, two reported learning better when studying with a group vs. alone, whereas two were fine studying with a group or studying alone (mixed type). This finding suggests, as expected, that solitary learners would prefer self-review over other review methods. One of the case participants, however, reported a contrasting learning style. He just could not study alone in an extended period of time. In fact, he termed his review as “more than ICU”.

✓ *Strong academic background*

Incidentally, the participants were academic performers. Participants reported being consistently having good grades, one graduated valedictorian in high school, one graduated valedictorian in elementary and consistent honor student, a dean’s lister, someone who says he would rate himself as 4.5 out of 5.0, 5.0 being the highest, and another pushed himself to be at par with his batch mates as their school belongs to the top nursing schools in the country at present in terms of licensure rating.

The next question that was explored was: *What is it like to do self-review in preparation for the Philippine Nurses’ Licensure Exam (P.N.L.E.)?*

✓ *Self-review is “tailor-fit” to the reviewee.*

The case study findings, as confirmed by the responses, revealed that self-review is tailored fit to the individual review needs of the reviewee. Foremost, self-review addressed the circumstantial and preferential review reasons of the participants. To prove, findings revealed self-review to the very least, is “self-paced”, “accommodates individual differences” as well as “flexible”.

✓ “Unaided”

Not having a guide nor a syllabus, relying on personal resources, and not having support from their schools expectedly make self-review as an unaided review, as aired by the case participants. This characteristic of self-review was found to have an advantage as well as a disadvantage. It was an advantage as it allowed review strategies to be “tailor-fit” to personal review needs and style of the reviewee, as well as a disadvantage as no one guided nor assisted the participants.

✓ *Self-review helps increase sense of self-efficacy.*

There was a chorus of responses among the self-reviewees that self-review made them feel that in their own ways and capacity, they can accomplish something on their own. Responses such as “I proved to myself”, “without help”, “anything is possible”, “I applied it in...” “I can do whatever task is given to me as long as I put my heart on it” were some of the responses.

These findings, taken together, while only a representative few and cannot be generalized, suggest a confirmable probability that those who have tried to self-review and eventually passed the licensure could have preference in constructive strategies, preference in solitary over outgoing activities, and have strong academic background to make them confident that they have a chance in passing on their own.

Before proceeding to the review strategies used by these board passers, let’s take a look at what they have to say about their self-review experience. Here are some verbatim responses:

1. *“For me, self-review is like giving oneself freedom. You control your own destiny, creating study schedules and gathering study materials. If you slack off from studying, you have no one to blame but yourself” (Ms. NurseK).*
2. *“Self-review for me is an interesting experience. It saves time because I get to concentrate on the topics that I don’t really know rather than going to a center that goes over all the topics. Plus I can adjust everything to fit my study schedule rather than adjusting to a review center’s schedule” (Ms. NurseL).*
3. *“I was already decided to take the board exam. Before I started to work, we had an in house review for about a week to give us updates, share information, and so I attended that. After that, I was on my own...Then I told myself that as long as I haven't passed the board exam, I won't have a right to communicate or go to our school because, of course, I was ashamed. I felt that I would be the only one who did not attend a review center, and so I was the only one who had a*

- chance not to pass. I was the only one who did not enroll in a review center, and knowing that my school is one of the top schools in Manila in the lower bracket. I had low self-esteem back then because I felt that I will be their only failing student. So I did not go to school, I was alone. No communication with anyone else even with my classmates. I was really on my own" (Mr. NurseO).
4. "It was very challenging in terms of time management and resources because I had a job"(Mr. NurseMM)
 5. I didn't have a choice but to self-review" (Mr. NurseO).
 6. "...And so it was our first day, Monday. All papers were still blank and then it was my turn, Monday, because we were five and I was assigned on Monday. 'Oh, this is what I'll teach you, Pharmacology!' I remarked. On every wall, there was someone assigned to write...It was better when we did it ourselves, because it was fun...We were like playing! (Ms. NurseG).
 7. "A vacant space in the room. The books, the pencils, and papers were at the center. Around the room were manila papers posted... When you enter the room, you'll see everything. The posts had big characters... the laboratory values... Every now and then, topics on the wall were replaced...Then there was a white board with a marker. The whiteboard had the list of the scheduled presenters. We were five. Each subject had someone who acted as a professor...The place served as our study room" (Ms. NurseG).
 8. "I am satisfied because the intention was just to pass. Whether I pass or not, I didn't even expect that I'll get more than 80% rating. Even if I reviewed, I was not 100% hopeful that I will pass. I left a room for doubt; a small 20% room for doubt" (Mr. NurseR).
 9. "Yes, because when I was studying, even if I didn't have to study for long hours, a short time of two hours that I allot in the morning, or two hours for example, my focus was really there. I really absorbed what I was studying. When I was taking the exam, during the day of exam, I was really focused. There was nothing in my mind but to take the exam" (Mr. NurseR).
 10. "That was August and we had pre-review. We had prayer-fasting at our church which ran for a month. It was like a sacrifice. I was already reviewing at dawn, and I still go to the morning devotion at our church from 4:30 to 6 AM. So after the prayer I would go straight to our school. That time I already built a deeper faith with God, because I also accompany my review with prayer. You can call it a sacrifice... It was really a sacrifice. Actually, my body got used to the less sleep, more on long review. Because I prayed" (Ms. NurseE).
 11. "I learned from my friends the mnemonics of the drugs (a really great help!!!) the delusion of grandeur, bipolar, schizo, a lot of terms to learn, but with the help of my friends it was fun because we would make fun of each other and relate the terms to ourselves (ex. histrionic) "(Ms. NurseL).
 12. And the moment he found out from his neighbor that he passed, he remarked "I slipped from the stairs!" (Mr. NurseR), and he started laughing.
 13. "I cried on the bus. My name was in the list! Our school got a 100% rating...I was proud. My self-confidence was boosted. I could now enter the school premises with pride...I saw my parents very proud of me...My parents hang a big tarpaulin bearing my name at our house and the high school where I studied at...During that time, our finances were already okay. There was just really a late payment with my dad's client at the time" (Mr. NurseO).
 14. "Like what I was telling you earlier...I felt my uncle became proud of me too because he attended my 'thanks giving party'. It's like, of all the graduations that I had, that was the only time that I asked for a celebration. He attended my party, and I saw him proud of me. I'm proud that I was able to do it. When I passed, if there was someone who can be a bigheaded, I could, because I was not someone who just passed, I got a good rating. I became proud" (Ms. NurseE).

15. *"I knew I already gave everything...focus, all of them. When I was already reviewing back then, I gave all of me" (Ms. NurseE).*

At this juncture, we ask: **What review strategies and techniques, if any, helped them pass the P.N.L.E.?** The analysis of multiple cases of 11 successful self-reviewees provides fourteen Self-review Strategies collectively present at various paces of the participants' review.

The study revealed that a self-reviewee board passer:

✓ 1. **Conducts self-analysis.**

Realizing the limited timeframe between graduation and the day of licensure exam, conducting a self-analysis helped participants tailor their review schedule to the subjects that they really needed more attention with. Those that did not do so failed to cover all of the topics even a day prior to the exam.

✓ 2. **Picks a strategy that best fits his/her learning style and study needs.**

Evident in the responses of the seven main participants who were interviewed were differences in review strategies, but all of them shared their review strategies were tailored on their existing learning style, review strategies during college and review needs and circumstance at the time.

✓ 3. **Prioritizes and manages his/her weak areas.**

Findings revealed that ten out of eleven participants prioritized their weakest subjects/ areas first in consideration to the duration of their review as against the date of the licensure and pressed urgency to finish those that needed more time reviewing and those that they still were weak at.

✓ 4. **Organizes his/her topics to review.**

Organizing topics coincides with prioritizing and managing the weak areas first and there were two variations as to how the participants did it: First, by plotting a review timeline complete with list of topics to cover in their review, and second was to create a review calendar without a timeline. While all had their review calendars, noteworthy were those two participants (Ms. NurseG and Mr. NurseR) who challenged having a timeline for each subjects as they prioritized "understanding" vs. "completing" their topics. Upon further validation, however, while both emphasized quality vs. quantity, they nonetheless completed their review calendar as they started right on time to complete all topics listed.

✓ 5. Tailors his/her review duration and frequency based on his/her review needs.

On the negative side, those that did not set a timetable without a bargain of a longer review duration seemed to have crammed. Those were the lessons shared by Mr. NurseN, Mr. NurseJ and Ms. NurseL, all of whom had time constraints. Mr. NurseN hid his review from his classmates and acquaintances and to make it believable, he had to go out with them more often than he wanted to, thereby, compromising his review schedule. Ms. NurseL, on the other hand, was studying Medicine at the time and so she just did not have enough time to finish her review schedule right on time, and Mr. NurseJ reportedly took the licensure to “have a feel” and since he was working at the time, only reviewed for two days. Meanwhile, participants took the time to pause, or take a break to “relax” and “re-energize”, as some would say. Their experience, as compared with those who completed their respective review timelines and calendar point to the need to tailor the review duration and frequency based on individual review needs.

✓ 6. Finds his/her right venue.

While majority reviewed at home, not all did, and all had their preferred place or area to study at. Common themes, however, were found such as place being “secluded, quiet, no disturbance, personally and ergonomically comfortable, well ventilated, and private” emanated from their choices of venue.

✓ 7. Gets a good review material.

Two participants gave strong opinion on using textbooks in reviewing instead of reviewing through traditional review materials. While participants used different review materials, findings suggest that review materials must be “latest”, “complete”, “reliable”, and must trickle down to “simpler explanations” for better grasp of the topics in the licensure exam.

✓ 8. Maximizes help from other people and exhausts available resources.

Self-review being “unaided” has to be coupled with maximizing available help and resources. Such was one of the findings that was revealed. From review materials acquisition, boosting each other’s morale, up to asking for pieces of advice and tips in the licensure, participants were found to be resourceful in those aspects.

✓ 9. Is receptive

Participant Ms. NurseE purportedly found this helpful in two ways: first, she mentioned that her friend advised her to be aware of health related current events, which she did. She claimed that current health issues at the time such as AH1N1 virus did appear in the licensure exam during her time. Second was about being receptive with the usual type and topics of the exams given in their in-house review. She underscored being sensitive to those as a way to be up-to-date downsizing the self-review being unaided.

✓ 10. Inclusive, comprehensive and integrates other topics when reviewing.

Mr. NurseMM, mentioned for instance, “Before the review- 10- I thought I covered everything. After the review- 8- after the exam there were questions that were very tricky...” (MM36). Same thing happened to Mr. NurseO as he focused more on Medical-Surgical Nursing, but missed on Community Health Nursing (CHN) and so he got the lowest rating in CHN. In hindsight, he said it could have been better if he studied CHN more intently. Conversely, positive portrayal of inclusivity, for example, was found through Mr. NurseR wherein even if he did not like memorizing topics, he still went ahead and did it, only that he pictured out the laboratory values as a table and did a mental image, and then he would relate the questions against the values in the table and how they were arranged in the table.

✓ 11. Executes the strategy precisely, but flexible in containing shortcomings.

In order to carry out what was planned, like the review timeline and review calendar, findings showed that correct execution is necessary. Ms. NurseE, for instance, would “stick to the plan” and, if she had shortcomings, would catch up and penalize herself by extending extra time, or skipping her nap time to cover topics she missed.

✓ 12. Incorporates test-taking and review strategies.

As in any test, the case participants also had various test-taking strategies, and they reportedly used them when they were still studying as well as on the day of the licensure exam itself. Test strategies such as “elimination”, “select all that apply” and “the longest option being the right answer (or the umbrella technique) were mentioned to the least. Being analytical, concepts association, rooting it from the basics, finding connections and preferences in constructive

learning helped as claimed by the participants. There was emphasis on constructive strategies as found in the actual licensure exam being scenario or situation-based questions.

✓ 13. Implements quality-control measures.

Quality control was achieved in four ways: first, through “self-testing”. Like what was expected, participants did self-testing and self-testing was done through Q & A, pre and posttest after each topic, using the compilation of licensure exam questions and bring home assessment, to name a few. As Mr. NurseJ remarked, they served to “recall” topics when faced with the same in the licensure. Second measure was by following through on missed target like what Ms. NurseE did when she missed a topic because of oversleeping. Third was by double checking answers just like what Mr. NurseR did. When he spots a keyword on an answer, he mentioned that he did not hastily pick that option as his answer. He would double check to make sure before answering. Mr. NurseO, for his part, put the answer of his handbook on trial by checking against other references especially when “in doubt”. Finally, by having a standard of reference. Ms. NurseG, for example, stated that they measured what they knew against their classmate whom they consider intelligent. Ms. NurseE, similarly used self-testing as a standard of reference. When the time came when she was already getting correct answers on practice tests, it was then that she felt she already had enough.

✓ 14. Successfully pacifies his/her worries.

Participants undeniably felt anxiety, pressure, and even fear of failure and while inevitable, the participants shared ways on how they reportedly coped with such strong feelings. Ms. NurseE acknowledged the existence of fears as well as positive diversion to reassess and brace herself up. In addition, Ms. NurseE, Mr. NurseN and Mr. NurseR reported having low expectations in the results to cope with untoward feelings. Most of them just prayed and hoped they will pass, and Mr. NurseO further mentioned constantly reassuring himself that he was prepared well by his school and that whatever those who passed knew, he also knew of them.

Self-review Models

Presented below are the seven self-review models of the case participants along with their self-made review strategies.

1. "Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach"

Mr. NurseR designed his review without a timeline. He says what was important was that he understood the topic. He asserts that timelines are what he hates most, and the reason why he did not enroll in a review center as he did not want any constraints. If he has a space for him to finish the review, then he would as he has focus on what he is doing. His reasoning was that if he will not be able to cover all of the topics, at least those that he did cover, he is sure that he was able to study them thoroughly.

Mr. NurseR's review ran from April to June (two months). He says he usually started his review with an exercise in the morning and reviews from either seven or eight up to eleven in the morning with breaks in between. He did those in their store as he was asked to watch over their store at the time. After lunch, he would continue reviewing until 3 PM, would take a break, then would resume before he slept at night. He says he did that every day except on Sundays. On Sundays, he only reviewed from 1-4 PM. Meanwhile, he says that if he could not understand a topic, he would stop as nothing will enter into his brain. His view was that a reviewer should not review when he no longer understands as it will not be effective. He has to stop, do something else and may have to go back onto it at a later time. Depending on what he was studying, he says he would create a diagram out of it, something simpler. If there was a diagram in the book, he would still make it simpler than what the book has and would try to re-write a summary or the essence out of the diagram on a piece of paper, although he says not all of the topics—only those topics that he was confused of. He would get the essence and re-write at the back of the paper without looking the way he understood the topic.

The way he strategized his review was in line with his learning style. He says he practiced “situational” questions, and that he needed to see the concept from the context of a situation. To illustrate, he says if one would tell him the difference between the definitions of “malpractice” and “negligence” he will not be able to easily tell the difference. Give him a situation and he would easily be able to differentiate them. Similarly, with Medical-Surgical, Pediatric, Psychiatric Nursing subjects, he liked to study them with cases, and with situational problems so that he could analyze what is happening and then he would integrate the others. He would start his review with situational questions and if he gets confused, then he will read the definition. As he writes his own diagram, he would imagine the diagram and relate the figures as applied on the situation. The way he described it, he says “it’s like connect the dots”. As he went on studying, he would observe some labels or keywords, although he says that even if he sees those keywords, he would still double check with the question. He would not answer right away, unless he is really sure that it is the right answer.

2 *Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach*

Mr. NurseN started sharing his review strategy by saying that the moment he graduated, he already planned to create his own reviewer. He bought a notebook and he would read his books in college and make a summary in his notebook. He claims he already had like 20% of preparation even if he was not yet sure he would take exam. He says he collated licensure reviewers, although

was not able to use them as he preferred using his textbooks in college. He reasons that while studying from textbooks will be a lot of work, it yields better results and you will learn more from them instead of using standard reviewers.

The way he designed his personal reviewer was like commercial review materials, though. He wrote them by system, and by topic. When he was already doing the teach-back to his classmates, he would take what he will discuss from his notebook, and use a blank paper and while explaining he would draw and illustrate them on the blank paper. He says he intentionally did it on a blank paper so he will be forced to recall what he wrote on his notebook-reviewer. He designed his notebook-reviewer patterned on how he wanted to explain the topics to his classmates. He recounts, “That was my strategy, I guess that was the core strategy that I was able

to make. I had a lesson plan, I explained it to myself, and I knew how to explain this and that...and when I was already in front of my classmates..." He would explain the topics while he writes on a blank paper, do the illustrations and would give the paper with his write ups to his classmates afterwards. He emphasized going back to the basics, using logic. During the interview, he gave some examples on how he defines "basics". He says "In general, you know the basic concept...for example, in Medical Surgical, you should know the blood flow, the anatomy" and then he would analyze a disease based on the basic concepts and then integrate the others. When asked how he filtered a semester long of topic into a notebook reviewer, he says "...somehow you already know what's written there... you would just put them back to your brain." When he was not reviewing his classmates, he would read on his own at home; most of the time on their rooftop.

3 *Ms. NurseG's "The Combo Approach" a.k.a. "The Vacant Room"*

Ms. NurseG's review strategy was a combination of group review and self-review. As what has been presented earlier, the highlight was the group review. With group review, they had some safeguards. She says they would not start when someone is missing, and the facilitator (presenter) must be knowledgeable on the topic. Initially, they used fish bowl to choose whoever will be the presenter, but said they had a problem with it as sometimes the presenter may not be well versed on the topic. As a presenter, the intention was to tinker each and everyone's stock knowledge. For example, she narrates, if she gives a drug she would ask the group of the indications, etc. and so prior reading of the topic was important. She says "...you should've read, as you will be asked...you're all like reciting." What happened was that it became brainstorming. Once the presenter asks the group, the presenter will be responsible to expound on the topic and then will integrate other topics related to the topic at hand until they reach the point wherein they would tackle the associated disease condition of that topic. The review itself was done from 8-5 PM and they did it from the first week of April until June. Concurrent with group review was self-review at home. As she already had a study habit while in college, she did her self-review from 2-5 AM. She did it as she already estimated what will be covered in group review and what other topics she had to focus on. She had a calendar of review activities at home and once done would tick 'yes'. She studied in her room and the way she designed her room was like their review venue with the group. She says there were paraphernalia posted around even in their restroom.

When it comes to review materials, what they used were their college textbooks plus they would photocopy some other reviewers when they thought can be useful. As a measure of effectiveness, they bought a compilation of board exam questions and they would answer them at home. The following day, they would discuss them together towards the end of the day. She mentioned that it had to be done towards the end of the day so as not to cause information overload at the start. She reasons that at least even when their brains get stretched toward the end of the day, they would have learned the topics discussed prior to that. When asked if they had a standard on their readiness to take the exam, she said that they compared themselves with their bright classmate. She said “...if she knows this, we should know it, too. It shouldn’t be that she knows it and we don’t”.

4 *Mr. NurseJ's Recalling Approach*

It was two days of review. **Mr. NurseJ** says he reviewed in two out of three days of his leave and on the third day, he used it to rest at home. As he was working at the time, he took the exam a year after he graduated and remarked “it was still fresh”. Prior to his review, he says that he gathered all his notes as he is more of an OC (Obsessive-Compulsive). Acknowledging the difficulty of what he was facing, he stated that even in those two days, he had a timeline. He

reasons that in his four years of college, in the results of his exams, he knew his weaknesses and so he focused on them. To illustrate, he asserts that in Fundamentals of Nursing, in a count of ten, ten being the highest, he would rate himself as eight or nine, so he did not review it any longer. On Maternal & Child and Medical Surgical Nursing, however, there he struggled and so he gave more focus on them. He focused on the basics and nursing actions. He reasons that 'nursing is caring'. He would still remember his topics and accounts them more on his learning style and says that they would just pop up in his mind.

His notes helped as they were summarized the way he would be able to easily recall them. It was in line with his learning style that he would ask questions as he reminded the researcher that he had memories as "...every day is meaningful to me" and that "if it's meaningful, you would remember it", and since something meaningful happened, and he also wrote it down, same thing happened when he was studying his notes. He says it was more on "recalling", and that post tests after review helps the recalling process. During the actual exam, he says that he used the test taking strategy of "elimination" and that he would always leave two possible correct answer for that particular question and that there he would start to rationalize with his stock knowledge and experience before picking an answer. While he was only partly able to do it due to time constraints, he outlined what, in his view, is an ideal self-review: "...one must identify his weaknesses first, after such is to come up with a timeframe. Of course, you know where you're

weak at. You know your personal abilities, how fast you're able to absorb a subject matter. After identifying your weaknesses, only then you'd be able to come up with a time line".

5 *Mr. NurseB's "Traditional Q & A Approach"*

Mr. NurseB said that what he did in his review was that he used a book-reviewer where he would read the topic first and then there would be 10-15 questions after every topic. He stated that he prioritized the subjects that he was having most difficulty with. The other reviewer he had (same author) was a pure Q & A questions. If the topics were not in his primary reviewer, then he would use the hand-outs and materials he acquired from his school. He would usually start his review at home at their dining table, which the family was using as their study table from 8-9 AM until 12 noon, then he would start again at 2 PM until the afternoon. At night, he would stay from 7-8 PM until 12 midnight; 1 AM being the latest. That ran from Monday to Sunday, although sometimes he said that there were some interruptions.

At home, only his mother and father were around so he was able to read alone. He would read a topic in his book-reviewer, take sample questions, and then check the answers and the rationale

afterwards. In other words, from the book, he applied what he read on the test questions. He says he also used that strategy when he passed his NCLEX-RN®. When reviewing, he claimed he would not eat at the same time. When felt hungry, he would just go to the kitchen to eat. He used to listen to Japanese music to relax and re-energize. He used testing strategies such as elimination, the longest word, etc. that he learned in school although he cautioned that one should still read the questions to be sure. He advised to get the latest, and reliable review materials complete with topics and then read the topics first then do the Q & A and the rationale. He expressed that his review consisted of test taking strategies and his prior knowledge. He also said that when he answered a question, that served as his final answer. He would not go back to check to save time and prevent any confusion as too much brooding may just lead to an incorrect answer.

6 *Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach*

Mr. NurseO's review strategy was an espousal of his study style when he was still in college. He said he believes in the power of writing and takes time to write down questions and answers on a yellow pad or bond paper [normally about 5 pages per subject and that he would memorize as he writes them down to aid recall. Once his self-made reviewer was done, he would run the Q & A again and check how he fared. The questions would come from his notes in college which consists of, for example, definition of terms and then he would brainstorm whatever he would remember about that topic. When asked how he compressed a topic of one semester into a 5 page reviewer, he says that as a student he knows what important details to include and that his college notes had special marks, extra notations, highlights and so those were what he would write down. Afterwards, he used a standard Q & A reviewer (a pocketbook-like of reviewer) to check for his understanding. The bulk of his review were spent on Q & A using his Q & A reviewer. After he answers a question, he would check the answer and rationale at the back of the reviewer. If he answered wrong, he would dig deeper why his answer was wrong as against the answer of the reviewer. He recounts that he would recheck his answer most especially if he was confident that he answered the right one, but got it wrong. He would assume that the answer of the reviewer is wrong, would critique the answer, and check other references to investigate. When at work, he reviewed during breaks and/or lunches after he ate, and when he arrived home, he would spend an hour or two reviewing. When he was not at work, he says he would review on a study table at home, in a quiet place, with good ventilation, where his brain can function well.

He says he starts his review upon waking up while the brain is still 'absorbent'. He reviewed from the basics although he focused on 3rd and 4th year subjects. His review ran from April after he graduated until a couple of days before the board exam and that 60% of it was spent on Medical Surgical Nursing. The rest were spent on other subjects and those that he thought will appear in the board exam. As he was working at the same time, his way of relaxation was to sleep and that whenever he had an idle time, he would sit and review. In his words, "...instead of going out and having fun, me I was reviewing". A week before the exam, he extended his review hours and reviewed during his breaks, lunches, once he arrived home, and even said that he would even review while eating his breakfast and on his way to work.

Despite his efforts, Mr. NurseO did not escape from fear of failure. He says the very crucial part was after he took the exam and airs that "it is the waiting that kills" as he was clueless. There were some recollections as to why he answered this and that. To help him cope with that feeling, he says he prayed every day and made himself busy with work so as not to entertain thoughts about the result of the exam.

7 *Ms. NurseE's "Textbook Approach"*

Ms. NurseE claims that even before she graduated, she already had a study habit of reviewing at midnight. Once she arrives home from school, she would sleep until midnight, wake up around 12 and then study until 4 AM and would sleep again until 6 AM before going to school. That became her study habit. She already started reviewing on her own at the time concurrent to their in-house review at school. By the time that she graduated, as mentioned on the precipitating circumstance earlier, she was already decided to self-review. So she created a calendar of review activities for the day, for the week, and prioritized her most difficult subjects to the least difficult ones. She says she focused on the most difficult subjects as she felt that they are the areas that she still had more to study on. She says that with her review, she used a textbook like of reviewer and just used other reviewers for references or if there were techniques that she can use such as mnemonics. She would look at them, but she claimed she did not read them. She says that when she writes and summarizes the topics, she will just put the root-words highlighted, but when reviewing, she prefers detailed reviewers so she can understand them. Once done reviewing on a topic, she would take the end-of-chapter assessment. The questions and answers on her reviewer were separate, and so she stressed that she could not cheat. She would not read the answers and rationale as of yet and would mimic the actual board exam. Whenever she gets a wrong answer, she would just remember the answer and rationale and would not go back to it later as it might just confuse her more as she already started reviewing other topics. Whenever there were some

delays, she would make it up to meet her target review activities. If she had to take a nap that day, she would skip the nap so she can catch up on that subject.

In between her review was their pre-board exam and she said she failed on the exam. In her words, "...my review was not effective" and calls it as her assessment. But that did not discourage her, though, as she said she thought that she just had to study more as she noted the questions on their pre-board exam. Ms. NurseE was receptive to the common questions on their exams. She said she would notice that those topics would appear more often, and so she studied them including their nursing management, signs and symptoms, etc. and those topics that she was not sure of. She said "...there I failed, and so there I focused". In addition, she says that her school made them sensitive to the board of examiners that would craft the board exam that time and so she focused on them, too. Moreover, there were trending health conditions at the time that she had to particularly be attentive to. She says "...it was AH1N1 back then...and the gas mask".

A closer look: What do they mean?

The reader may already have noticed that each review strategy that they have used, as shown and depicted in the self-review flow charts created, are tailored with the way they learn best and are bounded by their circumstantial and preferential self-review reasons. Below is a table that shows how the data could be interpreted showing their self-review strategies as tailor-fit to reviewees' learning style and study needs:

Self-review Reason	Self-review Strategy
<i>Preferential</i>	Mr. NurseR's Diagram Approach
	Ms. NurseE's Textbook Approach
	Mr. NurseJ's Recalling Approach
	Mr. NurseB's Traditional Q & A Approach
	Mr. NurseO's "Self-made Q & A Reviewer" Approach
<i>Circumstantial</i>	Mr. NurseN's Blank Paper Approach
	Ms. NurseG's Vacant Space: the Combo Approach

Pushed by varied preferential and/or circumstantial self-review reasons, the experience of self-review itself, being "unaided", sprang different self-review approaches. The circumstances, through self-review reasons, which these self-reviewees were in born creative and tailor-fit strategies based on their learning beliefs, style, and approaches and the way they thought they would learn best at the time. For instance, Mr. NurseR learns best when concepts are made "simpler" and put into diagram and when he sees the concepts in the context of situations and so that is how he reviewed. Similarly, Ms. NurseE learns best when there are detailed explanations so she used textbooks when self-reviewing. Same was true to Mr. NurseJ, Mr. NurseB, and Mr. NurseO. They have their respective stories and justifications. Conversely, Mr. NurseN and Ms. NurseG's review strategies can be considered incidental, or mixed type. Mr. NurseN took advantage of his classmate's situation and did his review with them. It does not mean, however, that he did not incorporate his learning approaches. On the contrary, his "Blank Paper Approach" suited the way he learns through "logic" and rooting from the basics. Further, Ms. NurseG, who was also challenged like Mr. NurseN, maximized the situation they were in when they reviewed in a vacant space (room) while reviewing at home. The fact that all of them used different review strategies mean that self-review accommodates, regardless of the declared reason, individual differences and review needs of the reviewees. And, since they were successful and eventually passed, the experience translated to increase in self-efficacy.

The Present Understanding: "What do they say...?"

We quickly glance at the extant literature on the present understanding on review strategies.

Individual Study Strategy Differences Exist

Not all students report using the same strategies—like learning styles, individual differences also exist between students with regard to their study habits (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012). Theories of Self-regulated Learning (SRL) claim that learners use a variety of strategies to achieve their learning goals, and that the quality of strategy use should be related to performance (e.g., Winne & Hadwin, 1998; Dunlosky & Metcalfe, 2009). To support that notion, studies have shown unique differences between high- and low-achieving students in the specific strategies they engage in to achieve academically (Zimmerman & Martinez-Pons, 1990). According to Ormrod (2004), processes or strategies employed by a learner while studying influences how the information is stored and later retrieved.

Below are some quantitative studies and their results:

Concept	Significant results
Self-testing	✓Self-testing has been demonstrated to be quite effective and can boost student learning (Roediger & Butler, 2011).
Self-testing	✓Self-testing by recalling the target information boosts performance on subsequent recall and multiple choice tests of the target information, and it also boosts performance on tests of comprehension (Roediger & Butler, 2011; Roediger & Karpicke, 2006; Rawson & Dunlosky, 2011).
Self-testing and Time management	✓Stronger predictors of academic performance than aptitude (West & Sadoski, 2011)
Self-testing and rereading	✓Both positively associated with GPA (Grade Point Average) (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012)
Self-testing & spacing	✓Self-testing (vs. restudying) or spacing study (vs. massing study)—are likely to enhance learning (Kornell & Bjork, 2007; McCabe, 2011).
Caution about Self-testing	✓Self-testing (which was related to GPA) can be used ineffectively, such as when students test themselves by evaluating their familiarity with a concept without trying to recall it from memory (Dunlosky, Rawson, & Middleton, 2005).
Cramming	✓Spacing study (vs. cramming) were not significantly related to GPA, even though spaced (vs. massed) practice is known to have a major impact on retention (Cepeda, Pashler, Vul, Wixted, & Rohrer, 2006).

Cramming	✓Cramming the night (and immediately) before an exam might support relatively good exam performance, even though students who use this strategy might remember little of the content even a short time after the exam (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).
Outlines, Collaborative Learning, Use of Diagrams	✓The reported use of outlines and collaborative learning demonstrated slightly negative relationships, and the use of diagrams and highlighting were not significantly related to GPA (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).
Highlighting Texts	✓Students' use of highlighting has been shown to yield mixed results, depending on the skill of the user (e.g., Bell & Limber, 2010; Fowler & Barker, 1974).
Scheduling	✓Differences in scheduling did arise between the highest and lowest achievers, with the lower achievers focusing (a) more on impending deadlines, (b) more on studying late at night, and (c) almost never on planning their study time (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).
Scheduling	✓High performers are more likely to schedule their study ahead of time (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).
Re-reading	✓When used correctly, it can boost retention and performance (e.g., Rawson & Kintsch, 2005), and the present rereading–GPA relationship may in part arise from students who read (a lot) versus those who do not read (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012).
Time of Day	✓Lowest performers are most likely to engage in late-night studying (Hartwig & Dunlosky, 2012). Afternoon and evening studying would better match college students' peak diurnal rhythms (May, Hasher, & Stoltzfus, 1993), and hence might be related to GPA.

Self-reported traits of a Self-reviewee Board Passer

And so now we turn our attention to the question “*What are the self-reported traits that were significant to the review of these successful self-reviewees?*”

Three self-reported traits came on top of the list: self-confidence, self-discipline, and determination.

✓ *Self-confidence.*

Responses from six participants revealed that self-confidence is needed in self-review as well as a positive outcome of self-review. Mr. NurseJ, for instance, managed the feeling of the risk of failure with strong self-confidence; a trait that he already developed within him for some time. As a result of what they did, both he and Ms. NurseK claimed that self-review boosted their confidence. Self-review strengthened and boosted their self-confidence and efficacy.

✓ *Self-discipline.*

Closely related to self-confidence is self-discipline, and the responses revealed self-discipline as a reported cause of success of the self-review as well as an acquired trait as a result of that success. Evident in the words of Ms. NurseK was the role of self-discipline: “For me, it’s all about discipline. If you don’t instill discipline in yourself and just slack off then self-review would not be effective” and even Mr. NurseN, learning his lesson when he was not able to finish his review schedule due to distractions, affirmed the importance of discipline in self-review. Likewise, both Ms. NurseK and Mr. NurseMM agreed self-review taught them the art of discipline. In the end, Ms. NurseK said, “Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline”.

✓ *Determination.*

Appearing third is the trait for determination, and this key trait liaised other positive traits such as diligence, spirituality, and focus to drive the case participants to finish their review program and ultimately pass the licensure exam. And, determination was not only shown in determination to pass, but also determination to finish self-review and ultimately become a Registered Nurse. Some other self-reported traits of the case participants that were identified were spirituality, curiosity, diligence, patience, stubbornness, and of course resourcefulness.

Here are some responses as regards participants’ self-reported traits:

1. *“Yes, because when I was studying, even if I didn't have to study for long hours, a short time of two hours that I allot in the morning, or two hours for example, my focus was really there. I really absorbed what I was studying. When I was taking the exam, during the day of exam, I was really focused. There was nothing in my mind but to take the exam” (Mr. NurseR).*

2. *"I think number one is trust in God as "...you can do it because he trusts you, that's the number one. Maybe it will be followed by trust in yourself, your ability to trust yourself. I don't have anyone to trust, anyway. I will still be the one to do it. The task will still come from me so you just have to trust what you do" (Mr. NurseN).*
3. *"Discipline. Because it is hard to discipline yourself especially if you'll self-review. It's hard to discipline yourself, it's hard to control yourself not to go out just like what I said" (Mr. NurseN).*
4. *"I had self-discipline. It was self-discipline. I would attend the review even if I was sleepy. When we had the group review, it's not that you left for home at 5 PM you'll arrive home right away, sometimes you would go out. Sometimes, you still have other friends that will ask you out and of course you can't say no. So it's like you'll go to the dorm like that, that you're intoxicated" (Ms. NurseG).*
5. *"Hunger for wisdom... even when we were still students, I would ask 'what is this for? What's his name?' The doctors were like annoyed with me because I asked a lot" ... "I was called 'Ms. Bakit'. And then she remarked, "And why would that happen? That's curiosity" (Ms. NurseG).*
6. *"That was August and we had pre-review. We had prayer-fasting at our church which ran for a month. It was like a sacrifice. I was already reviewing at dawn, and I still go to the morning devotion at our church from 4:30 to 6 AM. So after the prayer I would go straight to our school. That time I already built a deeper faith with God, because I also accompany my review with prayer. It can be called a sacrifice". It was really a sacrifice. Actually, my body got used to the less sleep, more on long review. Because I prayed "(Ms. NurseE).*
7. *"With regard to my studies, I am focused. I don't waste every single time. I am not intelligent, but I am hardworking. I remember what my teacher in the C.A.T. said, that I get my achievement all by myself, because he said I'm hardworking. That I may not be a brainy student that I'll be on top of the class, but I'm able to achieve something" (Ms. NurseE).*
8. *"And she has some interesting thoughts to other reviewees: I hope that he/she will also be diligent. It's because I believe that in the board exam, not only the brainy examinees pass the board exam. Because I also see other intelligent examinees fail. Therefore, those that are diligent in studying are the ones who excel in the board exam. It's regrettable... because you've already exerted an effort -why not push harder? You've already graduated...the board exam is just months away, and it's hard if you keep on taking it over again. Take this opportunity... just a onetime difficulty. And it's a disgrace to your parents... if it is money matters. I'm just fortunate that my school offered a free review, what if they did not? What if your parents don't have the capacity to support your review? (Ms. NurseE).*
9. *"Maybe my trait is that I am an optimistic person. In all that I do, I know that the outcome will turn out good. If ever that it turns out bad, or it was not what I expected, just like what I told you I have faith. So whatever happens, there's a purpose. The outcome that I know of is the outcome that I desired for, but of course we can't get all things. So that I won't feel regrets, I just think that it's the will of God" (Mr. NurseJ).*
10. *"Even if I initially thought that I only wanted to know how the board exam works, my pride was still there that I will pass. Two days of review, you still have that pride that "I can do this!" So I still really exerted an effort. I am not even saying that I only passed because I relied on my memory. I really exerted an effort..." (Mr. NurseJ).*
11. *"I get what you're saying. Maybe it depends on what will I be doing, on what will I be preparing for. The board exam is do or die. I am a person who has a high pride, so it's a lot. My pride is at stake. And I did not review, it's what at stake. Like I've also worked hard for it. Like in two days, I deserved to pass for those two days" (Mr. NurseJ).*

12. *"It is about perseverance... the mentality of not giving up; that there's still hope. Another is trust in your instinct, as there are times when you don't trust yourself when in fact it was already the right answer, and don't brood on too much on simple things "* (Mr. NurseB).
13. *"I consider myself as the least intellectual among my siblings, but the best trait I have is that when I start on something, I will complete it, so I am very diligent. Maybe my family thought that I can make it; maybe it's more of trust and confidence from my parents. Whatever I wanted, they just supported me"* (Mr. NurseO).
14. *"Determination"--of course from the very start I already set a goal that I needed to pass. I shouldn't be an outcast from my batch. Another is 'perseverance'- I thought that there are other nurses who passed through self-review, so I thought that whatever they know, I must also know..."(O189). "I thought that I studied for four years, my parents spent money for me, it will be impossible that I didn't learn anything, or it's impossible that we didn't touch on them in college. Aside from that, there was the power of prayer, it gave me hope. My own knowledge and coming from above" (N144). Finally "...hard work" it really boils down to hard work because you can't achieve anything if you won't work hard for it. It's like there's nothing that is easy to achieve. All are earned through hard work"* (Mr. NurseO).

Self-review in the eyes of the participants

Below were the responses to the question: **"If you can put your entire review experience in a statement, what would it be?"**

1. Mr. NurseR: *"Slow paced". "I relish what I was studying, I did it slowly, no pressure. I told myself that the exam is still far ahead. And so at least I still had the time to take things slowly, and if there was something I couldn't understand, I can skip it, then I'll go back to it brand new, or if I was really curious to know what that was, or why was it like that, then I would research."*

"It's slow paced because when I was reviewing, it was not continuous, not like I'll spend the whole day just reviewing. No. I would read in the morning, I'll do something else at noon, I'll read a bit, then read in the afternoon until night time. I didn't do it continuously, I went back to it."

2. Mr. NurseN: *"It was challenging"*
"Because before you take the exam, you don't know what's going to appear in the exam. And there's this part that I have acquaintances that were in a review center and they didn't know that I would take the exam. I would overhear them discuss this and that; topic they've discussed in the review center, and I knew I didn't know them yet!"

"I didn't know they existed and they were saying that based from their review center, they will appear in the exam. And when you hear those things that you've only heard for the first time, they will make you feel paranoid."

3. Ms. NurseE: *"The Best". People's impression is different once they found out that you only self-reviewed. There's a different imprint on people if they found out you reviewed on your own and passed."*
4. Ms. NurseG: *"Challenging." "It was challenging, and for me I like it when I'm challenged. There's this "thrill" and I like it when I'm thrilled. If you pass the board exam without the help of others, it's also like you found a job without the help of others."*

5. Mr. NurseJ: *"It's difficult". "More than ICU (Intensive Care Unit), dude." "Board exam is do or die. I am a person who has a high pride, so it's a lot. My pride is at stake. And I did not review, it's what at stake. Like I've also worked hard for it. Like in two days, I deserved to pass for those two days."*
6. Mr. NurseO: *"Hard work beats talent when talent does not work hard. Hard work beats Talent. "It really boils down to hard work because you can't achieve anything if you won't work hard for it. It's like there's nothing that is easy to achieve. All are earned through hard work."*
7. Mr. NurseB: *"Fulfilling". I just focused on my review then it was a mystery, it was faith. I asked the Lord to help me choose the right answer. I knew I can do it. I studied well, I did review, I asked Him to help me choose the right answer to the questions that I'll encounter."*
8. Ms. NurseK: *"Truly enriching experience where the impossible became possible through confidence in one's knowledge and capabilities." "Self-review as a whole is a test of discipline."*
9. Ms. NurseL: *"Self-review: Epic! One of those things that you thought you can never do but when you finally did it, it feels like you're Superman and kryptonite can't hold you back."*
10. Mr. NurseMJ: *"It's a great achievement". "Self-review is self-fulfillment".*
11. Mr. NurseMM: *"It was priceless!!"*

Closing notes: To the prospective self-reviewee

Few years ago, I myself embarked on self-review and passed the NLE on my first take. As I look back, I was more of a combination of Messrs. NurseJ, NurseR & NurseN, plus I hopped on places for me not to fall asleep. I was a working-reviewee back then. This study, therefore, has a personal relevance to me, and to you. For one, I was excited that since my study was about those "board passers" whatever the study would produce will be of help, at any rate, to future self-reviewees like you. For sure, the participants in this study agreed to share their stories so you may be able to learn from them. As what case participant Mr. NurseO opined, "Maybe if there was a research such as this before that would serve as my guide, maybe I would've gotten a higher rating..." Such necessity was underscored in the words of participant Mr. NurseR, "If you don't know what you'll cover in your review, you'll lose many things; if you don't know what you're supposed to study". My guess is, if it was not me who conducted this study, then somebody else in the near future will. Mind you, I do not have to endorse self-review to anyone, as if it is meant for the person either by circumstance or preference, then he/she would self-review. Except for Mr. NurseB who was, in some way, convinced by his two sisters to self-review, the eleven of us self-reviewed in our own volition. Of course we were pushed by our respective reasons either preferential or circumstantial, but as mentioned, self-review is only one way of getting the desired output- the "RN" beside our names. There are other ways, of course. However, since the first local board examination in 1919, my calculated guess is that self-review has been used since that time long before review centers were established; and it is also being used until now, and my belief is that it will still be used in the future. The way licensure reviews will be done may evolve in the not so distant future, but I argue that self-review will still remain to be the "default".

With regard to the fourteen self-review strategies and the seven self-review models, I say they are the core message of this manuscript. Be creative on your own based on what will suit

your need and personal signature. For a more detailed discussion of their review strategies, you are welcome to glance at my thesis. In the end, it is only you who can decide for yourself. These are only marks, guides or antecedents of what worked for some. Use them to your advantage, but remember that you can discover your own. As such, I hope that this short manuscript has given you more answers than questions. This was conceived to be that way. I hope it has given you some vigor, if not inspiration. And if I was not successful in relaying the participants' message, then it was only me who screwed up and not them. Lastly, with all the good intentions, good luck. Whoever or wherever you are, I hope to call you soon – “my RN colleague”.